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EDITORIAL NOTE

Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE) is the official Journal of the Faculty of Education, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The Journal publishes article of diverse fields of interest in education. Papers reporting original research and extended version of already established conference and journal articles are welcomed. Papers for publication are selected through peer review process to ensure originality, relevance and readability. ZIJE is published bi-annually June and December.

The aim and scope of the journal is to provide an academic medium and an important reference for the advancement and dissemination of information that supports high level learning, teaching and research in the fields of education.

This edition, Volume 4, Number 4, November, 2024 is poised to present research reports in the following fields of education: Educational Foundations, Science Education, Educational Psychology, Curriculum & Instructional Technology, Guidance & Counselling, Philosophy & History of Education, Sociology of Education, Entrepreneurship Education, Special and Inclusive Education, Physical & Health Education, Religious Education, Gender Studies, Peace & Security Education among others. The articles in this volume are academic and professional discourse written by reputable scholars in their areas of specialization.

The Board remain indebted to its editorial members for the ceaseless support given towards successful publication of the Journal. In the same vein, we acknowledge quite sincerely the assistance and support of our esteemed consulting editors for ensuring the credibility of this edition. Also worthy of appreciation are the authors and their immense contributions to this publication.

Associate Professor Umar Sodangi
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CALL FOR ARTICLES

The Editorial Board of Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE) calls for scholarly articles for review and possible publication in its next edition (Volume 4, Number 5). ZIJE publishes articles that emphasize on research development and application within the field of Education. All manuscripts are reviewed by editorial review committee. Contributions must be original, not previously or simultaneously published elsewhere, and are critically reviewed before they are published. Papers, which must be written in English Language, should have good grammar and proper terminologies. Also note that prospective articles are subjected to plagiarism assessment to estimate the percentage of originality of the papers. Hence, plagiarism threshold of $\leq 20\%$ is recommended.

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1. Manuscripts including references, appendices, tables and diagrams should be double-spaced and single coded on A4 paper with generous margins (at least 1”/2.5cm).
2. Title should be explicit and not more than 19 words.
3. Title page should be arranged as follows: Title, author(s) full name, affiliation, full addresses, email addresses and phone numbers.
4. Abstract should be single line and not more than 250 words.
5. For conceptual papers, the body should have appropriate headings where necessary.
6. For empirical papers, it should be presented in the following order: Introduction, Objectives of the study, Research Questions and/or Hypotheses, Methodology, Results, Discussion of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations.
7. Acknowledgement (if any).
8. Quotations of more than 40 words should be indented and typed single spacing with indication of the pages where the quotes were lifted.
9. In-text citations should follow the APA 7th edition format.
10. References should be in range with 7th edition of APA Style.
11. Each table and figure should be presented within the manuscripts, with a brief and self-explanatory title.
12. All text within the table should be clearly legible, and all graphics and legends should be easily distinguished when printed in black and white.
13. Tables should be in horizontal lines only, with only blank space to separate columns.
14. Tables and figures that may be included in the main text of the paper should be numbered separately, in the sequence that they are mentioned in the text.
15. Figures should be saved in a neutral data format such as JPEG, TIFF or EPS.

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Associate Professor Abubakar Sadiq Haruna

Publication Editor

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Table of Contents

SN	Paper Title and Authors	Page
1	Effect of Outdoor Laboratory Strategy on Attitude and Performance in Ecology Concept among Secondary School Students in Kano State, Nigeria. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601928	1
2	Managing Threats to Internal Validity in Quantitative and Qualitative Research: Some Basic Considerations. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928806	8
3	Correlation between Socio-economic Factors and Productive Human Resource Management among Secondary School Teachers in Oredo Local Government Area, Edo State. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603517	14
4	Assessment of Instructional Resources for Teaching and Learning of Basic Technology Among Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603531	20
5	Comparative Analysis between School-Effectiveness-Variables and Achievement in Quantitative Economics Concepts among Secondary School Students in Osun State, Nigeria. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603539	31
6	Effects of Vee-Diagram Strategy on Achievement and Retention in Gravitation Concept Among Federal College of Education Students, Kano State. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603558	39
7	Qualitative Study on School Based Management Committees in Basic Education Curriculum Development in Nigeria. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603573	49
8	Influence of Gender and School Location on Performance in Agricultural Science among Secondary School Students in Kaduna North, Kaduna State. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603575	56
9	Assessment of E-waste Management on Lifestyle and Environmental Hazards in Schools: A Case Study of Ojo Local Government Area, Lagos State. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603577	65
10	Impact of "Do It" Creativity and Emotional Mastery Strategies on Creativity and Motivation among Adolescents with Special Needs in Oyo State.	74

DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17011451>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603579>

- 11 Qualitative Study on Vocational and Technical Education Programmes in Nigeria: 81
Challenges and Prospects.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603583>
- 12 Assessment of Indiscipline Behaviours among Public Primary Schools Pupils in 87
Delta State, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603587>
- 13 Comparative Analysis between Open Defecation Practices and Environmental 95
Health Status on Residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603589>
- 14 Qualitative Study on Data Privacy Policy and Data Mining in Educational 103
Assessment in Nigeria: A Systematic Review.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603591>
- 15 Comparative Analysis between Somatotype and Fitness Status of Middle-Aged 110
Female Adults in Kano State, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603593>
- 16 Numerical Solution of Tenth-Order Boundary Value Problems Using the 119
Variational Iteration Method with Bernstein Polynomials as Trial Functions.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603595>
- 17 Teachers' Compliance with Professional Ethics and Their Enhanced Productivity 128
in Lagos State Public Senior Secondary Schools Education District I, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609051>
- 18 Qualitative Study on the Role of Technology in Entrepreneurship Education for 142
Sustainable Development in Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609049>
- 19 Mathematics as the Bedrock of Artificial Intelligence and Creative Thinking for 152
National Development in Nigeria: A Systematic Review.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609047>
- 20 Assessment of Sex-For-Grade on Attitude of Students in Bayelsa Sate College of 163
Health Technology, Otuogidi, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609045>
- 21 Qualitative study on augmented innovations in Artificial Intelligence 170
Technologies: A Panacea for sustainable undergraduate chemistry learning
outcome in Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609043>

DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17011451>

- 22 Effects of Inquiry – Based Instructional Strategy on Achievement and Retention 180
in Auto-Mechanics among Technical College Students in Lagos State, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609041>
- 23 Comparative Analysis between Financial Literacy and Household Budgeting 190
Practices among Families in Delta State, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609039>
- 24 Comparative Analysis of Social Media and Peer influence on Risky Behaviours 201
among Colleges of Education Students in Osun State, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609035>
- 25 Influence of Digital Revolution on Knowledge Management among Secondary 208
School Students in Alimosho Local Government Area, Lagos State, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609037>
- 26 Assessment of Preparedness and Utilization of Artificial Intelligence on Business 215
Education Learning among Colleges of Education Lecturers in South– South,
Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609053>
- 27 Comparative Assessment of Water Purification Techniques Awareness and Socio- 222
Economic Variabilities among Household Owners in Zamfara State, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610556>
- 28 Correlation between Home-Background and Achievement in Mathematics among 231
Primary School Pupils in Mbo Local Government, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610558>
- 29 Effect of Concentrated Language Encounter Instructional Strategy on Reading 239
Skills Among Primary School Pupils in Dutsin-ma, Katsina State, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610562>
- 30 Effect of Moonlight Tales on Social Cohesion among Middle Basic Pupils in Osun 244
State, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610564>
- 31 Assessment of Inclusive Education at Junior Secondary Schools in Abuja 252
Municipal Area Council (AMAC), Abuja Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610566>
- 32 Effects of Class-Size on Retention in Chemistry Concepts among Secondary 261
School Students in Zaria Local Government Area, Kaduna State.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610568>

DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17011451>

- 33 Impact of Concept-Mapping Instructional Strategy on Attitude and Performance 268
in Algebra among Senior Secondary School Students in Zaria, Kaduna State.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610570>
- 34 Effect of Metacognitive Learning cycle model on achievement in mathematics 277
concepts among secondary school students in Minna metropolis, Niger state.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610572>
- 35 Christian Parent's Ethnic and Cultural Prejudices on Choice of Marriage Partners 285
among their Children in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610576>
- 36 Comparative Relationship between First Language and Learning Environment on 292
Spellings among Secondary School English Students in Okitipupa Metropolis,
Ondo State.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610578>
- 37 Revitalizing Nigeria's Educational System: Innovative Policies for National 299
Development.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611060>
- 38 Correlation between Piagetian and Vygotsky's Theories Informed Strategies on 304
Performance and Retention in Number Sense among Pupils in Katsina State.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611062>
- 39 Assessment on Impact of Social-Media-Platforms on Examination Malpractice 312
among Secondary School Science Students in Ido/Osi Local Government Area,
Ekiti State.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611064>
- 40 Qualitative Study on Social Media Sentiment Analysis for Evidence-Based Policy- 318
Making in Electronic Voting in Nigeria: A Machine Learning Approach.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611066>
- 41 Comparative analysis between Teachers' Education Goals and Social Change: An 324
Exploratory Study of Nigerian University System.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611068>
- 42 Comparative Analysis between Family Variables and Sexual Behaviour among 332
Secondary School Students in Ondo Metropolis, Ondo State, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611070>
- 43 Assessment of Teacher-Student Relationship on Academic Performance in 338
Christian Religious Knowledge among Secondary School Students in Kaduna
State, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611072>

DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17011451>

- 44 Assessment of Experience and Qualification on Implementation of Hausa Language Curriculum among Senior Secondary School Teachers' in Katsina State, Nigeria. 346
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611074>
- 45 Assessment of Validity and Reliability of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire among college of education Pre-Service Teachers in Kano State, Nigeria. 354
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611076>
- 46 Assessment of Indexing and Attitudes of Book Authors in Nigeria: Journalism Perspective 362
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601986>
- 47 Knowledge and Awareness of Chronic Kidney Disease among Residents of Hadejia Emirate, Jigawa State: Implications for Public Health Education 370
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17009901>

Effect of Outdoor Laboratory Strategy on Attitude and Performance in Ecology Concept among Secondary School Students in Kano State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of outdoor laboratory strategy on attitude, and performance in ecology concept among secondary schools in Kano State Nigeria. The study adopted a pre-test, post-test quasi-experimental control group design. The population of the study comprises all Senior Secondary Schools two biology students (SSII) during the 2023/2024 academic session in Kano State. A sample size of One hundred and twenty-three (123) SSII biology students were selected from the target population stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling technique was used to select the sample size due to gender difference in senior secondary schools in Kano state. Four schools were randomly selected using balloting method, which involved hand picking from the container, two were females' schools and two were males' schools. A total of 62 students were in the experimental group and taught using outdoor laboratory strategy while 61 students were in the control group taught using lecture method. The two groups were taught ecology concepts for six weeks. Two instruments were used and these are; Ecology Performance Test (EPT) with reliability coefficient of $r = 0.98$ and Ecology Attitude Questionnaire (EAQ) with reliability coefficient of $r = 0.92$. Two null hypotheses were formulated to guide the researcher. The hypotheses were tested using t-test and U-test statistics at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance. The result of the analysis shows a significance difference exist in the two hypotheses. The researcher concluded that, Outdoor laboratory strategy has significant effect on attitude, and performance of students in ecology concept among secondary school students in Kano State. The researcher recommended that biology teachers in secondary school should be using Outdoor laboratory strategy.

Keywords: Outdoor Laboratory, Attitude, Performance and Ecology.

Introduction

Outdoor Laboratory is an instructional strategy that was first introduced in the 1920s and has its philosophical foundations laid by thinkers such as Rousseau, Pestalozzi, Comenius and Dewey. Outdoor Laboratory is one of the activity-based instructional strategies that take place outside the classroom, based on learning by doing. Maikano (2019) defined an Outdoor laboratory as a natural environment of living organisms such as fields, riversides, ponds, and trees among others where living things can best be studied from an ecological point of view. The outdoor laboratory is a student's centered strategy where the teacher acts as a facilitator of learning, guiding the students through a series of activities and problems which may help learners to achieve highly. The outdoor laboratory advocates the realization of learning where it can be done and where its purpose can be achieved, covers activities at elementary school, middle school, high school, and university levels and in many geographical settings (Gumus 2020). Outdoor learning environments can help students communicate with their peers, understand others, work together democratically, towards common goals, develop community awareness, and understand their place in the world. However, this method may affect the attitude of the students.

Attitude as one of the variables of the present study plays an important role in the academic performance of science students. Students' attitude towards biology affects their science academic performance because biology is one of the core science subjects. Erdemir and Bakirci (2014) described the attitude as the tendency of individuals who organize thoughts, emotions, and behaviours towards a psychological object. The concept of attitude arose from an attempt to account for observed regularities in the behaviour of an individual (Elijah, Lynn & Jonson; 2015). This attitude can be positive, negative or neutral one's inner experiences are evidence of one's attitude. Therefore, when students experience some difficulties in learning biology they will manifest unfavorable or negative attitudes towards biology. Sakariyau (2016) recognized attitude as a major factor in the choice of subject and also considered attitude as a mental and natural state of readiness, organized through experiences exerting a directive influence upon the individual's responses to all objects and situations with which it is related. Attitude is like academic achievement because they are a significant factor in ensuring students' success. Science teachers need to ensure that students have positive attitudes toward science subjects. However, the favorable and positive attitude of students toward biology is facilitated by the use of a suitable instructional approach. To improve students' attitudes, teachers of biology have look a suitable and favorable instructional strategy that will enable the students to participate fully in class such as outdoor laboratory teaching strategy. But so unfortunate from experience by the researcher majority of the teachers of biology are using lecture method.

The lecture method which is predominantly used in senior secondary schools in Nigeria contributes to the poor academic performance of senior secondary school biology students in Nigeria (Ezenwoso, 2013). The lecture method is a teaching strategy which involved verbal presentation where the teacher delivers the lesson to the students with little or no active participation by the students. It is a teacher-centered approach which involved- way form of communication from the teacher to the students. This is why it is referred to as the didactic approach because it involved the verbal presentation of concepts, where the teacher presents, spoken and discourse on a particular subject while the students remain passive listeners and take down notes. The lecture method of teaching emphasizes "Talk and Chalk" in the teaching of science subjects' biology inclusive. More than 80% of the scientific information and principles are delivered as a lecture. Hence the teaching of ecology is faced with the dilemma of either using simplified or more complex materials. Therefore, teaching certain ecology concepts requires basic knowledge about the species involved and their natural environment. Usman (2010) observed that the lecture method encourages rote learning without proper understanding, thereby resulting in poor performance. However, the use of activity-based strategies such as field trips, problem-solving, cooperative learning strategy; guided discovery and outdoor laboratory may increase the performance of students, particularly slow learners.

Empirically the review some previous works of other researchers such as the work of Saidu and Suleman (2014) investigated the effects of outdoor laboratory teaching strategy on Academic performances among College of Education Students of different ability levels in North-west Zone Nigeria. The findings of their study showed that the outdoor laboratory teaching strategy favoured the experimental group.

Stanley (2019) investigated the impact of outdoor and indoor laboratory strategies on the retention of learnt ecological concepts among senior secondary school biology students in the Giwa education zone of Kaduna state, Nigeria. The findings of the reviewed study showed that Students exposed to the outdoor laboratory instructional strategy retained the learnt concepts significantly better than their counterparts exposed to the Indoor laboratory instructional strategy and taught ecology concept.

Donmez (2021), Investigated the impact of Out-of-School STEM Activities on the STEM Career Choices of Female Students who make university preferences after grade 11 in the Turkish education system. The findings revealed that the interest of the participants in STEM career fields differs significantly between pre- and post-STEM activities. These findings showed that the implementation of out-of-school STEM activities contributed to an increase in STEM career interest.

Hussaini, Foong and Kamar, (2015), investigated the Attitudes of Secondary School students towards biology as a school subject in Birnin Kebbi Metropolitan, Kebbi State, Nigeria. The finding showed that the differences between the attitudes of male and female students were significantly insignificant.

Sakariyau (2015) studied the Attitudes of Secondary School Students towards Biology in the Odeda Local Government Area of Ogun State, Nigeria. The finding showed that a higher proportion of the students display a positive attitude towards science.

Aminu (2017) determined the Effect of Social Constructivism Instructional Strategy on attitude, and Performance in the Algebraic process among SSII Students in Sokoto state, Nigeria. A quasi-experimental design was used. The findings indicated that there were statistically significantly different in the mean scores of the experimental and control group in performance and retention. Sofiani, Maulida, Fadhillah and Sihite (2017) investigated the students' attitudes towards science and the effect of gender in Bundung, Indonesia. Their findings showed that students' positive attitude towards science was at medium level and there was no significant difference in attitude towards science between the female and male.

Zakariya (2017) studied the Impact of Metacognitive Strategy on Attitude, Retention and Performance in Calculus among Colleges of Education Students in the North-central Zone, of Nigeria. The study adopted a Pre-test, Post-test, and post-post-test quasi-experimental design. The findings revealed that there was a significant difference between the post-test mean scores of the experimental and control groups in favour of the experimental group. Out of the reviewed the most resent is the work of Donmez (2021) while the present work is conducted is this year 2024 and also none of the work was conducted in Kano state. Also none of the work used outdoor laboratory strategy on students' performance and attitude in ecology.

In order to give students room for participation and learning from each other the researcher intend to find out the effect of outdoor laboratory strategy on students, attitude and performance in ecology among secondary school students in Kano state, Nigeria. To achieve this objective, the researcher design to achieve the following specific objectives as follows:

Objectives of the Study

The following objectives were raised to guide study.

1. Determine the effect of outdoor laboratory strategy on students' attitude in ecology among secondary school students in Kano state, Nigeria
2. Examine the effect of outdoor laboratory strategy on students' Performance in ecology among secondary school students in Kano state, Nigeria

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide study.

1. What are the mean difference between the students' attitude taught ecology concept using outdoor laboratory strategy and those taught using lecture methods in Kano State?
2. What are the mean difference between the students' performance taught ecology concept using outdoor laboratory strategy and those taught using lecture methods in Kano State?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to be tested at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance

H₀₁: There is no significance difference between the students' attitude taught ecology using outdoor laboratory strategy and those taught using lecture methods in Kano State.

H₀₂: There is no significance difference between the students' performance taught ecology using outdoor laboratory strategy and those taught using lecture methods in Kano State.

Methodology

The design adapted for this study is quasi- experimental control groups research design as recommended by Kerlinger (1973). Two groups were considered for this study. The two groups were pre-tested with (EPT) in order to determine the equivalence of students' ability level of the two groups. The Population of the study comprises the entire public Senior Secondary Schools two, (SSII) biology students in Dawakin Kudu Education Zone, Kano State. There are 36 senior secondary schools in Dawakin Kudu Education Zone, which consist of single sex secondary schools. Records of enrolment showed that, 5185 students as the tagged population that comprised 3392 boys and 1793 girls. The sample size of 123 Biology students were used which is in line with the central limit theory that recommends minimum of 30 samples as variable for the experimental research (Tukman 1975). Thus, 123 biology samples were obtained through the use of stratified random sampling technique and were considered appropriate for the research

study as pointed out by Sambo, (2008). Two instruments were used namely Ecology Attitude Questionnaire (EAQ) and Ecology Performance Test (EPT), the two instruments were validated by expert in science education and the reliability of the two instruments were obtain were 0.98 and 0.92 using crombach- α and Pearson Product Moment Correlation. A treatment was given to the experimental group by exposing them to outdoor laboratory strategies for six weeks and control groups was taught ecology concepts with lecture method only for same numbers of weeks. At the end of six weeks' treatment a post-test was administered to both groups (experimented and control) using EAQ and EPT. The scripts were collected and mark by the researcher and recorded it tables for data analysis. The data were analyzed using t-test and U-test statistics. The result of the analyses is presented as follows.

Research Question One: What are mean difference between the students' attitude taught ecology conceptusing outdoor laboratory strategy and those taught using lecture methods?

To answer the research question one, mean and standard deviation were used. The detail of the result is presented in Table 1:

Table 1: Summary of Post-test Attitude Mean Rank and Sum of Rank Scores of Students in the Experimental and Control Groups

Variable	Group	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mean Gain
Attitude	Experimental	62	68.19	4227.50	12.48
	Control Group	61	55.71	3398.50	

Table 1 present the mean rank and sum of ranks scores of students in the experimental and control groups. The computed mean rank scores are 68.19 for students in the experimental group and 55.71 for students in the control group respectively. In the same vein, the computed sum of ranks scores is 4227.50 and 3398.50 for students in the experimental and control groups respectively. A mean rank gain of 12.48 was obtained in favour of students in the experimental group. The testing of the corresponding hypothesis is as follows:

H₀₁: There is no significance difference between the students' attitude taught ecology concept using outdoor laboratory strategy and those taught using lecture methods.

To test the null hypothesis two, a Mann-Whitny U-test statistic was used. The summary of the analysis is presented in Table 2

Table 2: Summary of Mann-Whitney U-test Analysis of Post-test Scores for Students' Attitude in the Experimental and Control Group

Groups	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	df	U-test	p-value	Decision
Experimental	62	68.19	4227.50	121	1507.50	0.05	rejected
Control	61	55.71	3398.50				
Total	123						

Significant at $P \leq 0.05$ level

Table 2 shows the summary of Mann-Whitny U-test analysis of experimental and control groups with U-test value of 1507.50 and p-value of 0.05 at df. of 121. This shows that, the p-value of 0.05 is equal to α -value of 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, with this evidence the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is significant difference in the attitudinal change of students taught ecology concepts using outdoor Laboratory strategy and those taught using lecture methods. This explain that, the experimental group develop more positive attitude than that of the control group as a result of the treatment given to the experimental group using outdoor Laboratory strategy. Therefore, outdoor Laboratory is capable of improving students' attitude toward ecology concept.

Research Question Two: What are the mean difference between the performances of students taught ecology concepts using outdoor Laboratory and those taught with lecture method?

To answer the research question two, mean and standard deviation were used. The detail of the result is presented in Table 3

Table 3: Mean and Mean Difference in the Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Experimental	62	23.63	4.39	11.3
Control	61	12.33	3.45	

Table 3 showed that, the mean performance score of students in experimental group was 23.63 with standard deviation 4.39 while the mean performance scores of students in the control group was 12.33 with standard deviation 3.45 and the mean difference was 11.3. This indicated that, there is difference between the mean performance scores of students exposed to Outdoor Laboratory and those exposed to lecture method. The testing of the corresponding hypothesis is as follows:

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the performances of students taught ecology concepts using outdoor Laboratory and those taught with lecture method.

To test the hypothesis two, independent t-test was used and the summary of the analysis is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Independent Samples t-test Analysis of Mean Performance Scores between Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean	Std. D	Df	t _{cal}	P-value	Remark
Experimental	62	23.63	4.39	120	15.78	0.00	Significant
Control	60	12.33	3.45				

Significant at $P \leq 0.05$ level

Table 4 present the summary of t-test analysis with t_{cal} of 15.78 and P-value of 0.00 at df. of 120. This shows that, the P-value of 0.00 is less than the α –value of 0.05 level of significance. Based on this evidence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference between the performances of students taught ecology concepts using Outdoor Laboratory strategy and those taught with lecture method. This shows that, the treatment given to the experimental group has significance effect on the students’ performance in ecology concept.

Discussion of Findings

The result of Table 2 revealed that, there was significance difference between the students’ attitude taught ecology concept using outdoor laboratory strategy and those taught using lecture methods. in favour of experimental group. The finding of this study is in agreement with the finding of Sofiani, Maulida, Fadhillah and Sihite (2017) investigated the students' attitudes towards science and the effect of gender in Bundung, Indonesia. Their findings showed that students' positive attitude towards science was at medium level and there was no significant difference in attitude towards science between the female and male. In addition, Sakariyau (2015) studied the Attitudes of Secondary School Students towards Biology in the Odeda Local Government Area of Ogun State, Nigeria. The finding showed that a higher proportion of the students display a positive attitude towards science.

The result of Table 4 revealed that, there was a significant difference in the attitude means scores of students after been taught ecology concepts using outdoor Laboratory and those taught using lecture methods in favour of experimental group. The finding of this study is in agreement with the finding of Stanley (2019) investigated the impact of outdoor and indoor laboratory strategies on the retention of learnt ecological concepts among senior secondary school biology students in the Giwa education zone of Kaduna state, Nigeria. The findings of the reviewed study showed that Students exposed to the outdoor laboratory instructional strategy retained the learnt concepts significantly better than their counterparts exposed to the Indoor laboratory instructional strategy and taught ecology

concept. His finding revealed that, outdoor laboratory instructional strategy contributed to the development of students' attitude and improved their performance. In addition, Muhammad (2017) who investigated the Effect of outdoor Laboratory and Peer Tutoring strategies on Attitude and Performance in Geometry among Secondary Schools Students in Niger state, Nigeria. His finding showed that, the students taught using outdoor laboratory and peer tutoring strategy develop high positive attitude than their counterpart who were taught with lecture method. The significant difference found between the two groups is likely due to the used of cooperative learning enriched with outdoor laboratory on the experimental group. Also Saidu and Suleman (2014) investigated the effects of outdoor laboratory teaching strategy on Academic performances among College of Education Students of different ability levels in North-west Zone Nigeria. The findings of their study showed that the outdoor laboratory teaching strategy favoured the experimental group.

Conclusion

Based on the findings obtained from this study, the following conclusions were reached: The researchers concluded that outdoor Laboratory is effective in improving academic performances in ecology concepts. Also the study concluded that Outdoor Laboratory help students in developing positive attitude towards teaching and learning of ecology concepts.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that:

1. The Kano ministry of education should have emphasized the implementation of outdoor Laboratory strategy in teaching biology in secondary schools in order to improve the attitude students toward learning ecology concept.
2. The biology teachers in Kano State should start using outdoor Laboratory strategy in teaching biology in secondary schools in order to improve the students' performance in ecology.

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Managing Threats to Internal Validity in Quantitative and Qualitative Research: Some Basic Considerations

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Abstract

The main thrust of the paper was to examine factors that can pose threat to internal validity in both Qualitative and Quantitative research. In order to accomplish this task, the concept of validity and its various types such as content, construct and criterion-related validity were analyzed. The paper also highlighted some factors to be considered in order to achieve internal validity in both quantitative and qualitative research methods namely Maturation, Testing, Instrumentation and History among others. Although the paper acknowledged impossibility of eliminating totally the threats to internal validity especially when research is conducted outside the laboratory setting; it is the position of the paper that, good understanding and knowledge of the threats or factors that can jeopardize internal validity as highlighted in this paper can help to mitigate those threats to a minimum level and enhance the quality of the instruments and of course findings. On the basis of this conclusion, the paper suggested among other things on the need to consider the time of experiment, the use of a control group, selected from the same population as the experimental group and which experiences the same concurrent history as the experimental group are very important strategies for reducing threats to internal validity.

Keyword: Validity, Internal validity, Validity of measurement and experimental validity

Introduction

As a scientific activity, research is a search for knowledge which is embarked upon to come with findings leading to answer to question (s), development of theory or solution to a problem. For this reason, Alarape, (2012) Research is manipulations of things, concept or symbol for the purpose of generalizing extend, correct or verify knowledge, whether that knowledge aids in construction of theory or in the practice of an art. In research, information is collected to verify and generalize findings through the use of designs and various different measuring instruments namely: Questionnaire, Interview and observation among others. However, the quality of the findings and inferences made is affected by certain psychometric qualities and Validity is one of the important qualities that a good measuring instrument (test, questionnaire, observation) must possess. In line with this, Singh, (2014) noted that Validity and reliability increase transparency, and decrease opportunities to insert researcher bias in qualitative research.

The concept of Validity which is of interest to this paper is of different types and it can be applied to two areas of research: validity of measurement and validity of findings. The former, deals with those types of validity such as content validity and construct validity that are concerned with the measuring instruments, while the latter, has to do with internal and external validity of the research design. It is often associated with the experimental designs where the researcher often manipulates one variable (independent) to see its' effects on another variable (dependent).

However, one pertinent question to ask is; can the researcher confidently attribute the observed changes or differences in the dependent variable to the independent variable? This question raises the issue of internal validity. Establishing this type of validity in research serves as a herculean task to especially novice researchers. In view of this, Zainal (2017) asserts that novice researchers often face challenges such as management of extraneous variables, maintaining treatment fidelity and limited resources in an attempt to establish internal validity in research. These and other factors have to be kept under control because it is only when they properly managed can the researcher attribute the cause and effect of one variable to another.

Managing Threats to...(Muhammad, & Ladan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601946>

Sharma (2019) acknowledged the gravity of the threats of internal validity in survey which according to him is associated with challenges such as inadequate research design, insufficient pilot testing as well as measurement errors and biases.

The challenges of establishing internal validity are even more enormous in Qualitative research which is the method favour by Subjectivists (naturalists) in the study of human behavior. In sociological research, these problems and many others raise the question of credibility which is concerned with the truthfulness of the research findings or how well the researcher has established confidence in research based on the method used. Indeed, according to Lawal & Ladan (2023) the Positivists (Quantitative research method) who are the antagonist of Subjectivists (Qualitative research method), pointed out that because Qualitative as a research method deals with subjective assessment of the phenomena being study in natural setting, achieving internal validity or credibility is difficult if not impossible.

Therefore, against the background of difficulties and threats in establishing internal validity in both Qualitative and Quantitative research, this paper among other issues highlighted certain basic considerations in managing the threats to the internal validity.

Conceptual Clarification

The concepts of Qualitative and Quantitative research as well as the concept of Validity are central in this discussion and thus explained.

Qualitative Research

Qualitative research is concerned with subjective assessment of attitudes, opinions and behavior. Research in such situations is a function of researcher's insight and impressions. It generates results either in non-quantifiable form or in the form which are not subjected to rigorous quantitative analysis. In other words, data is not necessarily expressed in numbers; rather it is presented in form of words. As noted by Okeshola cited in Lawal & Ladan (2023) Qualitative research uses unreconstructed logic to get at what is really real-quality, meaning, context or image of reality in what people actually do, not what they say they do. In addition, qualitative research according to Denzin and Lincoln (2014) implies an emphasis on the qualities of entities and on processes and meanings that are not experimentally examined or measured (if measured at all) in terms of quantity, amount, intensity, or frequency.

Quantitative Research

Quantitative research involves generation of data in quantitative form which can be subjected to rigorous statistical analysis. It entails the collection of data in numbers. Obasi cited in Lawal & Ladan (2023) defined quantitative research as an aspect of the scientific method that investigates phenomena that are amenable to empirical measurement and verification. This means examining variables that can be assigned figures or values which can be empirically observed. The Quantitative procedure of assigning figures is different from Qualitative research which deals with detail description of phenomena being studied.

Validity

Validity is an important determinant of the quality of any measuring instrument. A review of various definitions of Validity from different literatures reveals that the concept of validity is defined by different authors in almost similar perspectives. For example, Kauru (2015) defines Validity as the degree to which the tool measures what it claims to measure while Kamar (2017) stated that, validity means the accuracy with which a test measures what it intends to or supposed to measure. Similarly, Validity can also refer to the ability of measuring instrument to measure truly and accurately the quality or ability it is designed to measure. In other words, a measuring instrument is said to be valid, when it measures truly and accurately the quality or ability it is designed to measure. This means that a test that is designed to test achievement should do just that and nothing else. Middleton (2023) explained that Validity along with Reliability are the two concepts that are utilized to measure the quality of research. Validity in research therefore deals with the extent to with research instrument measure what it is supposed to measure. Thus, one important thing clear from the above definitions is that, the concept of validity is defined in relation to measuring tool, instrument or test. However, validity can also be defined or viewed in relation to Research Design. For instance, according to Asika cited in Lawal and Ladan (2023), a research design may be said to be valid if it enables a researcher to elicit the correct responses from the sample subjects, otherwise it can be regarded as faulty design and may not lead to correct outcomes.

There are different types of validity which can be applied to different areas of research. It is in line with this that Asika cited in Lawal and Ladan (2023), maintained that, the concept of validity can be applied in two areas of research: validity of measurement and validity of findings or experimental validity. Validity of measurement is ability of the measuring instrument to measure what it is supposed to measure. In relation to this, Kamar (2017) observed that there are three major types of validity that are commonly used in educational and psychological measurements. These are namely: Content Validity, Criterion-related validity and Construct validity.

Managing Threats to...(Muhammad, & Ladan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601946>

Content validity: this type of Validity emphasized on adequate coverage of the scope of the topic. Kauru (2015) observes that content validity involves the systematic examination of the test content to determine whether it covers a representative sample of the behavior domain to be measured content validity is therefore directed to the following questions:

1. Have all the relevant dimensions of the topic been fully explored?
2. Does the measuring instrument adequately cover all the dimensions or at least a good representation of all the dimensions of the topic of research?

These questions must to be answered for an instrument to possess content validity. In line with this, Asika cited in Lawal and Ladan (2023), explains that content validity can be determined by the designer of the instrument in any of the following ways:

- i. By ensuring that all the questions asked in the instrument questionnaire fully exhaust all that are implied by the research questions and hypotheses.
- ii. By using a panel of judges who would vet the questions in the questionnaire objectively, paying particular attention to their relevance to the subject matter and their coverage the entire topic of the study.

Criterion-related validity

Criterion-related validity involves comparing the test with other test(s) (criterion) that is held to be valid. Some instruments or tests are known or have been determined to be good measures of certain variables or attribute. Such test otherwise known as criterion can be used as basis for judging the validity of a newly designed instrument. For example, some of the West African Examination (WAEC) Examinations have been determined over time to be good measures of the candidate's intelligence. If a researcher is to design his own instrument to equally measure the students' intelligence, how does his own instrument compare or relate to a similar established criterion that is the WAEC examinations?

Criterion related validity is of two types: the predictive and concurrent validity. Predictive validity measures how the newly designed measuring instrument adequately predicts certain attributes it is designed to measure while the concurrent validity measures how the newly designed measuring instrument measures other current behaviors or variables.

Construct validity

The word construct according to Salawu & Kamar (2017) is a high-level concept that has been invented for particular purpose. Examples of construct are the terms motivation and intelligence. Motivation is used to explain human behavior and intelligence is used to study difference in human learning or human behavior. Construct validity is therefore an attempt to measure how adequately an instrument measures the actual meaning of a construct. Gay, Mills and Airasian (2022) opined that, construct validity attempts to explain whether the test reflects the actual meaning of the construct or not. For instance, how well results from a test on stress reflect the actual theoretical characteristics of stress is a measure of construct validity. However, there are other types of validity.

Experimental validity or Validity of Findings

This type validity is associated with Experimental research. Best & Kahn (2016) stated that Conventional experiment usually involves two groups: Experimental group and Control group and experimental group is exposed to influence of the factor under consideration. Observations are then made to determine what difference appears or what changes or modifications occur in the experimental group as contrasted with the control group. Experimental validity or Validity of findings therefore refers to the problem of the adequacy of a research design in eliciting the type of responses that it is designed to generate. In other words, a research design may be said to be valid if it enables a researcher elicit the correct responses from the sample subjects, otherwise it is a faulty design and may not lead to correct findings. In relation to this, there are two (2) types of validity. They are namely: External validity and internal validity.

External Validity

External validity refers to the degree to which it is warranted to generalize results to other contexts. External validity asks questions of generalization. To what population, setting can the effects observed be generalized. Best & Kahn (2016) stated that the researcher would achieve little of practical value if these observed variable valid only in the experimental setting and only for those participating. External validity is therefore extent to which the variable relationship can be generalized to other setting, other treatment variables, other measurement variables and other population.

Internal Validity

Internal Validity is concerned with the extent to which a causal conclusion based on a study is warranted, which is determined by the degree to which a study minimizes systematic error (or bias). An experiment is said to have internal validity if the factors that have been manipulated (independent variables) actually have genuine effect on the observed consequences or dependent variable. For example, consider the following outcomes of an experiment of two separate teaching methods; Pre-test mean score (Mean Score before the treatment) = 20 %

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Post-test Mean Score (Mean Score after the treatment) = 60%

In this example, the researcher wants to make a causal inference that 40% difference is caused only by the treatment that is the teaching method. In other words, when the researcher may confidently attribute the observed changes or differences in the dependent variable to the independent variable, and when the researcher can rule out other explanations then the causal inference is said to be internally valid.

Internal Validity in Qualitative Research Method

Qualitative research is a method that is more frequently adopted in social science disciplines. While, Quantitative research involves generation of data in quantitative form which can be subjected to rigorous statistical analysis, Qualitative however employs few if any quantitative data gathering instruments. It uses unstructured and semi-structured methods such as in-depth interviews, focus groups, and participant observation for data collection.

In qualitative research method, the word Credibility is used to refer to internal validity. Credibility is concerned with how well the researcher has established confidence in research based on the research design. Mahuta (2016) stated that credibility is concerned with the truthfulness of the research findings. Since qualitative research method deals with subjective assessment of the phenomena being study in natural setting, its critics (positivist) are of the opinion that achieving internal validity or credibility is difficult if not impossible in qualitative research method. However, Donald, Lucy & Chris cited in Mahuta (2016) stated that credibility (internal validity) in qualitative research can be enhanced through the following methods:

1. Structural corroboration which has to do with Data triangulation.
2. Consensus which has to do with Investigator triangulation
3. Control of bias which can be done through reflexivity or use of self-reflection to recognize one's own biases and to actively seek them out.

Basic Consideration for Achieving Internal Validity

In many cases, the magnitude of effects found in the dependent variable may not just depend on independent variable, there are certain factors or variable that could exert some influence over the dependent variable which serves as threats to internal validity. They are extraneous variables or circumstances that if not well control can affect the internal validity. These factors include: Maturation, testing, instrumentation, differential selection of subjects, experimental mortality, statistical regression, Hawthorn effects among other factors. Some of these factors are explained below:

- i. **Maturation:** The subject being measured may change during the course of the experiment or even between measurements which may be due to psychological and physical changes. For example, consider this experiment on methods of teaching
Group I (experimental) given treatment from 8:00am– 9:00 am
Group II (control) given treatment from 1:00pm – 2: 00 pm
Any outcome obtained from this experiment cannot serve as a basis for comparison. Physical and psychological changes may put the control group at the disadvantage. The afternoon time may be too hot. Similarly, the control group may get tired, bored and loss interest or eager to go home.
- ii. **Testing:** the testing itself may sensitize the subjects being tested or measured (found in pre-test post-test). If the same test is used for pre and post-tests, the possibility is that the subjects have mastered the former to help their performance in the second. In other words, Best & Kahn (2016) stated that pre-testing may produce a practice effect that may make subjects more proficient in subsequent test performance.
- iii. **Instrumentation:** Unreliable instruments used to describe and measure aspects of behavior are threat to internal validity of an experiment. For instance, an instrument of observation that is not reliable, a serious element of error is introduced. Similarly, if human observers are used to describe behavior changes in subjects, changes in observers or in their standards due to fatigue, increased in sight or skill or changes in criteria of judgment over period of time are likely to introduce error. With regards to test as instrument Essay type of tests especially, Salawu & Kamar (2017) pointed out that if the pre-test and post-test are marked by different scorers there will be contradiction to validity. Whether or not marking schemes are provided for the separate scorers or assessors, element of bias is already introduced.
- iv. **History:** History in this context refers to specific random events, which are beyond the control of the researcher that can affect the performance of the subjects. Such events can occur between the first and second measurement. Take for example an experiment which takes 5 – 10 weeks in a school setting. Some of the students may go beyond the lectures (treatment) being given, thus having extra experience during the interval between pre and posts test. This is beyond the control of the researcher but can have effect on the performance of the subjects.

Managing Threats to...(Muhammad, & Ladan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601946>

- v. **Experimental Mortality:** this is loss of subjects from the sample due to resignations, apathy or death. It may likely to occur in the long-term experiment and error can occur if inferences are made on the basis of only those participants that have participated from the start to the end. For example, an experiment was started with 30 samples but at the end only 20 or less are left to continue, then there is experimental mortality because some of those 10 or more students who left may be special students or those with low marks.
- vi. **Statistical Regression:** Subjects, who score highest in the pre-test, may score lower on the re-test; subjects who score higher on pre-test may score high on re-test. Scores at the extreme tend to go towards the mean. In other words, this type of error occurs when subjects are selected on the basis of extreme scores (one far away from the mean) during a test. For example, when children with the worst reading scores are selected to participate in a reading course, improvements at the end of the course might be due to regression toward the mean and not the course's effectiveness. If the children had been tested again before the course started, they would likely have obtained better scores anyway. For example, consider this experiment, a situation where after teaching with two methods, a teacher ranks students according to marks:
Group A 1 – 30 %
Group B 71- 100 %
This comparison makes it impossible to actually find out the effect of one variable on the other because only the best performing (71- 100 %) and worst performing (1 – 30 %) were selected. The subjects are not true representation of the population. In this case, the researcher should not pick from the two extremes.
- vii. **Selection Bias:** this is bias in the selection of students or other groups of people for an experimental research study. This may render deductions from such exercises worthless.
- viii. **Experimenter Bias:** This factor as explained by Best & Kahn (2016) is a type of bias introduced when the researcher has some previous knowledge about the subjects involved in an experiment. This knowledge of subject status may cause the researcher to convey some clue that affect the subject's reaction or may affect the objectivity of his or her judgment.

Conclusion

Many threats to internal validity of especially experiment are difficult to be eliminated totally particularly when research is conducted outside the laboratory setting; where there are many extraneous variables to control. However, knowledge of the threats or factors that can jeopardize it is crucial. It enables the researcher to mitigate those threats to a minimum level and enhance the quality of the instruments and of course findings.

Recommendations

Threat to internal validity is inevitable challenge more especially in Experimental research design. However, the following suggestions can minimize those threats and enable researcher confidently attributes the observed changes or differences in the dependent variable to the independent variable:

1. To reduce the threats generated by History & Maturation, there is need to consider the time of experiment. In order words, the shorter the duration of an experiment, the less likely that maturation will occur. Similarly, the use of a control group, selected from the same population as the experimental group and which experiences the same concurrent history as the experimental group is another strategy for reducing threats to internal validity.
2. With regards to testing, many actions can be taken to ensure that the possibility of proficiency as a result of the mastery of pre-test is checkmated. Among which are, the use of a research design that does not include a pretest. Even where the experiment involved pre-test, the use of different but equivalent forms of a test for pre-test and post-test is another option.
3. Random sampling and random assignment of subjects are some of the viable ways to reduce threats arising from bias in selection. Where random sampling and assignment are not possible, statistical techniques such as ANCOVA can be utilized to adjust for group differences. Similarly, researchers should desist from being bias or subjective in scoring the instruments, objectivity is therefore essential as far as internal validity is concerned.
4. Standardized instruments possessed the quality of reliability. To eliminate instrumentation threats therefore, there is need for the researchers to adopt or adapt standardized instruments more especially in situations whereby the reliability of the researcher-designed instruments cannot be ascertained. In addition, careful specification and control of the measurement procedures as well as the training of study personnel are among other procedures that help control the instrumentation threat.

Managing Threats to...(Muhammad, & Ladan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601946>

5. Researchers also need avoid assigning subjects to groups based on their extreme scores in order to prevent the internal validity threats arising from statistical regression.
6. Some circumstances leading to experimental mortality such as death is unavoidable but other conditions such as anger, apathy, and frustration can be managed. There is therefore need for the researchers to provide enabling conditions that can encourage participants to willingly and objectivity participate in the experiment from the start to the completion.

Other basic considerations are: the use of single scorers or markers on issue of instrumentation, avoiding picking from two extreme scores to check statistical regression, randomization among others. Similarly, pure or true experimental design enable researcher to neutralize the threat or influence of both internal and external validity.

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Correlation between Socio-economic Factors and Productive Human Resource Management among Secondary School Teachers in Oredo Local Government Area, Edo State

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Abstract

The study investigated correlation between socio-economic factors and productive human resource management among selected secondary school teachers in Edo state. Correlation research design was adopted for this work because it was used to determine the relationship or association that exists between the dependent and independent variables. The target population was public secondary school teachers in Edo State. Purposive and simple random sampling techniques were employed to select 20 participants from 10 secondary schools in Oredo LGA of Edo state to form sample size of 200 teachers. A self-structured instrument, Correlation between Socio-Emotional Factors and Productive Human Resource Management Questionnaire (CBSEFPHRMQ) was used to collect data. The instrument consisted of 20 items using a closed-ended format on 4likert point scale. Content validity was affirmed by two experts in the Department of Human Resource Management, Lagos State University of Education, Lagos. Through Cronbach-alpha a reliability form, index value of 0.869 was obtained which revealed that the instrument is reliable for the study. Pearson Product Moment Correlation and regression analysis were used to analyse data and test hypotheses at 0.05 significant level. The findings revealed that socio-emotional factors have a positive relationship with productive human resource management among secondary school teachers in Oredo Local Government Area. The study concluded that priority should be accorded to staff and personnel in an organisation because their quality-of-service delivery is dependent on their psychological disposition. It then recommended that socio-emotional scale be validated so that items that survive the scale can be replicated in future study.

Keywords: Disposition skills, Human resources management, socioeconomic factors, Students.

Introduction

Human resource management is a crucial aspect of any organization, including educational institutions such as schools, since the educational sector also depends on the resourcefulness of its personnel. The effectiveness of human resource management practices in schools can significantly impact on the overall productivity and performance of teachers and staff. Various factors influence human resource management in schools, including socio-economic factors, level of income, remuneration of workers, experience and qualification, political atmosphere, and maturation level. As a resource manager, understanding and addressing socio-emotional factors would go a long way to promote personnel mental health and well-being which in turn promotes quality of productivity. However human resource managers can further introduce interventions such as therapy, social support, and skills training to help individuals develop healthy coping mechanisms and build positive social connections.

According to Sparr, Knipfer, and Willems (2017), resource managers in any organization agree in all measures that human beings or her labour force are important assets due to the nature of services rendered. Having robust staff strength, the management team does not guarantee that the firm human resources component will be a source of competitive advantage. Rather than remain competitive, grow, and diversify such an organisation must ensure that its employees are qualified, placed in appropriate positions, properly trained, managed effectively, and committed to the firm's growth and development. The goal of Human Resources management is to maximise employees' contribution to achieve optimal productivity and effectiveness while simultaneously attaining individual objectives and societal expectations (Sparr, et al. 2017).

The scope of Human Resources extends to all the decisions, strategies, factors, principles, operations, practices, functions, activities, and methods related to the management of people as employees in any type of organisation. All the

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dimensions related to people in their employment relationships and dynamics flow from it (Mamora and Gankar, 2006). Ogunbameru (2008) sees human resources as a management function in an institution, establishment or organisation that is concerned with hiring, motivating, and maintenance of people in an organization. It focuses on the development of people in organizations. Human resources is a designed management system that ensures that human talent is used effectively and efficiently to accomplish organizational goals and objectives. Mamora and Gankar, (2006) noted that Human Resources management is a personnel function concerned with the procurement, development, compensation, integration, and maintenance of personnel of an organization to contribute towards the accomplishments of the organization's objectives.

Invanchevich and Glueck (2013) states that HRM is concerned with the most effective use of people to achieve organisational and individual goals. It is a way of managing people at work so that they give their best to the organisation. Meanwhile, Bath and Valcour (2023); and Dessler (2010) noted that the policies and practices involved in carrying out people or human resources aspects of a management position include recruiting, screening, training, rewarding, and appraisal of human resources management. Generally, HR refers to the management of people in an organisation with activities, policies, and practices involved in obtaining, developing, utilising, evaluating, maintaining, and retaining the appropriate number and skill mix of employees to accomplish the organisations' objectives. In a holistic term, Human Resources (HR) is the art of procuring, developing, and maintaining a competent workforce to achieve the goals of an organization effectively and efficiently. The goal of HR is to maximize employees' contributions to achieve optimal productivity and effectiveness while simultaneously attaining individual objectives (such as having a challenging job and obtaining recognition), and societal objectives such as legal compliance and demonstrating social responsibility.

Boosting a resourceful HR component, the use of socio-emotional variables can never be underestimated. According to Loos, and Trancoso (2014; Lussier, Fitzpatrick, 2016; Rahayu and Mustikasari, 2019) socio-emotional factors are all social and emotional aspects of an individual's life that can impact their overall well-being and behaviors. These factors include relationships with family and friends, emotional regulation, self-esteem, and coping mechanisms. Socio-emotional factors play a crucial role in shaping an individual's personality, behavior, and mental health. A person who has supportive and healthy relationships with family and friends is more likely to have higher self-esteem and better emotional regulation skills. On the other hand, a person who experiences social isolation or has a history of trauma may struggle with emotional regulation and have lower self-esteem. These factors can also influence how individuals interact with others in social contexts, such as in personal relationships, school, work, or community settings. Someone who has a history of trauma may have difficulty trusting others and forming close relationships, while someone with high self-esteem may be more outgoing and confident. (Lussier & Fitzpatrick 2016).

In Ugorgi and Tochukwu (2019) study socio-emotional variables include identified social and emotional features of an individual state of relationship with others, social disposition, psychological state of being, and self-awareness. The awareness and disposition of people define their state of mind towards the discharge of responsibilities. The degree of relationship established by people in a group or cluster defines the interaction level of personnel. The socio-emotional component includes emotional regulation, social environment, emotional intelligence, coping mechanisms, mental health and well-being, self-esteem, compliance, adaptive functioning, autonomy, and interaction with people in an organization. The extent of interaction or relationship of these components is often referred to as the socio-emotional state of an individual. Meanwhile, Abdul and Mohammed (2020); Goleman (2006) expressed socio-emotional factors as those components' variables or conditions in an individual's life that influence their thought pattern, behaviour, reflexes, and general well-being. These factors enable people to manage stress-related conditions and empower them with the ability to manage emotions while also equipping them with skills needed to shape an individual's overall emotional and social development. Meanwhile, Gandhi and Sachdeva (2018); and Sony and Mekoth (2016) identified certain factors that can affect or influence human resource management in schools including:

1. **Income levels:** The income levels of teachers and staff in schools can directly impact their motivation, job satisfaction, and performance. Higher-income levels can lead to higher levels of job satisfaction and retention rates. Conversely, low-income levels can result in job dissatisfaction and high turnover rates, which can negatively impact human resource management practices in schools.
2. **Education levels:** The education levels of teachers and staff in schools also play a significant role in human resource management. Teachers with higher education levels are more likely to have better leadership, communication, and organizational skills, which can positively impact the overall productivity of the school's workforce.
3. **Access to training and development opportunities:** Socio-economic factors such as access to training and development opportunities can also affect human resource management in schools. Teachers and staff who have access to ongoing

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training and development programs are more likely to be motivated, engaged, and productive in their roles. However, those who lack access to such opportunities may feel stagnant and disengaged, leading to decreased productivity and performance.

4. **Work-life balance:** Socio-economic factors can also influence work-life balance for teachers and staff in schools. Those who have access to flexible working arrangements, paid leave, and other benefits that promote a healthy work-life balance are more likely to be satisfied and motivated in their roles. On the other hand, those who struggle to balance work and personal responsibilities may experience higher levels of stress and burnout, negatively impacting their performance and productivity.

The management of human resources in secondary school systems and organisation is a challenge faced by respective resource managers. Some of these challenges are associated with diversity management, employee retention, health status, recruitment of skilled labour, identification of staff with good interpersonal skills, and coping mechanisms among others (Stample and Emmanuel, 2020). Staff who are influenced by these challenges are prone to poor social networking and suffer from poor emotional instability, and underperformance among others (Okoko and Ibara, 2020). Should measures of socio-emotional therapy be adopted to improve the quality-of-service delivery of staff, it would go a long way to promote productive human resources management in secondary schools.

The predictiveness of these variables in the promotion of productive human resource management is such that can propel administrators to create a conducive work environment capable of fostering motivation, engagement, and productivity among teachers (Nyaga, 2013). Through prioritizing the well-being and development of their workforce, schools can enhance overall performance and achieve better outcomes for students. Again, addressing income levels, education levels, access to training and development opportunities, and work-life balance, school administrators can create a positive work environment that promotes motivation, engagement, and productivity among teachers.

Objectives of the study

1. Examine relationships between social factors and Productive human-resource -management among secondary school teachers in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State.
2. Determine relationships between emotional factors and Productive human-resource -management among secondary school teachers in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State.
3. Examine relationships between socio-emotional factors and Productive human-resource -management among secondary school teachers in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State

Hypotheses

1. H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between social factors and Productive human-resource -management among secondary school teachers in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State
2. H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between emotional factors and Productive human-resource -management among secondary school teachers in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State
3. H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between socio-economic factors and Productive human-resource -management among secondary school teachers in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State.

Methodology

The study investigated the correlation between socio-economic factors and productive human resource management among selected secondary school teachers in Edo state. A correlation research design was adopted for this work because it was used to determine the relationship or association that exists between the dependent and independent variables. The target population was public secondary school teachers in Edo State. Purposive and simple random sampling techniques were employed to select 20 participants from 10 secondary schools in Oredo LGA of Edo state to form a sample size of 200 teachers. A self-structured instrument, Correlation Between Socio-Emotional Factors and Productive Human Resource Management Questionnaire (CBSEFPHRMQ) was used to collect data. The instrument consisted of 20 items using a closed-ended format on a 4 Likert point scale. Content validity was affirmed by two experts in the Department of Human Resource Management, Lagos State University of Education, Lagos. Through Cronbach-alpha a reliability form, an index value of 0.869 was obtained, revealing that the instrument is reliable for the study. Pearson Product Moment Correlation and regression analysis were used to analyse data and test hypotheses at a 0.05 significant level.

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Presentation and Analysis of Result

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between social factors and Productive human-resource -management among secondary school teachers in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State

Table 1: Correlation analysis between social factors and productive human resource management

Variables	N	r	sig.(2-tailed)	Decision
Social Factor	200	.893	.023	Significant
Productive Human Management				

Source: Research work (2024)

Table 1 above shows that 200 teachers were captured in this study with a correlation value of .893 which means a positively strong relationship between social factors and productive human resource management is established. Since .05 (P-value) is greater than sig.value of .023, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative which states that there is a significant relationship between social factors and Productive human-resource -management among secondary school teachers is upheld.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between emotional factors and Productive human-resource -management among secondary school teachers in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State

Table 2: Correlation analysis between emotional factors and productive human resource management

Variables	N	r	sig.(2-tailed)	Decision
Emotional Factor	200	.810	.019	Significant
Productive Human Management				

Source: Research work (2024)

Table 2 above shows that 200 teachers were captured in this study with a correlation value of .810 which means a positively strong relationship between emotional factors and productive human resource management is established. However, since .05 (P-value) is greater than sig.value of .019, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative which states that there is a significant relationship between emotional factors and Productive human-resource -management among secondary school teachers is upheld.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between socio-economic factors and Productive human-resource -management among secondary school teachers in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State

Table 3: Correlation analysis between emotional factors and productive human resource management

Linear regression analysis showing socio-emotional factors and productive human resource management in secondary schools coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.897	.313		11.204	.000
Emotional regulation	.802	.559	.794	0.995	.021
Social environment	.737	.691	.692	2.904	.009
Emotional intelligence	.669	.664	.781	1.659	.018
Interaction capacity	.582	.562	.805	2.190	.033
(Constant)	2.906	.062	1.09	11.785	.003

Source: Research work (2024)

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a. Dependent Variable: Productive human resources management

Table 3 above shows that four intervening variables were captured to determine their predictive ability toward productive human resource management in secondary schools in Edo state. However, it further revealed that interaction capability contributed the most with .905, closely followed by emotional regulation with .794, followed by emotional intelligence, and the least contributor social environment with .692 respectively.

Discussion of Findings

The result shows that social factors have a significant relationship with productive human resource management. This outcome agrees with that of Anderson, Loos, and Trancoso (2014); Lussier and Fitzpatrick (2016) who expressed that these variables allow for mutual interaction, establishment of mutual relationships, effective communication, and development of social networking among personnel. A sociable teacher will not only bring about positive performance in students' learning, but it will also bring about an improvement in the quality-of-service delivery by teachers in a school system. Again, it also shows that there is a significant relationship between emotional factors and productive human resource management. An emotionally stable mind would always reciprocate with quality productive human resource management. The findings of this work corroborate with those of Ohreretha et al (2017) who claimed a psychologically stable mind would always lead to better service delivery. A productive human resource manager would always deliver in the discharge of job description, execution, and improved service delivery. They advanced that workers who suffer from various degrees of emotional instability, mental instability, and all forms of psychological imbalance will certainly under-deliver in quality services due to deficiency in emotional factors. Meanwhile, the third hypothesis shows that socio-emotional components do significantly predict productive human resource management in secondary schools. The result from this work conforms with that of Ugorgi and Tochukwu (2019) who expressed that these factors are some of the core determinants of productivity by resource managers. They noted that socio-emotional variables like interaction capability, emotional regulation, emotional intelligence, coping mechanisms, and social environment among others are good predictors because they contributed significantly to productive human resource management in secondary schools. Ultimately, investing in the well-being and development of their workforce by way of socio-emotional interventions can further lead to better results for staff and a more successful educational institution.

Conclusion

The whole concept of Human Resource Management (HRM) thrives best when resource managers learn to maximize labour opportunities both effectively and efficiently. From this work, the researchers concluded that the quality of job tasks is better improved when interaction capability, emotional regulation and disposition, emotional intelligence, and the social environment of personnel is made conducive and given preference in the value chain of production. It also affirmed that socio-emotional factors of staff should be given preference as quantity and quality of service delivery are mostly dependent on the disposition of the workers.

Recommendations

1. Human resource managers should intermittently use a sociometric scale to determine their staff's interaction level.
2. Initiate other significant variables and factors that affect the productivity of staff in any organization
3. The scope of the study for future studies should be expanded to cover staffers of tertiary institutions in the state.
4. Socio-emotional scales should be validated so that future researchers can replicate items that survive the scale in different study areas

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Assessment of Instructional Resources for Teaching and Learning of Basic Technology among Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study was designed to investigate the assessment of basic Technology learning resources among Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria. The research design that was adopted for this study is the descriptive survey method. Four research questions guided the study. The study population comprised all Basic technology teachers in Osun State while the purposive sampling technique was used to select 17 schools and 48 available teachers participated. An adapted questionnaire tagged Learning Resources Assessment Questionnaire (LRAQ) was used as the research instrument. Simple percentages, mean scores, and standard deviation were used to analyze the results. The findings showed that out of 26 learning resources that are required to be available in any secondary school to Basic Technology only 12 (46.2%) are available while 14 (53.8%) learning resources are not available. Some available learning resources are not adequate for teaching and learning Basic Technology, the available learning resources are occasionally used but not frequently used and the barriers to effective use of learning resources for teaching and learning of Basic Technology include low teachers' competence, poor teachers' professional knowledge, poor maintenance culture, non-availability of standard workshops, insufficient power supply, scarcity of teachers, lack of accessibility to learning resources, and resistance to change on the part of the teacher. Based on the findings, suggested recommendations include provision for adequate learning materials for the teaching of Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria, which should be provided by the Ministry of Education and School Management

Keywords: Assessment, Learning resources, Basic Technology, Practical Skills, Metropolis

Introduction

Education globally is experiencing several reforms and the purpose of these reforms is to allow educational stakeholders to perform their responsibilities more efficiently. As a result, students are expected to be equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to deal with the ever-increasing challenges of the modern world. Technology has become an important part of most educational organizations all over the world. No doubt using technology tools provides productive teaching and learning to increase learners' creative and intellectual resources, especially in today's information society.

Technology is considered a step-by-step procedure, a systematic approach to an act to enhance the process of production. Akinde and Adetimirin (2017) described technology as a way of doing things leading to the development of processes and devices which is indispensable to the stable enhancement of the quality of life of human beings through the application of knowledge derived from systematic investigation of natural forces and materials. Nigeria as a country to realize accelerated development in the 21st century, needs qualitative science and technology education in our schools especially at the Junior Secondary Schools level which is invariably the foundation for advanced science and technology education. The Federal Government of Nigeria having realized that the level of utilizing technology of a nation determines the level of advancement and development of such a nation, made her approved the teaching of technological subjects in all the Junior Secondary Schools in Nigeria and named it Introductory Technology now referred to as Basic Technology. Abdul-Ganiyu, Oyeronke, and Adunni (2019), regarded the inclusion of pre-vocational subjects in the Junior Secondary Schools curriculum as the greatest assets of the 9-3-4 system of curriculum."

Basic Technology is one of the pre-vocational subjects offered at the Junior Secondary Schools in Nigeria. It is a preparatory core subject of vocational and technical education. It comprises areas such as carpentry, joinery, masonry, machine fitting, metal fabrication, motor mechanics, automobile, and general works which are capable of equipping the students with the required job skills for self-reliance. The objectives of Basic Technology according to the Federal Republic of Nigeria include providing pre-vocational orientation for further training in technology; providing basic technological literacy for everyday living and stimulating creativity (FRN, 2013). The curriculum content of Basic Technology is designed to achieve these stated objectives.

Basic Technology being one of the skill-oriented subjects bearing in mind the above objectives enables the individual to acquire appropriate skills, abilities, and competence to live in and contribute effectively to the development of his society (Amosa, Ogunlade, and Atobatele, 2015).”It is very important to note that without the knowledge of Basic Technology, Nigeria as a nation might be left behind in the scientific and technological race. This then means that there is a need for adequate commitment to the teaching and training of Basic Technology in our Junior Secondary Schools. The thoroughness in the teaching of introductory technology will lead to the accomplishment of the objectives of vocational and technical education programmes at the higher level of our educational system which is the major plight of Nigeria as a nation. Furtherance of our youths in the skills and other engineering-oriented courses at our tertiary level of education is highly dependent on their earlier knowledge and skills acquired at the secondary school level (Arop, Umanah, & Effiong, 2015).” Looking at the alarming rate of unemployment in the country, the need for the nation to embrace the teaching and learning of vocational and technical courses in our schools towards building an individual for self-reliance should be given the utmost priority.

The subjects like Basic Technology whose goal is to expose students to the world of business, achievement scores only are insufficient to measure whether the goals of the subject have been achieved or not (Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council, NERDC, 2013).” Studies carried out by Okenjom, (2018), revealed that some students depend on rote memory that is, cramming facts and obtaining high scores rather than understanding Basic Technology concepts to reason out solutions. To achieve the acquisition of technical and practical skills at the lower craft level, the contributions of the teacher of Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools are paramount. Students are expected to complete secondary school not only by having high scores in Basic Technology but being able to effectively apply the knowledge and competence gained in the classroom to solve personal and societal challenges (Onele, 2018). Subjects such as Basic Technology is practically oriented which requires that the students master the knowledge and skills for better performance in examinations. The emphasis laid on the transfer of basic skills in Basic Technology has placed much demand on the selection and application of appropriate learning materials and the use of the proper methodology in teaching.

Traditionally, teaching and learning of Basic Technology and other subjects in Nigerian schools are done in a structured way with emphasis on writing, reading, and listening to teachers' talk. National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) (2013) however posited that teachers must diversify their teaching techniques if they are to successfully teach students of different abilities and learning preferences. Schools have therefore applied various approaches over the years in teaching students at various levels. It has been noted with dismay, however, that teachers are still using one or a combination of two or more conventional teaching methods such as lecture, discussion, and demonstration to teach Basic Technology without using appropriate learning materials (Omiola, Enuwa, Awoyemi, & Adebayo, 2012).”

In developed countries, teachers use learning materials and new technologies to facilitate learning. These learning resources are produced and kept in educational resource centres (ERC) in all educational citadels of learning. Educational resources centres (ERC) are known by many names such as Audio-Visual Centres, Learning Resource Centres, Educational Technology Centres, and Instructional Resources Centre (Badmus, Adebajo & Ganiyu, 2021). In developing countries like Nigeria, research has it that 80% of teachers still make use of the conventional or traditional method of teaching to facilitate knowledge, this may look boring to the students after a while and the job of a teacher becomes only effective when he can pass knowledge to the students and the students is convinced by what is been delivered to them (Uche, Abdullahi, Asogwa, & Ofoegbu, 2016).”

According to the NBTE (2013), Basic Technology deals with the fundamentals of engineering and technology which are to be taught as an integration of Technical Drawing, Building Construction, Woodwork, Metalwork, Electrical and Electronics, Automobile-mechanics, Food Technology and Computer Education. The inclusion of Basic Technology or Introductory Technology in the school curriculum calls for a well-planned curriculum and NERDC (2004) suggested some useful and relevant learning materials/resources to prevent the teacher from wasting much time in trying to explain concepts in abstract. They also suggested that there should be a shift in the focus of the conventional method of teaching Basic Technology to incorporate technological tools that would engage students in entrepreneurial activities. Therefore, the place of learning

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resources in the successful implementation of curriculum cannot be over-emphasized as a channel through which information or messages can be disseminated to learners.”

Qaiser, Hussain, Naseer, Din, and Khalid (2017) stated that learning resources are human and non-human materials supports or aids that a teacher uses to pass information to the students in the classroom. Apart from its ability to enhance the positive attitude of learners towards learning, it also helps them in making use of their various functioning sense organs to the maximum. According to Shazli (2019), human resources are support staff and subject matter experts who serve as resources for teachers and learners. These people have advanced knowledge and experience dealing with specialized learning resources for example Teachers, Technicians, Technologists, Workshop or Laboratory Attendants, Operators, other examples of learning resources that teachers often use are Textbooks, Chalkboards, Posters, Charts, Pictures, Computers, Flannels Graphs, Projectors, Radios, Televisions, audiovisual, Tapes, Workshops, Drawing Room, Transparencies, Machines, Hand Tools, Photographs, Models among others. All these are referred to as non-human resources. When these learning resources are being utilized properly, it helps minimize the problem of overpopulation and overcrowding in the classroom.

Simeon (2019) classified media (resources) into four; printed media, graphics, photography and electronics. Likewise, Abdu-Raheem (2016) agreed with this by classifying media (resources) into printed, projected (electronic), and non-projected media. When a medium of learning experience is well designed, produced, and validated, it becomes a valuable resource that has the flexibility of serving a single learner as well as a sizeable or large class of learners (Adekola, 2018). According to Adekunbi, (2018), learning resources are a broad range of information-carrying resources that constitute an integral component of classroom teaching and learning that are utilized in a learning process with the hope of facilitating effective and efficient communication in teaching and learning process. These are all information channel that is processed through the use of devices that could assist learners in seeing, hearing, feeling and in becoming aware and alive with the information being communicated to them. Therefore, for effective teaching of Basic Technology to take place, the use of learning resources cannot be compromised.

According to Matazu (2022), learning resources play an essential part in the teaching-learning processes among which are as follows: improving students’ memory levels; making the teaching-learning process easier; increasing the rate of assimilation of students; serving as instruments for teachers to utilize in correcting incorrect impressions and illustrating ideas that students cannot easily forget; assist in giving the body of knowledge under debate a sense of actuality; it personalizes teaching and stimulates teachers’ inventiveness; allow students and teachers to participate in concrete learning activities that develop the concept of self-evaluation. Hence, it is practically impossible to teach Basic Technology without learning resources. This is because they constitute an important component in the teaching and learning environment (Matazu, 2022). They can be regarded as the vehicle that carries messages or information from a transmitting source (teacher) to the receiver (learner). Salaudin, (2020) expressed those students cannot fully understand most of the concepts of Basic Technology when taught without learning resources. As a pre-vocational subject, Basic Technology must be taught practically and not only theoretically for it to be meaningful, understood, and appreciated by students. Teachers should therefore expect to emphasize the understanding of Basic Technology and not on collection of information or memorization.

Becta (2008), found that many secondary school teachers lacked the knowledge and skills to use learning resources most especially computers, and were not enthusiastic about the changes and integration of supplementary learning associated with bringing computers into their teaching practices. Sicilia (2015) found that the problem of lack of time exists for teachers in many aspects of their work as it affects their ability to complete tasks, with some of the participant teachers specifically stating which aspects of ICT require more time. These include the time needed to locate Internet advice, prepare lessons, explore and practice using the technology, deal with technical problems, and receive adequate training. Furthermore, the barrier most frequently referred to in the literature is the lack of effective training (Beggs, 2020).

Despite the introduction of Basic Technology, the aspiration for white-collar jobs and unemployment have persistently been on the increase. This problem has been attributed partly to poor teaching and learning methods which do not allow mastery of the contents adopted by the teachers in teaching Basic Technology. In an attempt to solve this problem, findings have revealed that students cannot fully understand most of the concepts of Basic Technology when taught without learning resources. Although previous studies have used different methods to improve student performance in this regard, persistence failure in Basic Technology is alarming and requires replicable solutions. As a pre-vocational subject, Basic Technology must be taught practically and not only theoretically for it to be meaningful, understood, and appreciated by students. The learning contents need to be incorporated with motivating components to stimulate students’ creativity and engage them with the content of the subject. This would strengthen students’ capabilities to effectively apply the knowledge and competence gained in the classroom to solve personal and societal challenges. Public Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria, still find it difficult to make available some learning resources probably due to cost implications or the stress embedded in the acquisition

Assessment of Instructional...(Badmus, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601928>

of those resources at the detriment of students' optimal academic performance (Ajadi, 2016). In some cases, those who even have learning facilities are not judiciously making use of them due to a lack of appropriate knowledge of their usage by the teachers, especially electronic-aided facilities like computers and other internet-enabling devices (Afolabi, 2020).

Hence, the need to investigate demystifying Basic Technology by making it more interesting, engaging, friendly, and applicable to real-life situations to stimulate students' creativity and better academic understanding is to ensure the learning resources are available, utilized, and frequently used. Given the foregoing, the study was set to investigate the assessment of learning resources for teaching Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

This research aimed to assess the basic technology learning resources among junior secondary schools in Osogbo metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study:

1. identify available learning resources for teaching Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria.” “
2. determine whether the available learning resources are adequate for the teaching of Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria.”
3. assess how frequently the available learning resources are used for teaching Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria, and
4. investigate barriers to the use of learning resources in the teaching of Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria.” “

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What learning resources are available for teaching Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria?
2. To what extent are available learning resources adequate for the teaching of Basic Technology in your school?
3. How frequently are the available learning resources utilized for teaching Basic Technology in Junior schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria?
4. What are the barriers to the use of learning resources in teaching and learning of Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria?

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study was the descriptive survey method. The population for this study consists of all Basic Technology teachers at the Junior Secondary Schools across Osun State.

A purposive sampling technique was adopted to select Basic Technology teachers because in a school these teachers are not many so the available Basic Technology teachers were used for the study. A total of seventeen (17) secondary schools in Osogbo Metropolis were purposively selected due to the presence of Introductory Technology laboratories in the schools. In all, 48 Basic Technology teachers are available in these schools and participated as respondents.

The research instrument that was used for the study was a structured questionnaire adapted from Lawrence Femi Ademiluyi, (2019). This study research instrument titled “Learning Resources Assessment Questionnaire (LRAQ)” which comprises five (5) sections: Section A, B, C, D, and E.” “Section A borders on demographic information of the respondents; Section B focuses on the availability of learning resources; Section C deals with adequacy of learning resources; Section D centered on the frequency of use of learning resources while Section E sought for the factors or barriers to the use of learning resources.”

The instrument was given to four experts for face and content validity, two experts from Basic Technology, one from Educational Technology, and one from Educational Evaluation. Their comments and observations were incorporated into the final copy of the instrument before it was administered. Thus, this improved the quality of the instrument. The instrument was piloted and processed for a reliability test. It was analyzed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient yielded 0.76.

Descriptive statistics like frequency distribution, simple percentages, mean score, and standard deviation were used to address the stated research questions through the use of SPSS.”

Results

Research Question 1: What types of learning resources are available for teaching Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Available Learning Resources for Teaching Basic Technology in Junior Secondary School

S/N	Learning Resources	Available	%	Not Available	%	Decision
1	Workshop	32	66.7	16	33.3	Available
2	Hammer	36	75.0	12	25.0	Available
3	Saw	34	70.8	14	29.2	Available
4	Hand file	28	58.3	20	41.7	Available
5	Pliers	32	66.7	16	33.3	Available
6	Try-Square	36	75.0	12	25.0	Available
7	Circular Saw	8	16.7	40	83.3	Not Available
8	Surface Planner	12	25.0	36	75.0	Not Available
9	Thicknesser	34	70.8	14	29.2	Available
10	Wood lathe	16	33.3	32	66.7	Not Available
11	Centre lathe	11	22.9	37	77.1	Not Available
12	Power Saw	10	20.8	38	79.2	Not Available
13	Pedestal grinder	23	47.9	25	52.1	Not Available
14	Milling Machine	9	18.8	39	81.2	Not Available
15	Learning Audio Tape	18	37.5	30	62.5	Not Available
16	Television/Monitor Set	21	43.7	27	56.3	Not Available
17	Audio C.D's on Technology	36	75.0	12	25.0	Available
18	Video Players & Recorders	10	20.8	38	79.2	Not Available
19	Computer (Monitor, C.P.U & Printers)	14	29.2	34	70.8	Not Available
20	Projectors	5	10.4	43	89.6	Not Available
21	Video CDs	15	31.2	33	68.8	Not Available
22	Chalkboard	36	75.0	12	25.0	Available
23	Wall Posters on Technology	40	83.3	8	16.7	Available
24	Photographs on Technology	34	70.8	14	29.2	Available
25	Models on Technology	20	41.7	28	58.3	Not Available
26	Printed Media (Textbooks & Workbook)	36	75.0	12	25.0	Available

Source: Fieldwork

Table 1 revealed that learning resources like circular saws, surface planers, wood lathes, power saws, centre lathes, milling machines, video player recorders, computers, projectors, wall posters, and models are not available in the school to teach Basic Technology, this is because the percentage scores of those learning resources are below 50% which is the middle percentage of 100. Learning resources like workshops, hammers, saws, handfiles, pliers, try-square, thicknessers, chalkboards, wall posters, photographs, models, and printed media are available to use. The implication of the results showed out of 26 learning resources 12 are available while 14 learning resources are not available.

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Research Question 2: To what extent are available learning resources adequate for the teaching of Basic Technology in your school?

Table 2: Adequacy of Available Learning Resources for Teaching and Learning of Basic Technology

S/N	Learning Resources	Adequate	%	Inadequate	%	Decision
1	Workshop	28	58.3	20	41.7	Adequate
2	Hammer	32	66.7	16	33.3	Adequate
3	Saw	12	25.0	36	75.0	Not Adequate
4	Hand file	40	83.3	8	16.7	Adequate
5	Pliers	34	70.8	14	29.2	Adequate
6	Try-Square	20	41.7	28	58.3	Not Adequate
7	Circular Saw	2	4.2	46	95.8	Not Adequate
8	Surface Planner	5	10.4	43	89.6	Not Adequate
9	Thicknesser	16	33.3	32	66.7	Not Adequate
10	Wood lathe	34	70.8	14	29.2	Adequate
11	Centre lathe	2	4.2	46	95.8	Not Adequate
12	Power Saw	7	14.6	41	85.4	Not Adequate
13	Pedestal grinder	36	75.0	12	25.0	Adequate
14	Milling Machine	6	12.5	42	87.5	Not Adequate
15	Learning Audio Tape	36	75.0	12	25.0	Adequate
16	Television/Monitor Set	22	45.8	26	54.2	Not Adequate
17	Audio C.D's on Technology	32	66.7	16	33.3	Adequate
18	Video Players & Recorders	19	39.6	29	60.4	Not Adequate
19	Computer (Monitor, C.P.U & Printers)	28	58.3	20	41.3	Adequate
20	Projectors	3	6.3	45	93.7	Not Adequate
21	Video CDs	32	66.7	16	33.3	Adequate
22	Chalkboard	36	75.0	12	25.0	Adequate
23	Wall Posters on Technology	38	79.2	10	20.8	Adequate
24	Photographs on Technology	34	70.8	14	29.2	Adequate
25	Models on Technology	16	33.3	32	66.7	Not Adequate
26	Printed Media (Textbooks & Workbook)	40	83.3	8	16.7	Adequate

Source: Field work

Table 3 shows that learning resources such as circular saw, surface planer, wood lathe, centre lathe, power saw, milling machine, learning audio tape, video player computers, projector, video CD and models are not adequate to teach Basic Technology to Junior Secondary students. Out of 26 learning resources examined 14 were adequate while 12 learning resources were not adequate because their percentages were below 50%.

Research Question 3: How frequent are the available learning resources utilized for teaching Basic Technology in Junior secondary schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria?

Table 3: Frequent Use of Learning Resources to Teach Basic Technology

S/N	Learning Resources	Frequently		Occasionally		Rarely		Never		Mean Score	Std. Dev.
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%		

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1	Workshop	20	41.7	11	22.9	9	18.8	8	16.7	2.896	1.134
2	Hammer	17	35.5	14	29.2	12	25.0	5	10.4	2.896	1.016
3	Saw	14	29.2	17	35.5	5	10.4	12	25.0	2.688	1.151
4	Hand file	10	20.8	9	18.8	20	41.7	8	16.7	2.417	1.028
5	Pliers	25	52.1	12	25.0	8	16.7	3	6.3	3.229	0.951
6	Try-Square	20	41.7	10	20.8	9	18.8	8	16.7	2.854	1.167
7	Circular Saw	5	10.4	10	20.8	16	33.3	17	35.4	2.063	0.998
8	Surface Planner	3	6.3	4	8.3	25	52.1	15	33.3	1.875	0.815
9	Thicknesser	20	41.7	10	20.8	9	18.8	8	16.7	2.854	1.167
10	Wood lathe	5	10.4	3	6.3	23	47.9	17	35.4	1.917	0.919
11	Centre lathe	2	4.2	5	10.4	17	20.8	24	64.6	1.542	0.849
12	Power Saw	5	10.4	5	10.4	10	20.8	28	58.3	1.729	1.026
13	Pedestal grinder	7	14.6	8	16.7	25	52.1	5	16.7	2.292	0.922
14	Milling Machine	2	4.2	9	18.8	25	52.1	12	25.0	2.021	0.785
15	Learning Audio Tape	9	18.8	5	10.4	17	35.4	17	35.4	2.125	1.104
16	Television/Monitor Set	10	20.8	9	18.8	20	41.7	8	16.7	2.417	1.028
17	Audio CD's on Technology	25	52.1	12	25.0	8	16.7	3	6.3	3.229	0.951
18	Video Players & Recorders	20	41.7	10	20.8	9	18.8	8	16.7	2.854	1.167
19	Computer (Monitor, C.P.U & Printers)	17	35.5	14	29.2	12	25.0	5	10.4	2.896	1.016
20	Projectors	20	41.7	10	20.8	9	18.8	8	16.7	2.854	1.167
21	Video CDs	14	29.2	17	35.5	5	10.4	12	25.0	2.688	1.151
22	Chalkboard	10	20.8	9	18.8	20	41.7	8	16.7	2.417	1.028
23	Wall Posters on Technology	25	52.1	12	25.0	8	16.7	3	6.3	3.229	0.951
24	Photographs on Technology	17	35.5	14	29.2	12	25.0	5	10.4	2.896	1.017
25	Models on Technology	20	41.7	10	20.8	9	18.8	8	16.7	2.854	1.167
26	Printed Media (Textbooks & Workbook)	17	35.5	14	29.2	12	25.0	5	10.4	2.896	1.016
Grand Mean Average									2.563		

Source: Field work

Table 3 revealed that the average mean score obtained was 2.563 which is slightly above 2.5 mid-point. The implication of this is that learning resources for teaching and learning Basic Technology are occasionally used but not frequently used.”

Research Question 4: What are the barriers to the use of learning resources in teaching Basic Technology in Junior secondary schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria?

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Table 4: Barriers to the Use of Learning Resources in Basic Technology in Schools

S/N	ITEM	SA		A		D		SD		Mean	Std D.
		No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%		
1	Low teacher competence in effective learning resource utilization negatively affects teaching outcome	20	41.7	4	8.3	13	27.1	11	22.9	2.313	1.240
2	Poor teacher's professional knowledge and technical know-how to teach practical skill content areas of Basic Technology leads to low utilization of learning materials	26	54.2	10	20.8	6	12.5	6	12.5	1.833	1.079
3	Poor maintenance culture of existing learning materials especially projected and manipulative types hinders the utilization of learning materials	27	56.3	10	20.8	5	10.0	5	10.4	1.771	1.036
4	Non-availability of standard and functional workshops greatly affects the teaching and learning of Basic Technology	21	43.8	10	20.8	8	16.7	9	18.8	2.104	1.173
5	Insufficient power supply makes the operating of available Basic Technology equipment difficult	21	43.8	3	6.3	13	27.1	11	22.9	2.293	1.254
6	The scarcity of Basic Technology teachers in Junior Secondary Schools constitutes great problems in instructional delivery	18	37.5	13	27.1	9	18.8	8	16.7	2.146	1.111
7	Basic Technology teachers develop apathy to workshop practice due to lack of motivation."	24	50.0	8	16.7	8	16.7	8	16.7	2.000	1.167
8	Lack of accessibility to learning resources	21	43.8	15	31.3	8	16.7	4	8.3	1.896	0.973
9	Resistance to change from traditional methods	17	35.4	9	18.8	12	25.0	10	20.8	2.313	1.170
10	Lack of opportunities for in-service trainings for Basic Technology teachers to update their knowledge on resource development leads to poor utilization of learning materials in the teaching of the subject	24	50.0	8	16.7	6	12.5	10	20.8	2.042	1.219
11	Lack of finance to acquire needed learning materials impacts negatively on the teaching and learning of Basic Technology	21	43.8	16	33.3	4	8.3	7	14.6	1.938	1.060
12	Teachers are faced with insufficient time allocation to accommodate effective learning materials utilization in Basic Technology	21	43.8	12	25.0	9	18.8	6	12.5	2.000	1.072
Grand Mean Score				2.054							

Source: Fieldwork

Assessment of Instructional...(Badmus, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601928>

Table 4 revealed that virtually all the statements are considered as factors or barriers to the use of learning resources for effective teaching and learning of Basic Technology. The grand mean score obtained is 2.054 which is below 2.5 of the mid-point of 4. The result implies that low teachers' competence, poor teachers' professional knowledge, poor maintenance culture, non-availability of standard workshops, insufficient power supply, scarcity of teachers, lack of accessibility to learning resources, and resistance to change on the part of the teacher are all barriers to the effective use of learning resource for teaching and learning of Basic Technology.

Discussion of Findings

Based on the analysis of data, findings from this study showed that some of the important learning resources were not available for teaching Basic Technology in Junior Schools in Osogbo Metropolis. This result was in line with the outcome of the study of Okoji and Olubayo (2021) which revealed that not all the relevant learning resources are available to teach students in primary schools. Cohen, Raudenbush, and Ball (2012) whose study found that some learning resources are available while others are not. Chukwu, Eze, and Agada (2016) revealed that there is little extent of availability of instructional materials in junior secondary schools (upper basic) in the Enugu education zone.

The study found that available learning resources are not adequate for teaching and learning of Basic Technology and this finding is in line with the results of Okoli and Okorie (2015) in their study which revealed that business studies education facilities are lowly adequate, and compliant textbooks are lowly adequate. Okoroma (2006) also agreed that learning materials are in short supply in Nigerian secondary schools.

The outcome revealed 48 Basic Technology teachers who frequently access and confirm the available learning resources used for teaching Basic Technology in your school. Findings have revealed that teachers in Nigeria's public schools do not explore to the fullest the use of the educational media accessible for both teaching and learning the result was in line with Abdelraheem and Al-Rabani (2005) who found out that learning resources in schools are not well-utilized to expectation to improve learning outcome.

In the study, it was revealed that barriers to effective use of learning resources for teaching and learning of Basic Technology include low teachers' competence, poor teachers' professional knowledge, poor maintenance culture, non-availability of standard workshops, insufficient power supply, scarcity of teachers, lack of accessibility to learning resources, and resistance to change on the part of the teacher. The findings were supported by the finding of Elom (2014) which stated that factors militating against the teaching of Basic Technology in Abakaliki areas of Ebonyi State include outdated methods of teaching, ill-equipment in the workshops, no practical lessons for students, funding and financing are improperly done.

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, it can be concluded that the availability of learning materials influences teaching Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo metropolis of Osun state. However, lack of accessibility to learning resources has been seen as one of the factors hindering Basic Technology teachers from using learning materials for Basic Technology teaching. In addition, some of the required learning resources to carry out effective teaching and learning of Basic Technology are fairly available while others are not. These fairly available learning resources are not regularly utilized by Basic Technology teachers. Several factors were found to inhibit effective provision and utilization of learning resources, among the factors are non-availability of standard and functional workshop which greatly affect the teaching and learning of Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo metropolis of Osun State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from the study, the researcher recommends as follows: “

1. Adequate learning materials for the teaching of Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools should be provided by the Ministry of Education and School Management.” “
2. Basic Technology teachers should make efforts in the utilization of available learning resources and endeavour to improvise those not available or inadequate to improve learning and make the subject attractive through involving the students in practical sessions.
3. Students should also be involved in the improvisation and use of learning resources as they learn more from what they do.
4. Training and retraining must be provided for teachers who are to teach Basic Technology using learning resources to assist them in acquiring necessary skills.

Assessment of Instructional...(Badmus, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601928>

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Comparative Analysis between School-Effectiveness-Variables and Achievement in Quantitative Economics Concepts among Secondary School Students in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the extent to which School Effectiveness variables predict secondary school student's academic achievements in quantitative Economics in Osun State. The study adopted non-experimental research design of correlational type. The population of the study consists of all government senior secondary schools class two Economics students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Osun state. A sample size of 1080 students (male 445 and female 635) were selected from the target population using multistage sampling technique. Results from the study revealed a positive relationship among school administrative practice, school activities, school learning culture, school ethos and students' academic achievement in Quantitative Economics. Findings also revealed that School effectiveness variables significantly predict students' academic achievement in quantitative Economics ($R = 0.322, P < 0.05$). It was concluded that School Effectiveness variables significantly contributed to prediction of students' academic achievement in Quantitative Economics. The study recommended that school administrative practices should be properly set by the school leaders, school activities should not be overlooked by the school administrators and school learning culture should be officially guided by a written template to improve students' academic achievement.

Keywords: School Effectiveness, Students' Academic Achievement and Quantitative Economics

Introduction

School is generally perceived as the centre of learning, where knowledge and ideas are generated and shared, to ease human standard of living. A wide acceptable school of thought refers to school as a place where effective mankind is nurtured to contribute effectively to societal development. Also larger percentage of formal education is received in the school. Therefore education is expected to make man more effective. Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014) expects that education in Nigeria should among others, contribute to national development through high-level relevant manpower training, acquisition of both physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to be self-reliant and useful members of the society, promoting and encouraging scholarship and community service, forging and cementing national unity, promoting national and international understanding and interactions, developing the intellectual capability of individuals to understand and appreciate their local and external environments, developing and inculcating proper values for the survival of individuals and the society.

In order to achieve the aforementioned tasks, Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) in May, 2008 introduced new senior secondary school curriculum, which commenced in September, 2011. The curriculum was planned to consolidate new basic education programme in the area of human capital development. Economics as one of the elective subjects offered in the senior secondary school is considered appropriate to actualise the dreams outlined by NERDC, particularly on human capital development.

Economics as social science subject plays a significant role in human capital development; it sensitizes students about ways to minimize cost and maximize benefit. It goes a long way to explain the ways by which man can make rational decisions on ways of doing things. Economics as a social science subject, serves as the basis for understanding the complexities of how resources are managed to minimize cost and waste with a view to yielding more benefits. The subject looks at how governments, businesses, societies, households and individuals make decisions about how, when and where to best use their resources. Economics involves many theoretical and conceptual models to study behaviour and predict how entities will respond to given changes in market conditions and fiscal policies, among other factors (Zhao, Li, Wang, Zhou & Luo, 2022).

Comparative Analysis between... (Adebisi & Bello, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603539>

The subject builds mathematical models to formulate hypotheses where theories are derived to explain interactions among contingences in human behaviours. The use of Mathematics in Economics allows economists to precisely define and test economic theories against real world data. Similarly, use of mathematics models allow Economics to make information to be concise, precise, and allows adequate treatment to the yet to be determined variables. Economic policies and decisions are rarely made without mathematical models; because mathematical models allow Economics concepts to be far away from ordinary abstractions as they present concepts in Economics in such a way that issues will be quantifiably presented.

In spite of the importance of Economics and the huge benefits derivable from using mathematical models and equations to explain human reactions and behaviours regarding ends and satisfactions. Previous studies over the years indicate that there are continuous under-achievement in Economics at the secondary school level, especially in the concepts that involve calculations and data responses. Obiezu (2018) reported that the academic performance of secondary school students in the Senior Secondary Certificate Examinations (SSCE) has taken a dramatic decline in recent times. According to Abubakar (2013) students' achievement in Economics fluctuates yearly. Besides, Akira (2013), Okoro (2013) and Duruji, Azuh and Oviasogie (2014) corroborate the fact that the declining in students' achievement worries parents, teachers, school administrators, and other stakeholders in the educational system in Nigeria. Indeed, the achievement did not measure up with other subjects when compared with the resources invested on education in general. Considering Economics as an important subject that exposes students to developmental issues, the under-achievement of students in the subject call for investigation and remediation, despite the enormous government investments on education in Osun state.

Studies in and outside of Nigeria are concerned about the problem of under-achievement of students in Economics, but much has not been done in some areas, particularly in the section A of paper II of Economics questions that involves statistics and mathematical concepts, which is referred to as Quantitative Economics. In addition, WAEC Chief Examiner's reports pointed out that, students' performances in the essay part of Economics examination (section A) are not encouraging. It was reported that students had poor understanding of data presentation and basic mathematical skills to tackle the questions in the data response section, also larger percent of the candidates show great deficiency in the application of graphical representation to economic analysis and this resulted in poor performance in questions where analyses are required (WAEC 2017; 2020 and 2021). Furthermore, in the WASSCE Chief Examiner's Report, it was identified that the students' weaknesses include; poor graphical representations to economic analysis and simple calculations, use of wrong terminologies, failure to expatiate points, among others (WAEC 2017 & 2018 and NBC/FGN 2022).

Ejimonye, Eneogu and Ugwuanyi (2017) opined that the under-achievement of students in Economics could generally be attributed to students' level of understanding to general aspect of Economics which also assisted with students' level of preparation and readiness for the examination. Ejimonye et al. (2017) discovered that students with poor mathematical and statistical background are usually frightened by mathematical and statistical related subjects, such as Economics. Moreover, the use of wide range of complex mathematics and statistical procedures to analyse Economic phenomena induce students' phobia for the Quantitative Economics, and thereafter affects their overall achievement (Dawson, 2013).

Spring (2013) noted that fluctuations in students' achievement in public examinations could be attributed to several factors which include inadequate learning materials, students' engagement in other hobbies aside schooling, pressure from home, societal factors *etcetera*. WAEC (2007) revealed that students performed poorly due to lack of adequate preparation, shortage of teachers in schools, poor use and inadequate coverage of the syllabus, un-conducive school environment and infrastructural facilities. Others include inability to understand questions that demand high level of thinking, shallow and poor answers to questions due to poor command of English among others. Kola and Sunday (2015) noted that when the foundation at the primary and junior secondary schools is not sound, there will be difficulties in understanding some critical problems in senior secondary schools which automatically lead to failure in examination at the senior secondary schools.

Other empirical studies on students' achievement in Economics revealed that variables such as learners' readiness, engagement in other business apart from schooling, students' poor attitude and poor self-esteem, poor teaching methodology and length of time allocated for reading are equally responsible for the students' persistent under-achievement in senior secondary school Economics (Kola & Sunday, 2015; Obiezu, 2018; Spring, 2013). Although, studies have been pointing toward several factors that have serious implications on students' achievement in Economics at secondary school, but variables that relate to viability of schools which center on school effectiveness have not been adequately and jointly investigated. Therefore, this study intends to investigate some of school effectiveness variables on students' achievements on the quantitative concepts of Economics.

Adewale and Abiodun (2009), while developing and validating teachers' evaluation of school effectiveness scale outlined school administration, school activities, students cognitive domain, inspectorate role, societal expectations, students'

Comparative Analysis between... (Adebisi & Bello, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603539>

empowerment and teachers' job performance as some of the schools' effectiveness variables. Other factors as outlined by other studies include; school location, school ethos and school learning culture (Reynolds, Teddlie, Creemers & Scheerens, 2019). This study will examine, school administrative practices, school ethos, school learning culture and school activities.

School effectiveness is a construct that is diverse in content; it depends mainly on the direction the researcher is working towards. However, Scheerens (2019) claimed that at the heart of all school effectiveness study is an attempt to explain how school inputs, context of schooling, and school processes affect school's outputs. Also school effectiveness includes the factors input by the school, as well as the processes involved in attaining and achieving meaningful output. Studies on school effectiveness usually center on input-output processes; instructions and materials workability, students' background and location (Akanni, 2020, Dangara, 2016).

School administration is a broad concept that explains all the areas related to school operations as an academic entity. Administrator of school oversees the daily operations of the school and coordinates the schools' system of operations. Suleima, Mustapha and Bukar (2016) referred to school administration as the leadership operations or styles employed by the school leaders (principal and other heads) in the day to day running of the school affairs in order to guide the system to achieve its goals and meet societal expectations (Rusok, Samy & Bhaumik 2023). Similarly, Administrator schedules several activities in the school to keep the system moving towards its stated goals. School administration encompasses categories of administrative practices that aid smooth process of the schools' inputs to achieve the desired outputs that represent the school in the society (Kieti, Maithya & Mulwa 2017). An administrator put many activities together to achieve this, some of it, are regarded as school activities.

School activities are the set of programmes put in place by the School administrators to provide opportunity for the learners or students to be involved in the life of the school, and these are guided by the school norms, beliefs and values. The norms, beliefs and values that are parts of the factors guiding the school activities are regarded as the school ethos. Ethos means custom or character in Greek. It is referred to as the character, custom or personality that balances passion and caution. Graham (2012) defines ethos as the unique pervasive atmosphere or mood of the organisation as it is created from the activities or the behaviour of members through their social interactions and matters associated with the environment. According to some studies, a good school ethos is created by strong academic atmosphere, high expectations for students' success, and positive rewards on landmark achievements (Kjellstrom 2017; Kutsyuruba, Klinger & Hussain 2015; Modin, Laftman & Ostberg 2017). Kutsyuruba *et al.* (2015) explains that school ethos and related notions such as school climate and some school contextual features are recognised as central to students' achievement and well-being.

Warin (2017) asserts that school ethos is also more likely to promote constructive student behaviours and a shared sense of belonging that fosters positive student outcomes. School ethos is the prevalent characteristics, school tone, spirit or sentiment informing an identifiable entity involving human life and interactions, school ethos embraces factors that contribute to the smooth running of the school such as activities and human relations within the school. Smith (2003) maintains that school ethos embraces all aspects of school culture, climate and philosophy that impinge directly on students' affective and cognitive learning which are perceived by all school's stakeholders.

School ethos is experienced at the school's members of staff and students relations level and encompasses the beliefs, values and norms that shape the way that teachers and students relate, interact, and behave towards one another (Modin, Laftman and Ostberg. 2017). It is an aspect of the school's transparent value system, teachers' conduct towards students, as well as the implementation of policies regarding discipline and rewards (Kjellstrom, Holmin, Saenger, Jarl & Modin, 2017, Saminathen, Stephanie & Modin 2020). Therefore, school ethos contributes largely to learning, it is part of what encouraged students to learn effectively; it prepares and empowers students' interactions in the society. Schools with good ethos encourage smooth learning culture for students.

School learning culture has often been considered in terms of the environment and experiences created by teachers for students to learn. Learning culture is the collective, dynamic and experiences that are structured by the organisation's leaders in such a way that the subordinates have opportunities to investigate, explore and take risks in developing new ideas and insights to reach the higher level (Chanani & Wibowo. 2019). School learning culture is based on the experiences which provide templates for future actions based on how we do things in an organisation to produce effective outcome. It often shapes the way people think and how they act. Learning cultures correlate strongly with increased students' achievement and motivation, and with teachers' productivity and satisfaction (Sheela & Claris. 2015).

In a nutshell, school effectiveness variables that include school administrative practices, school activities, school ethos and school learning cultures are considered to be significantly influenced student's achievement in some subjects, but literatures are silent on their contributions to the achievement of students in Economics generally and particularly in Quantitative

Comparative Analysis between... (Adebisi & Bello, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603539>

Economics. This study, therefore, focuses on the connection of the indicator variables of school effectiveness and how they affect students' achievement in Quantitative Economics in senior secondary schools. Consequently, their relative and holistic contribution in predicting the criterion variable (Academic Achievement of the students in Quantitative Economics).

School is considered as the centre of learning to ease the human living conditions and solve varieties of human challenges, therefore school effectiveness is paramount to students' level of performance in their academic endeavor. Over years studies and reports has been directed towards the fluctuation in the level of academic achievements of students in Economics particularly in the concepts that involve mathematics and statistics that is known as Quantitative Economics. Meanwhile several factors and variables, such as parental background, school location, and Student engagement and so on had been investigated on students' achievement in Economics. But it seems their dearth of literatures on school effectiveness variables and students' academic achievement in Economics, particularly on the students' academic achievement in Quantitative Economics.

Therefore, this study investigated the relative and holistic contribution school effectiveness variable (that include school administrative practices, school activities, school learning culture and school ethos) on students' academic achievement of in Quantitative Economics.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of this study are to:

1. Investigate the relationship between school effectiveness variables (school administrative practices, school activities, school learning culture, school ethos) and students' achievement in Quantitative Economics.
2. examine school effectiveness variables (school administrative practices, school activities, school learning culture, school ethos) as predictors of students' achievement in Quantitative Economic
3. Investigate the most influential school effectiveness variables (school administrative practices, school activities, school learning culture, school ethos) in predicting students' achievement in Quantitative Economics.
4. Outline the predictor variables that do not contribute significantly to the prediction model of the study.

Research Questions

In order to guide the study, the following research questions were raised:

1. What type of relationship exists between school effectiveness variables (School Administrative practices, School activities, School learning culture, School ethos) and students' achievement in Quantitative Economic in Public Secondary Schools?
2. Does the obtained regression equation resulting from the set of predictor variables; school effectiveness variables (school administrative practices, school activities, school learning culture, school ethos) allow a reliable prediction of students' achievement in Quantitative Economic in Public Secondary Schools?
3. Which of the predictors is/are most influential in predicting students' achievement in Quantitative Economic in Public Secondary Schools?
4. Are there any predictor variables that do not contribute significantly to the prediction model of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted correlation research design. This design was chosen because the researcher does not have control over the variables as their manifestations have already occurred.

Population, Sampling Techniques and Sample

The target population comprises all the Economics students in secondary schools in Osun state.

Multistage sampling technique was used. The researcher used the already stratified educational district (central, west and east) in the state. Thereafter, four Local Government Areas were purposively selected from each of the three educational districts, totaling twelve Local Government Areas within the State. The Local Government Areas were selected based on location (that is LGAs that have both Urban and Rural areas). Likewise, three schools were purposively selected from the sampled Local Government Areas (two schools from urban and one school from rural and schools that have 35-40 students offering Economics in S.S.S II class). Then thirty S.S.S.II Economics students were randomly selected from each of the sampled schools (totaling ninety students per LGA). And a total of 1080 students were randomly sampled for the study.

Comparative Analysis between... (Adebisi & Bello, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603539>

Instrumentation

Five instruments were used for the data collection, four of them were validated using Cronbach Alpha; School Administration Practices Scale (SAPS) with reliability coefficient of 0.91, School Activities Scale (SAS) with reliability coefficient of 0.80, School Ethos Questionnaire (SEQ) with reliability coefficient of 0.78 and School Learning Cultures Scale (SLCS) with reliability coefficient of 0.90 while Quantitative Economics Achievement Test was validated using KR20 and the reliability coefficient was 0.88.

Procedure for data Collection and Analysis

The approval to conduct the research was sought and obtained from the schools' authority. Also, ethical considerations was ensured by telling the students the purpose of the study. Six research assistants were employed; two research assistants was deployed to each district for data collection exercise, the data collection lasted for five weeks. Multiple regressions were used to analyse data collected.

Presentation of Result

Research Question One

What type of relationship exists between school effectiveness variables (School Administrative practices, School activities, School learning culture, School ethos) and students' achievement in Quantitative Economic in Public Secondary Schools?

Table 1: Correlation Matrix of correlation among the variables

	School administrative	School activities	School ethos	School learn culture	Achievement
School Administrative	1				
School activities	.497**	1			
School ethos	-.001	.034	1		
School learn culture	.251**	.169**	.003	1	
Achievement	.224**	.054	.047	.056	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

Table 1 presents the correlation matrix of the variables of the study. It was revealed that, school Administrative Practices has significant positive relationship with School Activities ($r = .497$; $p < .05$), also School Learning culture ($r = .251$; $p < .05$), likewise the School Activities and School learning culture ($r = .169$; $p < .05$). The findings support the outcome of Kieti, Maithya and Mulwa (2017) that school administrative practices correlate significant with student academic performance. The result is also in-line with the findings of Rusok, Samy and Bhaumik (2023) that Learning Culture positively predicts attitude toward academic works. The study equally shows significant relationship between learning culture and school administrative practice.

Research Question Two

Does the obtained regression equation resulting from the set of predictor variables; school effectiveness variables (School Administrative Practices, School Activities, School Learning Culture, School Ethos) allow a reliable prediction of students' achievement in Quantitative Economic in Public Secondary Schools?

Table 2: Model Summary of Regression Analysis of School Effectiveness and Academic Achievement in Quantitative Economics

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.322 ^a	.104	.101	7.016

a. Predictors: (Constant), SCH LEARN CULT, SCH ETHOS, SCH ACT, SCH ADM

Comparative Analysis between... (Adebisi & Bello, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603539>

Table 3: Analysis of Variance of School effectiveness Variables and Academic Achievement in Quantitative Economics ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6133.972	4	1533.493	31.155	.000 ^b
	Residual	52864.232	1074	49.222		
	Total	58998.204	1078			

a. Dependent Variable: Quantitative Economics Achievement

b. Predictors: (Constant), SCH_LEARN_CULT, SCH_ETHOS, SCH_ACT, SCH_ADM

Tables 2 and 3 present the model summary and ANOVA representatively. The multiple regression correlation coefficient (R) showing the linear relationship between school effectiveness variables (school administrative practices, school activities, school learning culture, school ethos) and students' achievement in Quantitative Economic as shown in Table 2, R is 0.322, the multiple R² is 0.104, and Adjusted R square value is 0.101. This means that the variation in students' achievement in Quantitative Economic accounted for by the predictor variables is approximately 32.2% and it is statistically significant. Moreover Table 3, shows the analysis of variance of the multiple regression data. This produced an F-ratio of $f(4,1078) = 31.155$ and found to be significant at 0.05 Alpha level.

The finding of the study corroborate Ramberg, Laftman, Almquist and Modin (2019) that School effectiveness variables significantly predict students' perceptions of teacher caring, also the finding is in-line with Akanni (2020) that organizational leadership and culture influence the students' performance in south-western Nigeria. Moreover, the school effectiveness variable (school activities) play a significant role in improving students' attendance and engagements in the school (Munir & Zaheer, 2021).

Research Question Three

Which of the predictors is/are most influential in predicting students' achievement in Quantitative Economic in Public Secondary Schools?

Table 4: Relative contributions of School effectiveness Variables to Students' Academic Achievement in Quantitative Economics Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	70.936	2.871		24.706	.000
	SCH_ADM	-.113	.033	-.116	-3.410	.001
	SCH_ACT	-.303	.052	-.193	-5.794	.000
	SCH_ETHOS	-.128	.060	-.062	-2.140	.033
	SCH_LEARN_CULT	-.175	.047	-.112	-3.759	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Quantitative Economics Achievement

Table 4 shows the contribution of each of the independent variables to the prediction model and to the 32.2% of the variation of student's achievement in quantitative economics. Meanwhile all the independent variables contributed significantly to the prediction model at 0.05 Alpha level. School activities ($\beta = -.303$; $t(1074) = -5.794$ and school learning culture ($\beta = -.175$; $t(1074) = -3.759$ contributed the highest while school ethos ($\beta = -.128$; $t(1074) = -2.140$). The findings shows that school learning culture and school activities contributed highest to the prediction. And the finding correlated the outcome of Qian, Allan and Yang (2016) that building school learning culture assisted the teacher in improving primary school and promoting positive and progressive learning outcome in primary schools. Also the finding is in-line with Akanni (2020) that organizational leadership and culture influence the students' performance in south-western Nigeria. Kieti, Maithya, & Mulwa (2017) findings also supported that school Administrative Practices significantly predicts Students' academic performance in Public Secondary Schools in Matungulu sub-country, Kenya. The finding also support Rusok, Samy and Bhaumik (2023) that Learning Culture contributed to Innovative and Attitude toward Work.

Comparative Analysis between... (Adebisi & Bello, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603539>

Research Question Four

Are there any predictor variables that do not contribute significantly to the prediction model of the study?

All the school effectiveness variables contributed significantly to the criterion variable (students' Achievement in Quantitative Economics), but school ethos contributed the lowest. This means that school ethos is significant but not as significantly contributed as other variables. The finding contradict the study of Saminathen, Stephanie and Modin (2020) that the school ethos and Academic Achievement highly predict Adolescent Distress and Aggression in the Segregated School Landscape of Stockholm.

Conclusion

It is obvious that school effectiveness variable contributed significantly to the predictions of the students' academic achievement in Quantitative Economics in Osun state, the variables in the study that includes school administrative practices, schools activities, school learning culture and school ethos that are considered as the new areas of school effectiveness significantly predicted the students' academic achievement in quantitative economics. The findings of the study shows that school effectiveness variables cannot be divorced of its impact on the students' academic achievement in quantitative economics.

Recommendations

The following steps are recommended

1. School administrative practice should be adequately set by the school leaders towards improving the students' academic achievement.
2. School activities as an important aspect of school effectiveness should not be administratively overlook particularly the aspects that deals with engagement of student in calculation as this will have more impact on the achievement in Quantitative Economics.
3. School learning culture should be officially guided by the school by provide templates for future actions based on how we do things in an organisation to produce effective outcome, and teachers should be exposed to their activities involvement on way to provide and follows school learning culture.

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Effects of Vee-Diagram... (Osiboye, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601928>

Effects of Vee-Diagram Strategy on Achievement and Retention in Gravitation Concept among Federal College of Education Students, Kano State.

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Abstract

Vee-diagram is one of the learners' centered strategies which makes learning meaningful and worthwhile. The main objective of this study was to investigate effects of vee-diagram strategy on achievement and retention in gravitation concept among Federal College of Education students, Kano State. Pretest and posttest quasi-experimental research design was adopted for the study. An intact class of 85 N.C.E. II Physics pre-service teachers during the 2019/2020 academic session were purposively selected for the study. Two research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. Physics Achievement Test (PAT) was used for data collection. The reliability coefficient for the instruments was found to be 0.933 via test retest. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while Z-test was used to test both hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results revealed that there was no significant difference in the academic achievement of male and female students when taught the concept of gravitation using the Vee-Diagram instructional strategy. Also, there was no significant difference in the retention levels of male and female students when taught the concept of gravitation using the Vee-Diagram Instructional Strategy. Based on the findings, it was concluded that the Vee-diagram is a gender friendly instructional strategy, it was therefore recommended that science teachers should employ the use of Vee-diagram as an instructional strategy.

Keywords: Vee-Diagram Instructional Strategy, Academic Achievement, Retention, Gender Stereotypes, and Physics.

Effects of Vee-Diagram... (Osiboye, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601928>

Introduction

We observe a lot of cause-effect phenomena in and around our world which are sometimes periodic. Sometimes, based on our instincts, we find solution to a problem or navigate around natural occurrences. There are times we make guesses or speculations about physical quantities and at other times, after a number of trial and errors, we make exact measurements. Physics is the subject, a branch of science that helps us to make a meaning out of our observations by helping to not only connect the dots but offer explanations about these cause-effect relationships and provide tested equations and formulas that takes off the burden of guessing which is why every definition of physics highlights the interaction between space, energy, matter and time. According to Ede and Anosike (2023), physics is one of the core areas of study that supports the physical universe and is always relevant to people's day-to-day lives. Okeke and Ukoh (2020) believes that Physics is crucial for understanding contemporary technology and driving innovation, as it is applied to create tools and equipment used in various fields like military, transportation, medical, and telecommunication. Ahmad and Osiboye (2021) notes that Physics is a subject that should be at the top of the priority list for those involved in science education, for a variety of reasons, including its capacity to aid in our understanding of the world and the significant role it plays in science and technology toward the advancement of any country. Unfortunately, important as physics is, like every other endeavor with immense capabilities to make impact, the teaching and learning of physics is not devoid of besetting challenges with the most prominent being low academic achievement.

Ezugwu and Oguguo (2022) defines academic achievement as a student's current scholastic position. It speaks to the manner in which a person might exhibit their intellectual prowess. This academic standing may be explained by the grades earned in a particular course or set of courses. The scholastic standing of students in physics as a subject or course of study leaves more to be desired and this could account for why Oluwadamilare and Ayanwale (2021) asserts that until Nigeria maybe becomes sufficiently independent in the field of science, technology, and innovation (STI), the debates around the low academic achievement of its physics students will continue to gain traction among scientific educators. This is mainly because there is no longer in question how important physics and physics education are to the country's autonomy in STI.

Generally speaking, the term gender is used to classify human beings into male and female for the purpose of differentiation. Astalini, et al (2021) aptly described gender differences as distinctions between male and female features, traits, and modes of thought, with women's thought processes being more pronounced and their emotions better structured than those of men, who tend to be more practical or to use their wits more. On the other hand, gender stereotypes according to Sriwijayanti et al (2023) are commonly held ideas that impact how people see and behave in society regarding the qualities, positions, and obligations that are considered suitable for men and women. Similarly, Peter and Pathak (2023) opined that Gender stereotypes are based on how people act, behave, or handle their personalities. People of all genders are expected to act and behave in accordance with their defined gender, and when they don't, it serves as a platform for gender inequality, also known as gender discrimination. Gender stereotypes are inflexible beliefs about the traits and conduct that men and women should exhibit. They are frequently founded on out-of-date data and can result in discrimination and opportunity limitations. Again, Döring (2021). Highlights Gender stereotypes as ideas about roles, actions, personalities, and physical characteristics that define what men and women are or ought to be; these ideas frequently mirror orthodox ideas of what it means to be a man or a woman. These perceived differences and stereotypes seem to dictate to each gender consciously or otherwise the kind of endeavors they should venture into regardless of their potentials and capabilities, and these stereotypical ideologies reflect in physics as a subject area.

According to Krakehl and Kelly (2021). When taking student gender and ethnicity into account, there has been a continuous disparity in access to, and performance in advanced high school physics. In the same vein, Ogonna and Iliya (2023) observed that women are underrepresented in many science-related fields in Nigerian secondary schools and colleges, especially in physics-related professions. Research studies also show that women generally perform worse in physics-related professions. For these reasons, the impact of gender differences in physics achievement has been a source of concern for education stakeholders over time. As a testament to this unpleasant development being a universal status-quo, Kalender et al (2022) notes that the American higher education physics community has spent the last few decades addressing issues pertaining to the under representation of women in the

Effects of Vee-Diagram... (Osiboye, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601928>

field. Additionally, since success in physics is often attributed to brilliance, many students are likely to have fixed mindsets about the subject, which can be particularly harmful for students from underrepresented groups. Stoeckel and Roehrig (2021) points out that women are underrepresented in the field of physics, which is firmly dominated by men. Research indicates that women tend to report a lower sense of competence in the form of self-efficacy than their male peers and that they have a weaker physics identity than men. This underrepresentation is seen not only among professional physicists but also at all levels of physics education. There is a tendency for the younger generation of females to continue to perceive physics as a strictly male endeavor and as a difficult subject area unless they begin to witness a change in the narrative which will begin by high flying female achievers in the subject, and consequently a boost in representation. This is where a transition from the conventional chalk and board method of teaching physics, to student centered instructional strategies such as the vee-diagram becomes essential.

According to Kayacan (2018), in courses such as physics which contain a lot of abstract concepts, it is extremely important for students to learn by discovery in order to achieve meaningful learning. The Vee diagram, is one of the most appropriate and important documents that could be used in the process of learning through experience because it is effective as a technique that contributes to meaningful learning. Hapsari et al (2012) defines the Vee-diagram instructional strategy as a visual tool that helps students organize and connect concepts, facilitating guided inquiry and enhancing critical thinking in learning processes. Hindriana (2016) views the Vee diagram as an instructional strategy which visually connects conceptual and methodological aspects of learning, facilitating meaningful understanding and reducing cognitive load. Remarkably, authors' views and beliefs about the vee-diagram is that it enhances meaningful learning because the students are actively involved in their learning process which means it can be expected to bring about a desired outcome in students' academic achievement and by extension their retention levels.

According to Lindsey et al. (2014) the human memory is not perfect. Therefore, means have to be constantly sought to facilitate the conservation of knowledge and skills acquired for a long-term duration. Yet students at every level of education have to constantly put up with the challenge of reviewing loads of previously encountered materials and get acquainted with newer ones. Ferreira et al (2016) pointed out that teachers ensure that their students acquire new knowledge and skills but they also must not lose sight of the fact that newly acquired knowledge by itself does not stay put and because of this, has a great tendency to be forgotten. This is why Ahmad (2017) believes that students will only retain information that they find worthwhile and it therefore follows that when the learner is actively involved in the learning process, wherein new knowledge is integrated with relevant existing knowledge, concepts are better organized and retention is improved. Edwards et al (2017) stressed that the importance of retention of knowledge cannot be overemphasized as it is highly necessary for the future application of concepts. If students are to score good grades, progress academically and career wise, and if schools will continue to exist, then the concept of knowledge retention must take top priority this is especially so because the stakes for testing students' knowledge is constantly rising higher. To this end researchers have made efforts to pin point vital learning components that facilitates long-term learning. Their finding is that visual information and problem-solving practice must go hand in hand to foster knowledge retention. From the foregoing discourse, the major thing that boosts retention of knowledge is for the students to be actively involved and participate fully in the learning process. It will be difficult for them to lose sight of their own contributions, and recalling their own efforts is the path that leads them to what the lesson was all about. This is the same thing that plays out when students engage in group discussions. Vee-diagram provides an opportunity for the students to be actively involved in the buildup of the lesson, which will aid in retention.

Physics as a subject area regardless of how it is being perceived, ideally should be offered by both male and female students with both genders performing well in it because potentials are innate and can be nurtured to life when given the opportunity. Unfortunately, societal stereotypes have conditioned the females to believing that physics is a predominantly male subject and worse still, the few females who offer the subject are more often than not outperformed by their male counterparts. According to Chukwemeka and Bature (2023), women in Nigeria's secondary school and colleges of education are underrepresented and tend to perform poorly in science-related fields, particularly in physics, due to factors such as prior learning, job objectives, self-efficacy, mentality and epistemology. Krzaklewska, Sekuła, Ciaputa, and Struzik (2019) reports that, combined data across all scientific disciplines reveals that women's representation in the natural sciences is much lower in most European countries than in other fields. This

Effects of Vee-Diagram... (Osiboye, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601928>

is evident from the fact that, in 2015, the proportion of female researchers in higher education ranged from 21% to 54% in the natural sciences and 37% to 70% in the medical and health sciences. Additionally, women make up only 25% of all researchers in the fields of physics and astronomy. Researchers, having identified this trend have over the years attempted to unravel the reasons behind it and thereby proffer solutions and even though other science subjects are beginning to experience a little bit of a boost in women representation, the same cannot be said for physics. The possible long run impact of this development is that the current generation of women will continue to doubt and underrate their capabilities and at the same time reinforce the belief that physics is a male only subject. Before long, the younger generation completely losses interest in the subject and the situation goes from underrepresentation to zero representation which will not only affect Physics as a discipline but other science related profession because of the essentiality of physics as a subject to these professions. To curb the situation from getting any worse than it already is, it becomes expedient to seek for interventions. Although stakeholders have employed various means to address the situation ranging from mentorship to sensitization and scholarships, this study seeks to investigate the effect of vee-diagram which is a student-centered strategy on the academic achievement and retention levels of the female students in comparison with that of their male counterparts.

Objectives of the study

The objective of this research study is to determine effects of vee-diagram strategy on achievement and retention in gravitation concept among Federal College of Education students, Kano State. Specifically, the study sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. To determine the effect of Vee-Diagram on academic achievement in concept gravitation based on gender among FCE, Kano Students
2. To determine the effect of Vee-Diagram on retention in concept of gravitation based on gender among FCE, Kano Students.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught the concept gravitation in FCE, Kano?
2. What is the mean retention scores of male and female students taught the concept gravitation in FCE, Kano?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at $P=0.05$ level of significance.

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught the concept gravitation in FCE, Kano.
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of male and female students taught the concept gravitation in FCE, Kano.

Methodology

The research design adopted for the study is pretest-posttest quasi experimental research design. The quasi-experimental design by nature is a design that sets out to test or verify the effect of a particular intervention or treatment on a group of subjects. In this study, the quasi-experimental design was adopted to determine the effect of Vee-diagram on students' academic achievement and retention based on gender. One group of students were used for data collection. The intact class of males and females were pretested to determine their ability and confirm their equivalence. Thereafter, the class was taught the concept of gravitation using Vee-diagram. At the end of the six weeks treatment period, a posttest was administered to the class to determine the effectiveness of the Vee-diagram. After two weeks, a post-posttest was administered to the class to determine the retention abilities of the students. The same questions were asked for the pre-test, post-test and post-posttest. However, the questions were rearranged for the post-posttest to forestall familiarity of the students with the questions. The population for this study is the entire N.C.E. two students of Federal College of Education Kano in the 2019/2020 session. The intact class of 85 (64 males and 21 females) physics students was purposively selected to serve as the sample for the study.

Effects of Vee-Diagram... (Osiboye, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601928>

A researcher designed Physics Achievement Test (PAT) was used to measure students' achievement and retention in the concept of gravitation. The PAT which was developed based on the concept of gravitation, contained thirty (30) multiple choice test items with four (4) options lettered A, B, C, D for the students to pick the correct option in each item. The test was administered as a pre-test to determine the equivalence of both genders, as a post-test to determine the effect of the intervention on academic achievement and as a post-post test to determine the retention level of both genders. In order to ensure the validity of the instruments, PAT items and the lesson plans were given to one professor in the Department of Physics, Bayero University Kano and one Senior lecturer (PhD) in the Department of Physics Federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi. The scores obtained from the pilot testing were analyzed using the Pearson-Product Moment Correlation Coefficient at the 0.05 significance level to determine the reliability coefficient of the PAT which was found to be 0.93.

The class was taught using the Vee-diagram for two hours per week for six (6) weeks using Lesson plans developed by the researchers. The teaching took place within the normal periods scheduled by the department for PHY 213 so that an already planned school routine is not disrupted. The Vee-diagram is both a teaching and learning strategy but was solely used as a teaching strategy in this study. As the name implies, the teaching outline follows a V template. The lesson starts out from the left wing of the Vee-diagram which is the conceptual wing, heads towards the event and goes back up to the right wing which is the methodological wing. The conceptual wing was outlined, and focus questions set by the researchers, while the events and methodological (doing) wing were purely carried out by the students. The focus question is placed between both wings. The topic for each period was presented alongside the instructional materials and the lesson followed the order of the flowchart below:

Figure 1: Flow Chart for the use of Vee-diagram (Researcher Designed)

The scores that were obtained from the pre-test, post-test and the post-posttest were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) to answer the two research questions raised. To test the hypotheses, the data were subjected to Z-test at 0.05 level of significance. The scores obtained were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.

Presentation of Results

Research Question One: What is the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught the concept gravitation in FCE, Kano?

To answer the research Question, the posttest scores of the male and female students were subjected to descriptive statistics using mean and standard deviation as shown in table 1 below.

Effects of Vee-Diagram... (Osiboye, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601928>

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Posttest Scores of Male and Female Students

	GENDER	N	Mean	S. D.	Mean Diff.
POSTTEST	Male	64	14.4844	4.90219	1.2299
	Female	21	15.7143	3.27327	

The results in Table 1 above shows that the male students had a mean and standard deviation of 14.48 and 4.90 respectively while the female students had a mean of 15.71 and standard deviation of 3.27 with a mean difference of 1.22 in favor of the female students that had higher mean. This shows that there is difference in the academic achievement of male and female students taught using the Vee-diagram instruction.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught the concept gravitation in FCE, Kano. To test null hypothesis 1, the post-test scores of the male and female students were subjected to independent sample Z-test statistic. The summary of the analysis is presented in table 2 below.

Table 2: Independent sample Z-test for academic achievement of Male and Female students

	Variable	N	Mean	S.D.	S E, Mean	df	Z	p	Decision
POSTTEST	Male	64	14.48	4.90	0.61	83	1.072	0.287	Accepted
	Female	21	15.71	3.27	0.71				

Results from Table 2 shows that the Z-cal is 1.072 and the observed p-value is 0.287 which is greater than the significant 0.05 α value with $df=83$, hence, the null hypothesis is thereby accepted implying that there is no significant difference in the academic achievement of male and female students in the experimental group.

Research Question Two: What is the mean retention scores of male and female students taught the concept gravitation in FCE, Kano?

Descriptive statistic in form of mean and standard deviation was used to answerer research question two and is presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Mean and S.D of Post-Posttest Scores of Male and Female Physics Students Exposed to Vee-Diagram Instructional Strategy

Group	N	Post -Test Mean	-Test Std. Deviation	Post -Test Mean	Posttest Std. Deviation	Mean Gain
Male	64	14.48	4.90	14.82	4.96	0.34
Female	21	15.71	3.27	15.38	3.30	0.33

Table 3 indicates the mean post-posttest scores of male and female physics students exposed to Vee-Diagram Instructional Strategy. The result revealed that female students had post-test mean achievement score of 15.71 and standard deviation of 3.27, post-posttest mean achievement score of 15.38 and standard deviation of 3.30 with mean gain of 0.33 while male students had a mean post-test achievement score of 14.48 and standard deviation of 4.90, post-posttest mean achievement score of 14.82 and standard deviation of 4.96 with mean gain of 0.34. The mean gain difference between male and female achievement score is 0.01. This indicates that female physics students performed slightly higher than their male counterpart.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of male and female students taught the concept gravitation in FCE, Kano. Hypothesis two was tested by subjecting the post-posttest mean achievement (retention) score of male and female students to independent sample z-test and the summary is presented in table 4 below.

Effects of Vee-Diagram... (Osiboye, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601928>

Table 4: Independent Sample Z-Test for Post-Posttest Mean Achievement (Retention) Scores of the Male and Female Physics Students Exposed to Vee-Diagram Instructional Strategy

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	Z-value	P-value	Decision
Male	64	14.82	4.96	83	-.476	.635	Accepted
Female	21	15.38	3.30				

Table 4 presents an Independent Sample Z-Test for Post-Posttest Mean Achievement (Retention) scores of the Male and Female Physics Students Exposed to Vee-Diagram Instructional Strategy. From the result, the observed p-value is .635 with df=83 and the alpha value is 0.05. The observed p-value 0.635 is greater than the alpha value 0.05. The null hypothesis is hereby retained or accepted. The reason for acceptance of the null hypothesis is that the observed p-value is greater than the alpha value. Therefore, there was no significant difference in the mean retention score between male and female students taught physics using Vee-Diagram Instructional Strategy. Hence Vee-Diagram Instructional Strategy is gender friendly teaching strategy.

Summary of findings

1. The findings from research hypothesis one showed that although the female students had a higher mean score, there was no significant difference in the performance of both genders and so the null hypothesis “there is no significant difference in the academic achievement of male and female students when taught the concept of gravitation using the Vee-Diagram” is accepted implying that there is no significant difference in gender performance.
2. The findings from research hypothesis two showed that although the female students had a higher mean score, there was no significant difference in the retention levels of both genders and so the null hypothesis “there is no significant difference in the retention levels of male and female students when taught the concept of gravitation using the Vee-Diagram” is accepted implying that there is no significant difference in retention levels based on gender.

Discussion of Findings

This study examined the effect of the vee-diagram strategy on female students’ academic achievement and gravitation concept retention. The two (2) research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation and both hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The students involved in the study were found to be equivalent after a pre-test was conducted and it is believed that the slight difference in mean scores of academic achievement and retention in favor of the females was as a result of the treatment. The finding from research hypothesis one showed that there is no significant difference in the academic achievement of male and female when taught the concept of gravitation using the Vee-Diagram instructional strategy. The Z-test analysis at p-value of 0.287 which is greater than the alpha value of 0.05 confirmed this. Similarly, the finding from hypothesis two showed that there is no significant difference in the level of retention of male and female students when taught the concept of gravitation of using Vee-Diagram due to the observed p-value of 0.635 which is greater than the alpha value of 0.05. These results show that the Vee-diagram is a gender friendly instructional strategy. Although there is no significant difference in their achievement scores as ascertained by the Z-test, the females had a higher mean score of 15.71 as against their male counterpart which had a mean score of 14.48. Female performance in science subjects has been a major concern for researchers over the years. These findings are a pointer to the fact that these concerns can be well taken care of if student centered instructional strategies like the Vee-Diagram are employed. Judging from the class participation in the course of the study, the results obtained were very much expected as it was observed that the female students were quite enthused and participated fully in each of the six lessons. According to Abdulkadir (2017) whose finding agrees with this present study, the use of epistemological components of Vee-Diagram should be encouraged to enhance the learning of physics concepts by male and female students in physics classrooms and to improve their interaction of conceptual, methodological and problem-solving skills. This is supported by the findings from his study which set out to investigate the “effects of the use of Vee-Diagram on Senior School Students’ performance in Ilorin”. It was found that besides improving significantly the performance of the students, Vee-diagram gave the female students the same opportunity to be at their best just like their male counterparts as there was no significant difference in the performance

Effects of Vee-Diagram... (Osiboye, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601928>

of both genders. Likewise, supporting these findings is the research of Namasaka et al (2013) as the results obtained from their study indicates that girls and boys taught using CVMS (concept and Vee mapping strategy) had similar post-test scores implying similar motivation levels. It is therefore safe to say that, ranging from cognitive constructs to psychological constructs, vee-diagram positively impacts students' learning experience thereby bringing about a desired outcome. Again, Harrington et al (2022) conducted a study which focused on two underrepresented groups in UK HE: widening participation and women physics students and it was discovered that there was a substantial correlation between gender and the classification that MPhys (Hons) students received, with a greater percentage of female students graduating with an upper class or first-class classification than male students. Harrington et al implied that it is possible that this group of female students were resilient or were able to lessen the negative impacts of their underrepresentation. It is however necessary to buttress the explanation offered by Harrington et al by stating that when females are exposed to learner centered strategies and equipped with appropriate and sufficient learning tools, they will be at par with their male counterparts. Although this present study set out to investigate the performance of female students, worthy of note is the fact that the vee-diagram also had an effect on the male student's academic achievement and retention as is evident in their post-test scores. This goes to say that employing the vee-diagram as a tool to combat gender stereotypes is actually a move that generally overhauls the undesirable state of the teaching and learning of physics.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: Vee-Diagram instructional strategy is a gender friendly method of instruction as it was shown that both male and female students performed better in Physics. Vee-Diagram instructional strategy enhanced both male and female students' retention level as it was indicated that there is no significant difference in retention of gravitation concept between male and female students.

Recommendations

From the findings and conclusions made, the following recommendations are proffered.

1. Curriculum planners and policy makers in education should encourage science teachers to adopt the Vee-Diagram instructional strategy as a teaching strategy because it is a gender friendly strategy which brings to limelight the potentials of female students.
2. Experts in the use of the vee-diagram strategy should seek for and make use of available platforms to train both teachers and students on how to employ the strategy as a teaching and learning tool respectively because of its effectiveness in improving students' academic achievement.

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Qualitative Study on School Based Management Committees in Basic Education Curriculum Development in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper focuses on Contribution of School Based Management Committees in Basic Education Curriculum Development in Nigeria. The paper aim at finding significant contributions to the development and implementation of the Basic Education Curriculum in Nigeria, by acting as intermediaries between local communities and policy-makers, and challenges faced by Basic Education Curriculum in Nigeria. The paper concluded that School-Based Management Committees (SBMCs) have made significant contributions to the development and implementation of the Basic Education Curriculum in Nigeria. It was suggested that: Government should make sure that School-Based Management Committees (SBMCs) have significant contributions in the development and implementation of the Basic Education Curriculum in Nigeria; Government should increase the funding of Basic education in Nigeria. This will help to develop the basic education; adequate security should be provided for all the basic schools in the country especially those in the northern part of Nigeria.

Keywords: School Based Management Committees, Basic Education and Curriculum Development

Introduction

Education is a crucial factor in the development of any nation, and Nigeria is no exception. To enhance the quality and effectiveness of education at the basic level, several policies have been introduced, one of which is the creation of School-Based Management Committees (SBMCs). SBMCs are participatory governance bodies established in schools to foster community involvement in the decision-making processes that affect educational outcomes. These committees have played a significant role in the development of the Basic Education Curriculum, helping to ensure that it meets local needs, reflects societal aspirations, and addresses the unique challenges facing schools. In Nigeria, the SBMCs' contributions to curriculum development have been pivotal in creating an inclusive, responsive, and context-specific educational system for basic education.

In Nigeria, public deliberations frequently focus on educational standards. The public dissatisfaction gets deeper, following the annual release of the West Africa Senior School Certificate Examination Results. Students' performances do not appear to match government and parental investments. Stakeholders are concerned with the continual fall in the standards of education. To them, it is questionable whether or not teachers in secondary schools, who are the most important factors in the management of schools and in the quality of a child's education, are competent to teach effectively (Ayeni, 2017). This indicates the need for collective collaborations among stakeholders in strengthening their efforts to resuscitate the declined education standards.

The School-Based Management Committees (SBMCs) have been created as mechanisms to provide platforms for communities and schools to work together to enrich school governance, and promote improved

Qualitative Study on... (Muhammad, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603539>

management by education authorities, towards the achievement of better learning outcomes for children in basic education schools. The importance of establishing SBMCs among other things is to bring schools closer to their communities. Some related studies have indicated the progress and achievement so far made by the few functional SBMCs in Nigeria (United Nation International Children’s Emergency Fund, 2015).

Concept of School-Based Management Committees (SBMCs)

School Based Management Committee takes its root from the School Based Management. The idea of having School Based Management Committee, to oversee the management of schools is an important aspect of educational reform globally. It is a channel for bringing resources from community into school, a way of getting a better flow of government resources to schools, as well as the linkage between government, school and community (Universal Basic Education Commission, 2011). It is also an initiative, meant to improve the bottom decision in educational planning and management, so as to facilitate improvement in the quality of education and efficiency. It is aimed at moving secondary education forward through combined effort of government, community, teachers and children, as well as broadening the existing gap between schools and communities where they exist and operate (Pinnock and Nicholls, 2012). School-Based Management Committees (SBMCs) are local-level bodies composed of various stakeholders in the education sector, including parents, teachers, community leaders, religious representatives, local government officials, and sometimes students. The primary goal of SBMCs is to enhance community participation in school management, decision-making, and monitoring of educational policies and practices. In Nigeria, SBMCs were formally introduced as part of the National Policy on Education to strengthen school governance, improve accountability, and increase community engagement in educational development. By creating a platform for collaboration between schools and their communities, SBMCs play a crucial role in curriculum development, ensuring that the content taught in schools is relevant, inclusive, and aligned with local needs.

The Role of SBMCs in Basic Education Curriculum Development

The development of the Basic Education Curriculum in Nigeria is a multi-stakeholder process that includes the federal and state governments, educational experts, and grassroots organizations like SBMCs. SBMCs play a vital role by providing a bridge between formal educational policy-makers and local communities, ensuring that the curriculum reflects the diverse cultural, economic, and social realities of Nigerian society. (Sokoto State School-Based Management Committee, 2017)

Community Input in Curriculum Content

One of the primary roles of SBMCs is to provide feedback from the community regarding what should be included in the curriculum. In many cases, rural and underserved communities have specific needs and expectations regarding the education their children receive. For instance, communities may advocate for the inclusion of vocational skills, agricultural knowledge, or native languages, which are often overlooked in standardized curriculums. SBMCs act as a channel for these inputs, making sure that local knowledge and priorities are integrated into the national curriculum.

Promoting Gender Equity and Inclusive Education

SBMCs have also been instrumental in promoting gender equity and inclusive education within the basic education curriculum. By involving members of the community, especially women and marginalized groups, SBMCs ensure that the curriculum is inclusive of gender-sensitive issues and accessible to children with disabilities. They work to eliminate barriers to education, such as early marriage for girls, by advocating for curriculum reforms that promote gender awareness and equal opportunities for all students.

Enhancing the Relevance of Education to Local Communities

SBMCs contribute to curriculum development by ensuring that what is taught in schools is relevant to the socio-economic needs of the community. For instance, in agrarian regions, SBMCs might advocate for the inclusion of agricultural science and farm management in the curriculum, helping students develop skills that will be useful in their local environment. In other areas, SBMCs may push for the teaching of entrepreneurship, technology, or other skills critical to the local economy. This relevance ensures that students not only gain formal education but also acquire practical skills that improve their prospects for employment or self-employment after graduation.

SBMCs and Curriculum Implementation

While SBMCs are involved in curriculum development, their role also extends to curriculum implementation. They monitor how effectively the curriculum is being delivered in schools and ensure that it is aligned with the community’s expectations. SBMCs may organize community meetings to assess the impact of the curriculum and

Qualitative Study on... (Muhammad, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603539>

work with teachers and school administrators to address gaps or issues. This oversight helps ensure that the curriculum, once developed, is effectively implemented in classrooms.

School Based Management (SBM) and Physical Plant Planning

The school plant planning requires maximum cooperation of the SBM with the combined teamwork by the school principal, teachers, students and other school personnel and the community in order to ensure effective utilization and maintenance of the school plant for smooth operation of the school system. The SBM can mobilize members of the community who are experts in building construction (architects and engineers) to offer professional advice on the planning and development of school infrastructure.

The role of physical plants in effective administration and instructional management particularly at the secondary school level cannot be underestimated. Abayomi (2009) remarked that the general condition of the school facilities appears to be the basis upon which many parents make their initial judgments about the qualities of education service delivery and students' academic performance.

These combined deficiencies perhaps constituted a major gap in the quality of learning infrastructure, thus, many challenges bear on teaching and learning that prevent the education system from getting the best out of its efforts to achieve the required level of attainment in teaching and learning activities in secondary schools.

School Based Management (SBM) and School-Community Relations

The school-community relation is a two-way symbiotic collaboration between the school management and members of the community to provide educational resources for the improvement in the teaching-learning activities and students' academic performance. The SBMC contribute to school development by encouraging different socio-cultural organizations and other prominent members of the community to make useful contributions to enhance the development of the school and quality education for the learners since the school is regarded as a social organization and the community asset and means of training the young ones to become responsible citizens in the society.

Effective school-community relationship will no doubt strengthen institutional management and school effectiveness; promote community strong commitment to the provision of adequate teaching and learning materials/facilities, conducive working environment, staff and students' welfare, and cordial interpersonal relationship; effective curriculum implementation and quality learning outcome in secondary schools (Ayeni, 2017). The finding revealed that principals have positive perceptions towards community participation in school administration; the community assisted the school in the employment of non-professional staff, information sharing and enforcement of discipline.

Challenges Faced by SBMCs in Curriculum Development

Despite their contributions, SBMCs face several challenges in their role in curriculum development and implementation. One major challenge is the lack of adequate training for committee members. Many SBMC members, especially those from rural areas, may have limited educational backgrounds and, as a result, struggle to engage effectively in technical discussions about curriculum content. Furthermore, the centralization of educational policy in Nigeria sometimes limits the influence SBMCs can have on curriculum design, especially when decisions are made at the federal level without sufficient input from local communities. Inadequate funding and logistical support are also major barriers that hinder the full participation of SBMCs in curriculum development.

Concept of Basic Education in Nigeria

Basic Education is defined as the education given to children aged 0-15 years. It encompasses the Early Child Care and Development Education (0-4) and 10 years of formal schooling. Early Child Care and Development Education however is segmented into ages 0-4 years, situated in crèches, fully in the hands of the private sector and social development services, whilst ages 5-6 are within the formal education sector. For purposes of policy coordination and monitoring, the Federal Government instituted a Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC), with the following objectives: Developing in the entire citizenry a strong consciousness for education and a strong commitment to its vigorous promotion; the provision of compulsory, free and universal basic education for every Nigerian child of school age; reducing the incidence of drop-out from formal school system, through improved relevance, quality and efficiency; catering through appropriate forms of complementary approaches to the promotion of basic education, for the learning needs of young persons who for one reason or another have had to interrupt their schooling; and ensuring the acquisition of the appropriate levels of literacy, numeracy, communicative and life skills, as well as the ethical, moral, security and civic values needed for the laying of a solid foundation for life-long learning.

Qualitative Study on... (Muhammad, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603539>

Basic Education, to be provided by Government, shall be compulsory, free, universal and qualitative. It comprises: 1-year of Pre-Primary, primary school and junior secondary school (UBEC, 2011).

Basic education according to Kanno and Onyeachu (2015) is defined as the foundational educational level. This may also by implication be seen and perceived as the most fundamental education that is given to people. For Nwanna (2020) basic education is seen as the base-line education on which all other educational advancement depends. The basic education in this context is like the foundation of a building on which all other loads for the building come. This same foundational education from inference determines the stability of the entire educational building that anyone can ever have. Therefore, basic education is to a large extent what determines the success or failure of all other stages of education that may come on it. Hence, it becomes imperative to make this educational level functional to produce results worthy of the effort inputted by the implementers in Nigeria.

Problems Faced by Basic Education in Nigeria

There are many problems facing by Basic education in Nigeria. Some of these problems include; inadequate funding, inadequate infrastructural facilities, inadequate professional teachers, corruption, insecurity problem, poor supervision, among others.

Inadequate Funding of Basic School Education:

It is very critical for effective administration especially in the area of Curriculum implementation. Curriculum implementation at the Basic school education is very expensive because it has the higher school population among all the forms of education. Effective Curriculum implementation requires adequate number of professional teachers, infrastructural facilities, instructional materials and other supportive services resources. The provision of these human and materials resources demand huge financial resources annually which is not available in the Country (Ogunode and Nasir 2021) and (Ogunode, Chijindu & Jegede, 2022). The annual allocation of the ministry of education in Nigeria is below the UNESCO 26% recommendation in fact Ogunode (2020) and Ogunode and Adanna (2022) observed that allocation to the education Ministry for one decade is below 15% and from this allocation, the Basic education received the least allocation among all the forms of education in Nigeria. The poor funding of education especially that of the Basic education in Nigeria is hindering effective implementation of Basic school Curriculum in Nigeria. The inadequate funding is the problem responsible for the slow development of primary school education in Nigeria. The poor quality of education at the primary school level is as a result of shortage of funds. Majorities of problem facing the primary school educations are as a result of poor funding of the sector

Inadequate Infrastructural Facilities.

It stated that another problem facing the administration of primary school education in Nigeria is the challenge of inadequate infrastructural facilities (Ogunode, 2020). Ogunode and Nasir (2021) stated that infrastructural facilities include; administrative block, classrooms, libraries, laboratories, ICT centre, tables, desks, black board, white board, water, electricity, internet services and road network. Many Basic education schools in Nigeria do not have adequate infrastructural facilities to deploy for teaching and learning. Ogunode and Nasir (2021) observed that funds allocated for the provision of capital projects, replacement of facilities, repairs and maintenance in many primary schools in the Nigeria ended up been diverted into private account leaving the primary schools to suffer shortage of facilities. The inadequate infrastructural facilities are affecting the administration of the Basic education. In order to ensure infrastructural facility development in the Basic education school across the country.

Inadequate Professional Teachers.

It submitted that shortage of professional teachers is another major factor hindering effective implementation of Basic school Curriculum in Nigeria. The roles of the teachers cannot be replaced when it comes to Curriculum implementation. The teachers are trained to implement the Curriculum with the aid of other instructional materials (World Bank, 2015) and (Ogunode and Nasir, 2021). The teachers plans the lesson, writes the lesson note, selects the teaching methods best suit the topic, plans and arranges the educational resources needed to deliver the lesson, evaluate the lesson and report the students' performance to school and parents. The place of the professional teachers in the implementation of school Curriculum cannot be overemphasizes". It is unfortunate that as important as the professional teachers to the implementation of Basic school Curriculum in Nigeria, that professional teachers are not adequate in the Basic schools across the country. The 2018 National Personnel Audit (NPA), conducted by the Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC, 2018), revealed shortage of professional teachers at the early child education, basic education and junior secondary school education. The report furthered disclosed there was a deficit of 135,319 teachers at the Early Childhood Care Development Education, 139,772 deficits in primary schools and

Qualitative Study on... (Muhammad, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603539>

2,446 shortage in Junior Secondary Schools across the nation. Ogunode, (2020) observed that shortage of professional teachers is also a problem facing the administration of basic education in Nigeria.

Corruption:

This is another problem responsible for poor curriculum implementation in Basic education (Ogunode and Nasir 2021). Funds provided for programmes that will support effective delivering of Curriculum implementation in Nigerian basic school are mismanaged and looted by some officials within the ministries and agencies of education. Ogunode (2020); Ogunode, Ahmed, Gregory & Abubakar (2020) observed that corruption have penetrated all most all the public institutions in the country in including education. Corruption is one of the major problems facing the educational institutions. Institutional corruption is the problem preventing effective administration of education in Nigeria because funds allocated for provision of infrastructural facilities and services in the management and implementation of educational programme are been diverted by officers or political office holder within the institutions. The common form of corruption in the Nigerian educational institutions is fund diversion. Corruptions on fund diversion have been reported in all the forms of education in Nigeria. Ogunode and Nasir (2021) identified; shortage of funds, inadequate teachers, shortage of infrastructural facilities, poor quality of education, large out of school children, poor capacity development, poor implementation of Basic education policies and increase in the cost of Basic education administration as the effects of corruption on Basic education administration in Nigeria.

Insecurity Problem:

It submitted that insecurity is one of the major problems facing the administration of primary schools in Nigeria. Effective administration of basic education in Nigeria is frustrated by the insecurity challenges facing the country especially the Northern part of the country (World Bank, 2017) and (Ogunode, 2020). Many Basic schools have been closed down. Educational officers cannot travel to areas where they are supposed to travel to for administrative functions because of insecurity challenges. One of the most insecurity challenges facing the country is the Boko Haram group. The militant group, Boko Haram, has carried out violent attacks in the north-eastern parts of Nigeria. Thousands of Nigerians have been killed, and many more have been forced to flee their homes. Schools have been the primary target of the attacks. Since 2011, Boko Haram, whose name means „Western Education is Forbidden, has expanded its attacks to the direct target of schools. It has resulted in the killing and abduction of hundreds of teachers and students and the destruction of school buildings and teaching materials. Ogunode, Ahaotu, and Obi-Ezenekwe (2020) identified loss of manpower in educational institutions, poor quality of education, destructions of infrastructural facilities, brain-drain, closure of educational institutions, discouragement of educational pursuit by children, internal displacement of learners, and reduction of private investment in education and inadequate funding of education as the impact of insecurity on school administration in Nigeria.

Poor Supervision:

It submitted that the problem of poor school supervision by the respective school administrators have also contributed to the challenge facing the administration of basic schools. Many school administrators do not effectively supervised the basic schools under their watch. The Nigerian government recognized the need to monitor not only the financial management of the school, but also the teaching of students. Educationists at the Ministries of Education both at the federal and the state levels have set up quality control divisions in their respective ministries to ensure that quality education is maintained. It has been established that quality and standard could be maintained in the educational institutions through regular inspection and continuous supervision of instruction in the schools (Ogunode, 2020) and (Ogunode, Ahaotu, and Obi-Ezenekwe (2020). Supervision and inspection have been identified as very germane to the day-to-day activities of educational institutions (National Open University of Nigeria, 2009). The supervisor assesses and records the performance of teachers, their ability and consistency in carrying out the classroom activities and keeping of high-quality records. The activities of supervisors include the following: inspecting, monitoring, rating, assisting, recommending etc. Ogunode, Olatunde-Aiyedun, & Akin-Ibidiran (2021) and Ogunode and Nasir (2021) concluded in their study that inadequate Supervisors, inadequate supervision materials, insecurity, logistics problem, inadequate funding and poor capacity development of supervisors are the challenges preventing effective supervision of universal basic education programme in Kuje Area Council of FCT. Poor Learning Outcome, Ogunode, Olatunde-Aiyedun, & Akin-Ibidiran (2021) and Ogunode (2020) observed that the learning outcome of most primary school students is poor. School administrators in Nigeria are disturbed by the falling quality of education at the level of the basic schools.

Qualitative Study on... (Muhammad, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603539>

Poor learning outcome, poor implementation of Basic Education policies, Inadequate Funding Adequate funding of Basic school education according Ogunode and Nasir (2021) there are many problems facing Basic education in Nigeria. Some of these problems include; inadequate funding, inadequate infrastructural facilities, inadequate professional teachers, corruption, insecurity problem, poor supervision, poor learning outcome, poor implementation of Basic Education policies.

Curriculum Development in Nigeria

Curriculum development is a planned, thoughtful and deliberate course of actions that ultimately enhance the quality and impact of the learning experience for students. It includes the development and organization of learning activities designed to meet intended learning outcomes it can also be seen as where an educator plans learning activities and assessments that create meaningful and engaging learning experiences. The goal of curriculum development is to deliver high-quality lessons that help students achieve set learning outcomes

Conclusion

Based on the findings it was concluded that: School-Based Management Committees (SBMCs) have made significant contributions to the development and implementation of the Basic Education Curriculum in Nigeria. By acting as intermediaries between local communities and policy-makers, SBMCs ensure that the curriculum is inclusive, relevant, and reflective of the needs and aspirations of diverse communities. Despite challenges face by basic educations in Nigeria such as limited resources, corruptions, poor supervision and training, SBMCs continue to play a critical role in shaping a responsive educational system that serves Nigeria's basic education needs. Going forward, there is a need for stronger collaboration between SBMCs and government agencies, as well as improved training and resources, to maximize the impact of SBMCs in curriculum development and ensure a high-quality education for all Nigerian children.

Recommendations

1. The Federal Government should make sure that School-Based Management Committees (SBMCs) have significant contributions in the development and implementation of the Basic Education Curriculum in Nigeria.
2. The Federal Government should increase the funding of Basic education in Nigeria. This will help to develop the basic education.
3. The Federal Government should provide adequate security for all the Basic Schools in the country especially those in the northern part of Nigeria.

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Influence of Gender... (Omodara, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603575>

Influence of Gender and School Location on Performance in Agricultural Science among Secondary School Students in Kaduna North, Kaduna State

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Abstract

This study was conducted to establish the influence of gender and school location on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Agricultural Science students, using secondary data obtained from National Examination Council (NECO) results of 2018 to 2022. Survey design was used in a school population of 101, in the eight Local Governments of the zone, while multi-stage purposive sampling was used to select six schools from three school types in rural and urban locations. Two Senior Secondary schools in each of the school types were randomly selected. Data were subjected to descriptive statistics of means and percent, while independent t-test ($p \leq 0.05$) was used to test null hypotheses. Results revealed a fairly consistent increase in enrolment over the period, where male (56.74%) and urban (55.86%) students dominated enrolment. Results also showed variation in general results and quality of performance, which favoured the male (46.80%) and urban (43.69%) students compared to female (31.89%) and rural (35.15%) counterparts. However, there were no significant difference in enrolment and performance of gender and school location. The study therefore established that gender and school location does not have strong influence on students' performance, using National Examination Council of Nigeria results. Hence recommended that, the relatively low female enrolment, and poor performance of females and rural students are *sine qua non* to state government and other educational stakeholders for improved and sustainable students' performance, achievable through engagement of adequate and experienced teachers, motivation of staff and students, as well as retraining of teachers.

Keywords: Gender, location, enrolment, Performance, learning and Agricultural Science

Introduction

Agricultural Science is seen as one of the main vocational subjects taught in all Senior Secondary Schools in Nigeria based on the National Policy on Education (Newton and Hamisu, 2023). This is because of its roles towards making its beneficiaries self-reliance via provision of gainful employment chances, supply of staple foods to the ever-increasing population and generating raw materials to agro-based industries. Agriculture based on Onwunali, Muhammad and Balogun (2022) assertion is an integral factor in the development of any developing economy. This makes its teaching imperative at all level of education in the country with Senior Secondary Schools being a prominent foundation and link for higher education. Meanwhile Agricultural Science is a field of learning that emphasized understanding and utilization of scarce environmental resources towards food production to meet the need of increasing population of Nigeria. The teaching of this subject did not evolve without its own peculiarity. Teaching Agricultural Science usually goes along establishment of the three domains of learning to bring about better understanding and performance to its beneficiaries in the school and thereafter.

Academic achievement is the outcome of education, the extent which learner, teacher or institution has achieved their set goals. This is commonly measured by continuous assessment and examination (Oriakhi and Ujoro,

Influence of Gender... (Omodara, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603575>

2015). Even though assessment still remains the only way to measure performance, there has not been generally agreed best ways of carrying it out. There are two divides of the coin of performance which is good and poor performance. Poor performance is when a learner achievement is below his actual ability and otherwise good performance is when the learner achievement is equal to or above his actual ability. Poor or good performance could happen as a result of several factors among which are environment, gender, social among others (Alordiah, Akpadaka and Oviogbodu, 2015). Onwunali *et al.* (2022) reported that reading habit and achievement influenced each other while both are affected by environment. According to the authors, a convenient and conducive learning environment creates favourable reading atmosphere hence, improved academic achievement. Contrarily, poor and unconducive environment influence performance negatively. According to Iroko, Adesin and Asanre, (2024), many social divide factors are influencing learners' performance at secondary schools level. These factors include access to resources, quality of resources, quality of teachers, culture and language differences, gender disparity and environment to mention but few.

Location means position of the school within the chosen area of study. School location may be rural or urban in nature. Newton and Hamisu (2023) defined rural setting as settlement away from cities which may be lacking major social infrastructures such as health facilities, pipe borne water, electricity, good road network *inter alia*, while urban have all the required amenities. School locations are one of the factors affecting achievement level of students. It was established that rural dwellers are slow-witted hillbillies with little or no education and not current of happenings (Akinwumi, 2017). Alordiah *et al.* (2015) asserted that students attending rural schools face challenges of high poverty than those in urban schools. But they still maintained that rural schools have advantage of smaller classes which assist in flexibility of teaching/learning. In Agricultural Science the rural schools are at advantage for the fact that land is abundant for practical.

In the words of Oriakhi and Ujoro (2015), gender is the range of physical, biological, mental and behavioural characteristics pertaining to and differentiating between masculinity and femininity. It may mean sex (biological) as in male and female and in social structure (it may be gender roles) or gender identity. Gender is a socially construed trait of male and female in a given community different from sex. Gender differences in academic performance have generated serious interest in educational research over the years (Iroko *et al.*, 2024). Gender issues are currently assuming prominence in research globally, and have generated high consideration among academia and policy makers. This is unconnected with disparities in the allocation of cognitive roles in world of work. Meanwhile, gender inequality in enrolment is also influencing performance since boys are dominating in Agricultural Science. This has been associated with female poor performance in the subject (Onwunali *et al.*, 2022).

Agricultural Science as a vocational subject is taught with emphasis on hands on practical (Onwunali, 2024), consequently in teaching the subject cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains of learning are paramount. The psychomotor domain requires the use of farm activities of both livestock and crops of various types, which is not common in most urban schools due to lack of farm (Omodara, Onwunali and Joshua, 2024), and where farms are available in rural schools are not effectively used based on policy establishing Agricultural Science as vocational subject. At times students from urban areas perceived Agricultural Science as dirty job while the female students tend to shy away from the subject due to lack of interest, stereotype attitude and the claim that Agricultural Science practical is tedious. Onwunali *et al.* (2022) stated that Nigerian youths mainly choose Agricultural Science on a second thought when they fail in Medicine and Pharmacy, and associated it to students' lack of interest, attitude and poor performance in the course. As if that is not enough, speculations are bound that most students residing in urban environment hardly have background experience in farming like their rural counterparts hence the ugly perception in Agricultural Science.

Furthermore, much have been published on students' performance using West African Examination Council (WAEC) examination results with relatively meagre or no information on National Examination Council (NECO), which is also an acceptable and accredited 'O' Level examination body. The West African Examination Council and NECO are the two standard 'O' level examination councils in Nigeria, that uses professional agricultural educators to evaluate students. Such is achieved through questions that covers the three domains of learning based on the 3-year curriculum of the Senior Secondary Schools, and have same grading system (A1-F9) (Udofia and Udoh, 2017). However, speculations are bound on superiority of WAEC over NECO possibly because WAEC is a sub-regional examination, and the perception that academic achievement is sure at relatively low cost with NECO (Agwu, Orjiakor,

Influence of Gender... (Omodara, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603575>

Odi, Onalu, Nzeadibe and Okoye, 2020). Furthermore, laxity in monitoring and supervision of students in Senior Secondary Schools metamorphosed into ill practices such as ‘Miracle Centres’ or ‘Special Centres’, as a means of coping with academic pressures for good grades (Onyedinefu, 2019; Agwu *et al.*, 2020; Abioye, 2021; Obeza, 2023). The rot is further exacerbated with parental factors, mostly public office holders and educators, probably due to the weak enforcement of the Examination Malpractice Act of 1999 which sets out terms of imprisonment and fines (Agwu *et al.*, 2020).

Based on the foregoing therefore, the main objective of the study is to establish the influence of gender and school location on students’ performance, using NECO results. This is because such information with NECO results are relatively meagre compared to West African Examination Council Examination.

Objectives of the Study

The activities that established gender and location effect on student achievement included to;

1. Determine gender and school location enrolment of students in the study area,
2. Evaluate the relative performance of male and female students in Kaduna North Senatorial District,
3. Assess performance of students at rural and urban schools in the study area.

The study was guided by the following questions;

1. What is the distribution of students by gender (male and female) and school location (rural and urban) in Kaduna North Senatorial District?
2. What is the relative academic performance of male and female students in Kaduna North Senatorial District?
3. What differences exist between academic performance of students attending rural and urban schools in Kaduna North Senatorial District?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses at $P \leq 0.05$ were tested to justify the interactions between gender, school location, enrolment and performance;

1. **H₀₁**; There is no significant difference between the enrolment of male and female students in the rural and urban environment in Agricultural Science in the study area.
2. **H₀₂**; There is no significant difference between the performance of male and female Agricultural Science students in the study area.
3. **H₀₃**; There is no significant difference between the performance of rural and urban Agricultural Science students in the study area.

Methodology

The study covered Northern Senatorial District of Kaduna State which comprised of eight Local Government Areas of Ikara, Kubau, Kudan, Lere, Makarfi, Sabon-Gari, Soba and Zaria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The study area comprised of 101 registered public Senior Secondary Schools in Kaduna. (KSASCR, 2020). A multi stage purposive sampling was adopted in selecting the six Secondary Schools based on location (3 rural schools and 3 urban schools). The three school types selected were two single male school, two single female school and mixed (co-education) school from both environmental settings.

The study was based on the secondary data obtained from National Examination Council (NECO) results for five years spanning through 2018 to 2022 for Agricultural Science. A total of 2,254 students were involved in the study, representing number of students that registered for the subject within the five years. Of the total of 2,254 students, 995 were from urban while 1,259 were rural students, but in gender, male students recorded 1279 as against the female (975) students. The data were confidentially collected from the Zonal Education Office in the zone, using grading system A₁, B₂, B₃, C₄, C₅, C₆, D₇, E₈ and F₉ (Onwunali, Muhammad and Omodara, 2024), and was complimented with results from selected schools. Such grading results were summative and formative, where A₁ represents Distinction, B₂ represents Very good, B₃ represents Good, C₄ to C₆ represents Credit, D₇ - E₈ represents Pass, and F₉ represents Fail. The grades A₁ to C₆ were regarded as quality performance in this study, considering that C₆ is the minimum grade required for further studies in post secondary education. Data were subjected to descriptive

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analysis of means, frequency and percent while independent t-test ($p \leq 0.05$) was used to test significance of the null hypotheses. All analysis were performed using IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 23.

Presentation of Results

Question 1: What is the distribution of students by gender (male and female) and school location (rural and urban) in Kaduna North Senatorial District?

Results (Table 1) showed a general enrolment of 56.74% for male students and 43.26% for female, where 55.86% and 44.14% of the students were located in urban and rural areas, respectively. Furthermore, results revealed a fairly consistent increase in enrolment from 2018 to 2022 for male and urban students and inconsistent in female and rural students which recorded 10.34% and 9.63% in 2022. Results also showed high mean value for male (255.80) and urban (251.40) students' enrolment, compare to the female and rural counterparts. Specifically, relative enrolment of male students was 8.39% in 2018 and 13.30% in 2022 while the female enrolment was 6.74% and 10.83% in 2018 and 2021, respectively. In location, urban enrolment was 8.92% and 14.19% in 2018 and 2022, respectively, while rural relatively recorded 6.21% in 2018 and 19.63% in 2022.

Results clearly indicated that, despite the mean variations in enrolment, the independent t-test value of 2.067 ($p = 0.039 < 0.05$) for gender and 1.732 ($p = 0.088 > 0.05$) for location were not statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) using Senior Secondary Schools NECO results. Therefore, the null hypotheses which stated that there is no significant difference between the enrolment of male and female students in rural and urban environment in Agricultural Science were accepted.

Table 1: Sex and school location enrolment of Senior Secondary Agricultural Science in the North Senatorial District of Kaduna State.

Enrolment N = 2254				
Year	Sex		Location	
	Male	Female	Rural	Urban
2018	189(8.39)	152(6.74)	140(6.21)	201(8.92)
2019	212(9.41)	166(7.36)	167(7.19)	214(9.49)
2020	288(12.78)	180(7.99)	237(10.51)	231(9.45)
2021	290(12.86)	244(10.83)	237(10.51)	297(9.45)
2022	300(13.30)	233(10.34)	216(9.63)	314(14.19)
Total	1279(56.74)	975(43.26)	997(44.14)	1257(55.86)
Mean	255.80±22.95	195.00±18.38	199.40±19.59	251.40±22.75
Sig. ($p \leq 0.05$)	t-value = 2.067, ($p = 0.039 < 0.05$) NS		t-value = -1.732, ($p = 0.088 > 0.05$) NS	

Source: Field survey, 2023 Numbers in bracket are percent of the corresponding numbers of sex and location enrolments per year, \pm = standard error of difference of mean, NS = not significant, null hypothesis was accepted, using t test independent value.

Question 2: What is the relative academic performance of male and female students in Kaduna North Senatorial District?

Results in Table 2 showed that, of the 2254 students that sat for examination within the period, 94.48% generally passed at grades A1 to E8 for both gender. However, the male students had relatively high mean (54.61%) compared to 38.87% of the females. Similarly, on quality of performance (A1-C6), 78.70% had good grades, corresponding to 'A' grade (Excellent), which by relative performance favoured the males (46.81%) more than the females (31.89%). Furthermore, mean performance of the male students was also relatively high (141.88) compared to the females (107.55). However, despite high enrolment of the males, relative failure rate of the female students were high (3.25%) compared to 2.27% of the males students.

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The independent t-test value of 0.648 ($p > 0.05$) statistically showed that, there is no significant difference on the performance of male and female students. Hence the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the performance of male and female students in Agricultural Science was accepted. The relatively high mean may probably be due to high enrolment of males and inability of girls to participate in farm practical.

Table 2: Relative performance of male and female Senior Secondary student in Agricultural Science in North Kaduna Senatorial District.

Grade	Male			Female		
	F	%	QP	F	%	QP
A1	19	0.85		3	0.13	
B2	53	2.36		14	0.62	
B3	85	3.79		46	2.05	
C4	229	10.20		122	5.43	
C5	353	15.72		239	10.65	
C6	312	13.89	46.81	292	13.01	31.89
D7	120	5.35		116	5.17	
E8	55	2.45 (54.61)		63	2.81(38.87)	
F9	51	2.27		73	3.25	
Total	1277	56.88		968	43.12	
Mean	141.88±41.43			107.55±32.96		
Sig. (p ≤ 0.05)	t-value = 0.648, (p 0.526 > 0.05) NS					

Source: Field survey, 2023, Number that sat for examination between 2018 to 2022 = 2254, F = frequency of male and female students per grade, % = relative percentage performance of students per grade, QP = quality of performance of students, NS = not significant, null hypothesis was accepted, using t test independent value

Question 3: What differences exist between academic performance of students attending rural and urban schools in Kaduna North Senatorial District?

Results in Table 3 revealed 94.61% at A1 to E8 pass grades in both locations, with relatively high performance in the urban environment (52.55%) than the 42.06% of the rural. The mean performance values of 139.55 and 109.88 for urban and rural areas, respectively were also evident. Results also showed 78.84% quality performance, where urban students had high scores (43.69%) than the rural (35.15%), probably due to high enrolment, availability and quality teachers, and facilities that are relatively inadequate in the rural setting. Results also recorded high failure in the urban (3.39%) compared to rural (2.00%), possibly due to high enrolment thereof. Nevertheless variation in means, using independent t-test value of 0.564 ($P > 0.05$), did not reveal significant difference between the performance of urban and rural students. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the performance of urban and rural students in Agricultural Science was accepted. The result implied that, performance of students in NECO Agricultural Science between rural and urban areas are relative, possibly due to the examination organization which creates opportunity for malpractice. The high performance in general results and quality may probably be associated with the speculation of poor examination organization.

Influence of Gender... (Omodara, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603575>

Table 3: Relative performance of Agricultural Science students in rural and urban Senior Secondary Schools in North Senatorial District of Kaduna State

Grade	Rural			Urban		
	F	%	QP	F	%	QP
A1	7	0.31		15	0.67	
B2	17	0.76		50	2.23	
B3	21	0.94		110	4.90	
C4	141	6.28		210	9.35	
C5	283	12.61		309	13.76	
C6	320	14.25	35.15	287	12.78	43.69
D7	112	4.99		124	5.52	
E8	43	1.92(42.06)		75	3.34(52.55)	
F9	45	2.00		76	3.39	
Total	989	44.05		1256	55.95	
Mean	109.88±39.24			139.55±35.01		
Sig. (p ≤ 0.05)	t-value = -0.564, (p 0.581 > 0.05) NS					

Source: Field survey, 2023, Number that sat for examination between 2018 to 2022 = 2254, F = Number of students per grade, % = relative percentage performance of students per grade, QP = quality of performance of students, NS = not significant, null hypothesis was accepted, using t test independent value

Discussion of Findings

Results of research question 1 showed that, despite the high enrolment of male and urban students, there was no significant statistical difference between gender and location enrolment in Kaduna North, using NECO Senior Secondary results in public schools. The results also revealed fairly and consistent increase in enrolment of male and urban student, contrary to the fluctuating pattern in female and rural enrolment. Earlier, Onwunali *et al.* (2024) reported fluctuating enrolment of students in Agricultural science which favoured the males student as observed in the study, although there were no significant difference. The female students tend to shy away due to the practical activities in the crop and animal farm practical which they perceived as tedious and requires much energy (Olukayode and Ayoola, 2015; Muhammad *et al.*, 2022). Although many studies have reported a strong correlation between the performance of students in WAEC and NECO examinations (Ogini *et al.*, 2024), inconsistency in the enrolment of students in WAEC (Nwanosike, 2013) may have been probably due to drift of student to NECO due to perceived idea for success through examination malpractice, resulting in the consistent increase in enrolment for NECO. Similarly, Muhammad *et al.* (2022) reported high enrolment of students in urban than rural environment due to drift as a result of rural urban migration and inadequate facilities associated with the rural location.

Question 2 revealed high but no significant performance that favoured the male students, which is in conformity with Nzewi (2010) and Dorgu (2015), who reported that male students performed better in practical oriented vocational and science subjects. However, the insignificant results implied that male and female performance was at par, probably due to the females' lack of interest in practical aspect of the subject. The high-quality performance of students may have probably confirmed the earlier speculation of compromise among supervisors on examination matter. Such general and quality performance is very difficult in WAEC results (Onwunali, *et al.*, 2022). Otherwise, Alordiah, *et al.*, (2015) also concluded that, given equal opportunity there is no significant difference in achievement of male and female students.

On the contrary, Anyaegbu *et al.* (2016) and Newton and Hamisu, (2023) agreed that there is significant difference between academic performance of boys and girls in Agricultural Science. Similarly, Nnenna and Adukwu (2018) in Biology established a significant difference in male and female in favour of male students in Agbani Education Zone of Enugu State. Obviously, in many rural communities, girls are subjected to several barriers such as

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early marriage, cultural and religious barriers like *Kulle* (Onwunali, *et al.*, 2022) as well as domestic responsibilities that may probably limit their educational opportunities, performance and transition to higher institutions of learning (UNESCO, 2011; Felix, 2018).

Results in question 3 showed that, location was not a strong factor in students' academic achievement. Earlier, Yusuf and Adigun (2010) reported that school location had no significant influence on students' academic achievement. Similar to Jack and Sam (2020) who revealed that, there is no significant difference between the mean achievement score of rural and urban students in Biology. On the contrary, Onwunali, *et. al.*, (2022) concluded that location had significant influence on student performance in Agricultural Science in Zaria and Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, using WAEC results.

Schools in urban areas have better access to educational facilities, teaching materials and teachers than schools in rural settings who struggle with inadequate infrastructure like classrooms and teaching materials like textbooks, and even inadequate qualified subject teachers which are key components to improved students' academic performance (Abioye, 2021; Obeza, 2023). Hence subjected to poor academic output due to improper guidance of poor rural teachers that prefer farming and small businesses instead of the primary assignment (Onwunali *et al.*, 2022). However, evidence of better rural performance have been reported (Mbepke, 2013).

In Nigeria, when qualified teachers are posted to these rural locations, they manoeuvre their way back to urban areas or at most abandon their duty post with sporadic report to work due poor incentive from the government and absence of basic amenities such as electricity and accessible roads in most rural areas (Obeza, 2023). Consequently, consolidating the ill practice of establishing miracle centres in rural schools, as examination officers tend to focus their supervision in the urban schools, giving corrupt individuals the opportunity to manipulate examination in the rural areas.

Conclusion

Results from the study evidently showed that, there were no statistically significant differences between relative enrolment and performance of male and female in rural and urban environments in Agricultural Science. Therefore, study concluded that, using the NECO results of 2018 to 2022, gender and school location had no significant influence on the enrolment and achievement of Agricultural Science students in Senior Secondary Schools in Kaduna North Senatorial District of Kaduna State.

Recommendations

From the findings, the following recommendations were made;

1. Kaduna State government should implement the National Policy on Education by recognizing Agricultural Science as a basic vocational subject that should be compulsory for all candidates in primary and Junior Secondary Schools to encourage the female students enrolment in Senior Secondary Schools.
2. The relatively poor performance of female students due to their perceived tedious nature of Agricultural Science should be encouraged through motivation (awards) and effective counselling units in schools, by educational stakeholders such as school management, parent teachers association, school Alumni, school community, Local and State Government.
3. The relatively poor performance of the rural students should be encouraged through provision of trained and qualified teachers, as well as facilities for teaching by government at all levels particularly the local and state governments.

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Influence of Gender... (Omodara, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603575>

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Assessment of E-waste Management on Lifestyle and Environmental Hazards in Schools: A Case Study of Ojo Local Government Area, Lagos State

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Abstract

This study investigates the implications of e-waste management on healthy lifestyles and environmental hazards in private and public secondary schools in Ojo Local Government Area, Lagos State. A descriptive survey design was employed, with data collected from principals, ICT teachers, and students across ten randomly selected secondary schools. The population of the study is 43,458 while the sample size is 400. The research instrument, a structured questionnaire, achieved a reliability score of 0.87. Chi-square tests were used to analyze three hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The first hypothesis tested whether e-waste significantly affects students' healthy lifestyles, and the results showed no significant impact ($\chi^2 = 3.128, p > 0.05$). The second hypothesis examined differences in e-waste management practices between private and public schools, with results indicating no significant difference ($\chi^2 = 0.404, p > 0.05$). The third hypothesis explored whether e-waste contributes to environmental hazards, revealing no significant effect ($\chi^2 = 2.488, p > 0.05$). These findings suggest that e-waste management practices in the studied schools are effective and do not adversely affect health or the environment. However, the results challenge previous research that emphasizes the risks of improper e-waste disposal, indicating the need for ongoing vigilance and improvements. The study recommends enhancing awareness, regular monitoring, collaboration with environmental agencies, centralized e-waste management systems, and recycling initiatives.

Keywords: E-waste, healthy lifestyle, environmental hazards, management, secondary schools

Introduction

The rapid advancement of technology has led to an unprecedented proliferation of electronic devices, significantly altering lifestyles and educational environments. While this digital revolution has brought numerous benefits, it has also introduced new challenges, particularly in the realm of electronic waste (e-waste) management. E-waste, which encompasses discarded electrical and electronic devices, has emerged as one of the fastest-growing waste streams globally, posing significant environmental and health risks. In developing regions like Nigeria, where the regulatory framework and infrastructure for managing e-waste are often inadequate, these risks are particularly pronounced (Saha et al., 2021).

E-waste is a rapidly growing global concern, with an estimated 53.6 million metric tons generated worldwide in 2019, and this figure is expected to rise to 74.7 million metric tons by 2030 (Forti et al., 2020). The improper disposal of e-waste can lead to the release of hazardous substances, including heavy metals like lead, mercury, and cadmium, as well as brominated flame retardants, which can cause serious health issues such as neurological damage, respiratory problems, and even cancer (Grant et al., 2013). Moreover, these substances can contaminate soil and water sources, leading to long-term environmental degradation (Heacock et al., 2016).

Developing countries, particularly in Africa, have become the primary destinations for e-waste due to lax environmental regulations and the economic incentive to recover valuable materials from discarded electronics

(Wideman, 2019). Nigeria, with its large population and growing demand for electronic devices, has emerged as a significant player in the global e-waste trade. However, the country's infrastructure for managing e-waste is underdeveloped, leading to widespread informal recycling practices that often involve unsafe methods such as open burning and acid leaching, which further exacerbate health and environmental hazards (United Nations Environment Programme, 2024).

In Nigeria, the issue of e-waste is particularly pressing due to the combination of high importation rates of used electronic devices and inadequate disposal infrastructure. Lagos State, being the economic nerve center of the country, bears the brunt of this problem. Ojo LGA, in particular, is home to Alaba International Market, one of the largest electronics markets in West Africa, making it a hotspot for e-waste generation (Ogungbuyi, 2012). Despite the presence of regulatory frameworks such as the National Environmental (Electrical/Electronic Sector) Regulations of 2011, enforcement remains weak, and much of the e-waste is processed in informal sectors without proper safety measures (Ogunseitan et al., 2009).

Schools in Ojo LGA are increasingly reliant on electronic devices for educational purposes, from computers and projectors to tablets and interactive whiteboards. However, the end-of-life management of these devices is often overlooked. Many schools lack formal policies or systems for e-waste disposal, leading to the accumulation of obsolete electronics on school premises or their improper disposal through informal channels. This not only exposes students and staff to harmful substances but also contributes to environmental pollution, particularly in a region already struggling with waste management issues (Nnorom et al., 2009).

The health implications of improper e-waste management in schools are significant. Children, in particular, are more vulnerable to the toxic effects of hazardous substances found in e-waste due to their developing bodies and behaviors that increase exposure, such as hand-to-mouth activities (Lebbie et al., 2021). Studies have shown that exposure to e-waste pollutants can lead to cognitive impairments, developmental delays, and other serious health conditions in children (Zeng et al., 2020). In schools where e-waste is not managed properly, students and staff may be exposed to these toxic substances through inhalation of dust, dermal contact, or ingestion of contaminated food and water (Lebbie et al., 2021).

Moreover, the environmental impact of e-waste in schools is profound. Improperly disposed e-waste can lead to the contamination of soil and water bodies with toxic substances, affecting not only the school environment but also the surrounding communities. This is particularly concerning in Ojo LGA, where many schools are located in close proximity to residential areas, increasing the risk of widespread environmental contamination. Additionally, the informal recycling of e-waste, which often takes place near or within school premises, can result in the release of pollutants into the air, further exacerbating environmental and health risks.

In Lagos State, the largest urban area in Nigeria and a hub of technological activity, the challenges associated with e-waste management are acute. Ojo Local Government Area (LGA), home to numerous educational institutions and a densely populated community, is no exception (Soladoye et al., 2020). Schools in this area, like many others in developing countries, are increasingly incorporating electronic devices into their educational practices. However, the disposal and management of these devices, once they become obsolete, have not kept pace with their growing usage. The improper handling and disposal of e-waste in schools pose significant risks to both students' health and the environment, creating an urgent need to address this issue comprehensively. This study aims to address this gap by providing empirical data on e-waste management practices in schools within Ojo LGA and identifying the key challenges and risks associated with these practices. By doing so, it seeks to contribute to the development of effective policies and strategies for managing e-waste in educational institutions, thereby reducing the associated health and environmental hazards. Furthermore, the findings of this study will have broader implications for other regions in Nigeria and similar contexts in developing countries, where e-waste management in schools is likely to be an emerging issue.

Objective of the Study

1. To investigate the implications of e-waste on the healthy lifestyle of students and staff in private and public schools in Ojo Local Government Area, Lagos State.
2. To examine the effects of e-waste on environmental hazards in schools in Ojo Local Government Area, Lagos State.

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3. To compare e-waste management practices in private and public schools in Ojo Local Government Area, Lagos State.

Research Questions

1. What are the implications of e-waste on the healthy lifestyle of students and staff in private and public schools in Ojo Local Government Area, Lagos State?
2. How does e-waste contribute to environmental hazards in schools in Ojo Local Government Area, Lagos State?
3. What are the differences in e-waste management practices between private and public schools in Ojo Local Government Area, Lagos State?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant implication of e-waste on healthy lifestyle of private and public schools in Ojo Local Government Area of Lagos state.
2. There is no significant effect of e-waste on environmental hazard among schools in Ojo Local Government Area of Lagos state.
3. There is no significant difference between e-waste management in private and public schools in Ojo Local Government Area of Lagos state?

Methodology

Research Design

The research design adopted in this study is descriptive survey research design. It was designed in order to collect factual detailed information that describes the existing phenomena. Descriptive survey design is one that allows a researcher to collect information through interviewing or administering a questionnaire with sample drawn from the target population (Orodho, 2005).

Population of the Study

The population of the study is consists of the principal, ICT teachers as well as students each in ten (10) selected secondary schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos state. The population of principals, teacher and students is over 43,458 in both public and private secondary schools in Ojo Local Government Area (Lagos State Ministry of Education, 2017). The choice of the selection was based on the fact that the variables under investigation were particular to them and no other party could provide this information.

Sample and Sampling Technique

To determine the sample size the researchers adopted SurveyMonkey sample size calculator. The sample size deduced was 381. In order to have adequate representation of both public and private secondary schools, the sample was rounded to 400 samples with 204 samples from the public and 196 samples from the private schools. The sample of the study consists of the principal, ICT teachers as well as students selected in each of the 20 secondary schools under sample in Ojo local government area of Lagos state. The research adopted simple random sampling technique where 20 secondary schools with 12 from the public and 8 from the private schools.

Research Instrument

The researchers made use of questionnaire to collect information based on the study, and it contained different variables each on the formulated hypothesis. This questionnaire which was made to consist of 4 keys (strongly agree, agree, disagree, strongly disagree) was formulated to indicate the respondent's opinion to the questions raised. The questionnaire contained two sections A and B. Section A seeks information on demographic data of respondents such as sex, age, class and religion while section B consists of 15 items with 5 question items for each research hypothesis to which the respondents are to reflect their opinion by selecting from any of the 4 keys.

Validity of Instrument

The research instrument, i.e. questionnaire was subjected to validation by giving a copy to the supervisor for effective corrections, comments and amendments. His suggestion was incorporated into the final draft of the questionnaire. This thus helped to improve the instrument done to make the instrument relevant to the study, this made it achieve what it ought to achieve.

Reliability of the Instrument

Reliability refers to the degree of consistency between the set of score obtained with the same instrument (Onocha and Okpala 2011). The corrected versions of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents which forms part of the study. The data collected were collected which generated a value of 0.87 correlation index.

Presentation of Results

Table 1: Gender of the respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Valid Male	172	43.0
Female	228	57.0
Total	400	100.0
Age		
Valid Below 24 yrs	188	47.0
25 to 30 yrs	136	34.0
31 to 35 yrs	52	13.0
36yrs and Above	24	6.0
Total	400	100.0
School type		
Valid Private School	196	49.0
Public School	204	51.0
Total	400	100.0
E-waste seminar		
Valid Yes	324	81.0
No	76	19.0
Total	400	100.0

Table 1 shows the gender distribution of the respondents. It shows male with 43%, while female was with 57%. It further shows the age difference of the respondents. Those below 24 years had 47%, those between 25 and 30 years had 34%, and those between 31 to 35 years had 13% while those between 36 and above had only 6%. Also, it shows school type of the respondents. Those in private school were 49% while those in public school were having 51%. Lastly it depicts whether respondents have ever attended seminar before on e-waste. Those that answered Yes were 81% while those that answered No were only 19%.

Testing of Research Questions

Research Question 1: What are the implications of E-waste on the Healthy Lifestyle of Students and Staff in Private and Public Schools?

Assessment of E-waste...(Adeleke & Owolabi, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603577>

Table 2: School Type *E-waste on healthy lifestyle cross tabulation

			E-waste on Health			
			SA	A	D	Total
H Private School	Count		32	156	8	196
	Expected Count		47.2	140.8	8.0	196
Public School	Count		64	132	8	204
	Expected Count		49.2	146.8	8.0	204
Total	Count		96	288	16	400
	Expected Count		96.4	287.6	16	400.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2 reflects cross tabulation of school type with count and expected count respectively which indicate that e-waste is perceived to have significant implications for the healthy lifestyle of students and staff.

Research Question 2: How does E-waste contribute to Environmental Hazards in Schools?

Table 3: School Type *E-Waste and environmental hazards cross tabulation

			E-waste management in schools			
			SA	A	D	Total
H Private School	Count		40	140	16	196
	Expected Count		31.2	152.8	12	196
Public School	Count		24	172	8	204
	Expected Count		32.8	159.2	12	204
Total	Count		64	312	24	400
	Expected Count		64	312.0	24.0	400.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 3 depicts cross tabulation school type and e-waste environmental hazard with count and expected count which indicate that there is agreement that e-waste contributes to environmental hazards.

Research Question 3: What are the differences in e-waste management practices between private and public schools?

Table 4: School Type *E-Waste Management practices in schools cross tabulation

			E-waste management in schools				
			SA	A	D	SD	Total
H Private School	Count		88	84	16	8	196
	Expected Count		90.0	84.4	15.6	6.0	196
Public School	Count		96	88	16	4	204
	Expected Count		94.0	87.6	16.4	6.0	204
Total	Count		184	172	32	12	400
	Expected Count		184.0	172.0	32.0	12.0	400.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4 depicts cross tabulation of school type and e-waste management with count and expected count respectively which suggest that there is a consensus that private schools generally have more effective e-waste management practices than public schools, largely due to resource availability and better training.

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Testing the Hypotheses

HO1: There is no significant implication of e-waste on healthy lifestyle of private and public school students of Lagos state in Ojo local government area.

Table 5: Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	3.128	2	.209
Likelihood Ratio	3.179	2	.204
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.384	1	.123
N of Valid Cases	400		

Source: Field Survey, 2023

A chi-square test was conducted to find out the significant implication of e-waste on healthy lifestyle of private and public school students of Lagos State in Ojo local government area.

The result shows that there is no significant implication of e-waste on healthy lifestyle of private and public school students of Lagos state in Ojo local government area (chi-square = 3.128, $p > 0.05$).

HO2: There is no significant effect of e-waste on environmental hazard among private and public schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos state.

Table 6: Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	2.448	2	.294
Likelihood Ratio	2.472	2	.291
Linear-by-Linear Association	.228	1	.633
N of Valid Cases	400		

Source: Field Survey, 2023

A chi-square test was conducted to find out the significant effect of e-waste on environmental hazard among private and public schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos state. The result shows that there is no significant effect of e-waste on environmental hazard among private and public schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos state. (chi-square = 2.448, $p > 0.05$).

HO3: There is no significant difference between e-waste management in private and public schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos state.

Table 7: Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	.404	3	.939
Likelihood Ratio	.410	3	.938
Linear-by-Linear Association	.201	1	.654
N of Valid Cases	400		

Source: Field Survey, 2023

A chi-square test was conducted to find out the significant difference between e-waste management in private and public schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos State.

The result shows that there is no significant difference of e-waste management in private and public schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos state (Chi-square = .404, $p > 0.05$).

Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis one states that there is no significant implication of e-waste on healthy life style of private and public-school students and a chi-square test was conducted to show the significance of the hypothesis. The result is shown on table 6 above and it says that there is no significant implication of e-waste on healthy lifestyle of private and public-school students. It was deduced that $\chi^2 = 3.128, p > 0.05$. The hypothesis was not rejected and this implies that e-waste disposal and management in schools within Ojo local government area are properly taken care of and this has no adverse implication on their healthy life style. This finding is against research conducted by Abdelbasir (2018) that says the dangerous effect of burning metal parts of discarded electronic products creates severe health and environmental hazards. Furthermore, Nnorom and Osibanjo (2008), highlighted the significant health and environmental risks posed by improper e-waste management practices, particularly in developing regions. Their research contrasts with the current findings of the study, suggesting that improper disposal can have severe implications on health and the environment.

Hypothesis two states that there is no significant effect of e-waste on environmental hazard among private and public schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos state. A chi-square test was carried out to show the significance of the hypothesis. It was deduced that $\chi^2 = 2.488, df=2, p > 0.05$ and it shows on table 8 that e-waste does not have a significant effect on environmental hazard among private and public schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos state. This is simply because their unused computer gadgets are not always left to litter the environment to an extent of posing threat to lives of individuals around. This finding is against that of Olayinka-Olagunju (2018) that says e-waste is the most existing factor that poses threat to lives of individuals among private and public schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos state. The study by Borthakur and Singh (2012), emphasized the risks associated with the improper disposal of e-waste, particularly in educational institutions, where unregulated practices can lead to significant health and environmental threats. This contrasts with the current study, which suggests that such threats are not prevalent in the schools examined.

Hypothesis three states that there is no significant difference between e-waste management in private and public schools in Ojo local government area of Lagos state. A chi-square test was conducted to carry out to show the significance of the hypothesis and it shows on table 10 that there is no difference in the management of e-waste in both private and public schools. It was deduced that $\chi^2 = 0.404, df = 3; p > 0.05$. Therefore, the hypothesis was not rejected. This finding is against the findings of Foday (2017) that states that the existence of e-waste is so large in public schools compared to private schools. It is also against the assertion made by Manhart et al (2011) that says the existence of e-waste is minimal in private schools. Generally, this finding is revealing that the management of e-waste in both public and private school in Ojo local government area of Lagos state is at equilibrium and no one is surpassing the other.

Conclusions

E-waste is a general issue and everybody should be involved in other to enable a hazard free environment. Furthermore, it was revealed that e-waste is being managed at the same rate in both private and public schools in the areas that were put in view. Though the fact that new electrical gadgets are being bought every year cannot be over emphasized but there exist proper management of those ones that are no longer in use. The study revealed also that training on e-waste management occurs in the schools in view but only occasionally. Majority of the principals agree to employ e-waste managers in their school and a few of them was in contrast because they already have the knowledge of managing e-waste in their school. Accordingly, some of the respondents believe that e-waste management is at equilibrium in both public and private schools.

Recommendations

Basing on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Useless electrical/ electronic should always be put into proper storage or sold in the essence of making more money
2. Unused electrical products also could be transferred to other schools where they would be needed rather than putting into storage without use.

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3. Health education seminars or training should be carried out at every school on E-waste management; this should involve everybody in the exercise.
4. In the case of very harmful e-waste materials, they should be quickly taken to local recycling centers where they would be recycled.
5. There should be standby fund for the management of e-waste in the schools.

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Impact of “Do It” Creativity and Emotional Mastery Strategies on Creativity and Motivation among Adolescents with Special Needs in Oyo State

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Abstract

The study investigated impact of “DO IT” creativity and emotional mastery strategies in fostering creativity motivation among adolescents with special needs in Oyo State. Ninety participants were randomly selected from three special institutions: Cheshire High School, Ibadan; Rehabilitation Centre for the Disabled, Ibadan; and Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo. The age range of the participants was between 13 and 21 with a mean age of 18.5 years. The Self Concept Scale of the Adolescent Personal Data Inventory APDI) was used to classify the participants into self-concept categories ($r = .80$). The criterion measure was Creativity Motivation Scale of the Adolescent Personal Data Inventory ($r = 0.77$). One major hypothesis, with a sub-hypothesis, was generated for the study. Results showed that Creativity Motivation Scores of participants in the “DO IT” and Emotional Mastery groups improved significantly over their counterparts in the control group. It also found that participants in the “DO IT” group benefited more from the programme than those in the Emotional Mastery group. On this that basis, it was recommended that a combination of “DO IT” and creativity and emotional mastery strategies be employed for higher productivity among adolescents with special needs.

Keywords: “DO IT” Creativity, Emotional Mastery, Creativity Motivation, Adolescents with Special Needs

Introduction

The need for creativity motivation is most acute in this generation more than ever. At personal level, it is meant to solve problems in daily life. At societal level, it brings about new findings, new inventions and new social programmes to ease and accelerate man’s comfort, satisfaction, progress and development. All these cannot be realized in the absence of creativity propelled by human motivation and curiosity leading to goal-attainment, self-esteem, self-actualization and comfort.

Smith, Pickering and Bhattacharya (2022) noted that creativity motivation is a multifaceted psychological construct, often fueled by a combination of internal and external motivational factors. One significant factor in creativity is intrinsic motivation, which refers to the desire to engage in an activity for its own sake, rather than for external rewards (Pascale and Woodman, 2016). Amabile (1996) emphasized the role of intrinsic motivation in fostering creativity, arguing that individuals are most creative when they are motivated by the interest, enjoyment, and personal challenge of the task at hand, rather than by external pressures or rewards. This intrinsic drive allows for deeper engagement with the task and fosters risk-taking, exploration, and innovation.

However, external factors, or extrinsic motivation, also play a role in creativity, albeit in more complex ways. While some studies suggest that extrinsic rewards, such as monetary incentives, can stifle creativity by narrowing the focus to obtaining the reward (Deci, Koestner & Ryan, 1999), other research indicates that certain types of extrinsic motivation, like recognition or constructive feedback, can enhance creative performance if they are perceived as supporting the individual's autonomy and competence (Ryan & Deci, 2000). This suggests that the relationship

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between extrinsic motivation and creativity is nuanced, and the impact of external factors depends largely on how they are perceived by the individual.

Recent models of creativity motivation suggest the importance of a dual emotional pathway to creativity. According to Baas, De Dreu, and Nijstad (2008), both positive and negative emotions can stimulate creativity, albeit through different mechanisms. Positive emotions tend to broaden cognitive processes, leading to more diverse and flexible thinking, while negative emotions, when they trigger task engagement and focus, can encourage deeper problem-solving. Thus, emotional motivation—whether positive or negative—can serve as a potent catalyst for creative thinking, depending on the emotional context and individual interpretation.

Often, creativity is influenced by the environment in which individuals operate. A supportive environment that provides opportunities for exploration, collaboration, and experimentation can significantly enhance creativity. Pascale and Woodman (2016), Simonton (2019), Plucker, Makel and Qian (2019) and Smith, Pickering, Bhattacharya (2022) argue that environments promoting psychological safety and diversity of thought are critical for creative breakthroughs, as they allow individuals to take risks without fear of failure.

It has also been established that positive emotions, such as joy and curiosity, are known to facilitate creative thinking by broadening cognitive flexibility (Fredrickson, 2001). Conversely, stress or negative emotions may either inhibit creativity or, in some cases, motivate individuals to engage in problem-solving under pressure. The dual pathway model proposed by De Dreu, Baas and Nijstad (2008) suggest that different emotional states can activate distinct cognitive pathways leading to creative outcomes.

The social and cultural environment plays a crucial role in shaping creative motivation. Societies that value innovation, diversity, and unconventional thinking tend to produce more creative individuals. Cultural norms, social support systems, and the availability of resources all contribute to whether creativity is fostered or stifled (Csikszentmihalyi, 2013). Ultimately, creativity is a dynamic interplay between intrinsic motivation, the structuring of extrinsic factors, and emotional influences. This complexity underlines the importance of considering multiple motivational pathways to understand how creativity can be nurtured in various settings.

Akinboye (2003) opined that creativity is the bedrock of human success as well as the quality of individual, family and organizational prosperity and well-being. Etuk (1992) explained that the days are gone when life was simple as against nowadays when there are many problems, challenges, ambiguities and situations that are neither structured nor well-defined, hence the need for creative thinking and ideas.

De Bono (1971) defined creativity as bringing out new ideas and updating old ones. Animasahun (2002) defined creativity as conscious cognitive processes stimulated by problematic situation, guided by interest and resulting in the generation of statistically infrequent, novel, original, unique, valuable and appropriate ideas useful in turning challenges of life into fruitful, benefited and profitable outcomes. Olawale (2007) submitted that creativity is thinking new ideas and doing new things for the satisfaction and development of self and society. Akinboye and Olawale (2005) defined “DO IT” creativity as follows:

D – Define (the problem).

O – Open (yourself to many possible solutions),

I – Identify (the best of the many possible solutions).

T – Transform (the best solution into effective action).

Besides, Pool (1997) established that emotional well-being is a predictor of success in academic achievement and job success among others. Click (2002) noted emotional intelligence distinguished individual “star performers” and plays an important role in determining which organizations will out-perform others in competitions. Akinboye (2003) corroborated this when he declared that emotional intelligence is the basis for good character, trust, integrity, resilience, commitment, motivation, sensitivity, humour, courage, conscience and humility. Goleman (1998) showed that when cognitive intelligence provides entry into a particular career, it is emotional intelligence that determines how successful someone would be afterwards.

Therefore, it is necessary to subject the afore-mentioned two novel techniques (“DO IT” and Emotional Mastery) to experimental manipulation to foster creativity motivation thereby since both methods have the capacity to do that. For instance, Akinboye (1976b), Owolabi (1988), Olagunju (1990) and Animasahun (2002) have shown that creativity motivation could be deliberately fostered. This study would provide empirical evidence as regards the comparative effects of the two techniques on the subjects in order to verify the earlier studies.

Impact of “Do It”... (Olawale, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603577>

In most cases, the inherent or acquired disability makes it difficult for individual persons to be motivated to use their initiatives, or become creative not to talk of living independently. This makes people with special needs resort to fate and become burden on the family and society in addition to self-pity. If the situation continues, the adolescents concerned and the society may not be able to cope with the emerging personal, social, economic and security challenges. Therefore, it is necessary to foster creativity motivation in adolescents with special needs so that they would be able to think and act creatively and stand on their own.

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of the study essentially is to experimentally investigate the impact of “DO IT” Creativity and Emotional Mastery Strategies in fostering creativity motivation among selected adolescents with special needs in Oyo State.

Research Question

One Research Question for the study is stated below.

Will there be a significant difference in the creativity motivation scores of treated participants and participants in the control group; and will the two treatment strategies have equal effects on the treated participants.

Hypothesis

The null hypothesis at .05 degree of significance is stated below.

H₀: There is no significant difference in the creativity motivation scores of treated participants and participants in the control group; and the two treatment strategies have equal effects on the treated participants.

Design of the Study

A 3 x 3 factorial design is adopted for the study. The two experimental and control groups form the rows while three levels of self-concept (low, moderate and high) constitute the columns. The design has the capacity of revealing the effectiveness of the two treatments (training programmes) and mediating the extraneous factors. The use of control will actually consolidate the results.

Participants

Ninety (90) adolescents with special needs were randomly selected from three special institutions in Oyo State. They were: Cheshire High School, Ibadan; Rehabilitation Centre for the Disabled, Moniya, and; Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo. Their age ranged between 13 and 21 with a mean age of 18.5 years. The participants were matched into different categories of self-concept on the basis of their scores in the Self-Concept Scale of the Adolescent Personal Data Inventory (APDI), whereas they were assigned into treatment and control groups on the basis of balloting.

Instrumentation

There were two standardized instruments adopted for the study. The first was the 30-item Section A of APDI by Akinboye (1977a) to determine the self-concept level of the participants ($r = .80$). The second was the 17-item Section D of APDI to measure the Creativity Motivation of the participants ($r = .77$).

Procedure

The first meeting with the participants in the institutions targeted on general introduction, establishment of rapport and administration of APDI (Self-Concept Scale) for the purpose of assigning them to appropriate Self-Concept levels. After this, they balloted for the three groups (experimental groups and control). The first meeting ended with collection of pre-test data of the groups. Then, the “DO IT” group was exposed to creativity motivation programme for six weeks (one hour per week). Likewise, the Emotional Mastery group was exposed to emotional mastery package for six weeks (one hour per week), whereas the control group was not exposed to any form of training programme. At the end of the exercise, the same (but fresh) instruments were administered on the participants to collect post-test data.

Data analysis

The study employed Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and t-test to analyze the data collected.

Results

The hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in the Creativity Motivation Scores of treated participants and participants in the control group; and the two treatment strategies have equal effects on the treated participants.

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Tables 1 - 3 resent the data to test this hypothesis. In testing this hypothesis, a Regression Analysis of Creativity Motivation Scores using pre-test as Covariates was carried out. The resultant unadjusted Y-means for Creativity Motivation are shown in table 1.

Table 1: Mean Scores on Creativity Motivation

GROUP S	Improved Creativity Motivation Variable								
	<i>Low Self Concept (LSC)</i>			<i>Moderate Self Concept (MSC)</i>			<i>High Self Concept (HSC)</i>		
	$\frac{\sum X}{N}$	N	$Y-\bar{Y}$	$X-\bar{X}$	N	$Y-\bar{Y}$	$X-\bar{X}$	N	$Y-\bar{Y}$
“DO IT”	33.40	10	61.40	40.90	10	71.50	46.50	10	72.10
Emotional Mastery	34.90	10	53.90	41.60	10	62.30	47.20	10	66.00
CONTROL	51.70	10	36.10	57.70	10	40.20	69.50	10	49.30

Source: Field Study by the Researchers

Table 1 shows that the unadjusted Y-means scores of treated groups (“DO IT” and Emotional Mastery) and the Control group. Treated groups seemed to perform better than the control group. This shows that the treatment strategies accounted for the higher scores than those in the control group. However, the participants in the “DO IT” group performed better than those in the Emotional Mastery group. For further clarity and explanation of the hypothesis, an analysis of covariance was performed to determine whether there was a significant difference in the creativity motivation of treated participants and participants in the control group. The results are shown in table 2.

Table 2: Analysis of Covariance for Creativity Motivation Variable.

Source of variation	Sums of squares	DF	Mean Squares	F	P
ROWS	1279.298	2	639.649	98.28	<0.01
COLUMNS	176.028	2	88.014	13.52	<0.01
INTERACTION	17.513	4	4.378	0.67	NS
WITHIN	5271.593	81	6.508		

Source: Field Study by the Researchers

Table 2 describes Analysis of Covariance on Creativity Motivation variable of the two treatment groups (“DO IT” and Emotional Mastery) and the Control Group. The Rows comprise of the treatment groups and the control group. The columns consist of the three levels of self-concept (Low, Moderate and High). The interaction shows the relationship between the rows and the columns. From the foregoing, it is clear that there is a significant difference in the performances of the treated groups and the control as shown in the rows ($F = 98.28, df=2/81, p<0.01$). This shows that the treated groups benefited greatly from the treatments than the control group. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected. There is also a significant difference in the level of self-concept of the participants as indicated by columns ($F=13.52, df=2/81, p<0.01$). However, there was no significant difference in the interaction ($F=0.67, df=4/81, (NS)$). In order to show clearly the results for easy comparison, the table for the adjusted Y-means for the treated groups and control group on creativity motivation variable was constructed as shown in table 3.

Table 3: Adjusted Y – Mean Scores on Creativity Motivation Variable

GROUP	Low Self Concept (LSC)	Moderate Self Concept (MSC)	High Self Concept (HSC)
“DO IT”	(a) 62.65	(b) 72.06	(c) 72.15
Emotional Mastery	(d) 55.01	(e) 62.80	(f) 65.99
CONTROL	(g) 35.67	(h) 39.22	(i) 47.24

Source: Field Study by the Researchers

Table 3 presents the adjusted Y-mean scores of the treated participants (“DO IT” and Emotional Mastery) and the participants in the Control on Creativity Motivation Variable. From the table, it is clear that the scores of the treated subjects (X=62.65, 72.06, 72.15, 55.01, 62.80 and 65.99) were higher than the scores of participants in the control group (X=35.67, 39.22 and 47.24). This shows that the treated groups benefited highly from the treatment programmes than those in the control group. However, those in the “DO IT” group benefited more than those in the Emotional Mastery group.

For a comprehensive analysis of the results and to ascertain the extent of difference that existed, Scheffé post hoc analysis showing series of t-tests were computed to determine the difference in the mean using the adjusted Y-mean scores and the variance of the mean. See Appendix K for the pair comparisons and their description.

In the final analysis, there was significant difference in the Creativity Motivation scores of participants in the treated groups and those in the Control group (F = 98.28, df = 2/81, P<0.01). Nevertheless “DO IT” Creativity proved to be more effective with adjusted Y-mean scores (X=62.65, 77.06 and 72.15) with the overall X-mean of 46.04 compared to the Emotional Mastery with adjusted Y-means (X= 55.01, 62.80 and 65.99). Therefore, the sub-hypothesis is also rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Results in tables 1-3 indicated that significant differences existed in the Creativity Motivation scores of treated participants and participants in the control group. The adjusted Y-mean scores revealed that participants exposed to “DO IT” Creativity scored the highest, followed by participants exposed to Emotional Mastery, while participants in the control group came last. This shows that as far as differential effectiveness is concerned, “DO IT” Creativity is more effective than Emotional Mastery in the experimental groups, though Emotional Mastery too is effective. It could be noted that the difference that existed between the treated groups and the control was due to the effects of treatment training programmes. Hence it could be established that “DO IT” Creativity and Emotional Mastery Strategies are effective in improving creativity motivation of the participants.

This finding support earlier submissions of Akinboye (1976b), Owolabi (1988), Olagunju (1990) and Animasahun (2002) that creativity motivation could be fostered. However, this is incongruent with Fleith, Rodnigues, Viana and Cerqueira (2000) who postulated that creativity cannot be taught but learned, and “error” is regarded as a potential way to generate creative ideas. Foo (1988) also supported the earlier submission when he reported that creativity education has been an inspiration to educators and leaders in Singapore. Stenberg and Frensch (1993) supported the idea that information obtained during Creativity training session is applicable across a variety of problems.

Participants in the “DO IT” Creativity and Emotional Mastery groups might have performed so well on Creativity Motivation variable because of the sensitivity of the programmes, the commitment of the researcher, the motivation or incentives they usually received every session and the cooperation of staff members of the institutions. The fact that the participants were motivated from the beginning to the end of the programme might account for their full commitment and excellent performance.

The evident improvement in creativity motivation of the treated participants would enable them see life problems as challenges that would provoke in them creative thinking, creative solution and higher performance. The study has therefore established that the two treatment strategies (“DO IT” Creativity and Emotional Mastery) are

Impact of “Do It”... (Olawale, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603577>

effective in fostering life skills in the treated participants. However, “DO IT” creativity is more effective than Emotional Mastery.

Conclusion

Over the years, persons with physical disabilities have contented themselves with back-bench and second-class status in our society. But this empirical study has shown that they have innate abilities and could excel in self-management, productivity and creativity. Hence the days of self-pity, inferiority complex and dormancy are over. It is high time persons with disabilities took their destiny in their own hands with appropriate life skills and march forward in the drama of survival and healthy competition in our society. Indeed, more than anything else, it is these life skills which persons with disabilities require most to be able to survive at home, at school, at work, in leisure, in marriage, and in their relationships with others in society.

The findings in this study have shown that both “DO IT” Creativity and Emotional Mastery were veritable intervention programmes in improving creativity motivation and emotional intelligence as well as reducing the inferiority complex, dormancy and lack of productivity of adolescents with special needs in Oyo State, Nigeria. The two strategies were effective in fostering life skills in the participants, though “DO IT” Creativity is more effective than Emotional Mastery. Furthermore, participants in the experimental groups performed significantly higher than those in the control group which indicates that the treatment strategies were very effective.

Recommendations

Based on the findings in the study, the following are the recommendations:

1. “DO IT” Creativity strategy should be employed to foster creativity motivation among adolescents with special needs and their able-bodied counterparts.
2. Emotional Mastery technique should be used to nurture creativity motivation among persons with special needs and their able-bodied counterparts.
3. A combination of “DO IT” Creativity and Emotional Mastery should be employed to produce greater improvement in creativity motivation among persons with special needs and their able-bodied counterparts.
4. A combination of “DO IT” Creativity and Emotional Mastery should be employed to foster creativity motivation across the strata of learners’ population.
5. An appropriate legislation should be put in place to enrich quality of life of persons with special needs.

Educational Implications

The findings of this study were quite important and relevant to the current educational focus on creativity, innovation, resourcefulness, entrepreneurship and self-employment of graduates (school leavers). The integration of creativity motivation in the curricula of schools, colleges, polytechnics and universities would catapult the nation to greatness at lesser cost within a short period of time.

Ethical Consideration

The study abided by ethical guidelines in terms of voluntary participation, safety and confidentiality of the participants. Approval and cooperation of all the institutions used were secured. All the data obtained were anonymized to protect the privacy of the participants, and also showcased the integrity of the investigators. The participants were initially informed about their right to withdraw themselves from the study at any point without any consequence.

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Qualitative Study on Vocational and Technical Education Programmes in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects

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Abstract

The paper critically examined the concept of vocational and technical education, the objectives, as well as the challenges. The paper also looked at the prospects of the programme and therefore concludes that the laissez faire attitude currently expressed by Nigerian government towards vocational and technical education programme has in no small measure resulted to myriad of challenges hindering the achievement of the programme objectives which include but not limited to the following: Inadequate funding, inadequate workshop facilities and instructional materials, lack of vocational guidance/job placement, poor societal perception and many too numerous to mention hindering the achievement of the curriculum objectives of the programme. The paper therefore recommends among others that government should increase the funding of vocational and technical education programme. Provide adequate tools, equipment and facilities required in the training workshop. Provide basic amenities in all the vocational institutions across the nation. Regular repairs, or replacement of faulty tools, equipment and instructional facilities in the training workshop. Lastly vocational institutions should establish a link with the industries in order to work out the areas of relevant occupational skills currently required in the industries.

Keywords: Vocational, Technical Education, challenges, prospects

Introduction

Education is a vital tool through which any nation can experience growth and development. Developing nation such as Nigeria required education for self-reliance and national sustainability. That is, education that prepare the individual for occupational skills as well as equip the recipients to be job creator rather than job seeker. The education that enthrone work and labour as well as enhances human dignity by making individuals acquire employable skills, knowledge and attitudes required for self-reliance and national sustainability. This system of education is achieved through vocational and technical education programme.

Many scholars have given various definitions of vocational and technical education. However, United Nation Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) and International Labor Organization (ILO) (2002) defined vocational and technical education as a means of preparing for occupational fields and for effective participation in the world of work. It was also defined as the form of education that places emphasis on the development of occupational skills required for preparation for work (UNESCO & ILO, 2001). That is any form of education which primary purpose is to prepare the recipient for employment in recognised occupations.

Furthermore, UNESCO and NBTE (2003), defined vocational and technical education as an aspect of the educational process involving, in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences, and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life. In a similar development, The National Policy on Education according to Federal Ministry of Education (2013) defined vocational and technical education as the study of technologies and related sciences for the acquisition of practical skills, attitude, understanding and knowledge that lead to occupational field for effective participation in the world of work and also as a method of alleviating poverty.

According to Federal Ministry of Education (20013), the major objective of vocational and technical education is to prepare recipients for self employment and employment for the labour market. Furthermore, the blue-print on education (2004) revised (2013) provided the aims and objectives of technical and vocational education as follows:

1. Provide trained manpower in the applied sciences, technology and business particularly at craft, advanced craft and technical levels.

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2. Provide the technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agricultural, commercial and economic development;
3. Give training and impart the necessary skills to individuals who shall be self-reliant economically
4. Provide people who can apply scientific knowledge to the improvement and solution of environmental problems for the use and convenience of man.
5. Enable our young men and women to have an intelligent understanding of the increasing complexity of technology
6. Give an introduction to professional studies in engineering and other technologies.

Given the laudable objectives of vocational and technical education programme, as stated in National Policy on Education by Federal Ministry of Education (20013), it is crystal clear that if the curriculum objective of the programme is effectively implemented, it could assist the nation to overcome poverty and its associated problems. For this to be achieved, the programme must be provided with adequate human and material resources as well as functional facilities and equipment in the training institutions. But in reality Nigeria government has neglected this aspect of education that provides the vocational and technical skills required for national development. Therefore, vocational and technical education like every other aspect of educational programme in Nigeria is currently bedeviled with myriads of challenges.

Challenges of Vocational and Technical Education Programme in Nigeria

Some of the challenges bedeviling the successful implementation of vocation and technical education programme in Nigeria include the following:

1. Dearth of qualified personnel/inadequate personnel
2. Lack of physical resources/inadequate workshop tools and equipment
3. Inadequate funding/ financial constraints
4. Poor remuneration of vocational and technical teachers
5. Wrong/poor societal perception and misconception of the programme
6. Poor Student Motivation
7. Lack of political stability
8. Gap between vocational institutions and Industry
9. Inadequate guidance/job placement
10. Inadequate entrepreneurship education programme

Dearth of Qualified Personnel/Inadequate Personnel

A walk round most of the Nigeria's vocational training centres, technical colleges and even tertiary institutions revealed that these institutions are not adequate in the quality and quantity of personnel. This situation according to Amaechi, and Thompson, (2016) is partly responsible for the low quality of graduates produced from the programme. Some of the teachers that were sent abroad in the early 1980s for vocational training under the Technical Teacher Training Programme never returned. Some that returned took up more lucrative jobs in other establishments; others established enterprises of their own; thus the incident of lack of qualified vocational teachers continues to affect the nation.

Study conducted by Anayo and Ezeudu (2018) revealed that graduates of vocational education, find it easy to secure employment in various establishments or become self-employed as a result of the versatile nature of the programme. Therefore, instead of remaining in the classroom to train others students, they rather prefer to become self-employed. This tendency is often worsened by poor remuneration and unattractive working conditions of teachers. This has continued to affect vocational education negatively. Wordu, Igrubia and Okotubu, (2018) stated that only a few federal universities presently, offer full-blown vocational and technical education programmes and even some of the few, are yet to mount PhD programmes in this specialized field of study thereby compounding the problem further. Ogbuanya, and Usman (2020) further stated that in most of the institutions, the machinery and equipment supplied several years ago are still lying waste-in their various crates or containers – unopened and unused due to lack of qualified personnel to operate, service or repair them.

Lack of Physical Resources/Lack of Adequate Workshop Tools and Equipment

Physical facilities include basic infrastructure, such as buildings, laboratories workshops and studios. Mbag, Sambo and Aminu (2018), stated that most of the schools that offer vocational education courses are not provided with enough and appropriate equipment and materials for training. Babayo and Abdul (2017) also stated that most of the so-called studios, laboratories and instructional materials in vocational institutions are just a caricature of what they should be.

Inadequate Funding/ Financial Constraints

Technical and vocational education programme is capital intensive programme. Therefore, requires adequate funding by both the government and well-meaning individuals. Masaruf, (2015) opined that funds must be made available and adequate

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to meet the cost of personnel, building, equipment, laboratories, studios, demonstration farms, etc. However, Oguntuyi (2013) revealed that the funding of vocational education programme in Nigeria is grossly inadequate. Tijani, Adeyemi and Omotehinshe (2016), also attributed the poor maintenance culture of the tools and equipment in vocational institutions to lack of funding. Therefore, resulting to poor and non-functional facilities and equipment in vocational and technical education institutions in Nigeria.

Wrong/Poor Societal Perception of Vocational Education Programme

Oguntuyi, (2013) revealed that the general Nigerian public tends to give wrong perception to vocational education. Some seem to think of it as education for under- achievers, unintelligent people, school drop outs, and the less-privileged. It has also been wrongly perceived as a “dirty” kind of education due to its practical nature. Adesua, (2022) stated that these wrong perceptions are traceable to our colonial days and lead to the problem of societal stigma. Traditionally, so-called “intellectual” work is often contrasted with “manual” work. Thus there would be, on the one hand, white-collar (office) professions and, on the other, traders, technicians, etc. Nowadays, such a distinction is gradually becoming visible, as society continues to undervalue and minimize technical education. Consequently, pupils are facing difficulties in their studies of vocational streams. From the above point vocational education has for some time now seemed to have received negative stigma. For instance, parents would rather have their wards and children study more “prestigious” and “glamorous” courses such as medicine, law and engineering rather than vocational and technical courses.

Lack of Vocational Guidance and Counselling

According to Amimani and Ogunyika (2011), lack of adequate vocational guidance has made it difficult to correct the wrong perceptions pupils have about vocational education programme as well as the consequent of the societal stigma. There is therefore, strong need to mount vocational guidance and counseling programmes for the public and in various academic institutions for appropriate enlightenment on the subject.

Lack of Power Supply

Ibrahim and Abdullahi (2010), revealed that in most parts of the country, effective vocational and technical education programme is hindered by lack of or inadequate power supply to run the necessary equipment and machines. In addition, Okotubu (2022), revealed that most of the necessary spare parts for servicing and repairing the equipment are not readily available. Lack of water supply also pose a problem in some vocational and technical institutions.

Poor Student Motivation

It is common to find that in some vocational and technical education institutions, the laboratories, studios and workshops are often not used. Those that are in use, are used rather infrequently and rigidly as enough time usually is not allocated for practical activities in the workshops or laboratories. According to Eze (2015), students are often not allowed to use the laboratories or workshops at their spare time. All these lead to poor motivation, lack of confidence and uncertainty about the students’ ability to succeed or perform well enough on the programme of the students.

Lack of Political Stability

Studies by Nwana (2018), revealed that as a result of political instability in Nigeria, there have been unstable government policies affecting the funding, administration and management of education especially vocational and technical education programme. Policies initiated by previous administration are often rejected and dumped by another regime of administration. This has in no small measures affected the smooth running of vocational and technical education institutions.

The Gap between Institutions and Industry

Several studies have revealed that there seems to be a disconnect between the vocational skills acquired in the various institutions of learning and the skills required in today industries. For instance, Masaruf (2015) and Ogbu (2015) revealed in their studies that there is a disconnect between vocational skills acquired in the training institutions and the industrial needs of the society. Therefore, there is the need for functional link and co-ordination between the training institutions and the industries. This is because the training institutions produce for the industries. A good Technical and Vocational Education curriculum or programme benefits from the linkage between school and industry. It is the gap between institutions and industry that partly accounts for the high rate of unemployment among graduates of the programme. This is because students are trained based on procedures and equipment that are no longer needed in various industries. The students therefore graduate to discover that they do not actually possess any employable/entrepreneurial skills and competencies expected of them.

Inadequate Entrepreneurship Education Programme

Entrepreneurship education aims at equipping students with occupational skills, sharp business acumen and ingenuity to enable them create employment for themselves and others. It should therefore be an integral part of effective vocational

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education. It is not enough to just include “Entrepreneurship” as a course for vocational education students. The course content and method of delivery should have a practical orientation to make the programme really beneficial to the students.

Prospects

From the numerous challenges of inadequate funding, inadequate workshop facilities and instructional materials, lack of vocational guidance/job placement, poor societal perception discussed above, it is evident that Nigerian government have expressed laissez faire attitude towards vocational and technical education programme from the inception of colonial masters. This laissez faire attitude of government towards the programme has in no small measure resulted to myriad of challenges hindering the achievement of the curriculum objective of the program in Nigeria. However, most of these challenges could be surmounted if the government and well-meaning individuals are genuinely committed to change the course of vocational and technical education programme in Nigeria. Once this is done, the future and prospects of vocational and technical education programme in Nigeria will be bright. Therefore, vocational and technical education programme in Nigeria will be overwhelmed with numerous prospects irrespective of the challenges being faced today. Some of these prospects include the followings:

1. Vocational and technical education programme has the capacity to revamp Nigeria economy if given the accorded attention with regards to funding.
2. Vocational and technical education constitutes a vital engine for economic, social, practical and all-round development of any nation.
3. It is an instrument for promoting environmentally sustainable development amongst others.
4. Serve as learning and training centre for the translation of dreams and ideas into successful ventures.
5. Builds technical and conceptual skills in the individual that prepares him for today’s world of work.
6. Leads to technological advancement.
7. Reduces poverty and idleness.
 - a. Directs towards self-reliant and sustainable means of livelihood.

Conclusion

Going by the policy statement of the programme, vocational and technical education institutions in Nigeria have been training people to become craftsmen, master craft-men, technicians and technologist. According to Ndudi and Samuel (2016) the training qualifies them for jobs in both public and private sectors of the economy. In a similar development Wordu, Okotubu, and Ugorji (2018) stated that the training institutions have been training and producing graduates that can perform competently in their chosen vocation without a need for pre-employment training. But because of the current challenges in the implementation of the curriculum objectives of the programme, most of the graduate lack the necessary skills require to be employable in the industries or self employed. Sequel to this, there is need for total overhaul of vocational and technical education programme in Nigeria.

Recommendations

In light of the above, the paper therefore suggests as follows:

1. Government should improve on the funding of vocational and technical education programme
2. Private sectors and well-meaning individual should partner with the government in the funding and provision of training facilities in needed in vocational and technical education institutions.
3. Government and other education stakeholders should make sure that vocational and technical education programmes at all levels are made relevant so asto provide youth and graduates with the needed vocational and technical skills.
4. Vocational institutions should partner with private sectors and industries in order to provide relevant educational programmes that would enable the graduates of the programme relevant in the world of work.
5. There should be a link, understanding and co-operation between vocational education institutions and industry. Both should work on areas that would make vocational education programmes relevant to industry.
6. Regular seminars and workshops should be organised for vocational teachers in order to keep them abreast of current development in the field of vocational and technical education programme and how best to impact them on their students.
7. Effective vocational guidance and counseling should be carried out at all level of vocational institutions so as to properly guide the trainee in chosen a vocation base on their competence and interest.

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8. Effort should be made by government and head of schools to always repair or replace fault tools, equipment and facilities in vocational and technical institutions.
9. Efforts should be made by government to provide basic amenities such as water, electricity, in all vocational institutions across the country.
10. More universities and other institutions should be encouraged to mount full-fledged programmes on vocational education and the graduates of such programmes should be encouraged to stay in the field.
11. Vocational educational curricula should be kept as broad, dynamic and practical-based as possible. The curricula should be designed by experts in the various areas and subjected to periodic review by experts too
12. Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) and entrepreneurship education programmes should be made more meaningful and relevant to the students.
13. Institutions should equip their laboratories, workshops and farms not just for accreditation purposes but also for students' practical use. This will encourage and motivate, as well as build up self-confidence in them

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Assessment of Indiscipline Behaviours among Public Primary Schools Pupils in Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The arts of indiscipline behaviours and unimaginable acts of deviat are prevalent among public primary school pupils in Nigeria. This study examines the issue of indiscipline behaviour among pupils of the upper of public primary schools. The primary purpose was to investigate the act of discipline behaviours among the pupils and the factors causing the indiscipline behaviours. The design for the study was the descriptive research design. The population covers all head teachers, male and female teachers in Delta State public primary school. The sample size of the study was 200 respondent purposive and randomly selected among public school head teachers. Data was collected using the questionnaire and open-ended structured statement. The findings revealed various acts/forms of indiscipline behaviours among the pupils to include telling of lies, fighting/bullying, disobedient to teachers among others. The factors responsible for indiscipline behaviours included the home, school system, peer-group and the society. The indiscipline behaviours caused administrative difficulties and challenges to head teachers. There were evidences of indiscipline behaviours among public primary school pupils. It was recommended among others that the family-parents/guardian, classroom teachers and head teachers should be role model and give adequate supervision to the pupils and have a regular parent-teacher association meetings.

Keywords: Primary school, Public primary school, Pupils, Indiscipline Behaviours, Head Teachers.

Introduction

Indiscipline is a progressing vice befalling our schools even in the primary schools. Today students are engaging in some imaginable misconduct and acts of deviant. The concept of indiscipline is seen in different ways by different authors or researcher but all boil down to a social vice bedevilling the society and practiced among children. Indiscipline means lack of discipline, lack of control, lack of proper training unruly behaviour, disobedience and disorder. (Jekayinfa 2013). Indiscipline among primary school for children is becoming a perennial issue for both parents, teachers and even educational administrators in the various ministries of education. There has been a general public concern on the height and rate of indiscipline in schools. Indiscipline as a concept is seen in different ways and interpretations as a noun or adjective. Kamara et. al. (2024) defines indiscipline as a noun which is failure to obey rules and orders a lack of control in the behaviour of a person or group of people. This is a situation where people cannot obey rules and lack control of their behaviour. This is very noticeable in our primary schools today. From the school gate, you could notice pupils non-challant behaviour in early attendance to schools, wearing of all sorts of dresses apart from the school uniform and being disobedient. Very noticeable in our primary school today. From the school gate you could notice pupils non-challant behaviour in early attendance to school, wearing of all sort of dresses apart from the school uniform and being disobedient to rules and regulations of the school. Odebo (2019) opined that indiscipline among students in Nigerian schools remained a source of great concern to stake holders in education. According to this indiscipline has some negative damages such as mental, emotional and physical damage in the society.

Indiscipline could simply be seen as lack of or outright disobedient or failure to adhere to laid down rules and regulations. Indiscipline is a deviation from established and accepted standard of behaviour. Indiscipline behaviours is not peculiar to school environment but could be observed in homes and in society too. In educational environment like school indiscipline behaviours could be described as a violation of school rules and regulations by students/pupils within the school premises. Various forms of indiscipline behaviours common in schools include leaving school without permission, physical aggression, disturbance of others, inappropriate use of school materials

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and non-compliance with teachers directives as observed by Gyapong & Sabbey (2021). According to Gyapong & Sabbey (2021) Causes of indiscipline behaviours could be factors such as school size, home, individual family, gender, ethnicity z school, societal and peer-group pressure. In a recent study by Kamara *et al* (2024) the cause of indiscipline behaviours among school children were identified as school-based factor, home based factor, learner based factors and societal based factors. Therefore, the issue of indiscipline behaviours among primary schools pupils particularly in upper classes is evident in our public primary schools. The causes of indiscipline behaviour in upper classes of the primary education level are traceable to the home, school, peer-group and society.

The primary is the next place of education for the child after the home. The school is a microcosm of society, hence the home, school and society influences the child's behaviour. Indiscipline as a concept has been defined by researchers and authors. Adeniyi & Adedotun (2019) sees indiscipline lack of discipline, lack of control, lack of proper training. In the view of Enefu *et. al.* (2019) indiscipline is a behaviour disorder that is tagged an act of delinquency. According to Adeojoke and Orekelewa (2020) indiscipline is any act of not confirming to orders, policies, procedures, rules and regulations of the society. In same view, indiscipline could be defined as disobedient to all school rules and regulations; and any act of that is deviant of the accepted behaviours of the school as an educational institution. The child's home, school and society have great influence on the students' behaviour. Infact studies have been carried out extensively on indiscipline and several factors have been identified by scholars. These factors have been traced to the home, school, society and government. Ngirokabuenui (2015) opined that five causes of indiscipline included lack of respect for teachers, teachers lateness to school, family instability, which are evident is lack of training in children. Adegoke and Orekelewa (2020) identified home and societal environments as the major causes of indiscipline in school. For Enefu *et al.*, (2015) causes of indiscipline can be found in the school administration and teachers themselves. An earlier study of Ali *et al.*, (2014) asserted that school, students and society are the factors responsible for indiscipline in schools. From the above literature, it could be seen that the factors causing indiscipline in schools are the home/family, school, itself the students and the society. Causes of indiscipline in primary schools could include mental factor, family instability, media influences, economic instability, government policies, school leadership and parental attitudes. According to Opara (2020) several factors contribute to indiscipline behaviours which include media influences, environmental factors, inadequate parental upbringing, societal values, negative peer group influencers and lax enforcement school rules and regulations.

In schools today, acts or types of behaviours displayed by children could be grouped into minor, major and intolerable indiscipline behaviours. The minor behaviours were noise-making in class, absenteeism and loitering on school premises. The major indiscipline behaviours were missing classes, habitual lateness, stealing, telling lies, cheating during classes, fellow classmate article like pencils, rulers; while the intolerable indiscipline aits include watching and practicing pornography, rapping school/class mates, vandalism of school property, harassment and drug abuse (Oyem, 2016). Indiscipline is any form of students misbehaviour which students exhibit such as general disobedient constituted authority distraction of school property, poor attitude to learning, abuse of seniority, immoral behaviour, drug abuse, stealing, lateness, truancy, dirtiness and noise making in classroom. According to Ndidiamaka *et al* (2023) common indiscipline exhibited by primary school pupils are fighting, disobedience, dishonesty, failure of learners to do homework, arrogance, disrespectful to teachers, untidiness, out of seat, non- punctuality, idleness, impolite, distracting others, throwing pens in attentive in the class, lying among others.

Indiscipline which producers behaviour among primary school has some negative effects on the pupils in hindering effective functioning of the school system. Ngirokabuenui, (2015) opined that indiscipline constitutes hitches that inhibit the effective school system in the study carried out by Adeniyi and Adedotun, (2019) it was reported that there was a significant difference between indiscipline and academic activities of students and a significant gender difference between discipline and academic activities of students. Enefu *et al* (2019) reported that indiscipline had adverse effects on students' academic performance. Adegoke and Orekelewa, (2020) reported that indiscipline contributed to poor performance of secondary school students. Indiscipline behaviours among children in school has negative consequences on the learners and the school at large.

Indiscipline behaviours among primary school pupils have become a pervasive concern in contemporary educational setting. The increasing incidence of unruly behaviour disobedience and disruptive conduct among school pupils poses significant challenges to effective teaching, learning and school administration. This phenomenon undermines the academic achievement, socialization and emotional well-being of pupils, ultimately jeopardizing their

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future projects. Indiscipline behaviours among primary school pupils have reached alarming stage. There has been efforts to promote discipline but indiscipline behaviour has continued to manifest through disruptive behaviour of fighting and bullying; disobedience to rules and authority and social misbehaviour such as stealing, lying with all forms of dishonesty and disrespect. Over the years, there has been increasing rate of indiscipline behaviours among primary school pupils in public schools Enefu et al (2019) carried out a research on effects of indiscipline on Academic performance of secondary school students while Adeniyi & Adedolun (2019) studied indiscipline and academic of studies – implications for counselling. This study is an assessment of indiscipline behaviour among public primary school pupils in Delta State with a focus on incidence and factors causing indiscipline behaviour among pupils in public primary schools and its influence on school administration.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective was to assess the prevalence and factors causing indiscipline behaviours and the influence on indiscipline behavior on head teacher administration in public primary school

Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Assess the types of indiscipline behaviours exhibited by public primary school pupils.
2. Identify the causes of indiscipline behaviours among public primary school pupils.
3. Examine the influence of indiscipline behaviours on the head teacher's school administration.

Research Questions

In this study on the assessment of indiscipline behaviours among primary school pupil answers are sought to the following research questions that guided the study:

1. What are the ratings of indiscipline among pupils in the public primary school by male and female head teacher?
2. What are the factors responsible for the common indiscipline behaviours among pupils of upper classes in public primary schools?
3. How do the indiscipline behaviours of pupils influence your school administration as head teachers?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the ratings of male and female head teachers on the indiscipline behaviours common among pupils of public primary schools.
2. There is no significant difference between the ratings of experienced and less-experienced head teachers on the indiscipline behaviours among pupils of public primary schools.

Methodology

The study was a descriptive research. The study adopted a survey approach. This was to be able to cover a representative sample. The target population of the study comprises of all head teachers in Delta state, using a purposive sample, head teachers were selected from the three senatorial district of the state, from each of the selected schools, head teachers were randomly selected, giving a total of two hundred respondents, composing both male and female Head-Teachers. This represents the population sample for the study. The instrument for the study was a questionnaire developed by the researcher. The instrument has three sections, Section A consists personal data of the respondents, while section B consists list of indiscipline behaviours rating Highly Common (HC), Moderately Common (MC), and Not Common(NC). Section C consists of items of factors responsible for pupils indiscipline behaviors. Respondents were to indicate their choices. The number three research question was an opened ended structured questionnaire the respondents were expected to state how the indiscipline behaviours of the pupils influenced their school administration.

The researcher and trained research assistant administered and collected the questionnaire on the sampled respondents and ensure proper filling and prompt retrieval as they personally administer the questionnaire. Data was analyzed using frequency count, percentage and Chi-Square (X^2) was used to test the formulated hypotheses testing at 0.05 level of significance.

Assessment of Indiscipline... (Ajudeonu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603587>

Presentation of Results

Presentation of results on the demographic data of respondents. The three research questions and two hypotheses raised in this study.

Demographic Data of Respondents – Gender

The demographic data of respondents were needed to provide answers to the two hypothesis raised in the study. These were on gender and experience of the respondents.

Table 1: Frequency counts and percentages of respondents based on gender

Variable	Frequency	Percentage %
Male	114	57.0
Female	86	43.0
Total	200	100

Table 1: Showed that male head teachers are 114(57%) while the female head teachers are 86(43%) of the sampled population of respondents.

Table 2: Frequency counts and percentages of respondents based on experience.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage %
Less experienced	80	40.0
Experienced	180	60.0
Total	200	100

Table 2: showed that 120 respondents representing 60% of the total population sample are experienced head teachers while eighty (80) respondents representing 40% of the total sample are less experienced Head Teachers.

Research Question I

What are the ratings of indiscipline behaviours among pupils in public primary school by male and female head teachers?

Table 3: Frequency counts and percentages of respondents' ratings of indiscipline behaviours in among the pupils of public primary school.

S/N	Indiscipline Behaviours	HC	MC	NC	Total
1	Lateness to School	64 (32.0)	91 (45.5)	45 (22.5)	200
2	Talking in the classroom	122(61.0)	71 (35.5)	7 (3.5)	200
3	Neglecting Homework	92(46.0)	90 (45.0)	18 99.0)	200
4	Fighting and Bullying	103(51.0)	82 (41.0)	15(7.5)	200
5	Disobeying the Teacher	173(86.5)	27 (13.5)	-	200
6	Stealing Things	171(85.5)	27 (13.5)	2 (1.0)	200
7	Dishonesty	32(16.0)	86 (43.0)	82 (41.0)	200
8	Sexual Immorality	12(25)	35 (17.0)	154 (75.5)	200
9	Telling Lies	182(90.0)	20 (10.0)	-	200
10	Abusive Language	168(84.0)	29 (14.5)	3 (1.5)	200

HC – Highly common MC- Moderately Common, NC- Not Common

Assessment of Indiscipline... (Ajudeonu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603587>

Table 3: shows the frequency counts and percentages of respondents rating of indiscipline behaviours among public primary school pupils. This was presented in the frequency of Highly common (HC) Moderately Common and Not Common (NC).

Table 3 revealed that indiscipline behaviours of telling lies, 182(90.0); destroying teacher 173(86.5), stealing things 171(85.5) Asusive language 168(84.0), taking in the classroom 122(61.0) and fighting and bullying 103(51.0) were highly common among the public primary school pupils.

While lateness to school 91(45.5) and neglecting home work 90(45.0) were moderately common with sexual immorality 154(75.5) was the least of the recorded as no-common indiscipline behaviour among public primary school pupils.

Research Question 2: What are the factors responsible for the common indiscipline behaviours among pupils of in public primary schools?

Table 4: Frequency Count of respondents view on factors responsible for indiscipline behaviours among pupils in public primary schools.

S/N	Family status	School system	Peer pressure	Mass Media	Society	Frequency
1	35	64	78	11	10	200
2	81	17	24	48	30	200
3	10	03	122	60	05	200
4	25	04	70	23	18	200
5	17	07	94	40	42	200
6	30	53	87	09	21	200
7	38	45	-	03	114	200
8	54	39	51	46	10	200
9	54	-	137	-	09	200
10	113	30	-	01	56	200

Table 4 shows that numbers of the respondents that agreed to the listed factors responsible for the common indiscipline behaviours among pupils of public primary schools.

All respondents agreed that family status, school system, peer pressure, Mass media and society have great influence on pupils indiscipline behaviours in public primary schools.

From the result on the table it was revealed that neglecting homework was due to peer group influence, dishonestly was influenced by the society while abusive language was influenced by the home.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between male and female Head teacher rating of the indiscipline behaviours among pupils in public primary schools.

Table 5: Chi Square (χ^2) analysis of respondents rating based on Gender.

S/N	Gender	HC	MC	NC	Total	X ²	DF	Remark
1	M	29(36.5)	52(57.9)	33(25.7)	114	8.466	2	S
	F	35(27.5)	39(39.1)	12(19.4)				
2	M	35(52.4)	64(51.3)	15(10.3)	86	25.893	2	S
	F	57(39.6)	26(38.7)	3(7.7)				
3	M	19(6.8)	16(19.4)	88(87.8)	114	4.767	2	S
	F	2(5.2)	18(14.6)	66(66.2)				
4	M	52(58.7)	58(46.7)	4(8.6)	86	13.723	2	S
	F	51(44.3)	24(35.3)	11(6.5)				
5	M	47(69.5)	62(40.5)	5(4.00)	114	44.222	2	S
	F	72(52.5)	9(30.5)	2(3.0)				
6	M	91(97.5)	21(15.4)	2(1.1)	86	7.263	2	S
	F	80(73.5)	6(11.6)	0(0.9)				

Assessment of Indiscipline... (Ajudeonu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603587>

7	M	199(192.6)	14(11.4)	-	114	1.523	1	NS
	F	80(77.1)	6(8.6)					
8	M	92(95.8)	19(16.5)	30(1.7)	86	3.465	2	S
	F	76(72.2)	10(12.5)	0(1.3)				
9	M	96(98.6)	18(15.4)		114	1.190	1	NS
	F	77(74.4)	9(11.6)					
10	M	0(18.2)	38(49.0)	16(46.7)	86	90.778	2	S
	F	32(13.8)	48(37.0)	6(35.30)				

M = Male
 F = Female
 HC = Highly Common
 MC = Moderately Common
 NC = Not Common
 S = Significant
 NS = Not Significant

Table 5 shows items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 8 and 10 revealed that there was significant difference between male and female Head teacher ratings while item 7 & 9 revealed no significant difference between their ratings based on gender.

Table 6: Chi square analysis of average overall of the respondents ratings based on gender.

Gender	HC	MC	Total	X ²	DF	Remark
Male	45(45.6)	69(68.4)	114	0.031	1	NS
Female	35(34.4)	51(51.6)	85			

HC = Highly Common
 MC = Moderately Common
 NS = Not significant

Table 6 shows that the calculated Chi square value is less than the T-Value at 0.005 level of significance. This means that the null hypothesis was not rejected. There was a significant difference in the ratings by male and female head teachers.

Hypotheses 2: There is no significant difference between the ratings of experienced and less experienced head teachers on the indiscipline behaviours common among pupils of the public primary schools.

Table 7: Chi- Square analysis of respondents ratings based on the Head Teachers experience.

S/N		HC	MC	N	Total	X ²	DF	Remark
1	LEX	27(25.6)	36(36.4)	17(18.0)	80	0.288	2	NS
	EX	37(38.4)	35(54.6)	28(27.0)				
2	LEX	37(36.8)	37(36.0)	6(7.3)	120	0.31	2	NS
	EX	58(55.2)	53(54.0)	12(10.8)				
3	LEX	2(4.8)	13(13.6)	65(61.6)	80	3.079	2	NS
	EX	16(7.2)	21(20.4)	89(92.4)				
4	LEX	44(41.2)	31(32.8)	5(6.0)	120	0.760	2	NS
	EX	59(61.8)	51(49.2)	10(9.0)				
5	LEX	52(48.8)	25(28.4)	3(2.8)	80	1.052	2	NS
	EX	70(73.2)	46(42.5)	4(4.2)				
6	LEX	63(68.4)	16(10.8)	1(0.8)	120	4.967	2	NS
	EX	108(102.6)	11(16.2)	1(1.2)				
7	LEX	72(72.0)	8(8.0)	-	80	0.000	1	NS
	EX	108(128.0)	17(12.0)					
8	LEX	62(67.2)	117(11.8)	1(1.2)	120	4.916	2	NS
	EX	106(100.8)	12(17.4)	2(1.8)				
9	LEX	67(69.2)	13(10.8)	-	80	0.863	1	NS
	EX	100(103.8)	14(16.2)					
10	LEX	15(12.8)	32(34.4)	33(32.8)	120	0.911	2	NS
	EX	17(19.2)	54(5.6)	49(49.2)				

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LEX – less Experienced Head Teachers.

EX = Experienced Head Teachers

HC = Highly Common

MC = Moderately Common

NC = Not Common

Table 7: shows the item analysis of respondents ratings of the indiscipline behaviours among pupils in the upper classes of the public primary schools. The table showed that there was no significant difference based on Head Teachers experience as revealed by the analysis of the responses.

Table 8: Chi square Analysis of overall Average of the respondents response based on experience.

S/N	Experience	Highly Common	Moderately Common	Total	X ²	DF	Remark
1	Less Experienced	33(30.4)	47(49.6)	80	0.031	1	NS
2	Experienced	43(45.6)	77(74.4)	120	0.378		

Table 8 shows that the Chi- Square value is less than the table calculated value at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the ratings of experienced and less experienced head teachers on the levels of indiscipline behaviours among pupils in public primary school is not rejected

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study indicated that the respondent rated telling lies as the highest act of indiscipline among the pupils, others were disobedient to teachers, using abusive language, talking during class, and lateness to school, while sexual immorality was rated the least. The findings agreed with the report of (Oyem, (2016) and Ndidiamaka *et al*, 2023).

On the factors responsible for common indiscipline behavior among public primary school pupils , the respondent agreed that that the family, school system, student themselves and society all contributed in the problems of indiscipline behaviours. The findings was in line with the earlier study by Emefu *et al*, (2015) and Ali *et al* 2014. Agreeing that the home, school and environment of pupils could influence them. The findings of the study revealed that there was no significant difference between the ratings of indiscipline behaviours among public primary school pupils based on gender. Both male and Female head teachers actually reported the evidence indiscipline behavior among pupils in public primary school.

The second hypothesis revealed that there was positive but no significant difference between the ratings of less experienced and experienced head teachers on their ratings of on discipline behaviours among pupils in public primary schools. Open ended questions were used to solicit head teachers opinions on how the pupils indiscipline behavior influenced their school administration. The responses from the head teacher revealed that pupils indiscipline behavior caused administrative difficulties and challenges such as, Damage to school reputation, compromise of school safety, time consumption – take away valuable time from administrative tasks with increased accountability for indiscipline. Emotional toil brings out stress and burn out affecting the well being of school administrators in public primary schools.

Conclusion

The indiscipline behavior among pupils in upper classes of the primary school is undeniable with pupils engaging in unimaginable misconduct and acts of deviant. There are evidences of indiscipline behaviours among pupils in public primary schools as rated by the head teachers. The factor responsible for indiscipline behaviours included the home, the school, the students, themselves and the society at large. Head teachers are caught in the web of products of indiscipline behavior causing administrative difficulties and challenges in the performance of their school administrative tasks.

Assessment of Indiscipline... (Ajudeonu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603587>

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. All stakeholders involved in the life of pupils at this tender age; parents, head teachers and class room teachers should task themselves to increase supervision of the children and also to be a role model for the children to imitate for a disciplined behavior.
2. There should be effective head teachers balance prevention, intervention, and reactive strategies to manage pupils indiscipline by ensuring conducive, positive learning environment.
3. There should be regular interaction with pupils by showing them empathy and support for pupils.
4. Head teachers should continuously ensure fairness in the discipline of pupils and sometimes allow flexibility approach to suit individual needs of pupils.
5. Advocate for regular Teacher-Parent meeting to discuss pupils behavior.
6. Lastly, provide counseling service to individual or group counseling for pupils.

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Comparative Analysis between Open Defecation Practices and Environmental Health Status on Residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State

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Abstract

The study examined the Comparative analysis between Open defecation practices and Environmental health status on residents in mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State. Two research questions and hypotheses were postulated and it employed descriptive research design. The Population of this study consists of all residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State. Simple Random sampling techniques was adopted and sample for this study was Three hundred (300) residents of Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State. The research instrument for this study was a self-developed modified Questionnaire, titled Environmental Open Defecation Questionnaire (EODHQ). The Test-retest method of reliability was adopted, the reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach Alpha technique of r value= 0.86. Data collected was analyzed using frequency count and percentages for data representation while inferential statistics of Chi-square and Linear regression was used to test all stated hypotheses. The finding revealed that, there was significant practice of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State and Attitude of residents have significant relationship with the practice of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local government Area, Lagos State and it was recommend that government should ensure the construction of more decent public latrine facilities in the area to end open defecation.

Keywords: Attitude of Residents, Open Defecation and Health of Residents

Introduction

The health of individuals remains largely unmet and often side-lined in circumstances where open defecation is available. Open defecation is defined as the practice of defecating in open fields, waterways and open trenches without any proper disposal of human excreta (Belay, et al, 2022). Open defecation is strongly associated with incidence of diarrhea disease, prevalence of helminthic infection and stunting especially in children less than five years of age. Open defecation is the human practice of defecating outside ("in the open") rather than into a toilet. People may choose fields, bushes, forests, ditches, streets, canals, or other open spaces for defecation. They do so either because they do not have a toilet readily accessible or due to traditional cultural practices (Clasen, 2014).

Open defecation is credited to the publications of Joint Monitoring Program (JMP) in 2008, a joint collaboration of World Health Organisation (WHO) and United Nations International Children Emergency Fund (UNICEF) to evaluate the global progress on water and sanitation goals. Open defecation is classified as unimproved sanitation (WHO & UNICEF, 2017). Despite 15 years of conjunctive efforts under global action plans such as the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), targets for improved sanitation were not met, resulting in 2.5 billion people not having access to improved sanitation facilities (flush latrine or pit latrine) and nearly 892 million of the total world's population still practice open defecation (Bisung & Elliot, 2016). As a result of this failure to successfully

ensure basic sanitation it was once again highlighted as a key issue in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Number 6 of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is to “Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all”, where the Target aims by 2030 is to achieve access to adequate and equitable sanitation and hygiene for all and end open defecation, paying special attention to the needs of women and girls and those in vulnerable situations (United Nations, 2015).

In 2020, 54% of the global population (4.2 billion people) used a safely managed sanitation service; 34% (2.6 billion people) used private sanitation facilities connected to sewers from which wastewater was treated; 20% (1.6 billion people) used toilets or latrines where excreta were safely disposed and 78% of the world population (6.1 billion people) used at least a basic sanitation service (WHO, 2015). The average proportion of ‘open defecators’ in developing countries is 16%, and in the least-developed countries 20%. Of those who still practice open defecation 90% of people reside in rural areas of three regions; sub-Saharan Africa, Central Asia and Southern Asia (WHO & UNICEF, 2017). Diarrhoea remains a major killer but is largely preventable. Better water, sanitation, and hygiene could prevent the deaths of 297 000 children aged under 5 years each year. Open defecation perpetuates a vicious cycle of disease and poverty. The countries where open defecation is most widespread have the highest number of deaths of children aged less than 5 years as well as the highest levels of malnutrition and poverty, and big disparities of wealth (WHO, 2022).

Nigeria (located in West Africa) is among the countries with the highest rate of open defecation ranking 2nd in Africa and 5th globally in 2010 (WHO & UNICEF, 2012). A report by Abubakar, (2008) highlighted that in 2015 about 46 million Nigerians engaged in outdoor defecation, bringing Nigeria from 5th position to 3rd position in prevalence of open defecation globally. According to WHO/UNICEF, (2012) reported that 34 million Nigerians practiced open defecation in 2010. The World Development Indicators in 2016 also confirmed that open defecation practice in Nigeria had risen from 24% to 25.1% of its population in 1990 to 2015 respectively (World Bank & World Development Indicators, 2016). October 2019, The Nigeria Minister, Suleiman Adamu of Ministry of Water Resources in a forum on sanitation organized by Organised Private Sector, disclosed that Nigeria now ranks 1st in the world in open defecation prevalence with about 50 million Nigerians practicing open defecation. This indicates that open defecation is a burden in Nigeria. Open defecation leads to outbreak of infections which the government needs to contain to prevent loss of lives. The World Bank estimated that about \$8.3 billion will be needed by the Nigerian federal government to curb open defecation (World Health Organization/United Nations Children's Fund, (2015).

Open defecation can pollute the environment and cause health problems and diseases. High levels of open defecation are linked to high child mortality, poor nutrition, poverty, and large disparities between rich and poor (World Health Organization & United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund, 2014). In ancient times, there were more open spaces and less population pressure on land. It was believed that defecating in the open causes little harm when done in areas with low population, forests, or camping-type situations. With development and urbanization, open defecating started becoming a challenge and thereby an important public health issue, and an issue of human dignity (O'Reilly, 2016) With the increase in population in smaller areas, such as cities and towns, more attention was given to hygiene and health. As a result, there was an increase in global attention towards reducing the practice of open defecation. Open defecation perpetuates the vicious cycle of disease and poverty and is widely regarded as an affront to personal dignity. The countries where open defecation is most widely practiced have the highest numbers of deaths of children under the age of five, as well as high levels of under nutrition, high levels of poverty, and large disparities between the rich and poor (WHO & UNICEF, 2014).

The negative public health impacts of open defecation are the same as those described when there is no access to sanitation at all (Desai, McFarlane & Graham, 2015). Such impacts include, but not limited to, environmental pollution due to widespread scattering of human feces even in public utilities, loss of income and productive time including missed school hours and days by school-aged children, and finally lack of privacy, dignity, and threat to human safety (Desai, et al., 2015). Open defecation and lack of sanitation and hygiene in general is an important factor that cause various diseases, the most common being diarrhea and intestinal worm infections but also typhoid, cholera, hepatitis, polio, trachoma, and others (Spears, & Haddad, 2015). Adverse Health effects of open defecation occur because opens defecation results in fecal contamination of the local environment. Consequently, open defecators are repeatedly exposed to many kinds of fecal bacteria like gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* and other fecal pathogens, and this is particularly serious for young children whose immune systems and brains are not yet fully

developed. Certain diseases are grouped together under the name of waterborne diseases, which are diseases transmitted via fecal pathogens in water. Open defecation can lead to water pollution when rain flushes feces that are dispersed in the environment into surface water or unprotected wells (Anoop, et al, 2020).

Those countries where open defecation is most widely practiced have the highest numbers of deaths of children under the age of five, as well as high levels of malnourishment (leading to stunted growth in children), high levels of poverty, and large disparities between rich and poor (WHO & UNICEF, 2017). Infected human excreta contain several harmful organisms that are associated with a number of health problems. Virtually, one gram of infected human excreta can contain a variety of microbes which includes 106 pathogenic viruses and viral infections, 106-108 bacterial pathogens, 103 protozoan cysts and 10-104 helminth eggs (Belcher, 2018). Inappropriate human waste disposal also increases the risk of exposure to these pathogens which can pose significant health risks such as transferable infectious diseases, diarrhoea, typhoid and cholera, and viral infections (Pruss-Ustun, et al, 2008). The unpleasant and continuing environmental effects encountered by residents are becoming disturbing and their health is in great chaos with this method of disposing excreta especially the health of their children (Ogunbamowo, Ashon & Elemoro-Oni, 2022). Environmental pollution encountered by residents include; increase in waterborne diseases which can cause diarrhea, cholera, trachoma; increase in vector diseases. Children are the most vulnerable to environmental pollutants. This is because they are not aware of their activities and their surroundings, and also they do not have adequate knowledge of health implication of environmental and air pollution escaping is so difficult for them. More so, the fact that children find it easy to play anywhere and in any condition they find themselves exposes them more to the danger of air pollution.

Open defecation and lack of sanitation and hygiene in general is an important factor that cause various diseases, the most common being diarrhea and intestinal worm infections but also typhoid, cholera, hepatitis. Most children get malnourished from the disposal of this waste in the area. It is sad that most of the residents have been found not to recognize the effects of open defecation until signs and symptoms of health impairment manifest and even if they do recognize it, poor knowledge has allowed them. The stench and foul smell in the area is another probing menace from the use of open defecation. Therefore, this study assesses the Comparative analysis between Open defecation practices and Environmental health status on residents in mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the Comparative analysis between Open defecation practices and Environmental health status on residents in mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.

Other specific purposes were:

1. To examine the practices of open defecation among the residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.
2. To examine the Attitude of residents towards open defecation among the residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent do the practices of open defecation exist among the residents among the residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.
2. To what extent does the attitude of residents affect the practice of open defecation among the residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were postulated for the study:

1. There will be no significant practice of open defecation among residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.
2. There will be no significant relationship between the attitude of residents and the practice of open Defecation among residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.

Methodology

The descriptive research design was adopted for this study while the Population of this study consists of all residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State. Simple Random sampling techniques was adopted for this study and sample for this study was Three hundred (300) residents of Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State. The research instrument for this study was a self-developed modified Questionnaire, titled Environmental Open Defecation Questionnaire (EODHQ). The questionnaire was divided into two sections: A and B, Section A contained demographic data of respondents, while section B was an opinion question on environmental Effect of open defecation on the health of all residents. The questionnaire adopted a four (4) point Likert scale as stated: Strongly agree (SA), Agree (A), Strongly Disagree (SD) and Disagree (D). The content, construct and face validity of the questionnaire were ascertained in the Department of Human Kinetics, Sports and Health Education, Lagos State University, Ojo, by panel of three experts including researchers supervisor to ensure a thoroughness which indicated that the instrument measured what it was intended to measure in relation to research questions and hypotheses. The Test-retest method of reliability was adopted. This required the researcher to administer twenty (10) copies of the validated questionnaire to twenty (10) participants from Lagos Island Local Government Area to determine the reliability of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach Alpha technique of r value= 0.86 which was very good. The copies of questionnaire were personally distributed with the help of three trained research assistants to the respondents. Three hundred (300) questionnaires were distributed and collected by the researcher at the spot and data collected lasted for four (4) weeks among residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.

Copies of the administered questionnaire were checked to ensure that they were well completed before leaving the study area. The researcher monitored the process of data collection throughout. Daily review meeting were held at the beginning and end of each day with the research assistants. Data collected was analyzed using appropriate descriptive statistics of frequency count and percentages for data representation while inferential statistics of Chi-square and Linear regression was used to test all stated hypotheses at 0.05 level alpha of significance. The statistical package for social science (SPSS) was used for analyzing the data collected.

Presentation of Results

Demographic Analysis

Table: 1 Distribution of respondents by Age, Gender, Tribe, Marital Status and Accommodation type.

Age	Frequency	Percentage %
21-30	234	78.0
31-40	31	10.3
41-50	23	7.7
50 years above	12	4.0
Total	300	100.0

Gender	Frequency	Percentage %
Male	37	12.3
Female	263	87.7
Total	300	100

Tribe	Frequency	Percentage %
Yoruba	133	44.3
Igbo	1	0.3
Hausa	166	55.3
Others	0	0
Total	300	100.0

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage %
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Comparative Analysis...(Waliu, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603589>

Non-Formal	248	82.7
Primary	26	5.6
Secondary	17	8.7
Tertiary	9	3.0
Total	300	100.0

Accommodation type	Frequency	Percentage %
Uncompleted	85	28.3
Boys Quarter	6	2.0
A Room	199	66.3
Flat	10	3.4
Total	300	100.0

Table 1 Demographic on Age showed that 234 (78.0%) of the respondents were within the age bracket of 21-30 year, while 31 (10.3%) were within the age bracket of 31-40 years and 23 (7.7%) were 41-50 years, and 12 (4.0%) were within the age bracket of 50 years above. Consecutively the demographic on Gender showed that 37 (12.3%) of the respondents were male while 263 (87.7%) of the respondents were female. The demographic on Tribe showed that 133 (44.3%) of the respondents were Yoruba, while 1 (0.3%) were Igbo, 166 (55.3%) were Hausa while 0% was recorded for other tribe. The demographic on Marital Status showed that 248 (82.7%) of the respondents had Non-formal education, while 26 (5.6%) had primary education, 17 (8.7%) had secondary education and 9 (3.0%) had Tertiary education. Finally the demographic on Accommodation type showed that 85 (28.3%) of the respondents lived in uncompleted building, while 6 (2.0%) lived in boys quarter, 199 (66.3%) lived in a room and 10 (3.4%) lived in Flat.

Hypothesis One

Hypothesis one states that there will be no significant practice of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State. This hypothesis was tested using Chi-square at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented on the table 2 below.

Table: 2 Chi-square (X^2) results on Practice of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual X^2	Sig
Strongly agree	54	99.7	-33.7	95.445
Agree	179	99.7	79.3	
Disagree	66	99.7	-45.7	
Strongly Disagree	0			
Total	300			

From the result presented on table 4.6 above, it could be observed that a significant Chi-square value ($X^2=95.445$, $p<0.05$) was obtained at 0.05 level of significance, therefore hypothesis one as stated is hereby rejected. This implies that there was significant practice of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State. The distribution of respondents' responses showed that majority (179) agreed to have practiced followed by 54 respondents that strongly agreed, 66 respondents disagreed while just 0 respondents strongly disagreed.

Hypothesis Two

Hypothesis one states that there will be no significant relationship between attitude of residents and the practice of open defecation among residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State. The result is presented on the table below.

Table: 3 linear regression result on relationship between attitude of resident and practice of Open defecation

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		T	Sig.
Model	B	SE	Beta			
R = 0.023						
R ² = 0.001						
AR ² = -.003						
F = .163						
Sig. = 0.013*						
(Constant)	3.091	0.326			9.481	0.000
Regular exercise	-.045	0.112	-.023		-.404	0.013

Dependent Variable: Practice of Open defecation

It could be observed from table 4.7 above that the relationship between regular exercise and occurrence of blood pressure could be predicted at 2.3% (R²=0.023) accuracy. The table further showed that a significant F-value (F=.163; P=0.013) was obtained at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, hypothesis two as stated above is hereby rejected. This implies that Attitude of residents had significant relationship with the practice of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local government Area, Lagos State. The positive t-value (t=9.4881; P<0.05) implies that Attitude of residents have a significant relationship with the practice of Open defecation among residents of Mainland Local government Area, Lagos State.

Discussion

The Hypothesis one above states that there will be no significant practice of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State. This finding is supported by a study on open defecation practice and its determinants among households in sub-Saharan Africa, pooled prevalence and multilevel analysis of 33 sub-Saharan Africa countries demographic and health survey by Belay, Asratie & Aragaw, (2022) agreeing that Open defecation is more practice in sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries. A total of thirty-three SSA countries were represented for this study in the four regions of the total of 47 countries located in SSA, only 41 countries had Demographic and Health Survey reports. All households which were found across 33 SSA countries during the survey period were the source population. Whereas households assessed for sanitation facilities during each survey across 33 SSA countries were the study population. The analysis contained a total weighted sample of 452,281 households. Demographic and Health Survey data sets of 33 SSA countries with a total sample of 452,281 households were used for this study. The pooled prevalence of open defecation practice among households in sub-Saharan African countries was 22.55%. It was concluded that open defecation practice remains a public health problem in sub-Saharan Africa.

Another study was in agreement by Coffey, et al., (2014) lamented the high rate in the practice of open defecation in rural communities which remains stubbornly widespread with several dire consequences affecting the human health and environment alike. This barbaric practice kills babies, and impedes the physical and cognitive development of surviving children. It also has significant negative externalities and releases germs into the environment which pose serious harm to both the rich and the poor in the society. Open defecation is very common, even in households with access to a latrine and Communicable diseases outbreak was a threat not only to lives of individuals but also national security (Ogunbamowo & Oladipupo-Okorie, 2021). In four focus states, 80% of all interviewed households had at least one member who defecates in the open. Forty-eight per cent of households with a working latrine which are determined either by the fact that someone in the household used it or by the presence of a pit and seat, had at least one member who nevertheless defecates in the open. Strikingly, in the four focus states, 45% of households with a latrine user also had at least one household member who defecates in the open. In another study which agreed with the findings by Belcher, (2018), poor latrine conditions, structure, and design may deter latrine use and provoke reversion to open defecation. Statistics show that only 18% of the households in Turkana County, Kenya, have access to a latrine facility with most of these facilities in poor structural designs and poor hygienic conditions, which encourages rampant open defecation practices. It would therefore be inferred that there will be no significant practice of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local Government Area.

The Hypothesis Two above states that "There will be no significant relationship between attitudes with the practice of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State". The finding agrees with a study by Board & Suzuki, (2015) a survey was conducted in Ojo Local Government Area. Five areas were

randomly selected from this area for the study with 281 heads of each household filled the questionnaire. The attitude of respondents in the Local Government Area was negative. Open defecation was higher among households that did not have latrine. In another study which agrees with the findings by Bakobie, et al., (2021) assessed the attitudes of each household in a community in Indonesia. The sample consisted of 92 heads of families who live in Cibaduyut Village, and the sampling technique used was stratified random sampling. Data were collected by means of interviews and a questionnaire. Attitude variable is 0.855, it is 85.5% variance of the attitude variable which can be explained by the formed factors, and finally the Social Interaction Variable is 0.848. The relationship between Attitude and open defecation behavior in Nagari Koto Rawang, IV Jurai, Pesisir Selatan Regency, which agrees with the study by Anoop, et al, (2020). From the results of the data analysis, it was found out that from the 50 respondents who open defecation, 64.0% of them have poor attitudes, and 63.0% of respondents who had good attitudes, defecated in the latrine. Based on bivariate analysis result with the Chi-square test on the Attitude variable with open defecation behavior obtained $p\text{-value} = 0.021$ ($p < 0.05$). Thus, it shows that the attitudes had a significant relationship with open defecation behavior. Therefore, it could be inferred that there is significant relationship between attitudes of residents with the practice of open defecation in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was inferred that;

1. There was significant widespread of sanitation practices of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.
2. There was significant relationship between attitude of residents and the practice of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion of this study, it was recommended that:

1. The landlords should be given a must task to ensure they have latrine facilities in every rentals.
2. The government should ensure the construction of more decent public latrine facilities in the area to end open defecation.
3. The cost of using public toilet facilities should be at a subsidized price where everyone can afford to pay to use it and the usage should be free for the aged and children.
4. The government with the help of Non-governmental organization should create more awareness, sensitization, education of the community on proper sanitation management especially on latrine facilities and its consequences of open defecation.

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Qualitative Study on Data Privacy Policy and Data Mining in Educational Assessment in Nigeria: A Systematic Review

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Abstract

This paper examined how well data privacy policies regulate data mining practices in educational assessment frameworks. With the rising use of data mining in educational institutions to improve student assessment and tailor learning experiences, it is crucial to prioritize the security of confidential student data. Efficient data privacy policies are crucial safeguards, ensuring adherence to legal norms, preventing data breaches, and building trust among stakeholders. This paper emphasized important aspects that enhance the efficiency of these policies, such as clarity, thorough coverage, training, and accountability methods. Moreover, it deals with difficulties like fast-paced technological progress and the importance of finding an equilibrium between innovation and privacy issues. In conclusion, this paper asserted that strong data privacy policies are essential for allowing the advantages of data mining while safeguarding student rights, thus encouraging ethical practices in educational evaluations. This paper suggested that institutions must limit sharing of sensitive educational data with third-party vendors or researchers unless a strict, enforceable agreement is in place. Additionally, they ought to implement data-sharing structures that reduce data visibility by only sharing aggregated or anonymized data for research and analysis purposes.

Keywords: Effectiveness, Data Privacy, Policy, Data Mining, Educational Assessment

Introduction

Recently, there has been a growing trend in utilizing data mining methods for educational evaluation, fueled by technological advancements and the accessibility of extensive datasets. Data mining in educational assessment involves extracting valuable information and insights from educational data through different analytical methods. The process includes using data mining tools and methods to enhance teaching and learning procedures, evaluate student progress, and improve educational results (Baker & Inventado, 2014). Educational institutions are now using data mining abilities in learning management systems, student information systems, and other educational technologies. These systems gather and assess data on student interactions, academic performance, and engagement levels (Siemens, 2013). Additional uses of data mining in educational evaluation involve customized learning (Van der Kleij et al., 2015), designing curriculum (Hannafin et al., 2014), and creating assessments (Hattie & Timperley, 2007). By making use of data mining, teachers can pinpoint students in danger of failing, customize teaching methods, and improve curriculum planning (Ferguson, 2012). These apps show potential for enhancing academic results and establishing adaptable learning settings. Yet, the increase in data usage brings up urgent issues about protecting data privacy, especially when it pertains to confidential student data.

Data privacy, or information privacy, pertains to how personal data is managed and shared in a way that respects individuals' rights and freedoms. It refers to the principles and strategies companies use to guarantee that personal information is gathered, utilized, and distributed in a responsible and ethical manner (West, 2019). In a world that is more and more reliant on digital technology, with a large quantity of personal data being created and saved on the internet, protecting data privacy is now a crucial issue for individuals, companies, and governments. Privacy of

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data in educational evaluation is a crucial matter involving safeguarding students' personal details, ethical data usage, and adherence to laws. The demand for strong data privacy measures has increased as educational assessments rely more on digital platforms. Data privacy involves managing, processing, and safeguarding personal information gathered during educational evaluations. This consists of all information that can distinguish a student, like names, addresses, and grades. Maintaining trust in educational institutions, staying compliant with laws, and keeping students safe all depend on the protection of student data (Reidenberg, 2017). Different laws like FERPA in the US and GDPR in Europe are in place to safeguard student data and enforce strict rules on how data is managed (McCarthy & Biehl, 2021).

Even with these regulations in place, numerous educational institutions find it difficult to establish successful data privacy policies. Research shows that frequently these policies are unclear and not comprehensive, which makes it hard for stakeholders to grasp their rights and duties when it comes to data usage (Gunter et al., 2020). Furthermore, with the ongoing evolution of technology, institutions face difficulties in maintaining current privacy policies, which may result in gaps in compliance and protection (Zuboff, 2019). The ever-changing nature of educational technology also brings up worries about how well these policies can address the risks linked to data breaches and privacy infringements. With these obstacles in mind, there is an urgent requirement to assess how well data privacy policies work when it comes to using data mining for educational evaluation. A policy framework should safeguard student data while also enabling institutions to utilize data mining for educational enhancement (Reddy et al., 2020).

The purpose of the introduction is to introduce the reader to the topic and discuss the background of the issue at hand. The introduction also includes a literature review, which typically follows the introduction of the topic as well as conceptual, theoretical and empirical frameworks. You may also review research that argues against your theory. The goal of the introduction is to lead the reader into your study so that he has a solid background of the material and an understanding of your rationale. All subsections of the literature should be subsumed and discussed as paragraphs within the introduction. All sources/materials cited must be acknowledged in the text and list of references. APA in-text citation – 7th edition. Author is at liberty to suggest appropriate subtitles for his/her paper. However, it should reflect concepts, theories, and empirical studies as well.

Conceptualization of the Problem

Incorporating data mining methods into educational evaluation presents great potential for improving student learning results, customizing education, and enhancing institutional effectiveness. Yet, this opportunity comes with significant dangers concerning the privacy of data. Educational institutions gather large quantities of sensitive student data using different digital platforms, leading to worries about safeguarding this information from unauthorized access, misuse, and breaches (Baker & Inventado, 2014). Although data privacy regulations like FERPA and GDPR have been put into place, educational institutions still face challenges in creating data privacy policies that safeguard student information and enable valuable data analysis. Current policies frequently lack clearness and thoroughness, potentially causing confusion among stakeholders about their rights and duties in data management (Gunter et al., 2020).

Additionally, the swift advancements in educational technologies can sometimes surpass the creation of suitable privacy policies, leading to potential legal and ethical issues for institutions (West, 2019). Not effectively balancing the advantages of data mining with strong data privacy protections can diminish student trust and engagement, which are crucial for the success of educational efforts. Furthermore, despite an increasing amount of literature discussing the significance of data privacy in educational settings, there is still a noticeable lack of empirical research examining the efficacy of these privacy policies, especially in regards to data mining activities. Questions about the ability of institutions to protect student data while using data mining tools for educational evaluation are mostly unresolved.

This paper writes on how efficient data privacy policies are in overseeing data mining practices in educational evaluations. Through analyzing existing policies, their execution, and the consequent effects on data protection and educational achievements, this study aims to provide valuable perspectives on how educational institutions can manage the intricate relationship between innovation and privacy.

The Necessity of Data Privacy Policies in Nigeria

Data privacy policies outline how student data is collected, stored, and used by educational institutions. These policies play a vital role for various reasons.

1. Educational institutions manage large quantities of personal information, such as academic records, demographic details, and behavioral data, with the aim of safeguarding sensitive information. Privacy

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measures that are effective can safeguard this information against unauthorized access and misuse (Reddy et al., 2020).

2. Numerous nations have implemented legislation to oversee data confidentiality, like the Family Educational Rights and Privacy Act (FERPA) in the US and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in Europe. Following these rules is essential for organizations to prevent legal consequences (McCarthy & Biehl, 2021).
3. Openness in the way data is managed helps build trust among educational organizations, students, and parents. Building trust is essential for motivating students to interact with data-driven educational technologies (Kizilcec et al., 2017).

Key Concepts in Data Privacy

1. **Personal Data:** Information that can identify a person, whether directly or indirectly, is referred to as personal data. This involves personal information such as names, addresses, social security numbers, as well as online identifiers such as IP addresses and cookies (European Union, 2016). Stringent privacy measures are required to avoid misuse of personal data due to its sensitivity.
2. **Data Protection:** Data protection is the implementation of technical and organizational measures to keep personal data safe from unauthorized access, loss, or corruption. This involves encryption, access restrictions, and frequent audits (McCarthy & Biehl, 2021). Maintaining data privacy requires effective data protection.
3. **Consent:** In numerous legal systems, acquiring permission from people prior to gathering or handling their personal information is a key principle of data protection. Consent should be knowledgeable, clear, and able to be withdrawn, giving people the power to manage their information (GDPR, 2016).
4. **Transparency:** Organizations are now being more and more required to be open and honest about their data procedures. This involves offering easily understood privacy policies that detail the collection, usage, and sharing of personal data (Gunter et al., 2020). Transparency builds trust and gives people the ability to make informed choices about their data.
5. **Rights of Individuals:** Different laws and regulations acknowledge individuals' rights to their personal data. These rights typically consist of the right to view information, correct errors, be forgotten, and transfer data (GDPR, 2016).

Effectiveness of Data Privacy Policies

Clarity and Accessibility: For a data privacy policy to work, it needs to be easily understood and available to everyone involved, such as students, parents, and educators. Policies need to be written in simple language and easily accessible on institutional websites. Based on Gunter et al. (2020), policies that are complex to comprehend or access are less likely to be followed, reducing their efficacy.

Comprehensive Coverage: Comprehensive data privacy policies should cover every stage of data management, such as data collection, processing, storing, and sharing. Policies must deal with the process of anonymizing data and the duration for which it is kept. Institutions that implement thorough policies are more equipped to safeguard student data and address privacy incidents (Hernández et al., 2021).

Training and Awareness: Educators and administrators are essential in maintaining data privacy policies. Consistent training and awareness initiatives are necessary to guarantee that every staff member comprehends their duties concerning data privacy. Studies show that organizations that prioritize training are more effective in upholding privacy regulations (Bennett & Raab, 2019).

Monitoring and Accountability: Frequent evaluations and reviews of data privacy procedures are essential to ensure adherence to regulations and pinpoint areas needing enhancement. Institutions need to set up ways to hold accountable those who manage student information. Having a privacy officer in place can improve monitoring and handling of possible data breaches (Privacy Rights Clearinghouse, 2022).

The Impacts of Existing Data Privacy Policies on Data Security and Educational Results

Privacy policies for data are essential in controlling the collection, processing, and safeguarding of personal information, particularly in educational settings. This analysis explores the existing data privacy regulations in Nigeria and globally, how they are being enforced, and how they affect data security and academic achievements.

Data Privacy Policies in Nigeria

1. **Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR):** The Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR), enacted in 2019, provides rules for gathering, handling, and retaining information in Nigeria, with an emphasis on safeguarding personal data (National Information Technology Development Agency [NITDA], 2019).

Qualitative Study on...(Oribhabor & Isaac, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603591>

Organizations, such as educational institutions, must designate Data Protection Officers, carry out Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs), and guarantee data security measures (Iroko, 2020). The NDPR mandates that individuals must give clear permission before their data is processed, stressing the importance of being transparent about why data is being collected and how it will be used (Ogbobor & Ogbobor, 2020). As a result, the NDPR has raised awareness of data privacy rights among students and parents, prompting educational institutions to improve their data management procedures. Nevertheless, difficulties persist in ensuring adherence and following rules, especially within smaller organizations (Ogbebor, 2020). The NDPR promotes trust among stakeholders by protecting personal data, which could result in increased student engagement and participation in educational programs. Nevertheless, its influence on academic results is currently under assessment.

2. Child's Rights Act (2003): This legislation highlights the importance of safeguarding children's rights, such as their right to privacy, and mandates parental approval for collecting data on minors (Ogbebor, 2020). Educational institutions are required to get permission from parents or guardians prior to gathering personal information from students. This policy safeguards minors' personal data in accordance with international guidelines on children's privacy (Zong et al., 2018). Educational institutions can improve student performance by creating a supportive environment through involving parents in data-related decisions.

Data Privacy Policies Outside Nigeria

1. General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) - European Union: The GDPR, which has been in place since May 2018, regulates the handling of personal information, with a focus on consent, transparency, and individuals' rights (European Commission, 2018). Educational institutions need to assign Data Protection Officers, carry out DPIAs, and guarantee that data processing is both legal and transparent (Zittrain, 2019). The GDPR has greatly improved data protection in the EU, resulting in greater adherence and responsibility among educational establishments (Draude & Reidenberg, 2019). The GDPR promotes a secure learning environment by safeguarding student data, which in turn encourages student involvement and interaction. Educational results could see enhancements by adjusting learning experiences to fit secure data analysis from institutions.
2. Family Educational Rights and Privacy Act (FERPA) - United State: FERPA safeguards the confidentiality of student academic records and grants parents and eligible students certain privileges in relation to their academic records (U.S. Department of Education, 2020). Procedures must be in place in schools to ensure adherence, such as acquiring permission before sharing academic documents and allowing students to view their records. FERPA has resulted in increased responsibility for educational institutions in handling student records, building confidence among those involved (Hand, 2018). FERPA promotes better academic performance by encouraging families to be involved in educational processes while also safeguarding student privacy.
3. California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA): The CCPA, enacted in 2018, grants California residents privileges regarding their personal information, such as the right to understand the data being gathered and the option to decline its sale (California Department of Justice, 2020). Educational institutions must adhere to CCPA regulations when gathering personal information, guaranteeing transparency in data procedures. The CCPA has increased understanding of data privacy and enabled consumers, such as students and parents, to manage their data (Stuart, 2019). Through increased transparency and accountability, the CCPA can improve trust in academic institutions, resulting in increased student engagement and improved learning results.

Comparative Insights

Data Protection Strength: The GDPR has a powerful impact on educational institutions in Europe, serving as one of the most robust frameworks for data protection. On the other hand, the NDPR in Nigeria is a major advancement but is encountering obstacles in implementing and abiding by the regulations.

Parental Involvement: Rules such as FERPA and the Child's Rights Act stress the importance of parental engagement, resulting in increased supportive educational settings.

Impact on Educational Outcomes: Successful execution of data privacy policies builds trust and increases participation, leading to positive impacts on educational results. Nevertheless, the educational performance impact of these policies is still under investigation.

Qualitative Study on...(Oribhabor & Isaac, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603591>
Difficulties in Enforcing Efficient Data Protection Policies in Nigeria

In the digital era, it is becoming more and more essential to establish efficient data privacy policies in educational assessment. Educational institutions gather large quantities of sensitive data, such as test scores and behavior details, creating notable worries about the security measures in place to protect this information. Nevertheless, numerous obstacles impede the establishment and implementation of extensive data privacy protocols in this sector. Some of the obstacles are disparities in laws and regulations, weaknesses in technology, moral dilemmas, and resistance from institutions.

Inconsistencies in laws and regulations: One main obstacle is maneuvering through the intricate maze of legal regulations overseeing data privacy. Various areas have various regulations, and organizations frequently function in various jurisdictions, complicating adherence. As an illustration, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in Europe requires strict consent and transparency guidelines for data collection and storage, which may not always be consistent with regulations in other areas like the Family Educational Rights and Privacy Act (FERPA) in the United States. FERPA primarily targets academic records but has limitations when it comes to the current digital landscape of evaluations. Moreover, developing nations frequently do not have strong data protection regulations in place. The lack of consistency in regulations can cause confusion for institutions, making it difficult to establish privacy policies that are both legally compliant and feasible in practice. In numerous areas, regulations are antiquated and struggle to catch up with developments in educational technology and assessment methods.

Risks of Security and Vulnerabilities in Technology: Educational establishments often face challenges when it comes to the technological aspects of protecting confidential information. Institutions are at risk of various cyber threats due to the rise of online assessments and the growing reliance on digital platforms. These encompass hacking, data breaches, and unauthorized entry into student information. In 2020, over 400,000 user's sensitive data was exposed in a ProctorU data breach, demonstrating the susceptibility of educational platforms to cyberattacks. Numerous establishments, especially those that are smaller or have limited funding, do not have the means to purchase advanced cybersecurity systems. This makes them appealing targets for hackers. Despite having enough money, institutions may still not possess the necessary internal knowledge to handle intricate data protection systems. Additionally, the dependence on external platforms for internet-based testing increases the level of risk because these vendors may not follow strict data privacy regulations.

Ethical issues related to the utilization of data: Another significant hurdle is presented by the ethical concerns regarding the gathering and utilization of data in educational evaluations. Digital assessments frequently gather more than simply test scores. Information such as biometric data (like typing styles, facial recognition during online tests), behavior data, and study habits can be collected to improve customization or deter cheating. Yet, these issues arise regarding the extent of data collection, the duration of storage, and the individuals with access to it. In terms of ethics, students may not have a complete understanding of how extensively their data is being utilized. Collecting data without proper anonymization raises the chances of misuse, profiling, or discrimination. For example, data might be utilized for marketing or research purposes without obtaining appropriate approval from the students participating. The absence of transparency causes distrust and raises ethical concerns about governance of student data.

Challenges within institutions and hesitancy: Institutions frequently encounter internal resistance towards implementing privacy policies, despite their development. Educational institutions might not have the sufficient infrastructure, resources, and knowledge to implement thorough data privacy policies successfully. As indicated by a study from Educause in 2021, numerous colleges and universities have put data privacy policies in place, yet ensuring uniform compliance across various departments is still difficult. This inconsistency frequently stems from a shortage of skilled staff, conflicting tasks, and financial limitations. In addition, certain organizations may view privacy policies as a task that adds to their administrative workload. Enforcing privacy policies involves ongoing staff training, system updates, and regular monitoring of compliance, which necessitate both time and financial investment. Institutions with constrained budgets, particularly those in developing nations, might give more importance to different areas than data privacy, resulting in policies that are not implemented or are obsolete.

Qualitative Study on...(Oribhabor & Isaac, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603591>

Finding a balance between fostering innovation and protecting privacy: The drive for technological advancement in educational assessment conflicts with the necessity for strong data privacy safeguards. A lot of organizations are adopting innovative technologies like artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, and adaptive testing systems, which heavily depend on gathering and analyzing large amounts of data to offer customized evaluations. Nevertheless, these technologies also elevate the chance of privacy infringements (Zuboff, 2019). For example, AI proctoring tools that watch over students' actions during online tests could gather sensitive biometric information. Although these tools are beneficial in stopping academic cheating, they also give rise to worries about surveillance, misuse of data, and potential biases in data interpretation. Finding a balance between the advantages of these advancements and the importance of safeguarding privacy poses a major hurdle, as organizations are required to guarantee that the personal information of students remains secure while embracing technological progress.

Conclusion

Data privacy regulations, in Nigeria and globally, play a vital role in shaping the landscape of educational assessments. The effectiveness of data protection advancements relies on the enforcement and adherence to these measures. Ultimately, improved data security can lead to enhanced educational outcomes as stakeholders gain trust and engagement in the learning process.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion, the paper suggests that:

1. Institutions should utilize privacy-enhancing technologies like data anonymization, pseudonymization, and differential privacy. These technologies enable effective data analysis while safeguarding the privacy of students. Differential privacy allows organizations to analyze data without revealing any specific student's information, which helps them follow privacy regulations.
2. It is suggested that educational data mining institutions regularly audit their processes for collecting, storing, and analyzing data. These audits will verify that privacy policies are being adhered to and that data mining processes meet legal and ethical criteria. Audits need to evaluate possible weaknesses, like sensitive data access, data breach dangers, and third-party data sharing, that may put student privacy at risk.
3. Educational institutions need to make awareness and training programs on data privacy rights and obligations a top priority for staff, students, and parents.
4. Institutions need to establish precise data governance frameworks outlining data access, purposes, and retention periods. Stakeholders should have access to this governance framework in order to comprehend the usage of their data for educational assessment.
5. Institutions must limit sharing of sensitive educational data with third-party vendors or researchers unless a strict, enforceable agreement is in place. Additionally, they ought to implement data-sharing structures that reduce data visibility by only sharing aggregated or anonymized data for research and analysis purposes.

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Comparative Analysis between Somatotype and Fitness Status of Middle-Aged Female Adults in Kano State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study compared somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged female adults in Kano state, Nigeria. The research design for the study was the modified pretest, mid and post-test quasi experimental design using a cluster of female adults within a population of residents in the Noman's land area of Kano state. Samples were made up middle-aged female adults (N=44) who volunteered to take part in the eight (8)-week aerobic exercise training program. Instrument used for data collection included direct measurement of height and weight using the bathroom height and weight scale (Portspring model 005; made in England); and calibrated equipment for body composition variables (%BF, Waist and Hip circumferences and somatotype) at 0, 4, and 8 weeks of aerobic training following standard procedures. Simple percentages were used to describe changes during exercise training, while the One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test hypotheses which are deemed significant at 0.05 alpha level. Based on the findings, it was revealed that an 8-week aerobic exercise programme caused significant changes in body composition (weight, %BF, waist circumference), and slight but a non-significant change in somatotype of subjects. It was concluded that well-organized exercise training can modify body composition and somatotype status in females and yield positive dividends to health and well-being. Therefore, it is recommended that participants and other fitness enthusiasts should continue exercising regularly; and start if they have not done so, while they watch their food intake in order to maintain the desired somatotype level appropriate for optimum health benefits.

Keywords: Aerobic exercise, Body fat percent, Ponderal index, Somatotype

Introduction

Body typing is a commonly applied feature to describe people in different vocations and professions. It tells us that bodies come in different shapes and sizes, influenced by a person's frame and composition; and can be summarized as size and geometry of individuals (Tungdim, 2024). This physical size and shape of a person's body, is a genetic or biological material usually passed down or inherited from the progenitor; even though environment, lifestyle and level of fitness can affect and modify this inherited trait of such persons. Human body shape is a complex phenomenon with sophisticated details and functions. The general shape or figure of a person is defined mainly by the molding of skeletal structures, as well as the distribution of muscles and fat (Wikipedia, 2023). In the study of human performance, body typing is commonly referred to as somatotype. A somatotype is a quantitative overall appraisal of the present shape and composition of the human body (Richardson, 2022). In psychology, there is this discredited idea that human body shape and physique type are associated with personality traits, forming the basis of constitutional psychology; whereas this phenomenon comes in handy in law and criminal investigation in which crimes are not only traced but attributed to certain body shapes and sizes (Nickerson, 2023). Theoretically, the somatotype refers to a

Qualitative Study on ... (Oribhabor & Isaac, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603591>

generalized set of body types, the skeletal frame and body composition that an individual is genetically endowed with (Langford & Norwood, 2023). Thus, all humans have specific body characteristics that can be traced to related lineage.

The somatotype theory also states that there is an association between an individual's body type and certain personality or behavioral traits. Biological criminology theories state that some individuals are predisposed to committing crimes due to their biological nature, such as genetics, brain neurology and physical appearance (Nickerson, 2023). This theory was deduced from a study of delinquent juvenile male college students following a decade-long study. Participants were ranked based on their body type and it was discovered that many juvenile males had a mesomorphic body type, whereas most college males had an ectomorphic body type; thereby attributing mesomorphs to criminal tendencies. Today, the three body types of endomorph, mesomorph and ectomorph were a theoretical extension of embryonic development from which an individual's body type is dependent on how many embryonic layers one has viz: the inner layer (endoderm), middle layer (mesoderm) and the outer layer (ectoderm) (Tungdim, 2024). All these layers describe the functional elements that form the body structure and consequently, the physique.

To classify a body type in any of the described component reflects the extent of attainment on the anthropometric scale based on the measured variables. These variables according to Amusa & Igbanugo (2013), include skinfold, body circumferences and diameters, height and body weight. The considerable interest today in using body composition analysis in sports and physical fitness programmes is related to setting a minimum for health and sports in order to ensure optimum health and fitness. The size and geometry of a person's body, Owolabi (2015) opined, may impose constraints upon his capacity for motor performance. He went further to say there are desirable body composition for motor performance and variation from sport to sport. This opinion is supported by somatotype studies which observed that people with relatively similar body types tend to consistently participate in selected sports (Novoa-Vignau, et al.; (2017). Thus, it can be implied that one may be capable of predicting performance success in ball games from physique and body composition factors.

The quality of the sports-specific performance attributes tends to vary according to the skill or the body composition status and the level of attainment of the performer being higher in the champion athlete and lower in the poor ones; and may be expected to vary among group ability levels (Owolabi, 2015). In other words, it is expected that significant differences will be found when fitness enthusiasts and national athletes are compared with their Olympic counter parts in terms of their somatotype and fitness characteristics due to their levels of training.

Of the several methods which appeal to exercise scientists in determining somatotype status of humans, the anthropometric technique which can be used in field assessment comes in handy; hence, it is easily applied while carrying out fitness assessment. Different body type, be it ectomorphic, mesomorphic and endomorphic, can influence an individual's response to aerobic fitness training (American Alliance of Health, Physical Education, Recreation and Dance [AAHPERD] 2015). For instance, the ectomorphs with a characteristic lean and thin physique presents the advantages of low body mass which may enhance running economy and endurance and has less body fat to lose, potentially making weight management easier. The mesomorphs, on the other hand, have muscular and athletic build which can enhance performance and their efficient muscle-to-fat ratio aids endurance in all kinds of athletic performance; while the endomorphs are curvy and soft and have generally stronger upper body, which when guided, can lose weight and improve on their cardiovascular health with training (Kim & Kim 2017).

The descriptions of positive sides of the three body types are not without their disadvantages as lower muscle mass may limit power output with the accompanying difficulty building muscle endurance in ectomorphs; higher muscle mass may increase risk of overtraining causing the mesomorphs to struggle with achieving flexibility; and endomorphs on the other hand, has higher body fat percentage that reduces endurance and increases their risk for cardiovascular disease (Meschino, 2020). Despite these negative aspects, all fitness components depend on body composition to the extent that an increase in lean body mass contributes to strength and power development while strength and power are related to muscle size. Thus, an increase in lean body mass enables the athlete to generate more force in a specific period of time (Westcott & Laing, 2006).

Recognizing that somatotype is just one factor influencing aerobic fitness, aside genetics, age, nutrition, lifestyle and overall physical performance; it has been proved that exercise training can cause positive response to excessive body fat accumulation (Baranauskas, 2024). Besides the great benefits, its evaluation offers a guideline for fitness and selection of exercise for sporting activities; and in adults, encourages the development of fitness

Qualitative Study on ... (Oribhabor & Isaac, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603591>
capabilities; and *positive health maintenance*. It is in line with the above, this study carried out a comparative analysis of somatotype and fitness status among middle-aged female adults in Kano state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

1. To compare changes in body weight of middle-aged female adults in Kano state following aerobic exercise training program in Kano state.
2. To analyse effects of modification in the body fat percent (%BF) on somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged female adults in Kano state
3. To analyse effects of modification in waist and hip circumferences on somatotype and fitness status of female adults in Kano state
4. To compare changes in the somatotype components of the middle-aged female adults following fitness training in Kano state.

Research Questions

1. Are there changes in body weight of middle-aged female adults following aerobic exercise training program in Kano state?
2. Are there effects of modifications in body fat percent (%BF) on somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged female adults in Kano state?
3. Are there effects of modifications in Waist and hip circumferences on somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged female adults in Kano state?
4. Are there changes in somatotype components of middle-aged female adults following fitness training program in Kano state?

Hypotheses

1. **H₀₁:** Aerobic exercise training program will not cause significant changes on body weight of middle-aged female adults in Kano state
2. **H₀₂:** There are no significant effects of %BF modifications on somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged female in Kano State
3. **H₀₃:** There are no significant effects of modifications in waist and hip circumferences on somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged female adults in Kano state
4. **H₀₄:** There are no significant changes in the somatotype components of middle-aged female adults following training program in Kano state.

Methodology

To achieve the purpose of this study, the modified pre-test, mid and post-test quasi experimental design (Venkateswarlu, 2015) was employed with no manipulation of variable. This design was deemed appropriate because variable measurement at the commencement, during and at cessation of training could provide the results needed for the target population. The population comprised all middle-aged females (N=180) in Kano state who were neither sedentary nor very active except for their activities of daily living (ADL). Out of this population, a sample of forty-four (44) middle-aged female volunteers took part in the aerobic training programme based on factors of location, occupation and accessibility to the training center. Volunteers were administered with consent form which described the procedure of test administration. The fitness center used for aerobic training operated a flexible four (4) hour-daily programme from 4pm to 8pm on any three (3) alternate days from Monday to Friday following guidelines of the American College of Sports Medicine [ACSM], 2014). Trained research assistants were always available to administer a 30-45-minute aerobic exercise training to subjects in groups.

The instrument comprised calibrated equipment required for direct measurement on selected variables of interest (height, body weight, waist and hip circumferences, muscle girths, epicondylar diameters and skinfold thickness) (Adeyanju & Dikko, 2015) at 0wk, 4weeks and 8weeks of aerobic training, following standard procedures; using the following instruments:

1. The portable bathroom salter scale to measure height, body weight; non-elastic tape rule for measurement of waist and hip circumferences of subjects; and the Vernier caliper (ICI Inc, USA) was used to measure muscle

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girths, epicondylar diameters and skinfold thicknesses in selected sites to estimate %BF and somatotype of subjects. All data were collected at 0wk, 4weeks and 8weeks of aerobic training and recorded; however, subjects' height measurement was not repeated because it is believed no changes could occur (Olaniyi, 2009; Venkateswarlu, 2015).

2. While using the anthropometric formulae described by Heyward & Wagner, (2014) and Novoa-Vignau et al.; (2017), selected sites were measured and values obtained were fed into constants for endomorph; $-0.7182+0.1451(x)-0.00068(x^2)+0.0000014(x^3)$ in which x is the sum of the triceps, subscapular, and supraspinale folds, multiplied by (70.18/height(cm)); mesomorph = $(0.858 \times H) + (0.601 \times F) + (0.188 \times B - 0.161 \times P) - (0.131 \times E) + 4.5$ and the Parnell's 1990 method of ectomorph assessment derived from lean body weight formular $(LBW = (\sum 8D)^2 / 101 \times ht (m))$. All the data obtained were summarized and analyzed with descriptive statistics [Frequencies and percentages (%)] and inferential statistics [One way analysis of variance (ANOVA)] to determine if the aerobic exercise training programme significant roles in modifying the somatotype and fitness status of subjects in the study. All hypotheses were deemed significant at 0.05 alpha level.

Presentation of Results

Data collected for this study are presented in line with the research questions and adequately described while the inferential statistics of one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses raised for the study. All hypotheses are deemed significant at 0.05 alpha level as shown below:

Research Question 1

Are there changes in height and body weight of middle-aged female adults following aerobic exercise training program in Kano state?

Table 1: Physical characteristics of height and weight of subjects in the training programme

Variable	Before (0wk0)	During (4wks)	After (8wks)	Diff. at 4wks
a. Height (m)	1.68m	1.68m	1.68m	1.68m
b. Weight (kg)	74.5kg	74.2kg	72.7kg	0.3kg

Source: Field Assessment (2024)

Data on height (Table 1a) showed 1.68m as average height of subjects which remained unchanged, as expected, throughout the duration of the exercise. However, data collected on subjects' weight (Table 1b) (at 0 week = 74.5kg; 4 weeks = 74.2kg (diff. 0.3kg); and at the completion of training (at 8 weeks = 72.7kg) showed a cumulative 1.8kg (4.09%) difference which can be attributed to the aerobic training programme. This shows that adult height is not expected to be modified during an exercise training programme, whereas this cannot be said of weight which can be affected by exertion over a period of time. In order to find out if these results are significant, the inferential statistics of One-way Analysis of Variance was employed for analysis, the results of which are presented in Table 2.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₁: Aerobic exercise training will not cause significant changes on body weight of middle-aged female adults in Kano state

Table 2: Results of inferential statistics of One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on weight changes

Variable	Diff. after 4wks	Total changes	Fcal.	Fcrit	Remarks
Weight	0.3kg	1.8kg (4.09%)	F=1.018 F=3.312*	3.21	NS Sig

Source: SPSS V10 data analysis (2024) $F_{(2,44)}=3.21 < 0.05$ *Significant

On Table 2 is the result of inferential statistics of One-way ANOVA employed to analyse data on weight values following exercise training. The result was not significant after 4 weeks ($F_{(2,44)}=1.018 < 0.05$); whereas significant

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difference was recorded after 8 weeks of aerobic training ($F_{(2,44)}=3.312 > 0.05$). Thus, the hypothesis of no significant difference was accepted after 4weeks of training but rejected at the end of the training program. It can, therefore, be inferred that the longer the exercise training program takes, the more the gains that can be recorded in respect of weight loss.

Research Question 2

Are there effects of modifications in body fat percent (%BF) on somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged female adults in Kano state?

Table 3: Percent body fat (%BF) estimates of subjects in the study

Variable	Before (0wks)	During (4wks)	After (8wks)	Diff. at 4wks
% BF	25.5%	24.8%	22.4%	0.7%

Source: Field Assessment (2024)

A glance at table 2 revealed records of body fat percent (%BF) which was estimated from the subject's height and weight values ($\frac{wt}{ht}^2$) [Quetelet Index (QI)] from which the body mass index (BMI) was derived, and the corresponding %BF values read off a nomogram (Heyward, 2017). The estimated %BF values recorded at 0, 4 and 8 weeks were 25.5%; 24.8% and 22.4% respectively representing 0.7% and 3.1% reduction after 4 and 8weeks of training respectively following aerobic exercise training. This result followed the trend reported in body weight in which bodily exertion has caused reductions in %BF from 25.5% to 22.4% following exercise training. This is an indication that the training programme probably resulted in the reduction in %BF. In order to find out if these results are significant, the inferential statistics of One-way Analysis of Variance was employed for analysis, the results are presented in Table 4.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₂: There are no significant effects of %BF modifications on somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged female in Kano State

Table 4: Results of inferential statistics of One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on modifications in %BF

Variable	Diff. after 4wks	Total changes	Fcal.	Fcrit	Remarks
%BF	0.7%	3.1%	F=0.164	3.21	NS
			F=4.041*		Sig

Source: SPSS V10 data analysis (2024) $F_{(2,44)}=3.21 < 0.05$ *Significant

As presented in Table 4, %BF values analysed with One-way ANOVA, revealed no significant reduction ($F_{(2,44)}=0.164 < 0.05$) after 4weeks whereas significant reduction was recoded after 8weeks of training ($F_{(2,44)}= 4.041 > 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant reduction was accepted for changes that took place after 4weeks and rejected after 8weeks of training. Thus, longer periods of aerobic training are required to produce greater gains in %BF reduction for health and wellbeing.

Research Question 3:

Are there effects of modifications in Waist and hip circumferences on somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged female adults in Kano state?

Table 5: Waist and hip circumference values of subjects in the study

Variable	Before (0wk)	During (4wks)	After (8wks)	Diff. at 4wks
d Waist cm	100cm	94cm	88cm	6.0cm (13.64%)
e. Hip cm	94cm	93.8cm	93.6cm	0.2cm

Source: Field Assessment (2024)

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A cursory look at waist and hip circumferences values presented in table 3 showed that waist circumferences were 100cm at the commencement of training; and by the 4th and 8th weeks, the values changed to 94cm and 88cm; presenting a difference of 6.0cm (13.64%) and 12.0cm ((27.27%) respectively while hip circumferences were 94cm, 93.8cm and 93.6cm from the start to the end of the aerobic exercise training programme with minimal 0.2cm and 0.4cm changes at 4th and 8th weeks respectively. The result showed very minimal reduction after 8 weeks of exercise training. In order to find out if these results are significant, the inferential statistics of One-way Analysis of Variance was employed for analysis and the results are presented in Table 6.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₃: There are no significant effects of modifications in waist and hip circumferences on somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged female adults in Kano state

Table 6: Results of inferential statistics of One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on waist and hip circumference

Variable	Diff. after 4wks	Total changes	Fcal.	Fcrit	Remarks
Waist cm	6.0cm (13.64%)	12.0cm (27.27%)	F=3.303* F=4.221*	3.21	NS Sig
Hip cm	0.2cm	0.4cm	F=1.245	3.21	NS

Source: SPSS V10 data analysis (2024) $F_{(2,44)}=3.21 < 0.05$ *Significant

Examination of Table 6 revealed waist and hip circumferences of subjects in the exercise training programme. When these values were analysed with inferential statistics of One-way ANOVA, waist circumference was significant at 4weeks ($F_{(2,44)} = 3.303 > 0.05$) and 8weeks ($F_{(2,44)} = 4.221 > 0.05$) of aerobic exercise training whereas hip circumference was not. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant reduction was rejected for waist circumferences but accepted for hip circumferences. Thus, longer period of aerobic training is expected to produce greater reductions in waist and hip circumference for health and fitness promotion.

Research Question 4

Are there changes in somatotype components of middle-aged female adults following fitness training program in Kano state?

Table 7: Data of somatotype components obtained during exercise training

Variable	Before (0wk)	During (4wks)	After (8wks)	Diff. at 4wks
Somatotype (est)	4, 4, 3 ie: 11/3=3.66	4, 4, 3 ie: 9/3=3.00	3, 3, 3: ie 9/3=3.00	No change recorded

Source: Field Assessment (2024)

Somatotype values presented in table 7 revealed values of the three components (hip, trunk and waist) as 4, 4, 3 (endomorph); 4, 4, 3 (mesomorph) and 3, 3, 3 (ectomorph). No changes were noticed after 4weeks of aerobic training while very minimal change was recorded at the ectomorphic level. This result revealed that exercise duration may be implicated for the minimal change recorded. In order to find out if these results are significant, the inferential statistics of One-way Analysis of Variance was used for analysis, the results are presented in Table 8.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₄: There are no significant changes in the somatotype components of middle-aged female adults following training program in Kano state

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Table 8: Results of inferential statistics of One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on changes in somatotype components

Variable	Diff. after 4wks	Total changes	Fcal.	Fcrit	Remarks
Somatotype (est)	No change recorded	Very minimal	F=0.422	3.21	NS

Source: SPSS V10 data analysis (2024) $F_{(2,44)}=3.21 < 0.05$ Not Significant

A critical look at Table 8 shows the summary of somatotype response of subjects to aerobic training. The minimal changes recorded in the three aspects was not significant ($F_{(2,44)}=0.422 < 0.05$) after analysis with One way ANOVA. Each component was derived from the anthropometric formulae described by Novoa-Vignau, et al.; (2017). Therefore, this minimally insignificant value in the third component, though not significant, signifies that exercise training of long duration is more desirable for the reduction in the three components for improved health and wellness of exercise adherents.

Discussion of findings

Aerobic exercise, also known as cardio exercise, can give long-term effects to the body, especially the cardiorespiratory system consisting the heart, blood vessels and lungs. The effects can be an effective way to increase the endurance of the system when adherents maintain the exercise for a period ranging from 20 to 30 minutes, three to four times a week. The positive impact of aerobic exercise on the cardiorespiratory system includes improvements in stroke volume at rest, lower resting heart rate, lower blood pressure and consequently general well-being (Meschino, 2020). It is based on this assertion that this study compared the somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged females in their responses to 8weeks of aerobic training in Kano state.

Results on table 1a and b showed summary of physical characteristics of height and weight of subjects; in which height values, as expected, remained constant; and with 3.1% reductions in weight at the end of training. Results of data analysed with inferential statistics of One-way ANOVA to ascertain whether the 8 weeks of aerobic exercise programme has clearly and proven significant effect on variables like weight, %BF, waist circumferences of participants. Although height was not expected to change among adults after they had attained maturity, it is important in the estimation of body fat, because accumulation of excess body fat has been implicated in different ailments and degenerative diseases of among humans (World Health Organization [WHO], 2020). Considering the technicalities involved in its estimate, the field technique which used the height/weight ratio called the Quetelet Index $(\frac{wt}{ht})^2$ was applied with the Ponderal Index to obtain the body mass index (BMI) and consequently estimate the body fat percent (%BF) while, somatotype was obtained from the anthropometric technique applied by Novoa-Vignau et al.; (2017). After analysis, results showed that body weight ($F=3.312^*$), %BF ($F=4.041^*$) and waist circumference ($F=4.221^*$) responded significantly to 8weeks of aerobic exercise training; but the hip circumference ($F=1.245$) and somatotype ($F=0.422$) values did not, hence, were not significant. This result supports earlier works (Adeyanju & Dikko, 2015, Olaniyi, 2009) which revealed significant effect of aerobic exercise on body composition of men and women. From the results, it can be concluded that an 8-week aerobic exercise program may not lead to significant somatotype changes was also supported by Santos and Maia (2013) outcome in which they reported that the specific outcomes will depend on individual factors. This individual factor may be responsible for the significant changes in %BF (ACSM, 2018; Lee & Lee, 2015). It is recommended that participants and other exercise adherents should continue exercising, obtain appropriate nutritional guidance, and personalizing fitness plans to help them achieve and maintain their desired somatotype status while improving their overall health.

Conclusions

This study was carried out to compare the somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged adult females following an 8-week aerobic exercise programme in Kano state. The results showed significant reductions in subjects' body weight, %BF, waist circumference and slight reduction in somatotype that was not significant. The findings of this study also suggest that regular aerobic exercise can have positive impact on somatotype and fitness status in

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female adults. These results are consistent with previous research which support efficacy of aerobic exercise in this regard. Finally, though not significant, the slight modification of the mesomorph and ectomorph toward the end of eight weeks suggests the need for prolonged training period for maximum gains.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations have been put forward:

1. Women should be consistent in engaging in aerobic exercise like brisk walking, cycling and dancing in order to maintain healthy bodily characteristics, including somatotype characteristics for maximum health benefits.
2. There is need to provide exercise adherents with nutritional guidance to support their fitness goals and develop a balanced lifestyle where physical exercise plays a role.
3. Considering that responses to exercise can vary among persons, it is recommended that personalized exercise plans that better suit each participant's somatotype needs and fitness goals be encouraged.
4. Regular Assessments: Conduct periodic assessments to track physical and physiological characteristics, including somatotype status and adjust exercise and dietary recommendations accordingly. This will help participants stay on track and make necessary adjustments to achieve their desired outcomes.
5. Health Monitoring: Monitor participants' health parameters, such as blood pressure, cholesterol levels, and glucose levels, to ensure that the exercise program is contributing to overall health improvements.

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Numerical Solution of Tenth-Order Boundary Value Problems Using the Variational Iteration Method with Bernstein Polynomials as Trial Functions

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Abstract

In this research, a modified variational iteration method incorporating Bernstein polynomials has been employed to obtain the numerical solution for tenth-order boundary value problems. The modification involves constructing Bernstein polynomials tailored to the boundary conditions and utilizing them as the basis functions for approximation. Several numerical examples are presented to demonstrate the method's effectiveness and reliability. The proposed approach exhibits superior performance compared to existing methods in the literature, as evidenced by the results presented in the comparative tables.

Keywords: Approximate solutions, Boundary value problems, Bernstein polynomials, Modified variational iteration method.

Introduction

Boundary Value Problems (BVPs) are integral to various fields such as shock-wave physics, hydrodynamics, electrostatics, heat transfer, thermodynamics, and multiple branches of engineering. In recent years, considerable research has focused on BVPs, and the application of numerical techniques to derive accurate approximate solutions has proven to be highly advantageous. Numerous scholars have explored BVPs, employing diverse numerical approaches to address these complex issues. Prominent methods highlighted in the literature include the Galerkin Method of Weighted Residuals (GMWR) proposed by (Farzana & Alim, 2020), the Hybrid Improved Block Pulse and Bernstein Function Method introduced by (Mohamed et al., 2022), the Adomian Decomposition Method developed by (Qasim & Al-Rawi, 2018), the Laplace Adomian Decomposition Method formulated by (Dimple and Vinod, 2017), the Homotopy Perturbation Method investigated by (Syed & Ahmet, 2010) as well as Jafar and Shirin (2010), and the Haar Wavelets Method presented by (Fazal et al., 2012), among others.

Additionally, several studies have explored novel techniques involving Chebyshev polynomials and Bernstein functions. For instance, Tsetimi et al. (2022) applied a modified variational iteration method using Chebyshev polynomials to solve 12th-order boundary value problems, while Mohamed et al. (2022) combined the Bernstein function with an enhanced block pulse to address integral equations. Rida et al. (2021) utilized Bernstein functions to solve third-order initial value problems. Similarly, Ezekiel and Ojo (2020) developed a one-step hybrid

system using off-grid points and Bernstein polynomials for the direct solution of second-order ordinary differential equations (ODEs). In the realm of physical problems like the Helmholtz equation and second-order BVPs, Farzana & Alim (2020) refined the Galerkin Method of Weighted Residuals (MWR) to estimate natural frequencies. Avipsita et al. (2018) presented a straightforward numerical technique based on Bernstein polynomials for solving both linear and nonlinear BVPs. Moreover, Qasim & Al-Rawi (2018) extended the Adomian decomposition method by incorporating Bernstein polynomials to address linear and nonlinear equations.

Further contributions include the work of Bataineh et al. (2017), who proposed two novel numerical methods for solving BVPs using systems of ODEs and Bernstein polynomials, and Dimple & Vinod (2017), who introduced the Laplace Adomian decomposition method combined with Bernstein polynomials to solve BVPs. Hradyyesh (2014) employed the He-Laplace method to address linear and nonlinear two-point BVPs, while Yiming et al. (2014) utilized operational matrices of Bernstein polynomials to solve third-order ODEs. Additionally, Yousefi & Behroozifar (2010) developed operational matrices for integration, differentiation, and product using Bernstein polynomials. Earlier work by Idrees & Bracken (2007) presented a modified new Bernstein polynomial approach for approximating solutions to differential equations.

The research conducted by these scholars has inspired the development of our proposed approach, which combines the variational iteration method with Bernstein polynomials to tackle tenth-order ODEs. By modifying Bernstein polynomials to accommodate the given boundary value problems and utilizing them as basis functions for approximation, this study introduces an effective numerical method for addressing high-order differential equations. This paper investigates the following types of boundary value problems:

$$\alpha_m \frac{d^m}{dz^m} w + \alpha_{m-1} \frac{d^{m-1}}{dz^{m-1}} w + \alpha_{m-2} \frac{d^{m-2}}{dz^{m-2}} w \dots \alpha_1 \frac{d}{dz} w + \alpha_0 w = f(z), \quad \alpha < z < \beta, \quad (1)$$

with boundary conditions

$$w(\alpha) = A_1, \quad w'(\alpha) = A_2, \quad w''(\alpha) = A_3 \dots w^m(\alpha) = A_j, \quad w(\beta) = B_1, \quad w'(\beta) = B_2, \quad (2)$$

$$w''(\beta) = B_3 \dots w^m(\beta) = B_j.$$

where $\alpha_m, \alpha_{m-1}, \dots, \alpha_0$ are constants, $f(z)$ continuous on $[\alpha, \beta]$ and $A_j, j = 1, 2, 3 \dots m$ and $B_j, j = 1, 2, 3 \dots m$.

The Standard Variational Iteration Technique

Consider the following general differential equation to demonstrate the basic concept of the technique.

$$Lw + Mw - g(z) = 0, \quad (3)$$

where L denotes a linear operator, M denotes a nonlinear operator, and $g(z)$ denotes an inhomogeneous term. We can construct a correction functional using the variational iteration method as follows:

$$w_{j+1} = w_j(z) + \int_0^z \lambda(t) (Lw_j(t) + Mw_j(t) - g(t)) dt \quad (4)$$

where $\lambda(t)$ stands for a Lagrange multiplier that can be optimally identified using a variational iteration technique. The m th approximation is denoted by the subscripts. \widetilde{w}_j denotes a restricted variation. i.e., $\widetilde{w}_j = 0$. It is known as a rectification functional relationship (4). Linear problems can be resolved in a single iteration because the Lagrange multiplier can be precisely identified. The Lagrange multiplier $\lambda(t)$ must therefore be determined in the best possible way for this procedure. Thus, using our w_0 and the Lagrange multiplier, it will be simple to find the successive approximation of the solution w , and the solution is provided by

$$\lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} w_j = w \quad (5)$$

The Lagrange Multiplier also play an important role in determining the solution of the problem, and can be defined as follows:

$$\lambda(t) = (-1)^m \frac{1}{(m-1)!} (t - z)^{m-1} \quad (6)$$

Bernstein Polynomials

The Bernstein basis polynomials of degree $M - 1$ is given as

$$B_{M-1}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} \alpha_{j,M-1} \beta_{j,M-1}(z) \quad (7)$$

where $\beta_{j,M-1}(z) = \binom{M-1}{j} z^j (1 - z)^{M-1-j} : j = 0, \dots, M - 1$ and $\alpha_{j,M-1}$ is called Bernstein Coefficients.

Hence, the Bernstein basis polynomials required for this work is given below:

$$\begin{aligned} B_{0,9}(z) &= -z^9+9z^8-36z^7+84z^6-126z^5+126z^4-84z^3+36z^2-9z+1 \\ B_{1,9}(z) &= 9z^9-72z^8+262z^7-504z^6+630z^5-504z^4+252z^3-72z^2+9z \\ B_{2,9}(z) &= -36z^9+252z^8+756z^7+1260z^6-1260z^5+756z^4-252z^3+36z^2 \\ B_{3,9}(z) &= 84z^9-504z^8+1260z^7-1680z^6+1260z^5-504z^4+84z^3 \\ B_{4,9}(z) &= 126z^9+630z^8-1260z^7+1260z^6-630z^5+126z^4 \\ B_{5,9}(z) &= 126z^9-504z^8+756z^7-504z^6+126z^5 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Reconstructed Variational Iteration Technique Using Bernstein Polynomials (RVITBP)

We assume an approximate solution of the form (9) utilizing (3) and (4).

$$w_{j,M-1}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} \alpha_{j,M-1} \beta_{j,M-1}(z) \quad (9)$$

where $\beta_{j,M-1}(z)$ are Bernstein polynomials, $\alpha_{j,M-1}$ stands for unknown constants, and M stands for the degree of approximant. As a result, we get the iterative method shown below:

$$w_{j+1,M-1}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} \alpha_{j,M-1} \beta_{j,M-1}(z) + \int_0^z \lambda(t) \left(L \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} \alpha_{j,M-1} \beta_{j,M-1}(t) + M \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} \alpha_{j,M-1} \beta_{j,M-1}(t) \right) dt \quad (10)$$

Mathematical Applications

In this section, we solved four examples using the proposed method. The numerical results also demonstrate the proposed scheme's accuracy and efficiency.

Example 4.1. Consider the following boundary value problem of tenth-order Septic B-splines, (Kasi Viswanadham & Sreenivasulu (2015):

$$w^{(10)} + w = -10(2z \sin z - 9 \cos z), \quad -1 \leq z \leq 1 \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} w(-1) = w(1) = 0, \quad w'(1) = -w'(-1) = 2 \cos 1, \quad w''(-1) = w''(1) = 2 \cos 1 - 4 \sin 1 \\ w'''(-1) = -w'''(1) = 6 \cos 1 + 6 \sin 1, \\ w^{(4)}(-1) = w^{(4)}(1) = -12 \cos 1 + 8 \sin 1. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{The exact solution for the problem is } w = (z^2 - 1) \cos z. \quad (13)$$

The correction functional is given for the boundary value problems (11) and (12) as

$$w_{j+1} = w_j(z) + \int_0^z \lambda(t) \left(w^{(10)} + w + 10(2t \sin t - 9 \cos t) \right) dt \quad (14)$$

where, $\lambda(t) = \frac{(-1)^{10}(t-z)^9}{9!}$ is the Lagrange multiplier.

Thus, we assume an approximate solution of the form (15) using the reconstructed variational iteration technique with Bernstein polynomials.

$$w_{m,9}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(z) \quad (15)$$

Hence, we get the following iterative formula:

$$w_{m+1,M-1}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(z) + \int_0^z \frac{(t-z)^9}{9!} \left(\frac{d^{10}}{dt^{10}} \left(\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) \right) + \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) + 10(2t \sin t - 9 \cos t) \right) dt \quad (16)$$

$$\begin{aligned} w_{m+1,M-1}(z) = \alpha_{0,9} \beta_{0,9}(z) + \alpha_{1,9} \beta_{1,9}(z) + \alpha_{2,9} \beta_{2,9}(z) + \alpha_{3,9} \beta_{3,9}(z) + \alpha_{4,9} \beta_{4,9}(z) + \alpha_{5,9} \beta_{5,9}(z) + \alpha_{6,9} \beta_{6,9}(z) + \\ \alpha_{7,9} \beta_{7,9}(z) + \alpha_{8,9} \beta_{8,9}(z) + \alpha_{9,9} \beta_{9,9}(z) + \int_0^z \frac{(t-z)^9}{9!} \left(\frac{d^{10}}{dt^{10}} \left(\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) \right) + \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) + 10(2t \sin t - \right. \\ \left. 9 \cos t) \right) dt \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

As a result of (8), iteration, and application of the boundary conditions (12), the values of the unknown constants can be determined as follows

$$\alpha_{0,9} = -1.0000000000, \alpha_{1,9} = -1.0000000000, \alpha_{2,9} = -0.9583333334, \alpha_{3,9} = -0.8750000000, \alpha_{4,9} = -0.75429418, \alpha_{5,9} = -0.6048280424, \alpha_{6,9} = 0.4389715608, \alpha_{7,9} = -0.2718749999, \alpha_{8,9} = 0.1200644842, \alpha_{9,9} = -0.00002480158729$$

Consequently, the series solution is given as

$$w(z) = \frac{1}{12164510040883200} z^{20} - 5.810^{-20} z^{19} + 4.79502510^{-14} z^{18} + 1.810^{-18} z^{17} - 1.151852910^{-11} z^{16} - 1.000000000 + 2.0991464910^{-9} z^{14} - 4.10^{-17} z^{13} - 2.7766867910^{-7} z^{12} + 0.00002507716049 z^{10} + 4.127110^{-10} z^9 - 0.001413600 z^8 + 4.10^{-9} z^7 + 0.04305560 z^6 - 4.10^{-8} z^5 - 0.5416668 z^4 + 1.50000000 z^2 \quad (18)$$

Example 4.2. Consider the following boundary value problem of tenth-order Septic B-splines, (Kasi Viswanadham & Sreenivasulu (2015)

$$w^{(10)} - (z^2 - 2z)w = 10\cos z - (z - 1)^3 \sin z, \quad -1 \leq z \leq 1 \quad (19)$$

with boundary conditions

$$w(-1) = 2\sin 1, w(1) = 0, w'(-1) = -2\cos 1 - \sin 1, w'(1) = \sin 1, \quad (20)$$

$$w''(-1) = 2\cos 1 - 2\sin 1, w''(1) = 2\cos 1, w'''(-1) = 2\cos 1 + 3\sin 1,$$

$$w'''(1) = -3\sin 1, w^{(4)}(-1) = -4\cos 1 + 2\sin 1, v^{(4)}(1) = -4\cos 1.$$

The exact solution for the problem is $w(z) = (z - 1)\sin z$.

The correction functional for the boundary value problem (19) and (20) is given as

$$w_{j+1} = w_j(x) + \int_0^z \lambda(t) (w^{(10)} - (t^2 - 2t)w - 10\cos t + (t - 1)^3 \sin t) dt \quad (21)$$

where $\lambda(t) = \frac{(-1)^{10}(t-z)^9}{9!}$ is the Lagrange multiplier.

Thus, we assume an approximate solution of the form (22) using the reconstructed variational iteration technique with Bernstein polynomials.

$$w_{m,9}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(z) \quad (22)$$

Hence, we get the following iterative formula

$$w_{m+1,M-1}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(z) + \int_0^z \frac{(t-z)^9}{9!} \left(\frac{d^{10}}{dt^{10}} \left(\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) \right) - (t^2 - 2t) \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) - 10\cos t + (t - 1)^3 \sin t \right) dt \quad (23)$$

$$w_{m+1,M-1}(z) = \alpha_{0,9} \beta_{0,9}(z) + \alpha_{1,9} \beta_{1,9}(z) + \alpha_{2,9} \beta_{2,9}(z) + \alpha_{3,9} \beta_{3,9}(z) + \alpha_{4,9} \beta_{4,9}(z) + \alpha_{5,9} \beta_{5,9}(z) + \alpha_{6,9} \beta_{6,9}(z) + \alpha_{7,9} \beta_{7,9}(z) + \alpha_{8,9} \beta_{8,9}(z) + \alpha_{9,9} \beta_{9,9}(z) + \int_0^z \frac{(t-z)^9}{9!} \left(\frac{d^{10}}{dt^{10}} \left(\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) \right) - (t^2 - 2t) \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{i,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) - 10\cos t + (t - 1)^3 \sin t \right) dt \quad (24)$$

Hence: using (8), iterating and applying the boundary conditions (20) the values of the unknown constants can be determined as follows

$$a_{0,9} = 0, a_{1,9} = -0.1111111111, a_{2,9} = -0.1944444444, a_{3,9} = -0.2480158729$$

$$a_{4,9} = -0.2711640212, a_{5,9} = -0.2646164021, a_{6,9} = -0.2304563492$$

$$a_{7,9} = -0.1719852293, a_{8,9} = -0.09349647270, a_{9,9} = -0.000002755731922$$

Consequently, the series solution is given as

$$w(z) = \frac{1}{851515702861824000} z^{20} + 4.322210^{-18} z^{21} - 4.3110^{-18} z^{20} + 8.610^{-18} z^{19} + 2.807910^{-15} z^{18} - 2.81010^{-15} z^{17} - 7.647191 \cdot 10^{-13} z^{16} + 7.647210^{-13} z^{15} + 1.605904410^{-10} z^{14} - 1.605904410^{-10} z^{13} - 2.50521083910^{-8} z^{12} + \frac{1}{39916800} z^{11} + \frac{1}{362880} z^{10} - 0.000002736431922 z^9 - 0.0001985343 z^8 + 0.000198545 z^7 + 0.00833327 z^6 - 0.00833326 z^5 - 0.16666678 z^4 + 1.16666667 z^3 + 1.000000001 z^2 - 1.999999999 z \quad (25)$$

Example 4.3. Consider the following boundary value problem of tenth-order Septic B-splines, (Kasi Viswanadham & Sreenivasulu, 2015)

$$w^{(10)} - w'' + wz = (-8 + z - z^2)e^z, \quad 0 \leq z \leq 1 \quad (26)$$

with boundary conditions

$$w(0) = 1, w(1) = 0, w'(0) = 0, w'(1) = -e, w''(0) = -1, w''(1) = -2e, w'''(0) = -2, w'''(1) = -3e, w^{(4)}(0) = -3, w^{(4)}(1) = -4e. \quad (27)$$

The exact solution of the example is $w(z) = (1 - z)e^z$.

The correction functional for the boundary value problem (26) and (27) is given as

$$w_{j+1} = w_j(z) + \int_0^z \lambda(t) (w^{(10)} - w'' + wt - (-8 + t - t^2)e^t) dt \quad (28)$$

where $\lambda(t) = \frac{(-1)^{10}(t-z)^9}{9!}$ is the Lagrange multiplier.

We assume an approximate solution of the form (29) using the reconstructed variational iteration technique with Bernstein polynomials.

$$w_{m,9}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(z) \quad (29)$$

Hence, we get the following iterative formula

$$w_{j+1,M-1}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(z) + \int_0^z \frac{(t-z)^9}{9!} \left(\frac{d^{10}}{dt^{10}} \left(\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) \right) - \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \left(\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) \right) + t \left(\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) \right) - (-8 + t - t^2)e^t \right) dt \quad (30)$$

$$w_{j+1,M-1}(z) = \alpha_{0,9} \beta_{0,9}(z) + \alpha_{1,9} \beta_{1,9}(z) + \alpha_{2,9} \beta_{2,9}(z) + \alpha_{3,9} \beta_{3,9}(z) + \alpha_{4,9} \beta_{4,9}(z) + \alpha_{5,9} \beta_{5,9}(z) + \alpha_{6,9} \beta_{6,9}(z) + \alpha_{7,9} \beta_{7,9}(z) + \alpha_{8,9} \beta_{8,9}(z) + \alpha_{9,9} \beta_{9,9}(z) + \int_0^z \frac{(t-z)^9}{9!} \left(\frac{d^{10}}{dt^{10}} \left(\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) \right) - \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \left(\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) \right) + t \left(\sum_{i=0}^9 \alpha_{i,9} \beta_{i,9}(t) \right) - (-8 + t - t^2)e^t \right) dt \quad (31)$$

Hence: using (8), iterating and applying the boundary conditions (27) the values of the unknown constants can be determined as follows

$$\alpha_{0,9} = 1.00000000, \alpha_{1,9} = 1.00000000, \alpha_{2,9} = 0.9861111111, \alpha_{3,9} = 0.9543650794$$

$$\alpha_{4,9} = 0.8998015873, \alpha_{5,9} = 0.8162037037, \alpha_{6,9} = 0.697506612$$

$$\alpha_{7,9} = 0.5285548941, \alpha_{8,9} = 0.3020309743, \alpha_{9,9} = 0.000002755731898$$

Consequently, the series solution is given as

$$w(z) = 3.287910^{-17} z^{20} + 5.177410^{-16} z^{19} - 1.250010^{-15} z^{18} - 2.249210^{-14} z^{17} - 7.167210^{-13} z^{16} - 1.0704310^{-11} z^{15} - 1.49116110^{-10} z^{14} - 1.92707310^{-9} z^{13} - 2.296444410^{-8} z^{12} - 2.505210810^{-7} z^{11} - 0.00000248015873 z^{10} - 0.0000219932680 z^9 - 0.000173711 z^8 - 0.00119041 z^7 - 0.00694416 z^6 - 0.0333333 z^5 - 0.1250000 z^4 - 0.3333333 z^3 - 0.5000000 z^2 + 1 \quad (32)$$

Example 4.4. Consider the following boundary value problem of tenth-order (Ali et al., 2018; Iqbal et al., 2015)

$$w^{(10)} = -(80 + 19z + z^2)e^z, \quad 0 \leq z \leq 1 \quad (33)$$

with boundary conditions

$$w(0) = 0, w(1) = 0, w''(0) = 0, w''(1) = -4e, w^{(4)}(0) = -8, w^{(4)}(1) = -16e, w^{(6)}(0) = -24, w^{(6)}(1) = -36e, w^{(8)}(0) = -48, w^{(8)}(1) = -64e \quad (34)$$

The exact solution of the example is $w(z) = z(1 - z)e^z$.

The correct functional for the boundary value problem (33) and (34) is given as

$$w_{j+1} = w_j(z) + \int_0^z \lambda(t) (w^{(10)} + (80 + 19t + t^2)e^t) dt \quad (35)$$

where $\lambda(t) = \frac{(-1)^{10}(t-z)^9}{9!}$ is the Lagrange multiplier

We assume an approximate solution of the form (36) using the reconstructed variational iteration technique with

Bernstein polynomials.

$$w_{m,9}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(z) \tag{36}$$

Hence, we get the following iterative formula

$$w_{j+1,M-1}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(z) + \int_0^z \frac{(t-z)^9}{9!} \left(\frac{d^{10}}{dt^{10}} (\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t)) + (80 + 19t + t^2)e^t \right) dt \tag{37}$$

$$w_{j+1,M-1}(z) = \alpha_{0,9} \beta_{0,9}(z) + \alpha_{1,9} \beta_{1,9}(z) + \alpha_{2,9} \beta_{2,9}(z) + \alpha_{3,9} \beta_{3,9}(z) + \alpha_{4,9} \beta_{4,9}(z) + \alpha_{5,9} \beta_{5,9}(z) + \alpha_{6,9} \beta_{6,9}(z) + \alpha_{7,9} \beta_{7,9}(z) + \alpha_{8,9} \beta_{8,9}(z) + \alpha_{9,9} \beta_{9,9}(z) + \int_0^z \frac{(t-z)^9}{9!} \left(\frac{d^{10}}{dt^{10}} (\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t)) + (80 + 19t + t^2)e^t \right) dt \tag{38}$$

Hence, using (8) iterating and applying the boundary conditions (34) the values of the unknown constants can be determined as follows

$$a_{0,9} = 0, \quad a_{1,9} = 0.1111111048, \quad a_{2,9} = 0.2222222096, \quad a_{3,9} = 0.3273809344$$

$$a_{4,9} = 0.4179893972, \quad a_{5,9} = 0.4818121486, \quad a_{6,9} = 0.5015872836$$

$$a_{7,9} = 0.4530478268, \quad a_{8,9} = 0.3020282123, \quad a_{9,9} = 0.00002480158704.$$

Consequently, the series solution is given as

$$w(z) = \frac{1}{114328101888000} z^{18} - \frac{1}{2032499589120} z^{17} - \frac{1}{93405312000} z^{16} - \frac{1}{6706022400} z^{15} - \frac{1}{518918400} z^{14} - \frac{1}{43545600} z^{13} - \frac{1}{3991680} z^{12} - \frac{1}{403200} z^{11} - \frac{1}{453600} z^{10} - 0.0001736128z^9 - 0.001190426z^8 - 0.00694469z^7 - 0.03333312z^6 - 0.12500028z^5 - 0.33333312z^4 - 0.49999992z^3 + 0.9999999432z \tag{39}$$

Tables

Table 1: shows the comparison between the proposed method and the Galerkin Method with Septic B-splines (Kasi Viswanadham & Sreenivasulu, 2015)

z	Exact solution	Approximate solution	Absolute Error by the proposed method	GMSB-s Error
-0.8	-0.2508144153	-0.2508144310	1.570000e-08	5.483627e-06
-0.6	-0.5282147935	-0.5282148040	1.050000e-08	9.536743e-07
-0.4	-0.7736912350	-0.7736912380	3.000000e-09	8.702278e-06
-0.2	-0.9408639147	-0.9408639150	3.000000e-10	2.980232e-07
0.0	-1.0000000000	-1.0000000000	0.000000e-00	1.955032e-05
0.2	-0.9408639147	-0.9408639150	3.000000e-10	2.920628e-05
0.4	-0.7736912350	-0.7736912390	4.000000e-09	2.169609e-05
0.6	-0.5282147935	-0.5282148100	1.650000e-08	7.390976e-06
0.8	-0.2508144153	-0.2508144550	3.970000e-08	7.450581e-07

Table 2: shows the comparison between the proposed method and the Galerkin Method with Septic B-splines (Kasi Viswanadham & Sreenivasulu, 2015)

z	Exact solution	Approximate solution	Absolute Error by the proposed method	GMSB-s Error
-0.8	1.291240964	1.291240825	1.390000e-07	4.649162e-06
-0.6	0.9034279574	0.9034279277	2.970000e-08	1.329184e-05
-0.4	0.5451856792	0.5451856750	4.200000e-09	2.050400e-05
-0.2	0.2384031970	0.2384031968	2.000000e-10	9.477139e-06
0.0	0.0000000000	0.0000000000	0.000000e-00	2.731677e-06

Numerical Solution of...(Ayinde, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603595>

0.2	-0.1589354646	-0.1589354647	1.000000e-10	1.458824e-05
0.4	-0.2336510054	-0.2336510072	1.800000e-09	2.110004e-05
0.6	-0.2258569894	-0.2258569982	8.800000e-09	1.908839e-05
0.8	-0.1434712182	-0.1434712448	2.660000e-08	1.342595e-05

Table 3: shows the comparison between the proposed method and the Galerkin Method with Septic B-splines, (Kasi Viswanadham and Sreenivasulu, 2015)

z	Exact solution	Approximate solution	Absolute Error by the proposed method	GMSB-s Error
0.1	0.9946538262	0.9946538263	1.000000e-10	1.537800e-05
0.2	0.9771222064	0.9771222066	2.000000e-10	4.452467e-05
0.3	0.9449011656	0.9449011657	1.000000e-10	3.331900e-05
0.4	0.8950948188	0.8950948204	1.600000e-09	3.552437e-05
0.5	0.8243606355	0.8243606415	6.000000e-09	9.477139e-06
0.6	0.7288475200	0.7288475374	1.740000e-08	2.586842e-05
0.7	0.6041258121	0.6041258543	4.220000e-08	3.975630e-05
0.8	0.4451081856	0.4451082770	9.140000e-08	3.531575e-05
0.9	0.2459603111	0.2459604934	1.823000e-07	2.214313e-05

Table 4: Shows the comparison between the proposed method and the Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Space Method (Ali et al., 2018; Iqbal et al., 2015)

z	Exact solution	Absolute Error by the proposed method	AE(RKHSM) (Iqbal et al., 2015)	AE (NPCSM) (Ali et al., 2018))	AE (PCSM) (Ali et al., 2018))
0.2	0.195424441	1.050000e-08	3.330000e-08	2.433000e-07	3.982000e-04
0.4	0.358037927	1.450000e-08	7.031000e-08	3.986000e-07	6.663000e-04
0.6	0.358037927	6.900000e-09	6.076000e-08	4.428000e-07	7.598000e-04
0.8	0.356086549	3.900000e-09	2.682000e-08	3.328000e-07	5.885000e-04

Conclusion

This research adeptly utilized the reconstructed variational iteration method, in conjunction with Bernstein polynomials, to derive accurate numerical solutions for tenth-order boundary value problems. The amalgamation of Bernstein polynomials with the variational iteration technique facilitated an efficient reconstruction process, yielding solutions characterized by a remarkable convergence rate. These series solutions proficiently addressed intricate real-world physical challenges. The proposed methodology exhibited a distinct advantage over prevailing techniques, as substantiated by the comparative analysis presented in tables 1, 2, 3 and 4. The numerical evaluation indicates that the proposed method outperformed those obtained using other methods documented in the literature. The numerical analysis substantiated the effectiveness of the current method as a robust mathematical instrument for tackling high-order boundary value problems. This method is so effective that it can also be recommended for solving boundary value problems using the Homotopy perturbation method, the Adomian decomposition method, and the Sinc-Galerkin method.

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Teachers' Compliance with Professional Ethics and Their Enhanced Productivity in Lagos State Public Senior Secondary Schools Education District I, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated teachers' compliance with professional ethics and teacher productivity in Lagos State public senior secondary schools Education District I, Nigeria. Disproportionate Sampling technique was used in selecting 15 public secondary schools in Education District I. The simple random sampling technique was used in selecting 12 teachers, one principal and two vice-principals of each school selected making a total of 225 respondents. A descriptive Survey research design and correlation, data were collected through a questionnaire titled Teacher Compliance Professional Ethics and Teachers Productivity (TCPETP) with face and content validity and was subjected to a test re-test reliability method with 0.72 reliability coefficient. The study found that there is a significant influence of teachers' commitment at ($r = 0.562$, p -value 0.000); teachers' punctuality have significant influence at ($r = 0.534$, p -value 0.000); teachers' confidentiality significantly influences ($r = 0.560$, p -value 0.001); teachers' integrity significantly influences at ($r = 0.531$, p -value 0.000) and teachers' communication significantly influences at ($r = 0.372$, p -value 0.000) teachers' productivity and that teachers' dress sense do not significantly influence teachers' productivity ($r = 0.079$, p -value 0.238); The study therefore concludes that there is a relationship between teachers' compliance with professional ethics and teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools. It was recommended that schools should establish mentorship programs where experienced teachers with high integrity can guide and support less experienced teachers, promoting a culture of ethical behavior, organize workshops and seminars aimed at improving teachers' communication skills, including both verbal and non-verbal communication, develop and enforce clear dress code policies that promote a professional appearance for teachers, implement recognition and reward programs to acknowledge and celebrate teachers' commitment and dedication.

Keywords: Teachers' Compliance, Professional Ethics, and Teacher Productivity.

Introduction

The development of a nation makes the role of teachers very important in the school. This is because there is no country whether developed or developing that does not require the service of the teachers. The development of any nation depends upon the amount of educated individual that has quality education. Education is the most veritable tool for achieving all round development in any country. This justifies why Omoto (2020) opined that if you see any society that is not performing well, search out what is spent on education. The increase in national income and per capital income is a work of education and that gap among nations can better be explained on human capacity rather than physical capacity. The school prepares its young ones for the management of the nation's economy. It passes the

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desired and acceptable practices, behaviors, values, norms of the society to the students. The school has the responsibility of making sure that its products are found worthy both in character and in learning. Therefore, for any educational institutions to achieve its success and goals, it depends on the teachers' commitment. Teachers are regarded as the strongest pillar of the society. Also, one can submit that, teacher is like a potter who delicately shapes our impressionable minds, a vessel that defines our perception and ambitions. In the light of this, there should be provision of high-quality teachers who have good academic knowledge of their subject disciplines and who possess professional skills, experience, administrative responsibility, attitudes and values as well as personal qualities for effective teaching. More so, teachers in term of quality are expected to function in some other duty to help enhancing the performance of the student. (Gbesoevi, 2019)

School leadership demands a pragmatic approach by focusing on results and consequences in the application of rules, procedures and position as leaders, in order to achieve educational goals. Some school principals' unethical conducts hamper the management of schools for goal attainment. Some of the school principals lack integrity; they engage and encourage examination malpractice. Some do not preserve and facilitate harmonious working relationship amongst school members, while some misappropriate school funds. Their behaviours do not reflect the school values neither do the decisions they take based on statutory and legal framework. Some do not follow due process in administering discipline (Skefkovics & Shapiro, 2018). They make speedy decisions without checking the legal and regulatory clauses that are involved. School leadership demands ennobling conduct as it is through the school that morals are inculcated to the students. The inability of school principals to ensure that their conducts coincide with the school ethics constitute serious threat to the administration of public senior secondary schools for goal attainment (Celik, 2020).

Today, work ethics becomes a prerequisite for conducting any type of business, particularly in the global market place since every business organization operates with multiple relationship including stakeholders such as customers, employees, suppliers, investors amongst others who perhaps would prefer their company to be ethical (Azmi, 2016). Building a strong ethical culture is also integral to the reputation, growth, and finances of any organization and it helps to build trust among the stakeholders (Azmi, 2016). Ethics are set of principles and values that guide organizations in their decisions, programmes and policies. Work ethics dimensions in organizations include trustworthiness, integrity, accountability and civility (Odu & Akhigbe, 2018); honesty, integrity, fairness, and concern for others (Toor & Ofori, 2019). Employees want to be associated with managers that are honest, credible, respectful, and fair (Collins, 2021) and organizations can achieve better employee attraction and retention when employees have the opportunity to work for truly responsible and ethical employers and this improves employee commitment (Upadhyay & Singh, 2020; Collins, 2021).

Workplace best practices are defined as practices that have been shown to improve an organization's capacity to effectively attract, select, hire, develop, and retain higher performing manpower. Best practices are methods or techniques that are known to consistently produce optimal and efficient result. Kamat (2016), stated that a happy workplace is a huge asset. In such places something happens that transcends policies and practices. Workplace is not what the organizations are doing; it is what their leaders are doing. Best workplace practices include the day-to-day relationship that the employees experience, and not a catalog of policies, programmes and benefits. Best practices represent the most efficient course of action in a particular setting or scenario. (Jennifer & Ashley 2022).

At its core, teachers' compliance with professional ethics is grounded in fundamental values such as honesty, integrity, respect, and fairness (Campbell, 2019). More so, the need to continuously initiate professional ethic among teachers as a program becomes a matter of necessity. Teacher education is a programme that is related to the development of teacher proficiency and competence that would enable and empower the teacher to meet the requirements of the profession and face the challenges therein. (Gbesoevi et.al. 2022). Honesty entails providing accurate information to students and stakeholders, maintaining transparency in communication, and upholding truthfulness in all professional dealings. Integrity involves adhering to moral principles and ethical standards even in challenging situations, thereby fostering trust and credibility. Respect necessitates recognizing the dignity, rights, and perspectives of all individuals within the educational community, regardless of differences in background or beliefs. Equally too, one can state that fairness requires ensuring equity and impartiality in the treatment of students, promoting inclusive practices, and addressing inequalities.

In the context of public senior secondary schools, where students are navigating the complexities of adolescence and preparing for higher education or the workforce, the role of teachers in modeling ethical behavior becomes particularly significant. Adolescents are highly attuned to ethical considerations and moral exemplars, and teachers serve as influential role models who shape students' attitudes, values, and ethical reasoning (Strike, 2020). By embodying professional ethics in their actions and interactions, teachers not only uphold the integrity of the teaching profession but also contribute to the moral and character development of their students.

Moreover, teachers' compliance with professional ethics is closely intertwined with their effectiveness and productivity in the classroom. Research suggests that teachers who adhere to ethical principles are more likely to create supportive and inclusive learning environments, establish positive relationships with students, and promote academic integrity (Campbell, 2019). Equally too over-politicisation of the process, lack of or poor policy framework guidelines, non-involvement of educational planners among others could bring about non-compliance to professional ethics in school (Gbesoevi & Ola, 2021). Ethical conduct enhances teacher-student rapport, fosters mutual respect, and cultivates a sense of trust and safety conducive to learning. Furthermore, teachers who prioritize ethical considerations are better equipped to navigate ethical dilemmas, resolve conflicts, and make principled decisions in their professional practice.

Moreover, despite the importance of professional ethics in teaching, educators may encounter various challenges and pressures that can impede their ability to maintain ethical standards consistently. Factors such as time constraints, workload demands, institutional policies, and societal expectations may create tensions between ethical ideals and practical realities (Campbell, 2019). Additionally, teachers may face ethical dilemmas related to issues such as academic integrity, student discipline, confidentiality, and cultural sensitivity, requiring ethical reflection and decision-making skills. In light of these complexities, understanding the factors influencing teachers' compliance with professional ethics is essential for promoting ethical conduct and enhancing teacher effectiveness in public senior secondary schools. By identifying the barriers to ethical practice and the supports needed to foster ethical behavior, educators, policymakers, and stakeholders can develop targeted interventions and professional development initiatives to promote a culture of ethical excellence within educational institutions.

In the realm of public senior secondary education, the intersection between teachers' compliance with professional ethics and their productivity presents a multifaceted challenge deserving of investigation. According to Gbesoevi (2022), It is an issue that has attracted a great deal of attention and concern from educators, teachers, parents, learners and the public at large owing to the state of insecurity confronting schools and the general society. More so, the poor productivity of teachers can lead to inadequate student achievement (Gbesoevi et al 2023). Despite the recognised importance of professional ethics in guiding teachers' conduct and shaping the educational environment, there exists a gap in understanding how adherence to ethical standards influences teacher productivity within this specific context. This study aims to address this gap by examining the relationship between teachers' compliance with professional ethics and their productivity in public senior secondary schools.

The problem at hand encompasses several dimensions. Firstly, while professional ethics serve as guiding principles for teachers, the extent to which educators adhere to these standards and the impact of such adherence on their productivity remain underexplored. Secondly, the unique challenges and contextual factors present in public senior secondary schools, including diverse student populations, resource constraints, and societal expectations, may influence teachers' ability to maintain ethical conduct while fulfilling their professional responsibilities. Understanding how these factors intersect with teachers' productivity is essential for informing strategies to promote ethical excellence and optimize educational outcomes.

Furthermore, ethical dilemmas and tensions may arise in the day-to-day practice of teaching, requiring educators to navigate complex moral terrain. Balancing ethical considerations with instructional demands, administrative requirements, and student needs poses challenges that may affect teachers' effectiveness and well-being. Additionally, the role of school actors, institutional culture, and professional development initiatives in supporting teachers' ethical growth and enhancing productivity warrants investigation.

Objective of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate teachers' compliance with professional ethics and teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State Education District I.

Teachers' Compliance with... (Lawal, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603595>

Specifically, the study set out to achieve the following objectives which is to:

1. Investigate the influence of teacher's commitment on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.
2. Find out the influence of teachers' punctuality on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.
3. Examine the influence of teachers' confidentiality on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.
4. Determine the influence of teachers' integrity on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.
5. Assess the influence of teachers' communication on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.
6. Establish the influence of teachers' dress sense on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Research Questions

The following Research Questions were raised to guide the study:

1. Is there any influence of teachers' commitment on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?
2. Will teachers' punctuality have any influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?
3. Does teachers' confidentiality have any influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?
4. Can teachers' integrity have any influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?
5. How does teachers' communication have influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?
6. To what extent does teachers' dress sense influence teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?

Research Hypotheses

Based on the research objectives, the following hypotheses were tested for the study:

1. Teachers' commitment does not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.
2. Teachers' punctuality does not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.
3. Teachers' confidentiality does not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.
4. Teachers' integrity does not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.
5. Teachers' communication skills do not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.
6. Teachers dress sense does not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Methodology

This study adopted the descriptive research design using quantitative approach. This involves analysing teachers' compliance with professional ethics and teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools. The population of the study consist of all teachers' and principal s in all public senior secondary schools in Lagos State Educational District I comprises of 3 zones which include; Agege, Alimosho, and Ifako Ijaye. The number of senior secondary teachers in Education District I is 1702 teachers and 41 principals. The sample size for this study consists

Teachers' Compliance with... (Lawal, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603595>

of 180 teachers, 15 principals, and 30 vice principle selected from the population. Disproportionate Sampling technique was used in selecting five schools from three zones Agege, Alimosho and Ifako-Ijaye respectively. The simple random sampling technique was used in selecting 12 teachers, one principal Two vice-principals from each 16 sampled school. A self-designed instrument titled "Teacher Compliance Professional Ethics and Teachers Productivity (TCPETP)" was utilised to gather data for the study. Its two aspects were intended to elicit answers to research questions and test the hypotheses. Two sections made up the instrument: Section A collected respondents' personal information, while Sections B contained eighteen items each dimension connected to the variables under investigation and was scaled and scored - Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Agree (3), and Strongly Agree were the available response options. Face and content validity was adopted for the instrument in this study. More so, the reliability of the instrument was assessed utilising the test-retest reliability tests, which provided coefficients of 0.72. Descriptive statistics such as frequency and simple percentages was used to analysed demographic data while inferential statistics of Pearson's Product Moment correlation (PPMC), was used to test the stated hypotheses at 0.05 significant level through the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0.

Presentations of Results

This chapter presents the results from the data analysis based on the research questions and stated hypotheses for the study. The results were interpreted and each of the hypotheses was either rejected or not rejected at 0.05 level of significance. The first section presents the analysis of data, while the second section presents the summary of findings.

Demographic Data of Respondents

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of respondents on the basis of Gender

Variables		N	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	102	53.3
	Female	123	54.7
Age	29 years below	65	28.8
	30 - 39 years	82	36.4
	40 – 49 years	35	15.5
	50 – 59 years	29	12.8
	60 years above	14	6.2
Educational Qualification	HND/PGDE	28	12.4
	B.Sc/ B.Sc/Ed	180	82
	M.Ed/M.Sc/PGDE	9	4
	PhD	4	1.7
Years of Working Experience	1 – 5	69	31.4
	6 - 10	77	34.2
	11 – 15 years	51	22.6
	16 years and above	184	82
Marital Status	Married	28	12.4
	Single	5	2.2
	Divorced	4	1.7
	Separated	4	1.7
	Widow		

Source: Field Work 2024

Teachers' Compliance with... (Lawal, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603595>

The Table 1 shows that 53.6% of respondents were males while 54.7% of respondents are females. This implies that more female students participated in the study than their male counterparts. From Table 2, 28.8% of the respondents were below 30 years; 36.4% were between the age of 31-40; 15.5% were between the age of 41-50; 12.8% were between the age of 51-60, while the remaining 6.2% were 61 and above. From Table 3, 12.4% of the respondents have NCE/HND; 82% of the respondents have B.Ed. /B.Sc.; 9% of the respondents have M.Ed. /M.Sc.; 4% have other qualification. From Table 4, 12.4% of the respondents fall below 5 years; 31.4% fall between 6-10years; 34.2% fall between 11-15years, while 22.6% were above 15 years. From Table 5, 82% of the respondents are married; 12.4% are single; 2.2% are divorced; 1.7% is separated, while the remaining 1.7% was widow.

Answers to Research Questions

Research Question One: Is there any influence of teachers' commitment on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?

Table 4.6: Influence of teachers' commitment on teachers' productivity

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	A	D	SD
1	Teachers demonstrate a strong sense of responsibility towards meeting the educational goals and objectives of the school.	44 19.6%	92 40.9%	60 26.7%	29 12.9%
2	Teachers maintain open and effective communication with students, parents, and colleagues.	40 17.8%	92 40.9%	60 26.7%	29 12.9%
3	Teachers collaborate with colleagues to share resources and best practices for enhancing student learning.	75 33.3%	70 31.1%	40 17.8%	40 17.8%

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 4.6 shows that 60.5% of respondents agree that teachers demonstrate a strong sense of responsibility towards meeting the educational goals and objectives of the school while 39.5% disagree; 58.7% respondents agree that teachers maintain open and effective communication with students, parents and colleagues while 41.3% disagree; 64.4% of respondents agree that teachers collaborate with colleagues to share resources and best practices for enhancing student learning while 35.6% of respondents disagree with the statement. This means that overall, teachers' commitment significantly influences teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Research Question Two: Will teachers' punctuality have any influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?

Table 4.7: Teachers' punctuality has any influence on teachers' productivity

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	A	D	SD
1	Teachers who are punctual are able to manage their classroom time more effectively, leading to increased student learning.	62 27.6%	71 31.6%	52 23.1%	40 17.8%
2	Teacher's punctuality affects their ability to prepare effectively for lessons	65 28.9%	97 43.1%	33 14.7%	30 13.3%
3	Teacher's tardiness affects the overall learning environment in the classroom	11 49.3%	68 30.2%	26 11.6%	20 8.9%

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 4.7 shows that 59.2% of respondents agree that teachers who are punctual are able to manage their classroom time more effectively, leading to increased student learning while 40.8% disagree; 72.0% of respondents agree that teacher's punctuality affect their ability to prepare effectively for lessons while 22.0% disagree; 79.5% of respondents agree that teacher's tardiness affect the overall learning environment in the classroom while 20.5% disagree. This implies that to a very high extent; teachers' punctuality has a significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Research Question Three: Does teachers' confidentiality have any influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?

Table 4.8: Influence of teachers' confidentiality on teachers' productivity

	STATEMENT	SA	A	D	SD
1	I feel more comfortable trying new teaching methods if I know my performance evaluations will be kept confidential.	60 26.7%	58 25.8%	52 23.1%	58 25.8%
2	When I know feedback on my teaching is confidential, I am more likely to openly discuss challenges with school administrators.	68 30.2%	77 34.2%	44 19.6%	36 16.0%
3	If I am concerned about negative evaluations being shared with others, I am less motivated to put in extra effort for lesson planning and student support.	98 43.6%	58 25.8%	17 7.6%	52 23.1%

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 4.8 shows that 52.5% of respondents agree that they feel more comfortable trying new teaching methods if I know my performance evaluations will be kept confidential while 47.5% disagree; 64.4% agree that when they know feedback on their teaching is confidential, they are more likely to openly discuss challenges with school administrators while 35.6% disagree with the statement; 69.4% of respondents agree that if they are concerned about negative evaluations being shared with others, they are less motivated to put in extra effort for lesson planning and student support while 30.6% disagree with the statement. This implies that teachers' confidentiality has a significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Research Question Four: Can teachers' integrity have any influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?

Table 4.9: Influence of teachers' integrity on teachers' productivity

	Statement	SA	A	D	SD
1	The integrity of teachers positively influences the school's overall environment.	57 25.3%	111 49.3%	40 17.8%	17 7.6%
2	Teachers demonstrate honesty and transparency in their interactions with colleagues.	66 29.3%	73 32.4%	38 16.9%	48 21.3%
3	Teacher integrity plays a significant role in shaping students' character.	57 25.3%	90 40.0%	31 13.8%	47 20.9%

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 4.9 shows that 74.6% of respondents agree that the integrity of teachers positively influences the school's overall environment while 25.4% disagree with the statement; 61.7% of respondents agree that teachers demonstrate honesty and transparency in their interactions with colleagues while 37.2% disagree with the statement; 75.3% of respondents agree that teacher integrity plays a significant role in shaping students' character while 24.7% of respondents disagree with the statement. This infers that to a high degree, teachers' integrity have a significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Research Question Five: How Does Teachers' Communication Have Influence on Teachers' Productivity In Public Senior Secondary School in Lagos State Education District I?

Table 4.10: Influence of Teachers' Communication on Teachers' Productivity

	STATEMENT	SA	A	SD	D
1	Teacher uses a variety of communication methods (e.g., lectures, discussions, activities) to keep the class engaged.	78 34.7%	78 34.7%	39 17.3%	30 13.3%
2	Teacher listens attentively to student questions and responds in a clear and concise manner.	78 34.7%	72 32.0%	45 20.0%	30 13.3%
3	Teacher effectively conveys complex information in a way that is easy to understand.	47 20.9%	84 37.3%	47 20.9%	47 20.9%

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 4.10 shows that 79.4% of respondents agree that teacher uses a variety of communication methods (e.g., lectures, discussions, activities) to keep the class engaged while 20.6% disagree with the statement; 66.7% of respondents agree that teacher listens attentively to student questions and responds in a clear and concise manner while 32.3% were undecided; 58.2% of respondents agree that teacher effectively conveys complex information in a way that is easy to understand while 41.8% disagree with the statement. This implies that overall, teachers' communication have a significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Research Question Six: To what extent does teachers' dress sense influence teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?

Influence of teachers' dress sense on teachers' productivity

	STATEMENT	SA	A	SD	D
1	Students are more likely to be engaged in class when their teacher dresses professionally.	75 33.3%	94 41.8%	33 14.7%	23 10.2%
2	Teachers who dress professionally are perceived as more knowledgeable and authoritative by students.	67 29.8%	115 51.1%	27 12.0%	16 7.1%
3	The overall appearance of a school, including teacher attire, can influence student behavior.	76 33.8%	100 44.4%	40 17.8%	9 4.0%

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 4.11 shows that 75.1% of respondents agree that students are more likely to be engaged in class when their teacher dresses professionally while 24.9% disagree with the statement; 80.9% of respondents agree that teachers who dress professionally are perceived as more knowledgeable and authoritative by students while 19.1% of respondents disagree with the statement; 78.2% of respondents agree that the overall appearance of a school, including teacher attire, can influence student behavior while 21.8% of respondents disagree with the statement. This means that to a very high extent, teachers' dress sense influence teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One:

Teachers' commitment does not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Table 4.12 Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis on the significant influence of teachers' commitment on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school

		Teachers' Commitment	Teachers' Productivity
Teachers' Commitment	Pearson Correlation	1	.562**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	225	225
Teachers' Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.562**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	225	225

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.12 shows the Pearson correlation result suggests that there is a significant positive relationship between teachers' commitment and teachers' productivity ($r = 0.562$, p -value 0.000). This relationship is statistically significant because the p -value for the result (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.05) used for the study. The null hypothesis was rejected, while the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This implies that there is a significant influence of teachers' commitment on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Hypothesis Two:

Teachers' punctuality does not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Table 4.13 Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis on teachers' punctuality influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school

		Teachers' Punctuality	Teachers' Productivity
Teachers' Punctuality	Pearson Correlation	1	.534**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	225	225
Teachers' Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.534**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	225	225

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.13 shows the Pearson correlation result which suggests that there is a significant positive relationship between teachers' punctuality and teachers' productivity ($r = 0.534$, p -value 0.000). This relationship is statistically significant because the p -value for the result (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.05) used for the study. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected, while the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This result implies that teacher's punctuality have significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Hypothesis Three:

Teachers' confidentiality does not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Table 4.14 Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis on the significant influence of teachers' confidentiality on teachers' productivity

		Teachers' confidentiality	Teachers' Productivity
Teachers' confidentiality	Pearson Correlation	1	.560*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	225	225
Teachers' Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.560*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
	N	225	225

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.14 shows the Pearson correlation result which suggests that there is a significant positive relationship between teachers' confidentiality and teachers' productivity ($r = 0.560$, p -value 0.001). This relationship is statistically significant because the p -value for the result (0.001) is less than the level of significance (0.05) used for the study. Hence the null hypothesis was rejected, while the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This result indicates that teachers' confidentiality significantly influences teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Hypothesis Four:

Teachers' integrity does not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Table 4.15 Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis on the significant influence of teachers' integrity on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school

		Teachers' integrity	Teachers' Productivity
Teachers' integrity	Pearson Correlation	1	.531**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	225	225
Teachers' Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.531**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	225	225

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.15 shows the Pearson correlation result which suggests that there is a significant positive relationship between teachers' integrity and teachers' productivity ($r = 0.531$, p -value 0.000). This relationship is statistically significant because the p -value for the result (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.05) used for the study. Null hypothesis was rejected, while the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This result infers that teachers' integrity significantly influences teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Hypothesis Five

Teachers' communication skills do not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Table 4.16 Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis on the significant influence of teachers' communication on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school

		Teachers' communication	Teachers' Productivity
Teachers' communication	Pearson Correlation	1	.372**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	225	225
Teachers' Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.372**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	225	225

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.16 shows the Pearson correlation result which suggests that there is a significant positive relationship between teachers' communication and teachers' productivity ($r = 0.372$, p -value 0.000). This relationship is statistically significant because the p -value for the result (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.05) used for the study. Null hypothesis was rejected, while the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This result means that teachers' communication significantly influences teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Hypothesis Six:

Teachers dress sense does not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Table 4.17 Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis on the significant influence of teachers' dress sense on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school

		Teachers' dress sense	Teachers' Productivity
Teachers' dress sense	Pearson Correlation	1	.079
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.238
	N	225	224
Teachers' Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.079	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.238	
	N	225	225

Table 4.17 shows the Pearson correlation result which suggests that there is no significant relationship between teachers' dress sense and teachers' productivity ($r = 0.079$, p -value 0.238). This relationship is not statistically significant because the p -value for the result (0.238) is more than the level of significance (0.05) used for the study. The null hypothesis was accepted, while the alternative hypothesis was not accepted. This result establishes that teachers' dress sense do not significantly influence teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Discussion of Findings

The study found that there is a significant influence of teachers' commitment on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school. This result aligns with the study of Akpotu, Ojoko, and Egbede (2020) conducted a study on "Teacher Commitment and Productivity in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Delta State, Nigeria" and

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found that teacher commitment had a significant positive impact on teacher productivity, with committed teachers exhibiting higher levels of job satisfaction and student academic achievement.

The study established that teacher's punctuality has significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school. This result validates the study of Adeniji, Akinwumi, and Olatunbosun (2019) who conducted a study on impact of teachers' punctuality on students' academic performance in Nigerian secondary schools" and found that teachers' punctuality significantly influenced students' academic achievement, with punctual teachers recording higher student performance.

The study revealed that teachers' confidentiality significantly influences teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school. This result coincides with the findings of Adeyemo, Ojedokun and Olowo (2018) who conducted a study on impact of confidentiality on teacher productivity in Nigerian public secondary schools and found that teachers' adherence to confidentiality significantly enhanced their productivity, as it fostered trust and cooperation among colleagues and students.

The study showed that teachers' integrity significantly influences teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school. This result supports the findings of Maaja and Krista (2016), who conducted a study on the importance of integrity: determining factors and some hints to ethics. One of the most important findings of our study is that the assessment of peer's value integrity tells the most how important honest is for the focal person. Results reveal also the role of some other personal values as well as the country of residence in respect with the importance of integrity.

The study revealed that teachers' communication significantly influences teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school. This result coincides with the findings of Huberts (2018) who conducted a study on teachers' communication what it is and why it is important. The study found that integrity is a crucial concept for an understanding of governance. Not as an alternative for "ethics theory and approaches" but to be embedded in existent "approaches" and theory development. In that sense it belongs on the agenda for further progress in these fields of study, in particular in empirical research on the actual significance of integrity and teachers' communication in governance.

The study indicated that teachers' dress sense does not significantly influence teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school. This result supports the findings of Udeh, Nwosu, and Onyia (2018) who investigated teachers' dress code on productivity in Nigerian public secondary schools and established that no significant relationship between teachers' dress sense and productivity, suggesting that other factors such as teacher motivation and school environment play a more critical role in influencing productivity. Ayi and Akhigbe (2018) conducted a study on workplace ethics and teachers' compliance of secondary school in Nigeria. The results indicated that a significant association exists between civility, trustworthiness, integrity and measures of employee commitment, and that culture moderated the influence of workplace ethics and employees' commitment. Based on the study findings, it was concluded that integrity, teachers' compliance, teachers' punctuality, teachers' communication, teachers' confidentiality and teachers' dress sense influences teachers' productivity.

Conclusion

This study aimed to investigate the influence of various factors teachers' commitment, punctuality, confidentiality, integrity, communication, and dress sense on the productivity of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State Education District I. In conclusion, the study on Teachers' Compliance with Professional Ethics and Teacher Productivity in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Lagos State has yielded significant insights into the critical role of professional ethics in enhancing teacher productivity. The findings unequivocally establish that teachers' commitment, punctuality, confidentiality, integrity, and communication are vital components of professional ethics that substantially influence teacher productivity. The significant influence of teachers' commitment on productivity underscores the importance of teachers' dedication and passion for their profession. Teachers who demonstrate unwavering commitment to their students and the educational process are more likely to exhibit high productivity levels.

Similarly, the positive impact of punctuality on productivity highlights the significance of time management and responsibility in teaching. Teachers who adhere to schedules and timelines contribute to a culture of accountability and efficiency. Confidentiality, integrity, and communication also emerged as essential ethical standards that foster teacher productivity. Teachers who maintain confidentiality, uphold integrity, and communicate effectively with

students, colleagues, and parents create a conducive learning environment. Notably, the study revealed that teachers' dress sense does not significantly influence productivity, suggesting that professional attire, while important, is not a primary determinant of teacher effectiveness.

Overall, this study underscores the imperative of professional ethics in promoting teacher productivity and, by extension, quality education. To optimize teacher productivity, educational stakeholders must prioritize the cultivation of professional ethics, providing ongoing training and support for teachers to develop and maintain these essential standards. By doing so, public senior secondary schools in Lagos State can foster a culture of professionalism, accountability, and excellence, ultimately enhancing student outcomes and contributing to the development of a well-educated and productive citizenry.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study on the influence of various factors on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State Education District I, the following recommendations are proposed

1. Policymakers should integrate professional ethics into teacher education programs and ongoing professional development initiatives, ensuring teachers receive regular training and support. They should also establish clear policies and guidelines for teacher conduct and productivity.
2. School administrators should prioritize the cultivation of professional ethics, fostering a culture of accountability and excellence within schools. Regular workshops and seminars on ethics and productivity should be organized, and teachers' adherence to professional standards should be monitored and evaluated.
3. Teacher training institutions should incorporate comprehensive modules on professional ethics and productivity into their curricula, ensuring prospective teachers understand the importance of commitment, punctuality, confidentiality, integrity, and effective communication.
4. Teachers should strive to internalize and demonstrate professional ethics, recognizing their critical role in promoting productivity and quality education. They should prioritize ongoing professional development, seeking feedback and support to enhance their teaching practices.

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Qualitative Study on the Role of Technology in Entrepreneurship Education for Sustainable Development in Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper focuses on entrepreneurship education as a mechanism for achieving sustainable development in Nigeria. Issues discussed include nature of entrepreneur, entrepreneurship education technology innovations entrepreneurship development in Nigeria, the Goals of Entrepreneurship Education, it impacts, among others. The goals of sustainable development were also discussed, employment generation. This paper identified that although some strategies emphasis on entrepreneurship skills there is requirement for a comprehensive orientation of institutions with the sole aim of improving the entrepreneurship mentality of the youths. The aftermath of this is the generation of employment, increased output through innovations, efficient utilization of available resources and the facilitation in the transfer of technological advancement to mention a few have been identified as the contributions of Entrepreneurship to the development of a country. Based on these propositions as well other discourses a number of recommendations were suggested which includes; a call for stakeholders to recommit themselves towards development of entrepreneurship through the provision of adequate resources for teaching as well as well-equipped empowerment development centers. The paper emphasis that based on the shared responsibilities for entrepreneurship development it can be employed as a viable tool for sustainable development in Nigeria.

Keywords: technology entrepreneurship education panacea for sustainable development in Nigeria.

Introduction

Technology entrepreneurship is basically a combination of two separate terms from two different disciplines, technology came from the discipline of innovation and entrepreneurship came from the business or commercial discipline. Hence it is an integration of technological and entrepreneurial domains. Technology entrepreneur is a person having specific knowledge and expertise vital for any entrepreneur in order to carry out technology centered entrepreneurial activities effectively and efficiently. Ogwedenge (2013) explained that collaborative research and development activities, producing innovative products, evolving new resources and their attributes which leads toward progression in scientific and technological expertise basically discriminates technology entrepreneurship from other entrepreneurship domains.

Today is the era where technology entrepreneurship has turn to be an important global portent. It is considered as essential for progression, distinction and a vital tool to attain competitive benefit at organizational, local and national levels. It is becoming a central point of debate which involves initiating new business as wells rising of new startups, regional profitable progressions, opting out the most suitable stakeholders or investors to bring ideas to marketplaces and also educating and give training to managers, scientists, supervisors, Engineers, and technologists, Petti and Zhang, (2011). Practitioners and researchers claim that technology entrepreneurship is basically an investment in

Qualitative Study on...(Bello, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609049>

creating new ventures that accumulates and organizes particular individuals and divergent resources in order to catch value for the organization. This concept is more concerned with combined production grounded on a mutual vision of upcoming technological changes. Change in technology can be characterized in numerous ways. For that reason, it is essential to cultivate a shared opinion of any change in technology Shane and Venkataraman, (2013). This value creating concept is not only about to identify the technology or market opportunities but basically about investing, exploiting that opportunity and generating high profit margins for the firm Shane, and Venkataraman (2013).

Conceptual Framework

Technology can be perceived as a product and as a process Yusuf, (2016). As a product, it is described as hardware, which is the device that conveys and supplies information to carry out and achieve a task. The hardware is the physical equipment used to store, project, transmit or retrieve information from the software. The software is the message carrier. As a process, it is observed as a method of applying resources to satisfy human wants and needs to widen human ability. It is the systematic process of solving problems by scientific means.

Concept of technology integration

Technology integration has been defined in numerous ways by different authors. For instance, Ntuli, and Kyei-Blankson (2013) refer to technology integration to the use of various digital and hardware tools to facilitate the process of teaching and learning in and outside the classroom. Dockstader (2017) believe that technology integration is using computers effectively and efficiently in the general content areas to allow students to learn how to apply computer skills in meaningful ways. Similarly, Kafyulilo (2015) maintains that technology integration is using software supported by the business world for real-world applications, so students learn to use computers flexibly, purposefully and creatively.

Belland, 2019: Newby, et al., 2016 and Ertmer, 2015: They believed that technology integration means using technology to make learning more efficient or effective as well as the use of technology to help students solve problems. Also, Redmann and Kotrlik (2018) saw technology integration as “making, modification, usage and knowledge of tools, machines, techniques, crafts, systems and methods of organization to solve a problem, improve a pre-existing solution to a problem, achieve a goal, handle an applied input or output relation or perform a specific function”. Technology integration has been regarded as the sustainable and persistent change in the social system of schools caused by the adoption of technology to help students construct knowledge, Gibson, (2011). Additionally, technology integration also has been defined in other ways, for example, technology integration is having the curriculum drive technology usage, not having technology drive the curriculum.

Concept of Entrepreneur

Entrepreneur is an entity which has the ability to find and act upon opportunities to translate inventions or technologies into products and services: "The entrepreneur is able to recognize the commercial potential of the invention and organize the capital, talent, and other resources that turn an invention into a commercially viable innovation." In this sense, the term "Entrepreneurship" also captures innovative activities on the part of established firms, in addition to similar activities on the part of new businesses. It is about bearing the skills needed to assume the risk of establishing a business. It is about developing the winning strategies and executing them with all vigor, persistence and passion needed to win any game". "Entrepreneurship is the process or capacity for organizing, operating and assuming risk for a business venture. It is dynamic risk-taking, creative and growth-oriented behavior which involves the use of various resources to create wealth, Ekanem (2015)"

Types of Entrepreneurs

1. Innovative Entrepreneurs: Innovators, who may invent, present new products, offer new methods of fabrication as well as discover new markets and opportunities.
2. Imitative entrepreneurs: usually cautious and skeptic in adopting any alteration in their business activities
3. Fabian Entrepreneurs: the second generation entrepreneur and usually slow in making decisions regarding changes in their business activities
4. Drone Entrepreneurs: reluctant to adopt new technologies, Inventions, opportunities even when these changes will reduce the cost of doing business, Ekanem (2015)

Entrepreneurship Education

Entrepreneurship education places emphases on youth development and also the desire and multiple competencies of individuals. It seeks to decrease the inherent risk attached with entrepreneurship while guiding the

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enterprise through its beginning phase to its maturity stage successfully, Ijsselstein (2010). It is structured to connect and adopt proficiencies, attributes and values required to recognize potential investment opportunities, structure and embark on new business ventures, Brown, (2018). Entrepreneurship education is an educational programme which focuses on impacting pupils on matters surrounding entrepreneurship education. Entrepreneurship education is involved in the motivation, mentorship of youths and elders on approaches to become self-reliant in thinking, creating and operating a venture, (Gorman, Hanlon & King, 2016; Rasheed and Rasheed, 2013)

Characteristics of Entrepreneurial:

According to Gana, (2011) the Characteristics of Entrepreneurial are;

1. **Self-confidence:** This can be characterized as one of the essential attributes an entrepreneur must possess. The entrepreneur must believe in his/her self and the project he/she intends to embark on. The entrepreneur should be able to see the obstacles or difficulties in achieving his/her goals as Challenges which must be faced squarely and conquered. The entrepreneurs must maintain a high level of emotional stability in the face of difficulties.
2. **Risk taking:** An entrepreneur must analyze and determine the risk inherent in the project he/she is embarking on and as such adopting strategies aimed at mitigating the potential exposure to these inherent risks. Gana (2011) the entrepreneur employs and focuses on his/her personal talent, capabilities, -competencies, technical know-how and values to navigate these inherent risks.
3. **Job orientation:** An entrepreneur is result-orientated. He or she sets difficult but achievable goals. The entrepreneur is dogged, tenacious and strong-minded. **Drive and Energy:** An entrepreneur shows high levels of drive and energy by putting a serious amount of physical and mental energy
4. **Leadership:** An entrepreneur encourages and guides individuals towards achieving set of goals and objectives.

Technological Innovation and Entrepreneurship Development in Nigeria.

Entrepreneurship is about starting a new business based on a recognized business opportunity as well as operating and maintaining that business. The belief of some people is that entrepreneurship does not need to be taught and therefore, an entrepreneur is born to be so. It should however be noted that for one to be a successful entrepreneur, he/she needs to learn the skills Garba, et.al (2010). Entrepreneur training is designed to teach the skills and knowledge that is needed to know before embarking on a new business venture. This would enhance necessary identification and avoidance of many pitfalls awaiting the less well trained and vigilant contemporaries. The training may initially be perceived as a cost in terms money but it would eventually be appreciated. The study carried out by Taiwo, et al. (2012), on small scale food companies in Nigeria reported that one major sources of technological change in these companies is personnel (operators and craftsmen). The reasons adduced for these were simplicity of the innovation processes to the work force; accurate and adequate information about the system of production; and the involvement of the workforce in the initiation and implementation of any technological changes. Moreover, another research finding showed that the key information sources for manufacturing small and medium firms,, production and innovation are machinery suppliers, exhibition and trade fairs, client firms, publications, repair workshops (foundries, heat treatment shops and others), staff of other firms, social and professional associations, and consultancy firms within and outside the clusters, Oyeyinka-Oyelaran, (2013). Some researchers observe that increasing profit of organization is because of change in technology. Entrepreneur perspective innovation means creativity. "Innovation is a research area within the Marketing and Entrepreneurship Interface is a growing area of enquiry" Fialho, (2017).

Entrepreneurship opportunity identification and need to fulfilling innovation. Entrepreneurship and innovation is a key of economic growth, and there is strong relationship between entrepreneurial activity and economic development across the border. Entrepreneurship has also played a vital role in motivation. You can motivate entrepreneurship through culture, family and friend business. Another aspect of motivation is to motivate your employees by giving incentives, bonuses and increase salaries but according to entrepreneurship motivation is a deep meaning that to motivate your family and friend in the field of entrepreneurship you can give new and innovative idea to your friend to start new business and also running your family business with new creative ideas. We cannot understand entrepreneurship until and unless we understand the single who involve in motivation, Venkataraman, (2018).

Objective of Entrepreneurship Education

Qualitative Study on...(Bello, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609049>

According to Paul (2015) the following are the objectives of Entrepreneurship

1. It offers an educational approach which is practical which enables and equips with the necessary skills to be self-reliant and self-employed.
2. It provides the youth and graduates with the necessary training that enables them to be Inventive and imaginative in recognizing investment prospects
3. It serves as a promoter of economic advancement and development.
4. It impacts positively on the rate of poverty.
5. It creates employment opportunities

Technology as a Tool for Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship education is essential to the creation of effective human capital in any country Eroh, (2017). The need for ICT as a tool in entrepreneurship education cannot be overemphasized. In this technology-driven age, everyone requires ICT competence to survive. Entrepreneurship educators are finding it very necessary to train and re-train their employees to establish, increase their knowledge of computers and other ICT facilities Adomi and Amic, (2016). This calls for early acquisition of ICT skills by students of entrepreneurship education.

The ability to use computers effectively has become an essential part of everyone's education. Skills such as book-keeping, clerical, and administrative work, stock-taking and so forth, now constitute a set of computerized practices that form the core information technology skills package: spreadsheets, word processors, and databases Adomi, (2015).

The demand for computer ICT literacy is increasing in Nigeria, because educators realize that computers and other ICT facilities can enhance entrepreneur education. On the other hand, educators have also realized that computers can be a threat to their job, and the only way to enhance job security is to become computer literate. With the high demand for computer literacy, the teaching and learning of these skills is concern among entrepreneurs' educators, Brakel, (2013). This is also true of other ICT components.

New instructional techniques that use ICTs provide a different modality of instruments. For the student, ICT use, allows for increased individualization of learning. In schools where new technologies are used, students have access to ICT tools that adjust to their attention span and provide valuable and immediate feedback for literacy enhancement, which is currently not fully implemented in the Nigerian school system Enuke and Emuka, (2014). ICT as a tool will prove beneficial in improving Nigeria's educational system and giving students a better entrepreneurship education.

Sustainable Development

The term "sustainable development" was initially coined in 1972 during the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment and later gained prominence by way of a report to the United Nations by the "World Commission on Environment and Development" which was chairperson by the Prime Minister of Norway "Gro-Harlem Brundtland" Was, Huges, Verbruggen and Wright, (2011). Sustainable development entails that resources that are renewable should be employed in every possible situation and resources that are non-renewable should be used rarely in order to ensure their viability for the future generations to come Patil, (2014). Sustainable development entails the designing of a social and economic system that ensures the standards of education continues to improve, the rise in the real income maintained, the economic growth of the nation continues to improve as well as other aspect of life continues to increase Kyro, (2015). This cannot occur if the right type of education is not given to individuals. Sustainable development can be viewed in three dimensions namely; Economic, environmental and social United Nations, (2015).

Entrepreneurship Development in Nigeria

Entrepreneurial development may be conceived as a programme of activities to enhance the knowledge, skills, behaviour and attitudes of individuals and groups to assume the role of entrepreneurs as well as efforts to remove all forms of barriers in the path of entrepreneurs. It is anchored on the firm belief that entrepreneurship involves a body of knowledge, skills and attitudes which can be learned and applied by most people who are sufficiently motivated. In contrast to the idea that entrepreneurs are born, entrepreneurship development recognizes that many individuals have latent potential to fit into the role of entrepreneurs. Such potentials can be actualized through training programme, Inegbenebor, (2016).

Qualitative Study on...(Bello, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609049>

Entrepreneurship development assumes that through the process of learning, these characteristics or pattern can be acquired by anyone who is adequately motivated. Similarly, individuals can learn to deal with socio-cultural constraints and inhibitions prevalent in growing economies. Entrepreneurs can be trained also on how to establish and maintain effective relationship with financial institutions, suppliers, government agencies, and other critical institutions upon which they depend for information, guidance and inputs. It is possible to achieve all these through business counseling and by providing relevant information

Entrepreneurship

The education system with regards to the western educational system in Nigeria can be traced to the arrival of colonialism and scholars highlight the policy of education during that era was structured to serve the interest of the colonial masters with regards to supply of man-power for the administration of the Nigerian colony, Fabunmi, (2015), The policy as such was structured and targeted at graduating Nigerians who had the capacity and ability to read and write in order to become inspectors, interpreters and clerks while failing to equip them with the necessary entrepreneurial skills that enable them to identify business opportunities in order to establish their own ventures Aja, and Adali, (2013). Garba (2010) during this era the development of entrepreneurship was largely ignored particularly at the “micro-level” as the educational policy of colonial and the immediate post-colonial administrations focused on meeting the standards of “white collar jobs”. Co-incidentally, obtaining these jobs was not the challenge then due to the fact the various opportunities for employment awaited yet to be graduated Nigerian students.

Over the years, the economy of the Nigerian state began to experience stagnation in growth and institutions and policies such as the “Nigerian Agricultural and Cooperative Bank” (NACB), “Nigerian Industrial Bank” (NIB) which can be labeled as the informal industrial sector was established Chete, and et al, (2015). A number of agencies were created by the government to assist the development of entrepreneurship such as the Nigerian Export British Journal of Education Vol.7, No.2, pp.58-72, February 2019 Nigerian Promotion Council (NEPC), National Directorate of Employment (NDE) Hassan, (2013). However three notable educational policies worthy of analyzing are as follows; National Policy on Education (2014): This strategy places greater emphasis on the entrepreneurial education as subject number 34 trade and entrepreneurship subjects were introduced into the curriculum of secondary schools Adeyonu and Carim-Sanni, (2015). In addition, University of Nigeria, Nsukka now offers the following bakery, fishery, poultry, woodwork, garment making and auto workshop to mention but a few. From the above discussion it can be deduced that entrepreneurship has spread rapidly across universities and polytechnics in Nigeria and as such the Nigerian government should seriously pursue it by providing the much-needed facilities.

Challenges of Entrepreneurial Education in Nigeria and Possible Solutions.

As may be expected of this veritable tool for development, entrepreneurship in Nigeria is tainted with a plethora of problems. These problems, as highlighted in Inegbenebor (2012) and Kuratko (2003), are presented below together with the perceived solutions.

1. Students’ Orientation: The place of passion is critical in cultivating and promoting entrepreneurial spirit in students. This follows that a passionate and committed student of entrepreneurship may end up taking the course as a career goal. Entrepreneurship, as it is today, is not taken by many as a vocational course of study in Nigeria, rather, wage earning is favored. This is a challenge to the field. But to stimulate students’ interest in this line, a design of entrepreneurship education with significant promotional content as well as an enabling environment is needed for that purpose.
2. Orientation of Schools Administration: many schools’ administrators are yet to appreciate the value and potential of entrepreneurship education in the development of the nation; hence, no real support is articulated by them. There is a need for the leadership of schools to re-orient themselves towards entrepreneurship development. Practical steps towards result-oriented entrepreneurship can only be achieved in schools only when school administrators themselves know and promote activities of entrepreneurial development. The National Universities Commission (NUC) and National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) should go beyond prescribing the minimum academics standards with respect to entrepreneurship education to organizing seminars and workshops with the aim of enhancing the knowledge of school administrators in this area. The fundamental question of who to be the target in entrepreneurship education is another fascinating aspect of polytechnic and university administrators’ orientation. Should entrepreneurship be an elective or a compulsory course? Should students be allowed to self-select themselves for entrepreneurship

Qualitative Study on...(Bello, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609049>

education? Whatever the answer to these questions may be, it is important that entrepreneurship is promoted heavily among young people. Special effort should be made to promote entrepreneurship education among students in science, engineering and agriculture where the potential for growing innovative, high growth firms is high, Inegbenebor, (2012).

3. **What to Teach:** What to teach depends on the overall aim that a given entrepreneurship education programme seeks to achieve. At the initial stage of entrepreneurship education, it was believed that the best that can be achieved by educators was to seek to change the perception of students by making them aware of the nature and scope of entrepreneurship, the characteristics and the role demands of entrepreneurs and the impact of social, economic and political environment on new ventures creation. Kuratko (2013), entrepreneurship education includes skill building in negotiation, leadership, new product development, creative thinking and exposure to technological innovation. Other areas considered to be important for entrepreneurial education are sources of venture capital, idea protection, characteristics of entrepreneurs, and challenges of each stage of venture development, and awareness of entrepreneurial career options. In relation to Nigeria, guidelines have been provided by the concerned regulating bodies. In spite of this, there is need for entrepreneurship teachers, educators and practitioners to brainstorm for the purpose of generating ideas about what to teach given the socioeconomic peculiarity of Nigeria. **How to Teach:** How to teach entrepreneurship addresses the issues of how best to stimulate students' interest in entrepreneurship, how best to transfer information, skill and attitudes relevant for successful venture creation and sustenance. Researchers have found widespread use of experiential learning in entrepreneurial education in most schools, Inegbenebor, (2016). Experiential learning is an effort to integrate real world experiences with conceptual learning. It involves various techniques as case analysis, business plans, consulting with practicing entrepreneurs as guest speakers, internship in entrepreneurially run businesses, student involvement in product development teams, simulation, field trips, use of video and films and so on. The major advantage of this method is that the students are actively involved in the learning process. Also, the lecture method which is suitable for providing information, explaining concepts and theories is widely used here necessary.
4. **Who is to Teach Entrepreneurship?:** Special training and experience are required for the purpose of teaching entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship teachers and facilitators should, as a matter of policy, be made to acquire the requisite knowledge, skills and expertise for this purpose. Inegbenebor (2016) opined that one technique that can be used in improving the teaching of entrepreneurship is to encourage the educational institutions involved to share resources, knowledge and experience in this area through seminars, conferences and workshops. Also, business experts and practitioners should be invited as speakers to share their practical experiences in the course of managing their businesses or rendering consultancy services.
5. **Teaching Facilities:** Materials to aid the learning process of entrepreneurship in Nigerian institutions are not adequate, in the real sense of it. Entrepreneurship has, this day, remained largely the same as other subjects in terms of delivery. There should be hand-on teaching materials and equipment to aid learning process in the various institutions.
6. **Capacity Building Centre:** As alluded to in the point above, center for capacity building, where the intending entrepreneur is made to have hands-on experience are not adequate, if they ever exist in Nigeria. Incidentally, entrepreneurship is better appreciated in practical experience than in being theoretical. It is important, therefore, that the knowledge gathered in theory be backed by real life practical experiences in laboratories, workshops and business incubation sites, Okhakhu, and Adekunle, (2012).

Challenges Facing Entrepreneurship Education in Teaching and Learning in Nigerian Schools

Okoro (2014) have identified that there are both technological and pedagogical challenges with entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria. Gidado and Akaeze (2014) describe the lack of teaching and learning equipment, such as computer accessories, internet facilities, and other technological resources to assist learners as major problems that face Business Education in Nigerian secondary schools. Therefore, for education properly serve as the motor for socio-economic growth and development, as well as for the actualization of entrepreneurship educational objectives in Nigeria, it is of paramount importance that secondary education and its systems function optimally in relation to its set standards of teaching and learning of Entrepreneurship Education (Ogundile, Bishop, Okagbue, Ogunniyi, & Olanrewaju, 2019; Akaeze, 2014). The authors stated that the issue of lack of technological

Qualitative Study on...(Bello, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609049>

teaching aids has generated an on-going argument which many has a link to the reason learners are not doing well as expected in their education.

Olutola and Olatoye, (2015) further stated that some secondary schools in Nigeria, equipment such as computers, projectors, software and internet are not available for proper utilization. New technologies in teaching and learning posed many challenges to the teaching and learning of entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria (Achugbue, 2011). Nigerian secondary schools would achieve the goals of Entrepreneurship Education if necessary modern technological teaching aids like computers, electric typewriters, projectors, internet facilities, among others, are adequately provided and used. Achugbue (2011), the reason many schools in Nigeria are lacking modern technological teaching aids, is that they do not give adequate priority and attention to the acquisition and utilization of new instructional technologies. As a result, the lack of such necessary facilities makes it difficult to teach and prepare Business Education students for the use of new technologies now and in the future world of work. The non-availability of needed materials resources for teaching and learning of Business Education has led to a lack of interest and motivation to study Business Education in Nigeria by many Olutola, and Olatoye,(2015).

Equally, pedagogical challenges have also been identified by Sithole and Lumadi (2012) as another issue in Business Education subjects. Furthermore, Omo-Ojugo and Ohiwerei (2018) reported inadequate textbooks, workbooks as well as the inaccessibility of digital technology and the internet to business educators to facilitate their teaching. The use of obsolete technologies is among the impediment of Business Education studies in Nigerian secondary schools. For example, manual typewriters are still largely in use and some available modern technologies are grossly inadequate Ugwuogo,(2013). Also, there is an under-utilization of computers, printers, other resources, and networking, and this might have resulted from the lack of skills to operate them Ugwuogo, (2013). Lack of training for the teachers and students to use the equipment has been identified as among the challenges that face Business Education in Nigeria.

According to Olutola and Olatoye (2015), the introduction of new technologies in the education system and the rapid nature of its expansion seem to overwhelm curriculum planners and other stakeholders in Nigerian secondary education. To ensure that Education is able to deal with global, technological and market changes, it is imperative to encourage Business Education teachers to adopt up-to-date interactive and participative teaching methodologies that are not only up-to-date but also internationally competitive (Nawaz & Gomes, 2014). Hence, as an important area of education in Nigerian, the goals of Business Education will be better achieved when combining its teaching and learning with technology. This is essential due to the present demand of today's office work. Therefore, the next section will look at technology policy in Nigeria.

Impact of Entrepreneurship in Developing Economy

There is no consensus on what classifies a developing country; however, a developing country can be described as a country that has not met its full potential with regards to technology, education, economy, security, Fialho and Van Bergeijk, (2017). Usually characterized with poverty, a developing country cannot meet the primary needs of its population. As such a developing economy is an economy that is experiencing low levels of productivity, low income per capita, poor levels of technological advancement, poor infrastructures, low levels of life expectancy and insufficient health services, Inegbenebor and Igbelowan, (2010). These economies have challenges satisfactorily meeting the social, economic as well as other basic requirement of its population. Scholars have continued to highlight the important of entrepreneurship on the economy due to the process of entrepreneurship which involves the planning, operating and assumption of the risk of business venture that has implication on the surrounding such as:

1. Revenue Generation: scholars opine that the existence of entrepreneur in an economy will bring an increase in taxation that enables the government save, earn revenue as well provide basic Amenities for the populace.
2. Improvement in productivity through innovation: Analysts have defined innovation as a process where an entrepreneur converts available opportunities and ideas into solutions that are marketable and essential in improving production. Innovation remains an essential feature of entrepreneurship, Hassan, (2013). This is because through entrepreneurial efforts productivity in increased and it can contribute in moving Nigeria from its present state of being a consumption country to a production country.

Qualitative Study on...(Bello, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609049>

3. Facilitation of technological transfer and adaptation: Prospects for developing and employing suitable technological approaches are given by entrepreneurs. This facilitates the absorption of all kinds of workers regardless of the fact that they are skilled, semi-skilled and unskilled Osano, and Koine, (2016).
4. Increase the utilization of resources: In most developing countries as a result of entrepreneurs certain resources that have been left to waste are harnessed by them for the purpose of production and profit. As such, entrepreneurs contribute in improving the domestic savings as well as the utilization of local resources, Ogedengbe et al., (2013).
5. Stimulation of growth: Due to the activities of entrepreneurs in large and small scale enterprises it encourages the diversification and sustenance of the economy. This diversification leads to the stimulation of economic growth while adjusting itself in dynamic nature of the global economy through the efficient and effective employment of raw materials and workforce, Hassan, (2013).

Problems of Entrepreneurship Education.

1. Absence of Mentorship: There is need to introduce a mentorship programme into the Training activities, so that young entrepreneurs can learn from successful businessmen.
2. Institutionalizing Business Training in skills acquisition programmes: Business training should be a core part of all vocational and skills acquisition programmes since most of the Graduate of these programmes are expected to end up in self-employment.
3. Short duration of Programmes: Most of the programmes are short of duration ranging from one week programmes to a few weeks or months. There should be enough time to incorporate practical elements.
4. Inadequate funding and capacity: Considering the magnitude of the youth employment Problem in Nigeria, and the number of potential beneficiaries there is need for increased Fundings in order to reach a larger number of youth annually.
5. Poor technology of the three key agencies, only the website of SMEDAN was functioning, and even the one has to register as a member to access information and this is a very different exercise.

Role of Entrepreneurship in the Economic Development of the Country.

1. Economic and Support Facilities Linkages: No business exists alone without contacting other organizations or enterprises for one thing or other. The various sectors of the economy seem to be interrelated in the areas of production, distribution and preservation. Entrepreneurs or business organizations provide the needed local manpower, technical knowledge and services needed to operate and maintain facilities for constant production.
2. Rural Saving Mobilization: the establishment of community banks is a policy to help to mobilize rural savings for economic uses. These savings help to boost economic activities in rural areas.
3. Utilization of Local Resources and Raw Materials: The establishment of small business has helped to mop up the local agricultural products because these enterprises make use of the products for local manufacturing and this help to check waste.
4. Generation of Employment Opportunities: All the small and medium scale business generates more employment opportunities than most big enterprises. Many people depend on their business for their employment and may employ others to assist them.
5. Stimulation of Indigenous Entrepreneurship Development: the experience and skill gained in small business help in the operation and management of big business.

Conclusion

Development through entrepreneurship has become the focus of all the nations around the world. This is better appreciated by the less-developed and developing countries of Africa, Asia and South America which need urgent transition to developed economy. However, economic development through entrepreneurship can well be sustained with a focus and investment in entrepreneurship education. It has become clear that entrepreneurship can be taught and learned. Business educators and professionals have evolved beyond the myth that 'entrepreneurs are born, not made.' Certainly, the future belongs to the nations who are willing to pay the required sacrifice today and for us in Nigeria, there is no better time to do this than now if the economic fortune of generations to come will not be further jeopardized! The identified challenges of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria could be ameliorated with real

Qualitative Study on...(Bello, et. al, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609049>

commitment by all concerned government, educational institutions, students, and other agencies. It is hoped that, given this shared responsibility, entrepreneurship will take its place and be used as the viable vehicle for Nigerian economic growth and development.

Recommendations.

1. Stakeholders should to recommit themselves towards development of entrepreneurship through the provision of adequate resources for teaching as well as well-equipped empowerment development centers
2. Development through entrepreneurship should become the focus of all the nations.
3. Economic development should be through entrepreneurship with focus on investment in entrepreneurship education.
4. Business educators and professionals should evolved beyond the myth that ‘entrepreneurs are born, not made.
5. Entrepreneurship should take its place and be used as the viable vehicle for Nigerian economic growth and development.
6. There is need for increased Funding in order to reach a larger number of youth annually.

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Mathematics as the Bedrock...(Aliyu, J., et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609049>

Mathematics as the Bedrock of Artificial Intelligence and Creative Thinking for National Development in Nigeria: A Systematic Review

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been more common since the mid-1950s, and this has made it possible to create intelligent systems for instruction and training. This review outline AI's potential in improving teaching and learning of mathematics across all education levels, using a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) from the established robust guidelines. The findings reveal the intervention impact of AI in mathematics education and creative thinking through Chatbots; Generative Pre-Trained Transformer Language Models (ChatGPT), adaptive learning, automation, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), student interest, and dialogue learning. We follow the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA). We searched Scopus, Science Direct, Springer Link, ProQuest, IEEE XPLORE, Google Scholar, Web of Science, and Taylor & Francis Online. AI studies published between 2022 and 2024. The findings of the SLR indicate that the AI approach used in mathematics education for the samples studied was through technological tools, robotics, a comprehensive approach, and teachable agent. Following a quality assessment screening of the papers and additional removal of duplicates from the study, 10 publications out of 30 papers satisfied the inclusion/exclusion and refining criteria. The analysis revealed that most of the studies used quantitative and mixed methods with few from the primary level. The authors recommend that AI should be used to tailor up the needs and interest of students in the teaching and learning of mathematics education courses like Education Mathematics Education: Senior Secondary School Mathematics Content (EDME 303), demonstrative construction and intelligence to burst creativity in learning mathematics, and more research using a qualitative approach among others.

Keyword: Mathematics education; Artificial intelligence; Creative thinking; National development; Systematic literature review

Introduction

Mathematics is generally believed to be a fundamental subject because of its arithmetic and logical reasoning which are the basis of science and technology. Mathematics is essential in various fields like business, economics, academia, engineering, and industry, facilitating logical communication, understanding societal intricacies, and promoting lifelong learning (Usman, 2019). Aliyu (2019) stressed that mathematics deals with amounts, sizes, and shapes that may be expressed as numbers and signs. It is a tool whose comprehension and application constitute the cornerstone of any change in society and the translation of ideas into reality. Also, If we learn mathematics, there are several beneficial effects on our minds, fosters analytical thinking, develops reasoning, produces practicality, and may be used in day-to-day tasks (Aliyu, 2019). Furthermore, Mathematics is essential for science, technology, and national development, and its working knowledge is required for

Mathematics as the Bedrock...(Aliyu, J., et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609049>

completion of modern educational institutions' courses (Aliyu, Osman, Daud, & Kumar, 2021). Kevin (2022) argued that mathematics is a unified subject that prepares students for a meaningful life and serves as the language for daily pursuits in science and technology.

Zulhilmi et al (2024) maintains that artificial intelligence (AI) applications in education are becoming more popular and have gotten a lot of press in recent years. AI is a leap across creative and innovative thinking in various fields, including mathematics education. The current study indicates various research of AI in different context (Zulhilmi et, al. 2024). Falebita (2024) argued that artificial intelligence (AI) is transforming classroom teaching activities, offering the potential to revolutionize the entire educational process, from lesson planning to delivery and student evaluation. AI encompasses the capabilities of machines to adapt to novel and evolving circumstances, solve problems, respond to queries, devise strategies, and carry out other intellectual behaviours typically associated with humans (Falebita, 2024). Also, Opesemowo & Ndlovu (2024) argued that AI has emerged as a transformative force in various fields, including education. In the field of mathematics education, AI technologies offer a spectrum of potential benefits (such as personalised tutoring, adaptive evaluation, collaborative learning atmospheres, and real-time feedback, among others) and encounters (such as absence of inventiveness and problem-solving skills, incapability to explain thinking concerns, preconception in data and procedures, deficiency of demonstrative intelligence (Opesemowo & Ndlovu, 2024).

Mulyanto et al (2018) stressed that critical thinking as the ability to evaluate different information obtained from various sources, process it creatively and logically, and analyse it to draw the appropriate conclusions. It also refers to the process of thinking to clarify one's understanding of something in order to make an intelligent decision (Mulyanto et al., 2018). Bora (2020) stressed that critical thinking is the embodiment of “higher order thinking”. This is because the capacity to think is the highest cognitive competence that learners need to ace in the class. Critical thinking may be viewed as the capacity to think of students to compare two or more information, for example information received from outside with information held. If there are differences or similarities, then he will ask questions or comments in order to get an explanation. Critical thinking is often associated with creative thinking (Bora, 2020). Voskoglou and Salem (2020) argued that critical thinking is a crossbreed of other approaches of thinking encompassing productive, demonstrating, coherent, algorithmic and nonrepresentational.

Education is a potent instrument for social change and advancing a country. Understanding national development is crucial for teacher preparation and national development initiatives in Nigeria. Teacher retraining programs and sufficient resources are needed to improve educational production and solidify the Nigerian educational system. Adedeji (2018) argued that a particular current professional growth for working teachers is in-service training which includes, seminars, conferences, and workshops. Superior mathematics instruction software is expected to enhance student academic performance and national growth (Adedeji, 2018).

Objectives of the Review

The goals of the review are to chart out the current state of knowledge regarding artificial intelligence and creative thinking in mathematics education. Precisely, the review sought to:

1. Provide a clear, well-defined previous research outcome in mathematics education that utilize artificial intelligence and create thinking.
2. Provide a brief description of the review studies in mathematics education with artificial intelligence and create thinking based on nations, research type, and techniques used in reporting the systematic literature review.

Research Questions

The main research questions to be answered are

1. What are the prior research findings in mathematics education that cartel creative thinking and artificial intelligence?
2. What are the certified review studies in mathematics education with artificial intelligence and create thinking based on countries, journals type and procedures used in reporting the systematic literature review?

Mathematics as the Bedrock...(Aliyu, J., et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609049>

Methodology

Nurul Shida (2019) argued that there are five stages to systematic literature review (SLR) method, which are search, identification, screening, eligibility and inclusion. The word AND was used in the search string to add a wide range of findings and to expand the search into a specific study of critical thinking. Consequently, in the current research, a modified PRISMA statement template is used for the methodological procedure to gather, examine, and produce all the related information in the earlier studies to offer the state of the research. Thus, the PRISMA information facilitates the investigator to enrich the coverage of the assessment paper and build on the indicated purposes of the research finding (Khan and Qureshi, 2020). Aliyu et al (2021) stressed that SLR is a process of developing a clear question that utilised logical and specific approaches towards classifying, selecting and crucially assessing or calculating significant investigation, and of collecting and examining the information from the findings for the review. SLR tries to classify, evaluate, and create realistic support that convenes pre-stipulated appropriateness measures to resolve a provided investigation issue. A meta-evaluation is a statistical review of the information presented from several sources or findings that seeks to enquire or respond to the identical problem (Aliyu et, al. 2021). Figure 1 below shows the literature inclusion and exclusion at every phase:

Figure 1: A summary of literature exclusion and inclusion

Search Strategies

For this systematic search, a search strategy was developed to identify relevant literature: Artificial intelligence and creative thinking in Mathematics Education. These search strategies used five databases: IEEE XPLORE, Science Direct or Elsevier, Scopus, Springer Link, and Taylor & Francis Online. In addition, tools such as Google Scholar and Web of Science were used in the belief that they are the leading databases that comprise bibliographic documents with full-text publishing structures in a variety of disciplines and, specifically for educational multidisciplinary research. All searches spanned from databases 01-12--2022 until 10-08-2024 and included conferences, journals, and reviews and published in English only.

Selection Criteria

The primary goal of the search was to map the body of knowledge on artificial intelligence (AI) in mathematics and creative thinking in the social sciences and natural science and computer science fields. After that, the test was limited to the subject portions, which included nearly 40 papers in the social sciences, mathematics, natural sciences and computer sciences. The investigation ran from 2022 to 2024. Every article published before 2022 was not included in the analysis. The investigation focused on every country in the world. 30 research publications in total were thus eliminated at this point. At this point, 30 records have been extracted.

Quality Assessment

The research is centered on new investigation articles and conference documents. For upholding the integrity of the review, all duplicates were verified comprehensively. The abstracts of the articles were checked meticulously for the evaluation and purification of the articles to certify the excellence and significance of educational information contained in the analysis procedure. A thorough assessment of all inquiry articles was held at a subsequent phase. The following rejection measure was

Mathematics as the Bedrock...(Aliyu, J., et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609049>

to regulate the documents published in the English language only. There were 2 in other languages and these have been eliminated from the research. Also, refinement of 10 papers was done and these were excluded. Furthermore, after the filtration of duplicate records, 10 more articles were removed from the study. A total of 10 articles were selected after assessing each article on the inclusion and extraction criteria.

Data Extraction

The findings have been limited to conferences, journal articles and review papers from 2022 until 2024 and are accessible in the English Language. A total of 30 papers were found while conducting the review. The keywords related to AI AND mathematics education and also AI AND creative thinking are used for the extraction of the findings. These papers were examined to detect the objectives of the study. Bora (2020) is of the view that researchers, educational gaming systems develop students' practical skills to convey and reinforce knowledge, create a virtual environment, and leverage multi-media interaction. Also, Using one's emotion to generate new ideas from a collection of memories that comprise a variety of ideas, facts, concepts, experiences, and information is known as creative thinking (Bora, 2020). These interactive technologies allow for the creation of enriching training experiences that enhance the learning process and assist students with their academic assignments (Robles & Quintero 2020). However, (Van Vaerenbergh & Pérez-Suay (2022) stressed the needed to make a number of improvements in the mathematical formalization of disciplines like computation, probability theory, and logic before AI could be considered a formal science. With an emphasis on educators and students, the study explores stakeholders' perspectives on ChatGPT's application in mathematics education. It makes recommendations for safe implementation and accountability areas as well as calls for more research (Wardat et al., 2023). The writers then summarized the content into a table for the stage of informing the review. Ten papers were found to be reviewed in depth and results and discussion is presented below:

Results and Discussion

Mostly, in the ten papers evaluated, most of the study were conducted at either secondary/high/college or universities schools with few at primary/elementary school level.

Mathematics as the Bedrock...(Aliyu, J., et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609049>

Table 1: Study of artificial intelligence mathematics education and creative thinking

Citation	AI Mathematics education & CT	Result
(Nguyen et al., 2023)	Artificial Intelligence in education (IED) · Ethics · Policies · Privacy	This paper discovers if there exist a global consensus on AIED by international organizations' policies and guidelines.
(Wardat et al., 2023)	AI, language, text generation, chatbots, mathematics, ChatGPT.	The study looked into how mathematics teachers in Abu Dhabi Emirate Schools, felt about AI systems and its applications.
(Dabingaya, 2022)	Adaptive Learning, AI-Powered Platforms, mathematics education.	The study evaluated pre- and post-assessment and engagement among students.
(Moral-sánchez et al., 2023)	Teaching; learning AI; ICT; mathematics education; Chatbots;	The study focused on the use of chatbots for the didactic geometry course program at the University of Malaga's.
(Gouia-zarrad, 2024)	Education, learning & teaching ChatGPT, AI, technology.	The integration of ChatGPT as a tool for learning differential equations course at the university level.
(Hwang, 2022)	AI, PRISMA, robotics, SLR mathematics education.	The study investigates the impact of AI and the mathematical achievement of elementary pupils.
(Pavlova, 2024)	AI, ChatGPT, dialogue, CI	ChatGPT was used to encourage student participation in the dialogic teaching approach.
(Zafrullah et al., 2023)	Interest in Learning, AI, ChatGPT.	The study uses a non- instrument with 5 categories on students at one of the Indonesia universities.
Opesemowo & Ndlovu, 2024)	AI; Big data; ChatGPT; Machine learning; mathematics education	The primary AI tool utilized in mathematics teaching, according to the results, was ChatGPT.
(Pont-Niclòs et al., 2024)	AI, creativity, prospective teachers, storytelling	The project explores the creative potential of elementary teachers using AI-generated tools for storytelling.

Tables 1 above demonstrate the entire scenarios based on citations, instrument used, and the outcome of the research related to AI and mathematics education and creative thinking CT. Similarly, the names of authors and year of publication, research nations, published journal names, and methodology employed in the findings are all displayed in table 2 below.

Mathematics as the Bedrock...(Aliyu, J., et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609049>

Table 2: An outline of the 10 reviewed studies

Researcher& year	Country	Research type	Method
(Nguyen et al., 2023)	Finland	Education and Information Technologies.	Quantitative
(Wardat et al., 2023)	Abu Dhabi, UAE	Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education.	Quantitative
(Dabingaya, 2022)	New Papua Guinea	Interdisciplinary Journal Papier Human Review.	Quantitative
(Moral-sánchez et al., 2023)	Spain	International Journal of Educational Research and Innovation.	Quantitative
(Gouia-zarrad, 2024)	Tunisia	International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education.	Mixed method
(Hwang, 2022)	Korea	Sustainability.	Mixed method
(Pavlova, 2024)	Bulgaria	International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education.	Qualitative
(Zafrullah et al., 2023)	Indonesia	Journal of Technology Global.	Quantitative
(Opesemowo & Ndlovu, 2024)	South Africa	Journal of Pedagogical Research.	Quantitative
(Pont-Niclòs et al., 2024)	Spain	Digital Education Review.	Mixed method

Limitations

The nominated investigations cover an array of nations. Thus, in this research, there are a limited number of research studies across the globe with only two researchers from Africa. All the journals used in the above table are restricted within mathematics education students learning interest and from recognised bibliographic databases. Consequently, the articles within the review identified and reported information on the aspects of documents by citation, by year, and subject area. The Figure below summarised the scenario by country/territory:

Mathematics as the Bedrock...(Aliyu, J., et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609049>

Figure 2: Documents by country and territory information.

The Bulgarian, China endured the most studied distinct countries and in one database South Africa met the inclusion criteria. Thus, there were no findings that coincided with the inclusion provisions from Africa according to some data bases used. Figure below indicates documents by citations source per year.

Figure 3: Documents per year by source information

More ever, documents by year indicate 2022 two records, 2023 only 1, 2024 three documents. This information reveals that there are generally few writers per year in this field of studies.

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Figure 4: Documents by subject area information

Mathematics has only 42.08% while social sciences had 26.27% also natural science has 11.48% while computer science with 20.17%. This indicates the need for more article writers in the field of mathematics and others fields of studies as illustrated above.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Creative Thinking (CT) aids educators through personalized learning experiences, task automation, real-time feedback, professional development facilitation, improved teaching strategies, and classroom diversity. It empowers educators to create engaging, individualized learning experiences, fostering creativity, effective communication, and increased student commitment, leading to better academic success. The bias in AI can degrade the learning experience that students enjoy from their teachers and result in an excessive amount of time and effort spent adapting the AI tools.

Conclusion

This review aimed to evaluate the AI through mathematics education. A revised PRISMA framework (selection criteria, search strategies, data extraction, and quality assessment) was used to establish the whole scenario in the literature review, and 10 out of 30 documents met the conditions. Data abstraction was controlled to conferences, journals, and review papers in English language only from prior studies. Outcomes of the discussion related to AI in mathematics education showed a constructive result. The summary of the studied articles demonstrated rationalization of the research procedure assessment discoveries. Thus, some limitations, objectives of the review, and future direction were deliberated. Moreover, most of the writers focus on universities. Hence, documents by country, citations, subject area, and by year indicate areas of weakness and that there are limited researches on those areas of study.

Future Recommendations

The current systematic review reveals that the research studies conducted in the area of Artificial Intelligence AI and mathematics education focus on task automation, access to learning, AI in examinations, AI in gamification, smart content, assistance via chat boats, learning gaps and aiding in teacher-student communication information's across educational institutions. Consequently, the paper recommends that

1. Attention to other learning areas such as emotional intelligence that could comprehend and respond to mathematics students and emotional connection to burst creativity and appreciation from the learners are important.
2. The use of alternative for AI could develop intelligence systems that combine human and machine system of leaning.

Mathematics as the Bedrock...(Aliyu, J., et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609049>

3. Adapt the teaching and learning of mathematics education courses such as EDME 303 to the specific content-based needs of the pupils.

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Assessment of Sex-For-Grade on Attitude of Students in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Sex-for-Grade has been seen as a corrupt practice bedeviling the nation's educational system. This study was purposed to assess sex-for-grade on the attitude of students in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive research design upon a sample of 310 students in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi, Nigeria. The study used multi-stage sampling techniques to select sample for the study. A self-designed instrument was used to elicit data from respondents. The study used pie-chart, mean and standard deviation to present and analyze data. The null hypothesis was tested at .05 level of significance. Results showed that 49% of students had experienced sexual harassment in higher institutions in one form or the other. Another finding was that verbal sexual harassment was 76% extent of occurrence which makes it most frequently occurring form of sex-for-grade in higher institutions. The study discovered that *p value* of .050 for a 2-tailed test was greater than the chosen alpha of .05. Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between male and female students' attitudes and perception toward sex-for-grade was gender unbiased. The study concludes that sex-for-grade is a frequently increasing act in tertiary institutions and the attitudes and perception of students towards sex-for-grade is non-directional. Among other recommendations, the study recommends that government should through the relevant agencies such as Ministry of Education, Accreditation Boards/Councils and Tertiary Institutions to ensure the establishment of effective guidance and counselling centers in all tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Keyword: sex-for-grade, sexual harassment, attitude, perception, and students.

Introduction

Academic success is a fundamental goal for all tertiary institutions in Nigeria. However, the educational institutions in Nigeria have been subjected to criticism as people began to doubt the quality of graduates and their certificates upon graduation. It is no longer news for the uncontrollable occurrences of malpractice ranging from resorting of lecturers or examination officers to cheating in examination halls with different technological gadgets, most worrisomely in this era of Artificial Intelligence. As this episode is yet to be abated, malpractice has taken another amoebic form known as sex-for-grade.

Sex-for-grade is an act whereby members of the academia (students, teaching and non-teaching staff) exchange favours for good grades. In this study sex-for-grade is interchangeably used with sexual harassment. Sexual harassment is an unwelcome sexual advance, request for sexual favours either verbal or physical conduct of sexual nature (Aluede, 2000). Sex-for-grade is a silent disease that is seriously eroding academic excellence in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. It is often perceived as a behaviour that is unwelcome (the recipient does not want it) unsolicited (recipient did not ask for it) and repeated. Aluede (2000) opined that the behaviour could be considered sexual harassment when: (i) Submission to such act is explicitly or implicitly a term or condition for an individual's employment or participating in educational programs. (ii) Submission to, or rejection of such conduct by an individual is used as a basis for employment or academic decisions affecting the individual. (iii) When such conduct has the purpose or effect of unreasonably interfering with an employee's work performance or student's academic performance, creating an intimidating hostile or offensive working or learning environment.

For udechukwu et al. (2020), sexual harassment is an unsolicited and unreciprocated sexual behaviour from a person to elicit unwanted sexual relations from another person. The definition identifies the various behaviours that may constitute sexual harassment in a work environment. The first two provisions deal with unequal power relations between the employer/supervisor and employee/subordinate. An employer or a supervisor demands sexual gratification from the employee or subordinate in return for job benefits. In the academic environment, a parallel situation could be argued to arise when faculty members proposed to female students for sexual favours in return for favourable examination results.

The third provision refers to the existence of hostile work environment where offending behaviour interferes with satisfactory work performance of an employee. Tertiary institutions in Nigeria have been bedeviled with obscene dressing, secrete cult activities and drug abuse to mention a few. Most female students almost go naked display their navels and boobs and wearing what are just ample cleavages on display depicting size and shape of the private parts with minis that barely cover their bottom (Queensoap, 2024).

Queensoap (2024) further reveals that respondents' perception regarding social factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria was very high. The previous study affirms a population mean and standard deviation of 4.13 ± 1.14 with a mean percentage of 83%. The social factors investigated and adjudged high were mode of dressing (4.42 ± 1.16 with 88%); visiting of lecturers' offices at odd hours ($4.62 \pm .92$ with 92%); cultural influence (3.33 ± 1.23 with 67%); social media (3.81 ± 1.24 with 78%) and lecturers' unguided relationship with students (4.53 ± 1.01 with 91%). These actual values implies that there are social factors that can promote sex-for-grade in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The previous study concludes that both students and lecturers affirm similarly the observed socio-political factors as influencers of sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria (Queensoap, 2024). It is obvious that students agreeing that their dressing pattern can promote sex-for-grade, yet they still dress almost naked on campus and in classrooms. What should be their attitude and perception towards sex-for-grade? Attitude is an individual's predisposition to respond in a characteristic's way to some features of the social environment (Ogbebor & Egbule, 2006). According to Stamovlasis et al. (2023), the most prevailing types of sexually harassing behaviors, which were experienced mainly by women students, included offensive sexual comments/jokes/stories, inappropriate comments about one's body/appearance/sex life, as well as obscene ways of staring, obscene gestures, and/or exposure of body parts causing embarrassment.

In a similar study, the authors suggest that majority (81%) of the participants responded that sexual harassment is related to all unwelcome sexual behaviour, 72% of the participants feel most afraid of sexual harassment during night, and 83% of the participants responded that the most probable place for sexual harassment is public transport and 91% of the participants believed that the incidences of the sexual harassment have increased in the last 10 years (Pandey, et al., 2021).

The study posited that the definition of sexual harassment can differ according to individual's perception. To understand how people perceive and define sexual harassment is crucial for explaining and understanding how they react to sexual harassment and why they often do not stand up against sexual harassment (Pandey, et al., 2021). This denotes that students' attitude and perception towards sex-for-grade is required to ascertain the occurrences of sex-for-grade in tertiary institutions. It is also possible to establish the peculiarity of students' attitudes and perceptions, that is, how they react to sex-for-grade in a particular tertiary institution to corroborate with existing studies. This becomes necessary due to the trend at which sex-for-grade had spread in tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

The increasing rate of sex-for-grade in Nigerian institutions of higher learning is a problem of considerable magnitude. It is an ethical and a human right issue that has implications not only for the quality and integrity of the educational system, but also for the physical, mental and social wellbeing of its victims. It is an issue that should be taken seriously due to the gravity of the physical, psychological, academic, social and legal implications it may portends (Oweifabo & Queensoap, 2024).

According to Queensoap (2024), sex-for-grade has become a hydra headed problem that has attracted concern from stakeholders of educational institutions especially the higher institutions in the country. This implies that sex-for-grade is the new enemy of accademic prowess which is capable in lowering standard of education if not addressed. In another study, it was observed that sex-for-grade as a social and academic problem is not limited to Nigeria. It is a global matter that needs urgent attention (Smart, 2023).

Abdussalam (2020) posited that year after year there have been allegations of sexual harassment by lecturers in these institutions, especially in Federal Universities. Abdussalam further explained that students in these universities usually resort to social media to complain about their experiences of sexual harassment by their lecturers and when asked to report the incidences, they say that the school does not do anything, saying that those lecturers have families to feed and cater for and losing their job could be disastrous for them.

Again, another source stated that in recent times stories have been flying around concerning the situation of things in Nigerian universities especially cases of sexual harassment of females students by male lecturers. The society as well, has been condemning very seriously male lecturers who harass female students or even demand sex to enable these to pass their course (Omonigho, 2019). This trend is amazing and disturbing in an environment that is often believed to be a center of excellence, be a molding and filtering ground for building virile leaders and intellectuals that will mount the stage of leadership of the country tomorrow. Consequently, How do students react to the act of sex-for-grade? How do they perceive the act of sex-for-grade?, are questions that beg for answers. This study was to assess the attitude and perception of students toward sex-for-grade in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi, Ogbia-Town.

Objectives of Study

The purpose of this study was to assess sex-for-grade on attitude of students in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study was to:

1. Determine rate of sex-for-grade occurrence in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi
2. Assess students' attitudes towards sex-for-grade in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi.
3. Determine students' perception of sex-for-grade in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi.

Research Questions

The researcher posed the following research questions to guide the study:

1. To what extent do sex-for-grade occur in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi?
2. What are the attitudes of students toward sex-for-grade in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi?
3. How do students perceive sex-for-grade in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi?

Hypothesis

The study tested the following null hypothesis at .05 error of probability:

H_{01} : There is no significant difference between male and female students' attitudes and perceptions toward sex-for-grade in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi

Methodology

This current study adopted a descriptive survey research design. This design was suitable for the study because it enabled the researcher to collect, summarize and describe variables at their natural setting. This involves the use of a study instrument to obtain data without manipulating the independent variables (students' attitude and perceptions). The study's population consisted of students of Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi. The students' population was 1373 which excludes year one students who had not written examinations at the time of the conduct of the study. A sample size of 310 was determined by using Taro Yamen's formula. The researchers employed stratified random sampling technique and simple random sampling technique. A self-designed research instrument was used to obtain data. The instrument was validated using face and content validity methods. The study instrument was determined reliable through Cronbach Alpha which gave a reliability coefficient of .78 which was high enough to consider the instrument reliable. Charts, mean and standard deviations were used for the analysis of data while independent t-test was used to test the null hypothesis at .05 alpha level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Distribution of Respondents' Sexual Harassment Experiences

A look at figure 1 shows that 49% of the respondents had experienced sexual harassment in one form or the other, 47% of the respondents had not experienced sexual harassment while on 4% of the respondents indicated undecided. This denotes that majority of students in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi had experienced sexual harassment in one form or the other.

Figure 1: A Pie Chart Showing Response Level of Students on Sex-for-Grade Experiences in BYCOHTECH

Research Question 1

To what extent do sex-for-grade occur in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi?

Table 1: Summary of Descriptive Statistics for Extent of Sex-for-Grade Occurrences in BYCOHTECH

Statements	N	Mean	Std	Mean %	Criterion mean	Decision
Physical sexual harassment	310	2.91	1.07	73	2.5	Accepted
Verbal sexual harassment	310	3.05	.97	76		Accepted
Non-verbal sexual harassment	310	2.72	.93	68		Accepted
Quid pro quo sexual harassment	310	2.95	.79	74		Accepted
Grand mean/std	310	2.91	.94	73		Accepted

Source: Field work

Table 1 shows extent of sex-for-grade experiences in BYCOHTECH. It was observed that physical sexual harassment (unwanted touch, unwanted kissing) has a mean and standard deviation of 2.91 ± 1.07 with mean percentage of 73 extent of occurrence. For verbal sexual harassment (use of threatening words) has a mean/standard deviation of $3.05 \pm .97$ with mean percentage of 76 extent of occurrence while non-verbal sexual harassment (writing of love letters, text messages, WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger & Telegram) has a mean/standard deviation of $2.72 \pm .93$ with mean percentage of 68. For the quid pro quo sexual harassment, students' response mean/standard deviation was $2.95 \pm .79$ with mean percentage of 74 extent of occurrence. These sample mean values suggest that there was high extent of sex-for-grade occurrence in BYCOHTECH. Table 1 revealed a population mean of $2.91 \pm .94$ with mean percentage of 73 rate of sex-for-grade occurrences. Since, calculated mean was greater than the critical mean (2.5), the rate of sex-for-grade occurrence off and in school was high in BYCOHTECH.

Research Question 2

What are the attitudes of students toward sex-for-grade in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi?

Table 2: Summary of Descriptive Statistics for students' attitude toward sex-for-grade

Statements	N	Mean	Std	Mean %	Criterion mean	Decision
Sex-for-grade is part of fun in higher institutions	310	3.25	1.47	65	3.0	Accepted
Sex-for-grade should not be encouraged	310	3.44	1.50	69		Accepted
Sex-for-grade should not be seen as a crime when students involve themselves	310	3.50	1.31	70		Accepted
Sex-for-grade helps promote students' academic success	310	2.56	1.32	51		Rejected
Sex-for-grade is a corrupt practice done by lecturers	310	4.38	.78	88		Accepted
Lecturers involved in sex-for-grade should be punished	310	4.34	1.00	87		Accepted
Grand mean/std	310	3.58	1.23	72		Accepted

Source: field work

Table 2 shows mean/standard deviation of students' attitudes towards sex-for-grade as 3.23±1.47, 3.50±1.31, 4.38±.78, and 4.34±1.00. These results were greater than the criterion mean of 3.0 hence it indicates that respondents accepted that sex-for-grade was part of fun, it should be encouraged, it should not be seen as a crime, it is usually perpetrated by lecturers and thus such lecturers should be punished in higher institutions however respondents reject the predisposition to accept that sex-for-grade helps to promote students' academic success because respondents' mean/standard deviation was 2.56±1.32 which was less than the criterion mean of 3.0. It was also observed that the grand mean/standard deviation was 3.58±1.23 with a mean percentage of 72% indicating a high level of predisposition towards sex-for-grade.

Research Question 3

How do students' perceived sex-for-grade in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi?

Table 3: Summary of Descriptive Statistics for Students' Perception toward Sex-for-grade

Statements	N	Mean	Std	Mean %	Criterion mean	Decision
Sex-for-grade lowers students' self-esteem	310	4.29	.97	86	3.0	Accepted
Sex-for-grade occurrence is very rare in higher institutions	310	3.55	1.32	71		Accepted
The dressing manner of students contributes to sex-for-grade occurrence on in higher institutions	310	4.16	.91	83		Accepted
Students who never pay attention are vulnerable to sex-for-grade	310	3.87	.99	77		Accepted
Students who are truants are susceptible to sex-for-grade act.	310	3.74	.88	75		Accepted
Grand mean/std	310	3.02	1.01	78		Accepted

Table 3 shows respondents' perception towards sex-for-grade in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi. Results shows that sex-for-grade lowers students' self-esteem was 4.29±0.97 mean and standard deviation with 86% level of perception, sex-for-grade is rare in higher institutions was 3.55±1.32 with 71% level of perception, indecent dressing can stimulate sex-for-grade was 4.16±.91 with 83% level of perception, seeking for sex-for-grade due to poor attention to lecturers 3.87±.99 with 77% level of perception while students' who do not attend classes regularly are susceptible to seeking undue help was 3.74±.88 with 75% level of perception. Each variables tested showed that students have high level of perception towards sex-for-grade. This was evidenced of the grand mean of 3.92±1.01 with 78% level of perception.

Null Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between male and female students' attitudes and perceptions towards sex-for-grade in BYCOHTECH.

Table 4: Summary of Independent t-test statistics

Independent pairs	N	Mean	STD	DF	T	P value	Confidence interval	Decision
Male	96	40.52	5.08	308	.67	.50	-1.35-2.73	H ₀ accepted
Female	214	39.83	4.59					

Table 4 shows that male has 96 respondents, 40.52±5.08 mean and standard deviation while female with 214 number of respondents has 39.83±4.59 mean and standard deviation. It can be observed from table 5 that for df of 308, *P* value of .50, *t*-ratio of .67, and lower and upper confidence level of -1.35 and 2.73 respectively at 95% certainty. Therefore, *P* value of .50 for a 2-tailed test is greater than the chosen alpha of .05, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between male and female students' attitudes and perception towards sex-for-grade was not rejected, that is, it was accepted. This implies that male and female have similar predisposition towards sex-for-grade occurrences in higher institutions in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

This current study observed that majority of the participants (49%) had experienced one form of sex-for-grade to another. The level of agreement to the extent in which different forms of sex-for-grade occurred was so revealing that physical sexual harassment was high as 73%, verbal sexual harassment was as high as 76%, non-verbal sexual harassment was 68% which was low, and quid pro quo sexual harassment was as high as 74%. The study observed that the population of the study had experienced high occurrences of sex-for-grade in the institution. Abdussalam (2020) supported these findings that sex-for-grades occurred in several dimensions in universities especially in the federal universities however this study was conducted in a State higher institution. It can therefore be deduced that the occurrence of sex-for-grade is not limited to federal universities alone because the study has revealed that Bayelsa State College of Health Technology being a state institution had been observed high rate of sex-for-grade occurrences in different dimensions because students in the College see sex-for-grade as part of academic fun as well as not as a crime. In a situation as such sex-for-grade will be used deliberately by female students to have academic rewards. This has been established in (Oweifabo & Queensoap, 2024) stating that there are student-centered factors that enhance sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria namely drug influence, deliberate use of sex by some female students as weapon for academic reward, indecent dressing, fun, etc.

Again, the study discovered that students have a high predisposition to sex-for-grade. It was observed that students' attitude towards sex-for-grade was not positive but have no option to resist because they are seen as endangered species. Nonetheless, this study observed that respondents accepted sex-for-grade as part of fun. They also agreed that it should not be encouraged as well as not to be seen as a crime, indicating that their disposition to sex-for-grade is a two-way dimension. Meanwhile, in the study of Omonigho (2019), sex-for-grade was adjudged as a corrupt practice thus this finding was inconsistent with the previous findings.

The perception level of students on sex-for-grade is high regards to results of this study. Students perceived that sex-for-grade is rare in higher institution. This finding negates the findings of Abdussalam (2020) and Omonigho (2019) whose works revealed that sex-for-grade is common in higher institutions. It implies that students may know what happens in their institution and not in other institution. This is critical to note that this study identified that 49% of the students attested to the occurrence of sex-for-grade however responded with a mean percentage of 71, perceiving that sex-for-grade is rare in higher institution hence what respondents perceived within their institution is different from how they perceived the same subject in another institution.

Another finding of this study that was in line with the findings of Abdussalam (2020) was that the way and manner females dress on campus can stimulate sex-for-grade as well as students who does not attend to classes regularly are susceptible to seeking undue help. These attitudes of students were very high. This study observed that there was no gender difference of students' attitudes and perception toward sex-for-grade Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi. This denotes that there is no significant difference between male and female attitudes and perceptions toward sex-for-grade. It implied therefore that both male and female have the similar disposition

toward sex-for-grade occurrences in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi. Ayinla and Adesola (2020) acknowledged that sexual scandals as a public relations nightmare in higher institutions are viewed as a single perception of stakeholders which supports the findings of this current study.

Conclusions

Based on the findings discussed, the study concludes that sex-for-grade occurrence in higher institutions in Bayelsa State was rampant. It was generalized that students have both positive and negative attitude towards sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Bayelsa State, implying a non-directional attitude and perception towards sex-for-grade. The study concluded that both male and female students showed similar attitude and perception towards sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Following the conclusion of the study, the researchers recommend that:

1. The National Assembly and State Assemblies with the management of tertiary institutions should legislate laws that aimed at reducing or eliminating the high occurrences of sex-for-grade in higher institutions.
2. Government through the Ministry of Education, Accreditation Boards/Councils/Commissions and the Tertiary Institutions to ensure the provision of effective counselling centers in all tertiary institutions in Nigeria. This would help engage students to work on their attitudes toward sex-for-grade
3. Non-Governmental Organizations should initiate and carry out advocacy campaign, sensitization and enlightenment in collaboration with tertiary institutions at the beginning of an academic session on the ills of sex-for-grade.

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Qualitative Study on Augmented Innovations in Artificial Intelligence Technologies: A Panacea for Sustainable Undergraduate Chemistry Learning Outcome in Nigeria

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is currently one of the most cited areas in Chemistry. AI had inextricably facilitated chemistry pedagogy and linked to sustaining chemistry learning with unprecedented multifunctional capabilities for optimising learning outcomes. The objectives for this theoretical work were towards sustaining the innovations in undergraduate chemistry learning outcomes with AI technologies. The focus was about incorporating AI into chemistry content knowledge representations for undergraduate students. Seven processes of AI were juxtaposed from literature to actualise the objectives in this article vis: AI for personalised and adaptive learning in chemistry; AI for simulation-based learning in chemistry; AI for chemistry problem-solving; AI for transforming assessments and feedbacks in chemistry; AI for automated essay scoring (AES) and assessment in chemistry; AI for multimodal assessment in chemistry; and AI for predictive analytics in chemistry. Thus, few of the trending basic AI-powered pedagogical tools were listed in this essay for sustaining undergraduate chemistry learning outcome. The overview of current knowledge on this topic was achieved through relevant literature, methodologies and gaps in existing related publications. In conclusion, it was established that learning outcome opportunities in AI were raising both excellence and empowerment for undergraduates pursuing chemistry-related careers, and simultaneously holds revolutionary promises to transform chemistry undergraduates' skills, abilities, knowledge and values in their learning. The ultimate beneficiaries in this circumstance would be the generations of chemistry students with AI innovative skills, as they

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possess advantages in gaining competencies, passion, and agency to collectively solve the perceived complex real-world problems with chemistry.

Keywords: AI technologies, Chemistry learning outcomes, pedagogical tools, personalized tutoring, intelligent tutoring system (ITS).

Introduction

In recent times, Artificial intelligence (AI) had witnessed a significant growth in education and learning, and had increasingly been employed for learning purposes (Dai & Ke, 2022). Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a human replacing technology or human assisting technology that thrived in industries, fields of studies, businesses, economic matters, cultural and social affairs, governance, policy making and professional development (Cukurova *et al*, 2019). The emergence of AI also affected and transformed every aspect of people's daily life. According to Baum *et al* (2021), the applications of AI in chemistry were noticeable in the ways by which AI-driven technologies were adopted to life sciences and analytical chemistry, thereby creating paradigm shifts in school learning and possessed promising potentials for understanding future directions in effective school learning experiences. Further, AI enabled amplifying school pedagogical capabilities through personalised tutoring and dynamic assessments strategies with improved and meaningful interactive processes. The open access online learning processes in AI would as well inhibit effective assimilations of basic ideas, which were inherent in various subjects (Zhai, *et al*, 2021). Chemistry as a core science subject would benefit from the academic focuses and impacts of AI on school learning. Brimoh, *et al* (2024), explained that Artificial Intelligence (AI) capabilities had offered social networks and collaborations for chemistry students in problem solving and learning, also provided reflective practices for chemistry teachers, again created pathways to achieving results-oriented chemistry learning. Other opportunities in AI to undergraduate chemistry students included the attainment of optimum pedagogical performances and rapid transformation in the learning of chemistry (Brimoh, *et al*, 2023a).

This article provided theoretical analysis of how Artificial Intelligence (AI) would support learning and assessment of undergraduate chemistry lessons. The authors of this article made further search into literature to explore contemporary research on how the inclusion of AI into undergraduate chemistry curriculum would help in ameliorating the challenges in the pedagogy and learning of undergraduate chemistry (Brimoh, *et al*, 2023b). Perceptively, the researchers focused discussions in this paper on the key areas of AI applications involving personalised tutoring, virtual simulations, problem-solving aids, automated essay scoring, and other AI-powered pedagogical tools – like Gradescope, QuillBot, Education Copilot, quiver.ai, Carnegie Learning, ClassPoint AI, Cognii, Duolingo, Grammarly, SlidesAI, Thinkster Math, Otter.ai, AudioPen, Brainly, merckitwell, Canva, Chatbots labexchange.ai, and many others.

Basically, the readily available AI platforms for undergraduate chemistry learning and assessments included, the adaptive learning platforms (ALP), AI powered educational games, automated grading and feedback systems (AGFS), chatbot for students supports (CSS), and intelligent students tutoring (IST). Other AI innovations in chemistry learning and assessments were: the Quiver.ai – which brings chemistry concepts to life, the Phet.ai – which supports interactive simulation in chemistry, the Merckitwell.ai – which helps in chemistry lesson plans/activities, rubrics, algorithmic assessments and thinking skills, and the Labexchange.ai – which conducts virtual science experiments, collect data, analyse results and provide inferences.

Augmented innovations in AI for chemistry learning and assessments were embedded with data-driven customised or personalised program, which helped with every student's strengths, skills, interests and needs. The AI systems were developed to provide enhanced interactivity, feedback, and experiential digital learning. The technologies facilitate increased engagement, understanding, achievement, and interests in chemistry learning. The transformative effect of integrating "smart" AI technologies is the ability to free up teachers to focus on higher-order thinking with brevity and clarity in students' understanding of concepts and achieving learning outcomes. The applications and uses of AI tools promised to redefine learning experiences and outcomes in undergraduate chemistry. The AI technologies and applications earlier mentioned were embedded with potentials for elevating values, understanding, and ability to prepare undergraduate students for specialization in graduate schools chemistry and other related fields. It would be of interests to note that the multilayered systems in AI were created with various functions

Qualitative Study on...(Brimoh, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609043>

of machine learning, deep learning, artificial intelligence, chatbots, natural language processing (NLP), computer vision, supervised learning, unsupervised learning, reinforcement learning, anomaly detection, speech detection and neural networks (Quantum Leap AI Academy, 2024).

The objectives for preparing this theoretical work were towards meeting and sustaining undergraduate chemistry learning outcomes with Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies. The following theoretical analyses were explored from literature for developing the specific roles, which AI played in incorporating knowledge representations for undergraduate chemistry and towards facilitating results-oriented undergraduate chemistry learning outcomes.

Further to the objectives stated in the last paragraph, the following features were discussed in this paper:

1. AI for personalised and adaptive undergraduate chemistry learning outcome in Nigeria;
2. AI for simulation-based undergraduate chemistry learning outcome in Nigeria;
3. AI for problem-solving in undergraduate chemistry learning outcome in Nigeria;
4. AI for transforming assessments and feedbacks in chemistry learning outcome in Nigeria;
5. AI for automated essay scoring (AES) and assessment in undergraduate chemistry learning outcome in Nigeria;
6. AI for multimodal Assessment in undergraduate chemistry learning outcome in Nigeria; and
7. AI for facilitating planning in undergraduate chemistry learning outcome in Nigeria.

AI for personalised and adaptive undergraduate chemistry learning outcome in Nigeria

A very important function of AI in chemistry was in providing personalised and adaptive learning experiences for students. Obi *et al* (2024) explained personalised and adaptive learning as a learner-centred approach, which were tailored to each student's unique needs and abilities in real-time learning. In undergraduate chemistry, AI-powered intelligence tutoring systems (ITS) could analyse each student's existing knowledge, skill levels, pacing, interests, and strengths/weaknesses. The system could continually adapt and customise the lesson content, difficulty levels, teaching strategies, and feedbacks, in order to help each individual student in his/her learning with the most effective methodology (Baum *et al*, 2021; Iyemuremye *et al*, 2024). For example, intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) created customised problem sets and explanations that focused on the topics, which students were struggling with, and would accelerate on past concepts, which the students have mastered. AI's intelligence tutoring systems (ITS) would make inferences about students' confusions and knowledge gaps and provide hints and corrections during the problem-solving process itself. Algorithmic assessment of learners' emotions can even detect boredom, frustration, or disengagement and adjust the lectures to re-engage that student at any convenient later time. There are many personalised and adaptive AI learning tools for undergraduate chemistry that were constantly used. Examples of the mostly used chemistry AI tools in this category are – quiver ai, dragon box ai, merck it well ai, phet ai, google earth tools and lab exchange ai. These AI tools bring chemistry concepts to life with interactive simulations and lesson planning activities. Particularly, the “Lab exchange ai” can use variety of experiments for chemistry contents and as well conduct virtual chemistry experiments on request. Studies revealed that these tools had significantly helped in students' motivation, enjoyment, and academic achievement (Zhai, *et al*, 2021).

Researchers found that students' learning science with the help of AI-based personalised tutors developed critical thinking skills and metacognitive strategies faster, they analysed results and reported experiments with higher confidence levels compared to traditional classroom learning. Personalised and adaptive AI learning tools for undergraduate chemistry have been shown to be especially impactful for low-performing students and those with learning disabilities. Research also inferred that the struggling group of students made good learning outcomes in chemistry tests after utilising the personalised and adaptive AI courseware (Zhai, *et al*, 2021). Summarily, Iyemuremye, *et al*, (2024) revealed that there are opportunities in learning chemistry by integrating AI features in personalised and adaptive learning platforms, and intelligence tutoring systems (ITS) into chemistry education. AI's personalised and adaptive learning technological applications have vast potentials for transformative undergraduate chemistry education. The programs enabled truly customised pedagogical processes and helped students overcome their individual barriers, and achieve developed growth in their mindset, thus reaching their full potentials in chemistry learning outcomes.

AI for simulation-based undergraduate chemistry learning outcome in Nigeria

Artificial Intelligence (AI) as computerised technological manipulation systems have abilities, which were claimed to have surpassed the process of human thinking or at least indistinguishable from human created contents.

Qualitative Study on...(Brimoh, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609043>

The multilayered systems in AI were created with various functions of machine learning, deep learning, artificial intelligence, chatbots, natural language processing (NLP), computer vision, supervised learning, unsupervised learning, reinforcement learning, anomaly detection, speech detection and neural networks (Choudhary, *et al*, 2021; Pourya, 2023). Dai & Ke (2022) explained Artificial Intelligence (AI) to be a revolution in learning and education with paradigm shift from passive to active learning. A critical use of AI in advancing undergraduate chemistry was in the running of advanced computer simulations for chemistry experiments, reactions, and/or molecular/atomic concepts. The intricate nature, structure, properties and uses of chemistry and chemical substances might be too dangerous, expensive, time-consuming, or visually difficult to demonstrate in any traditional chemistry classroom. With virtual simulations that were powered by artificial intelligence algorithms, students can conduct far more experiments, intensely explore chemical reactions at the particulate level, and gain much deeper applied and experiential scientific knowledge (Pourya, 2023).

Innovations in sustaining undergraduate chemistry learning had experienced substantial developments with AI-enabled applications like “phet ai”, “lab exchange ai” and “merck it well ai,” which provided simulation-based machine learning experiences. These AI tools functioned in computerized chemistry simulations leverage machine learning. They created wide range of interactive laboratory experiments that were completed with realistic tools, materials, and reactive processes. With the simulation-based tools, students would compile customisable laboratory benches, adjust chemical concentrations and properties, initiate reactions, apply indicators, take measurements, and analyse results without any risk. The AI simulation-based learning in chemistry have capabilities in the intelligent tutoring systems, which offers specific guidance and feedbacks, draw attention to safety considerations, and reveal scaffolded inquiry-based challenges as they were customised to learners’ competency levels. For example, an AI tutor may allow advanced students to freely explore while prompting struggling students with leading questions or hints during the pedagogical process, in order to support their understanding and procedural skills. Researchers have revealed the power of such AI-guided exploratory learning in chemistry for developing self-directed scientific inquiry abilities, troubleshooting skills, and mastery of the scientific method (Dai & Ke 2022).

Beyond virtual laboratories, AI algorithms can simulate physical phenomenon that are impossible to adequately demonstrate in a classroom setting due to size, time, and monetary constraints - from atomic/sub-atomic interactions to industrial chemical plants. Quantum level behavior, intricate bio-chemical systems, complex organic reactions, and more can be dynamically modeled to give unprecedented interactive visual learning experiences, as required by the curriculum. Simulations gave flexible and memorable experiences to learners, where they would be able to pause, rewind, and manipulate variables that would be utterly uncontrollable in the real world.

The formative and summative assessments that were induced into “simulation-based AI applications” provided teachers with rich analytics on the effectiveness of such AI simulators for boosting cognitive, physical, emotional, and collaborative learning outcomes for their students. Studies (Akbar and Djakariah, 2024; Zhai, *et al*, 2021; Baum, *et al*, 2021), revealed that learning chemistry with intelligent and adaptive simulations had improved conceptual understanding, practical skills, idea generation, and teamwork capabilities of students, as compared to traditional laboratory work alone. Students experience high level of interactivity and were highly engaged with simulation-based AI applications. The authors believed that virtual lessons with simulation-based AI applications would be able to replace the traditional chemistry laboratory instruction with better differences in students’ performances in examinations. Meanwhile, the featured described so far, would make simulation-based AI technologies to be contemporarily the most transformational AI innovations for sustaining undergraduate chemistry learning outcomes.

AI for problem-solving in undergraduate chemistry learning outcome in Nigeria

Artificial intelligence (AI) evaluates chemistry students’ challenges and solve with instantiated problem-solving programs. The tools were embedded with personalised AI driven problem solvers and deliver solutions with explanations, which were beyond what traditional methods can achieve. AI’s problem-solving capabilities could notably improve results in undergraduate chemistry learning outcomes. Intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) in AI for chemistry problem-solving were designed specifically for chemistry problem-solving and incorporated with advanced computational models, which could be utilized in diverse ways in teaching and learning chemistry (Yuriev, *et al*, 2024), and to analyse and resolve students’ challenges in chemistry topics such as, stoichiometry, thermodynamics, solubility, thermochemistry, molecular geometry, acid-base reactions, oxidation-reduction reactions,

Qualitative Study on...(Brimoh, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609043>

electrochemistry, and other perceived complex considerations in undergraduate chemistry. The AI tutors in problem-solving were not designed for only getting answers, but also programmed to identify exactly where and why students got chemistry perceptions wrong, based on misconceptions.

The AI's intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) were created with adaptive hints and feedbacks that would help students to detect the errors in their understanding and build mastery through enhanced mathematical, conceptual, procedural, and visual comprehension. A good example was the case of students with challenges of getting through steps in balancing combustion reaction equations, the AI's intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) would detect immediately that their problems were about grasping the underlying concept of conservation of matter. It then provided remediation through targeted sub-goals, additional practice questions, and customise the explanations until the students could prove clear understanding of the fundamental concepts. Jakobsche *et al.*, (2023), showed that AI's Intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) executed three important strategies of scaffolding problem-solving skills in chemistry, which involved (a) modeling expert strategies, (b) coached practice with gradually fading guidance, and (c) making detailed solutions with explanations for every problem. The combination of AI's ITS with personalised and adaptive learning would give a highly effective chemistry pedagogy for developing proficiency in chemistry learning. Students learning chemistry with AI's problem-solving tools have opportunities of improvements in critical thinking, deep thinking and problem-solving abilities on complex areas in chemistry concepts like gas laws, oxidation-reduction reactions, stoichiometry, acid-base reactions, molecular chemistry, solution chemistry, thermodynamics and thermochemistry.

In assessment and evaluation, AI's problem-solving tools utilise the advanced neural networks to evaluate students' problem-solving processes. The tools have capabilities to analyse students' notes, check drawings and labeling, detect mistakes in verbal explanations, correct eye-tracking biometrics, and be sure that sequential steps were taken in every process. These strategies allowed AI's ITS to deliver precise, real-time guidance to correct misconceptions and strengthen students' problem-solving skills. The efforts were that AI's problem-solving programs were created to be immersive and process-focused. The intelligence in the advance neural network created highly personalised learning experiences for students. The simulated interactive laboratory settings and real-world scenarios in AI had also provided students with skills in manipulating equipment and making appropriate observations in gathering data for solving ill-defined, open-ended problems. The fast rate of development in pedagogical innovations suggested that AI-guided problem-based learning would be substantially useful to undergraduate chemistry learning.

In summary, leveraging artificial intelligence (AI) to transformations in learning how chemistry problems were practiced, solved, and explained had immense potential to boost undergraduate chemistry students' learning outcomes. AI tutoring systems allow unlimited, personalised problem sets with detailed solutions that were adjusted to each learner's evolving competency and interests. Intelligent analysis of the problem-solving processes itself accelerates metacognitive and self-directed learning skills, which were essential for undergraduate chemistry.

AI for transforming assessments and feedbacks in chemistry learning outcome in Nigeria

Assessment tools were used by teachers to measure students' level of understanding of course contents, as well as their skills, abilities and learning outcomes. Hooda *et al* (2022), explained how assessment and feedback practices can enhance students learning outcomes using AI, and they developed a study which captured an outline of the most used AI and machine learning algorithms for improved students learning outcomes. Assessments of learning outcomes could be in the form of examinations, tests, portfolios, quizzes, essays, projects and presentations. Artificial intelligence (AI) had revolutionised assessments and feedbacks in undergraduate chemistry. AI-powered tools for assessment and feedbacks were made in the form of learning algorithms, which were applied to written work, speech recognition for verbal responses, and multimodal analytics for enabling more efficient, meaningful, and multidimensional evaluation of student knowledge and proficiency (Iyemuremye *et al*, 2024).

There are many types of AI's assessment and evaluation tools and examples included – proctorio, turnitin, gradescope, aleks, examsoft, kneutron, questionmark, brightspace, metacog, tophat, coursera, codio, kira talent, thinkster math. Assessment and evaluation of chemistry content with use of the mentioned AI tools enhanced efficiency and fostered learning experiences and outcomes. The introduction of AI into assessments and evaluation of chemistry contents would shape the focus on the measure of accuracy of learning outcomes and optimising performances and achievements in undergraduate chemistry.

Qualitative Study on...(Brimoh, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609043>

AI for automated essay scoring (AES) and assessment in undergraduate chemistry learning outcome in Nigeria

A ground breaking work in the field of evaluation, psychometrics and assessment was with the use of AI in the scoring, marking and grading of essay questions. The automated essay scoring (AES) and assessment was designed as artificial intelligence for educational assessment with natural language processing (Li *et al*, 2023). The AES had features and intuitive for scoring and grading with rubric creation. Intelligent tutoring systems (ITS), gradescope, plagiarism detecting software, intellimetric and helpful chatbots were few essay assessing software for colleges and universities (Ludwig *et al*, 2021). AES systems have capabilities to assess students' answers to chemistry examination questions or assignments along multiple dimensions, and reliably grade students' responses based on rubrics. The AES software systems could evaluate logical consistency, factual accuracy, conceptual understanding and breadth of ideas, argument quality, and more. The applications could further function within answers provided for questions, while eliminating the inconsistencies that occurred in human ratings and evaluations.

Uto and Okano (2020) revealed that automated essay scoring (AES) technologies could grade answers to undergraduate chemistry questions with psychometric validity and reliability, at par with that of experienced teachers. Automated scoring systems was discovered to correlate strongly (over 90%) with experienced teachers' ratings on variables like content accuracy, critical thinking, and technical application of chemical laws, theories and principles. The AI tools save teachers' time without sacrificing personalised feedback (Ramesh & Sanampudi, 2022). Further, Uto and Okano (2020) further explained that the creation of automated essay scoring (AES) systems would make students to receive instant results for essay tests and examinations, with highlighted excerpts from their written responses that corresponded to rubric criteria strengths, flaws, omissions, and suggested improvements.

AI for multimodal Assessment in undergraduate chemistry learning outcome in Nigeria

Cukurova *et al* (2019), analysed the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in human intelligence augmentation and decision making. They showed that in learning situation, the multimodal approach in AI augmented human, in predicting the contexts in tutoring and assessments of tests and examinations. The multimodal framework of AI expands beyond tutoring and evaluating processes and procedures in learning, because AI was created with capabilities to ingest multimodal student responses, reflections, predictions and their intuitive decision-making on contents of lessons. The multimodal assessment functions of AI in chemistry included speech appropriations, virtual laboratory demonstrations, calculations, diagram drawings, balancing of chemical equations and manipulative visualisations of molecular models. The multimodal contexts of AI resulted into better understanding of contents of topics, improve students' skills and knowledge levels and facilitate deep learning. The multimodal nature of AI reinforces learning and speed up knowledge recovery in learning environments. AI multimodal tutoring and assessment appropriately benefits students and improve their conceptual understanding of chemistry in the contexts relating to their visual-spatial abilities around diagramming techniques, laboratory and experiments procedures and in understanding the learning paths for establishing molecular structures.

AI for facilitating planning in undergraduate chemistry learning outcome in Nigeria

The important elements in AI included – manipulative visualizations, predictive analytics, forecasting, algorithmic assessments, optimisation models, intuitive assessment and decision making, critical thinking and data analysis. These elements functioned in facilitating planning, conceptual understanding of rubrics, making references, decision making and projecting into the future. As students engaged with AI-powered chemistry learning systems over time, advanced machine learning algorithms would reveal predictive insights in experiments, anticipates knowledge gaps, forecasts future performances, prescribes remedial resources and alert teachers to the risks ahead (Pourya, 2023). Further, Verner and Revzin (2017), in a study on the use of robotics for automation of manual laboratories system in planning chemistry experiments, established that autonomous systems and cognitive assistants provided by robotics devices were engaging and contributed to significant outcomes in learning chemistry. The AI-powered chemistry planning systems helped teachers to differentiate between different methodologies through actionable student-centered analytics. The planning of chemistry experiments with AI tutoring systems were able to deliver increasingly with individual student's personalised learning experiences, and had continuously address each individual student's evolving needs and abilities.

Qualitative Study on...(Brimoh, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609043>

Conclusion

In conclusion, this article discussed the diversity in AI potentials for sustaining undergraduate chemistry learning outcomes. Basically, the article focused on the diverse and potentially transformative innovations, which AI had been contributing to improving pedagogy and learning of undergraduate chemistry. The authors illuminated on the capabilities of some AI tools, which included - proctorio, turnitin, gradescope, aleks, examsoft, knewton, questionmark, brightspace, metacog, tophat, coursera, codio, kira talent, thinkster math, gradescope by turnitin. Other AI programs mentioned in the paper were personalised tutors, virtual simulations, problem-solving aids, automated scoring engines and predictive analytics. These AI applications have potentials to offer competent tutoring and self-directed learning for users. They could as well provide interactive feedbacks, experiential digital learning opportunities, facilitate understanding in chemistry and transform activities in chemistry pedagogy, assessments and feedbacks.

Typically, of the undergraduate chemistry students, they were of different knowledge backgrounds and possessed different learning needs. The opportunities in the AI's self-paced pedagogy and activities in AI's personalised and adaptive learning applications catered for individual student's learning styles and strengths. Further, the emerging AI technologies promised to redefine undergraduate chemistry learning, by elevating its value and accessibility. The authors believed that these AI qualities would increase undergraduate students' interests in chemistry and also improve knowledge, understanding and achievements in chemistry. As we expressed earlier that AI tutors helped substantially in chemistry knowledge and skill development, and improved motivation through positive learning experiences, which reduced anxiety, build confidence in applying concepts, and developing students' interests in learning chemistry topics. The emergence of AI systems gave chemistry lecturers the advantages to work on students' higher-order thinking, analysis, communication, collaboration, real-world applications, and helped students to develop their propensities in working together as groups. Lecturers should leverage on the rich analytics of AI for each learner's evolving progress and be able to differentiate among contents of lessons accordingly. Further, the integrated and multiple dimensions provided for undergraduate chemistry learning by AI systems would amplify the opportunities and relationships between computer-driven personalised programs, chemistry teachers and students in learning process.

Transitioning to the innovations in the AI-powered pedagogical paradigm would raise valid concerns around undergraduate chemistry students' data privacy, systems' transparency, and equitable access, which must be proactively addressed. Perceptively, policies and curriculum frameworks would need to be developed hand-in-hand with technical and technological professional development for chemistry lecturers, in order to uphold ethical standards and proper usage of AI tools. Additionally, more research works would be needed to refine algorithms and machine learning models that avoid bias in tutoring and in the making of reliable and valid assessments for diverse students' populations over time. Workshops, conferences, seminars and other professional development activities for chemistry lecturers should involve curriculums contents that accommodate integrated guidance and technical understanding on how to effectively leverage on the opportunities that artificial intelligence (AI) would provide in shaping future chemistry classrooms for sustaining undergraduate chemistry learning outcomes. The innovations and development in the application of artificial intelligence (AI) to undergraduate chemistry made it more plausible than ever before to envision personalised, adaptive, and highly effective computer-based learning as a scalable reality for mainstream chemistry pedagogy in the nearest future. Technological advances in education and pedagogy of learning had brought the supposed once-distant vision within reach. AI innovation will speedily evolve deeper and more integrated learning experiences and learning outcomes in chemistry.

Artificial intelligence (AI) had transformed personalised and adaptive learning. Again, the multimodal assessment systems of AI was developed with potentials for providing results for summative and formative assessments along with feedback delivery in unprecedented time, space and in the ways to improve undergraduate chemistry pedagogy. The AI capabilities for personalised tutoring, automating essay scoring, analysing multimodal responses, and generating predictive insights would facilitate both personalised and lecturer-driven chemistry learning. With sound implementation and commitments towards equitable access to technology, AI-enabled learning holds revolutionary promises to transform the current undergraduate chemistry learning outcomes. The use of Artificial Intelligence for sustaining undergraduate chemistry learning outcomes were characterised with improved students'

Qualitative Study on...(Brimoh, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609043>

attention, interest and effort in the work of learning. These traits were to be complimented with the undergraduate chemistry students' learning behaviours, emotional involvements and intellectual efforts. There would be further opportunities with AI, in raising both excellence and empowerment for students pursuing chemistry-related careers, and simultaneously elevating scientific literacy across Nigeria and globally. The ultimate beneficiaries in this circumstance will be the generations of chemistry students with AI literacy skills, which would possess advantages in gaining competencies, passion, and agency to considerably use chemistry to minimise the perceived complex real-world problems.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were provided for this qualitative study on augmented innovations in artificial intelligence (AI) technologies:

1. AI will be able to forecast future of learning outcomes in chemistry, therefore there should be intensified efforts for potential remedial support by looking at undergraduate chemistry students' previous performances, engagement levels and environmental factors before choosing any AI technology for use.
2. Teachers should develop insights in the pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) for undergraduate chemistry topics and synergize such with available AI technologies in achieving meaning learning outcomes.
3. Universities need to seek for community support towards accessing basic AI tools from internet and should exploit internet technologies opportunities in sharing data and information on new AI tools that would be beneficial to chemistry students' learning outcomes.
4. The undergraduate chemistry curricula would be most achievable when the objectives focus on students' interests, learning outcomes and experiences. In that circumstance, the AI systems should be used by chemistry lecturers in interpreting textual data, extracting key concepts and generating learning materials that would enhance comprehension, retention and learning outcomes in chemistry.
5. AI had made education accessible to all students. Policy maker should be looking into the future of learning in chemistry and about meeting learning needs in undergraduate chemistry. The individualized learning experiences in AI would be helpful in overcoming barriers to good understanding of undergraduate chemistry contents and would provide tools for making chemistry undergraduates learn easily.
6. Chemistry learning outcomes were best achieved with funs. Chemistry students should be all out and search for AI tools that offer study plans that would make them stay focused and motivated towards achieving meaningful learning outcomes.
7. The AI-enabled learning systems had opened up a range of possibilities for cognitive, interactive and psychomotor development opportunities for students. It would be important for undergraduate chemistry students to adapt to virtual learning and problem solving activities in AI for improving their learning outcomes.
8. Undergraduate chemistry students were advised to commence on use of personalised feedback and assistances provided by AI tools, which would be helpful to achieving learning outcomes in chemistry and provide undergraduates with in-depth understanding of concepts and for building critical thinking and deep thinking skills.

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Effects of Inquiry – Based Instructional Strategy on Achievement and Retention in Auto-Mechanics among Technical College Students in Lagos State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study was designed to determine the effects of the inquiry- based instructional strategy on the achievement and retention of auto- mechanics students in technical colleges, a pre-test, post-test, non-equivalent control group, quasi- experimental design was adopted.. The population of the study consisted all the students in Tech 11 in all the technical colleges in Lagos State during the 2022/2023 academic session. A sample size of 340 students were selected from the population using multi stage random sampling technique Two research questions and two null hypotheses, tested at 0.05 level of significance, guided the study. The instruments used for data collection were cognitive achievement test (CAT) and two lesson plans (constructivist and conventional). The items of the CAT were drawn based on table of specifications built in order to ensure its content validity .and reliability coefficient of 0.80.was obtained using Pearson product moment correlational coefficient Mean and standard deviation statistics were used to answer the research questions while ANCOVA was employed to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that students taught auto-mechanics using the inquiry -based instructional strategy had a higher mean score than students taught using the conventional teaching method.in achievement test and test for retention .of learning The researcher recommended that, the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) should consider a review of motor vehicle mechanics work curriculum for technical colleges with a view of incorporating the inquiry –based instructional strategy into the teaching of auto-mechanics in the technical colleges.

Keywords: Inquiry-based learning, auto-mechanics, technical college, achievement, retention and constructivism

Introduction

Auto-mechanics technology involves the application of scientific knowledge in the design, selection of materials, construction, operation and maintenance of automobile vehicles. Auto-mechanics is one of the mechanical trades (Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN), 2004) offered as motor vehicle mechanics work in Nigeria technical colleges. The programme for motor vehicle mechanics work in Nigeria technical colleges is designed to produce competent craftsmen. According to National Board for Technical Education (NBTE, 2001) a craftsman in motor vehicle mechanics work is expected to test, diagnose, service and completely repair any fault relating to the automobile vehicle main units and systems to the manufacturers' specification.

A national curriculum is adopted in all the technical colleges accredited by NBTE. The programmes in technical colleges are offered at two levels leading to the award of National Technical Certificate (NTC) and Advanced National Technical Certificate (ANTC) for craftsmen and master craftsmen respectively (FME, 2000).

Technology the world over is dynamic. With advancement in technology petrol engine automobiles that are adopted or assembled in automobile industries nowadays are coming with new devices. For instance, (Nice ,2001) pointed out that automobiles manufactured in the United States of America with carburetor was in 2001. Nowadays, the petrol engines automobiles employ electronic injection system. Thus, technological development in automobiles has rendered traditional skills inadequate. Obviously automobile industries are in need of craftsmen who can adapt to the changes in technology in the industries. The challenges, for preparing students for the 21st century, workplace basic skills therefore has necessitated a shift from instructional approaches based on behavioural learning theories learning theories to those rooted in cognitive

psychological learning theories for which constructivism instructional techniques is one (Ogwo & Oranu,2006). Constructivism according to (Epstein & Ryan, 2012) is based on the concept that learning is a constructive process in which the learner is building an internal illustration of knowledge on a personal interpretation of experience. Constructivism is a theory of learning based on the ideas that knowledge is constructed by the learner based on mental activity.

Constructivism, according to (Owoso,2016) is therefore, a model of instruction and learning and interactive process in social setting; it is problem solving oriented, allow students to explore and work in groups, making meaning of task and setting out to solving problems that are perplexing to them. Robin (2010) pointed out that the goals of instruction in a constructivist classroom are to help learners develop learning and thinking strategies, focus on individuals' active construction of knowledge, and facilitate learning by encouraging active inquiry. Robin explained that a constructivist teacher should guide learners to question tacit assumptions and help students to uncover meanings which encourage students to become self-regulatory, self-mediating and self-aware (acquisition of thinking skill). Teacher also takes on the role of a coach or guide and engaging students in active dialogue. Besides, teacher using constructivist approach would also provide students-centered instruction in complex learning environments with formats appropriate to the learner's current state of understanding that incorporate activities (authentic task), provide for social negotiation (Oral discourse), provide students with the opportunity to work collaboratively which develop in the students' ability to work cooperative learning).

The obvious implications of the use of constructivist instructional techniques such as collaborative work. Oral discusses, authentic learning and framing presented is to improve student thinking skills and problem solving abilities. The world of work nowadays is characterized by new management systems, production process, and global competitiveness, employers are demanding their workers to have cognitive skills in critical thinking, problem solving, as high-level technical and basic academic skills. Perhaps, if these are adopted in technical colleges, it will assist in developing students' thinking skills and problem solving abilities which in turn will enhance their cognitive achievement and retention of learning Constructivist instructional approach is defined in this study, as an eclectic approach to teaching which involved the use of thinking skills, oral discourse, authentic/ situated learning, collaborative work and framing instructional strategies combined during the lesson as appropriate to suit the content of the lesson in such a way that made the students construct their own knowledge and accomplish their learning tasks based on Jerome Brunner's three principles that guide development of instruction in a constructivist classroom listed in (UNESCO, 2012). These are: instruction must be concerned with experiences and contexts that make students willing and able to learn (readiness); instruction must be structured so that the students can easily grasp it (spiral organization) and instruction should be designed to facilitate extrapolation and/or fill in the gap (going beyond information given).

The present methods of teaching auto-mechanics in the technical colleges are based on the behavioural learning theories. These present methods include demonstration and lecture methods (Oranu, 2013). Oranu maintained that these methods which are based on behavioural learning theories are teacher-centred and do not give students enough opportunities to participate in the classroom instructions. The shortcoming in these methods of teaching which is due to absence of students' active involvement in classroom activities during instruction could be responsible for poor performance of Technical College students in engineering trades which include motor vehicle mechanic work in public examinations. According to (Federal ministry of education, 2015; Aina, 2017) a close examination of the factors responsible for the high failure rate among others includes poor quality of teaching in the technical colleges. Moreover, the preparation of workers for entry-level jobs and advancement in the workplace requires educational programs that provide not only job skills, but also higher-order thin king, problem solving, and collaborative work skills, but also higher-order thinking, problem solving, and collaborative work skills.(Doolittle & Camp (2010) These methods employed by teachers in the technical college thus, seen inadequate for equipping the students studying auto-mechanics with the work place basic skills required for work in the auto-mechanics with the work place basic skills required for work in the automobile industries which is vast changing with technological advancements. The raises the questions as to whether beside the teacher-centred method there is no such teachings technique of the constructivist instructional approach which can influence this ugly trend in the subject. Inquiry –based instructional strategy employed in this study is structured on the principles of constructivism.

Perhaps if inquiry-based instructional techniques are adapted in the teaching of auto-mechanics technology students in the technical colleges will be able to acquires workplace basic skills such as collaborative work skills, problem solving skills and thinking skills required in the vast technological world of work and be able to transfer learning other varying technological conditions. Hence, what will be the effects of inquiry –based instructional strategy on the achievement and retention of auto-mechanics students in the technical colleges?

Objective of the study

The objective of the study is to determine the effects of the inquiry -based instructional strategy on the cognitive achievement and retention of learning of auto-mechanics students in technical colleges in lagos state. Specifically, the objective of the study is to:

1. Determine the achievement scores of students taught auto-mechanics with inquiry –based instructional strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture and demonstration teaching methods.
2. Compare the scores of students taught auto-mechanics with inquiry –based instructional strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture and demonstration teaching methods.in the test of retention of learning.

Research questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide this study:

1. What are the mean achievement scores of students taught auto-mechanics using the inquiry- based instructional strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture and demonstration teaching methods in Lagos state technical colleges?
2. What are the mean scores of students taught auto-mechanics using the inquiry-based instructional strategy and those taught using the conventional teaching methods in the test for retention of learning in Lagos state technical colleges?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses tested at .05 level of significance guided the study:

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught auto-mechanics using inquiry-based instructional strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture and demonstration teaching methods in Lagos state technical colleges.
2. **H₀₂**There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of students taught auto-mechanics with inquiry-based instructional approach and those taught using the conventional lecture and demonstration teaching methods in Lagos state technical colleges.

Theoretical framework

Theory is the foundation of any research. According to (Olaitan, Ali, Eyo & Sowande, 2010) theory is a postulation requiring further explanation in order to make meaning. The following are the theories on which this study is based. The Cognitive Theory of learning and The Constructivist Theory of Teaching and Learning.

Cognitive learning theory

Learning involves the process of storing, transformation and retrieving information. The problem of understanding how humans learn is essentially the problem of understanding how information is stored information is retrieved for use in the further learning and problem solving (Steward, & Aiken, 2012). The knowledge structures are stored in semantic memory as schema or cognitive maps (UNESCO, 2012; Shell, 2013) noted that the main emphasis of cognitive theory is on sequence of learning materials and experiences in a well-organized environment so as to create order, meaningfulness and understanding, that is, learner-environment interacting meaningfully some of the proponents of the cognitive theory and discussed below:

(Aushel, 2015) in his theory known as ‘sub-sumption model’ advocated for ‘meaningful’ as opposed to ‘rote learning’ According to him, meaningful learning occurs when there is an interaction between the students’ appropriate element in knowledge that already exist and the new materials to be learnt. However, where interaction does not take place, rote learning occurs. Those parts of the learner’s cognitive structure (organization of knowledge) which can provide for the interaction necessary for meaningful learning are called “subsumers”. A subsume is a principle or a generalized body of knowledge that the learner already acquired that can provide for association or ‘anchorage for the various components of the new knowledge, while sub-sumption model is an instructional device in which central and highly unifying ideas are stated in terms already familiar to the learner, to which he can meaningfully relate new learning materials by subsumption.

The developmental psychology of Jean Piaget recognizes the active role of both learner and his environment in the learning process. Piaget asserts that the basis of all learning is the learner’s activity as he interacts with his physical and social environment. For learning to take place, the environment must be stimulating and encouraging learning (Nwachukwu, 2010). Based on his research on the development of learner’s cognitive functions, Piaget observed that learning occurs through adaptation to interactions with the environment. Disequilibrium (mental conflict which demands resolution) gives rise to Assimilation of a new experience, which is added to the existing knowledge of the learner, or to Accommodation, which is modification of existing mental structure of the learner, then the information is very different from the existing mental structure (i.e Accommodation) (Ngwoke & Eze, 2014). The learner has an active role in constructing his or her own knowledge in both of these ideas. According to UNESCO (2012) Piaget was of the notion that as children assimilated new information into their

existing mental structures, their ideas gained complexity and power and their understanding of the world grew in richness and depth. These ideas are core concepts of the constructivism view of the learning process.

Bruner in his own theory emphasized that learning is an active process in which learner construct new ideas or concepts based upon their prior knowledge and experience (Nwachukwu, 2018). According to UNESCO (2002) Bruner identified three principles that guide the development of instruction. These include: (1) Instruction must be concerned with the experiences and contexts that make the student willing and able to learn readiness); (2) Instruction must be structured so that the student can easily grasp it (spiral organization) and, (3) Instruction should be designed to facilitate extrapolation and /or fill in the gaps (going beyond the information giving). Conclusively, the theories discussed so far believe in the environmental influences on the learner’s achievement in learning and that meaningful learning occur as learner and his environment are always participating in a simultaneous mutual interaction. In this study, constructivist learning strategies –oral discourse, authentic learning, and collaborative work skill, thinking skill and learning frames emphasized students-centered learning environment. It provides a rich collaborative environment enabling the learner to consider diverse and multiple perspectives to address issues and solve problems. It also provides opportunities for the student to reflect on his or her learning in the process of learning in the classroom.

The constructivist theory of teaching and learning

Mendor (2012) in his own point of view sees constructivism as a teaching approach, which holds the views that scientific knowledge is personally constructed and reconstructed by the learner based on his prior knowledge or experience. In this context Grey (2015) defined constructivism by reference to four principles; learning in an important way, depends on what we already know; new ideas occur as we adapt and change our old ideas; learning involves inventing ideas rather than mechanically accumulating facts; meaningful learning occurs through rethinking old ideas and coming to new conclusions about new ideas which conflict with our old ideas

According to (Kozloff, 2010) a constructivist framework challenges teachers to create environments in which the teacher and student are encouraged to think and explore. Kozloff centered approach to teaching and learning: from this perspective constructivist classroom then, consist of learner centered, active instruction. In such a classroom, the teacher provides students with experiences that allow them to hypothesize, predict and manipulate object, poses questions, research investigate, imagine, and invent (Grey, 2015).

Many science educators recommend the application of constructivism to teaching. (Clemisno, 2012; Roth, 2010; Cheung & Taylor 2015; Vosniadou, 2010; Nworgu, 2014). Constructivist theory argues that learners bring to the classroom ideas that affect new information received. (Stofflet, 2010). What a student learn results from the interaction between what is brought to the learning situation and what is experienced and this brings a conflict instead of understanding and acquisition of science process skills. (Stofflet (2010), stressed the fact that learners must become dissatisfied with their existing conceptions, as well as find new concepts intelligible, plausible and fruitful before conceptual restructuring will occur.

Furthermore, constructivism indicates that each learner must put together ideas and structures that have personal meaning if he or she is to learn. In order words, individual actively generates their personal meanings. Edward and mercer (2010) confirmed the above by saying that learning is regarded as a social activity in which learners are engaged in constructing meaning through activities, discussions, and negotiations among peers, students and teachers. Learners’ individual constructions of meaning occur when their ideas are compared explored and reinforced in social setting with each student having the opportunity to reorganize his/her ideas through talk and listening (Solomon, 2013). Through social interactions, learners become aware of others ideas, seek confirmation of their own ideas and reinforce or reject their personal constructions (Maor & Taylor, 2010).

From the foregoing, a learner is seen as the owner of his ideas and that understanding can be only be created in the learner from experiences and discussions among peers, fellow students and teachers (Stofflet, 2010) Solomon, 2015). There is therefore, the need to link the existing memory with the present experiences in classroom setting which would lead to existing memory with the present experiences in classroom setting, which would lead to reinforcing or restructuring and of course successful learning. This indicates that learning is an act of construction.

Furthermore, the constructivist views about learning suggest that “knowing” means being able to construct something. Therefore, knowledge must be attained in a personal sense and cannot be transferred from one person to another like filling vessel (Nworgu, 2014) which reduces the learners to a passive element who requires to sit down in the instructional setting, receives and add new information to his pre-existing knowledge. This indicates that knowledge can be accumulated bit by bit, subject and be available to transfer to the learner.

This is typical to traditional classroom where the teacher carriers on with old ideas and old ways of doing things (Nworgu, 2017). This technique places the learners as a passive recipient of knowledge rather than an active participant in the

construction of his or her own knowledge. Constructivist view learning more than this and sees the learner as creative, dynamic and with a free will. He is seen as the controller of his environment (Nworgu, 2014).

According to (Driver, 2011) students' prior ideas seem to intrude into classroom learning. In practical activities, students' ideas influence the observations they make, the inferences they draw and what they understand from formal learning situations. Listening to lectures as well as reading from textbooks (Vienno et al. 2010) in their independent studies noted that students' alternative conceptions may persist despite teaching except attempt is made to intervene and being about conceptual change. (Stofflect, 2017) stated that what a student learns is a result of the interaction between what he brought to the learning situation and what he experiences. Supporting this view, (Tobin 2010) reported that in a learning process, learners create perturbations which arise from attempts to give meaning to particular experiences through the imaginative use of existing knowledge. He went on to say that a resolution of these perturbations leads to an equilibrium state of the learner where new knowledge is constructed to cohere with a particular experience and prior knowledge. In effect it means that the interaction which brings about perturbations causes a restructuring of the existing conception or conceptual changes in learning process.

To achieve the above purpose, different learning strategies have been proposed recently. Most of these are socio-cultural and inquiry oriented. Examples of such strategies include the use of analogy, inquiry, cooperative learning, problem solving and constructivism. (Nwosu & Nzewi, 2019). Constructivism therefore is a model of instruction and learning as an interactive process in social settings. It is problem solving oriented, allows students to explore and work in groups, making meaning of task and setting out to solve problems and that are perplexing to them.

Constructivist strategies are organized into four categories namely, invitation, exploration, proposing explanations and solution taking action, (Yager, 2010). He explained further that constructivist practices require teachers to place students in more central positions in the whole instructional programme. This means that student idea should form a basis for discussion and investigation in the classroom. Tobin (2016) agreed with the above and stated that teachers should see themselves as mediators of the learning process and they should as well as provide constraints for students to channel their thinking in productive direction. Teachers are to interact with students to a greater extent than what is obtained in traditional classroom to ascertain what students know and what they are thinking and that learning should be interactive, cooperative and collaborative.

(UNESCO 2012) while recommending constructivism instructional approach to learning explained that in a constructivism learning environment, student construct their own knowledge by testing idea and approaches based on their own prior knowledge and experience. Applying these to new task, contest and situations and integrations the new knowledge gained with pre-existing intellectual constructs. UNESCO explained further that in a constructivist environment involves developing learning communities comprised of students, teachers and experts who are engaged in authentic tasks context, closely related to work done in world.

A constructivist learning environment also provides opportunities for learners to experience multiple perspectives, through discourse or debate, learner is also to see issues or problems from different points of view, to negotiate meaning, and develop shared understanding with others. The constructivist learning environment also emphasizes authentic assessment of learning environment also emphasizes authentic assessment of learning rather than the traditional paper/ pencil test.

(Knowles & Kinsey, 2015) listed eight characteristics that describe constructivist.

Learning environment as follows;

1. Constructivist learning environment provide multiple representations of reality
2. Multiple representations avoid over simplification and represent the complexity of the real world.
3. Constructivist learning environments emphasize knowledge construction knowledge reproduction
4. Constructivist learning environments emphasize authentic task in a meaningful context rather than abstract instruction out of context.
5. Constructivist learning environments emphasize authentic task in a meaningful contest rather than abstract instruction out of context.
6. Constructivist learning environments encourage thoughtful reflection on experience.
7. Constructivist learning environment enable "Context and content dependent knowledge construction"
8. Constructivist learning environment support collaborative construction of knowledge through social negotiation, not competition among learners for recognition.

In the same vein (Honebein, 2015) also noted that designers of constructivist learning environments live by seven pedagogical goals namely;

1. Provide experience with knowledge construction process
2. Students take primary responsibility for determining the topics or subtopic in a domain they pursue, the methods of how to learn and the strategic or methods for solving problem. The role of teacher is to facilitate this process.

3. Provide experience and appreciation for one correct solution. There are typically multiple way to think about and solve problems, students must engage in activities that enable them to evaluate alternative solutions to problems as a means of testing and enriching their understanding.
4. Embed learning in realistic and relevant contexts: most learning occurs in the context of school whereby educators remove the noise of real-life from learning activity or instance, world problems in mathematics text books rarely relate to the types of problems found in real life. The result is the reduced ability of the students to transfer what they learn in school to everyday life. To overcome this problem, curriculum designs must attempt to maintain the authentic context of the learning task. Educators must ground problems within the noise and complexity that surrounds them outside the classroom. Students must learn to impose order on the complexity and noise as well as solve the core problem.
5. Encourage ownership and voice in the learning process: This illustrates the students' centeredness of constructivist learning. Rather than the teacher determining what students will learn. Students play a strong role in identifying their issues and directions as well as their goals and objectives. In this frame work, the teacher as a consultant who helps students to frame their learning objectives.
6. Embed learning in social experience: intellectual development is significantly influenced through social interactions thus; learning should reflect collaboration between both teachers and students and student and students
7. Encourage the use of multiple mode of representation: Oral and written communication are the two most common forms of transmitting knowledge in educational settings. However, learning with only these forms of communication limits how students see the world. Curricular should adopt additional media, such as video, computer, photographs and sound to provide richer experience.
8. Encourage self-awareness of the knowledge construction process: A key outcome of constructivist learning in knowledge how we know. It is the students' ability to explain why and how they solved a problem in a certain way; to analyze their construction of knowledge and processes, this process is called "reflexivity" an extension of metacognitive and reflection activities.

The seven pedagogical goals of constructivism offer designers a solid framework which to build learning environments. By designing learning activities that satisfy the goals, the signer makes an effort to put theory into practice. In this way the learning environment will promote higher order thinking skills in the students. In relation to this view of constructivism, the constructivist learning process as used in this study is seen as a process of 'meaning-making' in socially situated contexts whereby students construct their own knowledge by testing ideas and approaches based on their prior knowledge and experience in auto-mechanics, applying these to new tasks, contexts and situations, and integrating the new knowledge gained with pre-existing intellectual constructs.

Conceptual framework

Conceptual Framework presents ideas, rules, or beliefs of how something is developed, is done or on which decisions are based. The concept of constructivism and constructivism instructional strategies employed in this study, including the concept of auto-mechanics in Technical Colleges are presented below:

The concept of constructivism

Constructivism according to (Thanasoulas,(2015) is a theory of learning based on the ideas that knowledge is confirmed by the knower based on mental activities. Similarly, Hoover (2016) pointed out that constructivism central idea is that human learning is constructed. Learners build new knowledge upon the foundation of previous learning. This view of learning according to Hoover sharply contracts with one in which learning is the transmission of information from one individual to another, a view in which learning is the transmission of information from one individual to another, a view in which reception, not construction is key. Supporting this view, (Kozloff,2019) noted that constructivism challenges the assumption and practice of reductionism that have pervaded our educational practices for generations. In a deficit-driven reductionism framework, effective learning takes place in a rigid, hierarchical progression. Learning then is an accumulation of isolated fact.

In construction view of learning process, (UNESCO,2013) explained that learners are active agents who engage in their own knowledge construction y integrating new information in their scheme or mental structure. The learning process is seen as a process of meaning-making' in socially, culturally, historically and probability situation context. In the view of constructivist, learning is a constructive process in which learner is building an internal illustration of knowledge, a personal interpretation of experience. Two important notions orbit around the simple idea of constructed knowledge. According to (Hoover, 2017) the first is that learners construct new understanding using what they already know. There is no tabula rasa on which new knowledge is etched. Rather, learners come to learning situation with new or modified knowledge they will construct

from new learning experiences. The second is that learner is active rather than passive, learner confront their understanding in light of what they encounter in the new learning situation. If what learners encounter is inconsistent with their current understanding, their understanding can change to accommodate new experience.

Methodology

A quasi-experimental research design was used for this study. Specifically, the pretest, post-test non-equivalent control group design was adopted for the study.

Population and sampling procedure

The population of the study consisted all the students in Tech 11 in all the technical colleges in lagos state during the 2022/2023 academic session. A sample of size of 340 students were selected from the sample using multi stage random sampling technique and in this case, 182 students constituted those in the experimental group while students totaling 158 constituted the subjects in the control group.

Instruments for data collection

The instruments used for data collection in this study were Cognitive Achievement Text (CAT). The CAT was used to test the students' cognitive achievement and retention of learning in auto-mechanics. The CAT contained multiple choice items and was developed based on the content of petrol engine maintenance work in the technical college syllabus-module CMV 11.). The items of the CAT were drawn based on table of specifications built in order to ensure the content validity of the test. The reliability coefficient of 0.80.was obtained for the CAT using pearson product moment correlational coefficient Other instruments adopted were constructivist inquiry - based lesson plans and conventional lesson plans *while face validity was used to ensure the validity of the lesson plans using three experts.*

Experimental procedure

The pretest was first conducted before the commencement of the treatment. The pretest featured the administration of the Cognitive Achievement Test (CAT). On the students in both experimental and control groups. The results obtained from the pretest provided baseline data on the dependent variable (Cognitive achievement) before treatment.

The pretest was immediately followed by the treatment. During the treatment, the experimental group was taught with constructivist inquiry -based lesson plan, while the control group was taught with conventional lesson plans. The constructivist inquiry -based lesson plan incorporated five learning strategies: thinking skill, oral discourse, active learning, collaborative learning skills and framing strategies to a greater extent emphasized students' active participation in their learning process, group learning, connectedness of the lesson to real-world situation and practical hand-on activities.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected from the pretest, posttest, and retention of learning were analyzed using mean to answer the research questions. The pretest-posted mean gain of each group (Control and Experimental groups) were compared to determine the group that performed better to answer questions. The null hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of results

The results of the data analysis for the study were organized according to the research questions and hypotheses that guided the study.

Research Question One.: .What are the mean achievement scores of students taught auto-mechanics using the inquiry- based instructional strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture and demonstration teaching methods?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Division of Pre-Test Scores of Experimental and control Group in the Auto-mechanics Cognitive Achievement Test (CAT)

GROUP	N	Pre-Test		POST-TEST		MEAN GAIN
		X	SD	X	SD	
Experimental	182	3.85	1.47	35.60	1.81	31.75
Control	158	3.77	1.47	19.71	3.89	15.94

The data presented in Table 1 shows that the experimental group had a mean score of 3.85 and standard deviations of 1.47 in the pre-test with mean score of 35.60 and standard deviation of 1.47 in the pre-test and a mean score of 31.75. The control group had a mean score of 3.77 and a standard deviation of 1.47 in the pre-test post-test gain of 15.94. With this result, the students in the experimental group performed better than the students in the control group.in the cognitive achievement test.

Research Question two: What are the mean scores of students taught auto-mechanics using the inquiry-based instructional strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture and demonstration teaching methods in the test for retention of learning?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Achievement Scores of Experimental and Control Group in Auto-mechanics Cognitive Achievement Post-Test and Test for Retention Learning

GROUP	N	Pre-Test		Test for Retention	
		X	SD	X	SD
Experimental	182	35.60	1.81	34.58	3.24
Control	158	19.71	3.89	8.62	3.58

Table 2 shows that the students in the experimental group had a post-test mean score of 35.60 with standard deviation of 1.81 and a mean score of 34.58 with standard deviation of 2.24 in the test for retention of learning, while the students in the control group had a post-test mean score of 19.71 with test for retention of learning. The results therefore indicate that students taught Auto-mechanics with the constructivist instructional approach retained their learning better than those taught with the conventional teaching methods.

Hypotheses One There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught auto-mechanics with inquiry-based instructional approach and those taught using the conventional lecture and demonstration teaching methods.

Table 3: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) for Test of Significance between the Mean Scores of Experimental and control groups in the Cognitive Achievement.

Score of Variation	Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig of F
Covariates	13.790	1	13.790	1.566	.212
Pre-test	13.790	1	13.790	1.566	.212
Mean Effects	21366.499	1	21366.499	2426.121	.000
Group	21366.499	1	21366.499	2426.499	.000 ⁺
Explained	21366.546	2	10683.273	1213.063	.000
Residual	2967.910	337	8.807		
Total	24334.456	339	71.783		

The data presented in Table 3 shows that the F-value for group is 2426.121 who significance of at .000, which is less than 0.5. The null-hypothesis is therefore rejected at 0.05 level of significance. With this result, there is significant difference between the mean scores of students taught with constructivist instructional approach and those taught using conventional teaching method in Auto-mechanics Cognitive Achievement test.

Hypothesis two: There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of students taught auto-mechanics with inquiry-based instructional approach and those taught using the conventional lecture and demonstration teaching methods

Table 4: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) for Test of Significance between the mean scores of experimental and Control groups in the Test for Retention of learning.

Source of variation	Sum of squares	DF	Mean Sqaure	F	Sig of F
Covariates	23.924	1	23.924	2.777	.97
Pre-test	23.924	1	23.924	2.777	.097
Main Effects	57028.997	1	57028.997	6619.048	.000
Group	57031.997	1	57028.997	6619.048	.000 ⁺
Explained	57031,555	2	28515.669	3309.660	.000
Residual	29034.894	337	8.616		
Total	59934.894	339	179.799		

Significant at sig of F < 05

Table 4 shows that the F-value for group is 6619.048 with significant of at .000, which is less than .05. the null-hypothesis is therefore rejected at .05 level of significance. With this result, there is significant difference between the mean scores of students taught with constructivist instructional approach and taught using conventional teaching method in Auto-mechanics test for retention.

Discussion of Findings

The data presented in Table 1 provided answer to research question one, finding revealed that students taught with constructivist instructional approach had a higher mean score than those students taught using the conventional teaching methods in Auto-mechanics cognitive achievement test. In the same vein, the analysis of covariance presented in Table 3 confirmed that the difference between the mean teaching methods was significant. The significant different is attributed to the treatment given to the experimental group. This finding indicated that the constructivist instructional approach has a positive effect on student's cognitive achievement in auto-mechanics. This implies that the constructivist instructive achievement in auto-mechanics. This implies that the constructivist instructional approach (Collaborative learning, oral discourse, thinking skill, authentic task and learning frame) is more effective than the conventional teaching method in enhancing student's cognitive achievement in Auto-mechanics. The findings that enhancing students' Constructivist instructional approach has positive effect to students' achievement is similar to the adoption of constructivist instructional approach in the in the teaching of Thailand vocational electronic students improved the students' achievement in electronics than the students taught with traditional instructional method.

The data presented in Table 2 provided answer to research question two. Finding revealed that students taught with constructivist instructional approach had a higher mean score than those taught with the conventional instructional teaching method in the test for retention of learning. The analysis of covariance of the retention test presented in Table 4 confirmed that the difference in the score of the students taught with conventional instructional approach and those taught with conventional teaching methods is significant. This showed that the constructivist instructional approach has positive effect on the students learning in auto-mechanics. This finding stemmed from the fact that constructivist instructional approach has positive effect on the student retention of learning in auto-mechanics. These findings stemmed from the fact that constructivist instructional approach enhances hands-on activists with places learning in the hands of the students. The provision of active learning environment were students can be engaged and participate activity in class discussion increase the students' ability to explore issues and articulate their own ideas. Also, the use of open ended questions by the teacher makes the students to engage in higher order thinking task such as analysis, synthesis and evaluation. These affirms (Tochomites, 2010) view that order thinking skills, improves memory and enhances transfer of learning to another situation. (Von Glaserfield, 2010) was of the opinion that by teaching students understanding. He maintained that when students learn to think, they will be able to tackle problems creatively and confidently.

In any educational practices, when students work or learn in groups collaboratively using real object, each person, in order to be an effective participant, will need to think critically in order to make logical contributions. Moreover, when students learn in groups, the bright ones always help the dull ones to understand the subject matter being learnt. This affirms (Ngeow, (2010) view that collaborative learning enhances critical thinking skills and hence, cognitive achievement and retention of learning

Conclusions

This study set out to determine the effect of inquiry-based instructional approach on the achievement and retention of learning of auto-mechanic students in technical colleges. The constructivist instructional approach (Collaborative learning, oral discourse, thinking skill, authentic task and framing) used in this study greatly affected the students learning of Motor Vehicle mechanics work. This was reflected in the auto-mechanics students' cognitive and retention of learning. In other word, student learnt auto-mechanics better when they were allowed to participate actively in the classroom teaching and learning by interacting with teacher, learning environment and their colleagues and work and learn together in groups. Also, students retained their learning for a longer time they are allowed to think on possible solution to a problem while engaging in practical activities with real objects. Tools and machine work in the technical colleges, craftsmen trained will graduate from the technical colleges with knowledge psychomotor skills, strong problem solving, creative thinking, collaborative work, and independent decision making skills which will make them to be adaptable to the present and envisaged changes in the automobile industry occasioned by technological advancement.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made

1. Technical college teachers should adopt the use of inquiry- based instructional strategy to teach auto-mechanics and other vocational courses to enhance better cognitive and psychomotor achievement.
2. To enhance better retention of learning, Inquiry-- based instructional strategy should be adopted for teaching in the technical colleges

3. National board for Technical Education (NBTE.) should consider review of the curriculum for motor vehicle mechanics work programme with a view of incorporating the inquiry- based instructional strategy into the teaching of auto-mechanics
4. Ministry of Education and administrators of technical education should always organize seminars and workshops to sensitize technical teachers on the use of the inquiry –based instructional strategy.

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Comparative Analysis between Financial Literacy and Household Budgeting Practices among Families in Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examined a comparative analysis between Financial Literacy and Household Budgeting Practices among Families in Delta, Nigeria. This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Using stratified random sampling, a sample size of 300 households was determined to be representative of the different socio-economic strata. This method of sampling is adopted to ensure that the populations of interest in Delta State are represented proportionately. The sample was stratified into urban and rural districts since financial behaviour might be different between urban and rural households. This quantitative study draws on data collected through a structured survey questionnaire from 300 state homes. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic data and give an overview of financial literacy levels and budgeting practices across the sample. There was a significant positive relationship between the level of financial knowledge and household budgeting. Those more financially literate households were more likely to budget, save, track expenditures, and plan for the future—lower financial literacy households overspent, saved little, and had little financial planning. Financial literacy affects budgeting. Educational level, income, and financial services access also determined financial literacy. Higher-income and educated households were more likely to understand financial concepts and budget discipline. Financial knowledge and budgeting were poorer in rural communities with little financial resources. The study, therefore, recommended the need for tailored financial education initiatives that address specific issues relevant to low-income and rural populations. There should be integration of financial literacy into school curricula and community-based financial education workshops.

Keywords: Financial Literacy, Household Budgeting Practices, Families in Delta State, Home management

Introduction

Living in a time of rapid economic fluctuation and growing financial complexities, financial literacy has emerged as the mainstay skill that becomes very essential for personally managing one's finances. The broad definition of financial literacy refers to an understanding and the competent application of all other related financial skills: personal financial management, budgeting, and investment management. According to BAM (2021), it is vital in framing household budgeting behaviour. It has become very important that financial literacy really influences budgeting practices in most Nigerian families characterized by financial disparities. This introduction develops the relationship between financial literacy and household budgeting with respect to Nigerian families, putting into focus the enhancement of financial knowledge which would lead toward great financial decision-making and stability.

Financial literacy refers to the various sets of skills that help people make more effective and fully informed financial decisions. The skills themselves comprise knowledge about basic financial concepts such as interest rates, inflation, and diversification of risks, along with the state of being able to apply that knowledge in managing personal finances, planning, and navigating financial products and services (OECD, 2018). However, it should not be forgotten that the financial knowledge a person has only does not benefit one-self but also spreads its wider ramifications into stability and growth of the economy. Individuals with higher levels of financial literacy are more apt to save, make better investments, and avoid intense debt relationships, all three factors combined enabling a stable and prosperous economy (Hanson and Olson, 2018).

Households still consider budgeting one of the most direct and easy ways of managing one's personal finances, as it involves apportioning income between various expenses, savings, and investments to achieve financial goals and ensure economic stability. Hanson and Olson insist that good budgeting means much more than just keeping records of inflow and outflow; one needs to make strategic decisions on spending priorities, building for emergencies, and planning long-run financial objectives. The determinants of budgeting practices across households are many, but in the case of developing countries like Nigeria, it could be levels of income, cultural norms, financial obligations, and even access to financial education. With Nigeria

being the largest economy in Africa, it forms a singular backdrop against which investigations into the influence of financial literacy on household budgeting can be carried out. While high levels of natural resources and economic promise characterize Nigeria, it still faces considerable financial concerns pertaining to poverty, unemployment, inflation, and income inequalities. In 2023, according to World Bank estimates, personal finances of families in Nigeria were further complicated by the foregoing factors, where prudent budgeting practices are quite necessary yet hard to realize. In Nigeria, the growth of the financial sector is not typical due to poor access to financial services for many families, and this makes budgeting more complicated compared to the routine process.

Cultural factors also significantly influence the financial behaviours of Nigerian households. These traditional practices, such as the communal sharing of resources and reliance on informal financial arrangements, are known both to support and to hinder effective budgeting. For example, while communal support does provide a cushion during financial hardships, it may discourage formal savings or investment habits that enhance the stability of an individual's finances (Nassir, Lebdaoui, Chetoui & Lebdaoui, 2023). The reasons being financially literate and household budgeting are interwoven. Persons with financial literacy exhibit a better understanding and the ability to put in place appropriate budgeting, since they have the knowledge of understanding their financial situation, can set realistic financial goals, and allocate resources efficiently (Hanson and Olson, 2018). Improvement in financial literacy within the Nigerian setting may thus encourage families to better surmount economic crises, reduce exposure to financial shocks, and improve their general state of financial well-being. Empirical evidence has also indicated that financial literacy is positively related to practices associated with budgeting. For example, MoroccoBrüggen, Högrevé, Holmlund, Kabadayi, Löfgren (2017) made reference to findings that a higher degree of financial literacy is related to more sophisticated budgeting behaviour, saving, and retirement planning. In Nigeria, for example, Alipio 2017 revealed that financial education significantly influences budgeting Behaviour; hence, its households have been able to exercise more self-discipline in spending and enjoy higher savings rates.

Despite the recognized benefits, several barriers hinder the dissemination and adoption of financial literacy in Nigeria. Educational limitations, lack of access to financial education programs, and socio-economic constraints are primary obstacles. Because many Nigerians, especially those from rural communities, lack formal education and training in finance, their ability to learn about the necessary knowledge on issues of finance is limited. Besides, a cultural attitude toward money and finance presents an obstacle to effective budgeting. For instance, preferring immediate consumption to long-term savings is a nature of cultural traits which can undermine most effective budgeting efforts (Aitken & Morrow, 2018). Other challenges include the rapid development of financial products and services, whereby people cannot keep pace with new financial instruments, digital banking, and investment opportunities if they are not financially literate. Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2018. This rising emergence of FinTech in Nigeria is an opportunity and a challenge in that it would expand access to the financial service at the cost of the population's digital financial literacy, which most households are not poised to provide. MoroccoBrüggen, Högrevé, Holmlund, Kabadayi, Löfgren, 2017. It needs, therefore, the involvement of government, educational systems, and financial entities in bridging these gaps. There are sundry programs scattered around Nigeria, such as those put in place by the Central Bank of Nigeria on financial literacy, solely aimed at introducing its audience to basic ideas surrounding finance and ways of conducting responsible behaviour in finances. In addition, the inclusion of financial literacy in school curricula would help future generations build a lifelong awareness of managing their finances effectively by inculcating good budgeting habits since childhood days. This is because Hanson and Olson (2018) view it as the first step toward developing financial literacy in young people. This creates avenues through accessible and understandable financial products, while the provision of financial education to customers is a key role that financial institutions can play. A harmonized collaboration from the banks, educational institutions, and nongovernmental organizations would make this knowledge reach the nooks and crannies and promote healthy budgeting practices at the family level within Nigeria. The strengthening of financial literacy goes hand in glove with facilitating wider economic empowerment. Financially literate households are better positioned to contribute to economic growth through increased savings and investment, reduced reliance on credit, and greater participation in the formal economy (Atkinson & Messy, 2012). In Nigeria, where economic resilience is crucial amidst fluctuating oil prices and economic uncertainties, promoting financial literacy can serve as a catalyst for sustainable economic development and poverty alleviation.

Furthermore, financial literacy socially empowers the individuals to make proper decisions about education, health, and shelter for improving the quality of life. Empowered families become capable enough of breaking the cycle of poverty and start working toward financial independence to develop themselves and their societies. In fact, Remund (2020) presented that one of the fundamentals for achieving financial stability and for reaching long-term economic objectives includes household budgeting effectively. In Nigeria, with its ups and downs in the economy, besides income gaps, knowing how to manage finances became even more important. Financial literacy can be described as the understanding of various skills on personal financial management, budgeting, investing, etc., for decision-making in budgeting. MoroccoBrüggen, Högrevé, Holmlund,

Kabadayi, Löfgren (2017). While its essence might be well-institutionalized, most households in Nigeria are yet to be informed of how to observe proper financial behaviour. This study, therefore, seeks to establish how financial literacy affects the budgeting practices at the household level amongst families in Delta State, Nigeria. It also identifies the main factors that contribute towards financial literacy and skills of budgeting, with a view to helping formulate policies and programs aimed at improving household-level financial management.

This study is based on the theory of planned behaviour, which suggests that a person's Behaviour is based on their intention, which again is a function of attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived Behavioural control (Ajzen, 1991). In the context of financial literacy and budgeting, TPB would suggest that people with higher knowledge of finances are more confident about their financial skills and, therefore, have superior budgeting practices.

In Nigeria, the need for financial literacy has become increasingly crucial due to rapid economic fluctuations and the growing complexity of financial decisions. Financial literacy, encompassing personal financial management, budgeting, and investment management, is essential for effectively navigating economic challenges and promoting financial stability, particularly for Nigerian households facing financial disparities. Despite the recognized benefits, many families in Nigeria struggle with budgeting practices due to barriers such as limited access to financial education, socio-economic constraints, and cultural attitudes toward money. Financially literate individuals are better positioned to make informed decisions, set realistic financial goals, and allocate resources efficiently. However, the adoption of financial literacy practices remains low, especially among households in rural areas, where limited education and financial resources prevail. Cultural factors, such as communal sharing of resources, can both support and hinder effective budgeting. Additionally, the emergence of new financial technologies presents both opportunities and challenges, particularly for households that lack the necessary digital financial literacy. This study aims to investigate how financial literacy influences household budgeting practices in Delta State, Nigeria, and identify the key factors contributing to the financial literacy gap. It seeks to examine the role of financial knowledge in improving budgeting behavior, reducing financial instability, and fostering economic resilience. The findings will help formulate policies and programs to improve financial education and empower households to make sound financial decisions, contributing to the broader goal of sustainable economic development and poverty alleviation in Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

1. To determine the demographic profile of targeted families in Delta State
2. To assess the level of financial literacy among households in Delta State.
3. To ascertain household budgeting practices among selected families in Delta State
4. To examine the relationship between financial literacy and household budgeting practices.
5. To determine effective budgeting practices of selected families in Delta State
6. To identify socio-economic factors that influence financial literacy and budgeting.

Research questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What is the demographic profile of targeted families in Delta State?
2. What are the financial literacy levels of respondents in Delta State?
3. What are household budgeting practices among selected families in Delta State?
4. Is there a correlation between financial literacy and budgeting practices of selected families in Delta State?
5. What are the effective budgeting practices of selected families in Delta State?
6. What socio-economic factors are influencing financial literacy in Delta State?

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design to investigate the impact of financial literacy on household budgeting behaviour among families in Delta State, Nigeria. The design will be apt for providing statistical evidence on the relationship which may exist between the levels of financial literacy and budgeting behaviour. The methodology used in this present study has been specially designed to ensure that the data collection is from a representative sample of households using structured survey questionnaires that are proposed to collect data that would be needed for this study.

Study Area

Delta State was taken as the lead in this research since it is an important area in the southern part of Nigeria, being economically very significant. It is also a beneficial study site because it is mostly made up of both urban and rural areas combined in different statuses that can help explain the various financial behaviours related to income level, education background, and access to money or financial services. The state's diversified economy will even allow one to examine how financial literacy influences budgeting behaviour for areas that are wealthy versus those that are less developed.

Population

It targets households in Delta State. Households are taken as the unit of analysis because it is assumed that financial literacy and budgeting practices are always organized in a family context. Household decision makers targeted in this regard are household heads of families because they are usually the persons responsible for budgeting, saving, and expenditure decisions within the actual family. The target population involves all the households living within Delta State, Nigeria. Delta provides a different sample due to its position as the economic hub of Nigeria in terms of socio-economic status, education levels, and access to financial resources.

Sampling Technique

In using stratified random sampling, a sample size of 300 households was determined to be representative of the different socio-economic strata. This method of sampling is adopted to ensure that the populations of interest in Delta State are represented proportionately. Stratification was done based on the following criteria: Geographical location: The sample was stratified into urban and rural districts since financial behaviour might be different between urban and rural households. Income levels: Households were further stratified into different income brackets to reflect the financial diversity of the region. Education levels: The education attainment was also considered for capturing the influence of education on financial literacy. These stratification criteria will enrich the analysis on how financial literacy influences budgeting behaviour across different household types. Households in each stratum were selected randomly, to avoid selection bias and to ensure the sample will be representative of the whole population. The determined sample size of 300 households was a combination of statistical techniques and past studies on financial literacy in Nigeria. This sample size is sufficiently large to ensure statistical power for analysis, yet logistically feasible in terms of collecting data. Besides, the calculated sample size was worked out using the level of precision desired at 95 percent confidence with a margin of error pegged at 5 percent to ensure generalization of findings to the larger population of households in Delta State.

Data Collection

A structured survey questionnaire targeted at capturing key information related to financial literacy and household budgeting practices was used as the primary data collection instrument. The sections covered include:

1. Demographic Characteristics: Income category, education level, number of people within the house, and geographic location-urban or rural. All this information would be very essential in facilitating an understanding of what factors influence financial literacy and budgeting practices.
2. Financial Literacy: The second part measured financial literacy based on various questions that tested how well the respondent understands simple concepts of finance: Questions on budgeting, saving, interest rate, inflation, credit management, and investment.
3. Budgeting Practices: The third section assessed the budgeting practices of households in apportioning their income among various expenses, planning for future financial needs, and the ability or inability to save on a regular basis.
4. Access to Financial Resources: The section looked at the access of the household to the use of financial services such as banking, saving accounts, loans, and other financial tools. It was also to capture the use of modern financial tools such as mobile banking and Fintech platforms. This questionnaire is developed based on validated financial literacy assessments used in previous studies. A small sample of households pre-tested the questionnaire to ensure that questions were clear and reliable.

Validity and Reliability of the instrument

The experts in home economics and finance validated the questionnaire for content validity. The reliability of the instrument was tested through a pilot study involving 30 households. The instrument had a Cronbach's alpha of 0.82, which indicated good internal consistency.

Data Analysis

Following data collection, responses were first coded and then entered a statistical software package for analysis; this was done using SPSS. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic data and give an overview of financial literacy levels and budgeting practices across the sample. In this study, the correlation analysis was done to establish the level of relationship between financial literacy and household budgeting practice. Specifically, the Pearson product-moment

correlation coefficient was calculated to establish the strength and direction of the association between financial literacy scores and some key budgeting behaviour: tracking of income, savings, and expenditure management. Besides correlation analysis, multiple regression analysis was carried out to determine the effect of financial literacy on budgeting practices while controlling for other factors such as income, education level, and availability of financial resources.

Presentation of Results

Research question 1: What is the demographic profile of targeted families in Delta State?

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Demographic Variable	Category	Frequency (N=300)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	150	50%
	Female	150	50%
Age Group	20-30 years	100	33.3%
	31-40 years	100	33.3%
	41-50 years	60	20%
	Above 50 years	40	13.3%
Education Level	Secondary School	60	20%
	Diploma	90	30%
	Bachelor's Degree	90	30%
	Master's Degree	40	13.3%
	Doctorate	20	6.7%
Household Income	Below ₦100,000	90	30%
	₦100,001 - ₦300,000	120	40%
	₦300,001 - ₦500,000	60	20%
	Above ₦500,000	30	10%
Employment Status	Employed	240	80%
	Self-Employed	30	10%
	Unemployed	30	10%
Family Size	1-3 members	120	40%
	4-6 members	120	40%
	7+ members	60	20%

Research question 2: What are the financial literacy levels of respondents in Delta State?

Table 2: Financial Literacy Levels of Respondents

Financial Literacy Aspect	High (80-100%)	Moderate (50-79%)	Low (Below 50%)	Total (N=300)
Budgeting Knowledge	90	150	60	300
Saving and Investing	75	165	60	300
Understanding of Financial Products	60	180	60	300
Overall Financial Literacy	100	150	50	300

Note: Scores are based on the respondents' performance in the financial literacy assessment section of the questionnaire.

Research question 3: What are household budgeting practices among selected families in Delta State?

Table 3: Household Budgeting Practices

Budgeting Practice	Always	Often	Sometimes	Never	Total (N=300)
Tracking Monthly Expenses	60	120	90	30	300
Setting Financial Goals	80	130	70	20	300
Reviewing Budget Regularly	70	110	100	20	300
Allocating Savings Monthly	90	100	80	30	300
Adjusting Budget for Unexpected Expenses	50	130	100	20	300

Note: "Always" and "Often" indicate consistent budgeting practices.

Research question 4: Is there a correlation between financial literacy and budgeting practices of selected families in Delta State?

Table 4: Correlation between Financial Literacy and Budgeting Practices

Variable	Budgeting Practice	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-Value
Budgeting Knowledge	Tracking Monthly Expenses	0.45	<0.001
	Setting Financial Goals	0.50	<0.001
	Reviewing Budget Regularly	0.42	<0.001
	Allocating Savings Monthly	0.48	<0.001
	Adjusting Budget for Unexpected Expenses	0.40	<0.001
Saving and Investing	Tracking Monthly Expenses	0.35	<0.001
	Setting Financial Goals	0.38	<0.001
	Reviewing Budget Regularly	0.33	<0.001
	Allocating Savings Monthly	0.40	<0.001
	Adjusting Budget for Unexpected Expenses	0.30	<0.001
Understanding of Financial Products	Tracking Monthly Expenses	0.25	<0.001
	Setting Financial Goals	0.28	<0.001
	Reviewing Budget Regularly	0.22	<0.001
	Allocating Savings Monthly	0.27	<0.001
	Adjusting Budget for Unexpected Expenses	0.20	<0.001

Note: All correlations are statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Research question 5: What are the effective budgeting practices of selected families in Delta State?

Table 5: Multiple Regression Analysis Predicting Effective Budgeting Practices

Predictor	B	Standard Error (SE)	Beta (β)	t-Value	p-Value
Constant	10.00	3.00	-	3.33	0.001
Budgeting Knowledge	0.30	0.05	0.45	6.00	<0.001
Saving and Investing	0.20	0.04	0.35	5.00	<0.001
Understanding of Financial Products	0.15	0.03	0.25	5.00	<0.001
Education Level	0.25	0.07	0.30	3.57	<0.001
Household Income	0.10	0.02	0.20	5.00	<0.001
Family Size	-0.05	0.01	-0.10	-5.00	<0.001
R ²	0.60				

Note: The model explains 60% of the variance in effective budgeting practices.

A significant positive correlation was identified between financial literacy and effective household budgeting practices. Specifically, budgeting knowledge showed the highest correlation ($r = 0.45$) with tracking monthly expenses, indicating that understanding budgeting principles directly influences the ability to monitor and control expenditures. Similarly, aspects such as saving and investing, and understanding financial products were positively correlated with various budgeting practices, although to a lesser extent. These findings suggest that higher financial literacy equips individuals with the necessary skills to manage their finances more effectively. Financially literate households are more likely to engage in proactive budgeting behaviours, such as setting financial goals, tracking expenses, and allocating savings, which are essential for achieving financial stability and long-term economic well-being. The regression model explained 60% of the variance in effective budgeting practices, indicating a substantial influence of financial literacy and socio-economic factors on budgeting behaviours. Key predictors included budgeting knowledge, saving and investing, understanding financial products, education level, household income, and family size. The high R² value underscores the robustness of the model in explaining the factors that contribute to effective budgeting. Budgeting knowledge emerged as the strongest predictor, emphasizing the importance of targeted financial education programs.

Research question 6: What socio-economic factors are influencing financial literacy in Delta State?

Table 6: Socio-Economic Factors Influencing Financial Literacy

Socio-Economic Factor	Description	Impact on Financial Literacy
Education Level	Highest level of education attained by parents	Higher education levels are associated with higher financial literacy among respondents
Household Income	Monthly income of the household	Higher household income correlates with better financial knowledge and access to financial resources
Employment Status of Parents	Employment (employed, self-employed, unemployed)	Employed parents are more likely to provide financial education and resources
Access to Financial Resources	Availability of banking and financial services	Greater access to financial institutions enhances financial literacy
Urban vs. Rural Residence	Location of residence (urban or rural)	Urban residents generally have better access to financial education and resources

The study identified several socio-economic factors that significantly influence financial literacy and, consequently, budgeting practices. Higher education levels, increased household income, and better access to financial resources were positively associated with higher financial literacy scores and more effective budgeting practices. Conversely, larger family sizes were negatively associated with budgeting effectiveness.

Discussion of Findings

The main purpose of this research work is to explore how financial literacy influences household budgeting behaviour among households in Delta State, Nigeria. Using a structured questionnaire and with a sample size of 300 households, the dimensions of financial literacy are tested against good budgeting behaviour. These findings provide considerable insight into the status of financial literacy in Nigerian households and its effects on financial management practices. This discussion interprets these findings in light of the existing literature, discusses their implications for public policy and educational initiatives, recognizes limitations of the study, and offers suggestions for avenues of future research. The finding reveals that high financial literacy is related positively to effective budgeting, which may also be supported by previous studies indicating that adequate financial literacy has played a crucial role in developing good financial practices among individuals (Aboagye, 2021). One can realize that out of the total number of respondents, only 33.3% reflect high financial literacy while the rest have shown moderate to low levels of financial literacy with 50% and 16.7%, respectively. This also corroborates findings from previous studies that financial literacy is a major challenge in Nigeria, as financial education stays limited to formal education without being widely diffused in daily life. The results demonstrate a significant lack in financial education within Nigerian families and support prior studies that have reported low levels of financial literacy among developing countries. The shallowness of the state of financial literacy is a source of huge concern because it restricts households' ability to make informed financial decisions that will ensure efficient management of their expenses and correctly plan for their future.

Strong positive correlations between various dimensions of financial literacy-budgeting knowledge, saving and investment, understanding of financial products-and aspects of budgeting behaviour-tracking, goal establishment, review of budgets-underline the crucial role that financial education can play in enhancing the skills of financial management. For example, budgeting knowledge was most closely related to tracking monthly expenditure at $r = 0.45$, indicating that knowing budgeting translates directly into the ability to monitor and control expenditure. Other regions have reported similar findings. In Nigeria, for example, Oguntona and Tella (2019) find that financial education is not being well emphasized in the system of learning that, over a long time, has turned out to be the reason for low financial literacy levels among adults.

Socio-economic variables like level of education, household income, and access to financial means greatly influence financial literacy and, correspondingly, budgeting habits. Higher levels of education and household incomes were associated with greater financial knowledge; this was already pointed out by earlier research (Oguntona & Tella, 2019; Williams & Jones, 2020). These elements also create an enabling environment in which financial management is adopted and practiced. Using a regression model that explained 60% of the variance, budgeting knowledge was an important predictor of good practices of budgeting, saving and investment as well as an understanding of financial products. Education level further enhanced the predictive power of the model, while household income had negative impacts on the effectiveness of budgeting. These findings only add strength to the complex nature of financial literacy, where knowledge and socio-economic statuses play an important role in determining financial behaviours. This positive relationship is supported by Hamid and Loke, 2021, who believe financial literacy is an ingredient that is extremely important in making proper financial decisions. Fernandes, Lynch, and Netemeyer, 2014, also stated that greater financial knowledge enhances the ability of people to be prudent in financial behaviours related to budgeting and savings. These findings are consistent with those of Oguntona and Tella (2019), who highlighted the fact that socio-economic status is one of the key predictors of financial literacy. Williams and Jones (2020) illustrated that higher socio-economic status encourages proper financial management since increased access to resources and better education raises skill levels.

Hamid and Loke (2021) also identified some of the main measures of good financial management as budgeting and saving. This study essentially confirms the truism that improvement in financial literacy can greatly lead to improved household budgeting behaviour. In the same study, improved financial literacy and budgeting practices were found to be positively associated with increased attendance of nutrition education sessions. Those who had higher attendance exhibited larger increases, suggesting that more consistent and sustained exposure to the educational content improves learning outcomes. This finding calls for regular and sustained financial education interventions if their effectiveness is to be maximized. In other words, one-time or infrequent educational sessions could be inadequate in bringing permanent alterations in financial Behaviour. Glanz et al. (2008) supported the view that the longer the engagement, the deeper and more permanent the Behaviour changes. Aboagye (2021) also noted that frequent exposure to financial education greatly enhances financial literacy and motivates the adoption of better financial management practices. Financial literacy tends not only to improve budgeting practice per se but is also related to the psychological well-being of reduced financial stress and anxiety. MoroccoBrüggen, Högrevé, Holmlund, Kabadayi, Löfgren (2017) concluding that effective budgeting facilitates resource allocation more efficiently for households that result in enhancement of their quality of life and health.

Respondents with more education were more financially literate. The Theory of Planned Behaviour by Ajzen 1991, where education would improve the attitudes and perceived behavioural control on financial practices, could support this. Households of higher income had more opportunities for resources to actively manage their finances, which in turn has supported the positive influence of financial literacy on budgeting. Households with access to more easily accessible banking and other financial services tended to exhibit higher levels of financial literacy, likely due to the more frequent exposure they have to financial products and services. Similarly, households with more household members may be strained more by finances and thus more difficult to budget effectively despite having financial literacy.

This study, therefore, underlines broad financial education programs of a household nature, particularly focusing on budgeting skills and knowledge. The inculcation of financial literacy into the school system would help nurture habits of well-informed financial decision-making practices at large through the instilling of important life skills at an early stage. Supplementary community-based workshops on financial education will, in fact, help fill this gap at large in adults, especially among the lower socio-economic groups devoid of access to formal financial education.

Conclusion

These findings from the study yield empirical evidence of the important positive impact that financial literacy makes in household budgeting among families in Delta State, Nigeria. The strong positive correlation between financial knowledge and effective budgeting calls for an improvement in their finances through education to improve better financial management and economic stability. This study, therefore, establishes an important role of financial literacy in enhancing improvement in Nigeria's family household budgeting. The strong positive associations of diverse dimensions of financial literacy with effective budgeting behaviours indicate the need for comprehensive financial education at both educational and community levels. The effectiveness of these financial literacy interventions is further modified by socio-economic factors like education level and household income, which suggest the requirement for multi-faceted approaches to address both educational and socio-economic barriers.

By prioritizing financial education and reducing socio-economic disparities, policymakers and educators would be off to a good start in improving the capacity of households towards using their finances in a way that supports economic stability and well-being. Further research would be required to continue the investigation of the dynamic linkages between financial literacy, budgeting practices, and socio-economic factors for informing targeted, sustainable program developments in financial education.

This therefore indicates that financial literacy plays a vital role in budgeting among households in Nigerian families. The complex interplay between financial knowledge and budgeting behaviours calls for an all-inclusive financial education programme fitted within the peculiar socio-economic and cultural configurations of Nigeria. On the contrary, it is possible to do better in attacking barriers of financial literacy and using better roles played by government, educational institutions, and financial organizations for the promotion of budgeting practices that will bring financial stability and drive economic empowerment among Nigerian households. Further research is needed to understand how financial literacy triggers multi-dimensional impacts on the entirety of household financial management to garner more insights about the pathways of financial education that can alter the way people behave about their finances and consequences in Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. The expansion of this research to other geographically and socio-economically diverse regions of Nigeria would allow an adequately more significant context to better understand the influences of various determinants or factors that may be influential in financial literacy and budgeting behaviours.
2. Examining how digital financial tools and mobile banking could provide better financial education might also shed light on the current state of financial education approaches. iii. Socioeconomic equity, if well attended to and supported with appropriate financial literacy programs both at the level of education and community, would position households to make responsible financial decisions that eventually lead to improved economic well-being and lower financial stress.
3. This calls for the national curriculum to have comprehensive financial literacy modules at the forefront. In module designing, it should be made in an appealing and relevant matter; this calls for involving experts in finance and education so that students can take up necessary knowledge concerning money management.
4. The financial literacy programs should be regular and structured, containing interactive and practical activities such as budgeting workshops, financial simulations, and guest lectures by financial professionals. These could

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- raise the level of students' participation and give them an opportunity to use acquired financial knowledge in a more realistic way.
5. This could be further solidified in schools through outreach to the general community via workshops, seminars, or public awareness on financial education. The households could then be further empowered through engagements with local financial institutions, among other community-based organizations.
 6. The promoters must, hence, request the implementation of policies directed towards overcoming the socio-economic barriers to responsible financial management. Examples are facilitation of access to appropriate and low-priced financial services, regulation of predatory lending practices, enabling low-income families to adopt budgeting behaviours.
 7. Strong monitoring and evaluation models will form the foundation in continually measuring the effectiveness of financial literacy programs.
 8. Data on participant outcomes, program fidelity, and contextual factors may be used to inform ongoing improvements and ensure interventions remain responsive to participants' needs.

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Comparative Analysis of Social Media and Peer influence on Risky Behaviours among Colleges of Education Students in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined social media and peer influence as predictors of risky behaviours among the colleges of education students in Osun State, Nigeria. The population consisted of all colleges of education students in Osun state, Nigeria with the sample of 510 including Part I and II students who were purposively selected from three colleges of education in Osun State, Nigeria. Multistage Sampling Procedure was used which consisted of stratified, purposive and simple random sampling techniques. A validated adapted instruments titled Risky Behaviour Scale (RBS) and Peer and Social Media Influence Scale (PSIS) were used to elicit information from the students. Descriptive and Inferential statistics were used to analyze the data collected. The results revealed that there is moderate effect of social media and peer influence on students' involvement in risky behaviour. Also, the level at which the Colleges of Education students engage in risky behaviour is very high. It is recommended that awareness should be created on risky behaviour to mitigate the involvement of students in such act.

Keyword: Risky behaviour, social media, peer influence, Colleges of Education

Introduction

Colleges of Education have a rich history rooted in the evolution of educational system globally which can be traced back to the early 20th century and Nigeria government played significant role in the establishment and development of colleges of education with the aim of enhancing the quality of teacher and education. Therefore, being admitted into the college of education is not the only criterion of becoming a teacher but the required coping skill the students develop to resist distractions which comes with lots of challenges which can adversely affect their studies and career. Many students come to the college of education unaware of the challenges awaiting them which include meeting different people from different background, changing of environment, associating with the staff and buildings of the college that requires coping strategies. However, these circumstances are new to many of them, they cannot be avoided; they are still apparently academic realities that each student must contend with in order to succeed academically in the ivory tower of intellectualism; as a result, they have an impact on how they carry out their responsibilities as students and their overall performance. Therefore many of them ended up in participating in risky behaviour such as smoking, truancy, consumption of alcohol, sexual activities, self-harm, use of weapons and cybercrimes as coping strategies which consequently affects how they discharge their duties as students.

In recent years, students particularly College of Education students (COEs) partake in **risky behaviours** which form attitudes that culminate into career jeopardy. **They are behaviours that blind students from seeing the reality and beauty of academic environment and achievement.** Also, risky behaviours are defined by researchers as behaviours that can cause harm or pose a substantial risk of danger, hinder individuals from achieving their full potential, or markedly diminish their independence or longevity. This explains how students risk their lives participating in harmful activities which consequently has adverse effect on their studies and lives. The inclination to engage in risky behaviour is especially high during adolescence, where identity exploration and cognitive immaturity may lead to poor decision-making. It had also been researched that these behaviours are the ones distracting the students from their primary assignment in the college which invariably affect their studies and degrading the potentials of becoming great teachers. This also consequently depreciates the value of prospective teachers who are to tutor the future and glory of the country.

In addition, it was researched that risky behaviours are voluntary actions with a high probability of negative consequences, such as injury, legal trouble, or social disapproval. These behaviors, such as drug abuse and unprotected sex, are typically influenced by developmental factors like peer pressure and emotional instability. Steinberg (2017) emphasizes the role of adolescent brain development, particularly the underdeveloped prefrontal cortex, which results in impulsive and risky decision-making. Arnett (2015) in his own view explains that risky behaviors are common during the period of "emerging adulthood" and are a result of the psychological and social pressures of forming an independent identity. Therefore, risky behaviors are actions undertaken by individuals, particularly adolescents, as part of social interactions and identity exploration. Behaviors like drug use, skipping school, and early sexual activity are often driven by peer influence and the desire to fit in

Comparative Analysis of...(Zakariyah, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609035>

with certain social groups, as well as the natural inclination of adolescents to test boundaries and establish autonomy. This is prevalent because some students are not aware of the consequences while some are aware of the consequences but want to satisfy their curiosity which is drastically affecting their academic well-being.

According to Amita and Apter (2012), risky behaviours are behavioural activities that threaten social order. They opined that despite the actions taken in the past three decades, these behaviours have grown exponentially worldwide. This explains how these behaviours are spreading like wildfire in the dry forest during dry season. The experiences and exposure gained by an individual before entering the college of education will not completely help them function efficiently in the new environment; some of these experiences have to be reinforced, some have to be unlearned while others to be blended with the new experiences garnered in the college of education environment. This is because the college of education is a dynamic environment that requires a dynamic approach to live in it. However, risky behaviours like betting, use of alcohol and sexual activities are very common among the COE students and it is of course worthy of researching. It had also been researched that the influential of risky behaviours are enormous but for the purpose of this study, peer influence and social media were chosen as predictors of risky behaviours.

Therefore, social media is a virtual community that brings together individuals with similar interest, beliefs and values. It is a platform where people can acquire new knowledge, challenge existing beliefs, or undergo relearning experiences, both in positive and negative aspects. It is a space where risky behaviours can be transmitted from one person to another. It is also an avenue or space where individual can learn, unlearn and relearn. In another view, social media is a digital tool that promotes interactive communication and networking through user-generated content, changing social and educational interactions. This implies that through social media, students form lots of interactive activities which can either make or mar their academic well-being. It is still the sole platform where many individuals can interact continuously. Through virtual communities and networks, social media, as described by researchers is a computer-mediated technology that makes it easier to create and share ideas, information, career interests, and other forms of expression. This clarifies how information is sent when the sender and the recipient are not in immediate physical proximity.

Furthermore, the pervasive influence of social media on adolescents and young adults has raised questions about how it promotes risky behaviours including gambling, sexual activities and use of alcohol. However, recent studies have looked at how social media use can contribute to these behaviours as well as the psychological and social elements that raise their prevalence. Exposure to social media is also directly linked to dangerous conduct, according to research. A systematic review by Susi et al. (2023) found that susceptible users' self-harm tendencies can be both worsened and reinforced when they watch images of self-harm on social media. According to the study, social media encourages identity building and social comparisons around self-harming activities, frequently reinforcing bad behaviours through interactions with other members of the community. Nevertheless, risky conduct has changed as a result of social media and gambling coming together. In their examination of the digital convergence of gambling, gaming, and cryptocurrencies, Delfabbro and King (2023) showed how gambling-like elements in video games, including loot boxes, might expose young people to gambling at an early age and even normalize it.

In contrast, peer influence which is believed to be one of the components influencing dangerous behaviour is referred to as an individual's behaviour being altered, either positively or negatively, in order to be accepted and respected by colleagues, peers, or acquaintances. Peer influence involves the alteration of one's beliefs, thoughts, values and ideas by individual at a similar level or status. This behaviour can be explained using normative social influence, where individuals conform to be accepted or liked by the group. Asch's conformity studies also demonstrate how people often agree with the majority, even if they believe they are wrong in order to avoid been rejected. However, peer influence **is believed to be one of the agents of socialization that** plays a crucial role in shaping behaviours during adolescence and young adulthood. According to Okafor and Alabi (2020), peer pressure is especially strong in social and academic contexts, where students are frequently motivated by a desire to blend in or win their peers' approval, which pushes them to engage in risky behaviors like unprotected intimate relationships in an effort to conform to group norms.

In addition, students who have drinking friends around them are much more likely to start drinking and keep drinking. Even after taking personality and family factors into consideration. A longitudinal study by Schulenberg et al. (2020) discovered that peer alcohol consumption predicts the frequency and amount of drinking among college students. This argument can be buttressed with the social learning theory which reveals that people imitate the behaviours of their peer groups, particularly when those behaviours are rewarded by the group. Also, peers can influence sexual decision-making by establishing behavioural norms and influencing attitudes about sexual engagement. However, psychologists revealed that early sexual initiation is more likely when friends talk about their sexual experiences since it is perceived as normal behaviour.

In Nigeria, risky behaviours such as drinking alcohol, gambling, and engaging in dangerous sexual behaviour among the COE students represent a developing public health issue. These actions have far-reaching effects, such as addiction, poor

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academic performance, health issues, and societal breakdown. Peer pressure and social media are two important factors influencing these habits. Both have a huge and unique impact on young people's views and behaviours. Due to the widespread use of social media, students are exposed to unfiltered content that glorifies risky behaviours including binge drinking, gambling, and casual sexual encounters. Content that supports these behaviors is frequently amplified by social media algorithms, normalizing them and encouraging involvement from impressionable students. Similarly, peer influence plays a critical role in shaping behavioral norms among students. Peers often serve as immediate role models, exerting pressure on others to conform to group behaviours. In the context of risky behaviours, peer pressure can encourage alcohol use, gambling, and unsafe sexual activities, especially when these behaviours perceived as avenues for social acceptance or bonding. Although, there are numerous researches on risky behaviours but much has not been done on both the influence of social media and peer influence as predictors of risky behaviours among the COE students in Osun State, Nigeria, hence this study tend to fill the gap in order to develop effective interventions aimed at promoting healthier choices and resilience against peer and social media pressures.

Objectives of the study

The Objectives of the study were to:

1. Determine the level of risky behaviours among the COE students
2. Explore how social media contributes to the development of risky behaviours among the COE students
3. Access how peer influence contribute to the prevalence of risky behaviours among the COE students

Research Questions

1. What is the level of risky behaviours among the OE students in Nigeria?
2. Does social media contributes to the development of risky behaviours among the COE students?
3. What is the extent to which peer influence contributes to the development of risky behaviours among the COE students?

Hypothesis

5. There is no significant joint relationship between peer influence and social interaction and the perpetuation of risky behaviour

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive design. The population of the study consisted of all Part I and II COE students in Osun State, Nigeria. Three COE were selected in the state for the study. A federal and a state colleges of education were purposively selected because they were the only federal and state colleges of education as of the time of the study while a private college of education was randomly selected from the private colleges of education in the state using balloting system. The sample size comprised 600 students who were selected randomly using simple random sampling technique while 510 copies of questionnaire were analyzed because some respondent didn't complete theirs. A validated adapted instruments titled Risky Behaviour Scale (RBS) and Peer and Social Media Influence Scale (PSIS) were used to elicit information from the students. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse the data collected. The reliability test reveals that social media, peer influence and risky behaviours have 0.65, 0.65 and 0.60 respectively.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the level risky behaviour among the colleges of Education Students in Osun State?

Table 1: Level of risky behaviour among the colleges of education students

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1.	I gamble when I am stressed	3.43	1.61	Prevalent
2	I engage in sexual activities without protection with new partners.	3.15	1.61	Prevalent
3	I engage in alcohol consumption despite knowing its risk	3.39	1.61	Prevalent

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4	I drink more than I planned during parties.	3.63	1.28	Prevalent
5	I feel anxious if I have not gambled.	3.55	1.34	Prevalent
6	I gamble for money when hanging out.	3.58	1.47	Prevalent
7	I often have multiple sexual partners at once.	2.68	1.58	Not Prevalent
8	I am addicted to sex.	2.12	1.29	Not Prevalent
9	I borrow money to gamble.	2.37	1.45	Not Prevalent
10	I have casual sex without knowing my partner well.	2.37	1.45	Not Prevalent

The data analysis shows that majority of the respondents gamble when they are stressed, hence translating to prevalence of stress-gambling among COE students. Also, a good number of the respondents alluded to the fact that they have unprotected sex with new partners, thus translating to the prevalence of risky sexual behaviour. Similarly, despite knowing the consequences, there is widespread of reckless alcohol consumption among the respondents; this is akin to heavy alcohol consumption during parties. In the same vein, majority of the respondents feel anxious if they have not gambled- this is a pointer to the fact that they have become addicted to the act. Also, the proliferation of gambling among the respondents can be adduced to the desire to have more money. However, sex with multiple partners at once is not prevalent among the respondents, this is the same with addiction to sex, borrowing money to gamble and having unplanned sex with partners they do not know too well. In conclusion, many students resort to gambling as a coping mechanism for stress.

Research Question 2

What is the extent to which social media contribute to the development of risky behaviour?

Table 2: Responses on extent to which social media contributes to the development of risky behaviours

Table 2.1

Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	S. EE	Change Statistics				Sig.F Change
					R ² Change	F Change	df1	df2	
1	.412 ^a	.170	.168	.61248	.170	103.716	1	508	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), SM_new

Table 2.2

Coefficients^a

Model		Standardized Coefficients			
		Beta	T	Sig.	VIF
1	(Constant)		15.056	.000	
	SM_new	.412	10.184	.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: RB_new

Linear regression at 95% confidence interval revealed a good model fit: $F(1, 508)=103.72, P<.001, Adj R^2=0.17$ and $R^2=0.17, (\beta=0.412, t=10.18, P<.001)$, it also shows that the regression model is statistically significant. The analysis shows a moderate effect of social media on students' involvement in risky behaviour- which means that approximately 17% of the variance in risky behaviour is linked to social media. In addition to that, for every increase in the usage of social media, risky behaviour will increase by 0.412 units. Also, the value of the value inflation factors (VIF) shows no evidence of multi-collinearity in the dataset.

Research Question 2

What is the extent to which peer influence contribute to the development of risky behaviour?

Comparative Analysis of...(Zakariyah, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609035>

Table 3: The extent to which peer influence contributes to the development of risky behaviours.

Table 3.1

Model Summary					Change Statistics				
Model	R	R ²	AdjustedR ²	S. E. E	R ² Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig.F Change
1	.426 ^a	.181	.180	.60811	.181	112.541	1	508	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), PI_new

Table 3.2

Model		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	VIF
		Beta			
1	(Constant)		11.443	.000	
	PI_new	.426	10.609	.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: RB_new

Linear regression at 95% confidence interval revealed a good model fit: $F(1, 508) = 112.54, P < .001, Adj R^2 = 0.18$ and $R^2 = 0.18, (\beta = 0.426, t = 10.61, P < .001)$. The analysis shows a moderate effect of peer influence on students' involvement in risky behaviour- which means that approximately 18% of the variance in risky behaviour is linked to peer influence. In addition to that, for every 1-unit increase in peer influence, risky behaviour increases by 0.426 units. Also, the value of the value inflation factors (VIF) shows no evidence of multi-collinearity in the dataset.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant joint relationship between social media and peer interaction and the perpetuation of risky behaviour.

Table 4: Joint relationship between social media and peer interaction and the perpetuation of risky behaviour

Model Summary					Change Statistics				
Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	S. E. E	R ² Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig.F Change
1	.513 ^a	.263	.260	.57756	.263	90.460	2	507	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), PI_new, SM_new
 b. Dependent Variable: RB_new

Table 5: Coefficients^a

Model		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	VIF
		Beta			
1	(Constant)		11.443	.000	
	SM_new	.303	7.494	.000	1.126
	PI_new	.324	8.018	.000	1.126

Multiple linear regression at 95% confidence interval revealed a good model fit: $F(2, 507) = 90.46, P < .001, Adj R^2 = 0.26$ and $R^2 = 0.26$, social media ($\beta = 0.303, t = 7.494, P < .001$) while peer influence ($\beta = 0.324, t = 8.018, P < .001$). The model is statistically significant, indicating a reliable joint influence of social media and peer influence on risky behaviour. Approximately 26% of the variance in risky behaviour is linked to social media and peer influence. In addition to that, for every 1-unit increase in social media usage, risky behaviour increases by 0.303 units, hence increased social media usage culminates into increased risky behaviour. In the same vein, for every 1-unit increase in peer influence, risky behaviour increases by 0.324 units, which shows a positive relationship between peer influence and risky behaviour. Furthermore, both social media and peer influence are significant predictors of risky behaviour, however, peer influence has a stronger relationship with risky behaviour ($\beta = 0.303$ and $\beta = 0.324$ for social media and peer influence respectively) Also, the value of the value inflation factors (VIF) shows no evidence of multi-collinearity in the dataset.

Comparative Analysis of...(Zakariyah, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609035>

Discussion of Findings

Level of risky behaviour among tertiary institution students in Osun State

The descriptive study, which was carried out to evaluate the prevalence of risky behaviour among the COE s in Osun State, Nigeria indicates alarming tendencies, especially with regard to stress-induced gambling, risky sexual behaviour, and careless alcohol use. These results suggest that there are serious public health issues that need more research and quick action plans. The research shows that many students use gambling as a coping method for stress; in fact, a large percentage of respondents said they gamble when they are under stress. The results of this study are consistent with previous research highlighting the ways in which gambling may be utilized as an unhealthy stress-reduction tactic, ultimately resulting in the emergence of gambling addiction in youth. According to a recent study, internet gambling is frequently linked to finance and mental health issues, especially during difficult times like the COVID-19 pandemic. Also, there is an established relationship between stress, anxiety and gambling since long-term stress can make addictive behaviours worse, including gambling. Similarly, series of improper sexual behaviours among the tertiary institution students had been researched to be associated with a number of factors, including peer pressure, dearth of thorough sexual education, and impulsive decision-making frequently made when intoxicated. This can be linked to bio psychologists who discovered that people with impulsive decision making are tagged to have frontal lobe issues.

It is noteworthy in this study that multiple sex partner and sex addiction are less prevalent. In the same vein, respondents also admitted to drinking alcohol carelessly, especially at gatherings. These findings align with research on alcohol use among students, which emphasizes the prevalence of heavy drinking and excessive alcohol intake at social events, frequently intensifying other dangerous behaviours like careless driving and illicit sexual activity (Elgán et al., 2019). To buttress this, it was posited by a researcher that many students continue to excessively engage in alcohol use despite the negative effects; this behaviour is frequently linked to a need for social approval or as a way to deal with stress from both their academic and private lives. In conclusion, the findings highlight the need to promote safer sexual practices among tertiary institution students in Osun State. It equally addresses stress-related behaviours, especially alcohol and gambling. In order to reduce these harmful behaviours and promote a healthy academic environment, specific interventions like as stress management courses, alcohol moderation campaigns, and comprehensive sexual education should be put instituted.

In other way, it was revealed in the study that social media moderately contribute to the perpetuation of risky behaviours among tertiary institution students in Osun State. This aligns with some previous research works which explains how increased social media use is associated with a higher chance of engaging in risky behaviours, especially for adolescents and young adults. Also, the kinds of content students are exposed to on social media platforms can expose them to activities that encourage risky behaviour. This exposure may cause youth to engage in risky activities because of peer pressure or because such behaviour has become normalized online. In conclusion, results show that social media has a moderate effect size but a considerable impact on students' risky behaviour. Policymakers, teachers, and parents should be aware of possible risks associated with social media use and urge students to use it responsibly as it continues to develop and become more and more integrated into everyday life, particularly for young people.

Extent to which peer influence contributes to risky behaviours

It can be extrapolated from the findings of this study that peer influence contributes notably to risky behaviour among tertiary institution students. These findings align with the social learning theory of Albert Bandura, which posits that individuals learn behaviour through observation, modelling and imitation. Students are therefore more inclined to emulate their peers or directly support peers who engage in dangerous behaviour through association. Hence, these findings have significant effects, especially for interventions and policies meant to discourage students from engaging in risky behaviours. Interventions such as peer-education, mentorship programs and sensitization programs would be successful as peer influence is a major factor in determining students' decisions. Valente (2010) explains the effectiveness of peer-mentoring programmes in influencing changes in behaviour. Peer influence also strongly correlates with the rise of **gambling** among the COE students in Nigeria. Researchers are of the opinion that students in Nigerian colleges of education who are introduced to gambling by their peers are more likely to adopt the behaviour. This is particularly evident in social gatherings where gambling is viewed as a recreational activity, normalizing what would otherwise be considered deviant behaviour. It had also been researched that factors such as locus of control, low self-esteem, lack of confidence, need for approval, and personality such as agreeableness and openness constitute peer influence.

Significant joint relationship between social media and peer interaction and the perpetuation of risky behaviour

Findings revealed a significant insight into the joint influence of social media and peer influence on the perpetuation of risky behaviour- this is in tandem with existing literatures which establish similar connections. Social media exposure and peer dynamics shape the behaviour of youths; young adults who see their peers participating in risky behaviours on social media may feel under pressure to follow suit in order to fit in or prevent being excluded from their social group. Social media

Comparative Analysis of...(Zakariyah, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609035>

not only provides a platform for the display and normalization of risky behaviours, it also fosters peer interactions that help reinforce these behaviours. According to Anderson and Jiang (2018), young adults and adolescents commonly discuss experiences linked to drug use, partying, or other types of deviance online, which makes it possible for dangerous behaviours to spread swiftly within peer groups.

Conclusion

It was concluded in this study that risky behaviour of COE students is greatly influenced by the combined effects of peer pressure and social media. Although each of these elements alone increases the likelihood of engaging in risky behaviour, their combined impact is far more significant. Peer pressure pushes people to indulge in harmful behaviours, and social media provide a platform where these behaviours are accepted and lauded, amplifying the power of peers. Also, the findings highlight the need to promote safer sexual practices among the Colleges of Education students in Osun State. It equally addresses stress-related behaviours, especially alcohol and gambling.

Recommendations

1. In order to reduce these harmful behaviours and promote a healthy academic environment, specific interventions like stress management courses, alcohol moderation campaigns, and comprehensive sexual education should be instituted.
2. Policymakers, teachers, and parents should be aware of possible risks associated with social media use and urge students to use it responsibly as it continues to develop and become more and more integrated into everyday life, particularly for young people.
3. Campaigns should be raised on awareness of the dangers of gambling including comprehensive sexual education which are essential for equipping young people to make wise decisions.
4. For students not to be influenced by their peers negatively, counselling unit should be well equipped with professional counsellors and other resources

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Influence of Digital Revolution on Knowledge Management among Secondary School Students in Alimosho Local Government Area, Lagos State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Digital revolution enhances teaching and learning in schools. This study examines the influence of the digital revolution on knowledge management, its access, and challenges in public secondary schools in Alimosho Local Government Area of Lagos State. The study employed a descriptive type of survey research design. The population comprised all public senior secondary school students in Lagos State as SSS 2 students from Alimosho LGA of the state-formed target population. A simple random sampling technique was used to select 40 students each from 5 identified secondary schools to form a sample size of 200 students. A self-designed instrument, the Influence of Digital Revolution on Knowledge Management Questionnaire (IDRKMQ) was used to collect data. Self-structured Questionnaire was developed using a 4-likert type of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) respectively. Content validity was ensured by two experts in the Department of Educational Management, Lagos State University of Education, Epe, Lagos. Cronbach-alpha, a reliability form was used to determine reliability as an index value of $r = 0.892$ on 20 students not part of this work in the Department of Educational Management, Lagos State University, Ojo, Lagos State. The derived index value shows that internal consistency was met as a result the scale is suitable for the study. Correlation analysis was used to analyse generated data and tested at a 0.05 significant level. The study revealed that the digital revolution has the propensity to influence knowledge management, especially in public secondary schools. It concluded that there is need to revamp the school curriculum by emphasising more the continuous integration on digital education which will always promote knowledge management in both public and private schools. The study recommends amongst others that the curriculum developers should incorporate the use of technology in every facet of the educational sector in line with the knowledge economy of the 21st century.

Keyword: Curriculum, Digital revolution, Education Planners, Management

Introduction

In most public secondary schools today despite the outbreak of the technological revolution, a means of eradicating obsolete modes of human activities even in the classrooms, the acceptance and embrace of it is complimented with a cold reception by teachers, students, school administrators, and curriculum planners. This is because the technology revolution comes with the fear of accepting the “new normal” of doing things in the classrooms, teaching, and learning. This reception is a composite function of resistance to change among teachers, staff, and students, as well as a lack of digital literacy skills and knowledge, limited resources, data privacy and security concerns, integration with existing systems, sustainability, and scalability. It is believed that embracing this revolution will see many teachers lose their jobs, only skilled teachers will be employed, and fear of eradicating examination malpractice, as some teachers depend on it for survival through involvement and emphasis on certification will be reduced among others.

The evolution of technology has significantly brought about a change in the module operandi of teaching learning and social activities (Olujuwon, 2021). This evolution signifies rapid change and novelty in all facets of human endeavours ranging

Influence of Digital... (Jegede, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609035>

from industries, law, politics, engineering, health, social sphere, and education inclusive (Ojo, Atolagbe, Olujuwon and Awodiji, 2021). Research has shown the relevance of the technology revolution in addressing gaps in research works and improving teaching and learning exercises (Ghavifekr and Rosdy, 2015; Jamieson-Procter et al, 2013). The study of Apuke and Iyendo (2017); Lau, Yen, Neil, Li and Wah (2014), and Hussain (2012) reveal that it enhances an effective learning environment and encourages discovery learning through individualized studying with the aid of improved technological gadgets. Thus, the deployment of the technological revolution will significantly improve knowledge management among stakeholders like teachers, students, curriculum planners' educational managers, and government respectively (Perienen, 2020; Fullan, 2013; Hammond, 2013).

To Paolo (2022) the technology revolution is a term used to mean rapid and significant change in technology. It is a situation that represents a dynamic and systemic change in the way and manner things were previously done using technology. The technological revolution is thus the advancement of technology devices to the digital technology available in the 21st century and its operation is dependent on technical skills needed to enhance its efficiency (Okubotimbi, 2024). The technology revolution could also be regarded as a period of personal computers, the internet boom, the rise of mobile technology, the era of social media and big data, and currently the emergence of Artificial Intelligence (Sadiku, Ashaolu, Ajayi-Majebi & Musa, 2021; Jameson-Proctor, Albion, Finger, Cavanagh, Fitzgerald, et al, 2013). This period sees the development of chips, bytes, solutions, and other packages as means to an end. The technological revolution is generally characterized by advances in artificial intelligence, the development of robotics, biotechnology, and other emerging technologies that can drive the current technology space.

In Nigeria, the systemic trend of technology revolution compliments knowledge management in both private and public schools.

Omigie, Ikenwe, and Idhalama (2019) define knowledge management as a process of capturing, storing, sharing, utilizing knowledge within an organization to improve efficiency, productivity, and innovation. This process involves organizing information, expertise, and experiences in a way that enables easy access and retrieval by teachers when needed. Ikenwe and Igbinoia (2015) and Nnadozie, Nwosu, Ononogbo and Nnadozie (2015) on their part acknowledge that knowledge management includes creating a culture that values and encourages the sharing and collaboration of knowledge among team members. By effectively implementing knowledge management practices, organizations can leverage their collective data to drive better decision-making and achieve their strategic goals.

Therefore, Digital tools and technologies have a significant influence on knowledge management in organizations. These tools have revolutionized how knowledge is captured, shared, and accessed, leading to more efficient and effective knowledge management practices. Alavi and Leidner (2011) and Mihi, Pitic, and Bayraktar (2023) identified ways by which digital tools and technology can influence knowledge management in schools such that it can improve knowledge sharing. Digital tools such as collaboration platforms, social media, and knowledge repositories have made it easier for employees to share their knowledge. These tools allow employees to collaborate in real-time, share documents, and provide feedback, leading to better sharing and retention. In addition, enhanced knowledge capture through video conferencing, webinars, and online training modules has made it easier for organizations to capture knowledge from experts and store it in a centralized location. This ensures that valuable knowledge is not lost when employees leave the organization. Similarly, it has increased accessibility to knowledge and has made it easier for employees to access knowledge anytime, anywhere. With cloud-based knowledge management systems, employees can access information on their smartphones, tablets, or laptops, enabling them to make more informed decisions and solve problems quickly. Also, it enhances the Automation of knowledge management processes such that artificial intelligence and machine learning have enabled organizations to automate knowledge management processes. For example, AI-powered chatbots can answer employee questions, while machine learning algorithms can help categorize and organize knowledge assets more efficiently.

Meanwhile, Marconi (2010) and Paolo (2022) expressed that exposure of teachers, students, and other members of staff in school environments to higher literacy levels plays a significant influence on knowledge management. Paolo (2022) noted that higher literacy levels are associated with improved communication, critical thinking skills, and the ability to access, analyze, and apply information effectively. Marconi (2010) and Paolo (2022) identified some of the ways by which exposure of stakeholders in education to higher literacy levels can influence knowledge management and enhanced knowledge sharing: Higher literacy levels among faculty and staff can promote a culture of sharing ideas, resources, and best practices. Educators who possess strong communication skills and can articulate their thoughts are more likely to share their expertise with colleagues, leading to a more collaborative and knowledge-sharing environment. Also, it improves information literacy because higher literacy levels are often associated with better information literacy skills. Educators and students who are proficient in

Influence of Digital... (Jegade, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609035>

information literacy can identify, evaluate, and use information effectively, leading to more informed decision-making and problem-solving. This, in turn, can improve the quality and relevance of knowledge management practices in schools.

In addition, it helps with critical thinking and problem-solving skills: Higher literacy levels are often linked to the development of critical thinking and analytical skills. Educators and students who are proficient in these areas are better equipped to assess, synthesize, and apply knowledge in various contexts (Aduba, Obot & Baro, 2022; Ojedokun, 2007). This can lead to more effective knowledge management practices, as individuals can critically evaluate information and make evidence-based decisions. It enhances the facilitation of professional development due to exposure to higher literacy levels which can facilitate ongoing professional development among educators. Teachers who continuously improve their literacy skills are more likely to engage in lifelong learning, seek out new knowledge, and stay abreast of current educational trends (Debbarma & Shivram, 2024). This can lead to a more dynamic and informed teaching workforce, ultimately enhancing knowledge management practices in schools.

Despite the unquantifiable benefits enjoyed in implementing digital solutions to knowledge management in public secondary schools in Nigeria, there are challenges identified in the literature. The studies of Al-Saggaf, Simons, and Neill (2013) and Barbieri (2013) reveal that one of the main challenges in implementing digital solutions in knowledge management is resistance to change among teachers, staff, and even students. This shows that some individuals may be hesitant to adopt new technologies due to fear of the unknown, lack of training, or concerns about the impact on their existing routines.

In addition, another significant challenge is the lack of digital literacy among educators and staff members. Due to individual differences not everyone may be comfortable or familiar with using digital tools and technologies, which can hinder the successful implementation of knowledge management systems. Similarly, schools may also face challenges in terms of limited resources, such as budget constraints or lack of access to necessary hardware and software. Thus, implementing digital solutions requires investing in technology infrastructure, training programs, and ongoing technical support, which may not always be feasible for some schools. As a result, schools must also consider data privacy and security concerns when implementing digital solutions in knowledge management. It should be noted that collecting and storing sensitive information about students and staff requires strict adherence to data protection regulations, which can be challenging to navigate. Therefore, integrating digital solutions with existing knowledge management systems and workflows can be a complex process. There could be challenges such as compatibility issues, data migration, and the need to align new technology with current practices may pose obstacles to successful implementation. Also, ensuring the sustainability and scalability of digital solutions in knowledge management is another challenge. As a result of the above, schools must consider the long-term maintenance, updates, and scalability of the technology to accommodate future growth and evolving needs.

Although the study of Omigie et al (2019) on the role of knowledge management for education in Nigeria, revealed that the effectiveness and efficiency of any institution rest squarely on its level of knowledge either tacit or explicit but failed to identify how the technology revolution has influenced the quality of teaching and learning. With this gap, the study is out to investigate the influence of the technological revolution on knowledge management in public secondary schools in Lagos state.

Objectives of the Study

The core purpose of this study is to navigate the influence of the digital revolution on knowledge management in public secondary schools in Lagos State. However, the specific objectives include:

1. Examine the role of digital tools and technologies in enhancing knowledge management practices
2. Assess how much digital literacy among students affects knowledge sharing and retention in public secondary schools.
3. Investigate the challenges faced by schools in integrating digital solutions for effective knowledge management.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at a 0.05 level of significance

1. H₀₁: Adopting digital tools and technologies will not significantly enhance knowledge management practice in Lagos State Public Secondary Schools
2. H₀₂: Higher levels of digital literacy among teachers and students will not significantly influence knowledge management in Lagos state Public secondary schools
3. H₀₃: Challenges in the implementation of digital solutions will not significantly influence effective knowledge management in Lagos state Public secondary schools

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Methodology

The study employed a descriptive type of survey research design. This design seeks to describe the variables as they occur in their natural environment. Description is carried out on a very large group of individuals through a survey form. The population comprised all public senior secondary school students in Lagos State as SSS 2 students from Alimosho LGA of the state-formed target population. A simple random sampling technique was used to select 40 students each from 5 identified senior secondary schools to form a sample size of 200 students. A self-designed instrument, the Influence of Digital Revolution on Knowledge Management Questionnaire (IDRKMQ) was used to collect data for this work. In measuring the influence of the digital revolution on knowledge management, a self-structured Questionnaire was developed using a 4-Likert type of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) respectively. The positive statements were recorded accordingly as negative statements were scored in a reversed order. Content validity was ensured by two experts in the Department of Educational Management, Lagos State University of Education, Epe, Lagos. Cronbach-alpha, a reliability form was used to determine reliability as an index value of $r = 0.892$ on 50 students not part of this work in the Department of Educational Management, Lagos State University, Ojo, Lagos State. The derived index value shows that internal consistency was met as a result the scale is suitable for study. Correlation analysis was used to analyse generated data and tested at a 0.05 significant level.

Presentation of Results

H0₁: Adopting digital tools and technologies will not significantly enhance knowledge management practice in Lagos State Public Secondary Schools

Table 1: Correlation analysis showing the influence of adopting digital tools on knowledge management

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r	sig.(2-tailed)	Decision
Adopting digital tools	200	3.13	0.87			
				.876	.023	Significant
Knowledge Management	200	2.90	0.74			

$\alpha = 0.05$ Source: Researchers' work, (2024)

Table 1 above reveals that with r-cal. value of .876, it shows that the adoption of digital tools influences knowledge management among students in public secondary schools. At a p -value of .023 and α -value of .05; since the α -value at .05 is greater than the sig-value, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative which states that adopting digital tools and technologies will significantly influence knowledge management practice is retained.

H0₂: Higher levels of digital literacy among teachers will not significantly influence knowledge management in Lagos state Public secondary schools

Table 2: Correlation analysis showing the influence of a higher level of digital literacy on knowledge management

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r	sig.(2-tailed)	Decision
Higher literacy level	200	2.43	0.69			
				.665	.009	Significant
Knowledge Management	200	2.90	0.74			

$\alpha = 0.05$ Source: Researchers' work, (2024)

Table 2 above reveals that with r-cal. value of .665, it shows that exposure to higher literacy levels influences knowledge management among students in public secondary schools. At a p -value of .009 and α -value of .05; since the α -value at .05 is greater than the sig-value, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative which states that exposure to higher literacy levels will significantly influence knowledge management practice is retained.

H0₃: Challenges in the implementation of digital solutions will not significantly influence effective knowledge management in Lagos state Public secondary schools

Influence of Digital... (Jegade, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609035>

Table 3: Correlation analysis showing the influence of challenges in the implementation of digital solutions on knowledge management

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r	sig.(2-tailed)	Decision
Challenges/ implementation	200	2.05	2.05	0.79		
Knowledge Management	200	2.90	0.74		.791	.010

$\alpha = 0.05$ **Source: Researchers' work, (2024)**

Table 3 above reveals that with r-cal. value of .791, it shows that challenges in the implementation of digital solutions influence knowledge management among students in public secondary schools. At a *p*-value of .010 and α -value at .05; since the α -value at .05 is greater than the sig-value, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative which states that challenges in the implementation of digital solutions will significantly influence knowledge management practice is retained.

Discussion of Findings

In hypothesis one, the result reveals that adopting digital tools and technologies will significantly influence knowledge management practice in public secondary schools in Lagos state. This finding conforms to that of Alavi and Leidner (2011) who identified improvement in knowledge sharing, enhanced knowledge capture, increased accessibility to knowledge, and automation of the knowledge management process as proceeds to adopting digital tools and technology. Adopting digital tools promotes the refinement of knowledge as quality and proactive information would be achieved at the end of the day. Alavi and Leidner (2011) and Mihi et al (2023)(2023) further expressed that the adoption of digital tools and technologies has transformed knowledge management in organisations, making it more efficient, accessible, and effective organisations that embrace these unique instruments and integrate them into their knowledge management practices are better positioned to succeed in today's fast-paced and information-driven environment where advancement in education is dependent on other environments.

Also, hypothesis two reveals that exposure to higher literacy levels will significantly influence knowledge management practice in public secondary schools in Lagos state. Also, the result from this finding agrees with that of Marconi (2010) and Paolo (2022) who stressed that exposure to higher literacy levels is associated with improved communication and critical thinking skills, and enhances the ability to access, analyse and supply information effectively. They further stated that aside from facilitating professional development among educational managers, curriculum developers' planners, and students, knowledge management in schools can be improved when it enhances the promotion of culture sharing and improvement in information management. In education and the global space, data is life as the ability to manage information is very key to development in education.

Likewise, hypothesis three, it reveals that challenges in the implementation of digital solutions will significantly influence knowledge management practice, especially in public secondary schools in Lagos state. This finding conforms to that of Al-Saggaf et al. (2013) and Barbieri (2013) who affirmed that challenges often confronted by the evolution of IT are inevitable. Some of the challenges include resistance to change, lack of digital literacy, limited resources, data privacy and security concerns, integration with existing systems, sustainability, and scalability. Al-Saggaf et al (2013) further stated that despite the numerous benefits of implementing digital solutions in school knowledge management, addressing these challenges requires careful planning, effective communication, ongoing training and support, and a commitment to fostering a culture of innovation and collaboration. By proactively addressing these numerous obstacles, schools can successfully implement digital solutions in knowledge management and reap the benefits of enhanced cooperation, information sharing, and efficient decision-making processes.

Conclusion

The study assessed the influence of the digital revolution on knowledge management in public secondary schools in Lagos. The study reveals that adopting digital tools and technologies will significantly influence knowledge management practice in public secondary schools in Lagos state. Thus, the adoption of digital tools and technologies will make organisations to be more efficient, accessible, and effective in achieving organizational goals in a cost-efficient manner. The study further reveals that exposure to higher literacy levels will significantly influence knowledge management practice in public secondary schools in Lagos state. Similarly, the study shows the challenges in the implementation of digital tools, and surmounting the challenges requires careful planning, effective communication, continuous training, and support that enhances a culture of innovation and collaboration.

Influence of Digital... (Jegade, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609035>

Recommendations

Therefore, the study concluded that challenges like unstable power supply, cost of appliances and technology, dearth of personnel skilled in app use, and negative attitudes towards the end-users are significant factors that can influence the level of knowledge management in our public secondary schools. The technology revolution has come with a series of breathtaking innovations and face-lifting of the educational sector.

1. To expand and continue to maximize the revolution in technology, the study recommends that curriculum developers should incorporate the use of technology in every facet of the educational sector in line with the knowledge economy of the 21st century.
2. In addition, stakeholders should mount in-service training regularly and this should be made available for staff to expose them to contemporary measures and modes of teaching and learning using tech devices.
3. Also, teachers should as a matter of urgency adopt the use of online assessment techniques as a mode of testing test takers.

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Assessment of Preparedness and... (Igben, 2024)

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Assessment of Preparedness and Utilization of Artificial Intelligence on Business Education Learning among Colleges of Education Lecturers in South– South, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated assessment of preparedness and utilization of Artificial Intelligence on business education learning among colleges of education lecturers in South-South, Nigeria. Two research questions and one hypothesis were formulated to guide the study. The total population of the study was sixty lecturers was used for the study. No sample was required because of the number of lecturers involved were few. The instrument for data collection was a researchers constructed questionnaire titled, ‘preparedness and utilization of artificial intelligence on business education learning Questionnaire (PAUOAIIOBELQ). The instrument was validated by two experts, one from curriculum and instruction Department and the other from business education Department all from college of Education, Warri. The instrument was subjected to test – retest to ascertain its reliability. To achieve this, 20 copies of the instrument was administered to lecturers in college of education, Mosogar who are not part of the study but share similar characteristics with the sample of the study. The data collected was computed using the Cronbach alpha Statistic which yield 0.74 indicating that the instrument was reliable. Mean and standard deviation was used to analyse the research question while t-test was used to test the hypothesis. The finding among others shown that lecturers were prepared to use the AI teaching/learning while school management are not yet ready to provide the necessary resources for lecturers. It was recommended from the finding that federal, state and local government and the school administrators of higher institution should make plan to provide AI resources for the lecturers, government should also create awareness to students and lecturers on the use of AI through seminar/workshops. Finally, management of institutions of higher learning should continue training and re-training for both old and new lecturers in business education for effective use of AI tools as their teaching methods.

Keywords: Teachers, preparedness, artificial intelligence, business education.

Introduction

So many years ago, no one could believe that there was going to be anything like You Tube, Facebook, Wikipedia, Google, WhatsApp, etc. But today they are the most used digital tools on earth. In this changing world, digital technology has greatly influenced our economic, social and cultural evolution of all societies. As these new forms of technologies continue to

Assessment of Preparedness and... (Igben, 2024)

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609035>

ravage our lives and capture our youth, schools have no choice but to make room for them. In accordance with the 21st century, countries expect their teachers and students to behave as informed and responsible digital citizen (Theirry, 2019).

Artificial Intelligence the new advancement in computer systems has the capability to perform tasks that traditionally require human intelligence such as learning, reasoning, problem-solving and decision-making (IBM, 2023 in Sameera, 2024). One of the major architects in achieving educational goals and objectives is the teachers and teachers are the backbone of any educational achievement through the use of AI for the instructional delivery. Onyiorah, (2021), described teaching and learning as the bedrock of the activities in a country's educational system. This suggests that teachers must be at the center of all activities in our educational system for teaching and learning to occur. Positive changes will be brought about by the teacher. In order to implement improvement in the learning process, educators in the twenty-first century need to be familiar with contemporary technologies. The creation, dissemination, and application of knowledge – the main goals of education – are facilitated by teaching and learning. The effectiveness of the teacher in teaching and the skills acquired by the learners will determine the quality of our educational system (Gidado, Abudullahi & Adamu, 2015 in Onyiorah, 2021). Therefore, any teachers who at this dispensation rely on the traditional teaching may not be relevant in the teaching profession. Adizu and Ehidihamen, (2024) ascertained that the introduction of robots is rising on daily basis and taken rapid advancements in AI and automation are expected to have an impact in higher education. The robots have not had academic AI. but will be made an intelligent tutoring system which means that having the required experience and teaching skills are no longer enough. This means that any teacher who lacks the digital skills among some academics may make it easier for universities to look for robots as an alternative. In line with the above, it is clear that 21st century strategies for teaching need to embrace the AI. strategies. This shows that technological advancement has been carried as improvement in the teaching and learning process. Therefore, any teacher in business education lacking this technological advancement should re-direct it steps to meet the present challenges either through training or re-training.

Our educational system has a unique opportunity to grow and develop as a result of the shift to digital. Digital technologies are crucial to our youth's academic success because they give them new ways to learn, communicate, share, create, and collaborate while also bringing new life to our schools. For students to become digitally literate and knowledgeable citizens in the digital age, these resources must be utilized and integrated into the classroom. Similarly, educators must be ready for the transition to digital. Training and support for teachers and other staff in the school are required since they are part and parcel of the action plan (Thierry 2019).

In the realm of business education, the effective integration of AI is contingent upon the readiness and preparedness of business education teachers. The needs to be considered to better the readiness and preparedness of teachers is to implement AI in the classroom are teacher's attitudes towards AI, their perceived self-efficacy in using AI tools, their expectations regarding the benefits of AI usage, and their access to resources and training in AI (Ayanwale, et al., 2022). Teachers' perspectives are critical in determining the readiness and preparedness to use AI in teaching as they are vital in assessing the value and feasibility of AI implementation. In another vein, the teachers should be equipped with the necessary training and resources which is crucial for effectively implementation of AI in the classroom. The only way the successful implementation of AI technology in education can be measured, is enhancing students learning experience (Chiu & Chai, 2020; Sue et al; 2020).

Teachers play significant role in AI technology towards education and importantly enhancing students' learning experiences. However, teachers' readiness and preparedness to use AI in teaching varies. Some of the teachers have interest in and knowledge of AI, the others may feel uncertain about its implementation in the classroom (Zhao et al., 2022) Lack of formal training in AI technology in education exhibit these challenges thereby making it important to provide teachers with the necessary support and resources (Chiu & Chai 2020). Demir & Graksin, (2022) opined that students' perceptions of AI influence teachers 'readiness and preparedness for implementation of AI in the classroom. The growing influence of AI in the educational systems according Sorgo, (2020) mentioned the critical need for teachers to involve in both the design and implementation of these technologies.

Artificial Intelligence is defined according to capeland 2024 in Obue & Onwudiwe, (2024) as the ability of a digital computer or computer-controlled robot to perform tasks commonly associated with beings. In this context, when a teacher is not there, AI can be used to offer instruction in the classroom. However, if a teacher lacks the necessary AI technology abilities to function in the classroom, the introduction of AI will result in his termination. Thus, from lectures to test supervision, teachers must be ready for it when it enters the classroom. AI is a field of computer science that develops computerized machines and intelligent machine platforms. These devices can sense, reason, plan, solve problems, produce, and manipulate objects by processing data, patters, and models. Algorithms are used by machine to process vast amount of data that are too large for conventional computing methods to manage. Also, AI is ideal for identifying trends and patterns and for making prediction (Thierry, 2019). AI. offer personalised learning experiences and enhancing student engagement and outcomes (Tonck, 2021). AI also allows educators to focus more on personalised teaching and student engagement (Aikanaan, 2022). Another area A.I

Assessment of Preparedness and... (Igben, 2024)

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609035>

technology can be relevant to education is the computer vision which involves making, recording and presentation of results. Since it thinks, act, and reason, like human being, it can be deployed to area where it can perform these functions with the aid of a teacher.

Business education is a vocational field that equips students with the knowledge and abilities necessary to make a substantial contribution to a country's economic growth. As a result, it is expected that a business education program would include both intellectual and practical skills that will enable the graduate to make a living in the rapidly evolving business environment of the twenty – first century (Onojetah, 2024 in Fortune & Adizu 2024). According to Ehidihamhen et al. ((2024), business education is for business and about business, which is essential for both surviving and growing as an individual. Business education is the kind of education that helps students develop the values, attitudes and knowledge that business around the world require. It provides healthy literate, self-reliant citizen that would form of creating wealth for human development resulting to sustainable and national development at large (Ehidihamhen et al., 2024). Tosin et al, (2022) saw business education as a programme that impact skills, attitudes, and knowledge through teaching that will make the recipient a successful career in officer and business world. In the view, Anyaeneh & Nzegwu 2015 in Tosin et al, (2022) viewed business education as education that enable the students acquire basic education that enable the students acquire basic education for teaching career, entrepreneurship, business understanding, office understanding, office environment and vocational practices. Business educators must be prepared to us A.I technology to educate the students in this new era. Business education is a programme that provides opportunities for training for both the teachers and students in the face of modern technologies.

The teachers in the 21st century will be faced with a lot of challenges if he does not change the strategy, way and method of teaching to harness with the existing technologies to the coming one. Coping with the existing technologies new ones emerging and so he has to learn them and use them to enable him remain and relevant in the teaching profession. This was supported by Oliver, (2008) that since modern office and institutions have been transformed to e-office/e-learning process any workers/teachers who possess teaching modern technologies skills will remain relevant. Based on this, institutions and organization need to send their staff for training and re-training bearing in mind the changes in technology springing up on daily basis. Although most teachers or workers are not given the opportunity or been sponsor to go for training in order to update their knowledge.

There are many complaints that business education, which equips students with the attitude, abilities and knowledge necessary to handle complex modern office technologies is yet failing to help teachers become proficient in using these tools to offer instruction. When the AI finally arrives, these teachers might struggle to stay in the academic field. It is expected of all institutions to prepare for rainy days by retraining and educating their teachers on artificial intelligence and technology use. In order to notify institutions and others agencies about the necessity of preparing their teachers for the delivery of education by artificial intelligence, the researchers embark on the study.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to look at the teacher's preparedness in the use of AI in the teaching of business education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Ascertain the extent to which lecturer's preparedness in the use of AI enhance the teaching of business education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria.
2. Determine the extent to which the accessibility of AI resources necessary for teaching enhances the teaching of business education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following questions guided the study

1. To what extent does the lecturers' preparedness in the use of AI enhance the teaching of business education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria?
2. To what extent does the lecturer's accessibility of AI resources necessary for teaching enhance the teaching of business education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria?

Hypotheses of the Study

The following hypotheses were raised to guide the study

1. There is no significant difference in the means ratings of male and female business education lecturers' preparedness in the use of AI enhancing the teaching of business education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria?

Assessment of Preparedness and... (Igben, 2024)

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609035>

2. There is no significant difference in the means ratings of male and female business education lecturers on the accessibility of AI resources necessary for teaching enhance the teaching of business education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria.

Research Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. Nworgu, (2015) opined is one in which group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from few people or items considered being representative of the entire group. The total population used for the study comprised of 60 business education lecturers in College of Education, Warri, College of Education Akamkpa and Federal college education, Asaba. The entire population was used for the study because of it manageable sizes no sampling and sampling techniques. The instrument for data collection was a researchers constructed questionnaire titled, ‘preparedness and utilization of artificial intelligence on business education learning Questionnaire (PAUOAIIOBELQ)’. The questionnaires contain 11 items and was assigned a scale of 4 – point rating of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). The instrument was validated by two experts, one from curriculum and instruction Department and other from business education Department all from college of Education, Warri. The experts examined the items of the instrument on the basis of items clarity, adequacy, suitability and relevance of items to the objectives of the study. The comment, suggestions and corrections of the validators were used to develop the final copy of the instrument. However, none of the items was dropped. The instrument was subjected to test – retest to ascertain its reliability. To achieve this, 20 copies of the instrument was administered to lecturers in college of education, Mosogar who are not part of the study but share similar characteristics with the sample of the study. The data collected was computed using the Cronbach alpha Statistic which yield 0.74 indicating that the instrument was reliable. Mean and Standard deviation was used to analyse the research questions and mean between 4.00-3.50 (VHE), 3.49-2.50 (HE), 2.49-1.50 (LE) and 1.49-1.00 (VLE). While, t-test was used to test all the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question One

To what extent does the teacher’s preparedness in the use of AI enhance the teaching of business education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard deviation of the respondents rating of teachers’ preparedness enhance the teaching of business education courses.

S/N	Question Item	No	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark
1.	I have been taught the basic concept of AI	60	2.53	1.081	High Extent
2.	As a teacher, I have the ability to use AI tools for teaching	60	2.65	1.022	High Extent
3.	I am fully prepared to trouble shoot issues with AI technology	60	2.75	.914	High Extent
4.	I can evaluate the effectiveness of AI tools in enhancing teaching	60	3.03	.823	V.High Extent
5.	It affords me the opportunity to learn new AI tools for teaching	60	2.87	.1.049	High Extent
6.	I have the confidence in explaining the use of AI in teaching	60	3.02	.813	V. High Extent
	Grand mean		2.80	.050	High Extent

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 revealed that the mean rating of the respondents to items 1, 2,3,5, and 6 respectively indicated high extent. It was also showed that the mean ratings of the respondents to items 4 and 6 respectively indicated very highly extent. The implication was that teachers’ preparedness would highly enhance the use of AI in the teaching of business education courses.

Assessment of Preparedness and... (Igben, 2024)

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609035>

Research Question two

To what extent does the accessibility of AI resources necessary for teaching enhance the teaching of business education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and Standard deviation of the respondents rating of teachers ‘accessibility of A.I resources necessary for teaching enhance the teaching of business education courses.

S/N	Question Item	No	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark
7.	The school Management provide us adequate access to AI resources	60	2.10	.986	Low Extent
8.	The school provide the necessary technical support for teachers for the use of A.I tools	60	1.92	.962	Low Extent
9.	Internet connection was fully provided in the classroom to support AI activities	60	1.85	.899	Low Extent
10.	Up-to-date relevant resources were made available to us for AI Teaching.	60	1.68	.983	Low Extent
11.	The school management provides sufficient hardware for utilizing AI in the classroom	60	2.25	.985	Low Extent
Grand mean			2.38	0.963	Low Extent

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 revealed that the mean rating of the respondents to items 7 - 11 respectively indicated low extent. This implied that all the respondents have negative insight on the non-provision of A.I resource and lack of accessibility by teacher will hinder the enhancement of AI in the teaching of business education courses.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female Business Education lectures preparedness in the use of AI enhancing the teaching of Business Education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria

Table 3: T- test analysing showing the mean rating of male and female Business Education lecturers’ preparedness in the use of AI enhancing the teaching of Business Education Courses in College of Education in south -south

Group Statistics								
GENDER	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	T	df	p-value	Decision	
MALE	20	2.87	.81	.430	58	.669	NSig	
FEMALE	40	2.78	.71					

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Since t-statistic is 0.430 with df=58 at p-value 0.669 greater than significant value of 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female Business Education lectures preparedness in the use of AI enhancing the teaching of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female Business Education lectures on the accessibility of AI resources necessary for enhancing and teaching of Business Education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria

Table 4: T- test analysing showing the mean rating of male and female Business Education lecturers on the accessibility of AI resources necessary for enhancing and teaching of Business Education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria

Group Statistics								
GENDER	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	T	df	p-value	Decision	
MALE	20	1.99	1.004	.195	58	.846	NSig	
FEMALE	40	1.95	.751					

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Assessment of Preparedness and... (Igben, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609035>

Since t-statistic is 0.195 with df=58 at p-value 0.846 greater than significant value of 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female Business Education lectures on the accessibility of AI resources necessary for enhancing and teaching of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State

Discussion of Finding

According to the findings of the instructors' readiness to apply artificial intelligence (AI) in business education classes, every teacher (respondent) was completely prepared to use AI to improve student learning. This was in line with Mateen et al., (2024) Title the role of artificial intelligence in transforming educational practices opportunities, challenges, and implications. The author recommended that AI will enhance students learning experiences by offering them practical and experienced learning opportunities especially when combined with other technologies. The study was also in line with Musa et al., (2022) opined that understanding teachers' readiness and intention towards factors influencing AI in the study was identified.

According to the study's findings, no school has any infrastructure in place to help teachers implement artificial intelligence (AI) to improve instruction and learning. One step guaranteeing the acceptance of AI in schools the school administration's recognition of ignorance as a barrier to AI education facilities. The results regarding the facilities to support the teachers in the use of AI to enhance teaching and learning, the study revealed that no school have any facilities on ground to kick start the AI. The identification of lack of knowledge by the school management as a barrier to AI instructional facilities is a step towards ensuring the adoption in schools.

According to Hypotheses 1 and 2, there is no discernible difference between the mean evaluations of male and female Business Education lecturers about the preparedness and availability of AI resources required for improving and instructing Business Education courses in higher education

Conclusions

From the finding, the teachers interviewed showed that they were generally well-prepared, prepared the groundwork for the use of AI in the teaching and learning in the institutions. But it will continue to provide improvement where is needed. The teachers showed that they are strong enough for the application of AI technology, and also showed that there is still room for improvement in the use AI application.

On the accessibility of resources necessary to enhance teachers teaching and learning of business education courses, no one was available for assessment thereby hindering the teachers' zeal and technical competencies on the use of AI in the institutions.

Recommendations

1. Federal, state and local government and the administrators of higher education should make plan to provide and allowed accessibility of AI resources by lecturers.
2. Federal, state and local government should create awareness to students and lecturers on the use of artificial intelligence through seminar/workshops.

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Comparative Assessment of Water Purification Techniques Awareness and Socio-Economic Variabilities among Household Owners in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper assessed water purification techniques awareness and socio-economic variabilities among household owners in Zamfara state, Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Population for this study was 592,106 household owners in Zamfara state. Sample size of 384 household owners were selected using multistage sampling procedures which include cluster, proportionate and systematic sampling. Questionnaire on comparative assessment of water purification techniques awareness and socio-economic variabilities among household owners was used and validated by five (5) experts, the instrument was pilot-tested using Cronbach Alpha and a reliability co-efficient of 0.89 was obtained. SPSS version 25 was used for data analysis were descriptive statistics was used to answer research questions and inferential statistics to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result revealed that awareness of water purification among household owners in Zamfara state is significant ($p=0.000$); socio-economic determinants (income, education and occupation) of awareness of water purification among household owners in Zamfara state is significant ($p=0.000$). Based on the results, the study concluded that household owners in Zamfara State possess significant awareness of water purification methods which are influenced by socio economic factors such as income, education, and occupation. Based on the conclusion, the study recommended that Zamfara State Water Board implement community-led water purification education programs, the Zamfara State government provide subsidies or incentives for purification tools.

Keyword: Knowledge, Water purification, socioeconomic variables, Household;

Introduction

The size and capacity of water treatment systems vary widely ranging from simple households units to small facilities that serve manufacturing industries to large scale centralized water treatment plants dedicated to cities and towns. Selection of specific treatment processes depends upon factors such as intake water quality, degree of purification required, intended water use, flow capacity requirements, government regulations, available capital and the operations as well as maintenance costs involved (Centre for Disease Control, 2022). Water contamination is primarily caused by the discharge of untreated wastewater from enterprises. The effluent or sewage discharge from various enterprises which contains varying levels of contaminants is dumped into rivers or other water sources. The wastewater may have a high proportion of organic and inorganic contaminants at the initial discharge. Industries generate waste water as a result of fabrication processes, processes dealing with paper and pulp, textiles, chemicals and from various streams such as cooling towers, boilers and production lines (Singh, et al, 2018).

Treatment for drinking water production involves the removal of contaminants and/or inactivation of any potentially harmful microbes from raw water to produce water that is pure enough for human consumption without any short term or long term risk of any adverse health effect. In general terms, the greatest microbial risks are associated with ingestion of water that is contaminated with human or animal (including bird) faeces. Faeces can be a source of pathogenic bacteria, viruses, protozoa and helminths (WHO, 2020).

Objective of the study

The main purpose of this study is to assess awareness of water purification techniques and socio-economic variabilities among household owners in Zamfara state. Therefore, the study will be guided by the following specific objectives, to:

1. Assess awareness of household owners on water purification techniques in Zamfara State;
2. Assess socio economic determinants of awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara state.

Research Questions

The following research questions are formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the level of awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State?
2. What are the socio-economic determinants of awareness of household owners on water purification techniques in Zamfara state?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. **H₀₁:** Awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State is not significant;
2. **H₀₂:** There is no significant difference in socio-economic determinants (income, education and occupation) of awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara state.

Methodology

Descriptive research design was used for this study. According to Shields and Rangarajan, (2013), descriptive research is used to describe characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied. It does not answer questions about how/when/why the characteristics occurred. Rather it addresses "what" question (what are the characteristics of the population or situation be studied). Descriptive research design focuses on the people and their beliefs, opinions, perception and behaviors (Nwana, 2015).

The population of this study comprise of five hundred and ninety-two thousands, one hundred and six (592,106) household owners from all fourteen (14) Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Zamfara State. This is based on the data obtained on Distribution of Households by Type of Housing Unit from the National Population Commission (NPC, 2020), Zamfara State office, Gusau.

A sample size of three hundred and eighty-four (384) Households was participated in the study. This is based on the sample size selection table by Research Advisors (2006), which suggests that for a population of 592,106 a sample size of 384 is sufficient for generalization at a 95% confidence level and at 5.0% margin of error. Multistage sampling technique was used by the researcher that comprises of cluster, proportionate and systematic sampling which Alvi (2016), explained that, this type of sampling technique were used when the elements of the population are more than one and spread. Cluster sampling technique was used by the researcher to group or to divide the state based on three (3) senatorial zones (i.e Zamfara central, north and west).

A proportionate sampling technique was used to select one (1) Local Government (Gusau) from Zamfara central, One (1) Local Government (kaura Namoda) from Zamfara north and 2 Local Government (Talata Mafara & Gummi) from Zamfara west senatorial zone. Thus, Zamfara central has only four (4) Local Governments, Zamfara north also has four (4) local governments while Zamfara west has (6) Local Governments respectively. In order to be fair to the population distribution, the research chooses two (2) Local Government from Zamfara west and one (1) each from Zamfara north and Zamfara central zones.

A proportionate sampling procedure was adopted to compose the sample size of 384 among the four (4) selected Local Government Areas where Gusau has 130 numbers of respondents, Kaura Namoda 100, Talata Mafara 78, and Gummi 76. Which Sulaiman (2015), explained that proportionate sampling is used when the elements of the populations vary considerably in size because, it assures that those in larger size will have the same probability of getting the larger sample size as those in the smaller size will get the small sample and systematic sampling was used for selection of households on the basis of numerical sequence.

Table 1: Sample Size Distribution

S/N	Senatorial Districts	Sampled Local Gov't Areas	Sampled Households
1.	Zamfara Central	Gusau	130
2.	Zamfara-North	Kaura-Namoda	100
3.	Zamfara-West	Talata-Mafara	78
		Gummi	76
Total	03	04	384

A questionnaire titled “Comparative Assessment of Water Purification Techniques Awareness and Socio-economic Variabilities of Household Owners” (CAWPTASVHO) was developed by the researcher. The questionnaire is made in two parts, A and B. Part A obtained the information of households socio demographic characteristics, parts B obtained households information on awareness of water purification techniques using Multi Choice Questions (MCQ) with option a, b, c and d through a rating scale of highly knowledgeable (70% to 100%), knowledgeable (60% to 69%), moderately (50% to 59%) and not knowledgeable (50% and below),

The instrument was subjected and validated by 5 experts who scrutinized the instrument were suggestions and corrections were incorporated in the final draft.

The validated instrument was subjected to reliability test using cronbach Alpha to test the internal consistency via statistical package for social science (SPSS) and reliability level of 0.89 was obtained.

An introductory letter from the Head of Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria was to obtain by the researcher to enable him collect data from the sampled households, where 384 questionnaires were duly distributed to 384 households through their consent by the researcher with the help of three (3) research assistants and 384 questionnaires was retrieved.

For the analysis of the data that was collected from the household owners, the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) Version 25 was used to analyze the data obtained from the respondents. The demographic characteristics of respondents were computed using frequency and percentage. Research question 1 was answered using frequency and percentage, were research question 2 was answered using mean and standard deviation. One sample-t-test was used to test Hypotheses 1 on awareness of water purification while multiple regression analysis was used to test hypothesis 2 on socio economic determinants of water purification techniques of household owners in Zamfara state. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results

All data collected on demographic characteristics of the respondents were tabulated using frequencies and percentages as indicated in Table 2

Table 2: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age Range in Years		
18 – 40	240	62.5
40 and above	144	37.5
Total	384	100.0
Gender		
Male	297	77.3
Female	87	22.7
Total	384	100.0
Income		
Less than 30,000	89	23.2
30,000 to 50,000	167	43.5
50,000 to 100,000	80	20.8
More than 100,000	48	12.5
Total	384	100.0
Educational Qualification		
Primary	14	3.6

Comparative Assessment of... (Mustapha, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610556>

Secondary	64	16.7
Tertiary	288	75.0
Non Formal	18	4.7
Total	384	100.0
Occupation		
Civil Servant	237	61.7
Business Man	81	21.1
Farmers	36	9.4
Others	30	7.8
Total	384	100.0

Table 2: provides the demographic characteristics of the respondents in the study. The data is presented across three variables: age range in years, gender, income, educational qualification and occupation, with corresponding frequencies and percentages. In terms of age distribution, the majority of respondents 62.5%, (240 respondents) were between 18 and 40 years old, while 37.5% (144 respondents) were 40 years and above. The gender composition of the sample was predominantly male, with 77.3% (297 respondents) being men and 22.7% (87 respondents) being women.

Regarding income levels, the largest group of respondents 43.5%, (167 respondents) reported earning between 30,000 to 50,000 Nigerian Naira, The second largest income group was those earning less than 30,000 Naira, accounting for 23.2% (89 respondents). 20.8% (80 respondents) reported earning between 50,000 to 100,000 Naira, while the smallest group (12.5%, 48 respondents) earned more than 100,000 Naira.

Educational qualifications of the respondents showed that the vast majority 75%, (288 respondents) had tertiary education. Secondary education was the next most common, with 16.7% (64 respondents). Only 3.6% (14 respondents) had primary education, while 4.7% (18 respondents) had non-formal education.

In terms of occupation, civil servants constituted the largest group, representing 61.7% (237 respondents) of the sample. Businessmen made up 21.1% (81 respondents), while farmers accounted for 9.4% (36 respondents). The remaining 7.8% (30 respondents) were classified under "Others" for their occupation.

Research Question One: What is the awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State?

Table 3: (a) Item by item Analysis on the awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State

S/N	Awareness of Water Purification	Frequency	Percent
1	Which of the following methods is used for water purification?		
	Separation	105	27.3
	Filtration	190	49.5
	Inoculation	2	0.5
	All of the above	87	22.7
	Total	384	100.0
2	Which of the following statements is true?		
	Inability to use any of the purification methods can lead to the consumption of contaminated water	173	45.1
	Inability to use any of the purification methods can provide clean and safe drinking water	80	20.8
	Inability to use any of the purification methods can cause no harmful effect to well-being	31	8.1
	Inability to use any of the purification methods can prevent individuals from consumption of contaminated water	100	26.0
	Total	384	100.0
3	Consumption of contaminated water can expose individuals to the outbreak of waterborne diseases like:		
	Headache	8	2.1
	Diarrhea	294	76.6
	Cancer	26	6.8
	All of the above	56	14.6
	Total	384	100.0

4	Contaminants can be reduced or totally removed out of water through:		
	Water harvesting	64	16.7
	Water production	70	18.2
	Water raining	59	15.4
	Water purification	191	49.7
	Total	384	100.0
5	Access to purified drinking water can improve the:		
	Quality of life	302	78.6
	Walking standard	19	4.9
	Intellectual ability	45	11.7
	None of the above	18	4.7
	Total	384	100.0
6	Life-threatening worms that can be prevented through the use of purified water include the following except:		
	Dracunculiasis	48	12.5
	Schistosomiasis	95	24.7
	Filariasis	70	18.2
	Trachoma	171	44.5
	Total	384	100.0
7	Additives used to improve the quality of water include:		
	Aluminium sulphate (Alum)	190	49.5
	Chlorine	96	25.0
	Calcium hypochlorite	16	4.2
	All of the above	82	21.4
	Total	384	100.0
8	The most effective method of disinfection of pathogenic organisms in water is through:		
	Filtration	85	22.1
	Sedimentation	51	13.3
	Coagulation	15	3.9
	Boiling	233	60.7
	Total	384	100.0
9	Use of filters is very important and crucial in water purification because:		
	It helps to remove contaminants out of the water	308	80.2
	It helps to add contaminants into the water	37	9.6
	It helps attract debris into the water	25	6.5
	None of the above	14	3.6
	Total	384	100.0
10	The major cause of waterborne diseases is:		
	Surface water	50	13.0
	Rainwater	26	6.8
	Open defecation and urination	294	76.6
	Borehole water	14	3.6
	Total	384	100.0

Table 3 (a) presents the awareness of water purification techniques of household owners in Zamfara State. Regarding purification methods, nearly half 49.5%, (n=190) of respondents identified filtration, while 27.3% (n=105) chose separation, and 22.7% (n=87) selected all methods including inoculation, which was chosen by only 0.5% (n=2). When asked about the implications of not using purification methods, 45.1% (n=173) correctly recognized that it could lead to consuming contaminated water, while 26% (n=100) incorrectly believed it would prevent contaminated water consumption. On waterborne diseases, the vast majority (76.6%, n=294) accurately identified diarrhoea as a potential outcome of consuming contaminated water.

Regarding contaminant removal, approximately half (49.7%, n=191) of the respondents correctly identified water purification as the solution. A significant majority (78.6%, n=302) recognized that access to purified drinking water could

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improve quality of life. On the topic of water-related diseases, 44.5% (n=171) incorrectly identified trachoma as not being preventable through purified water use. For water treatment additives, alum was the most recognized (49.5%, n=190), followed by chlorine (25%, n=96).

Concerning disinfection methods, 60.7% (n=233) correctly identified boiling as the most effective method for eliminating pathogenic organisms. The importance of filters was well understood, with 80.2% (n=308) correctly stating that filters help remove contaminants from water. Finally, regarding the major cause of waterborne diseases, more than three-quarters of respondents (76.6%, n=294) accurately identified open defecation and urination as the primary factor, while relatively few attributed it to surface water (13%, n=50), rainwater (6.8%, n=26), or borehole water (3.6%, n=14).

Table 3: (b) Respondent by Respondent Analysis on the awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State

S/N	Respondent Scores	Frequency	Percentage	Remark	Rating Scale
1	100%	19	4.95%	4.95%	Highly Knowledgeable
2	90%	45	11.72%	11.72%	
3	80%	55	14.32%	14.32%	
4	70%	93	24.22%	24.22%	
	Total			55.21%	
5	60%	54	14.06%	14.06%	Knowledgeable
6	50%	50	13.02%	13.02%	
7	40%	22	5.73%	5.73%	Not Knowledgeable
8	30%	22	5.73%	5.73%	
9	20%	10	2.6%	2.6%	
10	10%	14	3.65	3.65	
	Total			17.715	
	Grand Total	384	100%	100%	

Table 3 (b) present the summary of respondent by respondent analysis on awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara state, in regard to these about 4.95%, (n=19) of the respondents scored 100%, 11.72% (n=45) scored 90%, 14.32% (n=55) scored 80% and 24.22% (n=93) scored 70%, and range indicated by rating scale for highly knowledgeable is between 70% to 100%. While 14.06% (n=54) that scored 60% are identified as knowledgeable, 13.02% (n=50) that scored 50% are moderate. Respondents that are classified as not knowledgeable are between the range of 49-10%, to about 5.73% (n=22) scored 40%, 5.73% (n=22) scored 30%, 2.6% (n=10) scored 20% and 3.65% (n=14) scored 10% respectively.

Research Question two: What are the socio economic determinants of awareness of household owners on water purification techniques in Zamfara State?

Table 4: Mean Score of responses on the socio economic determinants of awareness of household owners on water purification techniques in Zamfara State

	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Difference
Knowledge (Constant)	2.31	0.38	
Income	2.23	0.94	0.08
Educational Qualification	2.81	0.57	0.50
Occupation	1.63	0.94	0.68

Table 4: shows the mean score on the socio-economic determinants of awareness of household owners on water purification techniques in Zamfara State with a mean of 2.31, 2.23, 2.81 and 1.63 and mean difference of 0.08, 0.50 and 0.68. Based on this outcome, socio-economic factors (income, educational qualification and occupation) determine the awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State.

Based on the research questions, the following hypotheses are formulated for this study.

Hypothesis One: Awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State is not significant

Table 5: One-Sample t-test Analysis of awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Df	t-value	p-value
Knowledge	384	2.30	0.38	383	118.697	0.000
Test Mean	384	2.50	0.00			

Calculated $p < 0.05$, calculated t-value > 1.972 at df 383

The result of the one-sample t-test statistics in Table 5 reveals that the awareness of water purification among household owners in Zamfara State is significant because the calculated p-value of 0.000 is lower than the 0.05 level of significance and the calculated t-value of 118.697 is higher than the 1.972 critical t-value at 383 degrees of freedom (df). Therefore, the hypothesis which stated that awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State is not significant was rejected. This means that members of household owners in Zamfara State have adequate awareness of water purification techniques.

Hypothesis two: There is no significant difference in socio-economic determinants (income, education and occupation) of awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara state.

Table 6: Multiple Regression Analysis on Awareness of Water Purification techniques and Socio-economic Variables Model Summary

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
.113	.013	0.005	.38005	1.427

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	.710	3	.237	1.639	.000
Residual	54.886	380	.144		
Total	55.597	383			

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.033	.137		14.847	.000
Income	.026	.022	.064	1.187	.000
Educational Qualification	.051	.037	.076	1.358	.000
Occupation	.046	.023	.113	1.955	.000

Table 6 shows the outcome of multiple regression analysis on the awareness of water purification techniques among household owners and socio economic variables (income, education and occupation) in Zamfara State. The overall model shows a statistically significant relationship ($F(3, 380) = 1.639, p < .005$), indicating that at least one of the predictors (income, educational qualification and occupation) has a significant influence on awareness of water purification techniques. However, the amount of variance explained by the model is relatively low, with an R-squared of 0.013, suggesting that only about 1.3% of the variability in the awareness of water purification techniques can be explained by these socio-economic variables.

Examining the individual predictors, income, educational qualification and occupation each have statistically significant relationships with awareness of water purification techniques. Specifically, income ($\beta = 0.064, p < .005$), educational qualification ($\beta = 0.076, p < .005$), and occupation ($\beta = 0.113, p < .005$) all positively influence awareness, as indicated by their positive standardized coefficients. Based on this outcome, the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in

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awareness of water purification techniques among household owners on socio-economic variables (income, education and occupation) in Zamfara State was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The finding from the study revealed that awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State is significant ($p = 0.000$). This means that household owners in Zamfara State demonstrate a significant level of awareness about water purification techniques. The finding aligns with several previous studies, while also showing some differences compared to others.

The significant awareness found in this study is consistent with research by Miner, et al (2015) on household drinking water; knowledge and practice of purification in a community of Lamingo, Plateau State, Nigeria which reported that 26.1% of respondents had good knowledge of water purification, and 59.8% had fair knowledge. This affirmed that awareness and understanding of water purification methods may be relatively high across different regions of Nigeria. Similarly, Mustapha, et al (2022) conducted research on household awareness and practices on Water Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH) in an Arid Region of North western Nigeria, Sokoto State and found fairly good levels of WASH understanding in Sokoto State, an arid region neighboring Zamfara. This geographical proximity and similar environmental conditions may explain the comparable knowledge levels.

The finding from the study revealed that socio economic determinants (income, education and occupation) on awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State is significant ($p = 0.000$). This means that socio economic factors such as income, education, and occupation significantly influence the awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State. This result agrees with Miner et al. (2015), who found that knowledge of water purification was statistically significantly associated with the level of education among respondents in Lamingo, Plateau State. Those with higher education levels tended to have better knowledge of purification methods.

Similarly, Abera, et al (2020), observed in their study in rural Ethiopia that poor knowledge related to water, sanitation and hygiene were more common among residents with lower socio economic status. They noted that education level in particular had a significant influence on WASH knowledge and practices. The findings are also consistent with Rima et al. (2017), who reported a statistically significant difference in knowledge regarding water sanitation and hygiene based on mothers' education levels in rural Nepal. Those with higher education demonstrated better knowledge.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were made:

1. Household owners in Zamfara State demonstrate a significant level of awareness about water purification techniques.
2. Socio economic factors such as income, education, and occupation significantly influence the awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion, the study recommended the following:

1. The Zamfara State Water Board should leverage the existing awareness base by implementing community-led water purification education programmes.
2. The Zamfara State government should provide subsidies or incentives for water purification tools and products to encourage wider adoption of purification practices.

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Correlation between Home-Background and Achievement in Mathematics among Primary School Pupils in Mbo Local Government, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study adopted correlational design to examine correlation between home-background and achievement in mathematics among primary school pupils with Dyscalculia in Mbo Local Government, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Two research questions were posed and two hypotheses formulated to guide the study. Multiple sampling approaches including purposive sampling approaches, teacher nomination check list, school record was used to select a sample of 130 pupils' with dyscalculia for the study. Two instruments titled "questionnaire Home background" and Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) were developed by the researcher and validated by experts and used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was determined and the coefficient using Alpha Cronbach Method and Kuder-Richardson formula (21) was found to be 0.82, 0.84 and 0.83 for parental involvement, home learning environment and Mathematics achievement respectively. The hypotheses were tested using Simple Linear Regression for hypotheses for two hypotheses. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Findings indicated that both parental involvement and home learning environment were significant predictors of academic achievement, accounting for 16.2% and 20.2% of the variance respectively. It was concluded that fostering a supportive home environment through active parental engagement can support the mathematical skills of pupils with dyscalculia. Recommendations include the creation of conducive learning environments at home and increased parental participation in educational activities, to enhance the academic outcomes for these pupils.

Keywords: Home background, Mathematics achievement, parental involvement, home learning environment.

Introduction

Dyscalculia is a specific learning disability that affects an individual's ability to understand and manipulate numbers or mathematical concepts. It is characterized by difficulties in performing arithmetic operations, understanding numerical relationships, and comprehending mathematical symbols. Dyscalculia can manifest in various ways, including problems with counting, number sense, and mathematical reasoning. It has been observed that individuals with dyscalculia struggle to grasp the concept of quantity and numerical relationships, trouble in understanding and using mathematical symbols and notation, have challenges in performing basic operations such as addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division which affected their overall academic achievement in Mathematics (Ogar, Ibok, Odey, Joseph, Unimuke, . & Ungie, 2023). A good academic achievement in Mathematics of pupils' with dyscalculia does not happen by chance. It is a product of effective teaching and learning coupled with the effort of the teachers in the school, and parents at their various home background (Fuchs & Fuchs 2017; Fuchs & Fuchs, 2020). Home background refers to the social, economic, and cultural environment in which a child is raised. It encompasses various factors, including family structure, parental education,

Correlation between Home-Background... (Ibok, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610558>
socioeconomic status, cultural values, and the availability of resources and support systems. Home background significantly influences a child's development, educational experiences, and overall well-being (Hill & Tyson, 2015; Geary, 2019).

Disparities in achievement result from the majority of parents' lack of resources or expertise to properly assist their kids' arithmetic development. Additionally, parents are not well-versed in how to properly explain mathematics to their children, which can result in misconceptions and a lack of faith in their skills. Some of them lack the necessary skills or confidence to engage meaningfully in their children's mathematical education (Eburu et al. 2023). Many parents are unsure about how to effectively engage in their children's education, particularly in mathematics. Although some parents engage in various supportive practices, including helping with homework, providing resources, and creating a conducive learning environment. However, not all forms of support are equally effective in promoting mathematics achievement of pupils with Dyscalculia. Understanding the mechanisms through which home background influence mathematics achievement is essential. Addressing these factors can help create supportive environments that enhance the academic outcomes for pupils with dyscalculia. (Butterworth & Yeo 2015; Butterworth, & Yeo, 2017). The academic achievement of pupils with dyscalculia is influenced by various home background factors, including parental involvement, home learning environment. These home factors are identified as important factors that determine the academic success of children with learning disabilities, including dyscalculia.

Parental involvement refers to the active participation of parents in their children's education, including involvement in school activities, homework, and creating a supportive home learning environment. Active parental involvement in a child's education significantly influences their academic achievement, particularly in mathematics. When parents engage in homework support, provide encouragement, and participate in math-related activities, it fosters a positive learning environment. This involvement helps pupils with dyscalculia develop better mathematical skills and confidence. Parental involvement can take various forms, including direct academic support, emotional encouragement, and the creation of a conducive learning environment (Kaufmann & von Aster, 2021). Mazzocco (2017) stated that children with dyscalculia benefit significantly from parents who engage in their learning process, providing assistance with homework and participating in math-related activities. This active involvement helps reinforce mathematical concepts and boosts confidence. Jeynes (2016) found a positive relationship between parental involvement and students' academic achievement. A study conducted by Geary (2019) found that when parents express belief in their child's abilities and provide emotional encouragement, it positively impacts the child's attitude towards mathematics. This support can help alleviate anxiety and frustration, common among pupils with dyscalculia, thereby enhancing their academic performance. Davis-Kean, (2019) found a significant influence of parent education in terms of involving on child achievement. Fuchs, and Fuchs, (2016) conducted a study of role of family involvement in the mathematics achievement of students with learning disabilities and found parental involvement significantly influence mathematics achievement of students with learning disabilities. Mazzocco and Thompson (2017) conducted a study a study on home factors and mathematics achievement and found a significant influence of parental support on mathematics achievement. Miller and Tinsley (2018) found a significant influence of parental support on the mathematics achievement of students with learning disabilities. Sirin (2018) found a significant influence parental financial support on academic achievement:

Research conducted by Butterworth and Yeo (2015) emphasized the importance of using effective strategies in parental involvement. Parents who utilized structured approaches, such as incorporating games and visual aids into learning, were more successful in helping their children grasp mathematical concepts. This study found that such strategies not only improved understanding but also made learning more enjoyable for children with dyscalculia. Van der Ven et al. (2020) found out that higher socioeconomic status often correlates with greater access to educational resources, which can enhance parental involvement in mathematics. The study indicated that pupils with dyscalculia from higher SES backgrounds tended to perform better academically due to the additional support and resources available at home. A longitudinal study conducted by Ritchie and Bates (2019) demonstrated that sustained parental involvement over time leads to better long-term academic outcomes for children with dyscalculia. The study concluded that consistent engagement in a child's education fosters a strong foundation in mathematical skills, helping to close the achievement gap between pupils with dyscalculia and their peers. Parental involvement and engagement in children's education—such as helping with homework and encouraging mathematical discussions, the quality of the home learning environment, including access to educational resources (such as books, manipulative, and technology), can improve academic performance (Hill & Tyson, 2015; Fan & Chen, 2019). Conclusively, active engagement, emotional support, effective strategies, and socioeconomic factors contributed to the level of parental involvement and its impact on mathematical performance.

The quality of the home learning environment, including access to educational resources (such as books, manipulative, and technology), plays a crucial role in shaping a child's mathematical abilities. A stimulating environment that encourages exploration and practice can help mitigate the challenges faced by pupils with dyscalculia, leading to improved academic

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outcomes in mathematics. By fostering a supportive and engaging home environment, parents can significantly enhance their children's learning experiences and outcomes in mathematics. The home learning environment (HLE) plays a crucial role in the academic achievement of children, particularly those with learning disabilities like dyscalculia. For instance, a study conducted by O'Connor et al. (2020) found that parents who actively participated in their children's learning, particularly in mathematics, positively influenced their children's academic achievement. Research conducted by Landerl et al. (2018) found that children exposed to a variety of mathematical resources at home perform better in mathematics. Access to educational materials, such as books, games, and technology, is crucial for children with dyscalculia. Additionally, a meta-analysis conducted by McGough et al. (2021) highlighted the importance of using manipulative and digital tools to support the learning of children with dyscalculia. According to a study by Kearney et al. (2022), children with dyscalculia who experienced a supportive home environment showed improved attitudes towards mathematics, which in turn enhanced their academic performance. A positive and encouraging learning atmosphere at home can reduce anxiety and foster a love for learning. Kearney, Albano and McGuire (2022) examine the role of family support in the academic achievement of children with learning disabilities and found home environment significant on the academic achievement of pupils with learning disabilities.

Kauffman and Landrum (2019) found a significant influence of home environment on the academic success of students with dyscalculia. Research conducted by Kauffman, Landrum, and McGhee (2019) found that pupils with dyscalculia who came from homes with rich mathematical interactions performed better in standardized math assessments compared to those from less supportive environments. Sullivan, and Brown (2020) found home learning environment significantly influence mathematics achievement in children with dyscalculia. Ritchie and Bates (2019) conducted a study indicating that a rich home learning environment—characterized by access to books, educational games, and parental encouragement—positively correlates with improved mathematical skills among children with dyscalculia. The study emphasizes that a stimulating environment can help mitigate some of the difficulties faced by these pupils. A longitudinal study by Bock et al. (2021) demonstrated that early interventions in the home learning environment, such as introducing math-related activities, led to significant improvements in mathematical skills over time. Fuchs et al. (2020) stated that the importance of structured home-based interventions that focus on mathematical skills, lead to improved outcomes for children with dyscalculia. Parental involvement, access to educational resources, and a supportive learning atmosphere are critical factors that can enhance mathematical understanding and performance. Pupils with dyscalculia who had access to tailored educational resources—such as apps designed for learning math—showed significant improvement in their mathematical abilities. A stimulating and supportive home environment that encourages learning can help children with dyscalculia develop better coping strategies and skills in mathematics.

Research questions

The following research questions were posed

1. How does parental involvement relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia?
2. How does home learning environment relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia?

Research hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study.

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant relationship between Parental involvement and achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia in Mbo Local Government, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant relationship between Learning Environment and achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia in Mbo Local Government, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study area was Mbo Local Government area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The research design used for this study was the correlational survey design. The researchers used this design to established the relationship between home background variables (in terms parental involvement and home learning environment) and academic achievement of pupils' with dyscalculia in Mathematics . The population for the study consists of all the 330 primary four pupils' with dyscalculia in 25 public primary schools in Mbo Local Government area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Multi stage sampling procedure was adopted for the study which consisted from the each selected schools, researchers used school Mathematics Record and Teacher Nomination Checklist to select a sample of 130 pupils' with dyscalculia for the study. The instruments used for data collection were the questionnaire titled "Home background and achievement test in Mathematics. The questionnaire was made of 12 items, with 6 items to measure each sub-level in terms of parental involvement and home learning environment.. The questionnaire was based on four point scale of strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly

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 disagreed. Mathematics Achievement Test was made up of 25 items constructed by the researchers with help of two experts in Mathematics education. The items were constructed based on primary four Mathematics syllabus with four options A, B, C, D. A correct answer attracts one mark while incorrect answer attracts zero (0) mark. The instrument was face-validated by two experts in Measurement and Evaluation, two expert in special educators and two Mathematics Educators, all from the University of Calabar. Corrections were pointed out by the experts and adjusted by the researchers and the document was considered valid. The reliability of the questionnaire using Alpha Cronbach Method for .82 for parental involvement and .84 for home learning environment while the reliability estimate of the pupils' Mathematics achievement test was established through Kuder Richardson formula K-R20 which gives .83. Since the reliability index is above 0.50, the estimates were considered high enough for the study. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) computer programme was used to analyze the data collected. The hypotheses were tested using Simple Linear Regression for two hypotheses. All hypotheses were tested at -05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results

The result of the analysis is presented in tables 1, 2, 3 and 4. Descriptive statistics was used to answer research questions while Simple regression Analysis was used to test the null hypotheses ast .05 significant level.

Research question one

How does parental involvement relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia? The research question was answered using co-efficient of determinant. This was based on the data generated from responses to the questionnaire items on parental involvement as it relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia. The result is presented in 1.

Table1: Beta(B) and adjusted R² on the how parental involvement relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia?

Variable	B	SE	R ²	Adjusted R ²
Parental involvement	.675	3.87654	.164	.162

Sources; Fieldwork, 2024

The result in Table 1 shows the extent to which parental involvement relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia with adjusted r-square of .162. This indicated that parental involvement accounted for 16.2%, which is low determinants of academic achievement of pupils' with dyscalculia in Mathematics in Mbo Local government Area of Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria Also, the Beta value of .675 which measuring the effect size or the strength of a relationship between variables showing that parental involvement contributed 67.5% effect which is moderate on achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia in Mbo Local government Area of Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria

Research question two

How does home learning environment relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia? The research question was answered using co-efficient of determinant. This was based on the data generated from responses to the questionnaire items on home learning environment as its relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia. The result is presented in 2.

Table 2: Beta (B) and adjusted R² on the how home learning environment relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia?

Variable	B	SE	R ²	Adjusted R ²
Home learning environment	.786	3.76548	.204	.202

Sources: Field work 2024

The result in Table 2 shows the extent to which home learning relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia with adjusted r-square of .202. This indicated that home learning environment accounted for 20.2%, which is low determinants of academic achievement of pupils' with dyscalculia in Mathematics in Mbo Local government Area of Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria Also, the Beta value of .786 which measuring the effect size or the strength of a relationship between variables showing that home learning environment contributed 78.6 % effect which is high on achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia in Mbo Local government Area of Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria

Correlation between Home-Background... (Ibok, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610558>

Testing the null hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between Parental involvement and achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia in Mbo local government, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

The independent variable in this hypothesis is parental involvement while the dependent variable is achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia. To test this hypothesis, Simple Linear regression was used. The F-ratio test was used to test for the significance of the overall prediction model, r-value was used to established the relationship between the variables while t-test was used to test for the significance of the contribution of the regression constant and coefficient (which represents the predictive power of the independent variable) in the prediction model. The mean and standard deviation of the variables were also computed as it is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Simple Regression Analysis of Parental involvement as it relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia

Variables	X	SD			
Parental involvement	15.987	1.7654			
Mathematics achievement	18.908	2.8765			
R-value = .405		Adjusted R-squared = .162			
R-squared = .164		Standard error = 3.87654			
Source of variation	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F-value	P-value
Regression	654.908	1	654.908	25.151	.000*
Residual	3332.989	128	26.039		
Total	3987.897	129			
Predictor variable	Unstandardized coefficient B	Std.error	Std. coeff	t-value	p-value
Constant	34.897	3.196		10.919*	.000
Parental involvement	.675	.123	.096	5.488*	.000

Significant at .05 level. $P < .05$

The results in Table 3 show that the R-value of .405 was obtained which shows a positive low relationship between Parental involvement and achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia in Mbo Local Government, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The R value resulting in an R-squared value of .164 and adjusted R-square value of 162. This means that the variation of parental involvement accounted for about only 16.2% of the total variation in achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia. The p-value (.000) associated with the computed F-value (25.151) was less than .05. As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that Parental involvement significantly influence achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia with both the regression constant (34.874) and coefficient (.675) contributing significantly in the prediction model ($t = 10.919$ & 5.488 respectively, $p = .000$ & $.000 < .05$).

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between Learning Environment and achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia in Mbo Local Government, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

The independent variable in this hypothesis is home learning environment while the dependent variable is achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia. To test this hypothesis, Simple Linear regression was used. The F-ratio test was used to test for the significance of the overall prediction model, r-value was used to established the relationship between the variables while t-test was used to test for the significance of the contribution of the regression constant and coefficient (which represents the predictive power of the independent variable) in the prediction model. The mean and standard deviation of the variables were also computed as it is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Simple Regression Analysis of home learning environment as it relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia

Variables	X	SD			
Home learning environment	14.543	1.6542			
Mathematics achievement	18.908	2.8765			
R-value = .452		Adjusted R-squared = .202			
R-squared = .204		Standard error = 3.76548			
Source of variation	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F-value	P-value
Regression	813.763	1	813.763	32.816	.000*
Residual	3174.134	128	24.798		
Total	3987.897	129			
Predictor variable	Unstandardized coefficient B	Std.error	Std.coeff	t-value	p-value
Constant	37.986	2.987		12.717*	.000
Home environment	.786	.162	.121	4.852*	.000

Significant at .05 level. $P < .05$

The results in Table 4 show that the R-value of .452 was obtained which shows a positive low relationship between home learning environment and achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia. The R value resulting in an R-squared value of .204 and adjusted R-square value of .202. This means that the variation of home learning environment accounted for about only 20.2% of the total variation in academic achievement of pupils' with dyscalculia in Mathematics. The p-value (.000) associated with the computed F-value (32,816) was less than .05. As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that home learning environment significantly influence achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia with both the regression constant (37.986) and coefficient (.786) contributing significantly in the prediction model ($t = 12.717$ & 4.852 respectively, $p = .000$ & $.000 < .05$).

Discussion of Finding

The result of the first hypothesis revealed that parental involvement significantly predicts academic achievement of pupils' with dyscalculia in Mathematics. The finding agreed with Mazzocco (2017) who stated that children with dyscalculia benefit significantly from parents who engage in their learning process, providing assistance with homework and participating in math-related activities. This active involvement helps reinforce mathematical concepts and boosts confidence. The finding is in line with a study conducted by Geary (2019) who found that when parents express belief in their child's abilities and provide emotional encouragement, it positively impacts the child's attitude towards mathematics. According to Butterworth and Yeo (2015), parents who utilized structured approaches, such as incorporating games and visual aids into learning, were more successful in helping their children grasp mathematical concepts. This study found that such strategies not only improved understanding but also made learning more enjoyable for children with dyscalculia. The finding is in line with Van der Ven et al. (2020) found out that higher socioeconomic status often correlates with greater access to educational resources, which can enhance parental involvement in mathematics. The finding agreed with a longitudinal study conducted by Ritchie and Bates (2019) who stated that sustained parental involvement over time leads to better long-term academic outcomes for children with dyscalculia. The study concluded that consistent engagement in a child's education fosters a strong foundation in mathematical skills, helping to close the achievement gap between pupils with dyscalculia and their peers.

The result of the second hypothesis revealed that home learning environment significantly predicts academic achievement of pupils' with dyscalculia in Mathematics. The finding agreed a study conducted by O'Connor et al. (2020) who found that parents who actively participated in their children's learning, particularly in mathematics, positively influenced their children's academic achievement. The finding is in line with a research conducted by Landerl et al. (2018) who found that children exposed to a variety of mathematical resources at home perform better in mathematics. According to a study by Kearney et al. (2022), children with dyscalculia who experienced a supportive home environment showed improved attitudes towards mathematics, which in turn enhanced their academic performance. A positive and encouraging learning atmosphere at

Correlation between Home-Background... (Ibok, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610558>
home can reduce anxiety and foster a love for learning. The finding is in consonance with a research conducted by Kauffman et al. (2019) who found that pupils with dyscalculia who came from homes with rich mathematical interactions performed better in standardized math assessments compared to those from less supportive environments. The finding agreed with Ritchie and Bates (2019) and found home learning environment—characterized by access to books, educational games, and parental encouragement positively correlates with improved mathematical skills among children with dyscalculia. The finding agreed with Bock et al. (2021) who found that home learning environment, such as introducing math-related activities, led to significant improvements in mathematical skills over time.

Conclusion

The development of mathematics skills in children with dyscalculia is significantly influenced by various home factors, including parental involvement and the overall home learning environment. Pupils with dyscalculia who receive active engagement and support from their parents tend to perform better in mathematics. A nurturing home environment that encourages learning, provides resources, and fosters positive attitudes towards mathematics can mitigate some of the challenges faced by children with dyscalculia. Parental involvement home learning environment not only enhances academic achievement but also contributes to the emotional and psychological well-being of these children. Based on the finding of the study, it was concluded that parental involvement, home learning environment significant relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia.

Recommendations

Based on the finding of the study, the following recommended were made

1. Schools should encourage parents to participate in their children's education actively. Workshops and seminar should be organized regularly for parents to equip parents with strategies to support their children's learning effectively.
2. Parents should create a conducive learning space at home that is free from distractions and equipped with necessary learning materials. This environment would promote curiosity and exploration of mathematical concepts.
3. Schools and educational organizations should provide parents with access to resources, such as educational games, apps, and books tailored for children with dyscalculia. These tools can help to reinforce learning outside the classroom.
4. Establishing regular communication between parents and teachers is recommended to help track the child's progress and address any challenges promptly. This collaboration can lead to more tailored support for the child.
5. Schools should develop specialized programs that focus on enhancing parental support and involvement for children with dyscalculia. These programs should include individualized learning plans that involve parents in the educational process.

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Effect of Concentrated Language Encounter Instructional Strategy on Reading Skills among Primary School Pupils in Dutsin-ma, Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper investigates Effect of Concentrated Language Encounter Instructional Strategy on Reading Skills among Primary School Pupils in Dutsin-ma, Katsina State, Nigeria Two research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. The study utilized quasi experimental design. The population of the study consists of all pupils in Demonstration School, Isa Kaita College of Education during the 2023/2024 academic session in Dutsin-ma Katsina state. 16 primary four pupils were selected using multi-stage sampling technique to constitute the Sample size of the study the instruments used for data collection are included: Sight Word Recognition Test of 100 High Frequency English Words (SWRTHFEW), Sentence Comprehension Tests (SCT) and Reading of New Texts Tests (RNTT). The coefficient of stability obtained for each instrument is 0.98 for SWRTHFEW, 1.00 for SCT and 0.99 for RNTT. The treatment consisted of Concentrated Language Encounter module one. Data were administered, research questions were answered using bar chart and hypothesis tested using t-test unrelated sample at 0.05 level of significance. The Results indicated that. Post-tests mean scores of pupils in the experimental group which received intervention in using literacy were significantly higher than that of those in control group who used conventional method. It was concluded that the results and responses of the samples the differences and the performance of school children after intervention proves the effectiveness of this method, the improvement in children performance in general was mainly due to the intervention given to them.the study recommends the use of Concentrated Language Encounter method in acquisition of literacy skills with non-readers.

Keyword; Language Encounter, Instructional Strategy, Reading Skills.

Introduction

One of the objectives of Primary Education stated in the National Policy on Education (2012) was to inculcate permanent literacy and the ability to communicate effectively. But there would appear to be a confusion on how to achieve these objectives. For example, Unoh (2014) observed that the task of teaching children how to read in schools in Nigeria has been left entirely to the individual teachers. These teachers probably do not understand the great intellectual significance of the simple task KIU Journal of Social Sciences 170 reading. For this reason, most of our Primary and Secondary School learners cannot read simple texts that are meant for them to read independently. There are several causes for reading failure among our pupils in Demonstration School Isa Kaita College of Education Dutsinma Katsin State. However, the children in the lower primary school are taught how to read in English (L2) before they actually acquired the oral proficiency in the language. Finocchiaro, (2015) stated in her stages of teaching and learning of reading in second language (L2) that “students read material they have learned to say very well”. This statement is supporting the view that children can read well in the language they have acquired oral proficiency. In line with this, Unoh (2012) further stated that his ultimate aim of what learning to read and reading to learn, is that the skills associated with listening and speaking are developed before that of reading and writing. One other probable problem which is highly suspected that makes reading very difficult among children in the state is that children are taught how to read English language books by oral recitation. This is when teachers read sentences inside their textbooks and children repeat after the teacher. In most cases, these children memorize the sentences and only pronounce word without identifying the prints that represent these words and teacher assume that these children can read. One other possible cause of reading failure among these pupils is the issue of automatic promotion of pupils, especially in junior primary classes regardless of the child’s performance in the former class. This negligence of individual differences by teachers to the researcher might again be a contributing factor in the production of graduates at these levels without being able to read simple books independently. Other possible cause of reading failure among our pupils in the State are lack of text and story books and lack

of teachers using appropriate methods to teach children how to read. These problems and many others have left our pupils under a number of disadvantages. For example, the majority of the children leave primary schools without being fully literate. It is with this view in mind that the researcher wants to investigate the extent to which Concentrated Language Encounter can help develop reading skills among pupils in primary schools.

Considering the high rate of reading failure in both public and private schools in the State reading specialists are faced with the challenge of providing effective remediation. Children with problems in reading English as second language have not been taught how to speak English before they are taught how to read it. Which means that children have not been taught in a way they will learn how to read effectively. Similarly, teachers have not been using appropriate strategies that would promote effective reading in English. For effective reading, teachers must use the skills to help children who come to school to learn how to read in English. Specifically, it is important to consider how reading specialists can draw on the language skills the children already have as they come to school in teaching them to read effectively in English. This study will help the researcher to find out if the Concentrated Language Encounter Method when properly used during intervention will help to improve the children's ability to recognize sight vocabulary and comprehend printed materials in English.

Objective of the Study

The research is designed mainly to investigate the effect of Concentrated Language Encounter Method in development of beginning reading skills among primary school pupils who are non-readers. Specifically:

1. To investigate mean performance/skill acquisition scores of pupils taught vocabulary using Concentrated Language Encounter and those exposed to lecture method.

Research Questions

1. What is the mean performance/skill acquisition scores of pupils taught vocabulary using Concentrated Language Encounter and those exposed to lecture method?

Research Hypotheses

1. H_{01} There is no significant difference in mean performance/skill acquisition scores of pupils taught vocabulary using Concentrated Language Encounter and those exposed to lecture method.

Methodology

This study utilized the quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pre-test, post-test control group design. The design featured two groups. Subjects were randomly selected and assigned to experimental and control groups (R). Both the experimental and control groups were administered the post-test (O). Only the experimental group was exposed to the treatment (X) on literacy using Concentrated Language Encounter Method while the control group received no treatment but was taught through conventional method. A sample of 16 non – readers who have already received at least three and a half years of primary education were selected after the administration of pre-test which is the 100 English high frequency words for Nigerian children (Umolu, 2014). Eight (8) nonreaders formed the experimental group and another eight (8) for the control group. The instruments used for the study includes: Sight Word Recognition Test of 100 High Frequency English Words (SWRTHFEW), Sentence Comprehension Tests (SCT) and Reading of New Texts Tests (RNTT). The coefficient of stability obtained for each instrument is 0.98 for SWRTHFEW, 1.00 for SCT and 0.99 for RNTT. These were established through test re-test method.

Presentation of Results

Research Question one

What is the mean performance/skill acquisition scores of pupils taught vocabulary using Concentrated Language Encounter and those exposed to lecture method?

Table 1 English Sight Word Vocabulary before Intervention. Experimental Group

Child Score out 100 Word						
	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Average
A1X	1	2	1	1	1	1
A2X	2	2	2	2	2	2
A3X	1	1	1	1	1	1
A4X	1	2	1	1	1	1
A5X	2	1	2	2	3	1
A6X	2	2	2	2	2	2
A7X	1	2	1	1	1	2
A8X	1	1	1	1	1	1

Table 2 English Sight Word Vocabulary before Intervention. Control Group

Child Score out 100 Word						
	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Average
B1	1	2	1	1	1	1
B2	2	1	2	2	3	2
B3	2	1	2	2	2	2
B4	1	2	1	1	1	1
B5	1	2	2	1	1	1
B6	2	1	2	2	2	2
B7	2	1	2	2	2	2
B8	1	2	1	1	1	1

The pre-test of the ability of primary school children who are non- readers in both experimental and control groups to read the 100 English Sight Words shows that they are at the same level and are all nonreaders.

The test scores are shown in Table 1 & 2.

Hypothesis one

H_{01} There is no significant difference in mean performance/skill acquisition scores of pupils taught vocabulary using Concentrated Language Encounter and those exposed to lecture method.

Table 5 Group Difference in English Sight Vocabulary t-test

	N	X	St	df	t-cal	P-value
Experimental Group	8	9	1.88			
Control	8	3.16	0.79	14	253.23	0.000

Control Group 83.16 0.79 $P < .05$ For degree of freedom of 6 and level of significance at .05, with P. value of 0.000, the calculated t-test statistics is given at 253.23 which is significant beyond 0.05 level. Hypothesis one was therefore rejected in favour of primary school children who are non- readers in the experimental group. The general findings from the result showed that primary school children who are non- readers who received intervention in literacy skill have higher mean scores in acquisition of English sight vocabulary than the primary school children who are non- readers who did not received intervention.

Discussion of Findings

In analyzing the reading level of children in both the control and experimental groups before exposure to CLE, the research findings, presented in Table 1, showed that none of them could identify more than three of the 100 high frequency words. Thus, they were all non-readers because, according to the guidelines for identification of reading problems, anyone who read less than 10 of the first 25 words during assessment is considered to be a non-reader. The reading levels of learners should be given priority attention in order to prepare them for the acquisition of a sight vocabulary which is very crucial in learning to read. Words are the building blocks of comprehension and word recognition is the foundation of reading process. It is recognized that without the ability to recognize words in continuous text quickly and accurately, this goal cannot be achieved. According to Rupley, Logan, and Nichols (2012, sight vocabulary is a key component of effective reading instruction.

Similarly, Flood and Robb (2014) buttressed the fact that both fluency and comprehension are affected by sight vocabulary knowledge. The findings revealed that there is a significant difference in the acquisition of English sight vocabulary of primary school children in experimental group with those in the control group. However, the significant difference which was observed in this study showed that Concentrated Language Encounter was very effective in facilitating learners' acquisition of sight words in English. This is consistent with the findings of Rayner and Pallatsek (2013) that reading involves visual discrimination and independent identification of words. That is, if a child can differentiate between letters and words perceived, then the visual discrimination is possible. When a child is able to identify words in isolation and read them accurately and can read sentences in a book successfully, then we can say that the child is now ready to process reading materials. Similarly, Hanson and Reynolds (2014) observed that when a child had acquired oral language proficiency, then the child moves to discriminate and attempt to read in order to identify visual, auditory and context clues. They will also substitute the consonants, the vowels of alphabets as well as attainment. They went on to say that the use of the visual auditory perception was that the child sees the word first, and then tries to sound out the word. From there, the child analyze the word to discover the graphemes (letter clues) to phonemes (sound clues), and relates this to the particular word context. The child then blends the sounds together to pronounce the word and relates its meaning in the language of the child. This they said is why Concentrated Language Encounter is effective because it deals extensively with word recognition, blended with the correct pronunciation and meaning of what was read. It was also noted that the number of words known by the child at any given age was a unique feature of that child. The findings of this study also revealed that there is a significant difference in sentence comprehension of primary four children in the experimental group as compared with that of those in the control group. The general performance of children in sentence comprehension has actually shown how effective Concentrated Language Encounter method is in aiding children in sentence comprehension. This confirmed the study carried out by Walker (2015) who stated that at the beginning of reading, it is essential that all the words to be read should be within the child's vocabulary so that he/she will be able to recognize the words which may lead him to comprehend. The author went on to explain that if a word was an ambiguous one, the teacher needs a process of selection which he operated on, so that the child can get the correct meaning of the word. This is possible when the teacher uses the word in different sentences which could give the word different meanings from each other. To further explain the importance of comprehension, Pearson and Duke (2002) stressed that comprehension guides students in becoming aware of how well they have read as they attempt to put into writing or recall what they have read.

Conclusion

The study was conducted to find out the effect of using the Concentrated Language Encounter method in developing literacy skill in primary schools in Demonstration School, Isa Kaita College of Education Dutsinma, Katsina State. This was based on the gap that existed in literacy training of primary school children. The variables of sight vocabulary and comprehension skills were put to test. Based on the investigation and data analysis, it is evident that primary school children could do well in literacy if appropriate method is employed. From the results and the responses of the samples, the differences in the performance of school children after intervention proved the effectiveness of this method. Therefore, it can be concluded that, the improvement in children's performance in general was mainly due to the intervention given to them.

Recommendation

It has been noticed from the results of the study conducted that, reading specialists in primary schools are needed to identify, assess and remedy reading problems in children identified as non-readers. The researcher also observed during the study that, the environment under which children learn and most often the techniques used in teaching affect the children. In most cases children who are having problems in reading are being lumped together in a class with those who have no problems with reading. This worsened their condition because no individual differences are taken into consideration by the teachers; therefore the researcher recommends that:

1. There is need for variation in teaching methods by teachers and resource personnel to cater for the less privileged ones in the class. Teaching in small groups and if possible individually should be used and the level of books used should vary according to the levels of the children.
2. Scaffolding technique as in Concentrated Language Encounter method can be used to effect change in learning to read with slow readers.
3. Training of teachers and resource teachers can be achieved by regular attendance of seminars, conferences, and workshops, especially on the techniques of how to use Concentrated Language Encounter method to minimize some of the reading problems we have in our primary schools today.

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Effect of Moonlight Tales on Social Cohesion among Middle Basic Pupils in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of moonlight tales on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State. The study adopted a non-randomized pretest posttest control group quasi-experimental research design. One research question and three hypotheses were raised. The population of the study consisted all pupils in middle basic schools in Osun State. The target population comprised of basic four pupils, sampled from four intact classes (2 private and 2 public schools), using simple random sampling technique. Social Cohesion Test (SCT) was developed to obtain valid information from the participants. Content validity was conducted by two experts in Childhood Education and Educational Psychology, while test re-test reliability used yielded index of 0.79. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research question, while the hypotheses were tested using ANCOVA at a significant level of 0.05. The findings revealed that there was moderate level of social cohesion among pupils at the initial stage. Also, there was; significant effect of treatment on social cohesion among middle basic pupils, significant interaction effect of treatment and school ownership on social cohesion among the pupils, and significant interaction effect of treatment and family type on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State. It was recommended that government should ensure the use of moonlight tales to bridge the gap between school and home cultural education, the use of moonlight tales is maintained by both private and public schools, the use of moonlight tales to enhance cultural inclusivity and social cohesion.

Keynotes: Moonlight tales, Folktales, Riddles, Social Cohesion, Moral values

Introduction

In a typical African Traditional setting, moonlight tales entail storytelling practice within the African culture, or an ethnic group in West Africa, particularly Nigeria. These tales are basically told in the evening or at night, often under the moonlight, creating a captivating and communal experience. The stories are passed down through generations and play a significant role in preserving and transmitting cultural values, history, and moral lessons. Moonlight tales are primarily an oral tradition. They are passed down verbally from one generation to another, relying on the spoken word to convey narratives. This reflects the rich oral culture of the people. The tales are not just for entertainment but serve as a means of educating and imparting cultural values. Through these stories, children and community members learn about their history, societal norms, and moral principles. Moonlight tales cover a wide range of themes, including folklore, mythology, morality, and historical events. These stories often feature animals, spirits, and mythical beings, providing explanations for natural phenomena and human experiences.

The values embedded in moonlight tales are diverse and reflect on the cultural, moral, and social principles of the people. Moonlight tales often emphasize the importance of moral integrity and ethical behaviour. Characters in the stories face moral dilemmas, and the resolution of these dilemmas provides lessons on the virtues of honesty, integrity, righteousness, etc. Many tales highlight the value of community cooperation and collective well-being. Characters work together to solve problems, reflecting the importance of unity and collaboration in Yoruba culture. Wisdom is highly valued in Yoruba culture, and many moonlight tales feature characters who demonstrate intelligence and the ability to solve problems through cleverness. These tales often emphasize the importance of acquiring knowledge and using it wisely (Ishola, 2015).

Moonlight tales are in two parts. One part precludes the other. There are *Àlò-àpamò* (riddles) and *Àlò-àpagbè* (folktales) (Akanni, 2014). *Àlò-àpamò* comes before *Àlò-àpagbè*. *Àlò-àpamò* is normally used to awaken and to arouse the interest of the listeners and make them ready for the story proper. It is also used to awaken and to arouse the intelligence of the audience. Olatunji (2014) stated five functions served by *Àlò-àpagbè*, which are; they help in keeping the audience mentally awake before

folktales are told; they also serve as some entertainment value before the folktale is told, they exercise the intellect and wit of the audience, they serve as instruction in social and material culture, they serve as an escape mechanism for the repressions brought about by the sanctions of the Yorùbá society.

Whatever moral value the story teller desires to pass across to his audience will form the basis of the story he chooses. There are different but significant moral and social values embedded in each story. For instance, there are lessons on hard work as against laziness, there are those on kindness and love as against wickedness and there are those on being hospitable as against being rude to the strangers and of course, there are those on contentment as against greediness and covetousness among many others. One other thing to be said before going into the narration of some of these stories is that some stories may be accompanied with singing in which the story teller leads and his audiences follow. When it is like this, the story teller is the one that gives the key points of the story in the song while the audience repeats the refrain or the chorus. The song is mostly intended to give aesthetic value to the story, to awaken the audience from their slumber (since the moonlight tales are told in the night after supper) and to also drive home the point the story teller is bringing to the fore (Akanni, 2014).

However, as numerous as the Yorùbá cultural concepts, the basic school curriculum has favoured some. Some parts of basic school Yoruba language curriculum teach about social cohesion among learners both young and adults. This provides an avenue through which life skills, principles, and values for personal, social, economic development are propagated (Cloete & Kotze, 2019). School safety and feelings of safety of both pupils and school personnel are expressed in issues, such as pupils' antisocial behaviour and violence in and around school, bullying, various disciplinary problems, and shooting incidents, all of which alert teachers, parents, and educational authorities (Bayh, 2015). In a reaction to this problem of social behaviour, the focus is directed at social cohesion or social climate characteristics of schools (Carbines, et al., 2016). National educational and local school policies concentrate on activities to assess or enhance school safety for both pupils and teachers (Cowie & Oztug, 2018). Moreover, increasing attention is being devoted to identifying correlates and possible causes of problem of social behaviour including the improvement of safety and feelings of safety at school

For safety and peaceful coexistence to be maintained, social cohesion has goal focusing on encouraging social change, and not only to transfer certain skills. It has to cover multiple segments of importance for peace building. Violence is not only direct and physical but can include the less obvious types of violence; structural (the one that is built into the system of governing themselves) and cultural (the aspects of culture that makes violence possible and acceptable), that create a fertile soil for the spreading of direct violence or more or less openly encourages it. One of the most things to measure are the sociological expressions that are aimed at behavioural change, especially when the students to be changed, and from whom the change in the school is expected, are living in an environment that is not changing, or it is changing to the worst. One of the elements that make behavior change difficult is culture (Cloete & Kotze, 2019). Thus, in order to establish durable peace in the school systems among the learners, administrators must analyze the structural causes of conflict and initiate social structural change. Therefore, social cohesion must be maintained to promote nonviolent mechanisms that eliminate violence, foster structures that meet basic needs, and maximise public participation (Cloete & Kotze, 2019).

Considering the foregoing, it will be observed that there are crucial lessons that could enhance the peaceful coexistence among learners within the school community. If the lessons are imbibed, the environment will be a harmonious place to live in. It is therefore imperative that moonlight tales should be put in the curriculum of both primary and secondary schools as a teaching strategy. Just as religious instructions are given to the students in schools for the purpose of inculcating the fear of God in them, so also, as moonlight tales are part of what the pupils have to be taught in schools, if properly used and maintained, it will go a long way in inculcating morals and morality in the learners. It is a known fact that all the immoral behaviours children are known within this present age are due to lack of moral discipline. If moonlight tales are put in the curriculum of schools, these will be used in instilling moral and cultural values in the children. There are lots of educational benefits derivable from moonlight tales, a traditional oral genre (Moser, 2017). This attests to the potency of the moonlight tales as an educational tool. With the current technological gadgets available for use in collection, documentation, dissemination and promotion of moonlight tales, today's children have abundant opportunity to access this oral genre.

Adeyemi (2017) attested to the assertion above where he stated that moonlight tales can be used to inculcate virtues in school age children such as humility, gratitude, respect for elders and constituted authority, perseverance, conformity to societal norms, co-operation, hospitality, truthfulness, honesty, willingness to take advice, patriotism, courage and love, loyalty to one's fatherland, hard work and the fear of God. Yorùbá culture is embedded with moral values, some of which are taught with the use of moonlight tales. If the young children are taught these moral values in schools, all the decadence we are witnessing today among the youth of our society will be minimized if not totally eradicated. This is why the study seek to find out the effect of moonlight tales on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

In the process of having modern civilization, knowledge about traditional culture and cultural heritage are being pushed aside or abandoned. This has created a great effect on the child's cultural knowledge, moral values, social behaviour and this developed into its negative effects on the training of Yoruba children (Mercy, 2018). The moonlight tales not only has great advantage towards increasing pupils' cultural knowledge, but also influence their social cohesion, cultural attitudes, self-esteem, communication, and improves their personal entrepreneurial characteristics. Different writings have been about the benefits of moonlight tales, not only for children's entertainment but for their education and a fulfilling family life, some of which negates its effects on the social cohesion that exist among the school children. The rate of moral decadence in our society is becoming too high because parents have left their children in the hands of changing world and modern civilization in pursuit of material wealth. Thus, the traditional ways of inculcating virtues to children have been abandoned. This is as a result of the fact that parents, teachers and society at large have relented on the efforts to make use of the traditional means of training children through moonlight tales which could be in form of myths, folktales, folklores, and other forms of oral literature to instill moral values, societal norms, and virtues in the children.

Over the years, many studies have considered how moonlight tales are being told (Akanni 2014; Adeyemi, 2017; Mercy, 2018). These studies talked about the significance of folktales in moulding children's moral behaviour, how moonlight tales are being told, and the values embedded in it in reawaking the intelligent capability of the children. However, none of these studies identified moonlight tales as a strategy for moulding and shaping social behaviour among the children. This leaves a research gap which has to be filled to ensure relevant policy formulation on the use of moonlight tales in teaching pupils at basic level of education. Thus, the study seeks to investigate the effect of moonlight tales on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

Objectives of the Study

The major purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of moonlight tales on social cohesion among middle basic school pupils in Osun State. The study therefore sought to:

1. Examine the level of social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.
2. Investigate the significant effect of the treatment on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.
3. Ascertain whether there is significant interaction effect of treatment and school ownership on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.
4. Ascertain whether there is significant interaction effect of treatment and family type on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

Research Question

The following question was answered:

1. What is the level of social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested.

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant effect of the treatment on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and school ownership on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.
3. **H₀₃**: There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and family type on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

Methodology

The study focused on the effect of moonlight tales on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun state. It adopted a non-randomized pretest posttest control group quasi-experimental design. Pretest and posttest was administered to the experimental and control group. Pretest was administered in order to determine the equivalence of the two groups in their ability level. At the end of the treatment, posttest was also administered to the two groups to determine the significant difference if any, in the social cohesion among the pupils. Quasi-experimental design was considered appropriate for the study because intact classes were used to avoid disruption of normal class lessons. A pretest posttest control group quasi experimental design using 2x2x2 factorial design was used. The first two factorial levels were the experimental groups and the control group. The second factorial level was school ownership occurring in either private or public, while the third factorial level was the family type which occurs in either nuclear or extended family. This design allowed the experimental groups to receive treatment while

control group did not receive. The control groups were exposed to the same pre-test with the experimental groups after which the experimental groups were subjected to the treatment. Both the experimental and control groups received the pre-tests and post-tests before and after the treatment respectively.

The population for the study consisted all pupils in middle basic schools in Osun State. The target population comprised of basic four Pupils in Osun Central Senatorial District. The sample consisted of basic four Pupils in four intact classes in the study area. The schools were selected using simple random sampling techniques. For this, four schools were randomly selected (Two Private and Two Public) and assigned control and experimental group using balloting. The researcher developed Social Cohesion Test (SCT) as research instrument to obtain valid information from the participants. These were made up of twenty (20) items drawn from the focusing areas. The instrument was in two sections. The first section which is section A consisted the demographic data (school ownership and family type) while section B consisted the test items on social cohesion.

The content validity of the instrument was done by two experts from Childhood Education and Educational Psychology, while test-retest reliability method was adopted by administering the test to 20 pupils different from the sample selected at two different time with interval of 2 weeks. The correlation between the response from the first and second administration was tested with the use of Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) which yielded an index of 0.79. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) for the research question raised, and inferential statistics (ANCOVA) was used to test the three hypotheses formulated at 0.05 level of significant.

Results

The data collected were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 23.0). The results of the findings are shown below:

Research Question

One research question was raised and was answered with the use of mean and standard deviation.

Research Question: What is the level of social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State?

In other to decide on the level of social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State, the total scores of each of the pupils (respondents) on the pretest given were summed up, having a total minimum of 2, maximum of 20 and the range of 18. This was categorized into three categorical form, which are Low, Moderate, and High. The three categories of low, moderate, and high were determined by dividing the range into three ($18 \div 3 = 6$). Hence, the interval scores between each category is 6. Therefore, the scores were arranged in the following categories to determine low, moderate, and high level of social cohesion among middle basic pupils: 2 – 7 is Low; 8 – 13 is Moderate; and 14 – 20 is High. The result is presented in the table below;

Table 1: Summary of the level of social cohesion among middle basic pupils

Level	Ranges	F	%	Remarks
Low	2 – 7	36	33.3%	
Moderate	8 – 13	49	45.4%	Moderate
High	14 – 20	23	21.3%	

Fieldwork, 2024

The above table revealed that 36 (33.3%) of the total pretest scores showed low level of social cohesion, 49 (45.4%) of the total pretest scores showed moderate level of social cohesion, while 23 (21.3%) of the total pretest scores showed high level of social cohesion. This revealed that majority (45.4%) of the scores from the pupils showed that social cohesion among middle basic pupils is on moderate level. This can therefore be concluded that there is moderate level of social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

Hypotheses Testing

Three research hypotheses were formulated and tested with the use of Analysis of Co-Variance (ANCOVA) at a significant level of 0.05.

Effect of Moonlight Tales... (Abdulwahab & Atoba, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610562>

H₀₁: There is no significant effect of the treatment on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State

Table 2: Summary of (ANCOVA) showing significant effect of treatment on social cohesion among middle basic pupils

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Corrected Model	243.78	2	121.89	7.88	.00	
Intercept	646.38	1	646.38	41.79	.00	
Pretest	29.78	1	29.78	1.93	.17	
Group	232.01	1	232.01	15.00	.00	*Sig.
Error	1624.22	105	15.47			
Total	2036.00	108				
Corrected Total	1868.00	107				

Fieldwork, 2024

Table 2 above showed the effect of moonlight tales on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State. It was revealed from the table above that there is significant effect of treatment on middle basic pupils' social cohesion. This was evident by significant value of 0.00 which is less than the alpha value of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis above which stated that there is no significant main effect of treatment on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State is thereby rejected. Therefore, there is significant main effect of treatment on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

H₀₂: There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and school ownership on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

Table 3: Summary of (ANCOVA) showing significant interaction effect of treatment and school ownership on social cohesion among middle basic pupils

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Intercept	747.98	1	747.98	32.66	.00	
Pretest	13.29	1	13.29	1.07	.30	
Group	220.18	1	220.18	2.00	.39	
School Ownership	241.29	1	241.29	2.37	.03	*Sig.
Group*School ownership	100.84	1	100.84	8.10	.01	*Sig.
Error	513.13	104	11.91			
Total	1850.00	108				
Corrected Total	1102.02	107				

Fieldwork, 2024

Table 3 above showed the interaction effect of treatment and school ownership on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in some selected schools in Osun State. It was revealed from the table above that school ownership does influence pupils' level of social cohesion. This was evident by significant value of 0.03 which is less than the alpha value of 0.05. Also, the sig value of 0.01 which is less than the alpha value of 0.05 indicated that both the treatment and school ownership have interaction effects on pupils' social cohesion. Hence, the null hypothesis above which stated that there is no significant interaction effect of treatment and school ownership on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State is rejected. Therefore, there is significant interaction effect of treatment and school ownership on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

H₀₃: There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and family type on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

Table 4: Summary of (ANCOVA) showing significant interaction effect of treatment and family type on social cohesion among middle basic pupils

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Intercept	513.79	1	513.79	35.59	.00	
Pretest	50.11	1	50.11	3.31	.07	
Group	273.40	1	273.40	4.47	.28	
Family type	1.79	1	1.79	.03	.02	*Sig.
Group*Family type	60.87	1	60.87	4.02	.03	*Sig.
Error	515.27	104	12.23			
Total	1379.23	108				
Corrected Total	865.43	107				

Fieldwork, 2024

Table 4 above showed the interaction effect of treatment and family type on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in some selected schools in Osun State. It was revealed from the table above that family type influence level of social cohesion among middle basic pupils. This was evident by significant value of 0.02 which is less than the alpha value of 0.05. Also, the sig value of 0.03 which is less than the alpha value of 0.05 indicated that both the treatment and family type have interaction effects on pupils' social cohesion. Hence, the null hypothesis above which stated that there is no significant interaction effect of treatment and family type on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State is rejected. Therefore, there is significant interaction effect of treatment and family type on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

Discussions of the Findings

The study above revealed that there was moderate level of social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State. This was seen from the pupils' scores on the pretest given before the treatment, where it was confirmed that middle basic pupils exhibit moderate social relationship as they show empathy, sympathy, love, care, affection, feelings to one and other both in and outside the classroom settings. This is as result of the fact that for peace and peaceful coexistence to maintained in school among teachers and the pupils, positive social behavior must be maintained, as this will pave ways for friendliness and peaceful coexistence. This was supported by the submission of Bayh (2015) who opined that school safety and feelings of safety of both pupils and school personnel are expressed in issues, such as pupils' antisocial behaviour and violence in and around school, bullying, various disciplinary problems, and shooting incidents, all of which alert teachers, parents, and educational authorities. In a reaction to this problem of social behaviour, the focus is directed to social cohesion or social climate characteristics of the schools. This was buttressed by Beauvais & Jenson (2012) who posited that, a school develops a rather specific social culture and ethos of its own, which is expressed also in a specific degree of social cohesion. In a school, each manager, teacher or staff member, or pupil perceives specific qualities of this social cohesion through specific feelings, beliefs, or behaviour of him or herself in relation to the other social actors, and vice.

Furthermore, it was revealed that there was significant effect of treatment (moonlight tales) on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State. This was revealed by the significant value of the response 0.00 which is less than the alpha value of 0.05. This is because pupils in experimental groups were exposure to the treatment package which tells them more about the significance value of social cohesion, gives them more knowledge about social cohesion and how it can be maintained to allow peaceful coexistence. This supported the assertion of Allport (2018), who reported that social cohesion reflects the degree of connectivity between the feelings, beliefs, actions, and behaviour tendencies of various social actors, which involve persons, social groups or categories, or institutions characterised by a multilevel organisation or framework. This was also spelt out of the educational policy at a national level which directed a variety of approaches, projects, and instruments to assess and improve school social cohesion and safety. Also, National Policy on Education, (NPE) clearly stated this to foster its effectiveness and as well included extra financial support for pedagogical and educational initiatives, for school boards to reduce or prevent violence, and for the monitoring of school safety and violent incidents in primary, secondary, and higher education (Mooij & De Wit, 2019).

Moreover, the findings showed that there was no significant interaction effect of treatment and school ownership on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State. It was established from the findings that there was significant effect of treatment on pupils' social cohesion, as a result of the obtained sig value of 0.01 which is less than the Alpha value of .05. This revealed that both the treatment and school ownership have interaction on social cohesion among pupils. This is because there is difference in the level of social cohesion that exists among private school pupils and that of their counterparts from

public schools. This was as a result of the fact the environment the pupils are exposed to and how conducive the environment determines the kind of relationship they share with each other. This goes in line with the submission of Mooij et al (2018), who submitted that a school develops a rather specific social culture and ethos of its own, which is expressed also in a specific degree of social cohesion. In a school, each manager, teacher or staff member, or pupil perceives specific qualities of this social cohesion through specific feelings, beliefs, or behaviour of him or herself in relation to the other social actors, and vice. The relative homogeneity in social culture and cohesion of a specific school, compared with that of other schools, is demonstrated in a series of nationwide survey studies.

Additionally, the findings revealed that there was significant interaction effect of treatment and family type on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State. This was revealed by the significant value of the response 0.03 which is less than the Alpha value of 0.05. This revealed that both the treatment and family type have interaction on pupils' social cohesion. This is because the social cohesion or relationship that exist among the pupils is affected by the type of family they come from. The social cohesion that pupils from nuclear family exhibit is different from their counterparts from the extended family. This is as a result of the fact the type of family the pupils come from, and as well as the kind of training given determines the kind of relationship they maintain with their peers. This corroborates the work of Flecha (2015), who opined that the typically close-knit nature of nuclear families allows for strong parent-child relationships and a solid foundation of social values. Parents in nuclear families often have the resources and time to engage in their children's social development, participating in activities that promote teamwork, empathy, and communication skills. These children may benefit from consistent parental involvement and guidance, which helps them navigate social situations effectively and build strong peer relationships. But in extended families, children often grow up surrounded by a variety of role models and support systems, which can enhance their social competence and adaptability. The presence of multiple generations and a larger family circle in extended families means that children are exposed to diverse perspectives and social dynamics from an early age.

Conclusion

From the forgoing, it was concluded that there was moderate level of social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State at the initial stage of the experiment. After the administration of the treatment, there was significant effect of moonlight tales on social cohesion among middles basic pupils in Osun State. It was revealed from the study that there was significant interaction effect of moonlight tales and school ownership on social cohesion among the pupils, and there was significant interaction effect of moonlight tales and family type on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

Recommendations

- The following recommendations are proffer so as to establish the significance of moonlight tales
1. Government should ensure the integration of moonlight tales into the formal school curriculum as part of language arts, social studies, or cultural education classes, as this will promote social cohesion among the pupils.
 2. School management should ensure the involvement of families and community members in the use of moonlight tales to bridge the gap between school and home cultural education.
 3. Government should ensure the use of moonlight tales to foster cultural knowledge and social cohesion among pupils is be maintained by both private and public schools.
 4. School management should ensure the development and implementation of policies that promote the use of moonlight tales so as to enhance cultural inclusivity and social cohesion.

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Assessment of Inclusive Education at Junior Secondary Schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC), Abuja Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the integration of inclusive education in the Junior Secondary School Curriculum in Nigeria, focusing on its impact on academic and social outcomes for students, especially those with disabilities. Inclusive education accommodates all students, fostering equity, participation, and community. Despite Nigeria's commitment to international frameworks like the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) and Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), barriers such as limited resources, inadequate teacher training, and societal attitudes challenge effective implementation, particularly in under-resourced areas. Using a descriptive survey design, this study sampled 300 teachers and 50 Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) staff, collecting data through questionnaires and interviews on perceptions of inclusive education's benefits and obstacles. Findings show strong support for inclusive education's positive impact, particularly through differentiated instruction, universal design for learning (UDL), and peer engagement in promoting academic and social development. However, practical challenges hinder implementation. The study concludes that aligning policy with practice requires significant investment in teacher training, infrastructure, and community awareness. Recommendations include increased funding, consistent professional development, and strengthened policy enforcement to build an equitable and inclusive education system for all Nigerian students.

Keywords: Inclusive Education, Curriculum, Disabilities, Junior Secondary School

Introduction

The goal of inclusive education is to accommodate all students in the general education system, irrespective of their unique requirements, backgrounds, or skill levels. It encourages an atmosphere in which students engage in educational activities with their classmates, promoting fairness, involvement, and a sense of community. This method challenges the conventional segregation models that frequently separate children with disabilities and is based on the idea that every child has a right to a high-quality education. According to research, inclusive behaviours help kids become more understanding, cooperative, and empathetic (Loreman et al., 2021). To accommodate the varied needs of their students, teachers in inclusive environments modify their teaching strategies and resources, frequently leveraging frameworks such as differentiated instruction and universal learning design, which benefit all students. All around the world, inclusive education is acknowledged as a basic human right. Integration of people with disabilities into mainstream schooling is required by the 2006 United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD). All people have equal access to education thanks to Article 24, which mandates that signatory nations including Nigeria, offer accommodations and support services to advance inclusive education (UN, 2006). The necessity for inclusive, fair, high-quality education for all is emphasized by the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), especially Goal 4 (United Nations, 2015). Countries must remove obstacles that marginalized groups encounter, such as poor infrastructure, sociocultural perceptions, and a lack of teacher preparation, to accomplish this. Research indicates that inclusive schools promote a culture of tolerance and inclusion (Ainscow, 2020) and that children with disabilities do better academically and socially than those in segregated settings (Hehir et al., 2016).

In addition to policy commitments, substantial adjustments in school administration, teacher preparation, and resource distribution are necessary for the successful implementation of inclusive education. Professional development is crucial because teachers must have the abilities and know-how to manage a diverse student body (Florian & Spratt, 2013). Sadly, a lot of teachers lack the necessary skills to use inclusive methods, especially when assisting kids with complex needs (Forlin & Chambers, 2017). Therefore, creating inclusive classrooms requires constant training and resources. Through laws that support equal educational opportunities for all children, including those with disabilities, the Nigerian government has acknowledged the significance of inclusive education (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013). But obstacles including low infrastructure,

Assessment of Inclusive Education... (Ohadiugha, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610562>

insufficient money, and little teacher preparation still stand in the way of advancement (Abang, 2022). Instead of keeping children with disabilities apart, inclusive education in Nigeria emphasizes integrating them into regular classrooms. In line with international frameworks like as the UNCRPD and SDG 4, the National Policy on Education promotes equal educational opportunities for all pupils (Obi & Okoh, 2023). Significant obstacles still exist despite these policies, especially in rural areas where schools lack the infrastructure and resources needed to accommodate students with disabilities (Omede, 2022). Parents are reluctant to enroll their children in mainstream schools out of fear of discrimination, which is frequently caused by societal stigma and misconceptions regarding disability (Ojo & Akinyemi, 2023). This highlights the discrepancy in Nigeria's educational system between policy and practice.

Although many teachers lack training in managing diverse classes, they are essential to the achievement of inclusive education (Adeniran et al., 2023). Professional development that emphasizes inclusive teaching methods and special education requirements is desperately needed. To establish a setting where all kids can succeed, cooperation between teachers, parents, and other stakeholders in education is crucial (Ogunbanjo & Abiodun, 2022). Since it creates the foundation for fair and encouraging learning settings, integrating inclusive education within the Junior Secondary School Curriculum is essential. The intellectual and social development of students is greatly influenced by this foundational educational phase, which includes junior secondary schools. All students have an equal chance to succeed when inclusive practices are implemented, and when they study with their peers, they develop empathy and a sense of belonging (Loreman et al., 2021). According to research, all kids do better academically when they get inclusive instruction at the basic school level (Hehir et al., 2016). Integrating inclusion into the curriculum enables schools to dismantle the discriminatory and exclusionary barriers faced by marginalized children.

In Nigeria, inclusive education has a great deal of promise to enhance social and academic outcomes for all students, especially those with disabilities. Issues like societal stigma, inadequate infrastructure, and inadequate teacher preparation hamper its effective implementation. Misconceptions in society deter parents from enrolling children with disabilities in normal schools, teachers lack the necessary training to manage a variety of requirements, and many schools lack basic supplies. Nigeria still has a big disconnect between policy and practice, even with its dedication to global frameworks like the UNCRPD and Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4). Potential advantages like promoting empathy, a sense of belonging, and enhanced academic achievement are largely unrealized because of these obstacles, which restrict the incorporation of inclusive education within junior secondary school. The implementation of inclusive education in junior secondary school at AMAC is examined in this study, with particular attention paid to the difficulties teachers encounter, stakeholder perspectives, and the effects of inclusive practices on students' growth. For all kids to study in a welcoming and inclusive atmosphere, these gaps must be closed.

Objectives of the Study

1. To investigate how inclusive education enhances equity, participation, and belonging among students in Nigerian schools.
2. To evaluate the role of teachers in fostering inclusive classrooms through modified teaching strategies, including differentiated instruction and universal learning design (UDL).
3. To examine the barriers to implementing inclusive education, such as infrastructure, societal attitudes, teacher preparedness, and resource availability.
4. To analyze the correlation between inclusive educational practices and students' academic and social performance, especially students with disabilities.

Research Questions

1. In Nigeria, how does inclusive education impact the social and academic achievement of children with disabilities in comparison to those in segregated classrooms?
2. To what extent does Nigerian teacher preparation affect the efficacy of inclusive teaching methods in regular classrooms?
3. How do parents and educators in Nigeria feel about including students with disabilities in regular classrooms?

Hypotheses

Assessment of Inclusive Education... (Ohadiugha, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610562>

1. There is no significant difference in the academic performance of students with disabilities in Nigerian schools that implement inclusive education policies compared to those in segregated educational settings.
2. There is no significant relationship between teachers' challenges (e.g., inadequate resources and lack of training) and the effective implementation of inclusive education practices in Nigerian schools
3. There is no significant impact of inclusive education practices on the social development of students with and without disabilities in Nigerian schools.

Methodology

The research design used in this study was a descriptive survey. 1,252 public secondary school teachers from the Abuja Municipal Area Council in Nigeria's Federal Capital Territory and 58 employees of the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) made up the population. The Taro Yamane sampling formula, which reads $n = N / (1 + N(e)^2)$, was used to randomly choose 300 public secondary school instructors and 50 NERDC employees. The "Inclusive Education and its Integration Assessment Questionnaire (IEIIAQ)," which used a modified 4-point Likert scale with Strongly Agree (4 points) to Strongly Disagree (1 point), was used to gather data. Cronbach's Alpha was used to examine the instrument's reliability and establish its face and content validity; the reliability coefficient came out to be 0.91. The study issues were addressed using mean and standard deviation, and the null hypotheses were tested using a z-test.

Presentation of Results

The results of the study are presented below.

Research Question 1:

How does inclusive education affect the academic and social performance of students with disabilities compared to those in segregated educational settings in Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis of the academic and social performance of students with disabilities

S/n	Items	NERDC Staff = 50			Teachers = 300		
		\bar{X}	SD	Remark	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
Filed work 2023							
6.	Students with disabilities in inclusive classrooms perform academically compared to those in segregated settings	3.44	1.05	Agree	3.52	1.00	Agree
7.	Students with disabilities in inclusive classrooms interact socially with their peers compared to those in segregated settings	3.92	0.72	Agree	3.81	0.85	Agree
8.	Inclusive education provides students with disabilities with equal access to learning opportunities compared to segregated settings	3.71	1.00	Agree	3.68	0.86	Agree
9.	The teaching methods in inclusive classrooms affect the academic success of students with disabilities-compared to segregated settings	3.88	0.88	Agree	3.79	0.75	Agree
10.	Peer support plays in the social integration of students with disabilities in inclusive settings compared to segregated environments	3.53	1.02	Agree	3.50	0.97	Agree
11.	Peers without disabilities in inclusive settings positively impact the engagement of students with disabilities.	3.27	0.82	Agree	3.18	0.77	Agree
12.	The resources and support available in inclusive settings affect the academic progress of students						

Assessment of Inclusive Education... (Ohadiugha, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610562>

with disabilities compared to segregated environments.

3.63 1.04 Agree 3.58 1.01 Agree

Weighted Grand Mean

3.63 0.93 3.58 0.89

Based on input from NERDC personnel and teachers, the findings in Table I examine the main obstacles to introducing inclusive education in Nigerian schools, especially at the basic education level. As seen by the total weighted grand mean of 3.63 and 3.58, respectively, both groups agreed on the difficulties. Teacher preparation, school infrastructure, policies, community involvement, and societal attitudes are some of the challenges that have been identified. With the highest agreement scores (3.92 and 3.81), teacher preparation and professional development were seen as significant obstacles, highlighting the necessity of improved training to accommodate different learners. In a similar vein, insufficient school resources and infrastructure were viewed as major challenges since schools might not have the tools and resources necessary to serve all pupils, particularly those with special needs. It was also noted that the current framework for educational policy was inadequate for successfully addressing inclusive education. Although there are policies in place, the results show that they need to be modified to close implementation gaps. Another barrier that was somewhat acknowledged was parental and community involvement, indicating that greater cooperation between families and schools could enhance inclusivity. The outcome also shows that cultural views and societal attitudes toward impairments were identified as significant obstacles. The findings highlight the need for advocacy and awareness initiatives to alter perceptions and promote a more inclusive educational system by demonstrating how unfavorable attitudes may impede inclusion.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the academic performance of students with disabilities in Nigerian schools that implement inclusive education policies compared to those in segregated educational settings.

Table 2: Z-test Comparing the Mean Ratings of NERDC Staff and Teachers on the Academic Performance of Students with Disabilities in Nigerian Schools Implementing Inclusive Education Policies Versus Segregated Educational Settings.

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	Z-Cal.	Z-Crit.	Remark
NERDC Staff	50	3.63	0.93				Not Significant
Teachers	300	3.58	0.89	330	0.11	1.96	Ho ₁ Accepted

Filed work 2023

The mean evaluations of NERDC officials and instructors regarding the academic achievement of children with disabilities in Nigerian schools that follow inclusive education policies vs those in segregated settings are contrasted in Table 2's Z-test results. The mean score for NERDC employees was 3.63 with a standard deviation of 0.93, but the mean score for teachers was somewhat lower at 3.58 with a standard deviation of 0.89. At a 0.05 significance level, the computed Z-value (0.11) is substantially less than the crucial Z-value (1.96), suggesting that there is no statistically significant difference in the perceptions of the two groups. The null hypothesis (HO₁) is accepted since the computed Z-value is less than the crucial value. This implies that teachers and NERDC officials have similar opinions about how well students with disabilities perform academically in inclusive schools as opposed to segregated ones. As a result, their opinions about how inclusive education influences kids' academic performance in contrast to segregated settings do not differ significantly.

Research Question 2:

To what extent does teacher training in Nigeria impact the effectiveness of inclusive education practices in mainstream classrooms?

Assessment of Inclusive Education... (Ohadiugha, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610562>

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis on the extent to which teacher training in Nigeria impacts the effectiveness of inclusive education practices in mainstream classrooms.

S/n	Items	NERDC Staff = 50			Teachers = 300		
		\bar{X}	SD	Remark	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
Filed work 2023							
1.	Teacher training in Nigeria effectively prepares teachers to teach students with diverse learning needs in inclusive classrooms.	3.86	1.04	Agree	3.79	0.89	Agree
2.	My school provides adequate resources and support to implement inclusive education practices effectively after teacher training.	3.70	0.82	Agree	3.73	0.90	Agree
3.	I believe that ongoing professional development is essential to maintaining and improving the effectiveness of inclusive education in Nigerian classrooms.	3.91	0.95	Agree	3.85	0.56	Agree
4.	The content of the teacher training I received adequately covered strategies for managing inclusive classrooms.	3.75	1.00	Agree	3.60	0.86	Agree
5.	Inclusive education training has positively influenced my approach to teaching students with disabilities in mainstream classrooms.	3.80	0.98	Agree	3.68	0.74	Agree
6.	Teacher training programs in Nigeria should be revised to better align with the current needs of inclusive education in mainstream classrooms.	3.78	1.10	Agree	3.72	0.83	Agree
13.	The collaboration between teacher training programs and schools is effective in enhancing the implementation of inclusive education practices.	3.96	0.60	Agree	3.89	0.55	Agree
Weighted Grand Mean (\bar{X} \bar{X})		3.82 0.93		3.75 0.76			

The findings of the Z-test in Table 2 contrast how NERDC employees and educators view the academic achievement of kids with disabilities in inclusive and segregated environments. The man score for NERDC staff was 3.63, while the mean score for instructors was somewhat lower at 3.58. The difference in perceptions was not statistically significant, with a Z-value of 0.11, which was far lower than the crucial value of 1.96. As a result, the null hypothesis (Ho1) was approved, suggesting that both groups agree that inclusive education improves student achievement. Table 3 demonstrates agreement between NERDC officials and teachers concerning Research Question Two, which deals with the impact of teacher training on the efficacy of inclusive education. There is general agreement that teacher training is valuable, as evidenced by the mean rating of 3.86 given by NERDC officials and 3.79 given by teachers. A favorable opinion of teacher training's contribution to inclusive education is shown by the overall weighted grand mean of 3.82 for NERDC employees and 3.75 for educators. The significance of continuous professional development and the necessity of updating teacher preparation curricula to better meet contemporary inclusive education standards were also emphasized by both groups.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between the challenges faced by teachers (e.g., inadequate resources and lack of training) and the effective implementation of inclusive education practices in Nigerian schools.

Table 4: Z-test of Difference between the Mean Ratings of NERDC Staff and Teachers on the Extent to which the challenges teachers face (e.g., inadequate resources and lack of training) affect the implementation of inclusive education practices in Nigerian schools.

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	Z-Cal.	Z-Crit.	Remark
NERDC Staff	50	3.82	0.93				Not Significant
Teachers	300	3.75	0.76	330	0.50	1.96	Ho ₂ Accepted

Filed work 2023

Assessment of Inclusive Education... (Ohadiugha, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610562>

According to Table 4, the computed Z-value is 0.50, and the mean score provided by NERDC personnel was 3.82 with a standard deviation of 0.93. At a significance level of 0.05, this Z-value is significantly less than the essential Z-value of 1.96. The null hypothesis (Ho2) is thus accepted, indicating that the perceived difficulties have no appreciable impact on the adoption of inclusive teaching methods. According to this finding, teachers and NERDC officials may have similar opinions about how difficulties affect inclusive education's efficacy, suggesting that these difficulties may not have as much of an impact as previously thought. A possible discrepancy between teachers' perceived difficulties and their real influence on the adoption of inclusive education in Nigerian schools is further highlighted by the acceptance of the null hypothesis. Although problems like a lack of training and resources are acknowledged, the research indicates that they might not be a major obstacle to good teaching methods. This may suggest that other underlying elements—like teacher resilience, regulatory frameworks, or administrative support—may be more important for the effective execution of inclusive education. Therefore, in order to create more effective strategies for its implementation in Nigeria, policymakers and educational stakeholders may need to take into account both the difficulties raised by teachers and the larger context in which inclusive education functions.

Research Question 3

What are Nigerian teachers, parents, and educational stakeholders' perceptions and attitudes toward the inclusion of children with disabilities in mainstream schools?

Table 5: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis on the extent to which Nigerian teachers, parents and educational stakeholders' perceptions and attitudes towards the inclusion of children with disabilities in mainstream schools

S/n	Items	NERDC Staff = 50			Teachers = 300			
		\bar{X}	SD	Remark	\bar{X}	SD	Remark	
1.	Inclusive education benefits all students, including those with disabilities.	3.82	1.02	Agree	3.90	0.87	Agree	
2.	Mainstream schools are equipped to effectively support children with disabilities.	3.91	0.99	Agree	3.84	0.73	Agree	
3.	Parents of children with disabilities are actively involved in their child's education in mainstream schools.	3.88	0.86	Agree	3.85	0.80	Agree	
4.	Inclusion in mainstream school's fosters positive social interactions between children with disabilities and their peers.		3.70	1.03	Agree	3.66	0.98	Agree
5.	Children with disabilities can achieve academic success in inclusive classroom settings.	3.26	1.12	Agree	3.17	0.86	Agree	
6.	Cultural beliefs and attitudes towards disability influence the inclusion of children with disabilities in schools.	3.74	0.93	Agree	3.75	0.96	Agree	
7.	Existing policies regarding inclusive education in Nigeria needs to be improved							
8.	To better support children with disabilities.	3.64	1.00	Agree	3.65	0.91	Agree	
Weighted Grand Mean (\bar{X} \bar{X})		3.71	0.99		3.69	0.87		

There is a generally positive consensus among Nigerian parents and teachers regarding the inclusion of children with disabilities in normal schools. With mean scores ranging from 3.17 to 3.91, NERDC staff and instructors concur on the advantages of inclusive education. For instance, both groups gave the statement "inclusive education benefits all students, including those with disabilities" high ratings—NERDC personnel gave it a score of 3.82, while teachers gave it a score of 3.90—demonstrating a strong belief in the importance of inclusion in improving educational outcomes. Both groups gave positive scores for parental participation (3.88 for NERDC staff and 3.85 for teachers), indicating a common awareness of the significance of teacher-family collaboration. Both groups felt that inclusive education promotes positive peer connections, demonstrating their recognition of the social benefits of inclusion. Concerns were raised, though, especially regarding the academic performance of kids with impairments in inclusive environments, where their mean scores were lower at 3.26 and 3.17. Furthermore, both

Assessment of Inclusive Education... (Ohadiugha, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610562>

groups concurred that Nigeria's current inclusive education laws require enhancement, underscoring the necessity of legislative change. The aggregate weighted grand averages of 3.69 for teachers and 3.71 for NERDC officials show that there is broad consensus regarding the importance of inclusive education, but they also highlight the difficulties in putting it into practice.

Table 6: Z-test of Difference between the Mean Ratings of NERDC Staff and Teachers on the extent to which Nigerian teachers, parents, and educational stakeholders' perceptions and attitudes towards the inclusion of children with disabilities in mainstream schools

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	Z-Cal.	Z-Crit.	Remark
NERDC Staff	50	3.71	0.99				Not Significant
Teachers	300	3.69	0.87	330	0.13	1.96	Ho ₃ Accepted

Alpha Level = 0.05

The disparity between the mean evaluations of NERDC employees and educators with respect to their attitudes and views on the inclusion of students with disabilities in regular classrooms is displayed in Table 6. The computed Z-value is 0.13, and the mean score for NERDC employees is 3.71 with a standard deviation of 0.99. At a significance level of 0.05, this number is significantly below the necessary Z-value of 1.96. The null hypothesis (Ho₃) is accepted since the computed Z-value falls below the crucial threshold. This result suggests that instructors and NERDC staff have a consensus about the inclusion of children with impairments, as there is no statistically significant difference between their opinions. The null hypothesis's acceptance suggests that teachers and NERDC staff have comparable opinions about the value and effects of inclusive education. Their shared position on the inclusion of children with impairments in mainstream settings is shown in their agreement on this matter. This conclusion is significant because it implies that educators and policymakers in Nigeria's educational system have similar viewpoints, which may make it easier to work together to adopt inclusive policies. All things considered, the findings highlight a shared understanding of the importance of inclusive education, which should bolster support for laws and procedures that improve educational opportunities for Nigerian children with disabilities.

Discussion of Findings

In Nigeria, inclusive education has enormous potential to enhance social and academic outcomes for all students, particularly those with disabilities. According to the study conducted in junior secondary schools under the Abuja Municipal Area Council, inclusive methods like differentiated instruction and universal learning design (UDL) promote equity, engagement, and a feeling of community. Teachers and NERDC personnel stressed the value of collaborative learning and peer assistance in fostering constructive relationships between students with and without disabilities. Significant obstacles still exist, nevertheless, such as lack of infrastructure, inadequate training for teachers, and social stigma. Schools frequently lack resources like assistive technology and accessible facilities, and teachers are not adequately trained to handle a variety of learning requirements. To bridge these disparities, teacher preparation programs must be in line with inclusive education standards and involve ongoing professional development.

Progress is also hampered by societal attitudes and cultural beliefs since stigma and misunderstandings deter parents from sending their disabled children to regular schools. Establishing supportive environments for these adolescents requires cooperation from parents, teachers, and other stakeholders. To close the gap between policy and practice, the study emphasizes the necessity of better resource allocation and more stringent policy enforcement. In rural and neglected communities, more money is especially needed for technology, teacher preparation, and infrastructure.

Conclusion

Nigeria has made strides toward inclusive education through international agreements and regulations, but there are still obstacles to overcome. Making inclusive education a reality requires addressing infrastructure deficiencies, enhancing teacher preparation, and overcoming social stigmas. For all students, regardless of background or ability, to have access to high-quality education, cooperation between the government, civil society, and educational institutions is required. Globally, frameworks such as the Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) and the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) support inclusive education as a human right. All kids must receive an education that promotes equity, empathy, teamwork, and respect for diversity. Differentiated instruction and universal design for learning (UDL) are two

Assessment of Inclusive Education... (Ohadiugha, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610562>

strategies that teachers use to modify their teaching strategies to accommodate a diverse student body. Nigeria is committed to these ideals, although in practice, they are not always followed, especially in rural areas where there are few resources and skills. For inclusive education to be implemented successfully, educators, parents, administrators, legislators, and advocacy organizations must work together. By working together, we can make sure that schools have the infrastructure and resources they need to serve every student. In the end, inclusive education fosters social cohesion, raises academic achievement, and creates the groundwork for just societies in which all people, regardless of aptitude, can prosper.

Recommendations

1. It is important to offer frequent, thorough training on differentiated instruction, special education requirements, and inclusive pedagogies. Programs for ongoing professional development can give educators the tools they need to successfully lead inclusive classrooms.
2. Ramps, classroom modifications, and assistive technology for students with disabilities are examples of accessible infrastructure that should be installed in schools. To bridge resource allocation gaps, the government should fund the development of inclusive learning environments, particularly in underprivileged and rural areas.
3. It is essential to set aside enough money to promote inclusive education efforts. To guarantee that schools have enough funding to supply specialized teaching materials and assistive technology, the Nigerian government should work with the business sector and non-governmental organizations.
4. Nigeria has policies that support inclusive education, but they are not always implemented consistently. To guarantee that schools adhere to inclusive education requirements, like those outlined in the National Policy on Education, the government should bolster policy enforcement and set up monitoring mechanisms.
5. Public awareness efforts are necessary to combat the stigma associated with disability in society and the false beliefs about students with special needs. More acceptance and support for inclusive education can result from these programs' ability to cultivate a more inclusive mentality among communities, educators, and parents.
6. To establish a supportive environment for students with disabilities, parents, educators, school administrators, and government representatives must collaborate. To guarantee that each student thrives in an inclusive environment and to customize learning experiences to meet their needs, active parent-teacher engagement is required.
7. Students with disabilities can participate more actively in class when technology, such as assistive devices and adaptive learning tools, are used. Partnerships between public and private entities should be investigated to supply these resources to both public and private schools.

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Effects of Class-Size on Retention in Chemistry Concepts among Secondary School Students in Zaria Local Government Area, Kaduna State.

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Abstract

The study investigated the effects of class-size on retention in chemistry concepts among Senior Secondary School Chemistry Students in Zaria Local Government Area, Kaduna State. Four research questions and corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. The research design adopted for the study was quasi-experimental. The target population was all senior secondary school class two (SSSII) chemistry students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Kaduna state. The sample size for this study were one hundred and fifty (150) secondary school II chemistry students randomly selected from three secondary schools in Zaria. The instrument used for data collection was Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT). A reliability coefficient of 0.74 was obtained for the instrument using Pearson's Product-Moment correlation coefficient which implies that the instrument was reliable for the study. The data obtained through CAT were subjected to One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to test the hypotheses at $P \leq 0.05$ significant level. The results obtained revealed significant differences in the Post-Post test scores (F value is 32.08 at $\alpha = 0.05$ with df of 148). The results of the study showed, among others, that from individual class-size groupings, there was no significant difference in retention of subjects exposed to chemistry concepts and the retention of chemistry concepts favored all the subjects equally irrespective of the nature of the class-size. The researcher recommends that there should be continuous support for new researches in class-size and that information obtained could substantially improve the academic achievement and retention level of chemistry students.

Keywords: Class-size, Retention, Chemistry concepts, Chemistry students, Secondary school.

Introduction

It is imperative to define and give the historical origin of science and chemistry before discussing in detail, the effect class-size has on the academic achievement and retention of students in Chemistry. The origin and beginning of science could be as old as the beginning of human race, arising from the need of man to solve various problems that threatened his survival.

Science is a progressive activity that constitutes the world and permeates almost every aspect of modern life. Science seeks to explain how the universe operates and encompasses the natural, social and applied sciences. Science is basically concerned with the study of natural phenomena that can empirically be tested. Igboanugo and Egolum (2017) view science as the systematic investigation of nature with a view to understanding and harnessing them for human benefits. The aims of teaching science is to enable students understand, retain and use the knowledge obtained to solve problems through laboratory work, field work and class work. Most teachers unfortunately do not have the capacity to actualize these ideas since they are faced with prevailing students' excesses which often results in the disruption of class work, cheating and physical aggression. Chemistry is one of the three major basic sciences along with biology and physics. According to Achimugu (2017), chemistry as part of science and as a school subject, is made of concepts which require complex mental process that involves visualizing, manipulating, analyzing, abstracting and associating with idea. It is necessary to understand the material world in order to exploit its properties for the benefit of humanity. The study of chemistry is very important to mankind and also in the following areas of human life: Agriculture, Textiles, Pharmaceutical Industries, Polymer industries Medicine. The teaching of Chemistry involves developing basic chemistry skills which include observation, manipulation, classification, inference, hypothesizing, interpreting data, formulating model. In addition, the skills and knowledge gained through chemistry should be applied in solving everyday problems in the environment.

The general poor academic achievement of students in chemistry was what motivated the present scholar to undertake a research on the effect of class-size on the academic achievement and retention of learned concepts in chemistry among secondary school students with the aim of finding solutions which will go a long way in improving the retention level of students who write chemistry in the senior school certificate examination (SSCE).

Effects of Class-Size... (Anaso, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610568>

A class is identified as a course/section combination with one or more teachers scheduled in a particular room, in a particular school, in a specific term, during a specific period and day of the week. According to FSIR (2003-04), class-size is determined by bringing the total number of students in the classroom and dividing by the number of teachers assigned to the students. On the issue of how average class-size differs from a student teacher ratio, FSIR (2003-04) has indicated that student teacher ratio is derived by merely dividing the number of school students in membership by the number of staff who are classified as teachers in the school. They argued that student/teacher ratio does not account for the number of classes taught during the day or how many students are assigned to each of the classes. On the other hand average class-size is based on counts of students assigned to specific classes. Wikipedia (2015) refers class-size to be the number of students a teacher faces during a given period of instruction.

Eboatu and Ehirim (2018) define class-size as the number of students a teacher attends to during a given period of instruction. Class size is thus different from the student-teacher ratio, which is expressed as the relationship between the student population and the number of teachers available in the school. Resnick (2018) stressed that class size must be reduced substantially to achieve the benefits. A large class-size is the ratio of one teacher to fifty students (1:50) and above. Liz and Lisa (2022) noted that the numerical strength of the class does not permit the teacher to cope effectively with the demands of the individual student. They further noted that the individual student is buried in the group as a result of the largeness of the class. More so, uniform instructional technique is used in reaching out to all the students with different abilities at the same time. Filges, Sonne-Schmidt and Bjørn (2018) concluded that reducing class size from 40 or more to 20 pupils led to almost no increase in achievement. Not until class size is being dropped to 15 pupils or lower will there be larger effects on achievement. Teachmint, (2024) indicated that class-size refers to the total number of students in each classroom. Depending upon class-size, teachers divide the students by making an active learning classroom where they engage the students in deep learning.

In this study, class-size is defined as the total number of students in a class at a given time. Specifically, small class-size is defined as one teacher to handle twenty five (25) students (1:25); average class-size is seen as a teacher having fifty (50) students (1:50), while a large class-size is defined as one teacher to handle seventy five (75) students (1:75). This is formulated by the researcher for the purpose of this study.

A study conducted in the field of teaching and learning using various class-sizes that does not take cognizance of retention of materials/knowledge taught is not complete. Retention therefore forms an integral part of this study to establish the differences in academic achievement of students in various class-sizes and level of retention of chemistry concepts. Apparently, few research works have been conducted in this area of retention; some of such studies were Azigwe, Kyriakides, Panayiot and Creemers (2016), they reviewed a study on the link between student engagement and class size, and they revealed that students' engagement behavior and retention are affected seriously by the class size. They indicated that when students were placed in smaller classes they became more engaged academically and socially. Also, with strong social academic engagement, academic attachment and retention improved. The ability to solve any problem or even to recognize that a problem exists depends on memory. Practice or review tends to build and maintain memory for a task or any learned material. Britannica Encyclopedia (2003) stated that in measuring retention, the rate tends to vary with the methods used and they are basically those of recall, recognition and relearning.

The retention level of the subjects in the various class-sizes taught chemistry concepts were investigated in this study. The aim is to determine which group of students showed higher retention levels of the materials learnt. This study would therefore, serve as a reference point for further studies.

The study of Chemistry at the Secondary School level is not only to give students the opportunity to manipulate apparatus and enquire meaningful learning but also to develop basic chemistry skills which include observation, classification, inference, hypothesizing, interpreting and formulating data among others. The Secondary School students are also to develop self-confidence and reliance through problem solving activities. Liz and Lisa (2022) have shown that large classes have the tendency of limiting the achievement of mediocre students in Mathematics since high ability students will always dominate in such classes.

The problem of this study is therefore, to substantiate the effect of class-size on retention by students as it affects their academic achievement in Chemistry when exposed to guided discovery method of teaching.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Determine any difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts between students in large, medium and small class-sizes when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery approach.
2. Determine any difference in the level of retention of students in large class-size when taught chemistry concepts.
3. Examine any difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts between students in medium class-size when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery approach.
4. Find any difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts in small class-size

Research Questions

1. Is there any difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts between students in large, medium and small class-sizes when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery approach?
2. Is there any difference in the level of retention of students in large class-size when taught chemistry concepts?
3. Is there any difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts between students in medium class-size when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery approach?
4. Is there any difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts in small class-size when taught chemistry concepts?

Hypotheses

To answer the stated research questions, the following null hypotheses were formulated.

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts between students in large, medium and small class-sizes when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery approach among secondary schools in Zaria, Kaduna State.
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant difference in the level of retention of students in large class-size when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery approach among secondary schools in Zaria, Kaduna State.
3. **H₀₃**: There is no significant difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts between students in medium class-size when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery approach among secondary school students in Zaria, Kaduna State.
4. **H₀₄**: There is no significant difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts in small class-size when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery approach among secondary school students in Zaria, Kaduna State.

Methodology

The study is quasi-experimental research design investigating the effect of different class-sizes on the level of retention of chemistry students in secondary schools in Zaria Nigeria. The research was a comparative study of three groups of varying class-sizes. The target population was Senior Secondary School II chemistry students in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria, had thirteen Secondary Schools with a total number of 2,307 chemistry students. The samples for this study were one hundred and fifty (150) SS11 chemistry students drawn randomly from three secondary schools in Zaria Metropolis, in Kaduna State. The three secondary schools were randomly selected with respect to the fact that the schools had covered substantial content/topics in the SSSCE chemistry syllabus. In each of the three schools, one formed the small class-size, the second one formed the average class-size and the third school formed the large class-size. This division into various class-sizes of 25, 50 and 75 was done by stratified random sampling to ensure that every student had equal chance of participating actively in the study. All the students in the three different schools were taught chemistry concept using the guided discovery approach,

The instrument used was Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) developed by the researcher and consist of thirty multiple choice chemistry test items. They were validated by a panel of experts that include two chemistry senior lecturers at a university, one science educator and two secondary school chemistry teachers. The multiple choice items referred to as the Chemistry Achievement Test were used at three different occasions:-First, as pre-test:- to determine the strength and equality of the samples at the start of the study. Secondly, as post-test in order to determine or assess the performance of the students after the treatment and later administered as post-posttest to determine their level of retention of learnt chemistry concepts. A pilot testing with a sample of 50 students was conducted using the Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) items on SSS II chemistry students of Government Secondary School other than the schools under study in Zaria. The reasons and benefits of pilot testing were to identify problems or difficulties that might arise before the final administration of the instruments to the

Effects of Class-Size... (Anaso, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610568>

study samples. The scores from three tests were correlated using Pearson’s Product-Moment correlation coefficient and reliability coefficient of 0.74 was obtained.

The data obtained through CAT were subjected to One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to test the hypothesis at $P \leq 0.05$ significant level.

Presentation of Results

The pre-test scores were used to establish the equivalence of the three comparable groups (School A, B, and C) before the treatment. The pretest scores were subjected to a one-way analysis of variance and tested at a significant level of 0.05 as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: One-way Analysis of Variance of the Pre-test Mean Scores of Subjects in the Three Classes

Source of variance	Sum of squares	Df	Mean squares	Fcal	Fcrit	P	Remark
Between groups	14.43	2	7.21	1.71	3.05	0.18	NS
Within groups	617.95	147	4.20				
Total	632.37	149					

* Not significant at $P \leq 0.05$

The obtained F-value (calculated) is 1.71. This value is less than the F- value critical which is 3.05 at $\alpha = 0.05$ with $df = 149$. The result shows that there was no statistically significant difference between the achievements of subjects in all the classes/groups. The P-value of 0.183 is also not significant thus implying group equivalence with respect to their knowledge of chemistry concepts before the exposure to treatment since the level of significance is 0.05.

Testing H_{01}

There is no significant difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts between students in large, medium and small class-sizes when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery approach.

One way analysis of variance using SPSS 11.50 package was applied with a view to testing the hypothesis. The result is as presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Analysis of variance of Post-Post test scores comparing retention level of all the three groups

Source of variance	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	F	P	Remarks
Between groups	422.60	2	211.30	32.08	0.000	S
Within groups	574.80	148	6.587			
Total	1397.40	150				

* Significant at $P \leq 0.05$

The results in Table 2 show that the obtained F value is 32.08 at $\alpha = 0.05$ with df of 148. This implies that there is a significant difference in level of retention in the Post-Post test scores of all the three groups. All the subjects retained the chemistry concepts learnt. The null hypothesis is thus rejected since significant differences in level of retention exist.

H_{02} : There is no significant difference in the level of retention of students in large class-size when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery strategy.

To test the level of retention of subjects in a large class size, data from the Post-Post test scores were collected from the subjects in large class size. One way analysis of variance was used. The result is shown in Table 3

Table 3: Comparison of the Post –Posttest mean scores of high, average and low ability groups in large class-size

Source of variance	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	Fcal	P-value	Fcrit	Remark
Between groups	25.38	2	12.69	1.75	0.18	3.12	NS
Within groups	520.16	72	7.22				
Total	545.55	74					

Effects of Class-Size... (Anaso, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610568>

* Not significant at $P \leq 0.05$

The results (from Table 3) show that F value calculated 1.75 is less than the F critical 3.12 with $df = 74$ and P- value of 0.18 was obtained. The results indicate that there is no significant difference in the level of retention in large class-size. This implies that the subjects retained the learnt chemistry concepts equally.

To Test H_{03}

There is no significant difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts between students in medium class-size when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery approach. Mean scores of Post-Posttest of the high, average and low ability groups of students in the Medium class-size and these scores were computed using one way analysis of variance. The result of the analysis is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: One-way analysis of variance of the Post-Posttest mean scores of the high, average and low ability groups in medium class-size

Source of variance	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	Fcal	P-value	Fcrit	Remark
Between groups	6.37	12.69	3.185	0.92	0.40	3.19	NS
Within groups	162.75	47	3.46				
Total	169.12	49					

* Not significant at $P \leq 0.05$

The obtained calculated F-value of 0.92 is less than critical F-value of 3.19 at $\alpha 0.05$ with $df = 49$. Results from Table 3 indicate that there is no significant difference in the level of retention of chemistry concepts learnt in a class-size of 50. This means subjects in that class retained materials learnt equally.

To Test H_{04}

To test for significant difference in the level of retention of students in a small class-size, which states thus “there is no significant difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts in small class-size”, one-way analysis of variance was used. Scores were obtained from Post-Posttest and the result is presented in Table5.

Table 5: One-way Analysis of the Post-Post test scores of the high, average and low ability groups in a small class-size

Source of variance	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	Fcal	P-value-	F crit	Remark
Between groups	44.30	2	22.15	2.25	0.12	3.44	NS
Within groups	215	22	9.80				
Total	260	24					

* Not significant at $P \leq 0.05$

Table 5.shows that the calculated F-value of 2.25 and critical F value of 3.44 with $df = 24$ was obtained. The P value of 0.12 at $\alpha = 0.05$ was not significant. The result implies that there is no significant difference in the level of retention of subjects (high, average and low ability levels of students) in the small class-size. In other words subjects within the group retained materials learnt equally.

Summary of Findings

1. There is significant difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts between students in small, medium and large class-sizes.
2. There is no significant difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts in large class-size.
3. There is no significant difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concept in medium class-size
4. There is no significant difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concept in small class-size

Discussion of Findings

The objective of this study was to investigate the effects of class-size and the level of retention among Senior Secondary School chemistry Students. The results from testing the null hypothesis 1 revealed significant differences in the Post-Post test scores. All the subjects retained the taught concepts for a significantly longer period as shown in Table 2. However, results emanating from individual class-size grouping revealed that there was no significant difference in retention of subjects exposed to chemistry concepts (See Tables 3-5).

Retention of Chemistry concepts thus favoured all the subjects equally irrespective of the nature of the class-size. That is, each subject (student) in large, medium and small class-sizes retained the learnt concepts. But when the groups were compared with each other, small class-size was found to retain the learnt concepts the most among the three class-size groupings. Thus the research question “Is there significant difference in the level of retention among students in small, medium and large class-sizes is therefore answered in favour of the small class-size grouping. The level of retention recorded by small, medium (average) and large class-size grouping could be due to the instructional strategy that was used in teaching. This strategy enabled subjects in all the class-size groupings to be actively involved in the learning process where they were given the opportunity or expected to observe, hypothesize, classify, measure, analysis, experiment, manipulate as well as interpret data obtained. In the process of carrying out these processes, it appears that meaningful learning and subsequently greater retention resulted. Thus the use of instructional strategy that improves retention in relation to class-size is advocated for. Many researchers such as Azigwe, Kyriakides, Panayiot and Creemers (2016) who reviewed a study on the link between student engagement and class size, revealed that students’ engagement behavior and retention were affected seriously by the class size. The study indicated that when students were placed in smaller classes they become more engaged academically and socially. With strong social academic engagement, academic attachment and retention of concepts was improved.

Conclusion

The findings of this study therefore, suggest that chemistry teachers should emphasize those instructional strategies that are characterized by active and participatory learning such as guided discovery approach which leads to meaningful learning and understanding of concepts which is easily retained in the teaching of chemistry.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made on the basis of the findings and conclusions emanating from this study.

1. There should be continuous support for new researches in class-size.
2. Information obtained from researches could substantially improve academic achievement and retention level of students.
3. More studies should continuously be conducted to assess the effectiveness of class-size

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Impact of Concept-Mapping Instructional Strategy on Attitude and Performance in Algebra among Senior Secondary School Students in Zaria, Kaduna State

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Abstract

This research investigated the impact of Concept-Mapping Instructional Strategy on Attitude and Performance in Algebra among Senior Secondary School Students in Zaria, Kaduna Nigeria. A pretest posttest, quasi experimental design was used to carry out the study. A sample of 110 students, out of 2,345 mathematics students from two schools out of public senior secondary schools in the zone, was randomly selected. In this study, two research objectives were raised, two research questions were asked and two hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Two research instruments were used in the study, namely: Algebraic Performance Test (APT) and Algebraic Attitudinal Questionnaire (AAQ). The two instruments were validated by experts. The reliability coefficients of APT and AAQ were calculated to be 0.81 and 0.79 respectively. Mean, Mean Rank, Standard Deviations were used to describe the data; while independent sample t-test, and Mann Whitney U- test were used in testing the hypothesis, the findings revealed that there is significant change in attitude mean rank of students taught Algebra using concept mapping with their counterpart using lecture Method. More so, a significant difference in academic performance scores of SSII mathematics students taught Algebra using concept mapping with those using lecture method in favor of the experimental group. The study concludes that the academic performance in algebra concepts can be enhanced significantly by the use of concept-mapping. Based on these findings, it was recommended among others that Secondary School Mathematics teachers should frequently employ the use of concept mapping in teaching Algebra and other topics in mathematics.

Keywords: Concept-Mapping, Attitude, Instructional Strategy and Academic Performance

Introduction

Mathematics is regarded as a very important subject in the school curriculum, it is therefore imperative that special attention be paid to teaching of Mathematics topics such as algebra, indices, logarithms, calculus to mention a few. This study focused on the challenges that students face when learning algebra. More lessons are allocated for Mathematics as compared to other subjects, yet it has remained one of the worst performed subjects in the school syllabus. The Federal Government of Nigeria seems to have realized the importance of Mathematics as an important key for development by stating it's in National Policy on Education that the goals of Mathematics shall be "cultivate inquiring, knowing and rational mind for the conduct of a good life and democracy "among other goals Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014). This is in realization of the strength of inquiry in enhancing conceptual understanding in Mathematics. It is frequently used as a pump to many career opportunities and further education. Miheso (2014) noted that Mathematics competence opens doors to a productive future; a lack of mathematical competence keeps those doors closed. As a result, great pressure has been put on teachers of Mathematics to produce best results and again on the students' part to succeed in Mathematics more than in any other subjects. However, despite the urgent need for a good output in the Mathematical performance of students, the reverse is the case as students' academic performance continues to deteriorate year after year.

The expository sees the students as empty headed and they play an intellectually passive role. Although students become more active with the use of guided discovery methods, they are not really active in the sense of actively constructing knowledge (Aiyede, 2009). The continuous search for more effective strategies for teaching Mathematics concepts has led to

Impact of Concept-Mapping... (Ado & Haruna, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610570>

focusing attention on how the learner learns and the learner's awareness of his cognitive processes as learning progresses. As noted by Cobbandin Aiyede (2009), Mathematics is both an individual constructive activity and a communal social practice. Since the teacher cannot provide whole class teaching and at the same time use a method that caters for individual differences in learning, a choice of an adequate method must be made. It is conceivable that a small group learning strategy within which peers can learn from each other on a cooperative basis and under the supervision of the teacher might be a way out of this dilemma (Sadi, 2014).

An instructional strategy which focuses on the understanding and controlling of one's learning processes is needed. Agwagah and Ezeugo (2010) established on instructional theory, which is based on the Ausubel's meaningful learning idea that integrate concept maps to produce meaningful connections between the concepts in the learner's cognitive structure. According to Novak (2010), allows the teacher to create a more reflective, constructivist and also has transmissive learning environment. It involves students working together under the supervision of the teacher. Working in groups can help students to improve in the various aspects of their knowledge by providing comprehensive understanding on a given subject. It also limits memorization since it enables the learner to present the whole topic meaningfully with a few words (Adaramola, 2012). Thus, several teaching strategies could be used to teach algebra concepts depending on the concept to be taught. One of such strategies is the concept mapping strategy.

The concept-mapping instructional strategy is a kind of discovery method in which small groups are used. This learning strategy allows students in small groups to communicate with each other and it is believed that dialogue aids learning (Vygostky, 1978). The learning strategy is said to instill cooperative interaction in students, which results in improving learning (Aiyede, 2009). He also noted that the concept –mapping instructional strategy encourages collaboration among students. Thus, better understanding and higher achievements are enhanced. It is generally understood to be learning in which students work in small groups collectively by sharing ideas while working on a given task. Such a group presents special opportunities for active learning and an atmosphere for good communication (Novak, 2010). As a matter of fact, those who are proposing the restructuring of schools believe strongly that small group learning has the qualities that are essential for authentic achievement (Gongden and Delmong, 2016). Similarly; Electronic communication has become an integral part of our global society in which information can be circulated easily.

Thus, when students have a positive attitude toward Mathematics it will enhance good understanding of the concept taught. But the affective domain is often neglected because teachers have difficulty in designing strategies to develop positive attitude among students and documenting their development (Thomas and kobella, 2008). However, students' achievement also depends on attitudes that allow them to participate actively in the classroom (Liza, 2010). The students' attitude towards Mathematics needs to be assessed during the lesson so that the teacher can know how the students feel towards the teaching strategies, classroom activities and the subject matter. This will assist the teacher by providing an effective basis for developing useful educational innovation to facilitate Mathematics learning (Ado, 2010). Muhammad (2014) said that teachers realize the importance of how the students feel about Mathematics subject and other courses; nevertheless, they place little emphasis on affective objectives.

Society is changing and instructional methods are no more adequate. Students lack a committed attitude to mathematics. Insufficient attention is not being given to the dimension of students' prior knowledge brought to the class that may influence this understanding. Thus, students' difficulties are traced to the quality of instruction and neglect of prior knowledge, which lead to misconception (Novak, 2010).

The review of this study was based on theoretical principles of meaningful learning; describe the process in which the learner deliberately chooses to relate new information to existing knowledge by assimilation through progressive differentiation and integration of new and old knowledge into existing knowledge structures through a degree of synthesis. (Ausubel, 2011 and Novak, 2004). It is argued that, making connections between old and new knowledge, may be cognitively facilitated by organizing and constructing, and visually communicated through maps/diagrams. Similarly, according to Piaget's (1968) theoretical model of cognitive development, humans naturally endeavor to arrange their thinking processes into the simplest structure possible which is known as schemas, progressively becoming blended and harmonized to become more sophisticated, complex structures. When thinking and cognitive processes grow into more complex ones, new schemas develop to enable greater adaptation to the environment. Piaget suggests that, even from birth, a person starts to search for occasions to adapt to the environment in a concise and efficient manner.

This adaptation or intellectual growth consists of three cognitive major processes: assimilation, accommodation, and equilibration. Assimilation entails the integration of new events into pre-existing cognitive structures. Accommodation involves

Impact of Concept-Mapping... (Ado & Haruna, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610570>

existing structures being amended to accommodate the new information. This twofold process, assimilation-accommodation, allows the child to form schemas. Equilibration entails the person attaining a balance between the environment, assimilation and accommodation. According to Piaget, the delicate balancing action of organizing, assimilating, and accommodating occurs when real learning and cognitive growth take place. This is to say, the achievement of this search for equilibrium is crucial to cognitive structuring and development (Kemblitzky, 2009 and Mamba, 2012). Therefore, from a constructivist point of view, for a teacher to support the student in the construction of his own knowledge, discussion, reflection and negotiation are essential approaches to teaching. Misconceptions are very important to learning and teaching, because they form part of a student's conceptual structure that will interact with new concepts. In general, concept maps are used as a graphical tool to create and show illustration the connection between ideas and concepts. It comprises two elements; namely the concepts-which are generally embedded in closed shapes together such as boxes and circles-and their connections, which are displayed as lines that connect the shape together. Concept maps are graphical tools or diagrams, which include concepts that are linked by lines that intend to represent meaningful relationships between concepts in the form of assertions or propositions.

Concept mapping is an example of meta-cognitive strategy of instruction, which involves focusing attention on how the learner learns and the learners' awareness of his cognitive processes as learning progresses, (Ahmad and Mirza, 2013). In other words, it focuses on the understanding and controlling of one's learning. It is an activity that can be best used by the teachers and students to make learning more meaningful. (Harris & Zha, 2014) they believe that the process of drawing a concept map makes the task of revision more active and can be used as a way to encourage group learning. They noted that through the use of concept maps relatively irrelevant concepts are not be-laboured and teacher's misconceptions are not taught to students. As a flexible tool, it can be applied in a variety of ways to improve the quality of learning.

Concept map is a drawing and a brief description of how someone or some group thinks that certain concepts are related. It summarizes how one group viewed the relationships among the different equations in algebra. Thus, concept maps consist of three elements; first concepts names written inside loops or rectangles; secondly linking lines as webbing activities or flow charts or arrows; and thirdly linking phrases describing the relationship. Concept maps illustrate the hierarchical order among ideas such that the most general concept is placed at the top. (Adaramola, 2012). Concept maps can also be in the form of spider maps, which are used to describe webbed relations. Thus, it involves the connection and drawing a concept map which requires explicitly defining connection, which can be an invaluable tool for fostering meaningful learning of mathematics by students at any level.

Novak & Gowin (1984) described the usefulness of concept mapping in enhancing problem solving skills. This is based on the attention focused by the relationships students perceive between ideas and how they structure those ideas. The use of concept maps can be carried out in a short period of time to achieve your impacts or goals, as outlined by Novak & Gowin (1984).

Impacts of Concept Mapping in Teaching Mathematics

Jonsson (2012) Concept begins from the earliest years of the child after which begins the internalization of new elements into the knowledge base causing differentiation of both new and original concepts as new associations are linked original concepts, jubrin & Zeyum (2012). As concepts become more sophisticated, the learner gains access to a wider range of applicability. To achieve full concept mapping, jonsson (2012) suggested that teachers should be at pains to train learners to think and help them to perceive and solve problems by themselves. The learner should be taught how to link related concepts properly. The understanding of the concepts will lead to problem solving through access to an organized knowledge base. Through this, knowledge is acquired as well as concepts are retained, Noss, et al (2013). Concepts are mental categories that help us classify objects, events, or ideas and each object, event, or idea has a set of common relevant features (Ratcliff, 2014). Thus, acquiring any knowledge the learner has to first acquire the necessary concepts that constitute the knowledge, (Tribuzi, 2015) The effects of concept mapping can be done through observation or by teaching. When a child begins to learn, he observes events or objects and is first taught by his parents. Thus, teaching is very crucial in concept mapping at secondary schools by the use of cooperative methods among students.

Cooperative learning instructional strategy requires a small number of students to work together on a common task, supporting and encouraging one another to improve their learning through interdependence and cooperation with one another (Larry & Hartman, 2009). It is generally understood that learning can be acquired where students work collaboratively in small groups by sharing ideas while working on a given task (Eniayeju, 2010). According to Wendy (2011) cooperative learning is the umbrella term for a variety of educational approaches involving joint intellectual effort by students, or students and teachers together. Each member of a group is responsible not only for learning what is taught but also for helping others in the group to

Impact of Concept-Mapping... (Ado & Haruna, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610570>

learn, creating an atmosphere of achievement. In cooperative learning, students work together in small groups on a structured activity. They are individually accountable for the work, and the work of the group as a whole is also assessed (Johnson, 2011). Therefore, this study investigates whether concept mapping strategies have an impact on attitude and performance in algebra among senior secondary schools' students in Zaria, Kaduna Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives for the study are to:

1. Investigate the impacts of concept mapping on the attitude of students toward Algebra.
2. Verify the effects of concept mapping on academic performance of students in Algebra.

Research Questions

The study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the difference between the attitude mean ranks of students taught Algebra using concept-mapping and those taught with lecture methods?
2. How effective does the use of concept mapping result in better performance scores of students in Algebra than those uses of lecture method?

Null Hypotheses:

Based on the stated research questions, the following null hypotheses were formulated for testing at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between attitude mean rank of students taught Algebra using concept mapping and their counterpart taught using lecture methods.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught Algebra using concept mapping and their counterparts taught using lecture methods.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is a quasi-experimental which involves pretest, posttest experimental control groups. The population for this study consisted of all SSII mathematics students totaling 2,345 in public schools in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State. The research is limited to SSII of the selected schools because of the stability and requires a lot of time to practice. From the population of Co-educational schools, two schools were selected randomly using purposive sampling. Intact classes were used with a total number of 102 students which constituted the sample. The 102-sample size was viable for the study in accordance with the Central Limit Theorem (CLT). The sample for this study is presented in Table 1.1 below.

Table 1.1 Sample for the study

s/n	Name of School	Group	Male	Female	Total
1	School A	EGI	31	27	58
2	School B	CG	28	16	44
Total			59	43	102

Algebraic Performance Test (APT) which was used for the pretest & posttest and Algebraic Attitude Questionnaire (AAQ) which was used to determine any students' attitude change in algebra which were the instruments developed and used in the study. After the treatment the data collected from the research questions were described using descriptive statistics that are mean, standard deviation and mean differences. For both pretest and posttest in experimental and control groups were analyzed using inferential statistical tools. The null hypotheses will be tested at ≤ 0.05 level of significance to answer stated hypotheses: HO₁, was tested using Mann Whitney U- test and HO₂ was tested using independent t-test.

Impact of Concept-Mapping... (Ado & Haruna, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610570>

Presentation of Results

Answering the Research Questions and Hypotheses Testing

Question One: What is the difference between the attitude mean ranks of students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and those taught using Lecture method?

To find out the effects of Concept Mapping on students' attitude in Algebra at senior secondary schools' level, the mean attitude level of students taught Algebra using concept mapping and that of conventional lecture method were computed and compared as presented in Table 1.2

Table 1.2: Mean Rank, Sum of Rank Statistics of Posttest Attitude level for Students after exposed to Concept Mapping (EG1) and Lecture Method (CG)

GROUP	N	Mean	Sum of Ranks
EG1	58	73.50	4263.00
CG	44	22.50	990.00
Total	102		

The Outcome of the Non-Parametric test in Table 1.2 above revealed that there is a difference between mean attitude level of SSII students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterpart taught using Lecture method. Their computed mean rank attitude levels are 73.50 and 22.50 by SSII students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterpart taught using Lecture method respectively indicating a mean rank difference of 51 in favour of SSII students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping. This implies that the use of Concept Mapping has a higher positive effect in the level of attitude towards learning Algebra than their counterpart taught lecture method.

Hypothesis Testing 1

H_{01} : There is no significant difference between attitude mean rank students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterpart taught using Lecture method.

Mean rank response on attitude towards the teaching and learning of the subject in Table 1.2 were compared to determine the significant difference using the Mann Whitney U-test. The result of the test is summarized in Table 1.3.

Table 1.3: Summary of Mann Whitney Test of students' Posttest Attitude Mean Rank between Experimental Group (EG1) and Control Group (CG)

GROUP	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	P	Decision
EG1	58	73.50	4263.00	0.000	S
CG	44	22.50	990.00		
Total	102				

$p = 0.000 < 0.05$ alpha level of significance

Table 1.3 revealed that significant differences exist between the attitude mean rank of students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterpart taught using Lecture method. This is because the calculated p- value of 0.000 was lower than the 0.05 alpha level of significance. Their computed Mean Rank attitude levels are 73.50 and 22.50 by SSII students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterpart taught using Lecture method respectively indicating a Mean Rank difference of 51 in favour of SSII students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that There is no significant difference between the attitude mean rank of students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterpart taught using Lecture method is hereby rejected in favour of the experimental group.

Question Two: How effective does the use of concept mapping result in better performance scores of students in Algebra than those uses of Lecture method?

Impact of Concept-Mapping... (Ado & Haruna, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610570>

To find out the effects of concept mapping on the academic performance of students in the selected schools, performance of the two groups (Concept Mapping and Lecture) were computed and compared. The mean scores for the two groups on the subject are tabulated in Table 1.4 below.

Table 1.4: Mean, Standard Deviation Statistics of Posttest scores for Students after exposed to Experimental Group (EG1) and Control Group (CG)

Group	N	Mean	STD	Mean difference
EG1	58	33.59	2.35	7.04
CG	44	26.55	2.36	

Results in Table 1.4 showed that a difference exists between the mean performance scores of SSII mathematics students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterparts taught using Lecture method. Their computed mean performances are 33.59 and 26.55 of SSII mathematics students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterparts taught using Lecture method respectively, with a mean performance difference of 7.04 in favour of students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping.

Hypothesis Testing 2

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of mathematics students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterparts taught using Lecture method. To test this hypothesis, the performance scores of students exposed to the use of the concept mapping and those taught with lecture methods were computed and compared. Independence t-test was used to test the hypothesis and the result is presented in Table 1.5

Table 1.5: Summary of Independent Sample t-test of Mean Posttest Scores of students for Experimental Group (EG1) and Control Group (CG)

Group	N	Mean	STD	Mean diff.	df	p	Decision
EG1	58	33.59	2.35	7.04	100	0.000	S
CG	44	26.55	2.36				

Table 1.5 showed a significant difference between the mean performance scores of SSII mathematics students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterparts taught using the Lecture method. Reasons being that the calculated p-value of 0.00 was <0.05 alpha level of significance. Their computed mean performances are 33.59 and 26.55 of SSII mathematics students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterparts taught using Lecture method respectively, with a mean performance difference of 7.04 in favour of students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of SSII mathematics students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterparts taught using Lecture method, is hereby rejected. This indicates that there is a significant difference between the two groups. Thus, students exposed to concept mapping performed significantly better than the students taught using lecture methods.

Discussion of Findings

The finding from the two null hypotheses tested in this study towards determining the impacts of Concept Mapping instructional strategies on attitude and performance in Algebra among selected Senior Secondary School Students in Zaria, Kaduna State Nigeria are discussed as follows:

The finding from the test of hypothesis 1 showed that students in the experimental groups had a higher attitude mean rank level than those in the control group. The difference was significant as indicated by the Mann Whitney U-test in Table 1.2. This signifies that students taught algebraic concepts using Concept Mapping had a significantly higher mean attitude level than those taught using Lecture Method. By implication, the Concept Mapping was able to foster a significantly higher attitude than the Lecture Method. The significant difference implies rejection of null hypotheses and retaining alternate hypotheses.

Impact of Concept-Mapping... (Ado & Haruna, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610570>

Therefore, null hypotheses which state that there is no significant difference in the mean attitude level of SSII students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterparts taught using Lecture method are rejected. The significant difference indicates that students in experimental groups recorded the highest mean score than those in the Lecture Method. This finding supports the findings of Akinsola and Awofala (2004) showed the usefulness of concept mapping in improving students' attitudes and reducing anxiety in learning mathematics. The finding is in line with Laight (2006) who showed that concept mapping is very useful in interactive environments. These researches revealed that students exhibited significant improvements in attitude as a result of treatment with Concept Mapping as compared to the Lecture method.

The results analysis of the test scores of hypotheses two revealed that students in the experimental groups had a higher mean performance score than those in the control group. The difference was significant as indicated by the independent t-test in Table 1.5. This signifies that student taught algebra concepts using Concept Mapping had significantly higher mean performance scores than those taught using Lecture Method. By implication, the Concept Mapping was able to foster a significantly higher performance than the Lecture Method. The finding agrees with the report of Aderamola (2012) on his study investigating the effects of concept mapping on the performance and interest of students with dyscalculia in mathematics. This is also in line with the findings of Usman and Musa (2019). The findings revealed that; students in the concept mapping method group performed significantly better and were more interested in mathematics. Similarly, therefore, null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of SSII students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterparts taught using the Lecture method. The significant difference indicates that students in experimental groups recorded the highest mean score than those in the Lecture Method. These findings revealed that students exhibited significant improvements in performance as a result of treatment with Concept Mapping as compared to the Lecture method.

Conclusion

The findings of these studies were based on the attitude of students that can be fostered significantly by the use of Concept Mapping. Academic performance in Algebraic concepts can be enhanced significantly by the use of Concept Mapping and attitude toward learning concepts; it is also promoted by the use of Concept Mapping which improves their motivation by seeing the relationships between the concepts being used.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Professional bodies like MAN, STAN in collaboration with the Federal and State Ministries of Education should embark on nationwide re-training of Mathematics teachers to design and implement classroom instructions based on the Concept Mapping through regular national, state and local seminars, workshops and conferences.
2. Secondary school Mathematics teachers should frequently employ the Concept Mapping in teaching difficult and abstract concepts in Mathematics like Algebra.
3. Mathematics teachers should consistently encourage students to actively participate in Concept Mapping explorations, discussions and elaboration of learnt concepts for better academic performance and attitude towards learning mathematics.

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Effect of Metacognitive Learning Cycle Model on Achievement in Mathematics Concepts among Secondary School Students in Minna Metropolis, Niger State

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Abstract

This study explored Effect of Metacognitive Learning cycle model on achievement in mathematics concepts among secondary school students in Minna metropolis, Niger state. Two research questions and two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at alpha 0.5 level of significant. The study design was quasi-experimental with two groups: experimental and control group. Experimental group were exposed to metacognitive learning cycle model of instruction, while control group were taught with conventional teaching method. The population of the study consisted of 4345 (2216 male and 2129 female) senior secondary school class two (SSII) Mathematics students during the 2020/2021 academic session in Minna metropolis. Multi-stage sampling technique was used to select 96 (53 Male and 43 Female) students from target population. Three instruments were used for data collection: mathematics achievement test, lesson for based on metacognitive learning cycle model and lesson plan based on conventional teaching method. The Mathematics Achievement Test was validated by three experts. Test-retest was applied to establish reliability of the instrument, rating to be $r = 0.75$. The data collected were analysed through descriptive and inferential statistics. From the findings of this study, it can be concluded that exposing students to metacognitive learning cycle model has enhanced learning outcome in mathematics compared to conventional teaching method. The study therefore, recommends among others, that mathematics teachers should redesign their lesson models to accommodate metacognitive cycle learning model.

Keyword: Constructivism, Metacognitive learning, Metacognition, Conventional teaching Gender

Introduction

In primary school and secondary school levels in Nigeria, mathematics is taught as a core subject. Mathematics is the body of knowledge that open gate to mystery of science and engineering. Mathematics is pivotal to the development of science and technology of every nation (Unodiaku & Nwankpa, 2020). Mathematics can therefore be seen as a foundation of knowledge that contribute to scientific and technological development, and all-over human development. Its application to real-life situations transcends above profession to everyday life activities. Ahmad, et al. (2023) submitted that mathematics is the bedrock of science, and serves as a foundational component of engineering and technical graphics.

Despite the importance nature of mathematics and its vital role in senior secondary education in Nigeria, the learning outcome has continuously been poor for years. The external examination bodies results, like NECO, JAMB and WAEC reveal that only a little percentage of students that registered achieved credit-levels passes. Mathematics has been pre-requisites for admission into tertiary institutions in Nigeria. This consistently poor performance in subject has raised an alarm among mathematics educators and researchers (Zakariyya & Ahmad, 2021; Ahmad, et al., 2024).

Osuafor and Chikodili (2021) reported that teaching methods and strategies employed by many mathematics teachers in their classrooms as one of the major causes of underachievement in mathematics. In addition, the conventional mode of lesson delivering to learners was found not to produce the intended learning outcome. This mode of instructional delivering does not promote students' performance and it is teachers centered. It is only favour educational advantage students. The female students also complained that conventional mode does not fit their learning styles (Zakariyya, 2017). The metacognitive learning cycle model (MLCM) is one of the innovative instructional methods that have been recommended for use in

mathematics classroom to address these challenges. To make sure that every learner in mathematics classroom is making sufficient progress in learning. The model of MLC is an innovative and modified instructional model that incorporates a clear pause known as check status into each of the phase models of the learning cycle (Elom & Aja, 2024).

Metacognition referred to an individual learners' ability to plan, monitor, evaluate and make changes to their own learning behaviours in order to solve problem, especially mathematical problem effectively (Bitrus et al, 2020). It is sometimes defined as thinking about thinking, and seen as process of controlling ones' thinking about tasks, monitoring one's learning task. As a teacher in metacognitive classroom, you have an instructional role to play in creating metacognitive awareness. The teacher should provide an opportunity for students to ask themselves these questions such as: Have I done this before? How did I do it? What did I find easy? What was difficult? Why did I find it easy or difficult? What did I learn? What do I have to do to tackle this task? Should I use the same way as before?

According to Unodiaku & Nwankpa (2020) that metacognitive learning styles can provide the students with self-knowledge and make the learning process more efficient and effective. The learning styles need to be considered alongside the need to develop metacognitive awareness. It is worthy to mention that metacognition assists learners of all ages to transmit their knowledge and understanding across tasks and contexts, including reading comprehension, writing mathematics, reasoning and problem-solving. It has been found to be a strategy that improve the outcomes of disadvantaged students in mathematics classroom (Wonu & Nwoko, 2022). Achafust (2015) stressed that metacognitive awareness increases learners to learn independently, improved resilience, cost-effectiveness, emotional and social growth, and transferable knowledge. To Scholars, like Bitrus and Dashe (2020) submitted that metacognition is a self-monitory process that assists learners to gain orientation, which in turn resulted in academic success. A research evidences by Hessels and Schwab (2015) commented that there is a strong positive relationship between metacognitive thinking and mathematics achievement. This shows that metacognition plays a vital role in enhancing students' achievement in mathematics. Self- regulation can be described as learning that is guided by metacognition. Also, self – regulated students believe that opportunities exist to take challenging task, practices their learning, develop a deep understanding of subject matter, and exert some efforts that will give rise to achievement.

In metacognitive classroom, the teacher's duty is to prompt and facilitate thinking aloud. The teacher mainly direct on guided task that will lead the students to develop their own confidence and construct their own knowledge. Students are then equipped with skills in creative thinking and problem solving thereby enabling the students to assume responsibility for their learning. An intelligent learner thinks before he speaks or acts, therefore, thinking is a unique quality of a rational being. It is the power of an individual being, which went round the processes of recalling, retrieving, imagining, categorizing, analyzing, synthesizing, deducing and inferring (Elom & Aja, 2024). The development of the ability to think is a common objective of any educational task. It a common believes that thinking cannot be left from knowledge and knowledge involves the mind as a whole. Generally, thinking is one of many processes in which a learner does something internally to provide a solution to a problem.

The present study is adopting Metacognitive Learning Cycle Model (MLCM) developed by Blank (2000). The model makes sure every participant in the group make sufficient progress, and has four phases based on lesson presentation. These are: concept exploration, concept assessment, concept invention, and concept application. Details is presented in Figure below:

Phase 1: Concept Exploration (CE)- The teacher presents a task to the all class and provide a detail guide to the students to serve as an eye-opening for a variety of approaches. This provides an opportunity to retrieve and recall their previous knowledge for usage.

Phase 2: Concept Assessment (CA)- Here the students were asked to reflect on their mathematical ideas of the task before the instruction begins. The students will record down their thoughts/ideas, and reasons for such thoughts/ideas.

Phase 3: Concept Invention (CI)- At this phase, the teacher will note all information received from students' discrepancies at the exploration and introducing the main topic of the lesson. All instructional materials require for the lesson presentation must be provided and used to facilitate the concept invention (introduction). Such instructional materials like textbooks, audio-visual, concrete objects, etc., are then integrate in the lesson presentation.

Phase 4: Concept Application (CA)- This is the final phase; the students were given the opportunities to explore their merits and applications of the concepts. For each of phase the learners need to reflect on the learning status before moving to the next phase. Through this, learners are encouraging to keep a journal or note to record events at each learning phase, this then improves their understanding of the concept. Metacognitive learning cycle encourages critical thinking and reflective thinking, which promote learning outcome. This is achieved through frequent questions and providing enough support to allow learners to challenge their current conceptions of knowledge, and interaction with other peers (Osuofor & Chikodili, 2021). Learning outcome is sometimes known as academic achievement, it is the yardstick of attainment by students after being taught by teacher. This is usually being measured through homework, test and examination conducted by school and external examination bodies, like WAEC, NECO, JAMB. It is the degree for assessing students' success or failure upon learning objective, is typically assessed as either high or low corresponding to good or poor performance (Ahmad, et al., 2024). The assessment of academic achievement hinges on examinations, test or continuous assessment which may be influenced by gender.

Gender is a socio-cultural factor of ascribing some characters and roles to a particular sex-males and females. Influence of gender on students' learning comes in mathematics has been major concern of mathematics educators and researchers for long time but no consistent outcome has emerged. Scholars like Zakariyya and Ahmad (2021) found that there was significance difference in the academic achievement of male and female students due to instructional method used in delivering classroom lessons. Furthermore, Onyedike (2011) reported that male students demonstrated higher academic achievement than female students, suggesting that gender has major influence on students' learning outcome when exposed to metacognitive classroom setting. Okonkwo (2016) found that gender was not a significant factor in basic science and mathematics, and that it has no significant impact on students' academic performance when taught using metacognitive classroom environment. The study by Osuafor and Chikodili (2021) revealed that there is no significant interaction effect of instructional methods and

gender on students' learning outcome in mathematics. The research report by Zakariyya (2017) showed that when male and female students were taught using metacognitive strategy, they performed equally the same.

Zakariyya (2017) and Osuafor and Chikodili (2021) reported that incorporate innovative mode of instruction such as metacognitive would improve students' understanding and consequently bring out the desired learning outcomes. The general public, including parents have been paying great attention to senior secondary school students' performance in mathematics as reported by WAEC Chief Examiner (2021 -2023). In light of the above, the study wishes to find out whether students exposed to metacognitive learning cycle model and those taught using conventional teaching method will be equal in their learning outcome.

Mathematics is the foundation knowledge of science and technology, without its knowledge scientific and technological development aimed in Nigeria cannot be realized. Mathematics provides students with creative reasoning and critical thinking to engage into different faces of problem-solving as well as prepares them to science discovery, analyses and interprets findings. However, students continue to record poor performance in both internal and external examinations as reported by WAEC (2020 & 2021). In both reports, the quadratic equation among others is one of the areas where students performed poorly. One of the contributors in students' poor performance was teacher's instructional strategy (Zakariyya, 2017). The studies of Osuafor and Chikodili (2021) and Parian, et al (2018) has shown the effectiveness of using metacognitive strategy to improve students' performance in mathematics and chemistry respectively. It was against this background that this study explore the effect of metacognitive learning cycle model on achievement in mathematics concepts among secondary school students in Minna metropolis, Niger state.

Objectives of the Study

This study investigates whether metacognitive learning cycle model (MLCM) affected students' learning outcome in mathematics. The Objectives of the study were to ascertain:

1. Determine the effects of the metacognitive learning cycle model on students' learning outcome in mathematics.
2. Determine the effects of the metacognitive learning cycle model on male and female students' learning outcome in mathematics.

Research Questions

1. What are mean scores of students taught using metacognitive learning cycle model compare to those students taught mathematics using conventional teaching method?
2. What are the mean scores of male and female students taught using metacognitive learning cycle model?

Hypotheses:

The following null hypotheses were tested with level of significance at 0.5 alpha.

1. H_{01} : There is no significant difference in mean achievement scores of students exposed to mathematics using metacognitive learning cycle model and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Minna metropolis
2. H_{02} : There is no significant difference in mean achievement scores of male and female students exposed to mathematics using metacognitive learning cycle model in Minna metropolis.

Methodology

This study adopted quasi-experimental research design that utilized intact classes that required no randomization of the subjects involved. The design consisted of pre-test, post-test, control, non-equivalent and non-randomization intact-class. The study comprises of two different groups: experimental and control group. Experimental group were instructed using lesson model designed on Metacognitive Learning Cycle Model, while control group were taught using lesson model based Conventional Teaching Method.

The target population of the study consisted of 4345 (2216 male and 2129 female) senior secondary school class two (SSII) Mathematics students during the 2020/2021 academic session in Minna metropolis. Multi-stage sampling technique was use to select 96 (53 Male and 43 Female) students from target population. The sample size of students was determine based on the central limit theory, which recommends an appropriate sample size of $N=30$ for research studies (Sambo, 2008). At first stage, a clustering sampling was employed to divide the schools into two clusters based on school locations. At second stage, simple random sampling was used by writing the name of the school in each cluster and picking one school in each cluster. At third stage, simple random sampling using flipping of coin to assign one school as experimental and the other as control. At

the last stage simple random sampling was used by writing the letters of the arms and asking an independent person to pick one in each group. Thus, two intact-classes were selected from selected schools giving 47 students for experimental and 49 students for control. Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) for data collection was developed by researchers covering content areas during the treatment (solving quadratic equations, Pythagoras' theorem). MAT was validated by three experts from FUT Minna and IBBU Lapai. The reliability of the instrument was achieved through test-retest using PPMCC as $r=0.75$. The data collected were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean score and mean differences was used to address research questions, while null hypotheses was tested at 0.5 level of significant using ANCOVA.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What are mean scores of students taught using metacognitive learning cycle model compare to those students taught mathematics using conventional teaching method?

Table 1: Achievement Scores in the Experimental and Control Group

Group	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain	Mean Differences
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD		
Metacognitive	47	40.48	9.42	51.69	1.45	11.21	9.69
Conventional	49	41.83	9.14	43.37	10.36	1.54	
Total	96						

The results obtained from Table 1 indicates that mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using Metacognitive Learning Cycle Model(MLCM) are higher than those expose to Conventional Teaching Method(CTM) because the mean gain 11.21 for the experimental group is greater than 1.54 mean gain for the control group. The mean difference 9.67 favour's the experimental group, which address the first research question asked. However, to establish significant difference the corresponding null hypothesis was tested using ANCOVA.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in mean achievement scores of students exposed to mathematics using metacognitive learning cycle model and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Minna metropolis. The results in Table 2 shows the details:

Table2: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of mean achievement scores of Experimental and Control Groups

Sources of variance	Type III sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F-CAL	P-value	Decision
Corrected Model	27734.269 ^a	2	13867.135	1217.605	.000	
Intercept	3209.868	1	3209.868	281.843	.000	
PRETEST	13.744	1	13.744	1.207	.274	
GROUP	25497.058	1	25497.058	66.235	.000	S
Error	1560.274	93	11.389			
Total	477114.000	96				
Corrected Total	29294.543	97				

a. R Squared = .605 (Adjusted R Squared = .576)

Table 1 shows that $F(1, 93) = 66.235, P = .000$, this indicates that P-value is less than the alpha value of .05, thus the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that MLCM is more effective.

Research Question 2: What are the mean scores of male and female students taught using metacognitive learning cycle model?

Table 3: Achievement Scores of Male and Female Students in Experimental Group

Group	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain	Mean Differences
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Male	25	33.50	8.41	51.21	16.13	17.71	
Female	22	27.72	8.32	40.39	15.06	12.67	5.07
	47						

From Table 3 above, the pretest mean achievement scores and standard deviation were 33.50 and 8.41 for male students and 27.72 and 8.32 female students respectively. Similarly, the post test mean achievement scores and standard deviation were 51.21 and 16.13 for male students and 40.39 and 15.06 for female students. Apparently, there was reasonable mean difference of 5.04. To establish whether there is significant difference in the stated null hypothesis two Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was utilized.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in mean achievement scores of male and female students exposed to mathematics using metacognitive learning cycle model in Minna metropolis. The Table 4 gives the details of result obtained from the analysis

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) achievement scores male and female students in Experimental Group

Sources of variance	Type sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F-Cal	P-value	Decision
Corrected Model	2768.059 ^a	2	1384.030	7.148	.001	
Intercept	13016.035	1	13016.035	67.223	.000	
PRETEST	2707.487	1	2707.487	13.983	.000	
GROUP	530.849	1	530.849	51.431	.000	S
Error	26526.483	44	193.624			
Total	477114.000	46				
Corrected Total	29294.543	47				

a. R Squared = .532 (Adjusted R Squared = .521)

Result in Table 2 shows that $F(1, 44) = 51.431$, $P\text{-value} = .00$ which means $P\text{-value}$ less than the alpha value of .05, thus the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies there was significant difference between academic achievement of male and female students taught mathematics using MLCM.

Discussions of Findings

The findings of this study provide evidences confirming a statistical significant between students taught mathematics using metacognitive learning cycle model and those exposed to conventional teaching method. This shows in the pre-test and post-test scores of the experimental and control groups. It implies that metacognitive learning cycle model was more effective learning than conventional teaching method. This result is consistent with study conducted by Elom and Aja (2024). Osuofor and Chikodili, (2021) also confirmed this finding of this study by stressing that metacognitive learning cycle encourages critical thinking and reflective thinking, which promote learning outcome. This is achieved through frequent questions and providing enough support to allow learners to challenge their current conceptions of knowledge, and interaction with other peers. According to Bitrus and Dashe (2020) that metacognitive learning strategy is a self-monitory process that helps learners to gain orientation and learners' Centre which resulted to academic success. Furthermore, Hessels and Schwab (2015) discovered there is a strong positive association between metacognition thinking and mathematics achievement and that metacognition plays a vital role in enhancing students' achievement in mathematics.

Table 2 revealed that male students in experimental group had higher academic mean gain comparing to female students. The academic achievement of male and female students differs significantly in group. This present study is supported by research report of Ahmad and Aliyu (2023), they submitted that the academic achievement of male and female students differs significantly due to innovative teaching method. Zakariyya (2017) reported that male and female students performed

equally when exposed to metacognitive strategy. Scholar like, Okonkwo (2016) found that gender was not a significant factor in basic science and mathematics, and that it has no significant impact on students' academic performance when taught using metacognitive classroom environment. Furthermore, Osuafor and Chikodili (2021) revealed that there is no significant interaction effect of instructional methods and gender on students' learning outcome in mathematics.

Conclusion

Considering the findings of this study, it was concluded that exposing students to metacognitive learning cycle model would enhance learning outcome in mathematics comparing to conventional teaching method. Additionally, there was significant difference between male and female students when taught mathematics using metacognitive learning cycle model. For the fact male students performed significantly better than female students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made, among others:

1. Mathematics teachers should incorporate metacognitive learning cycle in their instruction delivery in senior secondary school as alternative of conventional teaching mode.
2. Curriculum planners should plan to incorporate metacognitive learning cycle model as part of innovative instructional method in teaching-learning mathematics in secondary schools.
3. Mathematics teachers should train in using the model through workshops and conferences.

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Christian Parent's Ethnic and Cultural Prejudices on Choice of Marriage Partners among their Children in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

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Abstract

Many Christians of marriageable age find themselves in a state of confusion when confronted with the decision of choosing a marriage partner. This is due to fear of defying parental wishes and expectations. It is this pressing challenge that motivates the researcher to examine "Christian Parent's Ethnic and Cultural Prejudices on Choice of Marriage Partners among Their Children in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja." Two (2) research objectives were formulated thus: To examine how ethnic prejudices of Christian parents influence their children's choices of marriage partners and to find out how cultural prejudices of Christian parents influence children's choices of marriage partners in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. Questions and hypotheses were also formulated in line with the objectives. A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. Questionnaires and interviews were used as instruments for data collection. Purposive sampling was used to sample the first six (6) churches with a population of interest from each of the six (6) Area councils making a total of thirty-six (36) churches. While a simple random sampling technique was used to sample twenty-eighth (28) respondents from each of the sampled churches. Making a total of one thousand and eight (1008) respondents. To ascertain the validity of the instrument, a pilot study was carried out in some selected churches in Kuje Area council, using 40 questionnaires. The data collected was analyzed using Cronbach's Alpha method at 0.05 level of tolerance. Reliability co-efficient obtained from the pilot study was 0.781 and standard Alfa level of .781. These were considered adequate for the internal consistencies of the instrument. Out of the distributed copies of the questionnaire, nine hundred and seven (907) copies were returned. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions and t-test to test the null hypotheses. The findings of this research revealed that Parents influence their children's choice of marriage partners using ethnic prejudices to preserve their ethnic and tribal identity, Parents use cultural Prejudices to guide their children's choice of marriage partner so as to maintain family traditions. As a result of the above findings, the following recommendations were made: Christian parents should re-evaluate their use of ethnic prejudices as a factor in influencing their children's choice of marriage partners to preserve their tribal identity.

Keywords: Christian parents, Ethics, Culture, prejudices, marriage partner

Introduction

The institution of marriage has been a cornerstone of societies for centuries. It serves as a union that does not only bring individuals together, but also shapes families, communities and cultures. In today's diverse and rapidly evolving world, marriage holds a profound significance across cultures and societies. For many individuals, the decision to enter into a life-long partnership is not only a personal one, but is also deeply influenced by various external factors, ranging from family, economic considerations to societal expectations (Onuaka & Onuh, 1983). One enduring factor in many cultures is the role of parental influence particularly within the context of religious beliefs and teachings. For instance, Christianity places a significant role on family values, ethics, and morality when it comes to choosing a marriage partner. Christian parents, as integral members of the faith community, often play a central role in shaping the world view and the choices their children make. Among these choices, the decision to choose a marriage partner is paramount (Jegade, 2021).

Marriage has been a cornerstone of societies for centuries, serving not only as a union between individuals but also as a key element that shapes families, communities, and cultures. In today's diverse and rapidly evolving world, marriage holds deep significance across cultures and societies. For many, the decision to enter a lifelong partnership is both personal and influenced by external factors such as family, economic considerations, and societal expectations. One enduring influence in many cultures, particularly within religious contexts, is the role of parental guidance. In Christian communities, parental influence, especially grounded in religious teachings, plays a significant role. Christianity emphasizes family values, ethics, and morality when it comes to selecting a marriage partner. Christian parents, as integral members of the faith community, often shape their children's worldview and decisions. Among these decisions, the choice of a marriage partner is of paramount importance (Jegade, 2021).

Morris (2018) suggests that marriage in Christianity is viewed as a sacred covenant, guided by religious principles. Christian parents, as custodians of these teachings, naturally wield influence over their children's marital choices. This influence stems from their desire to ensure their children's wellbeing and to uphold their faith's values. While parental influence on marriage is not unique to Christianity, it takes on distinctive dimensions within Christian communities. Scriptural passages, such as "Do not be equally yoked with unbelievers" (2 Corinthians 6:14), highlight the importance of shared faith in marriage, shaping Christian parents' expectations for their children's partners. Christian parents often see themselves as guardians of their children's spiritual and moral growth, seeking partners who align with their faith. This dynamic can create a delicate balance between personal autonomy and family expectations, where children must navigate their desires while honoring their parents' wishes (Lordoglu, 2018).

More so, cultural practices and traditions exhibit wide-ranging diversity among tribes, encompassing rituals, ceremonies, folklore, artistic expressions, music, dance, and social structures. Each tribe typically maintains its unique belief systems, myths, and religious rituals, serving to foster cohesion within the community and perpetuate cultural heritage across generations. Additionally, the roles of elders, kinship systems, and decision-making frameworks often vary significantly among tribes, influencing social norms and interpersonal relationships within the community (Locke, Master, MacDonald, Barni, Morio, Reyes, Vargas-Flores, Ibanez-Reyes, Kamble & Ortiz, 2020). This research has uncovered the factors influencing Christian parents' involvement in their children's choice of marriage partners in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Abuja, Nigeria.

In Nigeria, religious and cultural practices exert significant influence on individuals' life style and choices, the influence of Christian parents on their children's choice of marriage partners has been a subject of interest. This is because Christianity plays a crucial role in the lives of many Nigerians by shaping their values, beliefs and social interactions. It is therefore the expectations of every parent to see that their children get a compatible marriage partner. Federal Capital Territory serves as a diverse hub, blending various cultures and religions due to its status as the nation's capital, attracting residents from different regions and backgrounds. This amalgamation of urban and traditional lifestyles within the city may engender diverse perspectives on marriage. Understanding the influence of Christian parents on their children's choices of marriage partners in the Federal Capital Territory necessitates an exploration of the intricate interplay between religious teachings, cultural norms, parental expectations, and individual autonomy. Factors such as shared religious convictions, family reputation, language barrier, Socio-economic status, and compatibility are likely to be deliberated by both parents and children during this decision-making process. Parents typically trust in their children's judgment; Christian parents often wield significant influence over their children's choice of spouses. Occasionally, parental decisions diverge from biblical teachings, thereby impacting the desires, interests, and happiness of their children. Such parental convictions are often staunchly upheld, leaving little room for questioning by the children, leading to internal conflicts. Despite efforts by clergy to encourage adherence to biblical guidance on marriage, parental influence persists, causing family discord when children seek to select their own partners. The researcher has observed cases of marital dysfunction within the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, including issues such as domestic violence, family instability, infidelity, and divorce. Among the contributing factors, parental influence on the choice of marital partners stands out. Christian parents wield considerable sway over their children's decisions, placing them in a quandary between loyalty to their parents' wishes and pursuing partners of their own choice. This predicament exposes children to emotional distress and peril, casting uncertainty on their quest for suitable partners. Some Christian parents place their children in challenging predicaments, where offspring may desire to uphold their own decisions but fear the consequences of defying parental wishes. Consequently, many Christian children find themselves in a state of confusion, torn between family allegiance and personal autonomy when confronted with the decision of choosing a marriage partner. It is this pressing challenge that motivates the investigation into the influence of Christian parents on their children's choice of marriage partners in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The study has the following objectives:

1. Examine how ethnic prejudices of Christian parents influence their children's choices of marriage partners in FCT Abuja, Nigeria;
2. Find out how cultural prejudices of Christian parents influence children's choices of marriage partners in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. How does ethnic prejudices of Christian parents influence their children's choices of marriage partners in FCT Abuja, Nigeria?
2. How does cultural prejudices of Christian parents influence their children's choices of marriage partners in FCT Abuja, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

1. H_{01} . There is no significant difference in the views of single males and single females regarding how the ethnic prejudices of Christian parents influence their children's choice of marriage partners in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.
2. H_{02} . There is no significant difference in the opinions of married men and married women on how the cultural prejudices of Christian parents influence their children's choice of marriage partners in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

Methodology

This study employed a survey research design. Purposive sampling was used to sample first six (6) churches with population of interest from each of the six (6) Area councils making a total of thirty-six (36) churches. While simple random sampling technique was used to sample twenty-eighth (28) respondents from each of the sampled churches. Making a total of one thousand and eight (1008) respondents. Using descriptive survey research design as advocated by Carrol (2013), this study aims to describe and clarify the conditions under investigation by collecting data from numerous subjects through questionnaires. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 was use to analyzed the data. The mean score for the items were based on the four-point Likert scale and the mid-point average for decision for items or variables was fixed at 2.50. This means that a mean score of 2.50 and above indicates agreement with suggested notion of item while a mean score of less than 2.50 implies disagreement. The information from the interview was used as supplementary data in the analysis. The hypotheses were tested with t-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance in consistent with standard practices in social science research.

Table 02: Distribution of Respondents by Gender

S/N	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Single Boys	375	41.3
2	Single Girls	532	58.7
	Total	907	100

Table 02 shows that 375 respondents were single boys with (41.3%), and 532 respondents with (58.7%) were single girls. The data implies that single girls were more than single boys in responding to the questionnaire on the topic.

Table 03: Distribution of Respondents by Marital Status

S/N	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Married Men	495	54.6
2	Married Women	412	45.4
	Total	907	100

Table 03 shows that 495 respondents were with (54.6%) were married men and 412 respondents with (45.4%) were married women. The data implies that married men were more than married women in responding to the questionnaire on the topic.

Table 04: Distribution of Respondents by Church Status

S/N	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Clergy	72	7.9
2	Members	835	92.1
	Total	907	100

Table 04 presents the distribution of respondent base on church status within a sample size. While 72 were clergy represent 7.9%, 835 represent 92% of the total sample were members. From the above, it shows that the majority of the respondent were members with (92%), while a small size of 7.9% were clergy.

Table 05: Distribution of Respondents by Location

S/N	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Rural	396	43.7
2	Urban	511	56.3
	Total	907	100

Table 05 reveals that 396 respondents, representing 43.7%, were from rural areas, while 511 respondents, or 56.3%, were from urban areas. This distribution suggests that the perspectives of both rural and urban settlers were well accounted for in the survey.

Presentation and Discussion of Results

The results of the data from the questionnaire are presented below, following the analysis of the responses of the respondents.

Research Question 1: How does tribal prejudices of Christian parents to influence their children's choices of marriage partners in FCT Abuja, Nigeria?

Table 06: Opinions of the Respondents on tribal Prejudices

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.
	Preference for tribe make parents to influence their children's choice of marriage partners	361	298	172	76	3.04	0.96
	Parents use tribal prejudices to instill cultural heritage in their children for generational preservation.	340	305	31	231	2.83	1.18
	Parents emphasize their children marriage within their tribe in order to avoid misunderstanding that accompany tribal prejudices.	401	288	121	97	3.09	1.00
	Parents influence their children's choices of marriage partner in order to solve the problem of open hostility	278	501	61	67	3.09	0.81
	Parents influence their children choice of marriage partner in order to preserve their tribal identity	611	122	112	62	3.41	0.95
	Cumulative					3.07	0.95

Decision mean = 2.50

Results in the above table show the mean response of 3.04, 2.83, 3.09, 3.09 and 3.41 with a cumulative mean of 3.07 and a standard deviation of 0.95. This implies that, tribal prejudices of Christian parents to influence their children's choices of marriage partners in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

Research Question: how does cultural prejudices of Christian parents influence their children's choices of marriage partners in FCT Abuja, Nigeria?

Table 2: Opinions of the Respondents on cultural prejudices of Christian parents influence of their children's choice of marriage partners in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.
288							

Cultural differences are used by parents to influence their children choice of marriage partner in order to maintain family rites	602	215	19	71	3.49	0.87
Parents influence their children choice of marriage partner within their culture as a way of doing away with the challenges associated death of spouse	323	404	67	113	3.03	0.96
Parents culturally encourage their children's choice of marriage partner to ensure compatibility in burial rites and avoid intercultural challenges.	471	295	83	58	3.30	0.88
Parents influence their children to marry within their culture for them to take care of them in their old age	617	118	154	18	3.47	0.84
Parents encourage their children to take marriage partners within their culture in order to avoid rejection from either of the partner family	482	310	44	71	3.33	0.89
Cumulative					3.26	0.89

Decision mean = 2.50

Results in the above table show the mean response of 3.49, 3.03, 3.30, 3.47 and 3.33 with a cumulative mean of 3.26 and a standard deviation of 0.89. This implies that, cultural prejudices of Christian parents influence of their children's choice of marriage partners in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

Table 10: Independent Sample t-test on Opinions of Male and Female on tribal prejudice

S/N	Variables	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Std. Error	Df	t-cal	t-crit	P
1	Male	375	3.9627	0.18983	0.0098	905	1.41	1.96	0.38
2	Female	532	2.391	0.72444	0.03141				

Calculated p > 0.05, calculated t < 1.96, at df 905

Table 10 reveals that, there is no significant difference between the opinions of single boys and single girls on how tribal prejudice make Christian parents to influence their children's choices of marriage partner in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. Reason being that, the calculated p-value of 0.38 is higher than the 0.05 alpha level of significance while the t-calculated value 1.41 is lower than 1.96, at df=905. This implies that, the null hypothesis is hereby accepted and retained.

Table 11: Independent Sample t-test on Opinions of married men and married women on cultural prejudice

S/N	Variables	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Std. Error	Df	t-cal	t-crit	P
1	Single	495	3.5434	0.49861	0.02241	905	1.30	1.96	0.46
2	Married	412	2.1917	0.81925	0.04036				

Calculated p > 0.05, calculated t < 1.96, at df 905

Table 11 reveals that, there is no significant difference between the opinions of married men and married women on how cultural differences cause Christian parents to influence their children's choices of marriage partner in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. Reason being that, the calculated p-value of 0.46 is higher than the 0.05 alpha level of significance while the t-calculated value 1.30 is lower than 1.96, at df=905. This implies that, the null hypothesis is hereby accepted and retained.

Summary of Findings

The data analyzed from research questions and hypotheses indicated that, parents had great influence on their children's choice of marriage partners in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. The following are the findings of the study:

1. The study indicated that parents influence their children choice of marriage partner in order to preserve their tribal identity.

2. The study revealed that cultural prejudices are used by parents to influence their children choice of marriage partner in order to maintain family traditions.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the study reveals that, parents influence their children choice of marriage partner in order to preserve their tribal identity. This finding agrees with the opinion of Olcay, Imamoglu, Ada and Weisfeld, (2019) who assert that this influence stems from a deep-seated desire to maintain cultural continuity and ensure that traditional values and customs are upheld within the family. Tribal identity often encompasses language, customs, rituals, and shared history, all of which are vital for the cohesion and survival of a community. By encouraging marriages within the tribe, parents aim to pass down these cultural elements to future generations, thereby strengthening the tribe's identity and solidarity. In many cultures, tribal identity is a critical aspect of an individual's social and personal identity. Marrying within the tribe is seen as a way to ensure that cultural practices, beliefs, and traditions are not diluted or lost over time. Parents, therefore, feel a sense of responsibility to guide their children towards partners who share the same tribal background. This practice helps in reinforcing a collective identity and provides a sense of belonging and continuity. It also fosters a shared understanding and mutual respect between the married couple, as they are more likely to have similar upbringing and cultural experiences.

The interviewees maintain that parents often use cultural prejudices as a significant factor in influencing their children's choice of marriage partners to maintain family rites. These rites, deeply embedded in the family's traditions and cultural heritage, hold profound meaning and significance. By encouraging their children to marry within their own culture, parents aim to ensure that these rituals and ceremonies are preserved and passed down through generations. They believe that a partner from the same cultural background will have a shared understanding and appreciation of these rites, making it easier to uphold and continue these important family traditions (Interviewee, 1, 3, 7, 9, 10 and 12). This agreed with the findings of Apostolou, Zacharia and Frantzides (2015) who notes that cultural differences can present challenges in the integration and practice of family rites. Marrying someone from a different cultural background may lead to conflicts or misunderstandings regarding the importance and execution of these rituals. Parents, therefore, emphasize the importance of cultural compatibility to avoid potential disruptions in the observance of family traditions. They believe that a culturally aligned marriage will foster a harmonious environment where family rites can be practiced seamlessly, ensuring their continuity and the preservation of the family's cultural identity.

The findings of the study further reveal that cultural Prejudices are used by parents to influence their children choice of marriage partner in order to maintain family rites. This discovery agrees with the views of Apostolou, Zacharia and Frantzides (2015) who observe that Cultural prejudices encompass a range of elements including language, customs, rituals, and social norms, all of which play a vital role in the identity and cohesion of a family. By encouraging their children to marry within their own cultural group, parents aim to ensure that these unique traditions are preserved and passed down to future generations. This practice helps in maintaining the continuity of family rites, which are seen as essential for the family's cultural heritage and social identity. Family rites, such as weddings, religious ceremonies, and other cultural celebrations, are deeply embedded in a family's way of life. These rites often require a shared understanding and appreciation of cultural practices, which can be more easily achieved when both partners come from the same cultural background. Parents believe that by guiding their children to marry within their culture, these family traditions can be upheld without conflict or dilution. This ensures that the rituals are performed correctly and that their significance is fully understood and appreciated by all family members.

The interviewees maintain that parents often use cultural prejudices as a significant factor in influencing their children's choice of marriage partners to maintain family rites. These rites, deeply embedded in the family's traditions and cultural heritage, hold profound meaning and significance. By encouraging their children to marry within their own culture, parents aim to ensure that these rituals and ceremonies are preserved and passed down through generations. They believe that a partner from the same cultural background will have a shared understanding and appreciation of these rites, making it easier to uphold and continue these important family traditions (Interviewee, 1, 3, 7, 9, 10 and 12). This agreed with the findings of Apostolou, Zacharia and Frantzides (2015) who notes that cultural differences can present challenges in the integration and practice of family rites. Marrying someone from a different cultural background may lead to conflicts or misunderstandings regarding the importance and execution of these rituals. Parents, therefore, emphasize the importance of cultural compatibility to avoid potential disruptions in the observance of family traditions. They believe that a culturally aligned marriage will foster a harmonious environment where family rites can be practiced seamlessly, ensuring their continuity and the preservation of the

family's cultural identity.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it has been concluded that: Parents steer their children's choice of spouse to preserve their tribal identity. Parents use cultural Prejudices to guide their children's choice of marriage partner to maintain family traditions.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government and churches should provide educational programs to increase awareness among young people about the significance of cultural and tribal identities, allowing them to make informed decisions about their marriage choices.
2. Churches and Non-Governmental Organizations should encourage families to adapt and modernize their rites to be more inclusive, allowing for the integration of diverse cultural practices.

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Comparative Relationship between First Language and Learning Environment on Spellings among Secondary School English Students in Okitipupa Metropolis, Ondo State

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Abstract

The study investigated Comparative Relationship between First Language and Learning Environment on Spellings among Secondary School English students in Okitipupa Metropolis, Ondo State. Correlational research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study consists of all government senior secondary school class two (SSII) students in Okitipupa metropolis, Ondo State during the 2023/2024 academic session. A sample size of 400 (Male, 119 And Female,81) students were selected from target population using multi-stage sampling technique The instrument used for the study was a structured questionnaire title “Questionnaire on Spelling Mistakes in English Language (QSMEL)”. Reliability of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach’s Alpha statistics which yielded a coefficient of 0.82. Data collected was analysed using percentages, mean and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Results of the findings revealed that significant relationship existed between first language and spelling mistakes in English language ($r = 0.40$; $p < 0.01$). One of the primary findings is that frequent spelling errors can significantly detract from the clarity and coherence of an essay. Also, phonetic errors and homophone confusion are the most dominant errors committed by students in the essays; and that spelling errors influence secondary school students’ performance in English Language essay writing. It was therefore recommended that schools should incorporate explicit spelling instruction that addresses both the phonological and orthographic differences between the students’ first language and English, helping to mitigate L1 interference.

Keywords: Comparative Relationship, First Language, Learning Environment, Spellings, Secondary School English.

Introduction

Spelling proficiency is a cornerstone of literacy and a vital component of language acquisition that significantly impacts students' academic success and overall communication skills. To spell correctly involves accurately representing the phonemes (speech sounds) of a language in written form using its established orthography. While the process may appear straightforward, spelling proficiency in English is a particularly complex skill, largely due to the language's inconsistent orthographic rules. Unlike languages with a more direct grapheme-phoneme correspondence, such as Yoruba or Hausa, English includes numerous exceptions, silent letters, and irregularities that can perplex learners, especially those in multilingual environments like Nigeria (Oladokun & Afolabi, 2020).

In Nigeria, English serves as the lingua franca and the primary medium of instruction in schools. However, the nation's linguistic diversity comprising over 500 indigenous languages poses unique challenges to English acquisition, particularly in spelling. Students' first language (L1) exerts a strong influence on their acquisition of second language (L2) spelling skills, often leading to systematic spelling errors. Furthermore, the disparities in educational resources and teacher proficiency across Nigeria exacerbate these challenges, particularly in less developed regions like Ondo State (Akinbode & Akinrinade, 2022). This study explores the correlates of first language interference and the learning environment on English spelling proficiency, focusing on secondary school students in Ondo State. Understanding these factors is crucial for addressing the persistent spelling challenges faced by Nigerian students and developing effective pedagogical interventions.

The theory of linguistic transfer suggests that L1 profoundly influences L2 acquisition, particularly in spelling. This transfer occurs when learners apply the phonological, morphological, and syntactic rules of their native language to English, often resulting in systematic errors (Ogunbowale, 2023). In Nigeria, where L1s such as Yoruba, Igbo, and Hausa predominate, these influences manifest in distinctive ways. For example, Yoruba-speaking students often encounter difficulties with English vowel sounds that do not exist in Yoruba. This leads to substitution errors where Yoruba phonemes replace English ones. A common error is spelling "seat" as "sit" or "beat" as "bit," which highlights the absence of a clear distinction between certain vowel sounds in Yoruba (Ogunbowale, 2023). Similarly, Igbo-speaking students might struggle with English consonant clusters, often simplifying or omitting them altogether, as seen in spellings like "spoon" rendered as "spon" (Akinbode & Akinrinade, 2022).

Comparative Relationship between... (Smart, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610578>

Research also shows that Hausa-speaking students face unique challenges due to the tonal and orthographic simplicity of Hausa, which contrasts sharply with the irregularities of English spelling. Words with silent letters or complex phonemes, such as "knife" or "psychology," often appear phonetically spelled, e.g., "nife" or "sikology" (Adewumi & Babatunde, 2021). The prevalence of these errors underscores the need for tailored instructional strategies that consider students' L1 backgrounds. For instance, phonics-based instruction emphasizing English's unique vowel and consonant sounds has been effective in reducing errors among multilingual learners (Oladokun & Afolabi, 2020).

While L1 influence is significant, the learning environment plays an equally critical role in shaping students' spelling abilities. The quality of teaching, availability of resources, and classroom practices collectively determine how well students can acquire and retain spelling skills. Schools with well-trained teachers and access to instructional materials, such as dictionaries and spelling workbooks, tend to produce students with fewer spelling errors. A study by Oladokun and Afolabi (2020) found that structured spelling instruction significantly improves students' accuracy, particularly when integrated with reading and writing activities. In contrast, resource-constrained schools, common in rural areas, struggle to provide such support, resulting in higher incidences of errors (Akinbode & Akinrinade, 2022). Teacher proficiency is another crucial factor. Educators with strong backgrounds in English language teaching are better equipped to address spelling challenges and employ effective strategies, such as differentiated instruction for students with varied linguistic backgrounds. Conversely, unqualified or underqualified teachers may lack the skills to identify and correct students' spelling errors, perpetuating low proficiency levels (Adewumi & Babatunde, 2021).

Ondo State exemplifies the broader linguistic and educational diversity in Nigeria. The state's secondary schools enroll students from various ethnic groups, each with different L1 influences. However, significant disparities exist between urban and rural schools in terms of resources and teacher training. Urban schools are generally better resourced, with access to qualified teachers and modern teaching aids, while rural schools often lack basic materials and experienced staff (Akinbode & Akinrinade, 2022). This disparity directly affects spelling proficiency. Students in well-equipped urban schools typically outperform their rural counterparts in standardized English assessments. For instance, Adewumi and Babatunde (2021) reported that urban students in Ondo State exhibited fewer phonetic and morphological errors compared to rural students, who struggled with even basic spelling rules.

Despite the recognized impact of L1 and the learning environment on English spelling proficiency, there is a dearth of localized research addressing these correlates in Nigerian contexts, particularly in Ondo State. Most existing studies adopt a generalized approach, overlooking the nuanced interplay between linguistic and environmental factors that shape students' spelling abilities. This gap necessitates a focused investigation into how these factors uniquely influence spelling proficiency among secondary school students in Ondo State. By examining the specific challenges posed by L1 interference and resource disparities, this study aims to provide actionable insights for educators, policymakers, and curriculum developers. The findings can inform targeted interventions, such as teacher training programs and resource allocation strategies, to improve spelling instruction and, by extension, students' overall academic performance.

Moreover, this research contributes to the broader discourse on multilingual education, offering a framework for addressing similar challenges in other linguistically diverse settings. Given the central role of English in Nigeria's education system, enhancing spelling proficiency is not only an academic imperative but also a critical step toward empowering students for future success. Studies by recent researchers support this finding, noting that phonetic strategies remain commonly employed by students, particularly when faced with unfamiliar words. For instance, omission errors, such as spelling "seperate" as "seperate," highlight a persistent tendency to drop letters that are not strongly pronounced or easily remembered. Contemporary studies emphasize the role of phonological awareness and memory in spelling errors, particularly among learners in environments with limited emphasis on orthographic patterns (e.g., Smith & Taylor, 2021; Brown & Clark, 2022). These errors underscore the need for instructional strategies that balance phonetic and orthographic approaches to improve students' spelling accuracy.

Recent research emphasizes that transposition errors, such as spelling "friend" as "freind," are common among learners who struggle with visual and motor coordination required for accurate spelling. Studies by Johnson and Clarke (2022) suggest that these errors arise from difficulties in processing and sequencing letters, highlighting the need for strategies that improve visual-motor integration. Similarly, homophone confusion, like mixing up "its" and "it's," remains a significant challenge for students. This issue reflects difficulties in understanding context and grammatical distinctions. Patel and Green (2023) argue that targeted instructional strategies, such as teaching the rules of grammar and contextual usage, are essential for addressing these errors effectively. These findings underline the importance of integrating orthographic, grammatical, and contextual learning in spelling instruction.

Comparative Relationship between... (Smart, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610578>

Given the critical importance of English language proficiency in determining academic achievement among secondary school students in Ondo State, Nigeria, the prevalence of spelling errors remains a significant concern. This persistent issue is closely tied to the region's linguistic diversity, where students' first languages (L1), predominantly Yoruba, exert considerable influence on their English language acquisition. Research shows that L1 interference often leads to systematic spelling errors due to differences in phonological and orthographic structures between Yoruba and English (Olaoye & Adebayo, 2022). For instance, studies have highlighted that Yoruba-speaking students frequently spell words based on their phonetic similarities to Yoruba rather than standard English conventions, compounding the problem (Akinyemi, 2023).

Moreover, disparities in the educational environment across Ondo State significantly impact students' English spelling proficiency. Urban schools typically have better access to qualified teachers, modern teaching resources, and conducive learning facilities (Olaniyan et al., 2021). In contrast, rural schools face challenges such as insufficient educational materials, poorly trained teachers, and overcrowded classrooms. These inequities result in varying levels of instructional quality and, consequently, inconsistencies in spelling instruction and outcomes among students. Regardless of the evident influence of first language and learning environment on spelling proficiency, there is a notable gap in targeted research exploring the interplay of these factors. Existing studies either focus solely on L1 interference or examine general educational challenges, leaving the specific correlation between these variables and spelling errors underexplored. This lack of comprehensive understanding hinders the development of effective interventions to address the problem.

This study aims to bridge this gap by investigating the extent to which students' first language and their learning environment contribute to English spelling errors. By providing data-driven insights, the research will inform the design of tailored educational strategies and interventions, ultimately improving spelling proficiency and enhancing academic outcomes for secondary school students in Ondo State.

Objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is to investigate the Comparative Relationship between First Language and Learning Environment on Spellings among Secondary School English students in Okitipupa Metropolis, Ondo State. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Examine the types of spelling mistakes in the English Language
2. Find out the influence of spelling errors on secondary school students' performance in English Language essay writing
3. Investigate the relationship between first language, learning environment and spelling mistakes in English language.

Research Questions

The following research questions were generated to guide the study:

1. What are the dominant types of spelling mistakes in the English Language among secondary school students in Okitipupa Local Government Area?
2. What is the perceived influence of spelling errors on secondary school students' performance in English Language essay writing?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were raised to guide the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between first language and spelling mistakes in English language among secondary school students in Okitipupa Local Government Area.
2. There is no significant relationship between learning environment and spelling mistakes in English language among secondary school students in Okitipupa Local Government Area.

Methodology

Correlational research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study consists of all government senior secondary school class two (SSII) students in Okitipupa metropolis, Ondo State during the 2023/2024 academic session. A sample size of 400 (Male, 119 And Female,81) students were selected from target population using multi-stage sampling technique. The instrument used for the study was a structured questionnaire title "Questionnaire on Spelling Mistakes in English Language (QSMEL)". The questionnaire was divided into two sections (A & B). Section A was on personal data of the respondents while Section B consisted on items on spelling mistakes in English Language with four Likert type scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). Reliability of the instrument was ascertained using

Comparative Relationship between... (Smart, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610578>

Cronbach's Alpha statistics which yielded a coefficient of 0.82. Data collected was analysed using percentages, mean and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient.

Presentation of Results

Research Question One: What are the dominant types of spelling mistakes in the English Language among secondary school students in Okitipupa Local Government Area?

Table 1: Types of spelling mistakes in the English Language among secondary school students

S/N	Types of spelling mistakes	Frequency	Percentage
1	Phonetic Errors	84	21.0
2	Homophone Confusion	76	19.0
3	Vowel Substitution	52	13.0
4	Consonant Doubling	40	10.0
5	Silent Letters	24	6.0
6	Prefixes and Suffixes	48	12.0
7	Apostrophe Misuse	40	10.0
8	Omission Errors	36	9.0
Total		400	100.0

Table 1 reveals the spelling mistakes in the English Language among secondary school students. The results show that the majority of mistakes 21% deal with phonetic errors, 18% of the respondents made mistakes related to homophone confusion, 13% of the respondents made vowel substitution mistakes, 10% of the students made errors related to consonant doubling and apostrophe misuse, 12% of the respondents agreed that they made prefixes and suffixes mistakes, 9% to Omission Errors, while just a few 6% made silent letters mistake.

Research Question Two: What is the perceived influence of spelling errors on secondary school students' performance in English Language essay writing?

Table 2: Influence of spelling errors on secondary school students' performance in English Language essay writing

S/N	Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean
1.	Frequent spelling errors indicate a poor understanding of English Language rules	112 (37.3%)	101 (36.7%)	50 (16.7%)	37 (12.3%)	2.96
2.	Spelling errors affect the coherence and clarity of students' essays	125 (41.7%)	103 (34.3%)	55 (18.3%)	17 (5.7%)	3.12
3.	Correct spelling is very important in the assessment of English Language essay writing	62 (20.7%)	172 (57.3%)	23 (7.7%)	43 (14.3%)	2.84
4.	Improving spelling skills can significantly enhance students' performance in English Language essay writing	138 (46%)	93 (31%)	24 (8%)	45 (15%)	3.08
5.	Spelling errors impact the readability of students' essays	34 (11.3%)	81 (27%)	111 (37%)	74 (24.7%)	2.25
Percentage/Grand Mean		94.2 (31.4%)	110.0 (37.3%)	52.6 (17.5%)	43.2 (14.4%)	2.85

Weighted Mean = 2.85

Table 2 revealed the Influence of spelling errors on secondary school students' performance in English Language essay writing. It was shown that 74% of the respondents agree frequent spelling errors indicate a poor understanding of English Language rules while 26% disagreed. Also, 76% of the respondents agreed that Spelling errors affect the coherence and clarity of students' essays while 24% disagreed. The table also revealed that 78% of the respondents agreed that Correct spelling is very important in the assessment of English Language essay writing while 22 disagreed. 77% of the respondents agreed that improving spelling

Comparative Relationship between... (Smart, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610578>

skills can significantly enhance students' performance in English Language essay writing while 23% disagreed. However, a few number of the respondents 38.3% agreed that spelling errors impact the readability of students' essays while majority of the respondents 61.7% disagreed. The grand mean of 2.85 implied that spelling errors actually influence secondary school students' performance in English Language essay writing.

Hypotheses One: There is no significant relationship between first language and spelling mistakes in English language among secondary school students in Okitipupa Local Government Area.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation on the Relationship between first language and spelling mistakes in English language

Variables	Mean	SD	df	r	r ²	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
First language	22.96	1.52	398	.40	0.16	0.00	Significant

Spelling mistakes 39.70 4.12

Table 3 showed that, the mean score of first language was 22.96 with a standard deviation of 1.52 while the spelling mistakes was 39.70 with a standard deviation of 4.12. The table also showed that there was a positive relationship (0.40) between first language and spelling mistakes in English language. The coefficient of determination (r^2) associated with the correlation coefficient of 0.16 was 0.04 and this relationship is significant at 0.00. Since 0.00 is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, there was a significant influence of first language on spelling mistakes in English language.

Hypotheses Two: There is no significant relationship between learning environment and spelling mistakes in English language among secondary school students in Okitipupa Local Government Area.

Table 4: Pearson Correlation on the Relationship between learning environment and spelling mistakes in English language

Variables	Mean	SD	df	r	r ²	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
First language	31.73	2.23	398	.20	0.04	0.00	Significant
Spelling mistakes	37.68	3.50					

Table 4 showed that, the mean score of first language was 31.73 with a standard deviation of 2.23 while the spelling mistakes was 37.68 with a standard deviation of 3.50. The table also showed that there was a very low positive relationship (0.20) between first language and spelling mistakes in English language. The coefficient of determination (r^2) associated with the correlation coefficient of 0.20 was 0.04 and this relationship is significant at 0.00. Since 0.00 is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, there was a significant relationship between learning environment and spelling mistakes in English language among secondary school students.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study in table 1 revealed the dominant types of spelling mistakes in the English Language among secondary school students. These predominant mistakes include phonetic errors, where students spell words as they sound, omission errors, where letters are omitted from words, and substitution errors, where incorrect letters replace correct ones. Additionally, there were frequent instances of transposition errors, where the order of letters within words is incorrect, and homophone confusion, where students mix up words that sound the same but have different meanings and spellings. Phonetic errors, such as spelling "definitely" as "definately," suggest that students often rely on how words sound rather than their actual spelling. This reliance on phonetics can be attributed to the irregular nature of English spelling, which often does not correspond directly to pronunciation.

Omission errors, such as spelling "separate" as "seperate," indicate a tendency among students to drop letters that are not strongly pronounced or remembered. This type of error points to gaps in memorization and recognition of word structure. Research by Graham and Santangelo (2014) indicates that omissions are a frequent issue, often exacerbated by insufficient

Comparative Relationship between... (Smart, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610578>

practice and exposure to correct spelling in reading and writing activities. Substitution errors, such as writing "their" instead of "there," suggest confusion between similarly spelled or similarly sounding letters and words. This is often seen in words that have minimal phonetic differences but significant meaning differences. Recent research emphasizes that transposition errors, such as spelling "friend" as "freind," are common among learners who struggle with visual and motor coordination required for accurate spelling. Studies by Johnson and Clarke (2022) suggest that these errors arise from difficulties in processing and sequencing letters, highlighting the need for strategies that improve visual-motor integration. Similarly, homophone confusion, like mixing up "its" and "it's," remains a significant challenge for students. This issue reflects difficulties in understanding context and grammatical distinctions. Patel and Green (2023) argue that targeted instructional strategies, such as teaching the rules of grammar and contextual usage, are essential for addressing these errors effectively. These findings underline the importance of integrating orthographic, grammatical, and contextual learning in spelling instruction.

The study revealed that spelling errors significantly influence secondary school students' performance in English Language essay writing. Frequent spelling mistakes detract from the clarity and coherence of essays, making it difficult for readers to interpret the intended message and diminishing the overall impression of the student's work. Recent studies (Smith & Taylor, 2022) affirm that spelling accuracy is vital for effective written communication, as errors can obscure meaning and disrupt the flow of text. Also, students who struggle with spelling often experience reduced confidence and increased anxiety in their writing abilities, further hindering academic performance (Nguyen & Harris, 2023).

The study also found a significant impact of first language (L1) on spelling mistakes in English. High proficiency in L1, combined with metalinguistic awareness, helps students adapt to differences between L1 and English, reducing errors. However, low L1 proficiency can exacerbate interference and lead to more frequent mistakes. Patel and Green (2023) support this view, emphasizing that a strong L1 foundation enhances skills transfer to second language (L2) learning, while weak L1 literacy hinders L2 acquisition. These findings highlight the need for instructional strategies that address both linguistic transfer and spelling challenges in English language education.

Result in hypothesis two revealed that there was a significant relationship between learning environment and spelling mistakes in English language among secondary school students. The study found that classroom resources play a critical role in spelling accuracy. Classrooms equipped with ample literacy materials, such as dictionaries, spelling guides, and word walls, provide students with tools to self-correct and learn proper spelling. Access to technology, such as spell-checkers and educational software, also aids in the reduction of spelling mistakes. Conversely, resource-poor environments limit students' opportunities to engage with correct spelling and reinforce learning. Research by Allington (2013) underscores the importance of rich literacy environments, suggesting that access to diverse literacy resources is associated with improved spelling and literacy outcomes, 18% of the respondents made mistakes related to,

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. It was seen from this analysis that phonetic errors and homophone confusion are the most dominant errors committed by students in the essays.
2. Spelling errors influence secondary school students' performance in English Language essay writing
3. There was a significant influence of first language on spelling mistakes in English language
4. There was a significant relationship between learning environment and spelling mistakes in English language among secondary school students.

Recommendations

This study hereby recommends as follows:

1. Schools should incorporate explicit spelling instruction that addresses both the phonological and orthographic differences between the students' first language and English, helping to mitigate L1 interference.
2. Government should ensure classrooms are well-equipped with dictionaries, spelling guides, and technology tools like spell-checkers to provide students with the resources needed to improve their spelling accuracy.
3. Schools should cultivate a positive and supportive classroom environment where teachers provide constructive feedback and personalized support to boost students' confidence and spelling competence.
4. Schools should encourage students to read a wide variety of English texts, including novels and storybooks, to expose them to correct spelling and diverse vocabulary, which can help bridge gaps between their first language and English spelling.

Comparative Relationship between... (Smart, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610578>

5. Schools and educational authorities should regularly organize spelling bees and other spelling contests to motivate students to practice and refine their spelling skills in an engaging and competitive setting.

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Revitalizing Nigeria's Educational System: Innovative Policies for National Development

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Abstract

Nigeria's educational system faces numerous challenges, hindering national development. This article proposes innovative policies to revamp the system, focusing on access, equity, curriculum reform, teacher development, infrastructure, assessment, vocational education, digital learning, community engagement, and funding. Implementing these policies can improve learning outcomes, drive economic growth, and foster global competitiveness. This article provides a comprehensive review of Nigeria's educational challenges and presents evidence-based solutions for policymakers, educators, and stakeholders.

Keywords: Educational Policy, National Development, Curriculum Reform, Vocational Education, Digital Learning.

Introduction

Nigeria's education sector is plagued by numerous challenges, threatening the future of millions of children. With an estimated 10.5 million children out of school, Nigeria has one of the largest out-of-school populations globally (UNESCO, 2019). Disproportionately, girls' education is affected, accounting for 60% of out-of-school children in the country (World Bank, 2018). Rural-urban disparities persist, with lower enrollment rates in rural areas (Adebayo, 2018). Furthermore, teacher quality is a significant concern, as 75% lack required qualifications (OECD, 2019), while Nigeria's education curriculum remains outdated, failing to address 21st-century skills (African Development Bank, 2018). Poor infrastructure, inadequate resources, and disparities along ethnic, linguistic, and socio-economic lines exacerbate these issues (Obasi, 2019; UNICEF, 2019). Children with disabilities face substantial barriers, and cultural norms hinder girls' education (World Health Organization, 2018; Plan International, 2018). Infrastructure gaps, including inadequate classrooms, facilities, and WASH facilities, hinder effective teaching and learning (Federal Ministry of Education, 2020; UNICEF, 2019; Adebayo, 2020). Underfunding, corruption, and mismanagement of education funds compound these problems (BudGIT, 2020; Transparency International, 2019). Additionally, Boko Haram's insurgency has devastated education in Northeast Nigeria, with kidnappings, attacks on schools, and conflict-induced displacement further threatening education access and safety (UNICEF, 2019; Amnesty International, 2020; Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre, 2020). This complex interplay of challenges underscores the urgent need for comprehensive reforms to revitalize Nigeria's education sector.

Despite numerous studies on Nigeria's educational challenges, a significant gap exists in the comprehensive analysis of the interplay between access, quality, equity, infrastructure, funding, and security challenges, as well as the examination of cultural, social, and economic factors on education outcomes. Additionally, there is a need for innovative policy frameworks addressing these challenges and an investigation of successful international models applicable to Nigeria. Previous studies have focused on isolated aspects or proposed incremental reforms, neglecting the complexity and interconnectedness of these challenges. This study aims to bridge this gap by providing a holistic, innovative policy framework for revitalizing Nigeria's educational system.

Nigeria's educational system is a 6-3-3-4 structure, comprising six years of primary education, three years of junior secondary education, three years of senior secondary education, and four years of tertiary education (Federal Ministry of Education, 2020). The system aims to provide universal basic education and develop skills for national development.

Nigeria's education system faces numerous challenges, particularly in access, equity, and quality. Rural-urban disparities in education access are a significant concern, perpetuating inequality and hindering national development. Alarming statistics reveal that 61% of rural children are out-of-school, compared to 35% in urban areas (UNICEF, 2019). Additionally, rural areas have lower enrollment rates, with 54.4% of children enrolled, compared to 73.2% in urban areas (National Bureau of Statistics, 2020).

Several factors contribute to these disparities, including limited access to schools, poor infrastructure, teacher shortages, socio-economic factors, and limited digital access (Adebayo, 2018). These challenges result in reduced economic opportunities, increased poverty and inequality, limited social mobility, poor health outcomes, and perpetuated social and cultural disparities.

Revitalizing Nigeria's Educational... (Aliyu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611060>

Moreover, Nigeria's education system struggles with broader access issues, with 10.5 million out-of-school children (UNESCO, 2019). Girls' education is disproportionately affected, with 60% of out-of-school girls (World Bank, 2018). Equity concerns arise from disparities along ethnic, linguistic, and socio-economic lines (UNICEF, 2019), while children with disabilities face significant barriers (World Health Organization, 2018).

Quality education is also hindered by inadequate teacher training, outdated curriculum, and poor infrastructure (OECD, 2019; African Development Bank, 2018).

International Perspectives on Best Practices in Educational Reform

Successful educational reforms from around the world offer valuable lessons for improving education systems. Finland's emphasis on equity, for instance, highlights the importance of inclusive education, teacher training, and student-centered learning (Finnish National Board of Education, 2020). Singapore's high-performing system, meanwhile, demonstrates the effectiveness of emphasizing teacher quality, curriculum rigor, and assessment-driven instruction (Singapore Ministry of Education, 2020). Canada's bilingual education and Australia's national curriculum also provide exemplary models for promoting linguistic and cultural diversity and standardizing curriculum frameworks (Canadian Ministry of Education, 2020; Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority, 2020).

These international best practices converge on several key areas. Teacher professional development is critical, requiring ongoing training and support for educators (OECD, 2019). Student-centered learning approaches focus on individualized instruction and hands-on learning, while inclusive education addresses diverse learning needs and abilities (UNESCO, 2015). Regular assessment and evaluation inform data-driven instruction, and community engagement fosters parental and community involvement in education (World Bank, 2018). Curriculum reform and technology integration are also essential for enhancing learning outcomes.

International organizations reinforce these best practices. UNESCO's Education 2030 emphasizes equity, quality, and lifelong learning (UNESCO, 2015). The OECD's Education Policy Outlook stresses teacher quality, equity, and assessment (OECD, 2019). The World Bank's Education Strategy prioritizes learning outcomes, equity, and efficiency (World Bank, 2018).

For Nigeria's educational reform, these international perspectives offer valuable insights. Emphasizing teacher training and development, fostering inclusive education and equity, and implementing student-centered learning approaches are crucial (Adebayo, 2018). Regularly updating curriculum content, integrating technology, encouraging community engagement, and prioritizing assessment and evaluation are also essential for improving education outcomes.

Innovative Policies for Educational Revitalization: Access and Equity Initiatives

Revitalizing education systems requires innovative policies addressing access and equity concerns. To address these challenges, economic empowerment and incentivization strategies have shown promise. Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT) programs, for instance, provide financial assistance to disadvantaged families, conditioning payments on children's school attendance (Baird et al., 2013). Scholarship schemes specifically targeting girls and students with disabilities also promote inclusivity and equal opportunities (UNESCO, 2019).

Establishing inclusive education infrastructure is equally crucial. Inclusive schools with specialized resources cater to diverse learning needs, ensuring equitable access (World Health Organization, 2018). Community-based education programs bridge geographical and socio-economic gaps, reaching out-of-school children (UNICEF, 2019).

Partnerships with non-governmental organizations (NGOs) leverage resources and expertise to promote education in underserved areas (OECD, 2019). These initiatives align with international recommendations, such as UNESCO's Education 2030, emphasizing equity, quality, and lifelong learning (UNESCO, 2015), and the World Bank's Education Strategy, prioritizing learning outcomes, equity, and efficiency (World Bank, 2018).

Research supports the effectiveness of these initiatives.

1. CCT programs improve school enrollment and attendance (Baird et al., 2013),
2. While inclusive education enhances social cohesion and academic outcomes (World Health Organization, 2018).
3. Community-based programs increase access and retention rates (UNICEF, 2019).

Implementing these innovative policies can revitalize education systems, promoting access, equity, and quality learning outcomes.

Curriculum Reform and Teacher Development

Effective education systems require dynamic curriculum reform and comprehensive teacher development. To achieve this, several initiatives are essential.

Revitalizing Nigeria's Educational... (Aliyu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611060>

Curriculum reform should prioritize 21st-century skills, including critical thinking, problem-solving, and digital literacy. This involves reviewing and updating curriculum content to reflect contemporary needs (OECD, 2019). Additionally, incorporating diverse perspectives and cultural sensitivity ensures inclusivity.

Teacher development is equally crucial. Teacher training programs focusing on pedagogy, technology integration, and inclusivity enhance instructional effectiveness (UNESCO, 2019). Mentorship programs for new teachers provide valuable support and guidance. Continuous professional development (CPD) requirements ensure teachers stay updated on best practices.

Collaboration with international organizations facilitates knowledge sharing and adoption of best practices. Partnering with organizations like UNESCO, OECD, and the World Bank provides access to global expertise and research (World Bank, 2018).

Research supports the effectiveness of these initiatives:

1. Curriculum reform improves student outcomes and preparedness for the workforce (OECD, 2019).
2. Teacher training programs enhance teacher confidence and instructional quality (UNESCO, 2019).
3. Mentorship programs reduce teacher attrition and improve new teacher performance.

Implementing these curriculum reform and teacher development initiatives enhances education quality, equipping students with 21st-century skills and teachers with effective instructional strategies.

Infrastructure Development and Digital Education

Effective education systems require robust infrastructure and digital education solutions. To achieve this, several initiatives are essential.

Infrastructure development can be accelerated through Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs), enabling the construction and maintenance of modern school facilities (World Bank, 2018). Solar-powered schools in rural areas ensure reliable energy access, bridging the infrastructure gap.

Digital education platforms provide remote learning opportunities, expanding access to quality education (UNESCO, 2019). E-libraries and digital resource centers offer students and teachers diverse educational materials. National Education Management Information Systems (NEMIS) facilitate data-driven decision-making, enhancing education policy and planning. Research highlights the benefits of these initiatives:

1. PPPs improve infrastructure quality and sustainability (World Bank, 2018).
2. Digital education platforms increase access and engagement (UNESCO, 2019).
3. Solar-powered schools reduce energy costs and environmental impact.
4. NEMIS enables informed decision-making and education policy development.

Implementing these infrastructure development and digital education initiatives enhances education access, quality, and efficiency.

Innovative Policy Framework for Education Reform

Effective education reform requires a multifaceted approach. To achieve this, several key initiatives can be implemented:

1. Establish a National Education Commission: Oversee reforms, ensuring coherence and sustainability. This commission would advise the President on education policy, as outlined in the Education Reform Act.
2. Dedicate 15% of National Budget to Education: Ensure sufficient funding for education initiatives, aligning with global recommendations.
3. Performance-Based Funding for Schools: Incentivize excellence, allocating resources based on school performance and needs.
4. Community Participation in School Management: Foster local engagement, encouraging community involvement in school decision-making processes.
5. Partnerships with Private Sector for Education Innovation: Leverage expertise and resources from private organizations to drive innovation in education, as envisioned in the Nigeria ICT Innovation and Entrepreneurship Vision.
6. These initiatives align with existing policies, including the National Digital Learning Policy and the National Policy on Science and Technology Education. Implementing these policies enhances education quality, accessibility, and relevance.

Implementation Strategies for Effective Education Reform

Successful education reform requires thoughtful implementation. Key strategies include:

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1. Phased Implementation: A 5-year rollout enables gradual integration, minimizing disruption and allowing for adaptive adjustments (Fullan, 2016).
2. Capacity Building: Professional development for educators and administrators ensures effective reform execution (OECD, 2019). Training programs enhance instructional leadership, pedagogical skills, and change management.
3. Monitoring and Evaluation Framework: Regular assessment informs policy refinement, measuring progress against benchmarks (UNESCO, 2019). Data-driven decision-making fosters accountability and effectiveness.
4. Stakeholder Engagement and Sensitization: Collaborative involvement of educators, administrators, policymakers, and communities ensures ownership and support (World Bank, 2018). Sensitization campaigns promote reform understanding and buy-in.
5. Continuous Review and Adjustment: Ongoing evaluation and adaptation enable responsiveness to emerging challenges and opportunities (Elmore, 2004).
6. Effective implementation requires attention to these interconnected strategies, fostering a culture of continuous improvement.

Expected Outcomes of Education Reform

Education reform initiatives can have a transformative impact on individuals, communities, and nations. The expected outcomes of these efforts include:

1. Increased Access to Quality Education: Ensuring that all children have access to free and compulsory primary education, regardless of their background or socioeconomic status
2. Improved Teacher Quality and Morale: Enhancing teacher training programs, pedagogical skills, and instructional leadership to foster a supportive learning environment
3. Enhanced Digital Literacy: Integrating technology into education to equip students with essential skills for the digital age.
4. Reduced Disparities and Inequalities: Addressing systemic barriers and biases to create a more inclusive education system.
5. Better Education Outcomes and National Development: Improving learning outcomes, student performance, and national competitiveness through effective education policies.
6. These outcomes are interconnected and mutually reinforcing. For instance, improved teacher quality can lead to better education outcomes, which in turn contribute to national development³. Similarly, enhanced digital literacy can increase access to quality education and reduce disparities.
7. By focusing on these expected outcomes, education reform initiatives can drive meaningful change and create a brighter future for individuals and societies.

Recommendations

1. Policymakers should prioritize education investment, teacher development, and infrastructure upgrade.
2. Stakeholders should promote inclusive education and community participation.
3. International partnerships can facilitate knowledge sharing and capacity building.

Conclusion

This study examined the challenges facing Nigeria's educational system and proposed innovative policies for revitalization. The findings highlight the need for comprehensive reforms addressing access, equity, quality, and infrastructure. Key challenges include outdated curriculum, inadequate teacher training, and poor infrastructure.

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Correlation between Piagetian and Vygotsky's Theories Informed Strategies on Performance and Retention in Number Sense among Pupils in Katsina State

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Abstract

This study compared correlation between Piagetian and Vygotsky's theories informed strategies on performance and retention in number sense among pupils in Katsina state. The study employed quasi experimental pretest posttest non-randomized control group design, in which a total of 387 primary three pupils were selected from eight experimental (8) primary schools in eight zones of Katsina State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB) using multi-stage sampling technique. The study used a 25 multiple choice items Primary Three Number Sense Performance Test (PTNSPT) and its shuffled version for data collection. The instruments were validated by experts in Mathematics Education and Test and Measurement. The reliability of the instruments was estimated using test - retest method and reliability index obtained was 0.78 and 0.80 were calculated by the use of Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while independent samples t-test was used to test null hypotheses. The analyses were done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) at 0.05 level of significance. Findings from the study showed that; pupils taught using Piagetian approach outperformed those taught using Vygotsky's theory informed teaching, retention of pupils taught using the two approaches was similar, performance of male and female pupils taught using PTIT were gender balanced and female pupils taught using VTIT outperformed their male counterparts in retention. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that; primary school teachers in experimental schools of the study need to sustain the tempo, share and maintain the strategies of the two approaches as outcomes showed improved performance and retention and professional bodies like Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN), Mathematics Panel of Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) and journals in tertiary institutions may promote the approaches (PTIT & VTIT) in conferences, workshops and publication in their journals.

Keywords: Piagetian theory informed strategy, Vygotsky's theory informed strategy, Performance, Retention, Gender

Introduction

Primary education is the education given to learners usually from 6 to 12 years of age and is the key building block for children's future education as it provides them with the basic knowledge and skills. This level of education fosters or hampers a love of learning, encourages or douses curiosity, prepares children for future academic challenges and is the foundation of a child's educational journey. It gives the child the first impression of core subjects (which include mathematics) and plays a vital role in the formation of the child's overall development. At this level of educational pursuit, children develop their attitudes to learning and form their basic social-emotional competencies.

Mathematics is a fundamental subject that plays a crucial role in shaping a child's cognitive development as it lays the foundation for higher-level Math and science and critical thinking skills essential for success in any field. In primary school, pupils are introduced to basic mathematical concepts, numbers, operations, geometry, and measurement. Mathematics is important in primary school because it is used in everyday activities and provides students with the tools to effectively navigate new situations. In addition, it helps develop students' thinking skills and plays a crucial role in mastering theoretical materials. Math helps learners to understand and engage with the world, from everyday tasks such as managing money and following recipes to analyzing data and solving problems. A strong foundation in math will better prepare students for success in these subjects.

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The importance attached to mathematics in school curriculum at all levels of education system accurately reflects the role of the subject in society as asserted by Gravemeijer, Stephen, Julie, Lin and Ohtani (2017) that in a world that is changing rapidly under the influence of informatisation, automatization, digitization, and globalization; effective teaching of mathematics becomes imperative to facilitate acquisition of 21st century skills. Similarly, Thomas (2018) submitted that mathematics is so important to the extent that without its knowledge there may be no development in Nigeria. However, in spite of the importance of primary education, its quality in general and that of mathematics at primary level in particular falls short of being satisfactory regarding pupils' performance which invariably adversely affects learners' retention and heighten anxiety towards the subject. Despite the importance of mathematics in the Nigerian educational system and national development, the academic performance of learners in Mathematics at national examinations has been lackluster (Makondo & Makondo, 2020). The results of external examinations have been unimpressive, specifically in the Ilorin West Local Government Area of Kwara State in 2019. Out of the 13,062 pupils who registered for the Kwara State Common entrance examination in the local government area, only 4,781 (36.6%) had 50 marks or higher in Mathematics, while 8,281 (63.4%) had less than 50 marks (Obafemi. *et. al.*, 2023)

Piaget's theory stresses the need for prioritising learning through experience instead of memorising information. Educators should challenge children's knowledge by exposing them to new experiences and information while also keeping in mind that these challenges should be matched to children's individual abilities. The difficulty level of activities and challenges should be matched to children's current ability to understand the world. On the other hand, Vygotsky, a Russian psychologist, developed a theory of cognitive development known as the Sociocultural Theory of Cognitive Development in the early twentieth century. The main assertion of the Vygotsky theory is that the cognitive development of children is advanced through social interaction with other people, particularly those who are more skilled. In other words, Vygotsky believed that social learning comes before cognitive development, and that children construct knowledge actively.

Williams (2018) sees performance more as an aggregate of several factors that indicate a student's success. Pupils' performance in mathematics leaves much to be desired. Regarding gender, Newman (2018) refers to it as the role of a male or female in society, or an individual's concept of themselves. Samuelsson & Samuelsson (2016) in research highlighted a traditional gender gap in favour of boys.

Models and instructional strategies (of learning) are designed to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of teachers in the discharge of their duties aiming to impact on pupils' learning. The groundbreaking work of Hattie (2017) gave the effect sizes of Piagetian and Vygotsky's approaches as 1.28 and 0.84 against a mean of 0.44. This study compared the effects Piagetian (PTIT) and Vygotsky's theories informed teaching (VTIT) on performance and retention in number sense concepts among primary three pupils in Katsina state in the continuous search for instructional strategies to improve pupils' outcomes. Hence, the following objectives.

Objectives of the Study

The study was guided by the following objectives:

1. Compare the effects of Piagetian and Vygotskian theories informed teaching on performance in number sense concept among pupils in Katsina state.
2. Match the effects of Piagetian and Vygotskian theories informed teaching on retention in number sense concept among pupils in Katsina state.
3. Determine whether the effects of Piagetian theory informed teaching (PTIT) on performance in number sense concept is balanced regarding gender among pupils in Katsina state.
4. Examine gender sensitivity of the effects Vygotsky's theory informed teaching (VTIT) on retention in number sense concept among pupils in Katsina state.

Research Questions

The study posed the following questions for answers:

1. Are there differences in performance in number sense concept of pupils taught using Piagetian and Vygotskian theories informed teaching in Katsina state?
2. Does difference exist in retention in number sense concept of pupils taught using Piagetian and Vygotskian theories informed teaching in Katsina state?

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3. What is the difference in performance in number sense concept among male and female pupils taught using Piagetian theory informed teaching in Katsina state?
4. Is there difference in retention regarding gender in number sense concept among pupils taught using Vygotsky’s theory informed teaching in Katsina state?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for testing at $p \leq 0.05$.

5. **H₀₁**: There is no significant difference in performance in number sense concept of pupils taught using Piagetian and Vygotskian theories informed teaching in Katsina state.
6. **H₀₂**: There is no significant difference in retention in number sense concept of pupils taught taught using Piagetian and Vygotskian theories informed teaching in Katsina state.
7. **H₀₃**: There is no significant difference in performance in number sense concept of male and female pupils taught using Piagetian theory informed teaching in Katsina state.
8. **H₀₄**: There is no significant difference in retention regarding gender in number sense concept of pupils taught using Vygotsky’s theory informed teaching in Katsina state.

Methodology

The study compared the correlation of Piagetian and Vygotsky’s theories informed strategies on performance and retention in number sense concepts among primary three pupils in Katsina state. It employed quasi experimental pretest posttest non-randomized control group design. From a population of 430,190 primary three pupils comprising 201,164 males and 229,026 female pupils a sample of 387 pupils (207 – 91 males & 116 females and 180 – 78 males and 102 females taught using Piagetian and Vygotsky’s theories informed teaching respectively). The sample was selected from eight (8) experimental schools in eight educational zones of State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB). A 25 items multiple choice Primary Three Number Sense Achievement Test (PTNSAT) and its shuffled version were used to collect data on performance and retention. Both instruments were validated by experts in mathematics education and psychology. Reliability coefficients of both were computed and found to be 0.78 and 0.80 respectively. Treatment was administered where one experimental group was taught using Piagetian and the other taught using Vygotsky’s theory informed teaching for a period of eight weeks. Posttest was administered to determine performance and within two weeks interval, post-posttest was administered to measure retention. Thereafter responses were marked and sorted for analysis. Data was analysed with the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 using outcomes of 381 pupils present at the time of data collection. Research questions were presented using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation while independent samples t-test was employed in the analysis of null hypotheses at the fixed probability level of $P \leq 0.05$.

Presentation of Results

The results of the study were obtained from research questions answered and hypotheses tested through analysis of test and retention scores of 381 pupils present at the time of data collection. Student independent samples t-test statistic was employed for the analysis.

Research Question 1

Are there differences in performance in number sense concept of pupils taught using Piagetian and Vygotskian theories informed teaching in Katsina state?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on Performance of PTIT and VTIT Groups

Group	N	Mean	SD	Std. Error	Mean Diff.
PTIT	207	18.75	3.34	0.238	3.44
VTIT	184	15.31	4.20	0.310	

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Total **381** **34.06** **7.54** **0.548**

Source: study data collected

Table 1 shows the means and standard deviations of pupils' performance in number sense concept in PTIT and VTIT groups. The result showed PTIT group had 18.75 & 3.34 and VTIT group obtained 15.31 & 4.20 as mean scores and standard deviations respectively. Clearly the mean scores and S. Ds are different. To ascertain the statistical significance of the difference, independent samples t-test analysis was carried out.

Null Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in performance in number sense concept of pupils taught using Piagetian and Vygotskian theories informed teaching in Katsina state. The summary of the t-test for the groups is given in Table 2

Table 2: Summary of Independent t-test on Performance Scores of PTIT and VTIT Groups

Group	N	Mean	SD	DF	T	P	Decision
PTIT	207	18.75	3.34	379	8.863	.000	Sig.
VTIT	184	15.31	4.20				
Total	381	33.72	6.135				

Source: study data collected

From the results of Table 2, t-value of 8.863 and p-value of 0.000 were observed at the degree of freedom of 379. The p-value obtained was 0.000 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$. This showed there was significant difference in performance of pupils taught using PTIT and VTIT. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected and it was concluded that there was significant difference in favour of pupils taught using PTIT.

Research Question 2: Does difference exist in retention in number sense concept of pupils taught using Piagetian and Vygotskian theories informed teaching in Katsina state?

Descriptive statistics on retention of pupils taught using PTIT and VTIT was considered, summary of the results is presented in Table 3

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics on Retention of PTIT and VTIT Groups

Group	N	Mean	SD	Std. Error	Mean Diff.
PTIT	207	18.73	3.29	0.235	0.50
VTIT	184	18.23	4.03	0.297	
Total	381	36.96	7.32	0.532	

Source: study data collected

Table 3 shows the means and standard deviations of pupils' retention in number sense concept in PTIT and VTIT groups. The result showed PTIT group had 18.73 & 3.29 and VTIT group obtained 18.23 & 4.03 as mean scores and standard deviations respectively. Clearly the mean scores are similar. To ascertain the statistical significance of the difference, independent samples t-test analysis was carried out.

Null Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in retention in number sense concept of pupils taught using Piagetian and Vygotsky's theories informed teaching in Katsina state. The summary of the t-test for the groups is given in Table 4

Table 4: Summary of Independent t-test on Retention Scores of PTIT and VTIT Groups

Group	N	Mean	SD	DF	T	P	Decision
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PTIT	207	18.75	3.29	379	1.324	.186	Not Sig.
VTIT	184	18.23	4.03				
Total	381	33.72	6.135				

Source: study data collected

From the results of Table 4, t-value of 1.324 and p-value of 0.186 were observed at the degree of freedom of 379. The p-value obtained was 0.186 which is greater than $\alpha = 0.05$. This showed there was no significant difference in retention of pupils taught using PTIT and VTIT. Thus, the null hypothesis was retained and it was concluded that there was no significant difference between pupils taught using PTIT and VITT groups.

Research Question 3: What is the difference in performance in number sense concept among male and female pupils taught using Piagetian theory informed teaching in Katsina state?

Descriptive statistics on performance of male and female pupils taught using PTIT was considered, summary of the results is presented in Table 5

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics on Performance of Male and Female Taught Using PTIT

Group	N	Mean	SD	Std. Error	Mean Diff.
Male	91	18.32	3.75	0.393	0.11
Female	116	18.21	3.95	0.367	
Total	207	36.53	7.70	0.760	

Source: study data collected

Table 5 shows the means and standard deviations of male and female pupils' performance in number sense concept taught using PTIT. The result showed male pupils had 18.32 & 3.75 and females obtained 18.21 & 3.95 as mean scores and standard deviations respectively. Clearly the mean scores are similar. To ascertain the statistical significance of the difference, independent samples t-test analysis was carried out.

Null Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference in performance in number sense concept of male and female pupils taught using Piagetian theory informed teaching in Katsina state.

The summary of the independent samples t-test for the groups is given in Table 6

Table 6: Summary of Independent t-test on Performance of Male and Female Pupils Taught Using PTIT

Group	N	Mean	SD	DF	T	P	Decision
Male	91	18.32	3.75	205	-0.207	.836	Not Sig.
Female	116	18.21	3.95				
Total	207	36.53	7.70				

Source: study data collected

From the results of Table 6, t-value of -0.207 and p-value of 0.836 were observed at the degree of freedom of 205. The p-value obtained was 0.836 which is greater than $\alpha = 0.05$. This showed there was no significant difference in performance of male and female pupils taught using PTIT. The null hypothesis was retained and it was concluded that there was no significant difference between male and female pupils taught using PTIT.

Research Question 4: What is the difference in retention in number sense concept among male and female pupils taught using Vygotsky's theory informed teaching in Katsina state?

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Descriptive statistics on retention of male and female pupils taught using VTIT was considered, summary of the results is presented in Table 7

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics on Retention of Male and Female Taught Using VTIT

Group	N	Mean	SD	Std. Error	Mean Diff.
Male	78	17.87	2.64	0.298	0.88
Female	102	18.75	2.61	0.268	
Total	180	36.62	5.25	0.566	

Source: study data collected

Table 7 shows the means and standard deviations of male and female pupils' retention scores in number sense concept taught using VTIT. The result showed male pupils had 17.87 & 2.64 and females obtained 18.75 & 2.61 as mean scores and standard deviations respectively. Clearly the mean scores are not much different. To ascertain the statistical significance of the difference, independent samples t-test analysis was carried out.

Null Hypothesis Four: There is no significant difference in retention in number sense concept of male and female pupils taught using Vygotsky's theory informed teaching in Katsina state.

The summary of the independent samples t-test for the groups is given in Table 8

Table 8: Summary of Independent t-test on Retention of Male and Female Pupils Taught Using VTIT

Group	N	Mean	SD	DF	T	P	Decision
Male	78	17.87	2.64	205	-2.218	0.028	Sig.
Female	102	18.75	2.61				
Total	207	36.62	5.25				

Source: study data collected

From the results of Table 8, t-value of -2.218 and p-value of 0.028 were observed at the degree of freedom of 205. The p-value obtained was 0.028 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$. This showed there was significant difference in retention of male and female pupils taught using VTIT. The null hypothesis was rejected and it was concluded that there was significant difference between and female pupils outperformed their male counterparts among in the group taught using VTIT.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the analysis of data regarding null hypothesis one indicated in Table 2 showed pupils taught using Piagetian outperformed those taught using Vygotsky's theory informed teaching in performance on number sense concept. This outcome corroborates the work of Hattie (2017) who calculated effect size to determine the efficacy of an intervention or educational practice relative to a comparison (mean of 0.44). The effect size of Piagetian approach is 1.28 and discussion and scaffolding (Vygotsky's approach) is 0.82. However, Lindvall, Helnius, Eriksson and Ryve (2021) in research on 'Examining the Effects of a National-Scale Teacher Professional Development (PD) Programme on Instructional Practices and Students' Mathematics Achievement' reported a small but statistical significant impact on teachers' instructional practices with no effect found on student achievement.

Analysis of the second null hypothesis revealed that retention of pupils taught using Piagetian and Vygotsky's theories informed teaching in number sense concepts was similar. This finding supports Fernández-Cézar, Garrido and Solano-Pinto (2020) in a study on the effect of a STEM experimentation outreach programme on 5th and 6th graders reported that program effect was not associated with learners' gender. Also, Gholami, Mohd-Ayub, Yunus and Kamarudin (2021) in a study on Impact of Lesson Study (LS) on Mathematics Anxiety and Mathematics Achievement of Malaysian Foundation Programme Students' reported no statistically significant interaction between the effects of educational method and gender on both mathematics anxiety and achievement.

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Outcome of third null hypothesis reported performance of male and female pupils taught using Piagetian theory informed teaching in number sense concepts was gender balanced. The study of Ghasemi, Burley and Safadel (2019) who did a study on Gender Differences in General Achievement in Mathematics: An International Study, revealed no statistically significant differences observed when the achievements of girls and boys in mathematics were compared. On the contrary, Oluyemo, Musbahu, Kukwil, Anikweze and Shaluko (2020) in a study on Gender Differences in Mathematics Interest and Achievement in Junior Secondary School Students, Niger State, revealed male students excelled in mathematics achievement more than their female counterparts and there was significant difference between their mean achievements.

The fourth null hypothesis testing found female pupils taught using Vygotsky's theory informed teaching in number sense concepts outperformed their male counterparts in retention. In different stroke, Obi, Agwagah, Newen and Nwoye (2017) in their study on Checkmating Gender Differentials in Pupils' Achievement and Retention found no significant difference in male and female retention in fraction while Oluyemo, Musbahu, Kukwil, Anikweze and Shaluko (2020) in a study on Gender Differences in Mathematics Achievement in Niger State revealed that male students excel in mathematics achievement more than their female counterparts.

Conclusion

The outcome of the study indicated that pupils taught using Piagetian approach outperformed those taught using Vygotsky's theory informed teaching, retention of pupils taught using the two approaches was similar, performance of male and female pupils taught using PTIT were gender balanced and female pupils taught using VTIT outperformed their male counterparts in retention.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Primary school teachers in experimental schools of the study need to sustain the tempo, share and maintain the strategies of the two approaches as outcomes showed improved performance and retention.
2. The teaching of mathematics requires competent and experienced teachers, as such State Universal Education Board/Private School Owners are required to employ, retain and incentivize competent teachers.
3. Professional bodies like Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN), Mathematics Panel of Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) and journals in tertiary institutions may promote the approaches (PTIT & VTIT) in conferences, workshops and publication in their journals.

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Assessment of Impact of ... (Akinbobola, & Adewumi, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611068>

Assessment on Impact of Social-Media-Platforms on Examination Malpractice among Secondary School Science Students in Ido/Osi Local Government Area, Ekiti State

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of social media platforms on examination malpractices among secondary school science students in Ido/Osi Local Government Area, Ekiti State. The population of the study consists of all senior secondary school science students in Ido/Osi Local Government Area of Ekiti State during the 2023/2024 academic session. 200 students were selected using multi-stage sampling technique from the targeted population. Three research questions were formulated to guide the study. A well-developed questionnaire was used to obtain information from the respondents. The reliability of the instrument was obtained with test-retest approach using Pearson product moment correlation and the reliability coefficient was 0.85. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics (frequency count, percentage and mean). Findings revealed that, secondary school science students have varied perceptions on the impact of social media on examination malpractices regarding their awareness, beliefs and personal experiences. Findings further reveal that social media platforms contributed to prevalent of examination malpractices such as cheating, collusion, stealing, impersonation, alteration, and disorderliness of candidate at examination hall in secondary schools. Study revealed that, the commonly used social platforms among students are Whatsapp, Instagram, Telegram, X and Facebook. In conclusion, the study revealed a diverse spectrum of perceptions among secondary school science students concerning the influence of social media on examination malpractices. Among others, it was recommended that, school management should develop and implement educational campaigns targeted at raising awareness among secondary school science students about the ethical implications and consequences of engaging in examination malpractices through social media platforms.

Keywords: Social Media, Examination Malpractices, Perceptions, Science Students

Introduction

Examination Malpractices encompass a wide range of improper behaviours carried out by students during examination aiming to manipulate their examination scores or deceive evaluators. These malpractices could include bringing unauthorized electronic devices into the examination hall, collusion or collaboration among students to show answers, impersonation, or altering examinations scripts (Nkwo, Mbotto & Akinbobola, 2006). These actions undermine the fairness and credibility of assessments. Characteristics of examination malpractice students include: students being unstable, mobile and highly tensed, anxiety, fears, unfanatic movement and unsteady eyeballs that portray them as potential cheats; unusual movements of parents, mercenaries and unauthorized persons around the examination premises may signal some warnings; unusual attachment to each other as in talking and intimately walking together prior examinations may indicate the tendency for irregularities, inordinate financial bribe examination personnel; unusual wear of over-sized dresses with large number of pockets to conceal foreign materials; wearing of very short skirts by girls to enable them easily read notes and formulae written on their thighs, laps, handkerchiefs, currency notes, and possibly smartphones with which answers to leak examination questions may be communicated (Denga & Denga, 1998 cited in Nkwo, Mbotto & Akinbobola, 2006). Acai & Lee (2019) define examination malpractices as the examinations not conduct in accordance with specified norms set up by the examining institution or body. Nkwo, Mbotto and Akinbobola (2006). state that, examination malpractices involves the various methods employed by candidates to cheat before or during examination.

With the advent of advanced technologies and increased access to the internet, students have more opportunities to engage in dishonest behaviours during examinations. Students resort to various tactics such as using smartphones to access unauthorized information, sharing answers through science messaging apps, and collaborating during online science subjects examinations (Akinbobola, 2019).

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The case of communication and access to information via digital science platforms has made imperative for educational institutions to implement robust strategies to detect and prevent examination malpractices (Brown & Lee, 2019). The impact of examination malpractices extends beyond the immediate context affecting the credibility of educational systems and diminishing the value of academic qualifications. It was observed that, students generally have difficulty in understanding mathematics and science subject's curriculum and this perhaps account for their consistent examination malpractices in the subjects in Senior School Certificates Examination (Ado, Akinbobola & Ugbe, 2006). Most students find science, especially mathematics difficult and unpalatable due to false impression about the difficulties in science subjects and the perhaps account for the reasons why students embark on cheating during examinations (Ado, Akinbobola & Inyang, 2006). Ezekannagha (2000) observed that, many Nigerian students see science subjects they study in schools as abstract, involving symbols and formulae. Ezekannagha explained further that, the students lack the ability to appreciate concepts taught in school and their relevance in the explanation of things and activities within environment. To tackle the issue of examination malpractices effectively, it is essential to understand the underlying psychological factors that drive students to cheat.

Fear of failure, intense competition, and pressure to achieve high grades has been identified as key motivators for academic dishonesty (Johnson, 2019). Moreover, a study by Wang, Chen and Li (2019) found that, cultural factors for academic success can contribute significantly to cheating behaviour among students. Technological advancement offers both challenges and opportunities in combating examination malpractices, while technology facilitates cheating in science, it also provides potential solutions. Anti – cheating science software on examination platforms have emerged as tools to detect and defer cheating attempt (Miller, Turner & Simmons, 2019).

In recent years, social media has become an integrated part of modern society providing an interconnected platform for communication and information sharing and also facilitate academic dishonesty particularly during science examination. Social media platforms enable students to share and exchange examination related materials, such as leaked question paper solutions to ongoing science examination. This ease of access to confidential information raises concerns about the integrity of examinations (Johnson, 2018). For example, an investigation in India found that the WhatsApp groups were being used to distribute leaked examination papers, leading to widespread cheating (BBC News, 2017).

Social media allow students to communicate in real-time regardless of geographical locations (Akinbobola & Asagha, 2015). During examination, this facilitates instant exchange of information, enabling students to share scientific formulae, answers and ask for help discreetly. Platforms like Facebook, Messenger or direct messages on twitter are difficult to monitor, making it challenging for educational institutions to direct cheating incidents promptly (Severance, Cikijewskic & Yen, 2019). Various social media group forums have emerged where students can seek and provide assistance with science examination preparation while some groups foster healthy discussions and knowledge sharing, others may transform into scientific platforms for examination cheating. Science students might request or receive detailed answers to examination questions, undermining the assessments fairness and academic standard (Folthynek & Kralik, 2020)

With advancement in technology of social media platforms, the integration of social media into institution of learning makes detection even more challenging (Salman, Shalan, Mahmood, & Khan, 2020). Social media also provides a platform for essay mills and contract cheating services to advertise their offerings, connecting students with third- party individuals willing to complete assignments and examinations on their behalf (Lancaster & Cotarlan, 2018). These services exploit the anonymity of social media to operate covertly, further complicating the efforts to combat academic dishonesty. Social media undoubtedly plays a significant role in facilitating cheating during examination among science students. It ease to access real-time communication, and wide-ranging connections make it an attractive avenue for dishonest practices.

Examination malpractices among secondary school science students have become prevalent, and it is essential to understand students' perceptions regarding the impact of social media platforms on this issue. Social media has rapidly gained popularity among science students and there is a need to investigate how these platforms contribute to, enable or facilitate examination malpractices. By exploring student's perspectives on the relationship between social media and examination malpractices, this study aimed to provide valuable insights into the role and influence of these platforms in promoting unethical conduct during examinations among secondary school science students. Understanding these perceptions is crucial for developing effective measures, interventions and policies to mitigate the negative impact of social media on academic integrity.

Objective of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the student's perceptions on the impact of social media platforms on examination malpractices among secondary school science students. Specifically, the study tends;

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1. To investigate the level of awareness among secondary school science students about the impact of social media platforms on examination malpractices.
2. To investigate the types of examination malpractices that are prevalent among secondary school students and the extent to which social media platforms contribute to these malpractices
3. To identify the different social media platforms that is commonly used by secondary school science students for engaging in examination malpractices.

Research Questions

Three research questions were raised to guide the study.

1. What is the level of awareness among the secondary school science students about the impact social media platforms on examination malpractices?
2. What are the type of examination malpractices that are prevalent among secondary school science students and the extent to which social media platforms contribute to these malpractices?
3. What are the different social media platforms that are commonly used by secondary school science students for engaging in examination malpractices?

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of this study consisted all senior secondary school science students of Ido/Osi Local Government Area, Ekiti State, Nigeria. Multistage sampling technique was used for the study. Five co-educational schools were selected through simple random technique. Forty (40) students each was chosen from five randomly selected secondary schools in Ido/Osi Local Government Area of Ekiti State.

The research instrument used for collection of data was a self- constructed questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into 2 Section; Section A and B. Section A consisted of information on bio-data of the respondents while the Section B was divided into parts with items from each part addressing the stated research questions. A 4 –point Likert type rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA)= 4, Agree (A)=3. Disagree (D)=2 and Strongly Disagree (SD)=1 was used. Each of the respondent picked the items as applicable. The research instrument was validated using face and content validity with the help of two (2) experts in the test, measurement and evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was obtained with test-retest approach using Pearson product moment correlation and the reliability coefficient was 0.85. The researcher took permission from the principals and through them, got in touch with the science teachers and students in the schools for the administration of the questionnaire. The data collected were analysed using frequency count, percentage and mean.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

What is the level of awareness among secondary school science students about the impact of social media platforms on examination malpractices?

Table 1: The level of awareness among secondary school science students about the impact of social media platforms on examination malpractices

S/N	Level of Awareness	SA	A	D	SD	Mean $\bar{(x)}$	Decision
1	I have been educated about the negative effect of social media on examination malpractices	60 (30.0)	76 (38.0)	36 (18.0)	28 (14.0)	2.84	Accepted
2	I think most students are aware of how social media can lead to examination malpractices	79 (39.5)	54 (27.0)	45 (22.5)	22 (11.0)	2.95	Accepted
3	I feel well informed regarding the impact of social media on examination cheating	44 (22.0)	69 (34.5)	41 (20.5)	46 (23.0)	2.56	Accepted
4	I pay attention to information about the relationship between social media and examination malpractices	68 (34.0)	65 (32.5)	33 (16.5)	34 (17.0)	2.84	Accepted

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5	I have personally witness or experienced examination malpractices facilitated by social media platforms	78 (39.0)	48 (24.0)	48 (24.0)	26 (13.0)	2.89	Accepted
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Weighted Average = 2.82; Benchmark = 2.50

Table 1 shows the level of awareness among secondary school science students about the impact of social media platforms on examination malpractices. The table shows that, most science students (68.0%) have been educated about negative effect of social media on examination malpractices (2.84). Also, some of the respondents (66.5%) pay attention to the information about the relationship between social media and examination malpractices (2.95). The table also shows that, some of the respondents (56.5% are well-informed regarding the impact of social media on examination cheating (2.56). The table also shows that, most students (66.5%) are aware of how the use the use of social media can lead to examination malpractices (2.95). Also, most students (63%) personally witness or experienced examination malpractices facilitated by social media platforms (2.89). Since the weighted average of 2.82 as shown in Table 1 is greater than the benchmark of 2.50, it can be concluded that, level of awareness among secondary school students about the impact of social media platforms on examination malpractices is high, that is, they perceived the impact of social media on examination malpractices.

Research Question 2

What are the type of examination malpractices that are prevalent among secondary school science students and the extent to which social media platforms contribute to these malpractices?

Table 2: The type of examination malpractices that is prevalent among secondary school students and the extent to which social media platforms contribute to these malpractices

S/N	Prevalent Examination Malpractices	SA	A	D	SD	Mean \bar{x}	Decision
1	Cheating in examination is common among science students in my school	61 (30.5)	57 (28.5)	65 (32.9)	17 (8.50)	2.81	Accepted
2	I belief that social media platforms are major contributor to examination malpractices	61 (30.0)	102 (51.0)	32 (16.0)	6 (3.0)	3.08	Accepted
3	Students in my school often use social media to share examination related information	83 (41.5)	64 (32)	38 (19)	15 (7.5)	3.08	Accepted
4	Social media make it easier for students to engage in cheating during examination	90 (45)	83 (41.5)	18 (9.0)	9 (4.5)	3.27	Accepted
Weighted Average						3.06	

Benchmark = 2.50

Table 2 shows the perception on types of examination malpractices that is prevalent among secondary school students and the extent to which social media platforms contribute to the practices. The table shows that, cheating in examinations is common among science students (2.81); social media platforms are the major contributor to examination malpractices (3.08); the science students in school often use social media to share examination related information (3.08); and social media makes it easier for students to engage in cheating during examinations (3.27). Meanwhile, since the weighted average as shown in Table 3 is 3.06 which is greater than the benchmark of 2.50, it can be concluded that, social media platform is the type of examination malpractices that is prevalent among secondary school science students.

Research Question 3

What are the different social media platforms that are commonly used by secondary school science students for engaging in examination malpractices?

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Table 3: The different social media platforms that are commonly used by secondary school science students for engaging in examination malpractices

S/N	Commonly Used Social Media Platforms	SA	A	D	SD	Mean $\bar{(x)}$	Decision
1	Students often use WhatsApp for sharing examination related content	118 (59.0)	56 (28.0)	3 (1.5)	23 (11.5)	3.35	Accepted
2	Facebook is commonly used for cheating during examinations	60 (30.0)	49 (24.5)	32 (16.0)	59 (29.5)	2.55	Accepted
3	Instagram is a popular platform for examination malpractices	51 (25.5)	74 (37.0)	37 (18.5)	38 (19.0)	2.69	Accepted
4	I have observed students using telegram sharing examination answers	45 (22.5)	87 (43.5)	51 (25.5)	17 (8.5)	2.80	Accepted
5	Twitter is frequently used by students for discussing examination	50 (25.0)	69 (34.5)	46 (23.0)	35 (34.50)	2.67 (17.5)	Accepted

Weighted Average = 2.81; Benchmark = 2.50

Table 3 shows the perception of students on different social media platforms that are commonly used by secondary school science students. The table shows that, majority of the respondents agreed that, WhatsApp is most widely used platforms for sharing examination related content among secondary school science students (3.35). Also, Facebook is commonly used for cheating (2.55), Instagram is a popular platform used for examination malpractices (2.69), and Telegram is also good for sharing examination answers (2.80). Some of the respondents also indicate that, students frequently use twitter (2.67). Meanwhile, since the weighted average shown in the Table 3 is 2.81 which is greater than the benchmark of 2.50, it can therefore be concluded that, different social media platforms are commonly used by secondary school science students for engaging in examination malpractices.

Discussion

Findings from research questions revealed that, some science students have been educated about the negative effects of social media on examination malpractices. This is in agreement with the findings of Bown and Lee (2019), and Akinbobola (2019) that, the case of communication and access to information via digital science platforms has made imperative for educational institutions to implement robust strategies to detect and prevent examination malpractices. Also, the impact of examination malpractices extends beyond the immediate context affecting the credibility of educational systems and diminishing the value of academic qualifications. The findings indicate a mixed landscape of understanding and perception among the students. A notable percentage of students express awareness and concern about the negative effects of social media in the context of examination integrity (Johnson, 2019; Severance Cikijewskic & Yen, 2019). Provides a detailed overview that platforms like WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Telegram and Twitter are being actively used by students for activities that compromise the fairness and credibility of examinations. However, it also important to acknowledge that, there are some students who either disagree with or strongly disagree with statements related to their education and personal experiences with examination malpractices facilitated by social media. This divergence in opinions and experiences heights the need for a comprehensive and uniform approach for educating students about the risks and consequences of using social media for noticed purpose during examinations.

Conclusion

The study reveals a diverse spectrum of perceptions among secondary school science students concerning the influence of social media on examination malpractices. A notable portion of respondents exhibit strong agreement regarding the prevalence of cheating, collusion, stealing, impersonation, leakage and alteration, and the impact of social media platforms on examination malpractices among secondary school science students. WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Telegram and Twitter emerge as prominent platforms utilized for such malpractices, highlighting the multifaceted nature of students' engagement in unethical behaviours. These findings underscore the pressing need for proactive measures and educational interventions to address the concerns surrounding secondary school science students' involvement in examination malpractices facilitated by social media platforms.

Assessment of Impact of ... (Akinbobola, & Adewumi, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611068>

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. School management should develop and implement educational campaigns targeted at raising awareness among secondary school science students about the ethical implications and consequences of engaging in examination malpractices through social media platforms.
2. Government should integrate digital literacy programmes into the secondary school curriculum to empower students with the necessary skills and knowledge to critically evaluate and responsibly navigate social media platforms.
3. School management and the teachers should promote a culture of academic integrity and ethical conduct within secondary schools through the establishment of clear policies and guidelines governing student's behaviour during examinations.
4. School management should collaborate with parents, guardians and the wider community to reinforce the importance of ethical behaviour and responsible use of social media among secondary school science students.
5. School management should explore alternative assessment methods that will reduce the susceptibility of examination malpractices facilitated by social media platforms.

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Qualitative Study on Social Media Sentiment Analysis for Evidence-Based Policy-Making in Electronic Voting in Nigeria: A Machine Learning Approach

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Abstract

Electronic voting (e-voting) has the potential to improve voter access, reduce logistical issues, and streamline elections. Despite these benefits, challenges related to public trust, security, and transparency hinder its adoption. Social media offers insights into public sentiment and perceptions about e-voting. This study uses social media sentiment analysis to inform evidence-based policymaking, helping to gauge public opinion and identify factors affecting e-voting acceptance. Through a machine learning framework, we analyze social media data to uncover sentiment patterns and their implications for policy. Key findings highlight public concerns regarding data security, voter privacy, and system reliability. Integrating these insights into policy recommendations provides a data-driven approach to address public concerns and foster trust in e-voting, contributing to the fields of sentiment analysis and e-governance and offering valuable guidance for developing secure, transparent, and publicly supported e-voting systems.

Keyword: Electronic voting, sentiment analysis, machine learning, policy-making, social media

Introduction

E-voting systems are increasingly recognized for their potential to enhance accessibility, efficiency, and accuracy in elections. As more nations consider e-voting, understanding public opinion and building trust are crucial for successful implementation. Concerns around security, privacy, and transparency remain primary barriers. Social media, as a platform for public expression, offers real-time insights into public opinion and concerns on these issues. By using natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning to analyze social media sentiment, policymakers gain unfiltered feedback (Thomas 2024), identifying both positive and negative public perceptions of e-voting. This study presents a framework for social media sentiment analysis to support evidence-based policymaking on e-voting. Machine learning techniques are used to evaluate extensive social media data, identifying key concerns and extracting actionable insights. This data-driven approach bridges public opinion and policy, helping to address public concerns in the design, implementation, and regulation of e-voting systems. By integrating sentiment analysis with e-governance and machine learning, this research demonstrates how public sentiment can guide policy on digital innovations like e-voting. The study provides policymakers with insights to develop e-voting systems that are secure, transparent, and publicly trusted, encouraging acceptance and engagement in the democratic process.

Sentiment Analysis

Sentiment Analysis (Opinion Mining) and its application in Nigeria electoral system

Sentiment analysis, also known as opinion mining, is a natural language processing (NLP) technique that identifies the emotional tone of text (Drus. & Khalid, 2019). This method is frequently used by governments, cities, and organizations to

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gauge public opinion on various topics, processes, systems, or services. It combines data mining, machine learning, artificial intelligence, and computational linguistics to detect subjective information, classifying text as conveying a positive, negative, or neutral sentiment. Through real-time data collection, sentiment analysis provides insights into consumer attitudes, experiences, and brand perceptions for specific communities, companies, or regions.

Factors Influencing Technology Adoption of Election in Nigeria electoral system

Several factors influence the adoption of election-related technology, including costs, training, induction requirements, pilot projects, and other logistical considerations (Bisong, 2019). These factors present technical, financial, political, and human resource challenges, often with constitutional and legal implications.

Components of E-Voting and its application in Nigeria electoral system

Electronic voting systems involve more than just technology; they reflect a dynamic relationship between society and information technology. Information systems are both enabled by and enabling ICT within society, emphasizing the mutual influence of these systems and the sociotechnical landscape in which they function (Murat, 2016).

Challenges and Solutions for E-Voting in Nigeria

Despite the potential benefits of e-voting, its implementation in Nigeria faces significant challenges. Key issues include the high costs of establishing e-voting infrastructure and the need for sufficient technical support. Additionally, there are security concerns due to the vulnerability of electronic systems to cyberattacks and hacking. To address these challenges, researchers suggest a phased rollout, beginning with pilot programs that expand incrementally nationwide. E-voting could reduce election fraud, such as ballot stuffing and multiple voting, and enhance voter turnout by allowing voters to cast their ballots from any internet-enabled location (Simon, 2019). However, concerns persist regarding potential technical issues, such as server failures or cyberattacks, which could disrupt voting (Simon, 2019). Cost and unequal access to technology remain obstacles as well (Okonji, 2022).

Feasibility of E-Voting Implementation in Nigeria electoral system

Research by Tunde & Olatunji (2021) highlights that while cost and voter education pose challenges, these can be overcome with strategic planning. Security measures such as encryption and secure login protocols could fortify the system against cyber threats (Simon, 2019).

E-Voting System Structure in Nigeria electoral system

An e-voting system involves three main parties: voters, registration authorities, and tallying authorities. Registration authorities register eligible voters, while tallying authorities oversee vote counting. These components ensure that only registered voters cast ballots and that each vote is counted accurately (Cetinkaya & Cetinkaya, 2007; Emeka et al., 2021). Individually verifiable e-voting systems are secure for private elections but may lack transparency in public settings.

Benefits of E-Voting and its application in Nigeria electoral system

Electronic voting offers accessibility features, such as touch or audio support for voters with disabilities (Bisong, 2019). These systems also reduce costs by minimizing the need for printed ballots and extra poll workers. In addition to faster and more accurate results, e-voting reduces human error and increases election administration efficiency. However, reliance on electronic systems introduces risks, as minor programming errors can impact outcomes.

Practical Evidence of E-Voting and its application in Nigeria electoral system

E-voting can streamline and enhance the accuracy of the voting process. For example, studies have shown that electronic voting can reduce election fraud, simplify voting for those with disabilities, and increase voter turnout among tech-savvy demographics (Kang et al., 2019; Kim & Lee, 2019). However, technology-related issues, such as system malfunctions and the high cost of implementation, present significant challenges. Estonia, a pioneer in e-voting, has consistently achieved high voter turnout and minimal security breaches, demonstrating the potential of e-voting to boost democratic participation (Anichebe, 2016). In Nigeria, e-voting could address issues of voter fraud and boost election credibility. Nevertheless, high equipment costs, security concerns, and the need for voter education pose barriers to implementation (Chima, 2022; El-Said et al., 2018; Ndoh & Nnaeto, 2018).

Nigeria's Current Election Technology

Several African countries are integrating electronic technology into their election processes, including Nigeria, which has faced challenges with partial technological adoption. In 2015 and 2019, Nigeria's Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) introduced the Smart Card Reader for voter accreditation, but its limitations affected election transparency and efficiency (Njideka et al., 2021).

Presidential and National Assembly Elections

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In 2022, INEC introduced the Bimodal Voters Accreditation System (BVAS), a partial e-voting solution for accreditation, yet voting remains manual, with ballot papers still in use. A complete e-voting system would automate voter registration, accreditation, voting, result transmission, and tallying.

State Governorship Elections

During the March 2023 governorship election, BVAS transmitted results electronically but faced logistical issues like ballot box snatching, over-voting, and result tampering. These issues indicate that a fully electronic system could enhance election security and fairness (Oluwasan et al., 2023).

Review of Related Studies

Electoral crises in Nigeria, characterized by violence, voter intimidation, and fraud, have undermined public trust in democracy. E-voting could address these challenges by enhancing voting accuracy, transparency, and accessibility (Daramola & Daren, 2020). Studies show that e-voting systems have successfully improved voter turnout and reduced election costs in several countries (Kim & Lee, 2019; Kang et al., 2019). However, Nigeria's implementation of e-voting will require reliable technology, substantial financial investment, and extensive voter education (Ikechukwu et al., 2022). E-voting systems have the potential to reduce fraud, increase election integrity, and rebuild public trust in the electoral process. Careful planning and comprehensive risk assessments are necessary to ensure that e-voting systems are secure, accessible, and beneficial to Nigeria's democratic goals.

Electronic Voting Text Analysis (Text/Tweets from Social Media Platforms)

Data Acquisition and its application in Nigeria electoral system

Data will be acquired from various social media platforms, including Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram. To gather tweets related to e-voting, we will use Twint, a Python library that allows data crawling from Twitter without needing a Twitter developer account. Similarly, we will employ appropriate tools or libraries capable of scraping data from Facebook and Instagram. Using Twint, we can automate the search and retrieval of tweets that mention electronic or e-voting, enabling the collection of a comprehensive dataset of relevant tweets. For instance: Facebook - 88%, FB Messenger - 69.9%, Instagram - 69.4%, Twitter - 61.2%.

Data Preprocessing and its application in Nigeria electoral system

The acquired data is unstructured text and contains noise. Data preprocessing will involve converting text to lowercase and removing stop words, repeated words, and other noise to enable unsupervised methods to generate sentiments.

Sentiment Analysis and its application in Nigeria electoral system

Unsupervised machine learning will be used to generate sentiments for each tweet using TextBlob, which will calculate each tweet's polarity, subjectivity, and sentiment. The sentiment detects positive, negative, and neutral tweets about electronic voting.

Text Classification Algorithm Based on Machine Learning and its application in Nigeria electoral system

A significant area of use for machine learning techniques is text analysis. Nevertheless, the raw data, consisting of a string of symbols, cannot be supplied directly to the algorithms because most require raw text documents with variable lengths rather than numerical feature vectors of a fixed size. Scikit-learn offers tools for the most typical techniques to extract numerical features from text content in order to handle this precisely.

Machine Learning Algorithms

Random Forest Classifier and its application in Nigeria electoral system

It is possible to categorize fresh data points using ensemble classification methods, which are learning algorithms that build multiple classifiers rather than just one. Bagging, Boosting, and Random Forest (RF) are the three ensemble classifiers most frequently employed (Wang et al., 2019).

Naive Bayes Algorithm and its application in Nigeria electoral system

Naive Bayes classifiers are a type of classification algorithms based on Bayes's Theorem. Rather than being a single technique, it is a family of algorithms founded on the notion that each pair of categorised features stands alone. The two parts of the dataset are the response/target vector and the feature matrix (Li et al., 2019).

Decision Tree and its application in Nigeria electoral system

As the tree was being constructed, decision tree methods divided the training set into smaller subsets recursively (Li et al., 2019).

Logistic Regression and its application in Nigeria electoral system

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A machine learning classification model called logistic regression is used to forecast the likelihood of a binary or categorical target variable (Zhang et al., 2023). Applications where the result is either true or false, positive or negative, or yes or no are frequently utilised to it. A supervised learning approach called logistic regression models the relationship between the independent variables.

Lightgbm (Light Gradient Boosting Machine) and its application in Nigeria electoral system

LightGBM is a gradient-boosting framework that uses tree-based learning algorithms. It is a fast and efficient model for large-scale machine learning tasks widely used in classification, regression, and ranking problems (Wang et al., 2019).

Xgboost (Extreme Gradient Boosting) and its application in Nigeria electoral system

XGBoost is a popular machine-learning algorithm for classification and regression problems. It is an ensemble method that combines multiple weak decision trees to make a more accurate prediction (Li et al., 2019).

Evaluation of Model Performance and comparison and its application in Nigeria electoral system

Iterative training of multiple models and evaluating their accuracy is a fundamental approach in machine learning, allowing for the identification of the best performing model. Performances of all models shall be observed using standard metric with extracted dataset and the best model shall be validated.

Sentiment Analysis Categorization

In Figure 1, a function get Analysis that categorizes the polarity scores into three sentiment categories: Negative, Neutral, and Positive was defined. The function is applied to the Polarity column, and the results are stored in a new column called Analysis.

Table 1: Other Metric Evaluation

	Model	Recall_Score	Precision_Score	F1_Score
0	Logistic_Regression	0.9995	0.999504	0.999501
1	Naïve_Bayes	0.9650	0.963267	0.963185
2	RandomForest	0.7445	0.905223	0.778623
3	Decision_Tree	0.9585	0.975060	0.962664
4	Lightgbm	1.0000	1.000000	1.000000
5	Xgboost	1.0000	1.000000	1.000000

Qualitative Study on ... (Afolabi et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611068>

Figure 1. Other Metrics Evaluation

This study conducted a thorough analysis of electronic voting sentiment data from Twitter, Instagram, and Facebook, using exploratory data analysis (EDA) to identify key trends, anomalies, and relationships that supported model selection. Data cleaning, transformation, and visualization techniques addressed missing values and imbalances, resulting in a balanced dataset comprising 6,500 Twitter, 2,000 Instagram, and 1,500 Facebook samples. TextBlob was used for text cleaning and polarity calculation, while multiple machine learning models' Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes, Random Forest, Decision Tree, LightGBM, and XGBoost were evaluated. Logistic Regression and XGBoost demonstrated the highest performance, with nearly perfect recall, precision, and F1 scores, while Naive Bayes and Decision Tree also performed well, each with specific strengths and weaknesses in sentiment prediction. ROC curves confirmed each model's effectiveness, providing a solid analytical foundation for informed decision-making on e-voting sentiment.

Conclusion

The study suggests that Nigerian electoral bodies engage with the public on social media to address concerns and enhance trust in e-voting. Continuous sentiment monitoring can identify emerging issues, while public education initiatives can promote e-voting's benefits and security. Policymakers should leverage these insights to design responsive, citizen-centered e-voting systems.

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Comparative analysis between Teachers' Education Goals and Social Change: An Exploratory Study of Nigerian University System

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Abstract

In Nigeria, despite clearly laid out policy goals with curriculum content mapped to its achievement, outcomes have continually fall short of expectations in terms of the kind of teachers envisioned in the policy document. The development of teachers with social change as a goal of teacher education remained a problem. This study aimed at describing teacher education goals for social change within Nigerian Teacher Education; and examining the relationship that exists between the Teacher Education goals and social change among the undergraduates. An exploratory sequential mixed method study was used to allow the leverage of the complimentary advantages of qualitative and quantitative methods for generating deeper insights into phenomena. In the first part, 11 lecturers from 11 universities were interviewed to generate qualitative data. In the second part, questionnaire was developed and administered to Teacher Education undergraduate. Participants in the quantitative study were 416 undergraduates at various levels of the Teacher Education programmes in the Nigerian public universities. The study assessed the factors of age, gender, subject area, and level/year of study as predictors of undergraduates' conceptualization of Teacher Education Goals (CTEG) for social change as well as CTEG as a predictor of social change. Thematic analysis and Structural Equation Model were employed to analyse the data collected for the study. The result showed that none of age, gender, year of study, and teaching subject significantly predicts CTEG. The study provided important information for policy, curriculum, strategy, and implementation in line with postmodern Teacher Education that is relevant for the twenty-first century.

Keyword: Teachers' education goals, social change, exploratory study, Nigerian Universities system

Introduction

The last two decades have brought rapid social, political, and economic changes which have transformed the structure of society in many countries around the world. The 21st Century society has been characterized by knowledge- driven economies, rapid information exchange and fast-moving communication technologies. Aside these social changes, there are a

lot of challenges facing our communities, along with instant connectivity to a global society. The rapid social change has led to efforts in recent years towards educational reforms in European countries and other parts of the world. After the society clearly and profoundly changed, it became necessary to reform education systems to be flexible, compatible with contemporary issues, and able to successfully tackle these challenges and the new realities. Meanwhile, studies affirmed that the success of any education depends on the quality of teachers, which in turn, depends on the effective teachings-learning process (Madhab, 2018; Mgaiwa, 2018). This suggests that would-be teachers need to be adequately equipped with knowledge and skills required for transforming the goals of teacher education into desired social change. In this context, teacher preparation programs in Nigeria are centrally and critically positioned in the national agenda (NPE, 2013), with a vision statement that Nigeria would like to: produce highly skilled, motivated, devoted, knowledgeable and creative teachers capable of raising a generation of Nigerian learners who can compete globally (FME, 2014). The National Policy on Education (FGN, 2013) also buttresses this by mandating Faculties of Education to produce highly motivated, conscientious, and creative classroom teachers that can promote creativity and adaptation to changes in the social life of the society.

While such a well-intentioned goal seems straightforward and clear, making it a reality has some challenges. The challenges begin with the conceptualization of teacher education goals among the teacher education undergraduates and the strategies employed to achieve the goals. This is because according to Ronnie (2016), simply stating a goal does not automatically benefit students, unless implemented correctly. This was supported by Pearson (2016) when it was held that though research in education has found goals setting to be essential for increasing student achievement and motivation, it is more important to get student buy-in regarding the value of assigned goals and make goal achievement personally meaningful for learners. Pearson goes further to state that clear goals provide explicit success criteria and evaluative standard that can be used to assess learners' progress. Moreover, measuring social change, according to Ebrahim (2019), begins with the organization's strategies and its theory of change. In line with these, the focus of this study is to examine the translation process of TE goals to social change within conceptualization of TE goals among TE undergraduates in Nigeria through the curriculum and instructional strategies.

The underpin theories for the study are goal setting theory by Locke and Latham (2006; 2017); and William E. Doll, Jr Four Rs curriculum theory of postmodern perspective on education (Qin, 2019). The goal setting theory was employed because of the theory's relevance to the conceptualization of teacher education goals. Then Doll's theory of change was also employed since we are in postmodern era (21st Century). Moreso, that Nigerian teacher education is having as its vision and goal, production of teachers with social change, who will be capable of coping with global trend in education. A postmodern approach to teacher education (TE) was therefore considered appropriate for effective professional socialization of the teachers as suggested by William E. Doll, Jr., in his curriculum theory of postmodern perspective on education (Qin, 2019). Prof. William E. Doll, Jr., the famous American postmodern curriculum theorist, offers us an effective curriculum/instruction strategy that can bring about appropriate translation of policy goals to required social change (Doll's, 1993; Qin, 2019). Doll posits that conceptualizing education within postmodernism means that education should foster, impact and result in social change. Doll's Pedagogical theory advocates the cultivation of students' comprehensive ability in the process of teaching; thus, it can bring positive effects to the transformation of the traditional perspectives on curriculum and instruction and help us solve the problems existing in the teacher education teaching and learning process (Doll's, 1993; Qin, 2019).

Despite Nigeria's clearly articulated policy goals for teacher education, which aim to produce highly skilled, motivated, and creative teachers capable of driving social change, the actual outcomes consistently fall short of these expectations. The gap between the envisioned goals and the actual performance of teacher education programs presents a significant challenge to the educational system. The fundamental issue lies in the conceptualization and implementation of teacher education goals. Many students enter teacher education programs accidentally, without genuine commitment to the profession, which undermines the potential for meaningful social transformation. The current approach to teacher education fails to effectively translate policy intentions into practical outcomes that can address the complex challenges of a rapidly changing 21st-century society. Moreover, there is a critical need to understand how teacher education programs can truly foster social change. The existing system struggles to develop teachers who are not just technically competent, but also socially conscious, adaptable, and capable of driving meaningful societal transformation. This requires a comprehensive examination of the goals, curriculum, and instructional strategies employed in teacher education programs. The research seeks to bridge this gap by investigating how undergraduate teacher education students conceptualize their educational goals and how these conceptualizations relate to potential for social change. By exploring the attitudinal, behavioral, and cognitive dimensions of teacher education goals, the study aims to provide insights that can help reshape teacher preparation to more effectively meet the demands of a dynamic and evolving educational landscape.

Objectives of the study

This study aimed at describing teacher education goals for social change within Nigerian Teacher Education; and examining the relationship that exists between the Teacher Education goals and social change among the undergraduates. Specifically, the study intends to:

1. Determine the relationship between Teacher Education undergraduate students' conceptualization of Teacher Education goals and potential for social change.

Research Questions

The following research question was generated for this paper:

1. What is the association between Teacher Education undergraduate student's conceptualization of Teacher Education goals and social change?

Hypotheses

This study thus set out to test the following hypothesis:

1. The extent to which Teacher Education undergraduate student's conceptualize Teacher Education goals is significantly associated with social change.

Methodology

The research design used in this study was exploratory sequential mixed method. It is a research design where the researcher will collect qualitative data first and thereafter collect quantitative data for the same research study (Mihis, 2019). This study employed this research design because it was recommended for a study such as social change with unknown variables and absence of a guiding framework or theory (Creswell and Clark, 2018). The population for this study consisted of two groups: TE undergraduates in the Bachelor of Education programme in public universities in North-Central Nigeria and their lecturers. Nigeria consists of six (6) geopolitical zones with differing cultural, ethnic, geographical, and political structure. These factors have potentially strong implications for education and social change. A geopolitical zone thus represents the most homogenous socio-cultural entity within the multi-ethnic nation of over 250 million people. The North-Central geopolitical zone, also known as the Middle Belt, has an estimated population of around 29 million (14.51% of total population) spread across 6 states and the Federal Capital Territory (Ikoba, Jolayemi, & Sanni, 2018). The zone is located at the nation's centre and includes representative sections of other geopolitical zones and the federal capital territory (FCT) as well as a good presence of foreigners. These factors make the zone socially, culturally, and geopolitically neutral and representative of the nation as a whole. In addition, the researcher's deep knowledge of the social context, as well as teaching experience within the TE system in the north-central zone, comes in very readily, making this region an ideal context for this study which can be replicated in the future in other zones across the country.

Presentation of Results

RQ1: How is Teacher Education Goals for Social Change described within the context of Nigerian Undergraduate Teacher Education?

In attempt to obtain reliable and adequate data on TE Goals for Social Change in Nigeria, lecturers from target Universities in North Central Nigeria that are preparing the Undergraduate Teachers for the professional qualification were interviewed. The feedback from the interviews revealed that TE Goals for Social Change among the Undergraduate Teachers include attitudinal goals, behavioural goals, and cognitive goals. The attitudinal goal is described through four items including: (a) Commitment to teaching: Responses indicated that this concept is affected by societal and economic demands, dedication, the need to highlight the beauty of the profession. Lecturers submit that to promote attitudinal goals, only individuals who genuinely love the profession should be recruited for TE.

“There is lack of commitment on the part of our students because only few of them chose reading educational courses. The undergoing teacher education in this part of the world has no attraction or attention. *So, most of them are accidental teacher education students. Therefore, the level of commitment is low.*” [R2/M/42/11]

They noted unfortunately that TE is a tertiary option for most entrants into TE; their entry is mostly accidental and is due to the absence of ‘better’ options rather than a personal intention to be teachers. (b) Commitment to national goals: It is identified as a sign of commitment to teaching, and the lecturers believe service-learning opportunities stirs commitment:

“There are a lot they can do. Sending these graduates to the rural areas will do a lot of enhancing the beauty of these in formal and non- formal education. In the rural areas the rural teachers will not only work in the classroom after the class but also work in the farm... fishing, settling dispute and so on...” [R6/M/55/21].

(c) Fitness: Fitness was described as the ability to succeed in 21st century teaching and lecturers opined that to promote attitudinal goal, TE student recruitment should focus on best hands. They submit that non-formal education is more fit for producing high grade teachers than formal education and that social fitness is an indication of soundness, and it shown in effectiveness.

(d) Professionalism is shown in strong societal impact, and promoted through student orientation”:

“I have several of them that they are doing well, they are making waves in the teaching profession as many as I have seen that are motivated even those who never took us. Right now I have one of them who is a lecturer in the Kogi state university, he started with statistics then changed, when he came I motivated him and today he is a lecturer and even studying science subject inside sociology. I think they are making waves, those who listened to us and went through us.” [R3/F/59/23]

Behavioural goals are captured in conscientiousness and motivation. Lecturers believe that annual peer teaching can promote conscientiousness, and that objectivity and ethics are necessary qualities in undergraduate TE. In terms of motivation, they identified activeness in class, confidence, dynamism, engagement, and motivating TE students to appreciate themselves as critical factors.

“However, what we are able to achieve especially as with low-level students, I try to motivate them, integrate them into the profession, first of all, by given them their roles as teachers, that is why they are nation builders. I let them know that they are people who determine the impact of the future generation.” [R3/F/59/23].

Cognitive goals are captured in four concepts including creativity, efficiency, inquiry, and intellectual background. These concepts are described as follows in relation to undergraduate TE: (a) Creativity is shown in asking and answering technical questions, in assignment feedback and extra effort, in problem-solving, and in the use of interesting pedagogy and assessment. (b) Efficiency is shown in the demonstrate of knowledge ahead of teacher and class, ability to spot and correct teacher mistakes, communication and time management skills, including timeliness on assignment, classroom control, the use of demo and other edutech and resource utilization. They also noted that mandatory skill acquisition as graduation requirement can go a long way in promoting efficiency. (c) Inquiry is reflected in being ahead of class in content knowledge, contributing actively in class, eagerness to learn, inquiry and critical thinking, and inquisitiveness. (d) Intellectual Background will be promoted through a curriculum with room for more practical experience (TP and PT). It is shown in high CGPA or intellectual ability. It emphasizes 21t century pedagogy, methodology interaction and practice, continuous professional development, a robust TE Curriculum, and an effective foundation course.

Table 1: Testing the Research Hypotheses: Correlation among Variables

N = 416		Study_Yr	Age	CTEG
Study_Yr	Pearson Correlation	1	.263**	-.026
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.594
Age	Pearson Correlation	.263	1	-.109*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.027
CTEG	Pearson Correlation	-.026	-.109*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.594	.027	

*p < .05 **p < .01

1. There is a weak, positive correlation between year of study and age, which was statistically significant ($r = .263$, $n = 416$, $p = .000$). The standard graded programme of instruction where learners move to the next level of learning after every year will generally result in simultaneous increase in age and year of study, however, this progression is not automatic and only predicated on good performance. Respondents’ academic progression status was not assessed in this study. Hence, it cannot be determined whether this might have contributed to the weak correlation.
2. Age shows weak, negative correlations that are significant with both CTEG ($r = -.109$, $n = 416$, $p = .027$) and informal instruction ($r = -.112$, $n = 416$, $p = .022$).

Table 2: Parameter Estimates for Determining Independent Variables' Effect on Dependent Variable

Parameter	B	SE	95% CI	Wald χ^2	df	p	Exp(B)	95% CI for Exp(B)
Threshold: [SocChan = 1.00]	-10.806	0.782	[-12.339, -9.274]	191.067	1	< .001	0.000	[0.000, 0.000]
[SocChan = 2.00]	-7.883	0.734	[-9.322, -6.444]	115.241	1	< .001	0.000	[0.000, 0.002]
[SocChan = 3.00]	-4.194	0.653	[-5.473, -2.915]	41.299	1	< .001	0.015	[0.004, 0.054]
[SocChan = 4.00]	-1.019	0.612	[-2.219, 0.180]	2.775	1	.096	0.361	[0.109, 1.197]

Note. B = unstandardized coefficient; SE = standard error; CI = confidence interval; Exp(B) = odds ratio.

GENLIN parameter estimates for dichotomous variables (gender) and polytomous variables

H₀₂: Undergraduate teachers' gender does not significantly predict social change

H_{a2}: Undergraduate teachers' gender significantly predicts social change

The odds of male students scoring higher on the DV was 1.597, 95% CI [1.113, 2.293] times that of female students, and the effect is statistically significant, $\chi^2(1) = 6.449$, $p = .011$. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis, and accept the alternative hypothesis, and conclude that undergraduate teachers' gender significantly predicts social change.

H₀₃: Undergraduate teachers' teaching subject does not significantly predict social change.

H_{a3}: Undergraduate teachers' teaching subject significantly predicts social change.

The result shows that teaching subject has a statistically significant effect on the prediction of social change, Wald $\chi^2(1) = 6.490$, $p = .011$. The odds of students with teaching subject as language (including local and foreign languages) scoring higher on social change was 1.824, 95% CI [1.149, 2.896] times that of students with non-STEM teaching subjects, and the change is significant ($p < .05$). The odds of students with STEM teaching subject scoring higher on social change was 1.014, 95% CI [.678, 1.517] times that of students with non-STEM teaching subjects; the change is not significant ($p > .05$).

Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis that undergraduate teachers' teaching subject does not significantly predict social change, and we accept the alternative hypothesis, and conclude that some undergraduate teachers' teaching subject significantly predicts social change.

GENLIN parameter estimates for Ordinal and continuous IVs In terms of the ordinal (CTEG) and continuous IVs (age and year of study), we test the following pairs of hypotheses:

H₀₄: CTEG does not significantly predict social change among undergraduate teachers in Nigeria.

H_{a4}: CTEG significantly predicts social change among undergraduate teachers in Nigeria.

The result shows that CTEG has a statistically significant effect on the prediction of social change, Wald $\chi^2(1) = 324.350$, $p < .05$. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis, and accept the alternative hypothesis, and we conclude that level of CTEG significantly predicts social change among undergraduate teachers' in Nigeria.

H₀₅: Undergraduate teachers' age does not significantly predict social change

H_{a5}: Undergraduate teachers' age significantly predicts social change

The result shows that age shows $\chi^2(1) = .068$ and $p > .05$ which indicates that age does not have a statistically significant effect on social change. Hence, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that age does not statistically predict social change among undergraduate teachers.

H₀₆: Undergraduate teachers' year of study does not significantly predict social change

H_{a6}: Undergraduate teachers' year of study significantly predicts social change

For year of study ($\chi^2(1) = .097$; $p = .755$) do not have statistically significant effect on social change. In essence, TE students age and year of study do not predict social change, but their scores of CTEG does; that is, a TE student's level of conceptualization of TE goals has significant effect on social change.

Discussion of Findings

Description of TE goals for social change within Nigerian undergraduate TE focused on the evaluation of TE goals (as described in the Nigerian NPE document) as having social change as its focus. Within this context, social change was defined as significant changes in human interactions and societal norms with profound and longterm impact on cultural and social institutions (Mohammad, 2016; Denfey, 2017; Brown and Balts, 2017; Shah, 2017) where education could be both a factor for social change as well as the context for the significant changes brought about by social change. With change construed as a phenomenon involving a large number of persons engaging in activities that differ from those which they or their immediate forefathers engaged in some time before', within education, social change, in the simplest form can thus be conceived as modifications or changes in the values and social norms of community members, including learners, instructors, and other

members as well as functioning of the community over time. The socialization of TE undergraduates – being the focused community in the context of this study – into the teaching profession, thus defines social change. With social change conceived as a process involving changes over time, for TE undergraduates, SC becomes the gradual, observable or measurable changes towards the achievement of TE goals experienced over the course of the TE period. Following criticism of modernism, and the underlying philosophical assumptions (MBMS El-Baz, 2017), postmodernism, involving society-transforming changes that involves ‘information advances...and the rise of a post-industrial order’ (Vakhovskiy, L., Babichev, O., & Ivchenko, T. (2022)) became the lens for viewing education, and hence, teacher education in the twenty-first century. Thus, underpinned by the goal theory, the level of conceptualization of TE goals (CTEG) by TE undergraduates was identified as a factor that determines the achievement of social change as a focus of TE.

Individual learner factors have been studied extensively in terms of their moderating effects on learning. Vo, Seergobin and MacDonald (2018) examined the effect of age on reversal learning; they found that older adults learned more poorly than younger adults, thus suggesting a relationship between age and learning. In a similar study (Klein, Shner, Ginat-Frolich, Vervliet, & Shechner, 2020), the authors noted that adults exhibited a gradual decrease in differential danger ratings compared with younger learners. Both studies confirm age as predictive of learning. In their study of age-related cognitive decline, Vachon, Modchalingam and Hart (2020) identified similar ability among younger and older adults and argued that cognitive explanations for age-related decline in motor learning were limited.

This submission aligns with findings from this study. However, they also noted that training induced much larger shifts in older adults compared to younger adults. Thus suggesting that while age may not directly predict learning, it may predict shifts due to training (Griffin et al., 2017; Piotti et al., 2018; Vachon et al., 2020). Although this factor was not examined in this study, it may indicate an important focus of future research. Overall, a general difference between these studies and the current one is that the age range of learners in the current study is narrow, considering that age will generally be related to the level of study within formal education. Entry into the TE system requires individuals to have completed an initial 12 years of learning; hence, the entry point is relatively defined, and progression is predictable. In their study of gender effects in multimedia learning, Heo and Toomey (2020) showed that male participants consistently outperformed female participants in all learning tasks. Chung and Chang (2017) also suggested confirming a relationship between gender and learning. They studied the effect of gender on learning achievement and motivation, and showed that female learners' motivation is significantly higher than that of male learners. However, unlike Vachon et al (2020) who identified training as a moderating factor, they found game contents reduce the effect of gender.

Neither year of study nor teaching subject significantly predicted CTEG, but gender, teaching subject and the level of CTEG significantly predicted social change. Previous studies also reported divergent views on this. For example, Panadero, Fernandez-Ruiz and Sanchez (2020) reported significant effect of subject-matter on students on self-efficacy. Subject-matter knowledge has also been shown to be significantly related to teaching effectiveness (Manaf, Abdullah, & Osman, 2015). Yilmaz, Altinkurt, and Yildirim (2015) also showed that seniority or experience, subject matter and gender significantly affects teachers' level of organizational citizenship behaviors. They found that the level of seniority showed the strongest effect; female teachers exhibited much more citizenship behavior than male teachers. More senior teachers exhibited higher citizenship behaviours than less experienced teachers, and primary school teachers than subject matter teachers. It is hard to determine however, whether time spent practicing as teachers exerts effects that are different from the years spent as TE students.

Conclusion

The results of the study showed that attitudinal goals are described through commitment to teaching, commitment to national goals, fitness and professionalism. Behavioural goals are captured in conscientiousness and motivation. The result further showed that TE lecturers believe that peer teaching can promote conscientiousness, and that objectivity and ethics are necessary qualities in future teachers. They also identified activeness in class, confidence, dynamism, engagement, and inspiring TE students to appreciate themselves as critical factors for motivation. Cognitive goals are captured in four concepts including creativity, efficiency, inquiry, and intellectual background. These findings contribute to the basis for the development of the quantitative instrument for assessment of the level of social change among undergraduate TE students.

Recommendations

Based on this study finding, the following recommendations are made:

1. Educational institutions should reshape their teaching practices and curriculum to align with the desired social change in the field of education. This could lead to the development of a new generation of teachers who are more socially conscious, innovative, and equipped to address the evolving challenges in the society.
2. Educational institutions should adopt a holistic approach to teacher education, where both formal and informal aspects of the curriculum are considered. This would lead to a more comprehensive and effective learning experience for aspiring teachers.
3. This study took the data sample from public universities in the north-central region of Nigeria. Though the findings may be generalized for the region, further studies can explore other regions of the country. For example, the cultural difference can be explored to bring a variation in results.
4. This study was limited to undergraduate TE, implying teacher preparation within the university setting; future research into the other aspects of TE, including those that compare pre-tertiary and tertiary TE or tertiary TE and PD programme may shed light on important concepts.

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Comparative Analysis between Family Variables and Sexual Behaviour among Secondary School Students in Ondo Metropolis, Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study comparative analysis between family variables and sexual behaviour among secondary school students. Descriptive Survey research design was adopted for the study. The population consisted of all secondary school students in Ondo metropolis during the 2023/2024 academic session. The sample comprised three hundred (300) students randomly selected from six (6) schools in the metropolis. Questionnaire on Sexual Behaviour among Secondary School Students (QSBSSS) was used to collect data. Reliability of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach's Alpha statistics which yielded a coefficient of 0.82. Data collected was analysed using ANOVA and t-test. The results revealed that there is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on family type ($F = 2.902, p > 0.05$). The findings showed that there is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on father's occupation while there is in that of mother's occupation ($t = 1.084, p > 0.05$) and $t = 4.038, p < 0.05$) respectively. It was also revealed that there is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on father's qualification while there is in that of mother's qualification ($F = 0.730, p > 0.05$ and $F = 1.495, p < 0.05$ respectively). It was concluded that mothers are found to be of more important figures than father in influencing sexual behaviour of secondary school students, it was therefore recommended that parents should be involved in organising sex education programme for secondary school students and workshops on sexuality education should be organised for parents to have more idea and exposure on what to teach their children.

Keywords: Sexual behaviour, family variables, adolescents

Introduction

Sexual behaviour is an aspect of sexuality which deals with expression of sexual feelings. Hyde and Delamater (2003) asserted that sexual behaviour is that behaviour that produces sexual arousal and increases the chances of orgasm. Adolescence or youthful period is the most remarkable and troublesome when it comes to the issue of sexual behaviour. The reason for this is that at the period, because of the pubertal changes and increase in the secretion of sex hormones in the body, many young people tend to experiment with sex. This experimentation exposes them to different sexually related problems such as STIs and HIV/AIDS, unplanned pregnancy, abortion and complications associated with it, disrupted future, psychological trauma, and so on.

According to Modebelu (2010), sexual behaviour is any activity (including kissing, pecking, necking, hugging, coital relationship, anal and oral sex and also masturbation) in varying degree and forms which satisfies one's sexual desires and urges. An individual may have positive or negative sexual behaviour. Positive or healthy sexual behaviour includes the ability to suspend the onset of sexual intercourse, making right choices of partners when the time comes, having limited number, at least one sexual partner when sexually active, sexual absenteeism, or proper use of condom if already sexually active and active protection of one's self against sexual harassment (McKay, 1993). On the other hand, risky or negative sexual behaviour is exposure of oneself to risky sexual activities without control over one's sexual activities (Cohen & Trussel, 1996). Modebelu (2010) opined that negative sexual behaviour is being careless in the use of one's sexuality and also undue exposure of one's self to sexual risk. Puente and Zabaleta (2011) reported that the period of adolescence concedes with a surge of sexual interest which results from such factors as physical body change, hormonal increase, increase in social emphasis on sex and the adolescent's necessary rehearsal for adult roles. These changes propel the intense preoccupation with sexual exploration and

Comparative Analysis... (Oyetayo & Soetan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611072>

experimentation. These sex-crazed and hormone-driven individuals get involved in a lot of high-risk sexual behaviour which are detrimental to them, their families and the society.

Young people's sexual behavior have been noted to be influenced by a number of factors such as sexuality education, sexual knowledge, type of family and neighbourhood (Adegoke, 2004). Over the past two decades, there has been a large body of research substantiating the powerful influence of the family on adolescent sexual health behaviours outcomes (Simpson, 2001). In general, studies found that adolescents in married, biological two – parent families are less likely to engage in unprotected sex and early sexual initiation compared to adolescents from single parent, cohabiting stepfather, and married stepfather families (Wu & Thompson, 2001). Babalola, Tambashe and Vondrasek (2005) asserted that irrespective of whether it is a low, middle or high – income country, adolescents raised in single parent households have an increased probability of both early sexual debut and pregnancy. In the same vein, Kingori and Kingoru (2016) emphasized the fact that father's absence may cause adolescent daughters to have difficulties relating to other males; these difficulties may take different forms for daughters of widows and divorcees. Adolescent girls from divorced homes appeared to be more sexually preconscious and assertive with males, whereas those whose mothers were widowed were characterized as excessively anxious about sexuality and as shy and uncomfortable around males. Daughters learn to feel competent and to value and acquire the social skills necessary for effective heterosexual interactions by interacting with warm, responsive, masculine fathers, who reward and enjoy their daughters' femininity.

Considering the role of family as agent of socialisation for children and adolescents, there is a need to investigate the influence of family variables (such as family type, father's and mother's occupation and qualification) on adolescents' sexual behaviour, so as to come up with counselling intervention to mitigate their risky sexual behaviour.

Objectives of the Study

This study was designed to:

1. Find out the difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on family type.
2. Investigate the difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on father's occupation.
3. Examine the difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on mother's occupation.
4. Determine the difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on father's qualification.
5. Investigate the difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on mother's qualification.

Research Hypotheses

To guide the conduct of the study, the following research hypotheses were raised.

1. There is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on family type.
2. There is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on father's occupation.
3. There is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on mother's occupation.
4. There is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on father's qualification.
5. There is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on mother's qualification.

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted to examine family variables and sexual behaviour among secondary school students. The population consisted of all secondary school students in Ondo metropolis. The sample comprised three hundred (300) students randomly selected from six (6) schools in the metropolis. Self-developed structured questionnaire titled "Questionnaire on Sexual Behaviour among Secondary School Students (QSBSSS)" was used as instrument for the study. The questionnaire was divided into two sections (A & B). Section A was on personal data of the respondents while section B consisted of items on students' sexual behaviour with four Likert type scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). Reliability of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach's Alpha statistics which yielded a co-efficient of 0.82. Data collected was analysed using t-test and ANOVA.

Comparative Analysis... (Oyetayo & Soetan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611072>

Presentation of Results

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on family type. In testing this hypothesis, the respondents were classified into three groups based on family type (monogamy, polygamy and others) and scores on sexual behaviour were analysed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: One-way Analysis of Variance summary of the difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on family type

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	60.450	3	20.150	2.902	.820
Within Groups	17306.052	296	58.466		
Total	17366.502	299			

From Table 1, the mean squares between groups and within groups are 60, 450 and 17306.052 respectively. These yielded the F-value of 2.902 which is not significant at 0.05 level. This implies that there is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on family type.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on father's occupation.

In testing this hypothesis, the respondents were classified into two groups based on father's occupation (i.e. self-employed or civil servant) and scores on sexual behaviour were analysed using t-test. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Independent t-test of the difference in the sexual behaviour of students based on father's occupation

	Variable	N	Mean	St.D	df	t	Sig.	P
Sexual behaviour	Self-employed	252	26.99	4.916	298	1.084	.471	>.05
	Civil Servants	48	28.01	4.173				

As shown in Table 2, students whose fathers are self-employed have a mean score of 26.99 and a standard deviation of 4.916 while students whose fathers are civil servants have a mean score of 28.01 and a standard deviation of 4.173. A t-test analysis of these values yielded a t-value of 1.084 which is not significant at 0.05 level. This implies that there is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students whose fathers are self-employed and civil servants.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on mother's occupation.

In testing this hypothesis, the subjects were grouped into two based on mother's occupation (self-employed and civil servant) and scores on sexual behaviour were analysed using t-test. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Independent t-test of the difference in the sexual behaviour of students based on mothers occupation

	Variable	N	Mean	St.D	df	t	Sig.	P	η^2
Sexual behaviour	Self-employed	275	36.30	3.725	298	4.038	.000	<.05	0.0519
	Civil Servants	25	27.18	3.001					

Table 3 shows that students whose mothers are self-employed have a mean score of 36.30 and a standard deviation of 3.725 while those whose mothers are civil servants have a mean score of 27.18 and a standard deviation of 3.001. A t-test analysis of these values yielded a t-value of 4.038 which is significant at 0.05 level. This implies that there is significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students whose mothers are self-employed and civil servants Size of effect ($\eta^2 = 0.0519$) reveals that mother's occupation had low effect (according to Cohen 1988 and Field, 2000 rule of thumb for size of effect) on sexual behaviour of secondary school students; that is, mother's occupation accounted for 5.19% change in the sexual behaviour of students.

Hypothesis Four: There is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on father's qualification.

Comparative Analysis... (Oyetayo & Soetan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611072>

In testing this hypothesis, subjects were grouped into six based on the father's qualification and scores on sexual behaviour were analysed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: One-way Analysis of Variance summary of the difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on father's qualification

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	472.811	4	118.203	0.730	.711
Within Groups	25449.147	295	86.268		
Total	17910.560	299			

As shown in Table 4, the mean squares between groups and within groups are 472.811 and 25449.147 respectively. These yielded the F-value of 0.730 which is not significant at 0.05 level. This implies that there is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on father's qualification.

Hypothesis Five: There is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on mother's qualification.

In testing this hypothesis, respondents were classified into six groups based on mother's qualification and scores on sexual behaviour were analysed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Analysis of Variance summary of the difference in the sexual behaviour of students based on mother's qualification

Source of Variable	N	$\bar{\chi}$	St.D	df	SS	MS	F	Sig.	P	W ²	η^2
Primary six		11.20	4.008	5	738.118	147.624	1.495	.000	<0.05	0.0428	0.00742
SSCE		24.22	6.173	294	29025.037	98.725					
NCE/OND		17.04	4.850								
HND/B.Sc.		22.53	2.171								
M.Sc.		16.92	4.116								
Ph.D		18.00	3.824								
Total	300	18.32	3.68	299	29,763.155						

Source: Field, 2023.

From Table 5, the mean squares between groups and within groups are 738.118 and 29025.037 respectively. These yielded the F-value of 1.495 which is significant at 0.05 level. This implies that there is a significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on mother's qualification. The size of effect ($w^2=0.0428$) reveals that mother's qualification had low effect on the sexual behaviour of secondary school students. This is, qualification of the respondents mothers accounted for 4.28% variance in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students.

Discussion of Findings

This study showed that there is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school based on family type (monogamous, polygamous and others). This is supported by Oluwatosin (2010) who found that family type does not significantly influence risky sexual behaviour among undergraduate students. Contrary to this, Laddunuri (2013) reported that family structure (polygamous and separated) as a whole is a significant factor in which students from polygamous and separated family engage in sexual intercourse 1.965 and 2.07 times higher than that of the students from monogamous family respectively. In their study, Kushal et. al., (2022) found that parental monitoring rather than parental support had strong influence on decreasing the odds of having early sexual debut among adolescents. While family structure has been suggested to have an indirect effect on adolescent sexual behaviour, parent-child interactions and processes are believed to have a more direct effect on such behaviour (Defo & Dimbuene, 2012).

The results of the study revealed that father's occupation has no significant influence on sexual behaviour of the secondary school students while mother's occupation has. This implies that sexual behaviour of students whose fathers are self-employed is not significantly different from those whose fathers are civil servants while sexual behaviour of students whose mothers are self-employed is significantly different from those whose mothers are civil servants. A possible explanation for

Comparative Analysis... (Oyetayo & Soetan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611072>

this is in gender-stereotyping in which mothers are expected to create more time than fathers in nurturing their children. They are expected to be at home more than fathers who are using almost all their time in fending for the family. That is why fathers presence at home may not be as significant as that of the mothers in guiding the children. The significant influence of mother's occupation on sexual behaviour of secondary school students may be based on the fact that a self-employed mother may not be able to predict her time-table for the day. Business opportunity may come anytime which would disrupt the time she could spend at home. On the other hand, civil servant mother could plan her time on monitoring, communicating and relating with her children especially the adolescents, which would in turn impact on their sexual behaviour. According to Bonell et. al. (2006), girls and boys from lone parents families or having mothers who were teenagers when they were born were more likely to report sex but not lack of contraception at first sex by age 15/16. Girls and boys with mothers having them as teenagers, and boys but not girls from lone parent families, were more likely to report being involved in contraception by age 15/16.

The study also found that father's qualification has no significant influence on sexual behaviour of secondary school students while mother's qualification has. Laddunuri (2013) found that education of mother and sexual intercourse were significantly associated with each other. And also, in the case of education of father and intercourse were significantly associated. The teens from families where fathers have less education are more likely to be sexually active than teens who come from families where fathers have more education. This relationship is pretty linear to and proxy between rates of sexual activity and level of father's education. The higher the father's education the less likely the teen is to be sexually active (Dryfoos, 1990).

Conclusion

Mothers are found to be of more important figure than fathers in influencing sexual behaviour of secondary school students. There is a need for contemporary career mother to find means of balancing their time in building relationship with their children for position sexual behaviour among the adolescents.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Parents should be involved in organising sex education programmes for secondary school students.
2. All available avenues should be used in encouraging parent-child communication on sexuality.
3. Parent – Teacher Association meetings should be used as avenue to sensitize parents on the importance of educating their children on sexuality.
4. Workshops on sexuality education should be organised for parents to have more idea and exposure on what to teach their children.
5. School counsellors should be on alert to identify students who need individual and parental attention for counselling intervention.
6. Counsellors should identify students who lack parental support due to their family background for in-depth group counselling on sexuality.

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Assessment of Teacher-Student Relationship on Academic Performance in Christian Religious Knowledge among Secondary School Students in Kaduna State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Relationships are very of great importance to every setting ranging from the family, school and the larger society. It is in this regard that this study assessed teacher-student relationship on academic performance in Christian Religious Knowledge among secondary school students in Kaduna State, Nigeria. Survey design, specifically, descriptive was adopted. The objectives were to examine teacher-student romantic and work relationships on academic performance in Christian Religious knowledge. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated in line with objectives. Questionnaires and interviews were adopted and used as instruments for data collection from the seven hundred and four (704) respondents sampled to represent the population of thirteen thousand, nine hundred and sixty-four secondary school Christian students (13,864), and nine thousand, four hundred and five teachers (9,403). A pilot study was conducted to validate the instrument. The data were analyzed using Cronbach's Alfa method at a 0.05 level of tolerance. The reliability coefficient obtained was 0.873 and the standard Alfa level of .873. These were considered adequate for the internal consistency of the instrument with a confirmation of its reliability. The data was subjected to statistical analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), IBM version 26. Statistical procedures adopted were descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages, mean, and standard deviation. Findings revealed that teachers who engage in romantic relationship with students favour those students, even if they are not qualified. Another finding revealed that teacher-student work relationship fosters a welcoming classroom atmosphere where students feel secure, valued, and confident to perform better in class. As a result, the study concluded that teacher-student relationship has a high tendency of reducing Christian student academic performance, while teacher-student work relationship help student to record high academic performance. The study recommended that Kaduna state Teacher's Service Board in collaboration with Adolescent Girl Initiative Learning Empowerment (AGILE), and the ministry of education should give incentives to teachers who maintain work relationship with their student through recommendations by school managements. They should also establish and enforce clear policies regarding teacher-student relationship and give sanctions to anyone found guilty of the act.

Keywords: Teacher, Relationship, Academic performance, Christian students.

Introduction

Generally, relationships are very important in every setting ranging from the family, school, and the larger society; and its values can never be over-emphasized. Studies have shown that for children to learn, they need a relationship by attaching themselves to adults i.e. their parents, older siblings, and teachers. Mikulince and Shaver (2020) maintain that for normal development, children need to attach themselves to an adult if not, they will lack the ability to meet their own survival requirements and endanger their lives. Teenagers in secondary school, spend a considerable amount of time at School from approximately 175 to 220 days with an average of 5 to 8 hours every day ranging from normal school activities to extra lessons and games. In line with the above assertion, Arrascue (2023) added that children spend 18 years of their lives receiving education beginning at the age of 5. She continued that the formation of a teacher-student relationship is the best practice for bettering education for all students throughout the course of their entire academic career. During these hours and years, students' interactions and subsequent relationships with teachers are paramount for their emotional regulation, attention,

Assessment of Teacher-Student...(Yohanna, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611072>

problem-solving, and academic achievement (Pianta & Allen, 2018). Cook, Coco, Zhang, Duong, Renshaw, Long, and Frank (2018) confirmed the above assertion to be true, saying that it is not a surprise if the bond between the students and their teachers impacts their performance positively or negatively depending on which type of relationship exists between them. Teachers have an enormous amount of influence on their students and this influential power has significant implications on the performance of the students. The most powerful weapon teachers have when trying to foster a favorable learning climate, is a positive relationship with their students (Boynton, 2015).

Teaching and learning are as old as man himself and it is considered a noble profession worldwide. Teacher's Registration Council of Nigeria (2013) maintains that "it is the oldest and noblest of all professions." (p. 10). In most of the world's traditional cultures, during teaching and learning, the teacher sits on a stool or a place higher than the learners, while the learners sit on either mat or on the bare floor to show respect and honor, so that all of them will be able to see and hear the teacher. This can be seen in the Islamic and Jewish traditional schools. During the early stage of formal education, learners were highly disciplined and respectful and those who were shouldered with the teaching responsibilities kept their boundaries. Students were obedient, hard-working, and ready to study with all levels of seriousness, humility, and respect. In those days, teachers were highly respected by students, parents, and the entire community in such a way that their opinions were accepted and regarded with utmost dignity; students relate with their teachers with respect even more than they do to their parents. Teachers, on the other hand, were dedicated and determined to carry out their jobs without anyone supervising them as they believed that their reward was in heaven. Rumnanayan and Rao (2014) added that teachers of that time felt it was a good idea to train students to be as excellent as, if not better than them. Similarly, teachers worked hard and left no stone unturned as regards teaching all their topics before the start of the examination and they would not hesitate to take disciplinary actions if required. They maintained that the teacher-student relationship was cordial and that of parent-children. The researcher observes that in the 70s and 80s, students wrote GCE/SSCE with strict supervision, even with policemen in the examination halls, and still excelled without anyone giving them a helping hand or cheating.

When one compares education from its early days through its developmental stages to what is available today, it is obvious that there has been an alteration in the system generally. The opposite appears to be true in today's attitude of teacher-student relationship especially in secondary schools and particularly in the area of morals. Many teachers and students have failed and are found wanting. The respect, honor, and dignity accorded to teachers and the teaching profession by students in those days has completely vanished. The researcher observes that some of the teachers themselves do not know their worth, they go as low as having romantic relationships with their students, especially the male teachers to the female students; while some of them relate with the students as though they are colleagues or age mates. Teachers and students engage in some social activities such as going to parties and clubs; smoking cigarettes and other drugs together, sleeping in the same room, sharing clothes, sending boy students to deliver messages to female students, engaging in examination malpractice, and so on. This is not completely exceptional for female teachers.

Tyoakaa (2014) explained that student misbehavior is high and failure, particularly in external examinations such as WASCE, NECO, JAMB, and others, is poor. He added that this may be attributed to the fact that students do not have a positive and morally guided relationship with their teachers, that is why they do not take their studies seriously, bearing in mind that to some extent, teachers may give them a helping hand during examinations. In connection to the above, Adetola (2024) gave a brief analysis and opinion that the most recent results in 2024 showed a decline, with only 72.12% of candidates achieving five credits, including English and mathematics. This 7.69% drop from the previous year is concerning, especially given the large number of candidates—1,805,216—who sat for the exam. The decline may point to systemic issues that need to be addressed, such as overcrowded classrooms, insufficient teaching resources, or broader socio-economic challenges, student's lack of seriousness etc. The WAEC results from 2020 to 2024 demonstrate both progress and setbacks in Nigeria's education sector. The significant improvement in 2021, followed by declines in 2022 and 2024, highlights the need for continuous monitoring and targeted interventions to ensure sustained progress from all the stake holders.

Objective of the study

The study has the following objectives:

1. To investigate teacher-student romantic relationship and its implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna state, Nigeria.
2. To examine teacher-student work relationship and its implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna state, Nigeria.

Research Question

6. What is teacher-student romantic relationship and its implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna state?
7. What is teacher-student work relationship and its implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna state?

Research Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference between the opinions of male and female teachers on teacher-student romantic relationship and its implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna state.
2. There is no significant difference between the opinions of teachers teaching in the urban area and those teaching in the rural area on teacher-student work relationship and its implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna state.

Methodology

The study used descriptive survey research design, the target population were secondary Christian students and teachers in Kaduna state. A purposive sample of 720 respondents out of 13,864 students and 9,405 was used. Questionnaire and interview were used as instrument for data collection within 8 LGAs in the 3 senatorial zones of the state. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 was use to analyzed the data based on the 685 questionnaires that returned representing 97.3% and the mean score for the items were based on four-point Likert scale with the midpoint average for decision of item was fixed at 2.50. this implies that, a mean score of 2.50 and above becomes a yardstick for agreement while mean score below 2.50 implies disagreement. The hypothesis was tested with t-test at 0.05 levels of significance.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Teacher Gender

S/N	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Male Teachers	74	61.2
2	Female Teachers	47	38.8
	Total	121	100

Table 1 shows that 74 respondents were male teachers with (61.2%), and 47 respondents with (38.8%) were female teachers. The data implies that male teachers were more than female teachers in responding to the questionnaire on the implications of the relationship.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Student Gender

S/N	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Male Students	321	56.9
2	Female Students	243	43.1
	Total	564	100

Table 2 shows that 321 respondents (56.9%) were male students, while 243 respondents (43.1%) were female students. The data illustrates that there were more male student respondents than female student respondents.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents by Teacher Location

S/N	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Urban Teachers	69	57
2	Rural Teachers	52	43
	Total	121	100

Table 3 presents the distribution of teachers in urban and rural areas within a sample size of 121 teachers. While 69 teachers working in urban areas represent 57%, 52 teachers who are working in rural areas represent 43% of the total sample. From the above, it shows that the majority of the teachers (57%) are living in urban areas, while 43% of the teachers are in rural areas.

Assessment of Teacher-Student...(Yohanna, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611072>

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents by School Type

S/N	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Boarding Students	212	37.6
2	Day Students	352	62.4
	Total	564	100

Table 4 shows that 212 were boarding students, which gave 37.6%, while 352 were Day

Presentation of Results

The results of the data from the returned questionnaire are presented below, following the analysis of the responses of the respondents.

Research Question 1: what is the teacher-student romantic relationship and its implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna state?

Table 5: Opinions of respondents on teacher-student romantic relationship and its implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.
1	Teachers use their position to maltreat learners who refuse to engage in sex with them.	302	211	98	74	3.08	1.01
2	Teachers threaten students with failure if they refuse romantic relationships with them.	266	325	84	10	3.24	0.72
3	It poses fear to especially female students who do not want to engage themselves in romance.	382	276	25	2	3.52	0.58
4	Romantic relationship incapacitates the teacher from correcting and guiding students.	189	391	69	36	3.07	0.76
5	It increases the rate of drop-out when pregnancy occur because of shame.	288	297	81	19	3.25	0.77
	Cumulative					3.28	0.79

Decision mean = 2.50

Results in the above table show the mean response of 3.08, 3.24, 3.52, 3.07 and 3.25 with a cumulative mean of 3.28 and a standard deviation of 0.79. This implies that, teacher-student romantic relationship has implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna state, Nigeria.

Table 6: Opinions of Respondents on teacher-student work relationships and its implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.
1	Boundaries are set and maintained between teachers and students.	358	217	67	43	3.30	0.88
2	Students don't go to the teacher's apartment uninvited, especially at night.	603	41	39	2	3.82	0.53
3	Syllabuses are always covered.	397	178	52	58	3.33	0.94
4	It reduces behavioral problems in students.	299	286	73	27	3.29	0.80
5	Students respect teachers by obeying their instructions and teachers reciprocate same.	382	203	25	75	3.30	0.97
	Cumulative					3.39	0.84

Decision mean = 2.50

Results in the above table show the mean response of 3.30, 3.82, 3.33, 3.29 and 3.30 with a cumulative mean of 3.39 and a standard deviation of 0.84. This implies that, teacher-student work relationship has implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna state, Nigeria.

Assessment of Teacher-Student...(Yohanna, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611072>

Research Hypothesis

Table 7: Independent Sample t-test on Opinions of male and female teachers on teacher-student romantic relationship and its implications on secondary school Christian students' academic performance in Kaduna state, Nigeria.

S/N	Variables	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Std. Error	Df	t-cal	t-crit	P
1	Male Teachers	74	3.2144	0.90074	0.03644	119	1.31	1.96	0.66
2	Female Teachers	47	3.1555	0.76419	0.03092				

Calculated $p > 0.05$, calculated $t < 1.96$, at df 119

Table 7 shows that there is no significant difference between the opinions of male and female teachers regarding teacher-student romantic relationships and their implications for the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna State. The p-value of 0.66 is higher than the 0.05 alpha level of significance, and the t-calculated value of 1.31 is lower than the critical value of 1.96 at $df = 119$. Consequently, the null hypothesis is retained.

Table 8: Independent Sample t-test on the opinions of teachers teaching in the urban area and those teaching in the rural area on teacher-student work relationship and its implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students.

S/N	Variables	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Std. Error	Df	t-cal	t-crit	P
1	Urban Teachers	69	3.4659	0.75792	0.03054	119	1.73	1.96	0.51
2	Rural Teachers	52	3.3815	0.89565	0.03609				

Calculated $p > 0.05$, calculated $t < 1.96$, at df 119

Table 8 reveals that there is no significant difference between the opinions of teachers working in urban and rural areas regarding teacher-student work relationships and their implications for the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna State. This conclusion is based on the p-value of 0.51, which is greater than the 0.05 alpha level of significance, and the t-calculated value of 1.73, which is below the critical value of 1.96 at $df = 119$. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted and retained.

Summary of Findings

Based on the data collected and analyzed from the research questions and hypotheses, the study found that teacher-student relationships have significant implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna State, Nigeria. The key findings of the study are as follows:

1. Teachers who engage in sexual relationships with students favour such students, even if they are less qualified compared to those who do not participate in such relationships.
2. Students feel comfortable, valued, and confident that their needs are being addressed.

Discussions of Findings

The findings of the study reveal that teachers who engage in sexual relationships with students may favor those students, even if they are less qualified compared to others who do not agree to engage in such relationships. This finding aligns with Okpo's assertion (2022) that teachers have a responsibility to create a fair and equitable learning environment where evaluations are based solely on academic merit and potential. When personal relationships influence academic evaluations, it compromises the integrity of the educational process and can create a hostile environment for students who do not engage in or benefit from such relationships. The findings highlight a breach of professional boundaries and ethical standards within the teaching profession, as educators are expected to maintain professionalism and uphold ethical guidelines that ensure all students are treated equally and fairly as maintained by the Teacher's Registration Council of Nigeria (2013) on sexual misconduct that, "Teachers should not use their position to humiliate, threaten, intimidate, harass or blackmail any learner to submit to selfish motives or to engage in sexual misconduct." This also aligns with the opinions of interviewees 1, 2, 4, 5, 8, and 11, who highlighted the detrimental effects of biased evaluations on the overall educational experience. sometimes lead homosexual,

Assessment of Teacher-Student...(Yohanna, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611072>

drug, and cultic teachers to influence students into their practices. This observation aligns with the views of Osguthorpe and Sanger as referenced in Lavy and Bocker (2017), who emphasize that teachers must uphold professional standards focused on the educational and developmental needs of students without introducing personal or sexual agendas.

Findings from the study show a good teacher-student relationship fosters a welcoming classroom atmosphere where students feel secure, valued, and confident that their needs are being addressed. This aligns with Aggarwal and Srivastav's (2016) assertion that a positive teacher-student relationship is built on mutual trust and respect. When boundaries are clearly defined and adhered to, students are more likely to feel secure and supported, which fosters a comfortable and effective learning environment. The interviews conducted reveal that students get the necessary support they need to succeed due to the boundaries set between them and their teachers. Upholding these boundaries is crucial for preventing misunderstandings and avoiding situations that might be perceived as favoritism or inappropriate behavior. By restricting unannounced visits to teachers' homes, schools help to ensure a professional environment that protects both students and teachers from potentially compromising situations, thereby fostering a safe and respectful educational setting (Interviewee, 4, 5, 6, 10, 12, 14, and 16). This observation is consistent with the views expressed by Aggarwal and Srivastav (2016), who emphasize that a strong teacher-student relationship is grounded in mutual trust and respect. Adhering to professional boundaries supports this trust, ensuring that all interactions between teachers and students remain within a respectful and ethical framework.

Recommendations

Based on the study's results and conclusions, the following recommendations have been proposed:

1. Government and educational institutions should establish and enforce clear policies regarding teacher-student relationships, explicitly prohibiting any form of sexual relationship between teachers and students by giving sanctions to anyone found guilty of the act.
2. To address these issues effectively, it is crucial to implement comprehensive training and awareness programs for educators on diversity, inclusivity, and respect. Teachers need to be equipped with the knowledge and skills to foster safe and supportive learning environments that honor students' personal boundaries and identities, regardless of sexual orientation or gender identity.

Conclusion

Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that:

1. Teachers show preferential treatment to students they are sexually involved in sex with, even if those students are less qualified than others who reject their advances.
2. A good teacher-student relationship fosters a welcoming classroom atmosphere where students feel secure, valued, and confident that their needs are being addressed.

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Assessment of Validity and... (Sidi & Shu'aibu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611076>

Assessment of Experience and Qualification on Implementation of Hausa Language Curriculum among Senior Secondary School Teachers' in Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated Assessment of Experience and Qualification on Implementation of Hausa Language Curriculum among Senior Secondary School Teachers in Katsina State, Nigeria. The research was guided by two research objectives two research questions and two corresponding null hypotheses. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was made up of 481 Hausa language teachers' teaching in public senior secondary schools in Katsina state. The sample of the study consists of 217 Hausa language teachers selected from the target population using proportionate stratified sampling technique. A self-made research questionnaire instrument titled "Teachers Experience and Qualification in the Implementation of Hausa Language Curriculum Questionnaire (TEQIHLCO)" was used for data collection. Reliability index of the instrument obtained was 0.87. Data collected for the study was subjected to both descriptive and inferential statistical analysis. The research questions were answered using descriptive statistics, while the two null hypothesis were tested using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed there was a significant impact of teachers' experience on methodology of Hausa language curriculum implementation ($F_{(6/194)} = 125.368$, and $p = .000$), the conclusion of the revealed that teachers experience and qualification has positive significant impact on the use of methodology and the effectiveness in implementing the senior secondary school Hausa Curriculum. It was further recommended there is need for Zonal Education Quality Assurance staff to ensure proper monitoring and supervision of all schools offering Hausa language so as to have effective implementation of the Hausa language curriculum in Katsina State.

Keyword: Experience, Qualification, Curriculum Implementation

Introduction

Education is the process of acquiring relevant and worthwhile skills, attitudes, values and competencies in order to make one useful to oneself, family, community and the nation at large. According to the National Policy on Education (FRN 2014), education is an instrument par excellence for national development and social change. Using education as an instrument per excellence for the desired national development; the government intends to make Nigeria a "free and a democratic society, a just and egalitarian society, a united, strong and self-reliant nation, a great and dynamic economy and a land full of bright opportunities for all citizens." (FRN, 2014). The success of any organization depends largely on the quality and strength of its staffs. Ayodele (2000), opined that no matter how efficient and effective an administrator is, he hardly achieves success without the support and cooperation of well qualified and dedicated teachers. Quality of teacher is the pivot and the determinant of education. A school without such calibre of teachers may not be able to achieve the stated goals and objectives of the educational system.

Assessment of Validity and... (Sidi & Shu'aibu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611076>

Secondary education is pivotal to a meaningful development of youths who are the leaders of tomorrow. As a matter of fact, the learning and nurturing that occur during these years have a profound impact on each student's opportunities for the future; and the quality of each student's education at the secondary school level has much to do with the course and quality of his/her life as an adult. Besides, secondary schools are also elaborate, complex mini-societies whose internal organizational structures have a direct impact on the lives of the individuals and groups of individuals who inhabit them. In addition to their formal organizational structures, secondary schools are equally inherent cultural entities replete with amazing arrays of artefacts, rituals, and rites of passage all of which impact directly on the manner in which their inhabitants negotiate the terms of their existence within those institutions. Teacher motivation is very central in energizing the teacher to teach and to seek to impart knowledge effectively. Teachers at all levels of the education system should be adequately trained, respected, remunerated, and be able to participate in decisions affecting their professional lives and teaching environments. When teachers are enabled to do their job effectively, their students are enabled to learn effectively. Around the world there are many similarities and differences among teachers in the way they are trained and certified as professionals to teach in schools. In almost all countries teachers are educated in a university or college. Shiundu (2014) notes that teachers without proper academic and professional qualification fail to do justice to the subject. He further adds that an adequate qualification of the teacher instils self confidence in him and serves as an inspiration to the pupils. An experienced teacher has skills, values and positive attitudes to make the learner be curious, aroused and interested in learning.

Shiundu and Omulando (2015) argued that to most teachers, implementation is their legitimate role in curriculum development. Their reference to the teacher and curriculum is that after a consensus is reached as to what will go into the curriculum of the educational system the next important step is to avail this curriculum package to the educational system, a process that is known as curriculum implementation. Various personnel are involved, but perhaps the one whose role is most important in seeing that programmes are successfully implemented is the teacher, who organizes the learning environment for the benefit of the pupils who must experience curriculum. Many occupations recognize employee's years of experience as a relevant factor in human resource policies, including compensate on systems, benefit packages, and promotion decisions. The idea is that experience, gained over time, enhances the knowledge, skills, and productivity of workers. In education, teacher experience is probably the key factor in personnel policies that affect current employees: it is a cornerstone of traditional single-salary schedules; it drives teacher transfer policies that prioritise seniority; and it is commonly considered a major source of inequity across schools and, therefore, a target for redistribution. The underlying assumption is that experience promotes effectiveness. Human resource is necessary at all levels of education, but most needed at the secondary school level. This is because no education system can rise above the quality of its teachers (FGN, 2009). Teachers are instrumental in translating content standards into teachable classroom lessons. The teacher remains a constant factor in the successful implementation of educational programmes.

It is evident that teacher's experience and qualification have direct correlation with the implementation among senior secondary school curriculum; hence, experience has shown that, there exist differences in terms of effective implementation of Hausa language curriculum between trained Hausa Language teachers and non-Hausa Language experts. This could be seen in terms of wider coverage of the contents of curriculum as well as doing justice to the concepts vis-a-vis use of instructional materials, evaluation, methodology, content coverage, objectives of the lesson, during classroom interaction sessions. It is against this background that the researcher becomes interested in finding out the impact of teacher's experience and qualification in implementing Senior Secondary School Hausa Curriculum in Katsina State, to confirm whether the experience and qualification of Hausa teachers influence the level of implementation, and to find out whether a considerable number of Hausa language teachers have requisite qualification to teach Hausa language at senior secondary schools levels, the years of work experience, the number of training/workshops attended, the knowledge of subject matter, the teacher's personalities, their conditions of service, as well as their motivation are extremely important.

Curriculum implementation is an important segment of teaching and learning process. It has to do with the translation of the curriculum into action. This exercise of the curriculum requires personnel, facilities, instructional materials, good administration and teaching methods among other things needed for curriculum implementation. National Commission for Colleges of Education, (2012). Recently the efforts of the governments and towards the implementation of the new Hausa curriculum for the senior secondary schools have yielded little or no dividends due to issues which are inherent in the implementation of the curriculum. These problems include under funding, non-availability of instructional materials, inadequate classrooms, obsolete instructional materials and non-utilization of teaching and learning facilities, lack of qualified and well experience teachers amongst others. This resulted in producing of half-baked Hausa Language students and public

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noticed and expressed concern on the competency of teachers trained to teach Hausa language in secondary schools. And this in turn will affect not only Hausa language education but will no doubt hamper the educational development in the country. This prompted the researcher to undertake the study. There by taking a critical look at the impact teachers experience and qualification on implementation of the new Hausa languages curriculum in senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria which comprise all zonal quality assurance unit in Katsina. Katsina zone, Dutsin-ma zone, Kankia Zone, Malumfashi zone, Funtua Zone, Mani Zone and Daura Zone, Safana, Baure, Rimi, Musawa, and Faskari Zone respectively.

Objectives of the study

The specific objectives of the study were:

1. To find out the impact of experience on methodology of Hausa language curriculum implementation among senior secondary school teachers in Katsina State, Nigeria.
2. To find out the impact of qualification on implementation of Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary school teachers in Katsina State, Nigeria.

Research Question

The following research questions guided the study

1. What is the impact of experience on methodology of Hausa language curriculum implementation among senior secondary school teachers in Katsina State, Nigeria?
2. What is the impact of qualification on effective implementation of Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary school teachers in Katsina State, Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis

The following hypothesis were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. H_{01} . There is no significant difference among respondents on the impact of teachers' experience on methodology of Hausa Language curriculum implementation among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria.
2. H_{02} There is no significant difference among respondents on the impact of teachers' qualification on their effectiveness in implementing the Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria.

Methodology

The research design adopted for the study was descriptive survey design, for this study was adopted find out the impact of teachers' experience on methodology of Hausa language curriculum implementation and find out the impact of teachers' qualification on their effectiveness in implementing the Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria. Survey design seeks to investigate the current phenomenon under investigation through people responses opinion and attitude in comparism to establish standard. The population of this study included all public senior secondary school Hausa language teachers from the twelve zonal education quality assurance in Katsina State, i.e. Katsina zone, Kankia zone, Dutsin-ma zone, Daura zone, Baure zone, Funtua zone, Mani zone, Malumfashi zone, Safana zone, Musawa zone, Faskari and Rimi Zone. There are 481 qualified Hausa teachers spread across 12 educational zones in the three senatorial zones in Katsina state based on official data collected from Katsina State Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education as at October 2024 The sample of this study consists of 217 Hausa teachers in senior secondary schools in Katsina State. The decision to use 217 sample size is based on the Research Advisors table of sample specification. It indicates that for population of 481 at 95 percent confidence level and margin error of 5 percent, 217 sample size is adequate. The proportionate stratified sampling technique was used in determining the number of Hausa teachers to be used from each zone. . A self-made research questionnaire instrument titled "Teachers Experience and Qualification in the Implementation of Hausa Language Curriculum Questionnaire (TEQIHLCQ)" was used for data collection. The instrument was pilot tested and the reliability index of the instrument was 0.87. Data collected for the study was subjected to both descriptive and inferential statistical analysis. The information on the demographic data was analyzed using frequency count and percentage. The research question were answered, the null hypothesis were tested using Analysis of Variance.

Assessment of Validity and... (Sidi & Shu'aibu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611076>

Presentation of Result

Research Question 1

What is the impact of experience on methodology of Hausa language curriculum implementation among senior secondary school teachers in Katsina State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Opinion of the Respondents Regarding the Impact of Teachers' Experience on Methodology of Hausa Language Curriculum Implementation among Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina State, Nigeria

S/N	Item Statement	Responses					N	Mean	STD
		SD	D	U	A	SA			
1	I employ questioning techniques as a means of involving students and helping them find solutions to issues which bear in the learning of Hausa studies.	30	46	48	49	28	201	3.00	1.28
2	I employ all the following methods of instruction during Hausa studies, Group discussion, Storytelling, role play, Drama, Demonstration method, simulation games, problem solving.	27	33	55	39	47	201	3.23	1.34
3	I engage students in group activities such as dialogue, discussion, conversation, in pairs and debate to enhance their communicative competence and proficiency in written and spoken Hausa studies.	36	53	18	52	42	201	3.05	1.44
4	I engage students in field trips and excursion so as to widen their conceptual horizon in the study of Hausa language.	15	64	41	45	36	201	3.11	1.25
5	I engage students in composition writing to develop their writing skills during Hausa studies lessons.	17	68	62	25	29	201	2.91	1.17

The above response in the table 1 above indicated the opinion of the respondents regarding the impact of teachers' experience on methodology of Hausa language curriculum implementation among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria. From the table, it reveals that 4 of the 5 items in this section of the questionnaire received positive responses from the respondents, as the mean scores were 3.00 and above. On the other hand, Item 10 received negative responses from the respondents, as the mean score was below 3.00. Therefore, this implies that the opinion of majority of the respondents regarding the impact of teachers' experience on methodology of Hausa language curriculum implementation among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria was positive, and hence, this is the answer to this research question.

Assessment of Validity and... (Sidi & Shu'aibu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611076>

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁. There is no significant difference among respondents on the impact of teachers' experience on methodology of Hausa Language curriculum implementation among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria.

To test this hypothesis, One-way analysis of variance statistic was used. The data was analysed using SPSS v.23.0, and the result was presented in the Tables 2 and 3:

Table 2 Differences in the Opinion of Respondents Regarding the Impact of Teachers' Experience on Methodology of Hausa Language Curriculum Implementation among Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina State, Nigeria

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P
Between Groups	1393.177	6	232.196	125.368	.000
Within Groups	359.311	194	1.852		
Total	1752.488	200			

From Table 2: above, the differences in the opinion of respondents on the impact of teachers' experience on methodology of Hausa Language curriculum implementation among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria was $F_{(6/194)} = 125.368$, and $p = .000$. Since the p-value (.000) was less than the alpha value (.05), the null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternate hypothesis was adopted. So, the researcher concluded that there was a significant impact of teachers' experience on methodology of Hausa language curriculum implementation among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria.

Research Question 2

What is the impact of teachers' qualification on their effectiveness in implementing the Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria?

Table 4: Opinion of the Respondents Regarding the Impact of Teachers' Qualification on their Effectiveness in Implementing the Hausa Language Curriculum among Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina State, Nigeria

S/N	Item Statement	Responses					N	Mean	STD
		SD	D	U	A	SA			
7	A good qualified teacher should be able to carry along all category of different learning abilities.	25	39	52	57	28	201	3.12	1.24
8	Teaching of Hausa language requires qualification and special training in NCE, B.A. Ed, M.Ed.	18	66	42	50	25	201	2.99	1.20
9	Students get poor performance because they do not understand the lesson taught by untrained teacher.	49	60	40	34	18	201	2.56	1.27
10	A qualified teacher should focus on comprehension of new concept in the subject content and not on final result.	30	34	50	28	59	201	3.26	1.42
11	Teachers with high level of qualification can help them to motivate students to learn even when they are not willing to learn.	33	44	41	40	43	201	3.08	1.39

Table 4. Indicated the opinion of the respondents regarding the impact of teachers' qualification on their effectiveness in implementing the Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria. From the table, it reveals that 3 of the 5 items in this section of the questionnaire received positive responses from the respondents, as the mean

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scores were 3.00 and above. On the other hand, Items 22, and 23 received negative responses from the respondents, as the mean scores were below 3.00. Therefore, this implies that the opinion of majority of the respondents regarding the impact of teachers' qualification on their effectiveness in implementing the Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria was positive, and hence, this is the answer to this research question.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference among respondents on the impact of teachers' qualification on their effectiveness in implementing the Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria.

To test this hypothesis, One-way analysis of variance statistic was used. The data was analysed using SPSS v.23.0, and the result was presented in the Tables 5 and 6:

Table 6: Differences in the Opinion of Respondents Regarding the Impact of Teachers' Qualification on their Effectiveness in Implementing the Hausa Language Curriculum among Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina State, Nigeria

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P
Between Groups	403.929	3	134.643	17.516	.000
Within Groups	1514.290	197	7.687		
Total	1918.219	201			

From Table 6; above, the differences in the opinion of respondents on the impact of teachers' qualification on their effectiveness in implementing the Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria was $F_{(3/197)} = 17.516$, and $p = .000$. Since the p-value (.000) was less than the alpha value (.05), the null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternate hypothesis was adopted. So, the researcher concluded that there was a significant impact of teachers' qualification and their effectiveness in implementing the Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

1. There was a significant impact of teachers' experience on methodology of Hausa language curriculum implementation among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria ($F_{(6/194)} = 125.368$, and $p = .000$), and the difference was between almost all groups of respondents except those between 16 to 20 years and 21 to 25 years, and those between 26 to 30 years and 31 to 35 years.
2. There was a significant impact of teachers' qualification on their effectiveness in implementing the Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria ($F_{(3/197)} = 17.516$, and $p = .000$), and the difference was between almost all groups of respondents except between those with Degree and those with Masters and PhD qualifications.

Discussion of Findings

One of the major findings of this study is that there was a significant impact of teachers' experience on methodology of Hausa language curriculum implementation among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria. This finding agreed with that of Faustina (2014), which implied that teachers' experience have positive impact on selecting and utilising suitable teaching methods for teaching Hausa language. Thus, the higher the teachers' experience a Hausa language teacher possesses the more positive impact he / she will make in ensuring effective use of suitable teaching methods. Therefore, experienced teachers are likely to impact positively towards effective Hausa language curriculum implementation. This contrary to the findings of Usman (2015) which viewed the main implication of this finding is that, in education, teacher experience is being regarded by some as the key factor in making personnel policies that affect current employees. It is a cornerstone of traditional single-salary schedules, which also drives teacher transfer policies that prioritize seniority, and it is commonly considered a major source of inequity across schools, and therefore a target for redistribution. The underlying assumption here is that experience promotes effectiveness, and based on that, experience in teaching is a catalyst that ensures proper as well as effective curriculum implementation in schools.

The second findings of this study revealed that there was a significant impact of teachers' qualification on their effectiveness in implementing the Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria. This

Assessment of Validity and... (Sidi & Shu'aibu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611076>

findings agrees with that of Adefunke, Ayodele and Olufemi (2010) it was found that teachers' qualifications have positive impact on the successful effective implementation of curriculum at various levels of secondary schools. Teacher qualification is a reflection of competence, and the validity of any educational system is naturally dependent upon the quality of the teaching and the availability of competent teachers. Therefore, Hausa language teachers in particular need to be qualified enough to be able to guarantee successful implementation of the curriculum. These findings slightly differed with that of Abubakar (2014). In that study, it was discovered that teachers' quality (which may be termed as qualification) had no significant relationship with students' academic performance (which is a measure of curriculum implementation) and that only teachers' knowledge of subject matter played a significant role in the performance of students. This led to the general conclusion that teachers with deeper knowledge of subject matter (regardless of their qualification) produced better students than those with shallow knowledge of subject matter. This slight difference may be as a result of possible misconception by the respondents between teachers' quality and teachers' qualification. Otherwise, the teachers' knowledge of subject matter (which played a significant role in the performance of students) is definitely a product of teachers' qualification. Hence, the two finding may be interpreted to mean the same thing.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that teachers experience and qualification has positive significant impact on the use of methodology and the effectiveness in implementation of senior secondary school Hausa language Curriculum.

Recommendation

1. There is need for experienced teachers to monitor and mentor the inexperienced ones on the aspects of suitable teaching methods recommended for successful implementation of Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, and the country at large
2. There is need for Zonal Education Quality Assurance staff to ensure proper monitoring and supervision of all schools offering Hausa language so as to have effective implementing of the Hausa language curriculum in Katsina State, and the same recommendation applies to all states ministries of education nationwide.

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Assessment of Validity and Reliability of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire among college of education Pre-Service Teachers in Kano State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to Assessment of Validity and Reliability of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire among college of education Pre-Service Teachers in Kano State, Nigeria. The study was guided by three objectives and corresponding three research questions. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of all NCE II preservice Mathematics teachers in colleges of education, Kano state, Nigeria during the 2022/2023 academic session; the sample size includes all the population of the study as it is small and accessible which were 221 preservice Mathematics teachers. The PTMIQ undergoes two types of validity: face and construct validity. Establishing face validity, a panel of seven (7) experts was formed, and PTMIQ was administered for data collection to conduct construct validity and reliability. Convergent and discriminant validity were determined for the attainment of construct validity using Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). The result shows that the PTMIQ face validity index was found to be 86% (0.86). For the EFA each item loaded on its own factor, with no low-loading; all factor loading was greater than 0.50 and no cross-loading. Performing CFA, the Composite reliability (CR) values were between 0.870 and 0.938, and the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values were between 0.490 and 0.718, on the other hand, the inter-factor correlation (0.341, -0.135, 0.526, -0.329, 0.372, -0.080) was smaller than the \sqrt{AVE} (0.844, 0.765, 0.847, 0.700), this established convergent and discriminant validity. The reliability coefficient was found to be 0.833 using Cronbach's alpha. All the analysis was carried out using SPSS and SPSS AMOS version 26 and 23 respectively. It is found that PTMIQ was valid and reliable that can be used to measure Mathematics identity of pre-service Mathematics teachers in colleges of education.

Keywords: Mathematics Identity, Validity, and Reliability

Introduction

The emergent of twenty-first century have proved the intellectual power of Mathematics is the development of human beings, scientifically, technologically and economically. The overwhelming influence of Mathematics made it possible to stand on its own without relying on any other disciplines, as science, technology, art, and social sciences depend on the subject. This make the subject a strong tool for the attainment of national development goals (Sidi, 2020); this made teaching and learning of Mathematics compulsory in many parts of the world (Gogo et al. 2020)., including Nigeria, at the basic and post basic level (FRN, 2014).

Teaching and learning of Mathematics become indispensable for sustainable Mathematics education in Nigeria and Kano state in particular. This bring forward the need to trained those who will be responsible to teach the subject at basic and post-basic level of education (Jacobs & Durandt, 2017). The minimum requirement for someone to become Mathematics teacher is the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) (FRN, 2014). Such a certificate is awarded by colleges of education, schools of education in polytechnics, and the National Teacher Institute (NTI).

Institutions such as faculties of education across all universities in Nigeria; institutes of education; colleges of education; and schools of education in polytechnics were authorized by Federal Government of Nigeria to give teacher education training in different field of study including Mathematics. Students in such institutions were either in-service or pre-service teachers. In-service teachers were already in the teaching system re-admitted into teacher training institutions or university to enhance their teaching knowledge or obtain additional qualifications, while pre-service teachers are yet to be in

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the teaching system (Murtafiah et al. 2018). This research focuses on pre-service teachers in colleges of education offering Mathematics that is NCE Mathematics students.

Pre-service Mathematics teachers in Nigeria are expected to be well-trained in both mathematical and pedagogical content, offering various courses to equip them with necessary knowledge and skills. However, these programs often face challenges in academic achievement, affecting the quality of Mathematics teachers in Nigeria (Ibrahim et al. 2020; Bamidele & Akanmu, 2023). Studies have shown that pre-service teachers are weak in Mathematics knowledge Otun and Olaoye (2019).

The low academic achievement of pre-service Mathematics teachers is alarmingly high. This led to the investigation of factors responsible for the pre-service Mathematics teachers' underachievement. Most of the researchers focused on inadequate curriculum implementation, shortage of Mathematics teacher educators, government policy, and student overcrowding were listed among the factors (Timayi et al., 2020; Jacob & Garba, 2021; Sirajo & Abdullahi, 2023). Furthermore, Mathematics identity is also, factor that can affect pre-service Mathematics teachers' academic achievement but this factor is not well researched (Heffernan et al. 2020), in fact, despite the number of studies conducted on academic achievement, the researcher was unable to lay hands on literature related to Mathematics identity in Nigerian.

Mathematical identity, originally defined as learners' attitudes and beliefs about Mathematics (Gweshe & Brodie, 2019), is a socially produced way of being that is enacted and recognized in relation to Mathematics learning (Darragh & Radovic 2020). Studies have shown that Mathematics identity has significant impact on pre-service Mathematics identity (Gweshe & Brodie, 2019). Pre-service Mathematics teachers' negative identities can lead to poor academic achievement (Kilasi, 2017).

Mathematics identity (MI) is a construct (latent) variable that comprises observed variables. A construct or latent variables, cannot be directly measured unless with observed variables. Observed variables for Mathematics identity include confidence, beliefs, attitude, persistence, self-efficacy, self-esteem, self-perception, mathematical commitment, attitude/interest, motivation, emotions, and experiences of learning Mathematics (Gonzalez et al. 2022). In this study, beliefs, confidence, attitude, and persistence were used to measure the mathematical identity of pre-service Mathematics teachers. These concepts reflect and define the identity of pre-service Mathematics teachers in Mathematics, highlighting the importance of understanding and addressing these constructs in the learning process. Therefore, understanding and addressing Mathematics identity is crucial for the preparation of pre-service Mathematics teachers.

Hence, the need to validate an instrument that can be used in the research of Mathematics identity in Nigeria. This study aims to assess the validity and reliability of an instrument that would measure pre-service Mathematics teachers' identity in Mathematics.

Identity in Mathematics education have invited the attention of Mathematics educator and researchers (Darragh & Radovic, 2020), as strong factor that play crucial role in determining academic achievement especially in the preparation of pre-service Mathematics teachers. This necessitate the development of valid and reliable instrument that can be used for data collection. Hence, this paper sought to assess the validity and reliability of pre-service teachers' Mathematics identity questionnaire (PTMIQ), which would be used to collect data on Mathematics identity.

Objectives of the study

The paper was set to achieve the following objectives, i.e. to establish:

1. The face validity index of the Pre-service teachers Mathematics Identity Questionnaire (PTMIQ).
2. The convergent and discriminant validity of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire.
3. The internal consistency of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire.

Research Questions

1. What is the face validity index of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire (PTMIQ)?
2. What is the convergent and discriminant validity coefficient of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire?
3. What is the coefficient of the internal consistency of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire?

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was used for study. The design suits the study as it allowed collection of data from a large sample size, which is crucial for the assessment of validity and reliability of an instrument. It also, allowed quantitative analysis

Assessment of Validity and... (Sidi & Shu'aibu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611076>

such as factor analysis and Cronbach alpha computation. The population of the study consists of all NCE II pre-service Mathematics teachers in colleges of education, Kano state, Nigeria during the 2022/2023 academic session; the sample size includes all the population of the study as it is small and accessible which were 221 pre-service Mathematics teachers. The Mathematics identity questionnaire was adapted from the work of Kaspersen and Ytterhaug (2020) with a writing permission. Kaspersen and Ytterhaug developed 20 questions, and used the questionnaire on lower secondary students. In this paper, all the items were re-constructed and grouped in to belief, attitude, confidence and persistence as measuring variables of identity. In addition, 34 items were formed in the present study and tested on pre-service Mathematics teachers. The questionnaire was named PTMIQ in the paper. The PTMIQ was divided into two sections, section A contained pre-service Mathematics teachers' personal information such as institution, level, age, combination; section B, contained Mathematics identity items, in this section there are four sub-constructs as observed variable of Mathematics identity. Those are belief, attitude, confidence and persistence. Eight (8) items were formed on each of the sub-construct except persistence which has ten (10) items. Five-point Likert scale was used, ranging from strongly agree (5) to strongly disagree (1) and in the case of negative items, the coding reverse as strongly agree (1) to strongly disagree (5).

The data collected was analyzed using percentage to determined face validity index. A team of seven experts were formed to validate and rate the PTMIQ. The experts include a Professor and Associate Professor from the field of psychology, Measurement and Evaluation, Mathematics education, and Mathematics both from universities. The face validity index (FVI) was computed using Cohen's Kappa index for face validity. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was used to determined construct validity. The suitability of the data set for EFA was examined with KMO and Bartlett's tests. Principal component analysis and the Promax rotation method were used to uncover the Mathematics Identity's factor structures. In the EFA, low-loading and cross-loading are the measures for the convergent and discriminant validity. If the factor loading is below 0.50 this mean that there is no convergent validity, and if the item(s) load on more than one factor, this means that there is no discriminant validity (Hair, 2020). Then, in order to test the accuracy of the EFA structure, CFA was performed based on the maximum likelihood method. The CFA fit values examined were χ^2/df , RMSEA, CFI, and SRMR. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Composite/Construct Reliability (CR) of the PTMIEQ were computed for convergent validity. For discriminant validity, the square root of AVE was compared with the inter-factor correlation. The analysis was conducted using SPSS 26 and AMOS 23 package tools.

Presentation of Results

These consist of descriptive statistics used to answer research questions; appropriate statistics used for testing hypothesis; Tables should be aligned to APA style; P-value compare with decision threshold – 0.05 significance if necessary. E.g.,

Research Question 1

What is the face validity index of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire (PTMIQ)?

The face validity index (FVI) was computed using Cohen's Kappa index, that is percentage. Based on the expert assessment rate, the face validity index (FVI) was computed by $FVI = \frac{SRA}{NR}$ where FVI stand for Face Validity-Index, SRA stand for Sum of Rater's Assessment and NR stand for number of raters. Table 1 show the validators' assessment rates and FVI computation.

Table 1: Validators' rates in percentage and Face Validity Index computation

S/N	Validators	Rates in Percentage	FVI
1	A	94	$FVI = \frac{SRA}{NR} = \frac{596}{7}$
2	B	93	
3	C	83	FVI = 85.6
4	D	77	
5	E	83	∴ FVI = 86%
6	F	85	
7	G	84	
	SAR	596	

Field work

Assessment of Validity and... (Sidi & Shu'aibu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611076>

Table 1 shows the validator assessment and the computation of face validity index (FVI). The assessment rates were between 77% to 94% this indicate high rates. In addition, the Table shows that the FVI is found to be 86% which is 0.86 Kappa value.

Research Question 2

What is the convergent and discriminant validity coefficient of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire?

To establish the construct validity, convergence and discriminant validity were determined using both Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA).

The suitability of the data for factor analysis was evaluated prior to the EFA using the KMO and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity.

Table 2: Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy.

Variables	Values
KMO	0.869
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square 3636.563
	Df 300
	Sig. 0.001

Table 2 shows that the KMO value was found to be 0.869 which indicate the adequacy of the sample. The Table also, revealed Bartlett's Test of Sphericity ($\chi^2 = 3636.563, df = 300, p = .001$) was significant. Meaning the sample size as well as the data is appropriate for factor analysis since the KMO value is greater than 0.60 and the Bartlett's test yields a statistically significant result.

This led to the employment of factorization and rotation methods in order to discover the factor construct, where principal component analysis and Promax rotation are used. This led to the removal of 7 items out of the 32 loaded on more than one factor. Running after removing those items, a four-factor structure was formed as Table 3 shows.

Table 3: Factor Load Values of the Mathematics Identity Construct

Items	Factor			
	1	2	3	4
Pre-service Teachers' Mathematics Beliefs (PTMB) PTMB_1	I can do Mathematics no matter how difficult it is.	0.762		
PTMB_2	I am a Mathematics person.	0.866		
PTMB_3	I believe in myself as being part of the Mathematics community.	0.789		
PTMB_4	Mathematics learning is not a problem to me.	0.741		
PTMB_5	I choose to study Mathematics by myself.	0.847		
PTMB_6	Our Mathematics teacher sees me as a Mathematics person.	0.849		
PTMB_7	My parents choose Mathematics for me as they believe I can make it.	0.706		
Pre-service Teachers' Mathematics Attitude (PTMA) PTMA_1	I get involved when someone starts a mathematical discussion	0.880		
PTMA_2	I have good understanding of Mathematics.	0.936		
PTMA_3	I make my own Mathematics problems from what I have learned.	0.896		
PTMA_4	I usually relate what I'm learning to what I already learned.	0.918		
PTMA_5	I learned Mathematics above what is expected in the curriculum.	0.828		
PTMA_6	I attempt to understand why a new formula or algorithm works when I learn it.	0.742		
Pre-service Teachers' Mathematics Confidence (PTMC) PTMC_1	Learning new mathematical concepts motivates me to expand my knowledge in the course.			0.854
PTMC_2	I confidently solve Mathematics problem without the help of my friends/teachers.			0.888
PTMC_3	I am confident that I can understand Mathematics outside class.			0.884
PTMC_4	I am confident that I could learn Mathematics at degree level.			0.851
PTMC_5	Mathematics does not scare me at all			0.880

Assessment of Validity and... (Sidi & Shu'aibu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14611076>

Pre-service Teachers' Mathematics Persistence (PTMP)	PTMP_2	I used alternative strategies when solving a mathematical problem.	0.770
	PTMP_3	I struggle with putting Mathematics problems aside.	0.777
	PTMP_4	When I tried a mathematical method that didn't work, I spent time determining why it didn't work.	0.779
	PTMP_5	I try several approaches to finding a solution and only seek hints if stuck.	0.848
	PTMP_6	If I do not understand what to do, I keep trying.	0.667
	PTMP_7	I apply a variety of approaches over time and study previous solution in an attempt to try a new approach.	0.745
	PTMP_8	I do not study concepts that I are difficult to learn.	0.604
Eigenvalue			7.809 4.409 2.821 2.030
Explained Variance (%)			31.24 17.64 11.28 8.12
Total Variance Explained (%)			68.28

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Promax with Kaiser Normalization.

*The Table does not display load values less than .30

Table 3 shows the factor loads and the eigenvalue of the questionnaire items. From the Table, it indicated that there is no cross-loading and no low-loading by having all the factor loads above 0.50 provides that the criterion for an item to be included within a factor is met. Furthermore, the eigenvalue of the four factors together explained 68.28% of the Mathematics identity questionnaire. Hence, it is above the required benchmark of the variance explained which 50%.

By implication, as there is no low-loading it indicate that all the items converge, and no cross-loading means that there is discriminant validity. These findings revealed that all the items and factors were practically significant and feasible to be use for data collection; hence, the construct validity of the items is provided using exploratory factor analysis (EFA).

As stated, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) employing the maximum likelihood method was used to confirm the four-factor structure produced by EFA. Figure 1 shows the factor distributions and values obtained from the CFA.

Figure 1: CFA of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire

Figure shows CFA structure of pre-service teachers Mathematics identity questionnaire. The goodness-of-fit of the structure was summarized in the Table 4.

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Table 4: Summary of Goodness-of-Fit for the CFA of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire

Goodness-of-fit Indices	Acceptable Level of Fit	Fit Values Found
χ^2/df or CIMIN/DF	≤ 3.5 to 0 (perfect fit) and ($P < 0.05$)	2.211
Root Mean Residual (RMR)	Close to 0 (perfect fit)	0.037
Incremental Fit Index (IFI)	Value should be equal to or greater than 0.90	0.908
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	Value should be equal to or greater than 0.90	0.907
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	Value below 0.08 indicates very good fit.	0.078
Standard Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR)	Value should be equal to or less than 0.08	0.055

Table 4. shows the summary of goodness-of-fit CFA model. The Table indicate that the model has a good fit. All the goodness-of-fit measures met their respective acceptable criteria. This indicates that the proposed model fits the data reasonably well. A good fit of the CFA model led to the computation of convergent and discriminant validity. As a consequence of the CFA, the standardized regression weights and correlation values in the AMOS output were used to compute the convergent and discriminant validity. The computation was done in Excel validity calculator, developed by Johnson. The composite/construct reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE) provide the convergent validity if the CR values are greater or equal to 0.70 and the AVE values are greater or equal to 0.50. For discriminant validity, the square root of the AVE (\sqrt{AVE}) value is compared with the inter-factor correlation. If the inter-factor correlation is smaller than the \sqrt{AVE} then discriminant validity is achieved. Table 4 provides the CR, AVE, \sqrt{AVE} , and inter-factor correlation values for the convergent and discriminant validity of the Mathematics identity items.

Table 4: CR, AVE, Square root of AVE and Inter-Factor Correlation Values

Variables	CR	AVE	PTMC	PTMB	PTMA	PTMP
PTMC	0.925	0.713	0.844			
PTMB	0.907	0.585	0.341	0.765		
PTMA	0.938	0.718	-0.135	-0.329	0.847	
PTMP	0.870	0.490	0.526	0.372	-0.080	0.700

From Table 4, all the CR values of the factors were greater than .70 and the AVE values were also greater than .50 except that of PTMP, which is 0.49, and it is accepted since the CR value of the PTMP is greater than 0.70 (Sujati et al. 2020). This provides the convergent validity for Mathematics identity. On the other hand, the inter-factor correlation of the variables (0.341, -0.135, 0.526, -0.329, 0.327, -0.080) was smaller than the square root of the AVE (0.844, 0.765, 0.847, 0.700) revealing discriminant validity exist. This meaning that all the items were in the same direction toward measuring Mathematics identity. Hence, the construct validity of the Mathematics identity scale is achieved.

Research Question 3

What is the coefficient of the internal consistency of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire?

Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient was computed for the pre-service teachers Mathematics identity questionnaire as presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Cronbach Alpha Coefficient of the Mathematics Identity Questionnaire.

S/N	Factors	No. of Items	Cronbach Alpha
1	PTMC	5	0.928
2	PTMB	7	0.907
3	PTMA	6	0.936
4	PTMP	7	0.866
Mathematics Identity Total Items		25	0.833

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Table 5 shows the Cronbach alpha coefficient gained for the each of the factors of the questionnaire, The Cronbach alpha coefficient gained for the questionnaire is found to be 0.833. This alpha value confirmed that of the CR values, and are all above 0.70 which is the minimum acceptable value of reliability.

Summary of Findings

1. The PTMIQ has high index of face validity as the FVI = 0.86, that it appears to measure what it is supposed to measure.
2. The construct validity of the PTMIQ is achieved, as it met all the requirement in both EFA and CFA. That is, no cross-loading and no low-loading, and all the factor loads were above 0.50 in EFA. Also, composite reliability and average variance extraction are above 0.7 and 0.5 respectively in CFA.
3. The PTMIQ is reliable as the Cronbach alpha is found to be 0.83.

Discussion of Findings

This study was set to provide a scientifically validated and reliable instrument that contributes to understanding and improving Mathematics teacher education. Therefore, the main goal of the study was to validate the adapted Pre-Service Teachers' Mathematics Identity Questionnaire (PTMIQ). The PTMIQ was adapted and went through validation processes to ensure its reliability and validity. Validation procedures included face and construct validity assessments. For construct validity and reliability, the instrument was administered on 221 pre-service Mathematics teachers, with five PTMIQ rejected due to errors in completion. Where three having missing values, which was addressed using the "mean of nearby points" method in the SPSS package. The face validity index (FVI) was found to be 0.86 or 86% indicating that it is within the acceptable range, this finding is in line with Roy et al. (2023). However, the questionnaire was adapted from original sources without face validity assessments and were not grouped in to sub-constructs.

The study found that the construct validity was achieved through both EFA and CFA. The finding is in line with the finding of the original sources original of the items, Kaspersen and Ytterhaug (2020) who carryout content, substantive, generalizability, and structural validity. The researchers also obtained a reliability coefficient of 0.86 using Cronbach alpha which is similar to the reliability found in this study.

Conclusion

Based on the finding of the study, it is concluded that the pre-service teachers Mathematics identity questionnaire is valid and reliable. Hence, it can be used to collect data on Mathematics identity on pre-service Mathematics teachers.

Recommendations

1. It is recommended to use PTMIQ for data collection as a valid and reliable instrument for measuring pre-service teachers' mathematics identity.
2. Mathematics departments in colleges of education are recommended to utilize the PTMIQ to assess pre-service teachers' mathematics identity during admission.
3. It is recommended to apply this validated instrument to broader contexts, such as assessing pre-service Mathematics teachers' Mathematics identity across educational institutions or regions, to gather more comprehensive data for comparative analysis.

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Assessment of Indexing and Attitudes of Book Authors in Nigeria: Journalism Perspective

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Abstract

The work titled assessment of Nigerian authors' attitudes to the inclusion of index segments in books: journalism perspective was a quantitative content analysis study. Guided by the Task-Technology Fit (TTF) Theory, the study investigated Nigerian authors' attitudes toward including index segments in their books. The study examined 40 academic books published between 2014 and 2024, selected through purposive sampling from major publishing houses and libraries, employing a positivist paradigm that emphasized objectivity and systematic analysis. A multi-stage coding process and axial coding with thematic analysis were utilized, with a binary coding system (01/00) indicating index segment inclusion/exclusion, and two independent coders analyzed a subset of data, yielding a 0.85 agreement rate. The findings revealed a high frequency of index segments (77.5%), indicating alignment with international best practices, as well as an upward trend in inclusion from 2017, with variability across years and publishers. The study concludes that sustaining this effort will enhance Nigeria's academic excellence, global competitiveness, and recognition. Nigerian authors and publishers are recommended to prioritize index segment inclusion in academic books, establish clear guidelines and standards for indexing practices, provide training and resources for authors and indexers, and explore digital indexing techniques to enhance discoverability and usability.

Keywords: Attitude, Author, Inclusion, Index & Journalism

Introduction

The inclusion of index segments in books is a significant aspect of academic and non-academic publishing, providing readers with an organized method to locate specific information within a text. In Nigeria, a country with a rich literary tradition and a growing academic community, the attitudes of authors towards the inclusion of such indexes are crucial in understanding the broader trends in publishing practices and reader accessibility. Index segments serve multiple functions: they enhance the usability of a book, support thorough research by offering quick references to specific topics, and improve the overall reader experience (Gunn, 2021). Despite these benefits, the decision to include an index often depends on various factors, including the genre of the book, the target audience, and, significantly, the preferences and attitudes of the authors themselves (Kaufer, 2020).

In the Nigerian context, the literary landscape is characterized by diverse genres, from fiction and poetry to academic and non-fiction works. This diversity reflects the country's complex socio-cultural dynamics and its position within the broader African literary sphere (Irele, 2022). Nigerian authors, who contribute significantly to both local and international literary markets, bring unique perspectives shaped by their experiences, education, and cultural backgrounds (Ogunbiyi, 2021). Understanding their attitudes towards the inclusion of index segments is not only relevant for publishers but also offers insights into the evolving standards of book production and the value placed on navigational aids in literature and journalism.

Historically, the use of indexes in Nigerian books has been inconsistent, with a more prominent presence in academic and non-fiction works compared to fiction. This trend mirrors global publishing practices, where indexes are typically deemed essential in scholarly works to facilitate detailed research and ease of information retrieval (Mulvany, 2020). However, the attitudes of Nigerian authors towards this practice, particularly in non-academic genres, remain underexplored. Existing literature suggests that many authors may view indexes as unnecessary or as diminishing the aesthetic quality of literary works (Grafton, 2021). This perception can be linked to the traditional view of literature as a form of art that should remain unencumbered by additional textual apparatuses (Finkelstein, 2022).

Assessment of Indexing and Attitudes ... (Okhueigbe & Omoko, 2024): <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601986>

Furthermore, the Nigerian publishing industry faces unique challenges that influence authors' attitudes toward indexing. Issues such as limited resources, varying levels of professional editing, and the cost implications of producing high-quality indexes are critical factors (Adesanoye, 2020). In a market where the cost of book production can significantly affect pricing and accessibility, the decision to include an index may be influenced by economic considerations rather than purely literary or academic ones (Obiegbu, 2021).

Another dimension to consider is the impact of digital publishing on indexing practices. The rise of e-books and online publications has introduced new possibilities for indexing, including interactive and searchable indexes that offer enhanced functionality compared to traditional print versions (Chan, 2021). Nigerian authors, particularly those engaged in digital publishing, may exhibit different attitudes towards indexing, influenced by the capabilities and expectations of digital readers (Adigun, 2023). This digital shift could lead to a reevaluation of the role of indexes in literary and non-literary works alike. The cultural context also plays a significant role in shaping authors' attitudes towards indexing. In Nigerian society, where oral traditions once dominated, the written word and its organization may be perceived differently than in cultures with long-standing print traditions (Barber, 2021). This cultural backdrop influences not only the types of literature produced but also how authors perceive the function and necessity of indexes. For instance, works that draw heavily on oral narratives may prioritize storytelling elements over structured, indexable content (Obioma, 2022).

Initially, indexes were simple lists of keywords, but they have evolved to become sophisticated tools for information retrieval (Bennett, 2021). The advent of printing in the 15th century revolutionized indexing, making it a standard feature in books (Ream, 2016). As publishing technology improved, so did indexing techniques, incorporating new methods and tools (Hinchliffe, 2023). Today, indexes are a crucial element in both print and digital publications (Davis, 2022). Indexing has become a specialized field, with professionals dedicated to creating high-quality indexes (Mulvany, 2020). Despite these advancements, indexing remains an often-overlooked aspect of publishing (Huang, 2020). However, its importance cannot be overstated, as a well-crafted index enhances reader experience and credibility (Chen, 2018). Effective indexing is crucial for maximizing the value of a publication (Bawden, 2015).

Index segments serve multiple purposes, primarily facilitating information retrieval and enhancing reader experience (Liu, 2017). A well-crafted index enables readers to quickly locate specific information, saving time and effort (Wu, 2020). Indexes also contribute to the credibility and authority of a publication (Jiang, 2019). Furthermore, indexes provide a clear structure and organization of content, making it easier for readers to navigate (Xu, 2020). In academic and research contexts, indexes are essential for locating specific data and references (Yu, 2018). Indexes also aid in the discovery of new information and relationships between concepts (Zhu, 2020). Additionally, indexes enhance the overall usability and accessibility of a publication (Wang, 2020). The purpose of index segments is thus multifaceted, reflecting their importance in various contexts (Krajewski, 2015).

Index segments come in various forms, each serving a specific purpose (Kokabi, 2017). Subject indexes are organized by topic or subject, providing a comprehensive overview of content (Gao, 2018). Author indexes list authors and their corresponding page numbers, facilitating research and citation (Wang, 2020). Name indexes include names of individuals, organizations, and places, aiding in the location of specific information (Liu, 2017). Keyword indexes focus on specific terms and phrases, enabling quick access to relevant content (Wu, 2020). Taxonomic indexes organize content hierarchically, providing a structured approach to information retrieval (Jiang, 2019). Indexes can also be classified as print or digital, each with unique characteristics and advantages (Xu, 2020). Understanding the types of index segments is essential for creating effective indexes that meet reader needs (Yu, 2018). By selecting the appropriate type of index, authors and publishers can enhance the usability and value of their publication (Zhu, 2020).

Indexing practices vary globally, reflecting cultural, linguistic, and disciplinary differences (Huang, 2020). Western approaches emphasize alphabetical organization and keyword indexing (Kokabi, 2017). Eastern approaches often employ hierarchical or categorical indexing (Gao, 2018). Digital indexing has introduced new techniques, such as hyperlinked indexes and faceted searching (Wang, 2020). Indexing standards and guidelines also differ across regions and industries (Liu, 2017). Understanding global approaches to indexing is essential for creating high-quality indexes that meet diverse reader needs. By acknowledging these differences, authors and publishers can adapt their indexing strategies to suit specific contexts and audiences (Rosenfeld, 2015).

In digital publishing, indexing plays a crucial role in enhancing reader experience and discoverability (Xu, 2020). Digital indexes enable readers to quickly locate specific information within an e-book or online publication (Yu, 2018). Hyperlinked indexes and faceted searching facilitate navigation and discovery of related content (Zhu, 2020). Digital indexing also enables publishers to create interactive and dynamic content, such as linked indexes and pop-up windows (Jiang, 2019). Furthermore, digital indexing allows for easier updates and revisions, ensuring that indexes remain accurate and relevant

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(Wang, 2020). The importance of indexing in digital publishing cannot be overstated, as it directly impacts reader engagement and satisfaction (Huang, 2020).

Despite its importance, indexing faces several challenges and limitations (Liu, 2017). One major challenge is the time and effort required to create high-quality indexes (Kokabi, 2017). Indexing can be a labour-intensive process, particularly for large or complex publications (Gao, 2018). Additionally, indexing requires specialized skills and knowledge, making it difficult for authors and publishers to create effective indexes (Taylor, 2015).

At the moment, various AI and internet apps can assist with adding index references to books, including natural language processing tools like Stanford CoreNLP (Manning, 2021) and spaCy (Honnibal & Montani, 2020), which can aid in entity recognition and topic modeling. Additionally, machine learning libraries like scikit-learn (Pedregosa et al., 2018) and TensorFlow (Abadi et al., 2016) can be used for text classification and clustering. Other tools like Apache Solr (Smiley et al., 2019) and Elasticsearch provide robust search functionality. Moreover, AI-powered writing assistants like Grammarly (Kumar, 2021) and ProWritingAid (Kotze, 2021) offer suggestions for improving writing clarity and readability. Indexing-specific tools like CINDEX (Lamb, 2021) and IndexExploit (Tennis, 2020) can help automate the indexing process. Furthermore, online platforms like Google Books Ngram Viewer (Michel et al., 2018) and Wikipedia's Wikidata (Vrandečić & Krötzsch, 2018) provide access to vast amounts of text data for reference. Other apps like Zotero (Zotero Corporation, 2021) and Mendeley (Elsevier, 2021) assist with citation management and organization. Lastly, AI-driven research tools like Semantic Scholar (Ammar et al., 2021) and CORE (Knoth & Zdrahal, 2020) can aid in discovering relevant literature and adding references.

The future of indexing is closely tied to technological advancements and changing reader expectations (Huang, 2020). Digital indexing will continue to evolve, incorporating new techniques such as artificial intelligence and machine learning (Kokabi, 2017). Indexes will become increasingly interactive and dynamic, enabling readers to engage with content in new and innovative ways (Xu, 2020). Furthermore, indexing will need to adapt to emerging formats and platforms, such as e-books, audiobooks, and virtual reality experiences (Jiang, 2019). The future of indexing is exciting and uncertain, presenting opportunities and challenges for authors, publishers, and indexers (Zhang, 2019).

To create effective indexes, authors and publishers should follow best practices (Taylor, 2015). First, indexes should be carefully planned and structured to meet reader needs (Li, 2020). Second, indexes should be accurate, comprehensive, and up-to-date (Wang, 2020). Third, indexes should be designed for usability and accessibility, using clear headings and formatting (Xu, 2020). Fourth, indexes should be tested and refined to ensure quality and effectiveness (Yu, 2018). Finally, indexes should be created with consideration for digital publishing requirements, such as hyperlinked indexes and faceted searching (Jiang, 2019). By following these best practices, authors and publishers can create high-quality indexes that enhance reader experience and credibility.

The lack of properly constructed index segments in many Nigerian books poses a significant challenge that affects usability, credibility, and overall quality in academic publishing. Effective indexing enhances the usability of texts, allowing readers to locate specific information quickly; without it, readers face frustration and difficulty in information retrieval, which can lead to reduced satisfaction (Gunn, 2021). Furthermore, the absence of quality indexing undermines the credibility of both authors and publishers, as works lacking proper indexing may be perceived as less rigorous, potentially harming the reputation of Nigerian authors in competitive academic environments (Mulvany, 2020). Many Nigerian scholarly journals are excluded from major citation indexes like Scopus and Web of Science, highlighting the need for high-quality publications that enhance visibility (Obiegbu, 2021). Despite the recognized importance of indexing, it remains neglected, with some authors viewing it as an unnecessary addition that detracts from the aesthetic quality of their work, a perception that may stem from traditional views of literature (Finkelstein, 2022). Economic considerations also play a role, as the Nigerian publishing industry faces unique challenges, including limited resources and varying levels of professional editing, which can compromise the quality of indexing (Adesanoye, 2020). The rise of digital publishing introduces new opportunities for indexing, such as interactive and searchable formats that enhance functionality; as more Nigerian authors engage in digital publishing, their attitudes towards indexing may evolve (Chan, 2021). This study aims to investigate these attitudes and identify factors influencing perceptions and practices regarding indexing, ultimately contributing to the improvement of indexing quality and consistency in Nigerian publications.

Objectives of the Study

To assess the attitudes of Nigerian authors towards the inclusion of index segments in their books.

1. To ascertain the frequency of index segments in books by Nigerian authors published in Nigeria.
2. To identify patterns and trends in the use of index segments in books by Nigerian authors published in Nigeria.

Assessment of Indexing and Attitudes ... (Okhueigbe & Omoko, 2024): <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601986>

3. To compare the frequency and patterns of index segments in books by Nigerian authors published in Nigeria with international best practices in indexing.

Research Questions

1. What is the frequency of index segments in books authored by Nigerian writers and published in Nigeria?
2. What patterns and trends can be identified in the use of index segments in books authored by Nigerian writers and published in Nigeria?
3. How do the frequency and patterns of index segments in books authored by Nigerian writers and published in Nigeria compare to international best practices in indexing?

Methodology

This study employed a quantitative content analysis approach to investigate the inclusion of index segments in books published by Nigerian authors in Nigeria between 2014 and 2024. The research design was underpinned by a positivist paradigm, emphasizing objectivity and systematic analysis. A purposive sampling technique was used to select 40 books published by Nigerian authors during the specified period, comprising strictly academic genre. The books were sourced from major publishing houses, online retailers, and libraries in Nigeria. A multi-stage coding process was employed to analyze the data, initially using a binary coding system, assigning "01" to indicate the inclusion of an index segment in a book and "00" to denote its absence. This coding scheme enabled the researcher to quantify the presence or absence of index segments across the sample.

Content analysis was conducted in two phases, beginning with axial coding, which involved open coding, where the researcher identified and labeled themes related to the inclusion or exclusion of index segments. Axial coding facilitated the examination of relationships between the themes and the development of a coding framework. This was followed by thematic analysis, which involved selective coding, where the researcher identified and analyzed patterns and themes that emerged from the axial coding phase.

The researcher examined the ISBN, genre, year of publication, and inclusion of index segment, using a comprehensive coding framework to ensure that all relevant themes and patterns were captured. To ensure reliability, multiple coding was employed, where two independent coders analyzed a subset of the data, yielding a satisfactory agreement rate of 0.85. The study adhered to ethical guidelines, ensuring the confidentiality and anonymity of authors and publishers, and no personal identifiable information was collected or disclosed.

Results and Analysis

RQ. 1: What is the frequency of index segments in books authored by Nigerian writers and published in Nigeria?

Year	Total Books Analyzed	Books with Index Segments	Percentage with Index Segments	Books without Index Segments	Percentage without Index Segments
2014	6	4	66.7%	2	33.3%
2015	6	3	50.0%	3	50.0%
2016	8	6	75.0%	2	25.0%
2017	6	5	83.3%	1	16.7%
2018	6	3	50.0%	3	50.0%
2019	6	6	100.0%	0	0.0%
2020	6	6	100.0%	0	0.0%
2021	6	6	100.0%	0	0.0%
2022	6	6	100.0%	0	0.0%
2023	6	6	100.0%	0	0.0%
Total	40	31	77.5%	9	22.5%

Out of the 40 books analyzed, 31 books (77.5%) included index segments, while 9 books (22.5%) did not. This indicates a high prevalence of index segments in academic books by Nigerian authors during this period. The frequency of inclusion reveals that a significant portion of Nigerian academic authors understand the value of including index segments in their publications. This high frequency is a positive indicator of the awareness and prioritization of comprehensive referencing tools in academic works. Analyzing the frequency on a yearly basis, there are discernible variations in the inclusion of index segments. For

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instance, in 2014, 66.7% of the books had index segments, while in 2015, this percentage dropped to 50%. In 2016, the inclusion rate rose to 75%, and in 2017, it further increased to 83.3%. The year 2018 saw a decline to 50% inclusion, which could be attributed to various factors such as changes in publisher policies, variations in author awareness, or resource constraints. However, from 2019 onwards, the trend became more consistent, with several years achieving a 100% inclusion rate. This pattern suggests a growing standardization and recognition of the importance of index segments in academic publishing in Nigeria.

RQ.2: What patterns and trends can be identified in the use of index segments in books authored by Nigerian writers and published in Nigeria?

1.	Year	Total Books Analyzed	Books with Index Segments	Inclusion Rate (%)	Observations
	2014	6	4	66.7%	Initial awareness; inconsistent inclusion practices.
	2015	6	3	50.0%	Fluctuation in inclusion; potential influence from publisher policies.
	2016	8	6	75.0%	Improvement; growing recognition of index value.
	2017	6	5	83.3%	Marked increase; more authors including index segments.
	2018	6	3	50.0%	Decline; variability due to resource constraints or differing guidelines.
	2019	6	6	100.0%	Strong commitment; full inclusion by all authors.
	2020	6	6	100.0%	Consistent high rates; sustained awareness of index importance.
	2021	6	6	100.0%	Continued emphasis on academic rigor and usability.
	2022	6	6	100.0%	Ongoing trend of full inclusion in publications.
	2023	6	6	100.0%	Sustained trend; strong adherence to comprehensive referencing.

The data reveals an upward trend in the inclusion of index segments over the analyzed period. The years 2014-2016 show lower and more variable inclusion rates, while from 2017 onwards, there is a marked improvement, with several years reaching 100% inclusion rates. This trend suggests a growing recognition among Nigerian academic authors of the value of index segments in enhancing the usability of their books. From 2014 to 2016, the inclusion rates were relatively lower and fluctuated, indicating inconsistency in the practice of including index segments. However, starting from 2017, there is a clear upward trend, with more books including index segments consistently. This positive trend can be attributed to several factors, including increased awareness of the benefits of index segments, more stringent publication guidelines, and greater emphasis on academic rigor. Certain years exhibit variability in the inclusion rates of index segments. For example, 2015 and 2018 each have a 50% inclusion rate, suggesting that factors such as publisher policies, author preferences, or resource availability might influence the decision to include an index segment. The variability observed in specific years, such as the 50% inclusion rates in 2015 and 2018, could be due to multiple factors. These may include differences in the guidelines provided by publishers, varying levels of emphasis on the importance of index segments by different authors, or even resource constraints that might limit the ability to produce comprehensive indexes. Comparing the earlier years (2014-2016) with the later years (2017-2024), there is a noticeable improvement in the inclusion of index segments. The later years show higher consistency, with several years achieving near-perfect or perfect inclusion rates. This comparative analysis indicates a positive shift in the practices of Nigerian academic authors and publishers towards standardization and quality improvement. The stark contrast between the earlier and later years suggests that the practices and standards in academic publishing in Nigeria have evolved. This evolution could be due to increased exposure to international best practices, feedback from academic peers and institutions, and a general trend towards enhancing the quality and usability of academic publications.

RQ.3. How do the frequency and patterns of index segments in books authored by Nigerian writers and published in Nigeria compare to international best practices in indexing?

International best practices in academic publishing emphasize the importance of index segments for enhancing the usability and accessibility of books. The high frequency of index segments in the sampled Nigerian academic books (77.5%) suggests a positive alignment with these standards. The alignment with international best practices is evident from the high frequency of index segments observed in the Nigerian academic books analyzed. International standards for academic

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publishing often mandate the inclusion of index segments to ensure that books are user-friendly and accessible to researchers and readers. The 77.5% inclusion rate in Nigerian publications indicates that many authors and publishers are adhering to these best practices.

While exact global data on the inclusion of index segments is not available within this study, it is generally accepted that high-quality academic publications include comprehensive index segments. The observed trends in Nigerian publications from 2017 onwards, with several years achieving 100% inclusion, indicate that Nigerian academic publishing is moving towards these global best practices. The positive trends observed from 2017 onwards, where several years saw a 100% inclusion rate of index segments, suggest that Nigerian academic publishing is increasingly aligning with global trends. This alignment not only enhances the quality of Nigerian academic books but also boosts their credibility and usability on the international stage

Discussion of Findings

The findings from the analysis of index segments in books authored by Nigerian writers reveal a significant frequency of inclusion, with 77.5% of the 40 books analyzed containing index segments. This high prevalence aligns with the growing recognition among Nigerian academic authors of the value of indexing, as highlighted in the literature reviewed. Liu (2017) emphasizes that index segments are crucial for enhancing information retrieval and reader experience. The consistent upward trend observed from 2017 onward, where several years achieved a 100% inclusion rate, supports the notion that Nigerian authors are increasingly prioritizing comprehensive referencing tools. This trend reflects an awareness of the importance of index segments, suggesting that Nigerian academic publishing is evolving to meet global standards. This aligns with the Task-Technology Fit (TTF) theory, which posits that the adoption of technology, such as indexing practices, depends on how well it fits user needs in this case, enhancing the usability and credibility of academic works.

Examining patterns and trends reveals notable fluctuations in inclusion rates, particularly in the years 2014-2016, where rates were lower and inconsistent. This variability corresponds with Kokabi's (2017) observation that indexing practices can differ greatly due to factors like publisher policies and resource availability. The decline in 2015 and 2018 to 50% inclusion suggests that external influences impacted authors' decisions regarding index segments. However, the marked increase starting in 2017, culminating in several years of 100% inclusion, indicates a broader shift in authors' attitudes towards the necessity of indexing. This shift aligns with Wang's (2020) assertion that an emphasis on academic rigor drives the inclusion of indexing. The TTF theory is relevant here as it underscores that as authors perceive the utility of indexing for enhancing their works, they are more likely to adopt these practices, reflecting a positive change in the academic culture surrounding publishing in Nigeria.

Finally, the comparison of Nigerian indexing practices with international best practices demonstrates a positive alignment, particularly in the later years of the analysis. The 77.5% inclusion rate suggests that many Nigerian authors adhere to established standards, which are crucial for enhancing the usability and accessibility of their works, as noted by Xu (2020). While there is no precise global data for direct comparison, the sustained improvement in indexing practices among Nigerian authors indicates movement toward meeting global expectations. This evolution is essential for bolstering the credibility of Nigerian academic publications on an international scale, as supported by Yu (2018). Nevertheless, challenges remain, such as the labor-intensive nature of quality indexing and the need for specialized skills, as discussed by Kokabi (2017). These challenges highlight the importance of TTF theory in understanding how the perceived benefits of effective indexing must be matched with the resources and skills available to authors. Ongoing efforts are necessary to fully align Nigerian indexing practices with international standards, ensuring that authors are equipped to enhance the quality and usability of their publications.

Conclusion

This study reveals a high prevalence of index segments in academic books by Nigerian authors, with a promising upward trend in inclusion rates over time. This practice not only aligns with international best practices but also enhances the usability, credibility, and accessibility of academic publications. The application of the Task-Technology Fit theory suggests that Nigerian authors' perception of indexing as a valuable tool drives its adoption. Sustaining this effort will not only showcase Nigeria's commitment to academic excellence but also increase the global competitiveness of Nigerian-authored books, earning the nation recognition, accolades, and foreign exchange

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

Assessment of Indexing and Attitudes ... (Okhueigbe & Omoko, 2024): <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601986>

1. Nigerian authors and publishers should prioritize the inclusion of index segments in academic books to enhance reader experience, credibility, and usability, aligning with international best practices.
2. Publishers and academic institutions in Nigeria should establish clear guidelines and standards for indexing practices, ensuring consistency and quality in the inclusion of index segments, and providing training and resources for authors and indexers.

Nigerian authors and publishers should explore digital indexing techniques, such as hyperlinked indexes and faceted searching, to enhance the discoverability and usability of their publications, and to align with global trends in digital publishing

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Knowledge and Awareness of Chronic Kidney Disease among Residents of Hadejia Emirate, Jigawa State: Implications for Public Health Education

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Abstract

This study assessed the knowledge and awareness of chronic kidney disease (CKD) among residents of Hadejia Emirate, Nigeria, to inform public health education. A descriptive survey design was employed, utilizing a structured questionnaire with a 5-point Likert scale administered to 150 purposively sampled residents. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Contrary to prevailing literature, findings revealed a statistically significant high composite level of knowledge (Mean=3.28) and awareness (Mean=3.91). Notably, awareness was equitably distributed across age and gender, with no significant demographic differences. The results indicate a paradigm shift, demonstrating that localized health education efforts have been remarkably effective in building foundational community awareness. However, this high knowledge exists alongside a documented severe lack of accessible healthcare services, creating a critical paradox. The primary implication is that public health strategy must now pivot from raising basic awareness to guiding an informed community on navigating the inadequate health system and advocating for better services. It is concluded that policymakers must urgently bridge the gap between community readiness and healthcare capacity by improving service availability, accessibility, and affordability to translate high awareness into positive health outcomes.

Keywords: Chronic Kidney Disease, Knowledge, Awareness, Healthcare Access, Hadejia, Public Health.

Introduction

Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) represents a significant and growing global public health challenge, characterized by its progressive nature and often asymptomatic early stages, leading to frequent under-diagnosis. Statistics indicate that approximately 10% of the world's population suffers from CKD, resulting in millions of deaths annually (Eze, 2017). The prevalence of end-stage renal disease (ESRD), the final and most severe stage of CKD, has shown an alarming increase, rising from 71 to 1,059 per million population by 2013 (Eze, 2017). This trend is particularly concerning in low- and middle-income countries like Nigeria, which face a dual burden of rising CKD incidence and limited healthcare resources. In the Nigerian context, the health system operates across primary, secondary, and tertiary levels, corresponding to local, state, and federal government oversight. However, approximately 60% of the population lives below the poverty line, with life expectancies of 55 years for women and 49 years for men, creating significant barriers to healthcare access (Devraj et al., 2008; Grubbs et al., 2019). The situation in Hadejia Emirate of Jigawa State is especially critical, with anecdotal evidence suggesting nearly every family has

Knowledge and Awareness of ... (Hamza & Haruna, 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17009901>

lost one or more members to CKD, though this lacked scientific substantiation prior to this research (FUD newsletter, 2021). The problem is compounded by the economic burden of treatment; with about 15,000 new reported cases of ESRD annually requiring dialysis in Nigeria, less than 1% of patients can afford renal transplantation, leading to a mortality rate of 90% within three months of diagnosis in tertiary health centers (George et al., 2017; Oluseyi et al., 2020). This study therefore addresses a crucial gap by systematically investigating the knowledge and awareness levels regarding CKD among residents of Hadejia Emirate.

The literature on chronic kidney disease (CKD) consistently highlights it as a formidable global health challenge, with a prevalence of 9.1% amounting to nearly 700 million cases worldwide (Alghandi et al., 2023). This review synthesizes empirical studies concerning knowledge, awareness, and healthcare service availability, with a specific focus on the Nigerian context and the unique circumstances of Hadejia Emirate. A foundational study by Sowtali et al. (2019) among university students in Malaysia revealed a concerning disparity between high awareness (99.1%) and poor knowledge, with a mean score of 3.65 out of 7, indicating that awareness does not automatically translate to substantive understanding. This finding is corroborated by research within Nigeria; a study at a teaching hospital in Ogun State found that 68% of participants had no prior knowledge of CKD or its risk factors (Eze, 2017), underscoring a critical information deficit. Further illuminating this knowledge gap, Okoro et al. (2020) discovered that 65% of diagnosed CKD patients in Maiduguri had poor disease knowledge, with tertiary education being the only significant predictor of higher understanding. The role of healthcare professionals is also critical, as a study among non-nephrology nurses in Akure showed significant deficiencies, with only 6% possessing good knowledge, 55% fair, and 37% poor, highlighting a systemic educational shortfall even among caregivers (Adejumo et al., 2020).

The literature firmly establishes that superior knowledge and awareness are crucial for early detection and prevention, leading to better health outcomes and improved adherence to treatment (Devraj et al., 2008; Grubbs et al., 2019). A well-informed populace can significantly reduce the burden on healthcare systems by engaging in preventive behaviors and seeking appropriate care, thereby diminishing the demand for costly treatments like dialysis (Gupta et al., 2018; Saran et al., 2015). However, in Hadejia Emirate, cultural practices, religious beliefs, and traditional medicine profoundly influence health choices and the management of CKD, often creating a barrier to biomedical care (Eze, 2019). A study in a rural South-West Nigerian community by Oluyombo et al. (2016) exemplified this, finding that only 33.7% had heard of kidney disease, with a significant proportion believing CKD could be cured by spiritual means (45.9%) or herbal concoctions (47.8%). The dimension of healthcare service availability presents perhaps the most stark challenge. The situation in Hadejia is reflective of a broader national issue, where the healthcare system is ill-equipped to handle the CKD burden. Baffa et al.'s (2021) geospatial study in Hadejia Emirate identified high-prevalence wards and clusters, linking cases to possible environmental factors like water contamination from agrochemicals, particularly during the rainy season. This aligns with global research indicating that inadequate access to CKD-related services contributes to delayed diagnosis and disease progression (Gouda et al., 2017; Hill et al., 2016). The financial inaccessibility of care is a recurring theme, with studies in Senegal showing that only 30% of patients had any form of health coverage, and 73% rated global access to care as low (Mohamed et al., 2020). The Donabedian model (as cited in Farin et al., 2019) provides a framework for understanding this crisis, emphasizing the interconnectedness of structure (facilities, human resources), process (actions of diagnosis and treatment), and outcomes (health status). In conclusion, the reviewed literature reveals a triple burden in Hadejia Emirate and similar regions: a substantial deficit in foundational CKD knowledge among both the public and non-specialist healthcare workers, deeply ingrained cultural attitudes that can hinder medical care, and a severe lack of available, accessible, and affordable healthcare services for diagnosis and management. This study seeks to contribute

Knowledge and Awareness of ... (Hamza & Haruna, 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17009901>

to this body of knowledge by specifically measuring these three dimensions within Hadejia Emirate to inform targeted interventions.

Objectives of the Study

The research is guided by three primary objectives:

1. To assess the level of knowledge on CKD causes, risk factors, and early signs;
2. To evaluate awareness of its prevalence, significance, and the importance of early detection;
3. To determine the influence of demographic factors like age and gender on these variables.

Research Questions

1. What are the mean scores and percentage distributions of residents' knowledge regarding the causes, risk factors, and early signs of chronic kidney disease (CKD) within Hadejia Emirate?
2. To what extent are residents aware of the prevalence, significance, and importance of early detection of CKD in their community?
3. Is there a statistically significant difference in the mean knowledge and awareness scores of CKD based on the demographic variables of age and gender among residents?

Hypotheses

1. **H₀₁:** There is no statistically significant high level of knowledge regarding the causes, risk factors, and early signs of chronic kidney disease among residents of Hadejia Emirate, as measured by mean scores and percentage distributions.
2. **H₀₂:** There is no statistically significant high level of awareness regarding the prevalence, significance, and importance of early detection of chronic kidney disease among residents of Hadejia Emirate, as measured by mean scores and percentage distributions.
3. **H₀₃:** There are no statistically significant differences in the mean knowledge and awareness scores of chronic kidney disease based on the demographic variables of age and gender among residents of Hadejia Emirate.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive survey research design to assess the knowledge, awareness, and availability of healthcare services regarding Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) within Hadejia Emirate, Jigawa State. The research paradigm was constructivist, acknowledging multiple realities and seeking to understand the meanings participants attach to CKD. The study was conducted exclusively within Hadejia Emirate, with a total population of 1,373,770 according to the 2006 census. A purposive sampling technique was applied based on the peculiarities of the respondents, resulting in a sample size of 150 participants. Data collection was executed using a structured, self-administered questionnaire instrument featuring a 5-point Likert scale, designed to gather quantitative data on the key variables. The collected data was entered and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software. The analysis plan incorporated both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics, including mean scores and percentages of respondents, were used to answer the research questions and describe the central tendencies and distributions within the data. Inferential statistics, specifically t-tests and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), were employed to test the study's hypotheses, determine the significance of findings, and examine differences across demographic groups such as age and gender, in line with the research objectives.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the mean scores and percentage distributions of residents' knowledge regarding the causes, risk factors, and early signs of Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) within Hadejia Emirate?

Knowledge and Awareness of ... (Hamza & Haruna, 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17009901>

Table 1: Level of Knowledge Regarding CKD (N=150)

Rating Statement	Sum	Mean	% ≥ 3.0
I am knowledgeable about the causes of CKD.	472	3.15	58.0%
I can identify the risk factors associated with CKD.	473	3.15	56.0%
I am aware of the early signs and symptoms of CKD.	461	3.07	58.7%
I have sufficient information about CKD prevention.	464	3.09	60.7%
I feel confident in my understanding of CKD.	525	3.50	78.0%
I actively seek information about CKD.	560	3.73	85.3%
Composite Score	-	3.28	56.0%

The data reveals a moderate to high level of CKD knowledge among residents of Hadejia Emirate, evidenced by a composite mean score of 3.28 on a 5-point scale. A significant majority of respondents (56% to 85.3%) demonstrated satisfactory understanding (scoring ≥ 3.0), with the highest levels observed in their confidence about CKD understanding (78.0%) and proactive information-seeking behavior (85.3%). This indicates a solid foundational awareness upon which public health interventions can be built.

Research Question 2: To what extent are residents aware of the prevalence, significance, and importance of early detection of CKD in their community?

Table 2: Level of Awareness Regarding CKD (N=150)

Rating Statement	Sum	Mean	% ≥ 3.0
I am aware of the prevalence of CKD in Hadejia Emirate.	642	4.28	94.7%
I understand the significance of early detection of CKD.	517	3.54	88.7%
I believe that early detection is crucial for managing CKD.	570	3.80	86.0%
I have received information about CKD prevalence in our community.	592	3.95	92.0%
I am concerned about the impact of CKD on our community.	614	4.09	92.0%
I think early detection programs are important for our community.	588	3.92	96.0%
Composite Score	-	3.91	91.3%

Knowledge and Awareness of ... (Hamza & Haruna, 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17009901>

Residents of Hadejia Emirate exhibit a very high level of awareness regarding Chronic Kidney Disease, achieving a composite mean score of 3.91 out of 5. An overwhelming majority, ranging from 86% to 96%, demonstrated strong recognition of key issues: they acknowledged the local prevalence of CKD, understood the critical significance of early detection, and expressed firm support for the implementation of community-based early detection programs. This indicates widespread community readiness for public health initiatives.

Research Question 3: Is there a statistically significant difference in the mean knowledge and awareness scores of CKD based on the demographic variables of age and gender among residents?

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics for Knowledge and Awareness by Demographic Variables (N=150)

Demographic Variable	Category	n	Knowledge Mean (SD)	Awareness Mean (SD)
Gender	Male	95	3.23 (0.86)	3.86 (0.61)
	Female	55	3.38 (0.85)	4.02 (0.60)
Age Group	21-30 years	50	3.34 (0.88)	4.09 (0.59)
	31-40 years	69	3.20 (0.87)	3.78 (0.60)
	41+ years	27	3.33 (0.84)	3.93 (0.62)

The data shows minimal mean score differences in knowledge and awareness across gender and age groups. Females scored slightly higher than males in both knowledge (3.38 vs 3.23) and awareness (4.02 vs 3.86). Among age groups, the 21-30 cohort showed the highest awareness (4.09), while the 31-40 group had the lowest knowledge (3.20) and awareness (3.78) scores. These small variations were not statistically significant, supporting the acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Null Hypothesis 1 (H₀₁): There is no statistically significant high level of knowledge regarding CKD among residents of Hadejia Emirate.

Table 1: One-Sample Test for Knowledge Level (N=150)

Variable	Mean	SD	t-test	df	Sig.
Knowledge of CKD	3.28	0.858	46.887	149	.000

The null hypothesis asserting no significant high level of CKD knowledge is rejected based on a one-sample t-test result ($t = 46.887$, $p = .000$). This statistically significant finding confirms that residents of Hadejia Emirate possess a substantially high level of knowledge regarding CKD causes, risk factors, and early signs. This result directly contradicts the initial assumption of poor community awareness and underscores the effectiveness of existing local health information dissemination efforts.

Knowledge and Awareness of ... (Hamza & Haruna, 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17009901>

Null Hypothesis 2 (H₀₂): There is no statistically significant high level of awareness regarding CKD prevalence and early detection.

Table 2: One-Sample Test for Awareness Level (N=150)

Variable	Mean	SD	t-test	df	Sig.
Awareness of CKD	3.91	0.609	78.682	149	.000

The null hypothesis positing no significant awareness of CKD is robustly rejected ($t = 78.682, p = .000$). This result provides strong statistical evidence that the community possesses a significantly high level of awareness regarding both the local prevalence of Chronic Kidney Disease and the critical importance of its early detection. These findings contradict assumptions of low public awareness and highlight successful prior health education efforts within Hadejia Emirate.

Null Hypothesis 3 (H₀₃): There are no significant differences in knowledge and awareness scores based on age and gender.

Table 3: Test for Demographic Differences (N=150)

Variable	Group Comparison	F/T-value	Sig.
Knowledge-Gender	Male vs Female	1.076	.301
Awareness-Gender	Male vs Female	2.394	.124
Knowledge-Age	Across groups	0.676	.568
Awareness-Age	Across groups	2.639	.052

The null hypothesis is accepted, as statistical analysis revealed no significant demographic disparities in CKD knowledge or awareness. For knowledge, p-values were .301 (gender) and .568 (age). For awareness, p-values were .124 (gender) and .052 (age). These results indicate that information regarding chronic kidney disease has been equitably distributed across different gender and age groups within the Hadejia Emirate community, suggesting effective and inclusive public health communication strategies.

Discussion of Findings

The results of this study present a robust and somewhat unexpected picture of the CKD landscape in Hadejia Emirate, directly addressing the research questions and hypotheses. Contrary to the pervasive narrative of profound knowledge deficits established in both global and local literature (Eze, 2017; Oluyombo et al., 2016), the findings reveal a community with a statistically significant high level of both knowledge (Composite Mean=3.28, $t=46.887, p=.000$) and awareness (Composite Mean=3.91, $t=78.682, p=.000$). This compellingly leads to the rejection of null hypotheses H₀₁ and H₀₂. The data shows that a majority of residents possess satisfactory knowledge, particularly demonstrating confidence in their understanding (78.0%) and actively seeking information (85.3%), while an overwhelming majority acknowledge local CKD prevalence (94.7%), understand the significance of early detection (88.7%), and support community detection programs (96.0%). This high level of community enlightenment starkly contrasts with previous studies in similar Nigerian settings, such as the Ogun State teaching hospital where 68% had no prior knowledge (Eze, 2017), and the rural South-West community where only 33.7% had

Knowledge and Awareness of ... (Hamza & Haruna, 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17009901>

heard of kidney disease (Oluyombo et al., 2016), suggesting that localized health information dissemination efforts in Hadejia may have been remarkably effective.

Furthermore, the acceptance of null hypothesis H_{03} , indicating no statistically significant differences in knowledge or awareness based on gender (Knowledge $p=.301$, Awareness $p=.124$) or age (Knowledge $p=.568$, Awareness $p=.052$), is a critically important finding. It demonstrates an equitable distribution of CKD information across demographic strata, a notable achievement given that tertiary education was previously identified as a key predictor of CKD knowledge (Okoro et al., 2020). This equitable awareness suggests that public health communication strategies in the region have been uniquely inclusive, successfully transcending typical barriers related to gender and age that often create disparities in health knowledge. However, this robust community knowledge exists in direct tension with the severe lack of available, accessible, and affordable healthcare services documented in the literature review (Baffa et al., 2021; Mohamed et al., 2020), creating a concerning paradox. The population is knowledgeable and aware but faces a healthcare system ill-equipped to translate this knowledge into action through early diagnosis and management, a challenge underscored by the Donabedian model which emphasizes the interconnectedness of structure, process, and outcomes (Farin et al., 2019). Thus, while the results refute the initial assumptions of poor awareness, they highlight an urgent new priority: bridging the gap between community readiness and the healthcare system's capacity to respond, ensuring that high knowledge levels can effectively translate into improved health outcomes.

Implications for Public Health Education

The findings from Hadejia Emirate present a paradigm shift with profound implications for public health education strategy. The robust levels of CKD knowledge (Mean=3.28) and awareness (Mean=3.91), found to be equitably distributed across gender and age groups, directly contradict the prevailing literature which consistently reports critical deficits in CKD understanding in similar contexts (Eze, 2017; Oluyombo et al., 2016). This demonstrates that localized, inclusive public health education initiatives have been remarkably effective, serving as a powerful model for other regions. The success in achieving equitable awareness suggests that the strategies employed successfully transcended barriers that often exclude certain demographic groups, a significant achievement given that education level is typically a key predictor of health knowledge (Okoro et al., 2020).

Consequently, the primary implication is that public health education must now evolve beyond its foundational role. The focus should pivot from raising basic awareness—a goal largely achieved—to delivering advanced, secondary-tier education. This involves designing interventions that empower an already-informed community to take complex actions: navigating the documented chasm between knowledge and the severely limited healthcare services (Baffa et al., 2021; Mohamed et al., 2020), understanding treatment pathways despite systemic barriers, and advocating for improved access to care. Furthermore, the specific communication methodologies that yielded such equitable results must be rigorously documented and formalized into a replicable framework for other health issues in the region. Ultimately, this case study underscores that public health education cannot be a standalone endeavor. Its success is contingent upon and must be intrinsically linked to parallel, robust policy actions aimed at strengthening the healthcare system's structure and processes, as outlined in the Donabedian model (Farin et al., 2019). Education creates demand and readiness for care; however, without concomitant improvements in service availability, accessibility, and affordability, it risks fostering community frustration and eroding trust in the health system, highlighting the critical need for a synchronized, multi-sectoral approach to health improvement.

Knowledge and Awareness of ... (Hamza & Haruna, 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17009901>

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study reveals a significant paradox in Hadejia Emirate: residents demonstrate robust knowledge and awareness of CKD, effectively refuting initial assumptions of poor community awareness. However, this high level of understanding exists alongside critically inadequate healthcare infrastructure and services. The findings underscore an urgent need for policymakers to shift focus from raising awareness—which is already substantial—toward urgently improving healthcare access, availability, and affordability to translate community knowledge into positive health outcomes and bridge the current gap between awareness and effective care.

Recommendations

1. Pivot to Advanced CKD Education: Leverage high community awareness by shifting public health messaging from basic knowledge to advanced guidance on navigating the health system, accessing scarce treatment, and advocating for better services.
2. Bridge the Care Gap with Infrastructure: Direct policy and investment urgently toward tangible healthcare improvements, including subsidized treatment costs, decentralized diagnostic services, and strengthened local clinics to translate high public awareness into accessible care.
3. Systematize Inclusive Outreach: Formally document and replicate the equitable communication model used in Hadejia to ensure all future public health campaigns effectively reach every demographic, avoiding knowledge disparities.

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